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WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

AEEG	Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water
BE	Belgium
BEERECL	The Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Credit Line
BU	Bulgaria
CARES	Community Renewable Energy Scheme (UK)
CCA	Climate Change Agreements
CCL	Climate Change Levy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CEEF	Central Energy Efficiency Fund (Scotland, UK)
CERT	Carbon Emission Reduction Target (UK)
CESP	Community Energy Saving Programme (UK)
CNR	National Research Council (Italy)
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CRES	The Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (Greece)
DE	Germany
DEC	Display Energy Certificates
DNO	District network operators
ECA	Enhanced Capital Allowances
ECO	Energy Company Obligation (UK)
EDR	Electricity Demand Reduction
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EESF	Fund for Energy and Energy Savings (Bulgaria)
ELMO	for electro-mobility program (Estonia)
EMS	Energy Management systems
ENEA	Stati Generali Efficienza Energetica (Italy)
EnEV	Energy saving ordinance (Germany)
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ES	Estonia
ESCO	Energy service company
ESME	Energy system modelling environment
ESOS	Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (UK)
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
GGC	Greening Government Commitments
GHG	Green House Gas
GR	Greece

HEIF	Renewable Energy Investment Fund (UK)
HGV	Heavy goods vehicles
HNDU	Heat Networks Delivery Unit (UK)
ICE	Incentive on Connections Engagement
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPEEC	International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation
IT	Italy
kfW	Energy consultation for SMEs (Germany)
KIK	The Environmental Investment Centre (Estonia)
Ktoe	thousand tonnes of oil equivalent
LCIS	Low Carbon Industrial Strategy (UK)
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
LESA	Landlords Energy Saving Allowance
MEEC	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (Estonia)
MIP	Milieu- en Energietechnologie-Innovatieplatform (Belgium)
MoE	Ministry of Environment (Estonia)
Mtoe	million tonnes of oil equivalent
NI	Northern Ireland
RCEF	Rural Community Energy Fund (UK)
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme (UK)
REECL	The Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (Bulgaria)
RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive (UK)
RTFO	Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (UK)
SE	Serbia
SEDA	Sustainable Energy Development Agency (Bulgaria)
SME	Small Medium Enterprises
TSB	Technology Strategy Board
TSO	The transmission system operator (Estonia)
UK	United Kingdom
ULEV	Ultra Low Emissions Vehicles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UREF	Urban Community Energy Fund (UK)
VEA	The Flemish Energy Agency (Belgium)
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
ZCH	Zero Carbon Hub

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This working paper presents the cross-analysis of the social, economic, cultural, institutional and educational barriers to implementation of energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors for all eight HERON partner countries. Barriers to energy efficiency are vast and complex and overcoming them is the key challenge for energy efficiency strategies. The main barriers for each country were identified in eight national reports, included in Annexes, prepared by the partner countries. A review of literature was undertaken and expert views were provided, in order to assess the relevant actors involved, and to understand the type and nature of the country-specific barriers associated with different policy measures and technologies. Through the national reports, the context of each of the eight partner countries was assessed in terms of the development and current stage of energy efficiency policies, and valuable insights were provided regarding the country-specific barriers.

The first chapter of this working paper presents an overview of the energy efficiency standards and targets in each of the partner countries, as well as a summary of the current energy consumption across the eight countries. An overview of policy instruments and measures is also provided, allowing for a direct comparison across the partner countries.

The second chapter provides a cross-analysis of the common and most relevant barriers in the building and transport sectors, across the eight partner countries. Findings from this chapter provide valuable insights regarding the key social, cultural, educational, economic and institutional barriers that policies in all countries need to take into consideration. It should be noted, that the review of national reports showed that there are discrepancies between the number of barriers identified in each of the partner countries in both the building and the transport sectors. This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and shows that partner countries are at different stages of identifying barriers and research on energy efficiency barriers is not equally developed across the partner countries.

The third chapter presents the list of policy measures that are in place in each of the partner countries in regards to the key barriers identified in the previous chapter. The Kky findings are summarised in the final chapter.

INTRODUCTION

A barrier is a postulated mechanism that inhibits investment in technologies that are both energy efficient and economically efficient. To determine the existence of barriers empirically we need to ask (Weber, 1997);

1. What is the barrier? e.g. hidden costs, risk, lack of capital, lack of information, inadequate financial incentives etc.
2. Who or what is it an obstacle to?: e.g. firms, public organisations, departments within organisations, individuals
3. What does it prevent? e.g. purchase of more efficient equipment, retrofitting insulation to a building, establishing a monitoring & targeting scheme.

Barriers to energy efficiency are vast and complex, and are usually inter-related, e.g. socio-economic, social-educational, social-institutional, and institutional-educational. Scaling up energy efficiency requires energy consumers to modify their behaviour in relation to both energy consumption and equipment investment. Several factors influence these behaviours, including: country specific incentive structures, consumer preferences, rules and regulations, decision-making practices and cultural considerations. Experts have also identified a number of factors that hamper behavioural change, such as market, financial, information, institutional and technical barriers that exist in all economies (Golove and Eto, 1996; IEA, 2007; Limaye et al., 2008) (Table 1).

Table 1 Barriers to energy efficiency (source: after IEA, 2010)

Barrier	Examples
Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market organisation and price distortions prevent customers from appraising the true value of energy efficiency. • Split incentive problems created when investors cannot capture the benefits of improved efficiency (IEA, 2007). • Transaction costs (project development costs are high relative to energy savings).
Financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up-front costs and dispersed benefits discourage investors • Perception of EE investments as complicated and risky, with high transaction costs • Lack of awareness of financial benefits on the part of financial institutions.
Information and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of sufficient information and understanding, on the part of consumers, to make rational consumption and investment decisions.
Regulatory and institutional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy tariffs that discourage EE investment (such as declining block prices). • Incentive structures encourage energy providers to sell energy rather than invest in cost-effective energy efficiency. • Institutional bias towards supply-side investments.
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of affordable energy efficiency technologies suitable to local conditions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Insufficient capacity to identify, develop, implement and maintain EE investments.
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According to the IEA Energy Efficiency Governance Report (IEA, 2010), widely acknowledged barriers include the following:

- Lack of information
- Low awareness
- Low energy prices
- Difficulty in accessing affordable financing
- Lack of EE implementation capacity
- Consumer indifference
- Higher initial cost of EE products
- Principal agent problem
- Lack of political leadership and intergovernmental co-ordination

This report presents the cross analysis of the social, economic, cultural and educational barriers to energy efficiency progress in the building and transport sectors for all partner countries. The main barriers for each country are identified to provide valuable insights; overcoming such barriers is the key challenge for EE policies. For each country (individual reports included as appendices), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the following criteria¹:

- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

¹ These criteria were proposed by partner No 1: UoA-KEPA.

CHAPTER 1: OVERVIEW

1.1 CONTEXT

The European Union, along with all EU Member States and the majority of the international community are Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC); the main international treaty for tackling climate change. In 1997 the Parties of the UNFCCC agreed the Kyoto Protocol; a worldwide legally binding instrument for cutting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Under the Kyoto Protocol's first commitment (2008-2012), 37 industrialised countries and the European Community committed to average reductions in GHG emissions of 5% against 1990 levels. Over the second commitment period, 37 Parties committed to reduce GHG emissions by a minimum of 18% below 1990 levels (EU Commission, 2015b).

In response, the European Union (EU) set and enacted targets; commonly known as the 20-20-20 targets (EU Commission, 2015a):

- A 20% reduction in EU GHG emissions from 1990 levels;
- Ensuring 20% of the EU's energy consumption is produced from renewable resources;
- A 20% improvement in the EU's energy efficiency.

In 2009, the EU enacted a climate and energy package which introduced four pieces of complementary legislation intended to deliver on the 20-20-20 targets; reform of the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), national targets for non-EU ETS emissions, national renewable energy targets, and carbon capture and storage. The climate and energy package did not directly address the energy efficiency target; instead this has been done through the Energy Efficiency Plan (2011) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (2012) (EU Commission, 2015a).

Under the 2012 Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU), individual EU countries have provided their own indicative national energy efficiency targets, in order to achieve an overall 20% reduction in the EU's energy efficiency. Projections undertaken in 2007 indicated a primary energy consumption in 2020 of 1,842Mtoe; therefore, in order to achieve the 20% reduction, the maximum primary energy consumption of the EU is to be 1,474Mtoe (EU Directive, 2012). The individual country's targets are based on primary or final energy consumption, primary or final energy savings, or energy intensity; depending on the country's preference. Table 2 outlines the absolute level of energy consumption targets for the eight countries involved in the HERON research project for ease of comparison.

Table 2. Absolute level of energy consumption in 2020 (Mtoe) targets for eight case study countries and EU Member States (EU Directive, 2012)

	Absolute level of energy consumption in 2020 [Mtoe]	
	Primary	Final
EU States	1,474.0	1,078.0
Belgium	43.7	32.5
Bulgaria	15.8	9.2
Estonia	6.5	2.8
Germany	276.6	194.3

Greece	27.1	20.5
Italy	158.0	126.0
Serbia	-	7.6
UK	177.6	157.8

¹ Serbia is a Candidate member of the EU and as such is not included in official EU EED figures. However, the First Serbian National Energy Action Plan (https://www.energy-community.org/portal/page/portal/ENC_HOME/DOCS/986181/NEEAP_Serbia_adopted_avg_2010.pdf) states that a 9% reduction on 2008 final energy consumption is to be achieved by 2018. Therefore the figure of 7.6mtoe is based on Serbia's 2018 target. The primary energy consumption target is unknown.

1.1.1 CURRENT ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Across the EU Member States, final energy consumption has increased from 1990 levels, but decreased since 2005 levels. Table 3 outlines the energy consumption in the eight case study countries in 2013; by sector. Since 1990, the majority have seen reductions in their overall final energy consumption (five out of eight) and all have seen reductions since 2005 (to 2013). Generally, the transport and building (residential and services) sectors accounted for the majority of the energy consumption in all countries and are outlined in the following sections.

Table 3. Energy consumption (mtoe) in eight case study countries and overall EU Member States in 2013; final energy consumption and by sector (Eurostat, 2015)

	Industry	Transport	Residential	Services	Agriculture & fishing	Other	Total final consumption ¹
EU States	276.6	348.5	295.9	152.5	25.0	5.2	1,103.8
Belgium	10.5	9.8	9.0	4.8	0.7	0.0	34.8
Bulgaria	2.6	2.8	2.2	1.0	0.2	0.0	8.8
Estonia	0.6	0.8	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.0	2.9
Germany	60.7	62.6	59.7	34.0	0.0	0.1	217.3
Greece	2.8	6.3	3.8	1.8	0.3	0.3	15.3
Italy	27.0	38.7	34.2	15.8	2.8	0.1	118.7
Serbia	2.5	2.0	2.9	0.8	0.2	0.0	8.3
UK	25.7	50.5	40.5	17.7	0.9	1.5	136.4

Notes:-

- Figures all in million tonnes of oil equivalent (mtoe)
- Other – includes energy use not specified elsewhere

¹Total final consumption excludes non-energy consumption (the consumption of energy products which have not been used to directly provide energy. This category includes use for chemical feedstock, solvents, lubricants and road making material.

1.1.2 BUILDING SECTOR

Overall, GHG emissions from the building sector (the residential and service sectors) across the EU have been decreasing from 1990 levels (EU Commission, 2015d). However, final energy consumption across the EU Member States continues to rise from 1990 levels; particularly in the services sector, which has seen a 40% increase from 1990 to 2013. The residential sector, although final energy consumption has risen from 1990 levels, has seen a reduction in final energy consumption from 2005 levels (3%). Across all the EU Member States, the building sector (residential and services sectors) accounted for 41% of the total final energy consumption in 2013. The average across the

eight case study countries was also 41%; and ranged from 36% in Bulgaria to 46% in Serbia (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage split of final energy consumption (2013) by sector for eight case study countries and the overall EU Member States

In terms of the change in final energy consumption in the eight case study countries from 1990 levels, all countries have increased final energy consumption in the services sector. However, four (Bulgaria, Estonia, Germany and Serbia) have seen a decrease in the final energy consumption of the residential sector (Eurostat, 2015). Whilst increases are to be expected due to population growth as well as an increase in buildings in the majority of the case study countries, such figures indicate the critical nature of improving energy efficiency across the building sector.

1.1.3 TRANSPORT SECTOR

Transport is the only major sector in the EU where GHG emissions continue to rise (EU Commission, 2015c). Road transport poses a particularly issue; despite falling by 3% in 2012, they are still 21% higher than 1990 levels, and contribute to approximately one-fifth of the EU’s total carbon (CO₂) emissions (EU Commission, 2015c). In terms of the eight case study countries, as Figure 1 shows, the transport sector ranged from 24% (Serbia) to 41% (Greece) of the final energy consumption in 2013, and, on average, accounted for 31% of the final energy consumption. Table 4 outlines the energy consumption in 2013 of the transport subsectors across the eight countries; notably the energy consumption from road transport is significant in all countries and has increased from 1990 to 2010 in the majority of the countries; only Estonia and Germany have seen decreases (Figure 2). As such, the transport sector is a key focus for energy efficiency policy; alongside the building sector.

Table 4. Energy consumption by transport subsector (ktoe) in eight case study countries in 2013 (Eurostat, 2015)

	Rail	Road	Int. aviation	Dom. aviation	Dom. navigation	Pipeline	Overall ¹
Belgium	192	8,081	1,274	3	158	53	9,760
Bulgaria	32	2,400	159	12	0	174	2,778
Estonia	28	699	29	0	4	0	762
Germany	1,370	51,607	8,331	679	290	277	62,621
Greece	27	5,013	674	177	431	0	6,339
Italy	451	32,876	3,001	683	985	256	38,703
Serbia	216	1,716	45	0	27	2	2,005
UK	1,022	37,027	10,931	715	782	0	50,476

Notes:-

- Figures all in thousand tonnes of oil equivalent (ktoe)
- Int. – international; Dom. – domestic

¹Overall consumption includes unspecified transport energy consumption

Figure 2. Road transport energy consumption from 1990 to 2010 across eight case study countries

1.2 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

1.2.1 BUILDING SECTOR

Most common among the countries are regulatory and financial policy instruments and measures. Apart from the new Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), the recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD; 2010/31/EC) has been the most important policy addressing the building sector (European Union, 2015). Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are also one of the most commonly cited regulatory policy.

Countries having introduced financial incentives with most offering loans, and often combined with a grant system (also housing allowances and funding). Grants usually cover a percentage of the total investments for the energy saving measure with a coverage of 15-40 % for different countries. There are programs that require implementation of certain technical measures in order to qualify for a grant of a certain percentage (European Union, 2015). Likewise, the Feed-in Tariff and Renewable Heat Incentive in the UK require that dwellings hold a particular EPC grade to be eligible. Therefore, in order to qualify for low/zero carbon energy improvements, a household must first improve the energy efficiency of the fabric; blending both regulatory and economic policy. Belgium, Bulgaria, Estonia, Serbia, and the UK cite green loans (incl. credit lines); in contrast to the Green Deal in the UK, the green loan (in Brussels-Capital) is a zero interest loan. All countries (except Italy) cite taxation policies to achieve energy efficiency (though policy summaries are not exhaustive).

The ‘fuel poor’ or ‘energy poor’ target group are a specific subset of households for which some countries have selected to implement economic policy regarding energy efficiency. In Germany, an energy check supports low-income households with a cost-free energy audit and direct support with instant technical measures. Slovenia also has an energy efficiency scheme for low-income households and a number of other funding schemes in which the issue of fuel poverty is explicitly addressed. In the UK, besides the former CERT-scheme, there are other funding schemes directly connected to fuel poverty, such as the warm front scheme and Energy Company Obligation (ECO) (European Union, 2015).

There are a number of different information and educational measures ranging from the publication of informational material (e.g. Energy guzzlers website in Belgium), consulting offers via telephone or in person (e.g. On-site energy consultation and energy consultation for SMEs (KfW) in Germany), and community organizing information campaigns (e.g. Open Homes Network in the UK). Figure 3 indicates the countries with wide-scale roll-out of electric smart meters by 2020.

Table 5 shows the actors involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of building sector policy instruments. Table 7 shows the National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the building sector.

Figure 3 Member States with wide-scale roll-out of electric smart meters by 2020 (source: European Union, 2015)

Table 5 Actors involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of building sector policy instruments

	National	Sub-national	Support
Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bruxelles Environnement (Brussels Capital Region Ministry of Environment) The Flemish Energy Agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENOVER / CONCERE (“Energieoverleg / Concertation État-régions pour l’énergie”) – coordinate

		<p>(VEA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government Wallon • Walloon Ministry of Sustainable Development, Housing and Energy • Public Service of Wallonia - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building • Walloon Energy Ministry 	<p>discussions between federal government and regional governments over energy-related matters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment - Environnement Alliance (professional associations, trade unions, public actors as well as economic, training, research and community actors)
Bulgaria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Energy • Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) - executive authority within the Ministry of Energy, which monitors and evaluates the implemented by the obligated parties measures and supports the development and actualization of the strategies and action plans 		
Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Department and Building and Housing Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) - overall responsibility for energy and economic policies • The Ministry of the Environment (MoE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cities of: Tallinn, Tartu, Võru, Valga, Jõgeva , Rakvere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Environmental Investment Centre (KIK) • KredEx • Competition Authority • Riigi Kinnisvara AS (RKAS), The State Real Estate Ltd • The transmission system operator (TSO) AS Elering
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Ministry for Economy Affairs and Energy • Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety 		
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC) • Ministry of Finance; • Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction; • Ministry of Culture, Education and Religious Affairs; • Ministry of Health; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative Divisions and Decentralized Divisions; • Local Authorities; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (GRES) • Public Properties Company • Buildings’ Infrastructures SA • Association of Building Manufacturers.
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of the Environment and Protection of Land and Sea, • Minister of Economy and Finance, • Ministry of Economic Development • Ministry for Regional Affairs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional authorities • Municipalities – develop and implement building regulations, local planning instruments, voluntary local Sustainable Energy Action Plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italian National Agency for New Technologies, • Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, • CNR (National Research Council) • RSE (Research on the Energy System) • Environmental and professional associations –

			awareness raising campaigns
Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of Mining and Energy - institution responsible for energy efficiency legal framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vojvodina Provincial Secretariat for Energy and Mineral Resources Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chamber of Engineers - training of engineers
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Department for the Environment and Climate Change (DECC) Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scottish Government Welsh Government Northern Ireland Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment Local Authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building Research Establishment Energy Saving Trust Zero Carbon Hub The Carbon Trust Innovate UK Salix Research Councils UK

1.2.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

The most commonly implemented policies at Member State level are those that seek to improve the efficiency of vehicles or encourage the purchase of cleaner vehicles. Other measures seek to encourage modal shift or change driver behaviour.

Though vehicle efficiency improvement measures are predominantly implemented at EU level through regulations targeted at vehicle manufacturers, there are also some novel policies at the national level. A wide range of policy instruments are used; the most common is fiscal measures, which now account for 28% of all measures, and are used in almost every Member State. In recent years (since 2008) there is a trend towards using fewer regulatory or normative measures, and more co-operative measures such as voluntary agreements (European Union, 2015).

The majority of policies (especially across regulatory, economic, and awareness policies) focus on cars: improving the efficiency of cars (e.g., energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernisation in Serbia), encouraging the take-up of energy efficient cars (e.g. CO₂ car guide and Ecotax incentive for the purchase of new, energy efficient vehicles in Belgium and CO₂-related motor vehicle tax in Germany and the UK), changing the behaviour of car drivers (e.g. eco-driving campaigns in all countries). Eco-driving measures have also been designed specifically for vans, HGVs, bus and coach drivers in the UK (SAFED): a one day complimentary driver development course combining driver training and assessment. Apart from country specific initiatives there are also European wide eco-driving initiatives such as ECO DRIVEN, an eco-driving campaign that covers nine countries and is aimed at drivers of passenger cars, delivery vans, HGVs and buses. Another example is the ECoWILL project focusing on reducing carbon emissions by 8Mt by 2015 through implementing more fuel efficient driving across Europe (European Union, 2015).

Efficiency measures are also being applied to other vehicle types such as with heavy goods vehicles (HGVs) in the UK, "Retibo", research project to stimulate a more efficient and sustainable public transport system in Belgium, a research and development (R&D) programme planned for transport energy efficiency development in Estonia, and industrial companies in improving the energy efficiency of Motor Driven Systems.

There are also an exceptional number of policies dealing with modal shift, e.g., encouraging passengers to walk or cycle instead of using a car, by improving and developing new transport infrastructures and / or by promoting cycling or walking. To encourage and incentivise passengers to cycle or walk instead of using a car, a number of countries have implemented or proposed planning measures that either develop or improve cycling and walking infrastructures (e.g. Belgium, Bulgaria, Estonia, and Germany) in order to increase the attractiveness of cycling and walking (or public transport), or make it increasingly difficult / expensive for people to use cars (e.g. expanding the area of paid on-street parking in city centres (Tallinn, Tartu) in Estonia).

Other cycling promotion policies include, cycle to work scheme in the UK, awareness raising campaigns for PT, walking and cycling (European Cycling Challenge 2012-2015) in Estonia, cycling in the city awareness campaign in Greece, National Standard for cycle training in the UK, and the implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment) in Italy.

Table 6 shows the actors involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of transport sector of policy instruments. Table 8 shows the National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the transport sector.

Table 6 Actors involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of transport sector policy instruments

	National	Sub-national	Support
Belgium		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bruxelles Environnement • The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) • Government Wallon 	
Bulgaria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directorate General for Mobility and Transport 		
Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Interior - planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cities of: Tallinn, Tartu, Võru, Valga, Jõgeva , Rakvere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network of sustainable urban mobility planning
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Ministry for Transport and Digital Infrastructure 		
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism • Ministry of Transportation and Communications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative Divisions and Decentralized Divisions; • Local Authorities; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Athens Urban Transport Organisation – OASA, • ATTIKO METRO S.A., • National Federation Motorists of Long-distance Communications – POYAS, • Railway Agency of Greece – OSE, Railway Agency of Greece – OSE, • Civil Aviation Authority (YPA)
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Transport • National Transport Authority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipalities - mobility and traffic plans. 	
Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Science and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia 		
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department for the Environment and Climate Change (DECC) • Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) – planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scottish Government • Welsh Government • Northern Ireland Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment • Northern Ireland Environment Agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Saving Trust • Innovate UK • Salix • Research Councils UK • Carbon Trust

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Department of Transportation – office of low emission vehicles (OLEV)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Local Authorities	
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Table 7 National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the building sector

	Belgium	Bulgaria	Estonia	Germany	Greece	Italy	Serbia	UK
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). Different implementations in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital • Energy Performance Certificate (EPC). Different implementations in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ordinance № 7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings; • Ordinance № RD-16-932 OF 23/10/2009 for the terms & conditions for energy efficiency inspection of boilers and air conditioning systems; • Ordinance № RD 16-1057 of 10/12/2009 on the conditions and procedures for conducting energy efficiency audits and certification of buildings, the issue of energy performance certificates and categories of certificates; • Ordinance № RD 16-1058 of 10/12/2009 on buildings indicators for energy consumption & performance; • Inspections of boilers and heating/cooling installations; • Heating cost regulation; • Energy performance certificate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various regulations set under the Building Act: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68). • Emergency Act 15.06.2009 (§ 34) • Environmental Charges Act 01.01.2006 (KeTS) • Electricity Market Act, Chpt.5.Generation, §57, 58, 59, • Energy audit of the buildings (04.04.2014 nr.16) • Flat ownership and co-operative flat law (19.02.2014), to be put on effect on 01.01.2018 (Krts) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance (EnEV) • Inspections of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Heating cost regulation • Energy performance certificate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency of hot water boilers • Energy inspectors for energy performance of buildings • Green Public Procurements Metering • Energy Performance of Buildings • Energy efficiency (energy audits, metering, procurements by Public Bodies, ESCOs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy performance in buildings. Transposition of EPBD and EPBD recast EU directives (Decree 195/2012 and Law 90/2013); • Transposition of the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU (Legislative Decree nr 102 July 4th, 2014); • Rules for implementing the national energy plan in the field of rational use of energy, energy saving and development of renewable energy sources (Law 10/91); • Regulation on Accreditation of Italian Energy Certifiers (Presidential Decree 75/2013); • Green Public Procurement. Minimum Environmental Criteria for several appliances related to buildings, in particular public lighting and energy services for buildings; • Energy labelling of households appliances (Legislative Decree 28 June 2012, n. 104); • Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures; • Regional Regulatory Schemes on energy efficiency in buildings; • Municipal buildings regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD • Introduction of energy management systems in the public and commercial sectors • Mandatory regular control of the combustion process of boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Performance of Buildings Directive EU Directives (EPBD) • EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED) • Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates) • Zero Carbon Homes • Code for Sustainable Homes • Warm Front • The Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • Renewable Energy Strategy • Planning and Energy Act 2008 • Smart Metering and Billing • Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Display Energy Certificates (DECs) • Low Carbon Transition Plan • Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) • Energy Efficiency Commitment 1 and 2 (EEC 1 and 2) • Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) • Community Energy Saving Programme (CESP) • Private and Social Sector Regulation (Scotland) • Greening Government Commitments (GGC) (similar schemes for the devolved governments) • Home Energy Conservation Act

								<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decent Homes Standard • Energy Act 2011 • National products policy (tranche 2 - adopted measures) • National products policy (tranche 1 - implemented measures) • Ecodesign for Energy Related Products Regulations (SI 2010 No 2617) • Ecodesign for energy related Products Directives 2009/125/EC • Energy Labelling Directive (2010/30/EU)
<p>Dissemination and awareness instruments/ Informative policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy guzzlers website (“Energivores/energievreters”) • Energy renovation programme 2020 (Flanders): energy consultancy and audits; dissemination of technical and financial information on energy efficiency measures, including website on energy savings www.energiesparen.be (Flanders) • « Technologie Wallonne Énergie-Environnement et Développement Durable » (TWEED), portal on energy efficiency (Wallonia) • “Maison de l’énergie”, part of COBRACE (Brussels-Capital) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information campaigns of SEDA; • Energy efficiency Bureau at Municipal administration in several municipalities; • Information campaigns of energy distributors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The educational programmes to encourage clients by Kredex • Establishment of the smart energy network data portal Estfeed • European Commission Green Public Procurement Toolkit (GPP) 2008 • The website of http://www.energiatalgud.ee has been established by the Estonian Development Fund in order to collect all energy related information for the new 2030 + 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seal of quality efficiency house • On-site energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs (KfW) • KfW construction monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy labelling • labelling and standard product information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National plan for Smart metering; • Transparent billing methods (AEEG decision 164/08); • National plan for Green Procurement; • ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” ; • Several dissemination campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes (all experiences are mapped in the NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014) ; • Buildings energy efficiency voluntary certification schemes and environmental voluntary certification schemes (Casa Clima, Protocollo Itaca, LEED.....). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the use of energy-efficient household appliances • Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon Trust Measures • Smart Metering Implementation Programme • Energy Saving Trust and Carbon trust • INVEST NI (Northern Ireland) • Energy Savings Advice Service • Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES) • Big Energy Saving Week • Green Economy Awards • Open Homes Network • Act on CO2 Advice • Committee on Climate Change Guidance • Mandatory GHG reporting scheme • Voluntary Agreement on the Phase Out of Incandescent Light Bulbs • Community Energy Programme • Market Transformation Programme • Community Energy Advice Programme (pilot)

<p>Economic policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal personal income tax relief • Financial incentives encouraging rational use of energy (RUE). Different implementations in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital • Energy renovation programme 2020 (Flanders): premiums and tax deductions • Property tax reduction (Flanders) • Ecopack (Wallonia) • “Primes énergies” (Wallonia and Brussels-Capital) • Zero interest green loan (Brussels-Capital) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund (EERSF); • The National Trust EcoFund; • The “Fund for Energy and Energy Savings – EESF” REIT; • The Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Credit Line (BEERECL); • The Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL) • Energy tax • Structural and Investment Funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\KIK) financial support to living associations and private house owners for energetic refurbishment • EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\KIK) financial support to private house owners to make fuel switch from LFO • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • Demolition support given by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre (KIK) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW Energy-efficient construction • KfW Energy-efficient refurbishment • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • Energy tax • BAFA cross-cutting technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial incentives, energy efficiency requirements • Taxation of energy products and electricity • Green Fund • Financial incentives (subsidy) (replacement of oil heating systems with natural gas ones) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermal Account ; • Tax deductions; • White Certificate (or Energy Efficiency Certificates) scheme and Obligation for national energy distributors; • Kyoto Fund; • National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”); • Measures for the energy efficiency in schools (“Misure per l’efficientamento energetico degli edifici scolastici”) (2015); • Plafond Casa (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings • Energy efficiency improvement measures in public and commercial buildings • Incentive rates for highly efficient coupled / combined heat and power generation in public and commercial buildings 	<p>schemes)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Deal Finance Company • Warm Front Scheme • Renewable Obligation (RO) • Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) scheme • Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) • Government Buying Standards • Salix Project and public sector loans • Loans to SMEs by Carbo Trust • EU ETS Carbon Price Floor • Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme (CRC) • Green Investment Bank • Climate Change Agreements (CCA) • Electricity Market Reform • Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition • Re:FIT national programme • Climate Change Levy (CCL) • Public Sector Central Energy Efficiency Fund (CEEF) (Scotland) • Home Energy Efficiency Programmes (Scotland) • Home Renewables Loan Scheme (Scotland) • Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland) • Resource Efficiency Scotland (SME Loans Scheme) • Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF)
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								<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni' Fro (Wales) • Enhanced Capital Allowances (ECA) incl. Energy Technology List • Nest: Home Energy Efficiency Scheme (Wales) • Sustainable Energy Programme (Northern Ireland) • Boiler Replacement Scheme (Northern Ireland) • Landlords Energy Saving Allowance (LESA) • Stamp Duty Relief for Zero Carbon Homes (tax) • Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) • Scottish District Heating Loan Fund • Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF) • Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)
<p>Capacity building and networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flemish support programme for energy consultants (Flanders) • Employment-Environment Alliance (Wallonia and Brussels-Capital) • Exemplary buildings contest (Brussels-Capital) • The facilitator network (Brussels-Capital) • Energy audit obligation for non-residential buildings (Brussels-Capital) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered (grant issuing, trainings and consultations). • Guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency networks Initiative • Promotion of energy management systems (EMS) • Funding for the retraining as an energy consultant • Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants • IPEEC (International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency ("Piano integrato di diffusione dell'efficienza energetica", PIDEE). • General conference on Energy Efficiency ("Stati Generali Efficienza Energetica" (ENEAE)); • ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Technologies Institute • Resource Efficient Scotland • Green Deal Training and Certification for Assessors/Installers • Peer-to-peer community energy mentoring scheme • Funding for facilities/management apprenticeships • Funding competition for energy efficiency training • Community Energy Strategy • Capacity Market • One Stop Shop for community energy projects • Community First funding 	

								and community organisers training
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEDESCO public/private energy service company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated budget for energy performance contracting in public buildings • ESCO portfolio guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The establishment of housing unit in Foundation KredEx to start the apartment houses energetic refurbishment programme. • Renewable Energy Action Plan 2020 and the new Energy Sector Development Plan 2030 • Estonian cities Rakvere and Tallinn have submitted their sustainable energy action plans to EU. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence centre for public buildings incl. default guarantees) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Legislative Decree 115/2008). 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Energy Performance Contract and list of available energy service contracts on government website • Best Practice Guide to Energy Performance Contracting • Updated Guide to Financing Energy Efficiency in the Public Sector (20120 • Guide to Financing Energy Efficiency in the Private Sector • Review of Energy Services Market • Quality Assurance labels e.g. Green Deal Quality Mark • License Lite • Energy Services Directive • RIIO ED1 Price Control model for network regulation • Time to Connect incentive for DNOs • Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs
Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Procurement Rules for Federal Administration and Public Services • “Milieu- en Energietechnologie-Innovatieplatform” (MIP), energy technology (Flanders) • Smart Grids Flanders (Flanders) • “Programme Mobilisateur ENERGYWALL”, energy efficiency and renewables (Wallonia) • “Programme Mobilisateur ERable”, 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030 +) which integrates many previous strategies under new and revised document • Grants programmes by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre, KIK. • EU 6th FP and 7th FP 6th an energy research programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low energy buildings project (dena) and efficiency house Plus • Research initiative “Zukunft Bau” and Research for energy-optimised construction • Public procurement guidelines • 6th energy research programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecodesign for appliances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Electric System Research (ENEA, CNR and RSE carry out R&D activities on urgent and strategic issues which have results for the benefit of the national electric system users as a whole); • National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds (2012 and 2013); • National prize for energy efficiency measures (GSE’s “Premio Efficienza Energetica”); • ENEA reports on energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modernization of public lighting system in towns and municipalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Technology Institute (incl. Energy system modelling environment (ESME)) • CHP Development Map • National Heat Map and Strategy • Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU) • Innovation Rollout Mechanism • Low Carbon Industrial Strategy (LCIS) • Low Carbon Buildings Programme • Low Carbon Networks Fund

	<p>smart grids (Wallonia)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • « Programme Mobilisateur R&D SOLWATT », photovoltaics (Wallonia) 					<p>efficiency best available technologies.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Entrepreneurs Fund • Technology Innovation Needs Assessment • Small Business Research Initiative • TSB Future Energy Management in Buildings Programme • Invest in Innovative Refurbishment • Advanced Heat Storage Competition • End Use Energy Demand Research Centres
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Table 8 National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the transport sector

	Belgium	Bulgaria	Estonia	Germany	Greece	Italy	Serbia	UK
Planning instruments		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitate and modernise the road infrastructure in order to allow for optimal travelling speeds and ensure that vehicle engines operate in the optimum mode; • Introduce intelligent transport systems on national roads and in urban environments; • Reduce the relative share of trips with private motor vehicles by improving public urban transport and promoting non-motorised transport; • Increase the share of electrified urban transport by rail, metro, trolleybuses and tramcars; • Develop and promote the use of bicycles; • Develop and build intermodal terminals for multimodal services; • Develop and promote the use of hybrid and electric vehicles; • Ensure that fiscal policy stimulates savings and less use of conventional fuels; • Reduce the number of urban transport vehicles using conventional fuels by 2020; • Reduce the freight transported more than 300 kilometres by road vehicles by changing it to more environmental modes of transport, including rail; • Build railway connections between the central airport hubs of Sofia, Varna, Burgas, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reconstruction of railways (increased speeds) • Renewal of passenger train fleet (2013) • ELMO quick EV-charging network covering all Estonia (165 charging points) • Green Investment schemes (incl. ELMO, Tallinn trams, 110 county buses). • Investment scheme for multi-modal access to rail stations facilitates the development of areas close to rail stations. • Investment scheme for urban mobility and county centres. • Local investment in cycling, walking and public transport • dedicated bus lanes in Tallinn • Plans for bicycle share schemes in 5 cities, new cycle infrastructure in city centres,. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility and fuel strategy: introduction of alternative fuels and innovative drive technologies • Improving bicycle infrastructure: investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks, and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic • Federal transport infrastructure plan 2015: stronger emphasis on railways and waterways (freight) concerning budget • National cycling plan • Single European Sky: Improving flight paths in regard to environmental efficiency 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020; • National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (PNIRE); • National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (2014); • Promotion of use of biomethane in transports (Article 8 of Legislative Decree No 28/2011); • Five years bus fleet renewal plan (2014); • "Contratto di programma" for the development of the national rail infrastructure; • Voluntary urban mobility plans (PUM and PUMS); • National plan for Green Procurement. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Infrastructure Plan 2014 • Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy) • Eco-towns: A supplement to Planning Policy Statement 1 • (Ultra-) Low Carbon Emissions Zones at local authority/regional level e.g. London • Renewable Energy Directive • Fuel Quality Directive

		Plovdiv and Gorna Oryahovitsa; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of rail infrastructure, improvement of inland waterways navigation and expansion of metro transport 						
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private or public bodies with more than 200 employees have to introduce transport planning (Brussels-Capital) Event managers with over 3000 participants have to introduce a transport plan to promote use of public transport (Brussels-Capital) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the production of biofuels and require state and municipal administrations to provide examples of good practices in the implementation of energy efficiency measures and RES use in the transport sector. Public procurement requirements for new vehicles to be able to run on blended and pure biofuels. CO2-emission standards of new vehicles Increase the number of electric vehicles and individual systems for production of electricity from RES in the transport sector by constructing and developing smart grids and electric vehicle charging stations; Maintaining sustainable transport statistic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electro-mobility program Energy labelling of cars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CO2-emission standards of new vehicles Fuel quality ordinance: fuel quality standards, biofuel quotas, biomass sustainability ordinance etc. Voluntary agreement with German National Railways: specific CO2 reduction targets for the period 2006-2020 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle Certification. Vehicle CO2 emissions standards (compliant with European policies on theme); Renewable energy in transport sector (D.lgs 28/2011); Urban traffic plans ("Piano Urbano del Traffico"), planning instrument which is compulsory for municipalities with more than 30.000 inhabitants; Obligation for national fuel producers to input into consumption 1% of biofuels of total traditional fuel (Law n. 81, 11 March 2006); National quality standards for biofuels (AEEG); Minimum Environmental Criteria for the acquisition of vehicles for road transport ("Criteri Minimi Ambientali per l'acquisizione dei veicoli adibiti al trasporto su strada") (2012); Limits to polluting vehicles (regional level); Road transport code ("Codice della Strada"), indirect effects on speed restriction, parking supply restriction, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction of the EU Regulation EC 443/2009 for energy efficiency in the transport sector Modernization of fleet in order to meet technical requirements for the performance of domestic and international transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Car policies (EU new car CO2 emissions targets: 130 gCO2/km by 2015 and 95 gCO2/km by 2020; and complementary measures) LGV policies (EU new LGV CO2 emissions targets: 175g CO2/km by 2017 and 147 gCO2/km by 2020; and complementary measures) HGV policies (low rolling resistance tyres and industry-led action to improve efficiencies) Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) Eco Driving training included in national driving tests Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) Road transport codes (speed limits etc.)
Financial policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax exemptions for employers who pay their employees allowances for home-workplace bike journeys CO2 tax on company cars based on the type of fuel and CO2 emissions Tax exemptions for capital gains made on inland waterway transport vessels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and promote the use of bicycles; Establish a support scheme for transport operators where there are significant differences between the prices of conventional fuels and biofuels, following an analysis and assessment of the economic and environmental benefits from the use of biofuels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing fuel excise duty 2016-2018 decreasing VAT reimbursement rate and procedures for company cars; Support scheme for electro-mobility program ELMO (supporting purchase of EV-s, support for EV charging, ELMO-rent and EV taxis). Abolishing earmarking of fuel duty revenues for roads. New schemes on investment for integrated solutions in urban areas/railway stations, county centres. Free public transport in Tallinn (local measure) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CO2-related motor vehicle tax Fiscal allowances for work-related travel expenses Heavy goods vehicle toll charges Municipal transport financing act and regionalisation act: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel), biodiesel and kerosene for transport for transport Registration tax rates (Euro 5) (Hybrid and electric cars are exempted) Circulation fee (road tax) Incentives to replace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (Law 134/2012); Incentives for the promotion of biofuels in transport sector (2013); Ad-hoc fund of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on PNIRE implementation (2013-2015); Ministry call in favour of the Regions to fund a network of electric vehicle charging points (5 million €); National electric car sharing project in cities (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction of incentive mechanisms for replacement of the existing vehicles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company Car Tax Reform Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) Plug-in car and van grants (including Electric Vehicle Homecharge Scheme) Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS) (successor scheme to the Green Bus Fund) Local Sustainable Transport Fund Rail Electrification Congestion Charges (local authority/regional level)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payback of the remaining 20% of public transport season tickets, if employers pay their employees 80% back of the ticket price (Flanders) • Green car registration tax (Flanders) • “Commuter fund”, to finance mobility action plans of companies (Flanders) • Ecotax incentive for the purchase of new, energy efficient vehicles (Wallonia) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding the area of paid on-street parking in city centres (Tallinn, Tartu) 	<p>transport of passenger in cities and municipalities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic • Ecological tax reform: eco tax on motor fuels, extension of tax reduction for natural gas in the transport sector • Levy on air traffic: “ecological” levy on air traffic at the national level for all flights from German airports 	old technology cars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National funds for the development of underground railways; • Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan”; • Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods”; • Road tax (tax exemption for electric vehicles and discount on car assurance) and regional schemes for tax exemption for GPL and methane vehicles; • National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). • Funding for energy efficiency, renewable energy and bike-sharing (Ministry of the Environment’s Call - Official journal n. 88/2010; Budget Law 2008), ended in 2011. 		
Dissemination and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • « CO2 car guide » • “Mobility desks”, assistance and advice on the development of companies’ commuter plans (Flanders) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in energy efficient driving; • Informed vehicle choices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising campaigns for PT, walking and cycling (European Cycling Challenge 2012-2015) • Compulsory eco-driving module for driving licence training. Eco-driving promotion. • Common information system for all Estonian PT providers – www.peatus.ee • Common ticket payment system (contactless card) for Tallinn city and Harju county • Speed limit enforcement through automatic speed controls on main intercity roads. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling • Mobility management action programme • “me and my car” campaign • “new driving” campaign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer information fuel economy and CO2 emissions of new passenger cars • Cycling in the city • Eco-driving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guide to fuel saving and decreasing CO2 emission by cars (Ministry of the Environment); • National Logistics Platform UIRNET ; • Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week; • National observatory on local public transports policies (“Osservatorio nazionale sulle politiche per il trasporto pubblico locale”); • Eco-driving Guide (Ministry of Economic Development). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme • Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel Economy labels for cars • The National Standard for cycle training • Eco Driving Training/FuelGood Driver Training • Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme
Policy instruments for Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Retibo”, research project to stimulate a more efficient and sustainable public transport system (federal, Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital) • “Test project on passenger vehicles” to analyse behaviour of vehicle use (federal, 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Estonia, E-Governance and other e-solutions • Smart City cluster to develop ICT tools • R&D program planned for transport energy efficiency development • Promoting co-operation between universities, authorities and businesses for common curriculum on planning. • Planning guidance being developed by Ministry of Interior; National Spatial Development Plan 2030+. • Network of sustainable urban mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National innovation programme for hydrogen and fuel cell technology • Government electro mobility programme • Funding programme for electro mobility in model regions • Electro mobility funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial companies in improving the energy efficiency of Motor Driven Systems • Agreement with car manufacturers ACEA etc 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment); • National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds (2012 and 2013); • National technological maritime platform (“Piattaforma Tecnologica Nazionale Marittima”). 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • £82 million of research and development funding available from UK Government to support the new generation of ULEVs; with a focus on identifying and funding emerging technologies that the UK can exploit and lead on globally. • Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP) • Funding for development of ultra low emissions vehicles

	<p>Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels-Capital</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Proeftuin elektrisch voertuig”, to support introduction of electromobility (Flanders) 		<p>planning (brings together cities, government, experts, NGOs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tallinn and Tartu travel survey (end of 2015) to analyse travel patterns and key drivers 				<p>(ULEVs) e.g. Technology Strategy Board’s Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Government funding for advanced biofuel research • Low Carbon HGV Technology Taskforce
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CHAPTER 2: MAPPING BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

2.1.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS

As shown in Figure 4 and Table 9, the most common social barriers indicated by the HERON partners countries are related to ‘social group interactions’ and to the ‘socio-economic status of the building users’. These barriers were reported by the majority of partner countries including Belgium, Germany, Greece Italy, Serbia and the UK. ‘Social group interactions’ are reported to be of importance when it comes to taking decisions on energy efficiency investments. Furthermore, sharing the information and expert advice among groups of people helps promote energy efficiency and environmentally conscious behaviour. Similarly, ‘strong dependency’ on social groups such as neighbours was reported in multi-family housing, which is a common barrier in Estonia, Bulgaria, Greece and Italy. In this case, shared ownership of buildings becomes a major barrier in reaching agreements that would allow the uptake of energy upgrading measures for the entire building, such as retrofitting. ‘Status considerations’ are reported as a key barrier in Estonia and the UK (Table 10, Figure 5), where improvements in living standards and increase in the socio-economic status of households result in different comfort expectations (e.g occupants being satisfied with higher indoor temperatures) and higher energy use (Roberts, 2008). This is a phenomenon often observed following refurbishments (Clinch and Healy, 2000; Milne and Boardman, 2000), and is linked to the rebound effect. This phenomenon occurs when energy efficiency improvements counter-intuitively lead to higher levels of energy consumption. Only two of the partner countries referred to this phenomenon, however, it is believed that this is mainly due to lack of evidence and relevant data provided in literature. In the UK, this phenomenon has been well documented and its effects were mapped (Barker et al., 2007; Oreszczyn and Lowe, 2005; Pelenur and Cruickshank, 2012; Dowson et al., 2012). An opposite trend was also reported in the cases of Estonia, Germany and Bulgaria, where the low income of pensioners and older population prevents them from investing in energy efficiency.

Table 9 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Social group interactions and status considerations	x			x	x	x	x	x
	Socio-Economic status of building users	x		x		x	x	x	x
	Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing		x	x		x	x		
	Inertia		x			x		x	x
	Low income of aged people		x	x	x				
	Commitment and motivation of public					x		x	x
	Rebound effect			x					x
	Expectations for electricity prices to remain low in future							x	
Cultural	Lack of interest/Low priority/Undervaluing energy efficiency	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
	Bounded rationality/Visibility of energy efficiency	x		x	x	x		x	x
	Missing credibility/Mistrust of technologies and contractors				x	x		x	x
Educational	Training and skills of professionals	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
	Lack of trusted information, knowledge and experience		x	x		x		x	x
	Lack of awareness on savings potential			x	x	x		x	x
	Lack of knowledge/Information gap on technologies	x		x	x	x			x

Figure 4 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Cultural barriers such as ‘lack of interest in energy efficiency’ and ‘habits and behavioural aspects’ are common across all countries and are also rated very high in terms of their impact (Figure 5, Table 10). Lack of interest and the act of undervaluing energy efficiency is a complex barrier that is related to aspects such as lack of knowledge, inertia and habit. Behavioural aspects linked to social norms and habits are a major barrier across the majority of the countries. This refers to social norms and expectations requiring carbon-dependent lifestyles. Socially-acceptable ways of behaving—for example, driving to work, frequent long-haul holidays and weekend breaks, leaving appliances on and the weekly supermarket shop—in turn become ingrained as unconscious habitual behaviours, making them unquestioned and thus more intractable (Jackson, 2005). Ownership and consumption, for example of electronic goods, are important status symbols in our society and people feel they are expected to achieve this (Steg and Sievers, 2000). Some of the literature argues that once people become accustomed to a particular standard of living, their perceptions of needs and expectations change. Their revised expectations are perpetuated in discourses about quality of life, and once absorbed into daily routine become interpreted as “needs” rather than “wants” (Steg and Sievers, 2000; Shove, 2003). The interdependency between physical infrastructures and social institutions contributes to creating a lock-in which restricts radical innovation (Jackson, 2005) and reinforces environmentally-detrimental behaviours (Hobson, 2003). For example, desires for consumption and links to status and cultural values are perpetuated in current western society by marketing mechanisms (Lorenzoni et al., 2007) and as a result this barrier is very difficult to tackle. In many markets, electricity customers do not see the real cost of power, which limits the potential for price signals to encourage changes in behaviour. Customers typically have no accurate information about the energy consumed by any particular application, such as the added cost of a spare refrigerator, or the relative benefit of having the refrigerator located in a cool basement, versus a warm garage. Furthermore, based on the way electricity is priced, customers do not receive accurate signals about the marginal cost of energy,

which, for example, can vary significantly throughout the course of a day. (Creys et al, 2007). The issue of the non-visibility of energy efficiency is linked to the barrier of ‘bounded rationality’.

As a result of the above, people often disregard the impact that energy efficiency measures will have, as they are unaware of the amount of energy they use and of their potential savings. This educational barrier was also reported as a major constraint by five partner countries (Estonia, Germany, Greece, Serbia, UK). Lack of awareness on savings potential can be encountered even among consumers, architects, engineers, builders, contractors, installers and building operators (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007) and is linked to another barrier that was identified across many partners countries, that of ‘lack of trained and skilled professionals’. This in turn leads to another barrier, that of the mistrust of technologies and contractors. It is therefore clear from these findings that limited information and lack of understanding and experience of public and professionals leads to a series of different problems that undermine energy efficiency in buildings.

Table 10 Assessment of main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Social group interactions and status considerations	High			Medium	Low	Medium	Low	Medium
	Socio-Economic status of building users	Medium		High		Low	Low	Medium	High
	Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing		High	High		Medium	Medium		
	Inertia		Medium			Medium		Medium	High
	Low income of aged people		High	Medium	Low				
	Commitment and motivation of public					Low		Medium	Medium
	Rebound effect			Medium					High
Cultural	Expectations for electricity prices to remain low in future							High	
	Lack of interest/Low priority/Undervaluing EE	High	Medium	Medium	High	Low	High	Medium	High
	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	High	Medium	High		High	High	Medium	Medium
	Bounded rationality/Visibility of energy efficiency	Low		Medium	High	Low		Low	Medium
Educational	Missing credibility/Mistrust of technologies and contractors				Low	Low		Medium	Medium
	Training and skills of professionals	Medium	Medium	High		High	Medium	Low	Medium
	Lack of trusted information, knowledge and experience		Medium	Medium		Medium		High	High
	Lack of awareness on savings potential			Medium	Medium	High		High	High
	Lack of knowledge/Information gap on technologies	Medium		Medium	Low	Medium			Medium

Figure 5 Assessment of main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

2.1.2 ECONOMIC BARRIERS

The most common and significant economic barriers indicated by the HERON partner countries are shown in Table 11 and Figure 6. Lack of financial incentives among the countries are found in a number of areas, e.g. in Italy and Belgium the concern is for the lack of incentives for building owners that rent buildings as they do not reap the energy savings and renters of buildings as they do not own the improvements but only pay the bills. In general other countries see a lack of incentives as a notable barrier to EE improvements or projects. In the UK incentives are needed due to the high cost of EE improvements and the low cost of energy consumption; this aligns this barrier along the same lines as other common barriers: High cost of innovative technologies for end-users and relatively cheap energy and fuel prices in some cases. High capital costs/financial risk received the highest barrier rating among a majority of countries. To add to the high capital cost, financial risk is compounded due to the high interest rates of bank loans (Bulgaria, Greece, Serbia and the UK).

In Belgium, Estonia, Greece, Italy, Serbia and the UK lack of funds or access to finance is also a significant barrier. Lack of funds or access to finance can relate to the inability to find a loan for a system or renovation because the funding agent will not back the investment (reluctance to contract a loan). Some people are also unable to get access to finance because of their financial history. This not only is a problem for individuals but can also be a problem for small-medium sized hotels in Greece. Due to poor credit ratings, smaller hotels face more costly loans than hotel chains. *The lack of funds* barrier is similar to *economic status of building users* barrier in that lack of capital prevents households (particularly lower income

sections of the population) from paying the upfront costs needed for investment in energy efficiency (Belgium). This is not only a problem for homeowners; Germany cites that service companies can also lack access to capital or available capital where a certain investment is not given a priority status due to less ‘profitability’. Finally in some countries, such as Italy and Greece, the economic stagnation or strain has created a condition where credit is difficult to access limiting EE investments.

Table 11 Main economic barriers in the building sector

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Lack of Financial Incentive (Public and Private sector)		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
High Capital costs/Financial Risk	x	x	x	x	x			x
Lack of funds or access to finance	x		x		x	x	x	x
Payback expectations/Investment horizons				x	x	x	x	x
Uncertainty on investment	x	x		x	x			x
Economic status of building users	x		x		x		x	x
High cost of innovative technologies for end-users			x		x			x
Relatively cheap energy and fuel prices		x	x				x	
Hidden costs	x	x						x
Financial crisis/Economic stagnation		x			x	x		
Embryonic markets					x			x
Tariff system not reflecting energy use/EE		x					x	
Costs vary regionally (Fragmented ability)			x					

Figure 6 Main economic barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Table 12 and Figure 7 show the qualitative assessment of the main common barriers according to their impact. Though lack of financial incentive is the most common, shared by seven countries, the barrier that seems to have the highest impact across the partner countries is high capital costs and financial risks for investing in energy efficiency in buildings. This includes refurbishment and investment in new technologies.

Table 12 Assessment of main economic barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Barriers type	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Lack of Financial Incentive (Public and Private sector)		High	High	Medium	Medium	Low	High	Medium
High Capital costs/Financial Risk	High	High	High	High	Medium			High
Lack of funds or access to finance	High		High		Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Payback expectations/Investment horizons				High	Medium	Low	Low	High
Uncertainty on investment	Low	High		Medium	Medium			Medium
Economic status of building users	Medium		High		Low		Medium	High
High cost of innovative technologies for end-users			Medium		Medium			High
Relatively cheap energy and fuel prices		Medium	Medium				High	
Hidden costs	Medium	Medium						Medium
Financial crisis/Economic stagnation		High			High	Medium		
Embryonic markets					Medium			High
Tariff system not reflecting energy use/energy efficiency		Medium					High	
Costs vary regionally (Fragmented ability)			High					

Figure 7 Assessment of main economic barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

2.1.3 INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS

As shown in Figure 8 and Table 13, the most common and significant institutional barriers indicated by the HERON partners countries are ‘split incentives’, ‘complex or inadequate regulatory procedures’ and ‘lack of relevant legislation’, as well as the ‘characteristics of the building stock’ (e.g. aging stock, non-cavity walls, etc.)

The most cited barrier, that of ‘split incentives’, refers mainly to the ‘landlord-tenant split’, which applies to most cases (UK, Serbia, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Bulgaria), whereby landlords may not invest in energy efficiency measures because their tenants pay the energy bills, or conversely tenants have no incentive to reduce their energy use as their landlord pays the bill (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). In the cases of Greece, Estonia and Germany, this barrier also appears where there are multiple owners and/or occupiers of buildings. Ownership and responsibility can be opaque, and it can be very difficult to agree on energy saving investments in multi-family residential buildings if many different property owners have to either approve a decision or make a financial contribution (BPIE, 2011).

‘Complex and/or inadequate regulatory procedures’, reported by seven countries, is cited as a major barrier in the case of Bulgaria (Table 14); where long administrative procedures and frequent change of the regulatory framework often prevent investments. Similar issues, related to bureaucracy, were reported in Italy, Serbia and Greece. In the UK and Germany, the policy framework for improving the energy efficiency of buildings appears to be fragmented, with numerous regulations, incentives and programmes addressing the buildings from different perspectives and not being well co-ordinated, making it difficult for households and companies to decide which programmes are most beneficial.

Table 13 Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Barriers type (Institutional)	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Split Incentive	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Complex/Inadequate regulatory procedures		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Lack of relevant legislation/Lack of regulatory provision		x			x	x	x	x
Building stock characteristics/Aging stock	x		x		x	x		x
Technical problems/ Performance Gap			x	x	x			x
Missing support chains/Skills and training	x			x		x		x
Policy coordination across different levels/Cooperation of municipalities	x		x		x	x		
Lack of data/information –diversion of management		x	x		x			x
Inadequate implementation network/governance framework				x	x		x	
Historical preservation		x			x			x
Disruption /Hassle factor				x	x			x
Poor compliance with efficiency standards/construction standards	x				x			x
Mismatch between policy and occupant reality				x	x			x
Inadequate implementation of policy measures				x	x	x		
Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division		x			x			
Security of fuel supply			x					x

Figure 8 Main institutional barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

The ‘building stock characteristics’ are cited as a barrier by five countries, and rank highly in terms of impact (Figure 9, Table 14). This barrier refers to the limitations that the building structure itself imposes on residents, for example, in terms of the space available in the building, the age of construction, the lack of cavity walls, poorly installed windows, or unsuitable roofs. A sub-category of this barrier includes the buildings which are facing difficulties in installing energy efficiency measures because they are either listed buildings or in a conservation area (Pelenur and Cruickshank, 2012). Aging stock is cited as a major barrier in Estonia, Greece, Italy and the UK.

‘Poor compliance with efficiency and construction standards’ is cited as a major barrier in Belgium, Greece and the UK (Table 14). This barrier points out the problem of enforcing and achieving compliance with building standards and efficiency targets, through monitoring of compliance and quality control. This is closely linked to quality of workmanship and the educational barrier of ‘training and skills’ of professionals. This issue is also linked with the problem of the ‘performance gap’ that refers to the discrepancy between the design and actual performance of buildings as a result of poor fabric or system performance. In the UK, several studies have focused on this topic, providing great insight on the reasons leading to the performance gap (Gupta et al., 2013; Gupta and Kapsali, 2014; Austin and Charlson, 2012; Bell et al., 2010)

Table 14 Assessment of main institutional barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Split Incentive	Medium	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Complex/Inadequate regulatory procedures		High	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Lack of relevant legislation/regulatory provision		Medium			Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Building stock characteristics/Aging stock	Low		High		High	High		High
Technical problems/ Performance Gap			Medium	Low	Low			High
Missing support chains/Skills and training	Medium			High		Medium		Medium
Policy coordination across different levels/cooperation between municipalities	High		Low		Low	High		
Lack of data/information		Medium	Medium		High			Medium
Inadequate implementation network/governance framework				Medium	High		High	
Historical preservation		Low			Low			High
Disruption /Hassle factor				Medium	Medium			High
Poor compliance with efficiency standards/construction standards	High				High			High
Mismatch between policy and occupant reality				Medium	Low			High
Inadequate implementation of policy measures				Medium	Medium	High		
Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division		Medium			Medium			
Security of fuel supply			High					Low

Figure 9 Assessment of main institutional barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

2.1.4 COMPARISON OF KEY BARRIERS

The review of all national reports showed that not all partner countries are referencing the same number of barriers in energy efficiency in the building sector, with some countries listing more than thirty barriers, with others listing less than twenty. This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and does not absolutely reflect the number of barriers encountered in the country. Instead, this finding is pointing to the fact that research on barriers in energy efficiency in buildings is not equally developed across all partners countries, which could in turn hinder the development of efficient policies. As shown in Figure 10, research on barriers in energy efficiency in the building sector is more progressed in countries such as UK, Greece and Estonia. Despite this, it can be observed that institutional barriers appear to be the most important type of barrier, followed by economic ones. However, social, cultural and educational barriers are also very significant, making up nearly half of the total number of barriers identified in each country.

Figure 10 Types of barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Figure 11 shows the main common barriers, in all categories, which were identified across the eight partner countries. The cultural barrier of ‘undervaluing energy efficiency’ and the institutional barrier of ‘split incentives’ are the most common; as they are reported by all countries. However, the economic barrier of ‘high capital costs and financial risk’ ranks highest amongst most countries in terms of its impact on energy efficiency in buildings (Figure 12). Other economic barriers such as ‘access to finance’ and ‘lack of financial incentives’ are also among the top common barriers identified. Other barriers such as ‘habits and behaviour’ (cultural) and ‘building stock characteristics’ (institutional) also rank highly in terms of their impact.

Figure 11 Main common barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

Figure 12 Qualitative assessment of main common barriers in the building sector across all partner countries

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

2.2.1 SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS

The barriers that appear to be most common and are rated the highest in terms of their impact on transport energy efficiency are linked to social and cultural issues such as the 'car as a status symbol' and 'habit and social norm of driving and car use' (Table 15, Table 16). 'Car as a status symbol' was reported as a major barrier in Belgium, Bulgaria and Greece, where, for many people, owning and driving a private car represents a certain status and lifestyle and is considered a symbol of comfort and freedom. Similarly, the 'habit and social norm of driving' is considered a major barrier in Greece and Germany.

As in the case of the building sector, 'limited environmental concern and low priority' is a common barrier in the improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector as well (Figure 13). Studies reveal that when it comes to car purchasing, environmental issues have a very low priority for private and fleet consumers. This is at odds, both with the high level of concern declared by members of the public, and with the increasing importance of environmental issues within the business sector (Lane and Potter, 2007) across the eight countries; and is a barrier that is linked to 'bounded rationality and buyer attitude'. Buyer attitude is often based on decisions that are only partially rational, and can be also characterised as emotional or irrational (bounded rationality). In the case of cars, people tend to discount heavily (or not take into account) future cost savings from fuel economy at the time of purchasing a car, even though it would seem to be in their own interests as well as those of the environment (King, 2009). Evidence from the UK suggests that buyers discount heavily, and some do not consider vehicle efficiency benefits at the point of purchasing a car. They are therefore less inclined to adopt efficient vehicles than the financial incentive from fuel economy savings might suggest. In addition, the majority of buyers tend to rate the environmental impact of vehicles relatively low in their purchase criteria. 'Limited awareness of impact of energy efficiency' in the transport sector was reported as a major barrier in Bulgaria, Greece and Serbia. This issue is related to the public perception that energy efficiency is not a priority and is linked with limited knowledge and understanding of environmental impacts, cost structures and fuel use.

Table 15 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Low satisfaction with public transport/Lack of trust		x	x		x	x	x	
	Concerns on vehicle reliability / Hesitation to trust new technologies	x			x	x			x
	Heterogeneity of consumers	x						x	x
	Suburbanisation trends/Low density			x	x				
	Vulnerability of pedestrians/ Lack of adequate space for walking				x		x		
	Cruising traffic / Parking problems					x	x		
	Inertia							x	x
Cultural	Attitude-action gap	x							x
	Car as a symbol status and group influence	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
	Habit and social norm of driving, car ownership and use			x	x	x	x	x	x
	Environmental concern/ Low priority	x			x	x	x	x	x
	Cycling is marginalized			x			x		x
Educational	Bounded rationality /Buyer attitude				x			x	x
	Lack of knowledge/information on green transport/ULEVs/EVs	x	x		x	x		x	x
	Limited awareness of impact of EE in transport		x		x	x		x	x
	Consumer understanding and use of fuel economy information				x			x	x
	Confusion about car and fuel costs (conventional vs ULEVs/EVs)				x				x
	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving					x			
	Low public awareness towards eco-driving					x			
Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals			x						
Lack of trained technicians for ULEVs/EVs								x	

Figure 13 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

Regarding the diffusion of Electric vehicles (EVs) and Ultra low emission vehicles (ULEVs), the most important barrier, that ranked highly among the majority of countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Serbia, UK), is the ‘lack of knowledge and information’ on these new technologies. In the UK, a lack of knowledge about EVs was identified as one of the main barriers to EV take-up. This related to all aspects of

purchasing and using EVs (e.g. purchase cost, running costs, financial incentives, range, variations in vehicle technology, available models and charging routines and infrastructure)(Hutchins et al., 2013). Evidence shows that potential plug-in vehicle buyers can be prevented from moving towards a purchase as a result of insufficient or inaccurate information (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013). A barrier reported in the UK is the lack of trained technicians for EVs and ULEVs.

As shown in Figure 14, the most common social barrier is the low satisfaction with public transport, reported in Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece, Italy and Serbia. In the cases of Bulgaria and Italy, this was reported as a major barrier, as it includes elements such as the perception of public transport as unsafe, more time consuming and less flexible than private means of transport.

Table 16 Assessment of main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Low satisfaction with public transport/Lack of trust		High	Medium		Medium	High	Low	
	Concerns on vehicle reliability/ Hesitation to trust new technologies	High			Low	Low			High
	Heterogeneity of consumers	Medium						Low	High
	Suburbanisation trends/Low density			Medium	Medium				
	Vulnerability of pedestrians/ Lack of adequate space for walking				Low		Low		
	Cruising traffic / Parking problems					High	Medium		
	Inertia							Medium	High
Attitude-action gap	High							Medium	
Cultural	Car as a symbol status and group influence	High	High	Medium	Medium	High		Low	Low
	Habit and social norm of driving, car ownership and use			Medium	High	High	Low	Medium	Low
	Environmental concern/ Low priority	High			Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
	Cycling is marginalized			Medium			Low		Low
Bounded rationality /Buyer attitude				Medium			High	High	
Educational	Lack of knowledge/information on green transport/ULEVs/EVs	Medium	High		Medium	High		High	High
	Limited awareness of impact of EE in transport		High		Medium	High		High	Medium
	Consumer understanding and use of fuel economy information				Medium			High	Medium
	Confusion about car and fuel costs (conventional vs ULEVs/EVs)				Medium				Medium
	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving					High			
	Low public awareness towards eco-driving					High			
	Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals			High					
Lack of trained technicians for ULEVs/EVs								Medium	

Figure 14 Assessment of main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

2.2.2 ECONOMIC BARRIERS

The most common and significant transport sector economic barriers indicated by the HERON countries are shown in Table 17 and Figure 15.

Lack of finance for new efficient vehicles is the most cited barrier; also cited as most important in most countries. In Belgium, Germany, Greece and Italy, ULEVs are more expensive to purchase and own than conventional vehicles (also with little-no financial assistance) acting as a barrier for take-up. In Germany the lack of finance also exists for more efficient public transport on a local authority level. In Bulgaria and Serbia, a majority of the population do not have access to finance or purchasing power for ULEVs. The financial crisis has taken a toll on efficient automobile ownership both privately and publicly in Greece. Also as a result of the economic crisis, Serbia saw a 60% decrease in new car registrations from 2008.

The second most cited barrier, ‘limited infrastructure investment’ is rated as highly significant by all countries which cited it (Table 18 and Figure 16). In Bulgaria the infrastructural problems are with lack of road improvements and the negative impact this has on the efficient performance of vehicles. In Estonia there is a disproportionate level of investment road infrastructure supporting private automobile travel over public transport. Similarly, in Germany allocation/prioritization of funding for *mega-projects* is jeopardizing the development of sustainable transport. In Greece, rail infrastructure suffers neglect due to the prioritization of road transport infrastructure. Finally, in the UK though there are and have been financial incentives for the take-up of ULEVs / electric vehicles, there is a causality dilemma between the need for electric charging station infrastructure and need for an increase in electric vehicles to make the business case for improved infrastructure.

Table 17 Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Barriers type (Economic)	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Lack of finance for new vehicles/ULEVs/public transport	x	x		x	x	x	x	
Limited infrastructure investment (road/train/cycling)		x	x		x	x		x
Low purchasing power of citizens/Financial crisis		x			x	x	x	
High Cost/Low cost competitiveness of electric vehicles				x	x			x
Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles				x				x
High cost of batteries for electric vehicles						x		x
Inefficient or absent fiscal measures			x	x				
Limited financial incentives for electric vehicles		x					x	
Low population density/Urban sprawl			x			x		
Investment schemes do not encourage transport EE			x	x		x		
Tax free/low tax company car schemes			x					

Figure 15 Main economic barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

Table 18 Assessment of main economic barriers in the transport sector

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Lack of finance for new vehicles/ULEVs/public transport	High	High		High	High	High	Medium	
Limited infrastructure investment (road/train/cycling)		High	High		High	High		High
Low purchasing power of citizens/Financial crisis		High			High	High	High	
High Cost/Low cost competitiveness of electric vehicles				High	Medium			High
Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles				Medium				High
High cost of batteries for electric						Medium		Medium

vehicles								
Inefficient or absent fiscal measures			High	High				
Limited financial incentives for electric vehicles		High					Medium	
Low population density/Urban sprawl			High			High		
Investment schemes do not encourage transport EE			High	Medium		High		
Tax free/low tax company car schemes			High					

Figure 16 Assessment of main economic barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

2.2.3 INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS

As shown in Figure 17 and Table 19, the most common and significant institutional barriers indicated by the HERON partner countries are related to ‘lack of integrated governance’, the importance of ‘energy efficiency in the government agenda’, and the development of infrastructure for public transport, walking, cycling and EVs. ‘Lack of integrated governance and administrative fragmentation’ appear to be a very common problem in the transport sector and is reported in Estonia, Germany, Greece, Italy and Serbia. In the cases of Germany and Estonia, responsibility for public transport is divided between the municipal, regional and national authorities, leading to different tariff structures, scattered information and non-integrated service schedules. Similarly, in Greece more than one authority is responsible for planning and operation of public transport in large urban centre. Furthermore, energy efficiency in the transport sector does not appear to be a primary objective of governmental agendas in the cases of Bulgaria, Germany,

Greece, Italy and Serbia. In the UK, recent changes in Government suggest that contradictory policy goals, particularly in terms of enhancing the national road and aviation infrastructures, are to become significant institutional barriers in the near future.

Table 19 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Barriers type (Institutional)	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance			x	x	x	x	x	
Transport EE on the Government Agenda		x		x	x	x	x	
Inefficient urban/public transport infrastructure and planning		x	x	x	x	x		
Undeveloped cycling/walking infrastructure		x	x		x	x		x
Lack of support for rail transportation/Limited rail infrastructure		x	x	x		x		
Lack of a national strategy for bike and pedestrian mobility		x	x		x	x		
Undeveloped infrastructure for recharging of EV	x			x	x	x		x
Limited/complex funding in urban public transport				x	x	x		
Lack of regular transport services in low density areas		x				x		x
Immature status of developing technologies for EVs/ULEVs	x					x		x
Range of distance travelled between charges for EVs	x			x				x
Biofuel distribution and infrastructure	x					x		x
Limited policy on freight efficiency/city logistics				x		x		x
Lack of improvements/investments in transport infrastructure				x		x		
Contradicting policy goals Car-oriented planning			x	x				
Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations for EVs					x			x

Figure 17 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

The barriers related to infrastructure of public transport, walking and cycling and EVs rank the highest among countries, along with the provision of funding for urban public transport (Table 20 and Figure 18). In Bulgaria, Estonia, Germany and Greece inefficient transport infrastructure and planning is considered a major barrier in the development of energy efficiency in the transport sector. In the cases of Greece and Bulgaria, the infrastructure and planning for urban transport is not effective in displacing car dominance and diminish congestion related problems. In the cases of Germany and Estonia, car focused planning and the extension of the road infrastructure contradicts the implementation of the respective energy efficiency strategies proposed by the national transport strategy of each country. A key barrier to the uptake of electric vehicles, commonly cited across most national reports, is the lack of developed infrastructure for recharging. In the case of EVs, similar concerns such as the time needed to recharge the vehicles, the vehicle range between charges, and the unclear traffic road regulations concerning EVs were also cited. Findings from studies in the UK, suggest that these issues are a major concern among potential buyers (Hutchins et al., 2013; Lane and Potter, 2007). Limited focus on the development of infrastructure for walking and cycling was reported as a major barrier in Bulgaria, Estonia and Italy and the UK (at national level). This includes lack of segregated cycling routes and lack of secure bicycle parking facilities.

Table 20 Assessment of main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Barriers	BE	BG	EE	DE	GK	IT	RS	UK
Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance			High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	
Transport EE on the Government Agenda		Medium		Medium	High	Medium	High	
Inefficient urban/public transport infrastructure and planning		High	High	High	High	Medium		
Not developed cycling/walking infrastructure		High	High		Medium	High		High
Lack of support for rail transportation/Limited rail infrastructure		High	High	Medium		Medium		
Lack of a national strategy for sustainable urban mobility/ bike and pedestrian mobility		Medium	High		Medium	High		
Not developed infrastructure for recharging of EV	High			Medium	High	Medium		Medium
Range of distance travelled between charges for EVs	High			Medium				High
Limited funding/complex funding structures in urban public transport				High	High	High		
Lack of regular transport services in low density areas/smaller settlements		Low				High		Medium
Immature status of developing technologies for EVs/ULEVs	High					Low		High
Biofuel distribution and infrastructure	High					Low		High
Limited policy on freight efficiency/city logistics				Low		High		High
Lack of long-term vision on improvements/investments in transport infrastructure				High		Medium		
Contradicting policy goals and implementation/Focus on road networks			High	High				
Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations for EVs					Medium			Medium

Figure 18 Assessment of main institutional barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

2.2.4 COMPARISON OF KEY BARRIERS

As in the case of the building sector, the review of all national reports showed that not all partner countries are referencing the same number of barriers in energy efficiency in the transport sector, with some countries listing more than twenty-five barriers, with others listing less than fifteen. This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and it is not a direct result of the actual number of barriers encountered in the country. This finding is pointing to the fact that research on barriers in energy efficiency in the transport sector is not equally developed across all partners countries. As shown in Figure 19, research on barriers in energy efficiency in the transport sector is more developed in countries such as UK, Germany and Italy. Similar to the building sector, institutional barriers appear to be very important in the transport sector as well. However, social and cultural barriers appear to be even more prominent in the transport sector, especially in some countries, with issues such as habit, social norm and status playing a very important role. The total number of economic barriers appears to be similar across all partner countries.

Figure 19 Types of barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

Figure 20 shows the main common barriers, in all categories, that were identified across the eight partner countries. Cultural barriers rank very highly: ‘car as a status symbol’ is the most common as it is referenced by seven countries, followed by the ‘habit and social norm of driving’ and ‘low environmental concern’. However, economic barriers such as ‘lack of finance’ and ‘limited infrastructure investment’ are rated highest among the countries in terms of their impact on energy efficiency in transport (Figure 21). These are followed by institutional barriers such as ‘inefficient transport infrastructure’ and ‘not developed infrastructure for walking and cycling’. Educational barriers are also referenced by the majority of countries, with ‘lack of knowledge on green transport and EVs/ULEVs’ and ‘limited awareness of the impact of energy efficiency in transport’ being the most influential (Figure 21).

Figure 20 Main common barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

Figure 21 Qualitative assessment of main common barriers in the transport sector across all partner countries

CHAPTER 3: BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

In Estonia, energy savings in existing buildings is the main driving factor of building sector policy, since most of the building stock was constructed before any performance requirements were introduced and buildings make up around 50% of the total energy consumption. In addition, about 92% of the buildings built in 2005 will also remain in 2020, and about 75% out of these will probably remain even by 2050. Moving forward, building energy efficient houses\apartment blocks and other buildings is considered a crucial investment as the decisions taken today will remain for the next century. The situation is similar in other partner countries such as Serbia, Germany and the UK.

In addition, in many of the partner countries, fuel poverty is a significant driving factor in achieving energy efficiency. Fuel poverty is increasingly becoming an issue in Italy and energy costs are assuming a relevant weight in some parts of population.

The Serbian government's commitment to energy savings is a strong driver for implementation of energy efficiency measures and reduction of barriers impacts, because significant annual investments are expected in order to reach the target. Another main driving factor in Serbia is energy import dependency as it is seen that improvement of energy efficiency indirectly contributes to an increase of energy security. Also, reducing government spending is a main driver where the focus is on implementation of energy efficiency in the public sector as many public institutions are dilapidated and comfort in these buildings is extremely poor. The Main driver for energy efficiency in the residential sector is the need for adaptation. Old buildings are constructed using outdated materials and technology whose low efficiency has continued to decline. Significant parts of residential buildings require urgent refurbishment. Any kind of renovation (walls, roofs, windows, etc.) will at least slightly improve the efficiency of buildings, even if the works are not directed towards energy efficiency improvement. The need for refurbishment is based on an effort to maintain the property and improve living comfort.

To an extent all countries deal with at least some barriers in policy. In Estonia for example, all barriers are in one way or another discussed in current Estonian policy documents and political strategy documents. Yet they are mainly elaborated as barriers to be still solved or which are being slightly worked on, but not entirely solved.

In the Flemish region of Belgium the city regulation of protected facades (barrier to exterior insulation) has been removed. In response to split incentives, federal regulations restrict Belgian landlords in most cases from raising the rent after an energy efficiency investment, even if the tenant would agree with such an arrangement. Firstly, the investment would have to raise the value of the building by more than 10% to justify a raise in the rent. This is seldom the case for the type of energy efficiency investments the Belgian government (as of 2010) stimulates (low cost separate components, no deep retrofits). Secondly, the frequency with which the landlord is allowed to raise the rent is restricted to every three years.

In Estonia, in response to the knowledge barrier, "Energy Wise" (Energiatark) energy week has been implemented to inform the general public on energy efficiency principal questions and practical learning sessions: Each year during a week in November the entire country is informed via all communication channels about energy efficiency issues starting from kindergartens, schools and universities up to wider public. Many experienced specialists in the field give lectures, introducing novel EE appliances and present news on EE applications. The ongoing yearly event has gained high popularity. The organising team includes Kredex, AS Eesti Energia, SEI Tallinn Centre, Estonian Housing Association, Tartu Regional Energy Agency, Tallinn Energy Agency, Swedbank, et al.

In Germany the following barriers are considered in current policy packages: Length of payback period, high up-front costs and lack of capital, split incentives, technical/construction issues, and missing supply of qualified craft business and energy consultants.

In Italy the main key barriers to EE have been addressed by policy instruments. Social, cultural and educational barriers are mainly tackled through awareness raising campaigns. These are conducted by the national energy agency ENEA, as well as, at regional and local levels, by regional and local energy

agencies which are active in their respective territories. As an example, the issue of fragmentation of home ownership is being addressed by specific awareness raising campaigns, which aim to inform people living in condominiums about the possibilities and benefits to jointly renovate their homes. Regarding economic barriers, the Italian government has launched different economic policy instruments aimed at reducing the impact of economic barriers on energy efficiency improvements to buildings. In particular a set of three main economic policy instruments were launched, targeted to specific building owners (e.g. tax deduction mechanism targeted to families, Thermal Account targeted to national and regional/local public authorities and White Certificate mechanism to industrial and commercial buildings). Several awareness raising campaigns are in place to inform consumers about energy savings possibilities connected with energy renovation and the purchase of more energy efficient appliances, as well as a more virtuous use of appliances. Transparent billing is another policy measure serving this purpose and is being used as a tool to increase consumers' awareness and understanding, as well as combat misinformation and distrust of energy suppliers and fuel costs.

Furthermore, in Italy, since the economic crisis, access to credit from bank and financial institutions has been restricted, which can be among the enabling conditions of an energy renovation decision by families. However, policies such as the establishment of dedicated funds (Kyoto fund until 2014 and since 2015 the National Energy Efficiency Fund) have been put in place to ease access to financial resources for energy renovation interventions. Also, other economic policy measures such as tax deductions for energy renovations and purchasing of energy efficient appliances have been enacted, even if they target only specific parts of the population. Among the institutional barriers, the lack of suitable installers and technicians was highlighted, and in Italy is being addressed through dedicated awareness raising campaigns, as well as through specific training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings set up by ENEA.

In the UK the following barriers (to name a few) are targeted through a variety of policy instrument types including economic, regulatory, dissemination and awareness, promotion of R&D and Best Available Technologies (BATs): Undervaluing of EE/lack of interest, rebound effect, lack of information on energy use (all met through dissemination and awareness, e.g. smart metering programme), externalising responsibility and blame, lack of awareness/information (met through dissemination and awareness), capital costs, lack of funds/access to finance, payback expectation (formerly met through Green Deal and ECO) and additional costs/hidden costs, risk and uncertainty, costs of energy tariffs (met through dissemination and awareness, e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Committee on Climate Change Guidance, and Energy Savings Advice Service).

Table 21 lists the social, cultural, educational barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them in the building sector across all partner countries; Table 22 lists the institutional barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them for each country; and Table 23 lists the economic barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them in the building sector across all partner countries.

Table 21 Social, cultural, educational barriers and policies in the building sector

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Lack of interest/Low priority/Undervaluing energy efficiency	No specific policy instruments address this directly	SEAP (Covenant of Mayors), Local/Regional action plans	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Promotion of energy management systems 	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c) Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal • Dissemination and awareness/informative e.g. Smart Metering implementation programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme (CRC) • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. the community energy strategy and community energy efficiency outreach programme
	Social group interactions and status considerations	No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Seal of quality efficiency house • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Energy performance certificate 	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Awareness raising campaigns.	Rulebooks on the labelling of energy-related products (refrigerating appliances, washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, electric bulbs and lamps, TVs, air-conditioning devices) Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal	No specific policy instruments address this directly

								measure in NEEAP)	
Socio-Economic status of building users	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly	Awareness raising campaigns.	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Decent Homes Standard, Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Warm Front
Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing		National Programme for Energy Renovation of Multi-family Residential Buildings, Structural funds	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Low income of aged people		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly					
Commitment and motivation of public						No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly
Inertia		No specific policy instruments address this directly				The MEECC in an effort to ensure that at least the minimum requirements are indeed secured proceeded with the implementation of the Energy Performance Certificate (see Ministerial Decisions and Presidential Degrees of year 2010 (Table 1 of this report) (Deliverables of WP1, D.1.1, D.1.2). These efforts concern the building sector as a whole and not only the sub-sector of Hotels from which the barrier was mentioned.		<p>Rulebooks on the labelling of energy-related products (refrigerating appliances, washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, electric bulbs and lamps, TVs, air-conditioning devices)</p> <p>Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)</p> <p>Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Greening Government Commitments (GGC) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Carbon Trust Measures and the Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Feed-in Tariffs (FITs)
Rebound effect			No specific policy instruments address this directly						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Smart Metering and Billing, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and

									Display Energy Certificates (DECs)
	Expectations for electricity prices to remain low in future							No specific policy instruments address this directly	
Cultural	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Companies' policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)	<p>Various regulations set under the Building Act:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009. - The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68). <p>In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.</p>		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. regional and community level energy efficiency schemes (Climate Challenge Fund, Low Carbon Communities Challenge, NEST) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Big Energy Saving Week
	Bounded rationality/Visibility of energy efficiency	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Rulebooks on the labelling of energy-related products (refrigerating appliances, washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, electric bulbs and lamps, TVs, air-conditioning devices)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EPCs and DECs, Smart Metering and Billing, EcoDesign and Labelling Directives
	Missing credibility/Mistrust of technologies and contractors				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Energy performance certificate • Seal of quality efficiency House • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs 	No specific policy instruments address this directly		<p>Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)</p> <p>Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. National products policy (tranches 1& 2), Ecodesign regulations and Directives, quality assurance labels • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES), Market Transformation Programme • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Green Deal training and certification for assessors/installers • <i>Promotion of energy</i>

									services e.g. Quality Assurance labels, best practice guides
Educational	Training and skills of professionals	No specific policy instruments address this directly	National policy framework on EE, Local/Regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No policy instrument is addressing this barrier yet. The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU is expected to temper the extent of the barrier.	Dedicated training courses and information campaigns.	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Energy Technologies Institute, facilities and management apprenticeship funding, Green Deal Training and Certification for Assessors/installers • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB funded innovation programmes, Low Carbon Buildings Programme
	Lack of trusted information, knowledge and experience		National policy framework on EE, Local/Regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)	Different state funded trainings by MEAC and KredEx Barrier addressed in the draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030 +)		This barrier was encountered for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) the Directives for nZEB and EPBD. Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.		Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Labelling Directive • <i>Dissemination and awareness/informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Energy Savings Advice Service, Committee on Climate Change Guidance • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. One Stop Shop, peer-to-peer mentoring
	Lack of awareness on savings potential				No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier. This is a barrier concerns the National policy for energy efficiency as a total. No specific policy		No specific policy instruments address this directly

						instrument is currently implemented to address the barrier.			Trust, Open Homes Network, Energy Savings Advice Service
	Lack of knowledge/Information gap on technologies	No specific policy instruments address this directly		The educational programmes thanks to EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\KIK) financial support. The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered (energy audits, trainings and consultations). Establishment of the smart energy network data portal Estfeed (http://estfeed.ee/en/) as one of the actions taken under the strategy of "Estonia 2020". Regulations set under the Building Act: -The issuing and formulation requirements of energy audit of the buildings (04.04.2014 nr.16)	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EcoDesign Directives and Regulations, EPCs and DECs • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Open Homes Network • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Energy Technologies Institute, facilities and management apprenticeship funding • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB funded innovation programmes, Low Carbon Buildings Programme

Table 22 Institutional barriers and policies

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Split Incentive	No specific policy instruments address this directly	National policy framework on EE	Establishment of Flat ownership and co-operative flat law (19.02.2014), to be put on effect on 01.01.2018 (KrtS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Inspections of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Heating cost regulation • Seal of quality efficiency House • Energy Performance Certificate 	It was a barrier for the Energy Building Certificate. After the public consultancy for Directive 2012/27/EU there may be relevant provisions in the new Law.	Definition of ESCOs	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Landlords Energy Saving Allowance (LESA)
Complex/Inadequate regulatory procedures		National policy framework on EE (as a whole)	<p>European Commission Green Public Procurement Toolkit (GPP) 2008 - http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/toolkit_en.htm</p> <p>Instruction Materials on green public procurement by the Estonian Ministry of Environment - http://www.envir.ee/et/trukised-ja-artiklid-keskkonnahoidlike-hangete-teemal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Saving Ordinance • Heating Cost Regulation 	National policy for energy efficiency (as a total)	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly
Lack of relevant legislation/Lack of regulatory provision		No specific policy instruments address this directly			This is a persistent barrier that has been identified in two cases: i) EXOIKONOMO (subsidies) and ii) incorporation of the new Directive about EPBD and energy standards. As aforementioned there was a second public consultancy for the second one. No actions are foreseen for this barrier.	Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures, Reforms to increase efficiency in the public administration	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (EPBD), EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED), Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Planning and Energy Act 2008, Low Carbon Transition Plan, Home Energy Conservation Act, Decent Homes Standard, Energy Act 2011
Building stock characteristics/Agin g stock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy renovation programme 2020; • Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD); • Energy Performance Certificate (EPC). 		<p>The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its funding programmes.</p> <p>The draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 +,</p>		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i>

			(ENMAK 2030 +). Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107)				e.g. TSB research funding, Energy Technology Institute
Technical problems/ Performance Gap				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy Performance Certificates • Heating cost regulation • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring • BAFA cross-cutting technologies • Competence centre for public buildings • Low energy buildings project and efficiency house plus • Research initiative Zukunft Bau and Research for energy-optimised construction • 6th energy research programme 	No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB research funding, Energy Technology Institute
Missing support chanis/Skills and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flemish support for energy consultants; • Employment-Environment Alliance; • Exemplary buildings contest; • The facilitator network; • Milieu- en technologie Innovatie Platform (MIP); • Programme Mobilisateur ENERGYWALL 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW construction monitoring • Energy checks • On-side energy consultation • Promotion of energy management systems • Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants 		<p>ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. funding for facilities/management apprenticeships, funding for energy efficiency training, Green Deal Training and Certification • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Model Energy Performance Contracts and best practice guides, quality assurance labels • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, TSB and Innovate UK

								research programmes
Policy coordination across different levels//Co-operation between municipalities	No specific policy instruments address this directly		After joining the Covenant of Mayors Act, Estonian cities Rakvere and Tallinn have submitted their sustainable energy action plans to EU. Such actions could indirectly help to increase co-operation between local governments.		No specific policy instruments address this directly	Energy efficiency control room" (Cabina di Regia efficienza energetica)		
Lack of data/information		Statistics Act	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Energy Technology Institute (incl. Energy system modelling environment (ESME)), CHP Development Map, National Heat Maps and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Technology Innovation Needs Assessment, TSB Future Energy Management in Buildings Programme, Invest in Innovative Refurbishment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres
Inadequate implementation network/governance framework					It was identified for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) EXOIKONOMO (subsidies). No proposals so far.		<p>Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c)</p> <p>Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination)(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 d)</p>	

Historical preservation		No specific policy instruments address this directly			Municipalities in cooperation with the respective Ministries are planning specific actions for historical and traditional buildings in the big urban centers (Municipality of Athens, 2014).			No specific policy instruments address this directly
Disruption /Hassle factor				No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly
Poor compliance with efficiency standards/ construction standards	No specific policy instruments address this directly				No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updated Building Regulations, Decent Homes Standard, Green Deal and ECO, Low Carbon Transition Plan, Greening Government Commitments (GGC), Home Energy Conservation Act, Energy Act 2011
Mismatch between policy and occupant reality				No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly
Inadequate implementation of policy measures/No compliance control				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding programmes for municipalities 	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division		National policy framework on EE (as a whole)			No specific policy			
Security of fuel supply			Grants programmes by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre, KIK.					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Low Carbon Transition Plan, EU Directives, Renewable Energy Strategy, Energy Act 2011, Planning and Energy Act 2008 • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Carbon capture storage (CCS) commercialisation competition, Re:FIT National Programme, UREF and RCEF, Scottish District Heating Loan Fund • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Peer-to-peer

								community energy mentoring scheme, community energy strategy • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Time to Connect Incentive for DNOs, Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs, best practice guides to energy performance contracting • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. CHP development map, National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Advanced Heat Storage Competition
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Table 23 Economic barriers and policy instruments in the building sector across all partner countries

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Lack of Financial Incentive (Public and Private sector)		National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies	The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW energy-efficient construction • KfW energy efficient refurbishment • Energy tax • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • BAFA cross-cutting technologies 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Thermal Account ; · Tax deductions; · White Certificate (or Energy Efficiency Certificates) scheme and Obligation for national energy distributors; · Kyoto Fund; · National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”); · Measures for the energy efficiency in schools (“Misure per l’efficientamento energetico degli edifici scolastici”) (2015); · Plafond Casa (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti). Low 	Regulation on Programme of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c) Rulebook on conditions for allocation and use of Budget fund of Republic of Serbia for improvement energy efficiency and criteria for exemption from energy audit obligation (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 2014 h), Regulation on the amount of special fees for incentives in 2015 The Regulation on the method of calculation and the method of distribution of funds collected from the fees to stimulate privileged power producers Rulebook on determination of contract model for energy services of energy efficiency measures implementation in public sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Smart Metering and Billing, EPCs and DECs, EcoDesign regulation and directives • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering, Energy Savings Advice Service, Big Energy Saving Week, Market Transformation Programme, Green Economy Awards • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Government Buying Standards, Loans to SMEs (national and devolved governments), EU ETS Carbon Price Floor, Climate Change Agreements/Climate Change Levy, Green Deal Finance Company, Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs) and Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Stamp Duty Relief for Zero Carbon Homes
Lack of funds or access to finance	Federal personal income tax relief Financial incentives encouraging rational use of energy Energy renovation programme 2020 Property tax reduction Ecopack Primes énergies				The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU includes relevant provisions that are expected to support ESCOs.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF)
Payback expectations/Investment horizons				Seal of quality efficiency House • Energy saving ordinance • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • On-side energy	This barrier is one of the most persistent ones. It has been identified during the implementation of the: i) national policy for energy efficiency (as a total); ii) the efforts for implementing		Financial instruments (credit lines, subsidies, loans) are proposed by measure PC1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings in NEEAP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Government Buying Standards, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans

				consultation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring • KfW energy-efficient construction • KfW energy efficient refurbishment • Energy tax • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • BAFA cross-cutting technologies 	the two most recent Directives (for NZEB and EPBD; iii) Covenant of Mayors - SEAP).		The Regulation on the amount of special fees for incentives in 2015 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b) The Regulation on the method of calculation and the method of distribution of funds collected from the fees to stimulate privileged power producers (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b)	to SMEs, EU ETS Carbon Price Floor, Electricity Market Reform, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition, Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni’Fro (Wales), Enhanced Capital Allowances (ECA) incl. Energy Technology List, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)
Uncertainty on investment	No specific policy instrument	EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Open Homes Network, Community energy Advice Programme • Promotion of energy services e.g. RIIO ED1 Price Control model
High Capital costs/Financial Risk	Federal personal income tax relief Financial incentives encouraging rational use of energy Energy renovation programme 2020 Property tax reduction Ecopack Primes énergies		The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered.		The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU includes relevant provisions that are expected to support ESCOs.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni’Fro (Wales), Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Scottish District Heating Loan Fund
Economic status of building users			The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its		No specific policy instruments address this		Financial instruments (credit lines, subsidies,	No specific policy instruments address this

			<p>activities and services offered.</p> <p>Various regulations set under the Building Act: -Introduction of stricter building codes in the new buildings. Minimum energy performance requirements (30.08.2012 nr.68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.</p>		directly		<p>loans) are proposed by measure H1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in NEEAP. Still there is no policy instrument dedicated to household sector.</p>	directly
High cost of innovative technologies for end-users			Electricity Market Act		<p>This barrier was encountered for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) the Directives for nZEB and EPBD. Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Scottish District Heating Loan Fund, Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF), Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Boiler Replacement Scheme (Northern Ireland)
Relatively cheap energy and fuel prices		National regulatory framework on energy	<p>Various regulations set under the Building Act: Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009.</p>				No specific policy instruments address this directly	
Costs vary regionally (Fragmented ability)			The requirements of					

			<p>minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68)</p> <p>In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.</p> <p>Environmental Charges Act 01.01.2006 (KeTS)</p>					
Hidden costs	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Committee on Climate Change Guidance
Financial crisis/Economic stagnation		EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies			the following policy instruments are already affected and new planning is required: Covenant of Mayors – SEAP; Financial instruments; supporting mechanisms; subsidies; JESSICA initiative	Kyoto fund and Energy efficiency fund. Tax deductions Definition of ESCOs		
Embryonic markets					The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU includes relevant provisions that are expected to support ESCOs.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, Climate Change Levy/Climate change Agreements, Salix Finance Limited, the UK Green Investment Bank, Re:FIT national programme, Electricity Demand Reduction • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. publishing guidance on financing energy efficiency for the public sector • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. initiating an

								assessment of compatibility of energy efficiency investments with the public sector budgeting framework, innovation rollout mechanism, Technology Innovation Needs Assessments (TINAs), Green Business Awards
Tarrif sysetm not reflecting energy use/energy efficiency		National regulatory framework on energy					Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy to the consumers connected to district heating system (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Regulation on determination of heat energy price (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b)	

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

In Estonia the main driving forces for energy efficiency in both public and private transport are economic. Increasing fuel prices and increased demand for transport increases both private and public transport costs and energy saving is an important source for saving. Reducing dependence on oil and coping with volatile oil prices are one of the drivers also listed in the National Transport Development Plan 2014-2020. Social drivers are also significant – urbanization, aging population, changing attitudes of younger generation towards car ownership and urban lifestyle, quality of living environment, health issues related to sedentary and car based lifestyles, renaissance of cycling culture in the cities and high mobility of young international workforce tend to support more sustainable mobility patterns in Estonia. International commitments are important but not necessarily a main driver.

In Germany the European CO₂-fleet emission limit for passenger cars and light duty vehicles is an important driver for the development and deployment of energy-efficient vehicles. Regarding alternative fuels and drive trains the EU directive “Clean Power for Transport” and the “Fuel quality directive” also have an important influence on domestic activities. In addition, investments in R&D and demonstration of electric vehicles are also driven by the objective to strengthen the domestic automobile industry and to achieve an international leading position as a supplier of electric vehicles. As road transport relies heavily on oil, diversification of the fuel mix to become less dependent on imports can be seen as an additional driving factor. Congestion relief in inner cities as well as on inter-regional routes and freight corridors is an additional driver for shifting trips to more efficient modes. Finally, on an individual public opinion level the main drivers of transport mode choice (Annex 4) are flexibility (75%), travel time (52%), punctuality (51%), comfort (47%), availability (44%) and costs (43%). Environmental protection and GHG emission mitigation were only rated 21%. To add to this, value for money is named by 61% as an important criterion in vehicle purchasing decisions.

In Serbia the main driving factors for achieving energy efficiency in the transport sector are as follows: Environmental impact, e.g. air quality, noise, climate change, water quality, soil quality, etc.; introduction of biofuels; global oil price; comfort; travel time; and cost of travel. Lack of appropriate transport infrastructure, driving culture, image of public transport and cycling, lack of fiscal incentives and capacity building are barriers that are being addressed by current Serbian policy measures.

Italian transport EE barriers (promotion of green vehicles, bio fuels, ITS, coordination among different logistics operators) have been addressed by central government-led policy instruments in place, supported by regional and local public authorities. Other barriers instead (mainly related to the strengthening of personal and freight transport infrastructures) received less attention in the Italian policies framework. Social, cultural and educational barriers are mainly tackled through awareness raising campaigns. In order to overcome the main economic barriers, ‘slowing down the renewal of Italian car fleets’, the Italian government established a wide set of subsidies supporting the purchasing of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), methane and electric vehicles. In addition, technical barriers to a nationwide dissemination of EVs/ULEVs (linked mainly to poor refuel/recharge infrastructures) were tackled by the Italian government through a national plan for the promotion of the methane infrastructures in Italian urban areas and by a plan and a set of funds dedicated to set up a wider national network of electric vehicles charging points.

In the Italian freight transport sector, the government set a national logistics platform (called UIRNET) which enables the sharing of information and data among logistic operators. Technical and technological barriers in the freight transports, related mainly to the scarce diffusion of EVs/ULEVs in the logistic sector, have been tackled by a plan to set up a national network of electric vehicles charging points.

In the UK the following barriers (to name a few) are targeted through a variety of policy instrument types including economic, regulatory, dissemination and awareness, promotion of R&D and Best Available Technologies (BATs): Marginalisation of cycling culture, limited understand of environmental impact, immature status of developing technologies, limited car-sharing initiatives, high purchase price and long payback, and Limited financial incentives for freight efficiency.

Table 24 lists the social, cultural, educational barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them in the transport sector across all partner countries; Table 25 lists the institutional barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them for each country; and Table 26 lists the economic barriers and corresponding policies seeking to combat them in the transport sector across all partner countries.

Table 24 Social, cultural and educational barriers and policies across all partner countries

	Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GR	IT	RS	UK
Social	Low satisfaction with public transport/Lack of trust		No specific policy instruments address this directly	Renewal of public transport vehicle fleet (all passenger train fleet renewed in 2013, new trams and buses), reconstruction of railways (increased speeds) awareness raising campaigns, dedicated bus lanes in Tallinn. Free public transport in Tallinn. Public transport campaigns.		No specific policy instruments address this directly	HighAwareness campaigns, Voluntary urban mobility plans (PUMS), National funds for local public transports	No specific policy instruments address this directly	
	Concerns on vehicle reliability of EVs/ULEVs/Hesitation to trust new technologies	No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling; • CO2-related motor vehicle tax; • “me and my car” campaign; • “new driving” campaign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal funding programme for energy efficient commercial vehicles to be launched in 2016 (BMW 2014c) 			No specific policy instruments address this directly
	Bounded rationality /Buyer attitude				No specific policy instruments address this directly			Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme is T2 measure in NEEAP.	No specific policy instruments address this directly
	Heterogeneity of consumers	No specific policy instruments address this directly						Foreseen instruments are targeted public information campaigns and Training and Education.	No specific policy instruments address this directly
	Suburbanisation trends/Low density				Better integration of transport and land use planning, encouraging more compact development – currently generally weak tools to enforce this policy. Planning guidance is being worked out in the Min of Interior.	No specific policy instruments address this directly			
	Vulnerability of pedestrians/Insufficient safety, lack of adequate space for walking					No specific policy instruments address this directly		Urban Traffic Plans, Voluntary urban mobility plans (PUMS)	
	Cruising traffic /						This is a persistent	Codice della strada,	

	Parking problems					barrier of local scale (big urban centers face it). It is not only a barrier for the national policy for energy efficiency, but also of the and transportation policy. Several efforts have been examined and applied that have restricted partially the problem. The Municipality of Athens is planning such actions (informative signs, Digital Athens etc) (Municipality of Athens, 2014).	Urban Traffic Plans		
	Inertia							Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme is T2 measure in NEEAP. Foreseen instruments are targeted public information campaigns and Training and Education.	No specific policy instruments address this directly
	Attitude-action gap	Certificate of professional competence (eco-driving)							No specific policy instruments address this directly
Cultural	Car as a symbol status and group influence	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National funding for the campaign "head on: engine off" targeting short distance travel Local campaigns (e.g. "cycling capital" Munich) 	No specific policy instruments address this directly		Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme is T2 measure in NEEAP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and Development e.g. Government funding to support new generation of ULEVs
	Habit and social norm of driving, car ownership and use			Increase of fuel excise duty; decreasing VAT reimbursement rate and procedures for company cars; proposal of energy labelling scheme for cars (to come into force 2016). Electro-mobility program.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentives for climate-friendly mobility in the federal administration aimed at the increased use of public transport Mobility management programmes 	There are no provisions for old drivers in the legislation for eco-driving (Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)	National programmes and funds aimed to improve public transport services, Road taxation, Awareness campaigns	Foreseen instruments are targeted public information campaigns and Training and Education.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory policy e.g. Eco-driving training included in national driving tests Dissemination and awareness e.g. Fuel Good driver training Economic e.g. Congestion Charges
	Environmental concern/Lack of 'green transport behaviour'/Low priority	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier. Proposals from municipalities (zones for	Awareness campaigns, National plan for Green Procurement (public administrations)	No specific policy instruments address this directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory e.g. EU Energy Efficiency Directive, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme

						cycling and walking) might assist in improving the situation (Municipality of Athens).			(ESOS) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for cars • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants, company car tax reform	
	Cycling is marginalised			Plans for bicycle share schemes in 5 cities, new cycle infrastructure in city centres, awareness raising campaigns (European Cycling Challenge 2012-2015).			Awareness campaigns, Voluntary urban mobility plans (PUMS) National events		• <i>Economic</i> e.g. Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. The National Standard for cycle training	
Educational	Lack of knowledge/information on green transport/ULEVs/Evs	No specific policy instruments address this directly	National policy on EE in transport sector		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax benefits for natural and liquid gas; • Tax exemption for electric vehicles, • Federal funding programme for energy efficient commercial vehicles to be launched in 2016 (BMW 2014c) 	No policy instrument is addressing specifically this barrier apart from the financial incentives that are mentioned (Table 1 of this report).		Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)	No specific policy instruments address this directly	
	Limited awareness of impact of EE in transport (ULEVs,eco-driving, etc.)		No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	• <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for car	
	Consumer understanding and use of fuel economy information				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax benefits for natural and liquid gas; • Tax exemption for electric vehicles, 			No specific policy instruments address this directly	• <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for car	
	Confusion about car and fuel costs (conventional vs ULEVs/EVs)				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling; • CO2-related motor vehicle tax; • “me and my car” campaign; • “new driving” campaign 				No specific policy instruments address this directly	
	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving						No specific policy instruments address this directly			
	Low public awareness towards eco-driving						There are no provisions for old drivers in the			

						legislation for eco-driving (Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)			
	Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals			Promoting co-operation between universities, authorities and businesses for common curriculum on planning. R&D program for energy efficient transport planned. Smart City cluster					
	Lack of trained technicians for ULEVs/EVs								No specific policy instruments address this directly

Table 25 Economic barriers and policies in the transport sector across all partner countries

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GK	IT	RS	UK
Lack of finance for new vehicles/ULEVs/public transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax exemptions for home workplace biking Tax • exemptions inland navigation • Green car registration Tax • Commuter fund • Ecotax 	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal transport financing act and regionalisation act: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities 	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Introduction of incentive mechanisms (subsidies - grants, loans, etc.) for replacement of the existing vehicles are foreseen as T3 measure in NAPEE. Also, measure T5 - Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance foreseen voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (procurement, energy-efficient public procurement technology, commercial and institutional voluntary agreement) as mechanisms for overcoming these barriers.	

Limited infrastructure investment (road/train/cycling)		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	National funds for local public transports		• <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-In Places (PIP) programme
Low purchasing power of citizens/Financial crisis		No specific policy instruments address this directly			This is linked with the economic recession and any recommendations need to be part of an integrated policy planning.	No specific policy instruments address this directly	Introduction of incentive mechanisms (subsidies - grants, loans, etc.) for replacement of the existing vehicles are foreseen as T3 measure in NAPEE. Also, measure T5 - Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance foreseen voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (procurement, energy-efficient public procurement technology, commercial and institutional voluntary agreement) as mechanisms for overcoming these barriers.	
High Cost/Low cost competitiveness of electric vehicles				• R&D funding for electric vehicles,	No specific policy instruments address this directly			• <i>Economic</i> e.g. The Plug-in car and van grants
Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles				• CO2-related motor vehicle tax				• <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants
High cost of batteries for electric vehicles						Subsidies for the purchase of low-emissions vehicles		No specific policy instruments address this directly
Inefficient or absent fiscal measures			No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly				
Limited financial incentives for electric vehicles		National Action Plan on Climate Change					No specific policy instruments address this directly	
Low population density/Urban sprawl			Planning guidance being developed by Ministry of Interior; National Spatial Development Plan 2030+.			No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Investment schemes do not encourage			Increasing fuel excise duty, government considering	No specific policy instruments address this		National funds for local public transports		

transport EE			other transport taxation alternatives (road charging, car taxation). Decreasing the VAT reimbursement rate for company cars. EV support scheme ELMO (purchase of EV-s, quick-charging stations, EV rent and taxis).	directly				
Tax free/low tax company car schemes			No specific policy instruments address this directly					

Table 26 Institutional barriers and policies in the transport sector across all partner countries

Barrier	BE	BG	EE	DE	GK	IT	RS	UK
Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance			Public transport centres created in a number of counties to better coordinate regional level PT. Common information system for all Estonian PT providers – Common ticket payment system (contactless card) for Tallinn city and Harju county	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of different transport association and introduction of a state wide tariff e.g. by the state of North Rhine-Westphalia 	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	
Transport EE on the Government Agenda		No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	
Inefficient urban/public transport infrastructure and planning		Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015, Local/Regional Mobility Plans, National Action Plan on Climate Change	National spatial development plan Estonia 2030+ stresses the importance of rail network as a backbone for regional and national mobility. Enforcement weak due to relatively weak influence on private property developers.	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		

			Ministry of Interior is working on planning guidance for integrating land use and transport planning. Investment scheme for multi-modal access to rail stations facilitates the development of areas close to rail stations.					
Not developed cycling/walking infrastructure		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No long-term investment plan for public transport and cycling. New schemes on investment for integrated solutions in urban areas/railway stations, county centres. Green Investment Schemes.		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Financial</i> e.g. Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Transport for London (TfL) and London Cycling Campaign (LCC) community bicycling project • <i>Planning</i> e.g. Development of London Bicycling Network since 2000
Lack of support for rail transportation/Limited rail infrastructure		Strategy For The Development Of The Transport Infrastructure Of The Republic Of Bulgaria By 2015	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Lack of a national strategy for sustainable urban mobility/ bike and pedestrian mobility		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Limited funding/complex funding structures in urban public transport				No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly	No specific policy instruments address this directly		
Lack of regular transport services in low density areas/smaller settlements		No specific policy instruments address this directly				No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly
Immature status of developing technologies for Evs/ULEVs	No specific policy instruments address this directly					No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Renewable Energy Directive • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Government’s strategy for ultra-low emission vehicles (ULEVs) ‘Driving the Future Today’, funding for

								advanced biofuel research
Not developed infrastructure for recharging of EV	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy) • <i>Dissemination and awareness instruments</i> e.g. The National Charge point Registry (NCR)
Biofuel distribution and infrastructure	No specific policy instruments address this directly					No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Low Carbon HGV Technology Taskforce, Government funding for advanced biofuel research
Limited policy on freight efficiency/city logistics				No specific policy instruments address this directly		No specific policy instruments address this directly		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle band, EU Directives (low rolling resistance tyres, LGV emissions targets and complementary measures) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme
Lack of long-term vision on improvements/investments in transport infrastructure				No specific policy instruments address this directly		Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020		
Contradicting policy goals and implementation/Focus on road networks			No implicit policy. R&D program planned for transport energy efficiency. SUMP network of experts and cities	No specific policy instruments address this directly				
Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations for Evs					No specific policy instruments address this directly			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Low Carbon Emissions Zones (regional/local authority)
Range of distance travelled between charges for Evs	No specific policy instruments address this directly			No specific policy instruments address this directly				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. £82 million of research and development funding has

								now been committed to support the new generation of ULEVs
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CHAPTER 4: KEY FINDINGS

This report presents the cross analysis of the social, economic, cultural, institutional and educational barriers to energy efficiency progress in the building and transport sectors for all eight HERON partner countries. The main barriers for each country are identified to provide valuable insights; overcoming such barriers is the key challenge for EE policies. Barriers to energy efficiency are vast and complex, and are usually inter-related. Scaling up energy efficiency requires energy consumers to modify their behaviour in relation to both energy consumption and equipment investment. Several factors influence these behaviours, including: country specific incentive structures, consumer preferences, rules and regulations, decision-making practices and cultural considerations (Golove and Eto, 1996). The following section summarizes the key findings identified through the analysis of the national reports on barriers in energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors.

It should be noted, that the review of national reports showed that there are discrepancies between the number of barriers identified in each of the partner countries in both the building and the transport sectors. This is considered to be due to the lack of relevant literature and does not absolutely reflect the number of barriers encountered in the country. Instead, this finding is pointing to the fact that research on barriers in energy efficiency in buildings and transport is not equally developed across all partners countries, which could in turn hinder the effective implementation of policies.

3.3 KEY FINDINGS ON BARRIERS IN ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

- Institutional barriers appear to be the most important type of barrier, followed by economic ones. However, social, cultural and educational barriers are also very significant, making up nearly half of the total number of barriers identified in each country.
- The cultural barrier of ‘undervaluing energy efficiency’ and the institutional barrier of ‘split incentives’, are the most common as they are reported by all countries:
 - Undervaluing energy efficiency is a complex barrier that is related to aspects such as lack of knowledge, inertia and habit. Behavioural aspects linked to social norms and habits are a major barrier across the majority of the countries. This refers to social norms and expectations requiring carbon-dependent lifestyles.
 - The most cited institutional barrier, that of ‘split incentives’, refers mainly to the ‘landlord-tenant split’, which applies to most cases (UK, Serbia, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Bulgaria). In the cases of Greece, Estonia and Germany, this barrier also appears where there are multiple owners and/or occupiers of buildings.

- Barriers such as ‘habits and behaviour’ (cultural) and ‘building stock characteristics’ (institutional) also rank highly in terms of their impact.
- The economic barrier of ‘high capital costs and financial risk’ ranks highest amongst most countries in terms of its impact on energy efficiency in buildings. High capital costs/financial risk received the highest barrier rating among a majority of countries. To add to the high capital cost, financial risk is compounded due to the high interest rates of bank loans (Bulgaria, Greece, Serbia and the UK).
- Economic barriers such as ‘access to finance’ and ‘lack of financial incentives’ are also among the top common barriers identified:
 - ‘Lack of financial incentive’s among the countries are found in a number of areas, e.g. in Italy and Belgium the concern is for the lack of incentives for building owners that rent buildings as they do not reap the energy savings and renters of buildings as they do not own the improvements but only pay the bills. In general other countries see a lack of incentives as a notable barrier to EE improvements or projects.
 - In Belgium, Estonia, Greece, Italy, Serbia and the UK lack of funds or access to finance is also a significant barrier. Lack of funds or access to finance can relate to inability to find a loan for a system or renovation because the funding agent will not back the investment (reluctance to contract a loan).
 - In some countries, such as Italy and Greece, the economic stagnation or strain has created a condition where credit is difficult to access; limiting EE investments.
- ‘Complex and/or inadequate regulatory procedures’, reported by seven countries, are cited as a major barrier in the case of Bulgaria where long administrative procedures and frequent change of the regulatory framework often prevent investments. Similar issues, related to bureaucracy, were reported in Italy, Serbia and Greece.
- The ‘building stock characteristics’ are cited as a barrier by five countries, and rank highly in terms of impact. This barrier refers to the limitations that the building structure itself imposes on residents, for example in the physical space available in the building, the age, the lack of cavity walls, poorly installed windows, or unsuitable roofs. Aging stock is cited as a major barrier in Estonia, Greece, Italy and the UK.
- ‘Poor compliance with efficiency and construction standards’ is cited as a major barrier in Belgium, Greece and the UK. This is closely linked to quality of workmanship and the educational barrier of ‘training and skills’ of professionals. This issue is also linked with the problem of the ‘performance gap’ that refers to the discrepancy between the design and actual performance of buildings as a result of poor fabric or system performance.

3.4 KEY FINDINGS ON BARRIERS IN ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

- Similar to the building sector, institutional barriers appear to be very important in the transport sector as well. However, social and cultural barriers appear to be even more prominent in the transport sector, especially in some countries, with issues such as habit, social norm and status playing a very important role. The total number of economic barriers appears to be similar across all partner countries.
- Cultural barriers rank very highly across all countries: ‘car as a status symbol’ is the most common as it is referenced by seven countries, followed by the ‘habit and social norm of driving’ and ‘low environmental concern’. ‘Car as a status symbol’ was reported as a major barrier in Belgium, Bulgaria and Greece, where for many people owning and driving a private car represents a certain status and lifestyle and is considered a symbol of comfort and freedom. Similarly, the ‘habit and social norm of driving’ is considered a major barrier in Greece and Germany.
- ‘Limited environmental concern and low priority’ is a common barrier in the improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector across most countries. Studies reveal that when it comes to car purchasing, environmental issues have a very low priority for private and fleet consumers
- ‘Limited awareness of impact of energy efficiency’ in the transport sector was reported as a major barrier in Bulgaria, Greece and Serbia. This issue is related to the public perception that energy efficiency is not a priority and is linked with limited knowledge and understanding of environmental impacts, cost structures and fuel use.
- The most common social barrier is the low satisfaction with public transport, reported in Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece, Italy and Serbia. In the cases of Bulgaria and Italy, this was reported as a major barrier, as it includes elements such as the perception of public transport as unsafe, more time consuming and less flexible than private means of transport.
- Economic barriers such as ‘lack of finance’ and ‘limited infrastructure investment’ are rated highest among the countries in terms of their impact on energy efficiency in transport.
 - Lack of finance for new efficient vehicles is the most cited barrier; also cited as most important in most countries. In Belgium, Germany, Greece and Italy ULEVs are more expensive to purchase and own than conventional vehicles (also with little-no financial assistance) acting as a barrier for take-up.
 - In Germany the lack of finance also exists for more efficient public transport on a local authority level. In Bulgaria and Serbia a majority of the population do not have access to finance or purchasing power for LEVs.

- ‘Limited infrastructure investment’ is rated as highly significant by all countries which cited it. In Bulgaria the infrastructural problems are related to the lack of road improvements and the negative impact this has on the efficiency performance of vehicles. In Estonia there is a disproportionate level of investment in road infrastructure; supporting private automobile travel over public transport. Similarly, in Germany allocation/prioritization of funding for *mega-projects* is jeopardizing the development of sustainable transport and likely near-future UK policy is similar.
- Institutional barriers such as ‘inefficient transport infrastructure’ and ‘not developed infrastructure for walking and cycling’ are very common among the majority of partner countries.
- A key barrier to the uptake of electric vehicles, commonly cited across most national reports, is the lack of developed infrastructure for recharging. In the case of EVs, similar concerns such as the time needed to recharge the vehicles, the vehicle range between charges, and the unclear traffic road regulations concerning EVs were also cited.
- Limited focus on the development of infrastructure for walking and cycling was reported as a major barrier in Bulgaria, Estonia and Italy and the UK.
- ‘Lack of integrated governance and administrative fragmentation’ appear to be a very common problem in the transport sector and is reported in Estonia, Germany, Greece, Italy and Serbia. In the cases of Germany and Estonia, responsibility for public transport is divided between the municipal, regional and national authorities, leading to different tariff structures, scattered information and non-integrated service schedules. Similarly, in Greece more than one authority is responsible for planning and operation of public transport in large urban centre.
- In Bulgaria, Estonia, Germany and Greece, inefficient transport infrastructure and planning is considered a major barrier in the development of energy efficiency in the transport sector. In the cases of Greece and Bulgaria, the infrastructure and planning for urban transport is not effective in displacing car dominance and diminish congestion related problems. In the cases of Germany and Estonia, car focused planning and the extension of the road infrastructure contradicts the implementation of the respective energy efficiency strategies proposed by the national transport strategy of each country.
- Regarding the diffusion of Electric vehicles (EVs) and Ultra low emission vehicles (ULEVs), the most important barrier, that ranked highly among the majority of countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Serbia, UK), is the ‘lack of knowledge and information’ on these new technologies. In the UK, a lack of knowledge about EVs was identified as one of the main barriers to EV take-up.

ANNEXES

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ANNEX 2 NATIONAL REPORT OF BULGARIA

ANNEX 3 NATIONAL REPORT OF ESTONIA

ANNEX 4 NATIONAL REPORT OF GERMANY

ANNEX 5 NATIONAL REPORT OF GREECE

ANNEX 6 NATIONAL REPORT OF ITALY

ANNEX 7 NATIONAL REPORT OF SERBIA

ANNEX 8 NATIONAL REPORT OF UNITED KINGDOM

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The housing stock in Belgium on average is old; and both demolition and renovation (retrofit) rates are low (below EU averages). Although both consumers (households) and supply side professionals in Belgium still lack considerable knowledge as far as energy efficiency measures and policy instruments are concerned, (qualitative) research seems to indicate that more or better knowledge has little or no effect on energy-related behaviour. On the other hand, social networks in Belgium matter a lot. Even the best advice of the most competent professional will not be accepted, if it is not corroborated by the opinions and experiences of relatives, friends, colleagues, ... (even if those networks are not as competent as they claim to be). The “attitude-action gap” is very real in Belgium. Households or individuals aware of energy-related and environmental issues (e.g. energy efficiency, renewables, climate change), or who claim to be, in general do not behave in more (or less) energy efficient ways than others. Energy efficiency has low priority, simply because households (even the environmentally aware ones) are much more attracted to other attributes of the products (be it dwellings or vehicles), such as thermal, visual and acoustic comfort, aesthetics, safety and health, ... – Last but not least, the financial barrier is real, especially for lower-income households. Although Belgium (or rather its regions) provide a large number of instruments to compensate the high initial investment costs, consumers are confused by the plethora of subsidies, premiums, tax rebates, etc.; or are simply not aware that they exist.

The most typical policy obstacle for Belgium is the extreme complexity of its state structure. Energy-related policies continuously overlap. Competences are very fragmented, not only between the federal state and the regions, but also between various authorities within the different regions. Attempts to improve coordination are rarely successful. The “sixth state reform”, in progress, is not likely to improve matters. The administrative burden to obtain subsidies is too high, and subsidies may not reach the right households. Energy-related taxes are low in Belgium, and do not provide much of an incentive. But households themselves clearly indicate that higher energy prices (internalisation of externalities) would steer them to more energy efficient behaviour. This should also be viewed from the perspective of Belgian stakeholders who see the multitude of subsidies more as “a tool of communication” rather than as an instrument to accomplish behavioural changes. Finally, the effectiveness of Belgian federal and regional energy-related policies is severely hindered by the lack of adequate monitoring and evaluation.

CHAPTER 1: CONTEXT

1.1 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

The Belgian institutional framework is made up of three regions (Flemish Region, Walloon Region, and Brussels-Capital Region) and three communities (Flemish Community, French speaking Community, and German-speaking Community), which do not have exactly the same competences.

Different competences related to energy policy have been allocated to the federal state and federated entities. Energy efficiency is with the regions.

There are specific advisory bodies to co-ordinate policies across governments, for example ENOVER / CONCERE (“Energieoverleg / Concertation État-régions pour l’énergie”), for discussions between federal government and regional governments over energy-related matters (including energy efficiency).

Belgian policies aiming at improving energy efficiency are to a large extent driven by guidelines decided at the EU level. Belgium’s contribution to the EU effort to improve energy efficiency are designed at the subnational level. There is no federal energy agency for energy efficiency. The federal government does intervene in setting standards and financing. There are thus de facto four Energy Efficiency Plans in Belgium, a national one and three regional.

Belgium is currently in the process of a new state reform aiming at transferring competences from the federal to the regional level (the so-called “sixth state reform”).

The following table gives an overview of the most relevant policy instruments for the building sector. If a region is not explicitly mentioned, assume federal.

Table 1: Overview of policy instruments for promoting energy efficiency in the building sector (Belgium).

Regulatory policy instruments	<u>Energy Performance Requirements (EPR)</u> . Different implementations of the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD) Directive in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels.
	<u>Energy Performance Certificates (EPC)</u> . Different implementations in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels.
	<u>Mandatory energy audit requirements</u> (Brussels). Not (yet fully) implemented in Flanders and Wallonia.
	<u>Heating audit</u> (Flanders).
Dissemination and awareness	<u>Energy guzzlers</u> (“ <i>Energivores / Energievreters</i> ”), website promoting energy efficient electrical appliances (federal and regional).
	“ www.energiesparen.be ”, reference website on energy efficiency in Flanders. Also part of policy package “ <i>Energie renovatie programma 2020</i> ” which includes dissemination of technical and financial information on energy efficiency (Flanders).
	<u>Energy desks Wallonia</u> (“ <i>Guichets Énergie Wallonie</i> ”), energy desks (Wallonia).
	<u>Energy House</u> (“ <i>Maison de l’énergie</i> ”) (www.maisonenergiehuis.be), also part of policy package COBRACE (Brussels)
Economic policy instruments	<u>Federal personal income tax relief</u> , tax break and maximum deductible amounts for roof insulation

	<p>Promotion of rational use of energy by electricity distribution companies as part of their public service obligation, different implementations of the “<i>Rational Use of Energy Public Service Obligations</i>” in Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels.</p>
	<p>Financial incentives encouraging rational use of energy (<i>RUE</i>). (federal and regional)</p>
	<p>Energy Renovation Programme 2020 (“<i>Energie renovatie programma 2020</i>”), policy package including premiums and tax deductions for retrofitting buildings (Flanders)</p>
	<p>Building renovation subsidy, subsidy accessible to owner-occupants with income below a certain limit for building renovation work, including energy efficiency improvements</p>
	<p>Property tax reduction, reduction of the so-called “<i>immovable withholding tax</i>” for new, energy-efficient builds (Flanders).</p>
	<p>“<i>Ecopack</i>”, interest free loans and subsidies for energy efficiency improvements (Wallonia)</p>
	<p>UREBA Subsidies to Improve Energy Efficiency of Public Buildings, (“<i>Rénovation énergétique des bâtiments UREBA</i>”), subsidies for Rational Use of Energy in public buildings</p>
	<p>Energy premiums (“<i>Primes énergies</i>”), subsidies for refurbishments of buildings (Wallonia and Brussels)</p>
	<p>Zero interest Brussels Green Loan (“<i>Prêt vert à taux zéro bruxellois</i>”), zero-rate ‘energy’ loan for energy efficiency investments (Brussels).</p>
Capacity building	<p>Flemish support programme for energy consultants, stimulating energy efficiency via consultancy (Flanders)</p>
	<p>Build Up Skills Belgium (Flanders and Wallonia), a consortium to improve construction workers’ skills</p>
	<p>Energ’ethic Communities (“<i>Commune Energy’éthiques</i>”), aimed at city counselors (Wallonia)</p>
	<p>Employment-Environment Alliance, an ‘alliance’ of actors in the field of “sustainable construction and renovation” (Wallonia and Brussels)</p>
	<p>Exemplary buildings (“<i>Bâtiments exemplaires</i>”), the ‘Exemplary Buildings’ call for proposals, an annual contest for design, construction or renovation of buildings, which have to meet (amongst other) strict energy efficiency standards (Brussels)</p>
	<p>Sustainable Building Facilitator Network (“<i>Facilitateur Bâtiment durable</i>”), energy specialists providing free-of-charge guidance to building managers of multi-family dwellings and non-residential buildings (Brussels)</p>
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<p>FEDESCO, third party investment in energy savings in public buildings</p>
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<p>Public Procurement Rules for Federal Administration and Public Services, 50% sustainable procurement procedures for all federal public procurements</p>

	“Milieu- en Energietechnologie-Innovatieplatform” (MIP), energy technology (Flanders)
	“Programme Mobilisateur ENERGYWALL”, R&D programme on energy efficiency and renewables (Wallonia)

The following table gives an overview of the most relevant policy instruments for the transport sector. If a region is not explicitly mentioned, assume federal.

Table 2: overview of policy instruments for the transport sector

Regulatory policy instruments	<u>Green Mobility Plan</u> , private or public bodies with more than 200 employees have to introduce transport planning (Brussels).
	<u>Action plan to promote use of public transport</u> , managers of events with more than 3000 participants have to introduce a transport plan to promote use of public transport (Brussels).
Dissemination and awareness	<u>CO₂ guide of the clean vehicle</u> (“CO ₂ gids van de schone auto / guide CO ₂ de la voiture propre / Der CO ₂ -Ratgeber des Sauberen Autos”), publication including advice on energy efficient driving.
	<u>www.ecoscore.be</u> , website with information on energy efficiency of cars (Flanders).
	<u>Provincial Mobility Desks</u> (“Provinciale mobiliteitspunten”), assisting and advising companies developing commuter plans (Flanders).
Economic policy instruments	<u>Fiscal benefits for commuting by bike</u> , tax exemptions for employers who pay their employees allowances for home-workplace bike journeys.
	<u>Fiscal benefits for commuting by car-pooling</u> , tax deductibility of home-work travel expenses when using car-pooling.
	<u>Deductibility under corporate tax of expenses related to the use of company cars</u> , the company car tax is based on CO ₂ emissions.
	<u>Tax exemptions for surplus value upon ship sale</u> , tax exemptions on capital gains made on the sales of inland waterway transport vessels.
	<u>80/20 system for public transport season tickets</u> . If employers pay 80% of the public transport season ticket price of their employees, the government pays the remaining 20%
	<u>Green car registration tax</u> (“Groene belasting op de inverkeerstelling, BIV”), registration tax based on CO ₂ emissions, exhaust emission standards, fuel and age of the car. (Flanders)
	<u>Flanders Commuter Fund</u> (“Pendelfonds”), a subsidy of max. 50% during 4 years if employers implement measures encouraging employees to use alternatives to the car (Flanders).
<u>Ecobonus-Ecomalus</u> (“éco-bonus, éco-malus”), bonus for the purchase of new, energy efficient vehicles (Wallonia)	

	<u>Bruxell'air premium</u> (" <i>La prime Bruxell'air</i> "), incentives for car owners returning their registration plate to the vehicle registration authority (Brussels).
Capacity building	<u>Eco-driving</u> , " <i>Certificate of professional competence</i> ", to promote eco-driving (federal, Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels-Capital)
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<u>"Retibo"</u> , research project to stimulate a more efficient and sustainable public transport system (federal, Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital)
	<u>Test project on passenger vehicles</u> , to analyse behaviour of vehicle use (federal, Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels-Capital)
	<u>Proeftuig elektrisch voertuig</u> , to support the introduction of electro-mobility (Flanders)

The main actors are listed below.

Federal:

- Federal Public Service of Economy, SMEs, Self-employed and Energy, DG Energy
- Federal. Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment, Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section.
- Federal. Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment, Department of Product Policy and Chemical Substances
- Federal Public Service of Finance

Flemish region

- Flemish government
- Flemish Energy Agency (VEA)
- Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE)
- Flemish Tax Agency

Walloon region

- Walloon government
- le Cabinet du Ministre en charge de l'Énergie (Wallonia)
- Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building
- Ministry of Environment
- La Société wallonne du crédit social
- Le Fonds du logement de la Wallonie

Brussels-Capital region

- Government of the Brussels-Capital Region
- "Le Ministre bruxellois de la Mobilité et des Travaux publics de la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale" / "Brusselse Minister van Mobiliteit en Openbare Werken van het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest
- Bruxelles Environnement, i.e Brussels Institute for Environmental Management (IBGE-BIM)
- Regional Energy Fund (Brussels)

Other :

- Scientific and Technical Centre for the Building industry (*“Wetenschappelijk and Technisch Centrum voor the Bouwbedrijf , WTCB)*,
- Building Industry Professional Training Fund (*“Fonds voor Vakopleiding in de Bouwnijverheid”*, fvb-ffc Constructiv)

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Building codes are the responsibility of the three regions.

1.1.1.1 Energy Performance Requirements (EPR) (Flemish region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Flemish Region. Flemish government. Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE).
- Implemented 2006, in force 2009.
- Energy performance obligations in general differ depending on the nature and use of the building, the construction measures (existing and new buildings), and the date of issuing the building permit. A minimum share of energy must come from renewable energy sources (e.g. PV or solar boiler) as of 1 January 2013 for schools and offices; and as of 1 January 2014 for residential buildings. The Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEB) 2020 target is introduced for new and existing residential and non-residential buildings as of 2015.

1.1.1.2 Energy Performance Requirements (EPR) (Walloon region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Walloon Region. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building
- Implemented 2007, in force 2008.
- The energy performance requirements depend on the building type, and covers the building envelope (U-values, global insulation level), the global Energy Performance rating [the primary energy consumption of the building (E_w); the specific energy consumption of the building (E_{spec})], and ventilation and overheating ratings. The requirements were tightened in September 2009 and June 2012.

1.1.1.3 Energy Performance Requirements (EPR) (Brussels-Capital Region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Brussels-Capital Region.
- Implemented 2007, in force 2008.
- The energy performance requirements depend on the building type and take into account amongst others the primary energy consumption, insulation level and the ventilation rate. In May 2011, new requirements were enforced regarding individual houses, offices and educational buildings. The Decree of February 2013 strengthens the requirements for thermal insulation for the renovation of buildings whose application for a planning permission is submitted from 1 January 2014 onwards. Starting January 2015, new construction of houses, schools and offices need requirements comparable to the Passivhaus concept.

The decree on the energy certification of buildings (rules and rating method) was issued by the Belgian government in 2008. The (practical) implementation is the responsibility of the three regions.

1.1.1.4 Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) (Flemish region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.

- Flemish Region. Implementation: Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). Ministry for Environment, Nature and Energy.
- In force: 2008.
- An Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is mandatory for all dwellings that are for sale as of 1 November 2008; and for all dwellings that are leased as of 1 January 2009. Flanders has a mandatory quality assurance scheme, run by the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA), and involves the accreditation of assessors and quality control of certificates using the regional EPC database. Only approved energy experts can issue certificates, and owners who do not have an EPC risk a fine. Public buildings with a floor area exceeding 1000 m² and as of 1 January 2013 with a floor area exceeding 500 m² have to display their EPC in public. The energy rating (scale) is based on primary energy consumption.

1.1.1.5 Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) (Walloon region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Walloon Region. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building. Ministry of Environment.
- In force since 2010 for existing residential buildings and 2011 for existing non-residential buildings.
- The “CPEB” is prepared by an energy Certificate Office authorized by the Walloon Region, and is compulsory when selling or leasing an existing residential building.

1.1.1.6 Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) (Brussels-Capital region)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Brussels-Capital Region. Government of the Brussels-Capital Region. Bruxelles Environnement.
- In force 2008, current version 2011.
- The EPB certificate allows potential buyers or potential tenants to compare the energy performance of buildings. The EPB certificate also includes recommendations for improving the energy performance level of the dwelling. The energy rating (scale) is based on primary energy consumption.

The implementation of the mandatory energy audit requirements of art.8 of Directive 2012/27/EC on Energy Efficiency (the Energy Efficiency Directive or EED) is regulated in Belgium by the three regions. The Flemish and Walloon regions have not yet (fully) implemented these requirements.

1.1.1.7 Mandatory energy audit requirement (Brussels-Capital region)

- Buildings – non-residential only.
- Brussels-Capital Region.
- In force: 2012.
- Audits must be carried out by operators applying for environmental permits. The audit must be carried out by an approved auditor at the request of the applicant and under the applicant’s responsibility, within the 12 months before the deposit of the application for the environmental permit. The energy audit is part of the environmental permit application, extension or renewal file.

1.1.1.8 Heating audit

- Buildings – heating appliances.
- Flemish region.
- In force.

- It is obligatory to carry out a heating audit for heating appliances with an output of 20 to 100 kW. This audit must be carried out on the first service after the appliance is five years old, and every five years thereafter, either by a liquid fuel or a gaseous fuel engineer. The heating audit for heating appliances with an output of more than 100 kW must be carried out every two years (liquid fuels) or every four years (gaseous fuels) by a heating audit engineer. These three types of engineer are accredited for a period of five years, after which they must undergo further training to renew the accreditation.

1.1.1.9 Green Mobility Plan

- Transport – passenger.
- Brussels-Capital region. Bruxelles Environnement (IBGE-BIM)
- In force, 2004. Amended 2011.
- All companies with more than 100 employees need to develop a green mobility plan (MP). Companies have to pay themselves for the mobility plan but there is a maximum of free support by the IBGE-BIM. Two of the following measures have to be implemented: internal mobility coordinator; obligation to inform employees of the MP and to organize awareness raising campaigns; a multimodal accessibility information (plan); measures facilitating the use of public transport; high quality bicycle racks for employers and visitors; car policy aiming at reducing the Ecoscore of the company cars; action plan for pollution peaks (smog days). Companies have to provide audit reports.

1.1.1.10 Action plan to promote use of public transport

- Transport – passenger.
- Brussels-Capital region. Bruxelles Environnement (IBGE-BIM)
- Managers of an event assembling over 3000 participants has to introduce an action plan to promote the use of public transport.

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS

1.1.2.1 “Energivores / Energievreters” (Energy guzzlers) website

- Buildings - appliances.
- Federal. Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section. Department of Product Policy and Chemical Substances.
- In force: 2006.
- A website (www.energievreters.be / www.energivores.be) evaluates the energy performance of existing residential appliances, and allows to select energy efficient appliances available on the Belgian market.

1.1.2.2 The “www.energiesparen.be” website

- Multi-sectoral
- Flemish region. Flemish Energy Agency (VEA).
- Implemented.
- The VEA website (www.energiesparen.be) is the reference website on energy efficiency for Flanders. The site welcomes some 1.2 million visitors per year. The so-called ‘energy profit calculators’ on the VEA website provide customised advice on a number of energy saving investments, such as roof insulation, wall insulation, replacement of single glazing, replacement of old central heating boilers, installation of a solar boiler or photovoltaic solar panels. The “grant search module” includes all the grants at the federal, Flemish, provincial as well as municipal level. The ‘test your EPC’ tool allows comparing the EPC of a particular

house (terrace, semi-detached or detached) or apartment with the average EPC reference value in a certain municipality or province or with Flanders as a whole. The VEA regularly issues new publications on energy grants, the EPC and the energy performance regulations for new buildings (EPB regulations). The *'Dito newsletter'* is an important communication channel between VEA and local councils.

1.1.2.3 “Energierenovatieprogramma 2020” (Energy renovation programme 2020)

- Buildings - residential
- Flemish Region. Flemish Energy Agency (VEA).
- In force: 2006.
- The goal of the policy package ERP is to ensure that by 2020 (1) every house has roof or attic insulation, (2) all single-glazed windows are replaced by at least energy efficient double glazing and (3) central heating systems and natural gas heating systems have a thermal efficiency of at least 90%. The ERP combines existing and new actions in the field of energy efficiency, such as premiums and tax deductions for investments in energy efficiency, energy consultancy and audits, voluntary agreements (covenants), and the *dissemination of technical and financial information on energy efficiency measures*.

1.1.2.4 Guichets Énergie Wallonie (Energy desks)

- Multi-sectoral.
- Walloon region
- Start date: 1986.
- 14 energy desks allow the public to get personal information about energy (renewable energies, subsidies, ..)

1.1.2.5 “Guide CO₂ de la voiture”/ “CO₂-gids van de auto” (CO₂ car guide)

- Transport.
 - Federal. Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section + Department of Product Policy and Chemical Substances.
 - In force: 2006
- The federal government annually publishes the “CO₂ car guide – energy-efficient driving – good for you and for the environment” A sub-site of the “energy guzzlers” website allows the visitor to quickly find the CO₂-emissions, the CO₂-category, the fuel consumption or the power in kW of all new models available on the market. The website provides several search functions (by make/model, car type, fuel type, max. CO₂-emission,) or lists the 20 ‘best choices’.

1.1.2.6 “Provinciale mobiliteitspunten” (Provincial Mobility Desks)

- Transport
- Flemish Region. Provinces.
- The Flemish region created “mobility desks” in each Flemish province, where companies can get assistance and advice on the development of their commuter plans.”... *the mobility points of Provinces in Flanders support companies in the development of small mobility plans and also assist companies in preparing proposals for the Commuter Fund*” [Ferri & Cuenca, 2010, p. 40]

1.1.2.7 The ecoscore (www.ecoscore.be) website (Vehicles environmental impacts appraisal)

- Transport
- Flemish region

- The website provides information about the energy efficiency and environmental features of cars, in order to encourage consumers and companies to choose an energy-efficient and eco-friendly car. The ecoscore evaluates the environmental performance of a vehicle by taking into account global warming (mainly through CO₂), air pollution (e.g., particulates and nitrogen oxides, impacting both human health and ecosystems) and noise nuisance. An ecoscore between 0 and 100 is attributed to every vehicle.

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.1.3.1 Federal personal income tax relief (for roof insulation)

- Buildings – residential.
- Federal. Federal Public Service of Finance.
- In force. Effective since end of 2004.
- Since 2004 tax breaks and maximum deductible amounts for a number of energy-efficient investments in housing could be added to the premiums offered by the regions. As of fiscal year 2014 (expenses made in 2013), the federal tax incentives for energy savings have been abolished, due to overlap with regional incentives, with the exception of roof insulation. The tax deduction for roof insulation accounts for 30% of the real expenses (i.e. the invoiced amount, including VAT). The maximum allowed deduction is 3010 EUR.

1.1.3.2 Promotion of rational use of energy (RUE) by electricity distribution companies as part of their public service obligations

- Buildings – residential and non-residential
- Flemish Region, Walloon Region, and Brussels-Capital Region
- RUE action obligations on the electricity system operators for existing buildings (both residential and non-residential): grants for roof and loft insulation; grants for wall insulation (external wall and cavity wall insulation); grants for cellar and floor insulation; and grants for high-efficiency glazing. The general principle is that the costs imposed on the electricity system operators and the operator of the local transport network via the network tariffs are passed on in the electricity tariffs.

1.1.3.3 Financial incentives encouraging rational use of energy (RUE)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential
- Federal. Flemish Region, Walloon Region, and Brussels-Capital Region.
- Financial incentives by regions, provinces and municipalities usually come in the form of premiums, and cover a wide variety of energy efficiency measures. The amounts depend on the energy efficiency performance level of the particular measure and are updated on a yearly basis.

1.1.3.4 “Energie renovatie programma 2020” (ERP) (2020 Energy Renovation Programme)

- Buildings - residential
- Flemish Region. Flemish Energy Agency (VEA).
- In force: 2006.
- The goal of the policy package ERP is to ensure that by 2020 (1) every house has roof or attic insulation; (2) all single-glazed windows are replaced by at least energy efficient double glazing and (3) central heating systems and natural gas heating systems have a thermal efficiency of at least 90%. The ERP combines existing and new actions in the field of energy efficiency, such as *premiums and tax deductions for investments in energy efficiency*, energy consultancy and audits, voluntary agreements (covenants), and the dissemination of technical and financial information on energy efficiency measures.

1.1.3.5 Building renovation subsidy

- Buildings - residential
- Flemish Region. Flemish government.
- In force, 2007. Amended, 2009.
- The Flemish region offers a subsidy accessible to owner-occupants with income below a certain limit for building renovation work, including a number of energy efficiency improvements such as insulating glass, high-efficiency boilers and solar heaters. The Flemish government also offers a subsidy for building rehabilitation, including roof and external wall insulation.

1.1.3.6 Property tax reduction

- Buildings – residential.
- Flemish Region. Flemish Tax Agency.
- In force: 2009. Amended, 2012.
- Real estate is subject to a tax known as the “*immovable withholding tax*”. The Flemish Region implements a reduction in property tax for new energy-efficient builds. New residential buildings with an E-level of E60 and new commercial buildings with an E-level of E70 receive a 20 % property tax reduction for a period of 10 years. New residential buildings with an E-level of E40 receive a 40 % property tax reduction (Flemish Decree of 23 May 2009). As of 1 January 2013 residential buildings with an E-level of E50 (E40 in 2014) receive a reduction of 50% for a period of 5 years; and buildings with an E-level of E30 receive a 100% reduction for 5 years (Amendment of 19.10.2012).

1.1.3.7 Ecopack

- Buildings – residential.
- Walloon Region. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building. La Société wallonne du crédit social. Le Fonds du logement de la Wallonie.
- In force, 2012.
- The programme grants interest-free loans and energy subsidies, provided the household in question carries out at least two energy efficiency improvements.

1.1.3.8 Rénovation énergétique des bâtiments (UREBA) (Subsidies to Improve Energy Efficiency of Public Buildings)

- Buildings – non-residential.
- Walloon region. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building.
- In force, 2000. Updated, 2014.
- Subsidies for Rational Use of Energy (RUE) in public buildings, ranging from audits, setting up an energy management system, investment feasibility studies to investments in building shell elements or systems. The subsidy varies according to the type of public building and type of RUE action. In addition to the regular annual call for projects, there are specific calls (e.g. in 2007, 2008 and 2013) with higher subsidy rates for specifically targeted type of public buildings (e.g. schools).

1.1.3.9 “Primes énergie” (Energy premiums) (Wallonia)

- Buildings – residential.

- Walloon Region. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building.
- Ongoing.
- The energy premiums (“primes énergies”) are subsidies for the production of heat from renewable energy sources (RES).

1.1.3.10 “Primes énergie” (Energy premiums) (Brussels)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Brussels-Capital Region. Bruxelles Environnement.
- The “primes énergies” are subsidies granted to natural or legal persons for refurbishments of buildings in all sectors (households, services and industry). Refurbishment may include insulation; efficient heating; or other energy efficiency improvement investments.

1.1.3.11 “Prêt vert à taux zéro bruxellois” (Brussels zero interest green loan)

- Buildings – residential.
- Brussels-Capital Region. Government of Brussels-Capital Region. Bruxelles-Environnement. Credal (a banking institution). Energy House.
- In force, 2008.
- The green loan is a zero-rate energy loan for (low or medium income) households who replace single glazing with high-performance double glazing; insulate the roof or attic; or install a regulating thermostat and thermostatic valves.

1.1.3.12 Fiscal benefits for commuting by bike (Tax deductions for travelling to work by bicycle)

- Transport - passenger.
- Federal.
- In place, 2001. Updated, 2009.
- Employers can pay a cycling allowance free of taxes and social security contribution. They can also provide their employees with a company bicycle. For the company, 120% of the costs are deductible from taxable profits. This is also valid for installations making it easier for employees to get to work by bike, e.g. bike parking spaces or showers and changing rooms.

1.1.3.13 Fiscal benefits for car-pooling (Tax deductions for travelling to work by car-pooling)

- Transport - passenger.
- Federal.
- In place, 2002. Updated, 2007.
- Carpooling is supported fiscally. Home -work travel expenses for using carpooling are deductible at a particular lump sum rate up to a particular maximum distance.

1.1.3.14 Deductibility under corporate tax of expenses related to the use of company cars

- Transport - passenger.
- Federal.
- In force: 2005
- Belgium penalizes companies for providing environmentally unfriendly vehicles to employees. The penalty rate is linked to the vehicle’s CO₂ emissions

1.1.3.15 80/20 system for public transport (rail) season tickets of private sector employees

- Transport – passenger – public transport.
- Flemish region

- The Flemish region pays back the remaining 20% of public transport season tickets, if a company decides to pay back 80% of the ticket price to their employees.

1.1.3.16 Tax exemptions for surplus value upon ship sale

- Transport – freight (inland waterway transport).
- Federal.
- In force: 2007
- The federal government provides tax exemptions on the capital gains made on vessels used for commercial inland waterway transport, on condition that the surplus is re-invested in new ships.

1.1.3.17 “Pendelfonds” (Flanders Commuter Fund)

- Transport – passenger.
- Flemish Region.
- Implemented, 2006. In force, 2007.
- The commuter fund supports for the first four years on a 1€ for 1€ basis the investments of companies and non-profit organisations in sustainable mobility solutions like shuttle buses, bicycle infrastructure or promotion of carpooling. .

1.1.3.18 “Groene belasting op de inverkeerstelling (BIV)” Green car registration tax (reformed First Registration Vehicle Tax)

- Transport – passenger - private.
- Flemish Region
- In force, 2012.
- The registration tax in Flanders is based on CO₂ emissions as well as exhaust emissions standards, fuel and age. Electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles are exempt from registration tax.

1.1.3.19 “éco-bonus” and “éco-malus”

- Transport – passenger - private.
- Walloon Region
- In force, 2008. Tightened in /2012.
- A bonus is granted to the private individual (company cars are not covered) who buys a vehicle with a CO₂ emission rate between 0 and 70 g of CO₂. Vehicles are penalized (“malus”) if their emission rates exceed certain CO₂ emission limits. The “éco-bonus” and “éco-malus” system was tightened in 2012.

1.1.3.20 “La prime Bruxell'air” (Bruxell'air premium)

- Transport – passenger.
- Brussels-Capital Region. “Le Ministre bruxellois de la Mobilité et des Travaux publics de la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale” / “Brusselse Minister van Mobiliteit en Openbare Werken van het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest”.
- In force: 01/10/2006.
- The Brussels-Capital region provides incentives to car owners returning their registration plates to the vehicle registration authority, e.g. a one- or two-year subscription to the car-sharing scheme called Cambio along with either a one- or two-year pass for the public transportation system; or a subsidy for the purchase of a bicycle and biking equipment.

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING

1.1.4.1 Flemish support programme for energy consultants

- Buildings -
- Flemish Region. Flemish Energy Agency (VEA)
- In force, 2011.
- The programme, mainly directed at (low-income) households as well as construction and agricultural companies, stimulates energy efficiency and the rational use of energy (RUE) via information campaigns and consultancy.

1.1.4.2 Build Up Skills Belgium (BUSB)

- Buildings – construction sector.
- Flemish region and Walloon region. Consortium of the Building Industry Professional Training Fund, the Scientific and Technical Centre for the Building industry, the Flemish Energy Agency and Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building.
- Start, 2011.
- The consortium conducts research in order to help ensure that the workers' qualification level is of such a nature that they are capable of erecting and renovating buildings that meet the EU 20-20-20 targets.

1.1.4.3 "Alliance emploi-environnement" (Employment-Environment Alliance) (Wallonia)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Walloon Region. Walloon government.
- First Alliance concluded in February 2012.
- The Alliance brings together more than 41 partners, with the aim of stimulating demand for sustainable renovation and construction of private and public buildings; increasing the availability and capacity of the construction sector; and developing skills through an extensive "green training" programme. The building owners receive an entitlement to a set of premiums and can cover the remaining net investment by a zero interest rate loan, provided that the renovation contracts include at least one improvement to the building envelope and one improvement of the heating or (domestic) hot water system.

1.1.4.4 'Alliance Emploi-Environnement / Alliantie Werkgelegenheid-Leefmilieu' (Employment - Environnement Alliance) (Brussels)

- Buildings
- Brussels-Capital Region
- Launched, 2011.
- The "Alliance" involves a variety of actors (professional associations, trade unions, public actors as well as economic, training, research and community actors) to facilitate a synergy of skilled manpower, technical expertise and business experience. Actions include sustainable construction and renovation, where companies in the construction industry must meet "high energy and environmental performance" standards .

1.1.4.5 "Commune Energ'éthiques" (Energ'ethic Communities)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential
- Walloon Region.
- In force, 2007. Walloon Public Service - Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy - DGO4 - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building

- A subsidy compensates the staff costs (education and operational costs) of city energy counsellors, who must: 1) reduce energy consumption in communal buildings; 2) verify the proper implementation of building codes when allocating a building permit ; 3) inform and advice communal staff in their every-day life with energy matters ; and 4) advice and support citizens to manage their energy consumption.

1.1.4.6 “Bâtiments exemplaires” (the ‘Exemplary Buildings’ call for proposals)

- Buildings.
- Brussels-Capital Region.
- Since 2007.
- The Brussels-Capital region launches annual contests for the design and construction or renovation of buildings meeting high energy and environmental standards. The four requirements for “Exemplary Buildings” (BatEx) are: 1) be very economical in energy, with the passive standard as a reference for new constructions and the low or very low energy standards for renovation; 2) be based on eco-design principles; 3) have high architectural quality and be well integrated in the building stock; and 4) be simple and reproducible from a technical and financial point of view. The region provides subsidies as well as technical support.

1.1.4.7 “Facilitateur Bâtiment durable” (Sustainable building facilitator network)

- Buildings – residential and non-residential.
- Brussels-Capital Region. Brussels Environment
- In force, 2008. Adapted, 2011.
- Facilitators are energy efficiency experts who provide free-of-charge, independent and impartial advice on rational use of energy (RUE) and renewable energy. Since 2011, the specialist network has been centralized under Brussels Environment. The professionals provide guidance and recommendations in all areas related to energy management, renovation, or the construction of passive buildings. The network service is aimed at two main categories: managers of multi-family dwellings and the tertiary sector (office buildings, schools, hospitals, ...).

1.1.4.8 Ecodriving (Certificate of Professional Competence CPC)

- Transport.
- Federal. Flemish region. Walloon region. Brussels-Capital region.
- Application of directive 2003/59/EC, on the initial qualification and periodic training of drivers of driver licence categories C (trucks) and D (buses). It consists in the inclusion of the optimisation of fuel consumption in the list of subjects of the qualification tests and periodic training for the Certificate of Professional Competence (CPC). The training courses for driving instructors and examiners include training on energy efficient driving.

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

1.1.5.1 FEDESCO

- Buildings – non-residential
- Federal
- Created in 2005.
- The Federal Government created FEDESCO, a Belgian public/private funded energy service company to promote energy efficiency in public buildings and remove obstacles to investment.

1.1.6 RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BAT PROMOTION

1.1.6.1 Public Procurement Rules for Federal Administrations and Public Services

- Buildings – non-residential.
- Federal.
- In force: 2014.
- The Belgian Federal government subscribes to the goal of the European Council and the European commission of 50% sustainable procurement procedures for all federal public procurements.

1.1.6.2 ReTiBo (Registration and Ticket System with On board computer)

- Transport - public.
- Federal. Flemish region. Walloon region. Brussels-capital region.
- Project on the integration of public transport systems. The four Belgian transport operators (De Lijn, STIB, TEC, SNCB) agreed to integrate their registration, ticketing and board computer systems.

1.1.6.3 “Milieu- en Energietechnologie-Innovatieplatform” (MIP)

- Multi-sectoral
- Flemish region. i-Cleantech Vlaanderen.
- MIP is both an innovation platform and innovation programme. The MIP brings together important players (authorities, businesses and research organisations) in various areas related to environmental and energy technology.

1.1.6.4 Experimental Garden Electric Vehicles (“Proeftuin Elektrisch Voertuig”)

- Transport.
- Flemish Region
- The Programme ran from 2011-2014.
- The programme supported the market introduction of electro mobility in the form of 5 pilot platforms, bringing together more than 70 partners (companies, organisations, research institutions) to test the feasibility and affordability of electric mobility development.

1.1.6.5 “Programme Mobilisateur ENERGYWALL” (Mobilising Programme ENERGYWALL)

- Multisectoral.
- Walloon region. Funding by « Service public de Wallonie ».
- Start, 2008.
- ENERGYWALL is a programme for research on, development of and demonstration of renewable energy and energy savings. The objectives are the development of a scientific knowledge base, including technical units, research centers and technological innovation in the energy business; the creation of new products and processes in areas related to control of future sustainable energy; and the demonstration of products and processes in order to convince potential investors and the public. Areas covered include the efficient use of energy and energy savings.

1.2 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

1.2.1 RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

1.2.1.1 Overview of energy consumption in Belgium

Total energy consumption in Belgium in 2013 equalled 44151 Ktoe. The share of residential buildings is slightly above 20%; of non-residential buildings; 11% and of transport a little more than 22%.

Table 3: Final energy consumption, in Ktoe (Belgium, 2013) (Source: EUROSTAT)

Sector	Total	Solid fuels	Oil (total)	Gas	Total RES	Wastes (non RES)	Derived heat	Electricity
Non-energy consumption	9349	54	8357	938	-	-	-	-
Industry	10460	1422	444	4079	685	143	485	3201
Transport	9760	-	9241	46	329	-	-	144
Services	4838	-	951	1897	37	-	62	1892
Residential	8978	108	2825	3709	629	-	4	1703
Agricultural / Forestry / fishing	719	9	409	226	48	-	3	23
Non-specified (Other)	47	-	47	-	-	-	-	-
Total	44151	1.593	22274	10894	1729	143	554	6963

RES = Renewable Energy Sources

Construction is included in industry. Energy consumption in the construction sector in Belgium in 2013 is 197.717 ktoe.

Table 4: Final energy consumption by energy source, in % (Belgium, 2013) (source: EUROSTAT)

	Total all products	Solid fuels	Oil (total)	Gas	Total RES	Wastes (non RES)	Derived heat	Electricity
Total	100,00%	3,61%	50,45%	24,67%	3,92%	0,32%	1,25%	15,77%

Solid fuels are mainly used in industry, in particular the iron and steel industry (as well as some relatively small amounts in non-metallic minerals and other non-specified industries). In the building sectors (residential & services) solid fuels represent less than 0.78% of the total final energy consumption in those two sectors; and are in fact only used for mostly local heating in some older dwellings. Oil products represent 27.3% of total energy consumption in the building sectors, compared to 40.6% for natural gas and 26.0% for electricity. Oil products represent 94.7% of total energy consumption in the transport sector, compared to less than 1.5% for electricity. Renewable energy sources (RES) consist mostly of solid biomass (74.43% of total RES consumption), and is used both in industry and the building sectors. Biodiesel and biogasoline have a share of 18.15% of total renewable energy sources or RES (transport sector). Finally, biogas has a share of 4.51% in total RES (both industry, buildings and agriculture); and thermal solar of 1.09% (buildings only). Industry (mostly chemical and petrochemical industry) takes up 87.6% of the total derived heat. There is very little district heating in Belgium.

Table 5: Final energy consumption by sectors (Belgium, 2013) (source: EUROSTAT)

Sector	Total all products
Non-energy consumption	21.18%
Industry	23.69%
Transport	22.11%
Services	10.96%
Residential	20.33%
Agricultural / Forrestry / fishing	1.63%
Non-specified (Other)	0.11%
Total	100.00%

The large percentage of non-energy consumption in Belgium is due to the chemical plants in Antwerp (one of the largest concentrations of chemical manufacturing in the world), where large amounts of naphtha and natural gas are used for the production of olefins and fertilizers.

1.2.1.2 Characteristics of the Belgian housing stock

We provide some numbers on relevant characteristics of the Belgian housing stock, such as ownership, age distribution, compactness, and energetic quality (mostly in terms of insulation levels).

Number of dwellings (assumed to be equal to the number of households – there are no official statistics on the number of residential buildings available) (Belgium, 2010): 4505444 dwellings.

Ownership of dwellings (Belgium, 2010): 67% of households own their dwelling. The regional figures are 73% for Flanders; 68% for Wallonia; and only 39% for Brussels [source: Jespers et al, 2012].

Age of dwellings (Belgium, 2010): 14% of Belgian houses were built before 1921; 12% between 1921 and 1945; 27% between 1945 and 1971 (just before the oil crises); 35% between 1971 and 2001; and 14% after 2001 [source: Jespers et al, 2012].

Demolition rate: 5024 dwellings per year (this is an estimated figure, as there are no official data on demolition rates) [source: CLIMACT, 2012].

Renovation (or refurbishment) rate (Belgium, 2011): 1% per year [source: CLIMACT, 2012]; 0.75% per year [source: BPIE].

Compactness (Belgium, 2010):

Table 6: Compactness of dwellings in Belgium

Type of dwelling	[CLIMACT, 2012]	[Jespers et al, 2012]
terraced	28%	34%
semi-detached	20%	18%
detached	29%	22%
flats	24%	26%

About a third of households in Belgium in 2010 reside in single-family, detached (open) houses; and a quarter in multi-family dwellings. There is however a substantial difference between the Brussels region and the two other regions. In Brussels, 69% of households live in an apartment, studio or loft.

Average heated floor area per type of building (Belgium, 2010) [source: CLIMACT, 2012]:

- existing single-family dwellings: 134 m² per dwelling;
- existing multi-family dwellings: 99 m² per dwelling;
- new single-family dwellings: 233 m² per dwelling;

- new multi-family dwellings: 111 m² per dwelling.

Average heated floor area per region (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

- Flemish region: 104 m² per dwelling;
- Walloon region: 101 m² per dwelling;
- Brussels region: 68 m² per dwelling;
- Belgium (average): 101 m² per dwelling.

Average thermostat setting (Belgium, 2010): 18°C [Estimated, source: CLIMACT, 2012]

Table 7: Shares of roof/attic, floor and wall insulation (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

	Roof or attic	Floor	Outer walls
total dwelling	65%	19%	29%
¼ dwelling	2%	1%	2%
½ dwelling	4%	2%	4%
¾ dwelling	1%	2%	3%
None	28%	76%	62%

Table 8: Shares of insulating glazing (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]

	single glazing	double glazing	High Efficiency glazing
Brussels	19,8%	73,9%	6,3%
Flemish region	16,6%	67,8%	15,6%
Walloon region	16,0%	75,0%	9,1%
Belgium	16,8%	70,8%	12,4%

Table 9: Shares of windows with double glazing or high efficiency (HE) glazing (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

	Double glazing	HE glazing
total dwelling	81%	68%
¼ dwelling	8%	8%
½ dwelling	7%	12%
¾ dwelling	4%	12%

1.2.1.3 Residential energy consumption per energy service and technology

Breakdown of heat demand (Belgium, 2010) [Source: CLIMACT, 2012]:

- space heating: 92.71 % (7% of households use electricity for space heating);
- domestic hot water: 7.19% (14% of households use electricity for DHW);
- space cooling: 0.10%

The specific final energy demands are as follows: (Belgium, 2010) [Source: CLIMACT, 2012]

Space heating:

- Existing dwellings: 111 kWh/m²;
- New dwellings: 99 kWh/m².

Domestic hot water (DHW):

- 1202 kWh per household.

Space cooling:

- 4% of households have air-conditioning (AC);
- Cooling demand: 1460 kWh per household (only households with air-conditioning).

Types of heating and domestic hot water systems (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

- 84% of Belgian households has central heating (71% individual and 13% collective);
- 61% of the Belgian *individual* central heating systems on natural gas are high efficiency (HR) boilers or condensing (HR TOP) boilers, whereas 29% does not have an energy efficiency label;
- 34% of the Belgian *individual* central heating systems on fuel oil are high efficiency (Optimaz label) or condensing boilers (Optimaz elite label); whereas 66% does not have an energy efficiency label;
- dwellings not equipped with a central heating system mostly use one or more separate heating appliances. The shares are 18% electric accumulator; 17% direct electric convertor; 1% electric floor heating; 35% gas stoves; 6% oil stoves; 7% coal stoves; 7% wood or wood pellet stoves; and 3% fireplaces;
- shares of domestic hot water (DHW) systems are 34% combi-geyser; 27% combi-boiler; 24% separate electric boiler; 6% separate boiler on natural gas; 1% separate boiler on butane/propane; 1% separate boiler on fuel oil; 5% geyser on natural gas; 1% geyser on butane/propane and 1% electric geyser.

Table 10: Breakdown of heating and cooling technologies (Belgium,2010) [Source: CLIMACT, 2012]

	% space heating	% DHW
Gas boiler (old)	42	42
Gas boiler (new)	8	8
Solid fuel boiler	4	4
Oil-fired boiler (old)	37	30
Oil-fired boiler (new)	1	1
Resistance heating	7	14
Air-source heat pump	1	1
Ground-source heat pump	1	1
Stirling engine micro-CHP	0	0
Fuel-cell micro-CHP	0	0
Geothermal	0	0
Community scale gas CHP	0	0
Community scale solid-fuel CHP	0	0
District heating from power stations	0	0

Breakdown of electricity consumption for lighting and appliances (Belgium, 2010)

- Lighting: 13% or 556 kWh per household;
- White appliances: 39% or 1668 kWh per household;
- Brown appliances: 41% or 1744 kWh per household;
- Electric cooking: 7% or 309 kWh per household.

Shares of energy efficiency labels (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

- Freezers: 13.6% A++; 25.5% A+; 24.9% A; 5.0% B; 1.9% C;
- Dishwashers: 16.54% A++; 27.4% A+; 28.27% A; 6.24% B and 1.25% C;

Shares of types of TVs and PCs (Belgium, 2010) [source: Jaspers et al, 2012]:

- Television: 49.29% LCD; 11.03% plasma and 40.68% CRT;

- Personal computers: 36.47% LCD; 3.61% Plasma; 9.45% CRT and 50.48% laptops

Almost 28% of Belgian households keep their LCD PC continuously in stand-by mode, but only 18% for the CRT PC.

1.2.2 NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

Data for non-residential buildings are very scarce to non-existent.

Breakdown of heat demand (Belgium, 2010):

- Space heating: 88%;
- Domestic hot water: 10%
- Space cooling: 2%

Domestic hot water has a share of 10% of total fuel consumption. Space cooling has a share of 3.5% of total electricity consumption.

Breakdown of electricity consumption for lighting and appliances (Belgium, 2010)

- Office lighting: 27% or 0.0344 GWh per M€ added value;
- Street lighting: 4% or 0.0045 GWh per M€ added value;
- Appliances: 66% or 0.0845 per M€ added value.

1.2.3 TRANSPORT

1.2.3.1 Data on transport activities and infrastructure

We provide some relevant figures on transport activities (passenger and freight transport), including infrastructure density, modal split, occupancy level and trip purposes.

Annual total passenger transport (Belgium, 2010): 167.7 billion passenger-km.

Annual total freight transport (road, rail, inland waterways) (Belgium, 2010): 69 billion ton-km.

Density (Belgium, s.d.)

- Density of motorway ("highway") network: 58 km per 1000 km²;
- Density of railways: 117 km per 1000 km²;
- Density of inland waterways: 50 km per 1000 km².

Share of passenger-km (motorized transport) (Belgium, 2010)

- Cars: 79%;
- Bus or Coach: 14%;
- Trains 7%.

Modal split of freight transportation, % of ton-kilometre (Belgium, s.d.)

- Road: 71%;
- Rail: 15%.
- Inland waterways: 14%;

Trip purpose (Belgium, 2010):

- Commuting and work related: 24%;
- Education: 9%;

- Major shopping: 20%;
- Special events: 5%;
- Socializing: 26%;
- Dining out: 3%;
- Recreation: 9%;
- Joyriding: 4%.

Occupancy level of passenger vehicles (Belgium, 2010): 1.373 passengers per vehicle on average.

1.2.3.2 Data on transport technologies in Belgium

Almost all of road transport in Belgium uses either gasoline or diesel fuel internal combustion engines (ICE). Electricity only matters for freight transport by rail, where it has a share of 55%.

Vehicle efficiencies (Belgium, 2009):

- ICE cars: no data available;
- Battery electric vehicles (BEV): 0.26 kWh per km;
- Fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV): 0.33 kWh per km;
- ICE buses: 3.93 TWh per billion of vehicle-km;
- Electric buses: 0.93 TWh per billion of vehicle-km;
- Trucks: 3.24 TWh per billion vehicle-km

Breakdown of passenger transport per type of drivetrain (Belgium, 2010)

- Cars: 100% ICE;
- Buses: 100% ICE;
- Rail: 93% electricity and 7% diesel;

Breakdown of freight transport per type of drivetrain (Belgium, 2010)

- Road: 100% ICE diesel;
- Rail: Electricity 55% and diesel 45%;

CHAPTER 2: MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

2.1.1 BEHAVIOURAL BARRIERS

The following table lists the most important behavioural barriers in the building sector in Belgium.

Table 11: Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Cultural	Low priority – other attributes	Households do not renovate or retrofit to save energy, but because of other attributes of the product (thermal, visual and acoustic comfort, aesthetics, create more living space, beneficial for health, ...)
Educational	Bounded rationality	People do not understand the concept of energy, as it is invisible and only manifests itself through its uses (light, heating, ...)
Cultural	Attitude-Action gap	Even households who are knowledgeable about energy efficiency, and even those who claim to be environmentally aware, do not show more or less “energy saving” behaviour than others.
Cultural	Behavioural spillovers	Adopting a particular energy saving behaviour reduces the likelihood of adopting energy saving behaviours
Cultural	Identity	Households like “to remain in control”, rather than be told what to do by energy experts
Social	Social interactions – credibility & trust	Expert advice from professionals has to be corroborated by information from relatives, friends, colleagues, ... or people will not follow up
Educational	Lack of dissemination of information	It is difficult to find reliable information, both on energy efficiency technologies as on incentives (subsidies, tax deductions, ...)
Educational	Badly presented information	The information on websites is sometimes incorrect, or energy professionals put too much emphasis on the payback period of energy efficiency investments
Educational	Information is too complex	The information is often too complex, even for highly educated people
Educational	Inconsistent information	People often get contradictory advice on energy saving technologies and materials.

2.1.1.1 Behavioural barrier: Low priority of energy efficiency | Other attributes

Energy decisions often have low priority, because:

- Energy costs only make up a fraction (3% to 4%) of total budget or disposable income;
- Energy efficiency measures have long payback times, in spite of positive net present value;
- The benefits of energy efficiency measures are generally “invisible”;
- Durables have many attributes, of which energy efficiency is but one. Moreover, to improve energy efficiency, the producers may have traded off other attributes. These other “attributes” (e.g. comfort, convenience, safety, health, ...) often receive higher priority than energy efficiency.

Saving energy is not the top priority of many households in Flanders.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013];

- “When building or renovating a house, people don’t dream of a zero-energy house; they dream of a large house with a chic bathroom and a big kitchen.” [Matthys, 2013];
- Underprivileged people have other, more important problems (financial problems, emotional problems) on which they have to focus [Hendrickx, Smets and Van der Wilt, 2011].

In Wallonia, the most obvious reason for insulating the roof and/or replacing windows and boilers is improving (thermal) comfort, but other motives (e.g. acoustic and visual comfort, health issues, creating more living space, ...) also come into play.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- Several women admit that they are more sensitive to cold than their spouses. “In winter, I like it nicely warm and I need... I’m also accustomed to heat” [Annette];
- Acoustic insulation is often cited as a secondary benefit of replacing windows;
- Another reason to renovate windows is to make them larger, either for visual comfort, “Light! For Light!” [a mother]; or to enjoy “the charm of having an old house and to make it modern” [a teacher];
- Roof insulation is often an (optional) secondary benefit of the primary need for more living space, in particular for children’s bedrooms in the attic;
- One woman with an asthmatic child invokes health as a reason to insulate the home;
- Home renovators sometimes give “saving energy” as a reason, but this is never an end in itself. Firstly, “saving energy” may mean different things to household members, e.g. “being environmentally aware” for one spouse and “saving money” for the other. Secondly, “saving energy” is always seen in combination with some other factor, e.g. health. One well-to-do respondent who bought a large and old but already renovated house a few years earlier claimed that he would like to save energy (e.g. by lowering the room temperature) for ‘health concerns, but although he admitted that the energy performance of his house was not so good (a D rating where categories range from A to E), he did not contemplate an energy related renovation because there was no “sensation of discomfort”.
- Several respondents underline that environmental concern is the main driver of their energy related renovations, related to “a voluntary reduction of consumption and/or another type of consumption, such as fair-trade products.”

Energy efficiency measures are just a part of home renovation projects, which are mostly carried out for other reasons than saving energy, such as providing (more) comfort, relaxation and a context for social interaction. A Belgian (non-representative) survey reveals that besides “energy savings” other criteria or attributes play a decisive role, such as comfort, (in)convenience, aesthetics and time issues.

[Gram-Hanssen et al., 2007]:

- A Belgian respondent did not follow up on the expert advice to insulate the attic, because it would not improve comfort, was considered inconvenient, and would not allow to increase living space. "... the improvement in this respect, if I remember well, was effectively the inside wall in the attic that could be improved. That is the improvement which could have been the most important, but it has not been realised because it is a huge work and it is an attic that is not fit, where it is hardly possible to stand and so it's true that we have not brought modifications to it because we do not feel now any discomfort." [Marie];
- A Belgian woman who claims to care about the environment and to be very aware of the consequences her aesthetical decisions would have on energy consumption, nevertheless opted for the aesthetical criteria during the renovation work. "... we have broken out the wall, here and downstairs, it's very beautiful, but I don't know if it is really great for energy consumption." Inconvenience also played a role for her not following up on expert advice "... again days and days of work and dust" [Clara].

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Belgian respondents most frequently cited "greater comfort" as a motivation for undertaking energy-related improvements (insulation and more efficient heating);
- Many respondents state that they switch off the lights when nobody is in the room or that they switch appliances to stand-by mode, but rooms would still be lit with powerful halogen bulbs because they want to "create an atmosphere", i.e. give an impression of life, space, warmth, intimacy, or cosiness.

2.1.1.2 Behavioural barrier: Bounded rationality

Bounded rationality may refer to constraints on attention, resources or ability to process information, in the case of energy efficiency aggravated by information failures. To resolve this, individuals resort to rules of thumb or stick to habits (inertia).

The most important issues stemming from behavioural economics are:

- - Inattentiveness (and 'salience' issues);
- - Short-sightedness / myopia;
- - Prospect theory (and 'reference point' issues);
- - Bounded rationality (and heuristic decision making) / cognitive limitations;
- - Systematically biased belief.

End users have limited attention, leading them to systematically underweight certain information. The energy operating costs of durables (major appliances, vehicles) can be difficult to observe and fully comprehend. Energy savings are therefore a "shrouded" attribute. The consumers focus on the more "salient" attributes instead. For example, inattentiveness may lead to systematic undervaluation of future fuel costs when buying a new car.

It is argued that end users make short-sighted decisions when only the costs are immediate, and the benefits are in the future. It has also been shown that end consumers tend to value losses more than gains. This in combination with near-term bias means that they do not invest in energy efficient durables to reduce the energy costs, because they are faced with the relatively high first year purchase costs, even though in the long run the average cost of energy efficiency is lower than the average price of energy.

End users have a status quo bias. They tend to stick to default options, or they tend to value the commodities they already have more (the 'endowment effect'). This may partly explain why they are

biased against more energy efficient products, or are reluctant to replace standard products with more (energy) efficient ones.

When there are many variants to choose from or there is an overload of information, end users rely on heuristics (i.e. simple empirical “rules of thumb”) for decision-making. This may lead to “non-optimal” decisions (viewed from mainstream “rational choice theory” in economics).

Finally, end users may also have systematically incorrect beliefs. For example, they may associate highly insulated buildings with low indoor air quality. Such systematic bias may contribute to undervaluation of energy savings.

There is very little empirical research on bounded rationality in Belgium.

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- The Belgian public at large finds it difficult to grasp energy as a physical parameter. Energy is only “made visible” through its various uses: heating, lighting, the functioning of household appliances, ...

2.1.1.3 Behavioural barrier: Attitude-action gap

In Belgium, being more knowledgeable about energy savings, renewables or climate change; or being more environmentally aware in general, does not seem to be correlated with more energy efficient behaviour.

Although households in Flanders find “saving energy” very important, this does not necessarily mean that they take the appropriate actions.

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- 90% of Flemish households find saving energy important (and 51% very important). 66% of those respondents described themselves as being (very) frugal with energy. But the survey also revealed that this attitude did not always result in concrete actions.

[Bartiaux, 2008]:

- Links between on the one hand being aware of energy efficiency, renewables or climate change and on the other hand “energy sound practices” such as “lowering the temperature during the night, while airing or during absences of several hours in the wintertime” are in most cases statistically not significant. Respondents appear to be significantly more knowledgeable on renewables if the lower the temperature during absences of several hours in wintertime (but this might be coincidence);
- Links between aforementioned awareness and the number of baths/showers per person per week are statistically not significant;
- Links between aforementioned awareness and practices such as “possessing CFLs” and “switching off the light when leaving a room for 5 minutes” are non-existent in the first case or weak in the second case;
- There appears to be a significant correlation between awareness of renewables and/or climate change and the number of (large) appliances in the household, in the sense that more appliances means more knowledgeable. More knowledge on climate change is associated with less usage of washing machine and dishwasher; whereas more knowledge on renewables appears to be associated with more frequent use of the dryer (again, this could all be just coincidence);
- In Wallonia 81% of respondents know, or claim to know, that a television in stand-by mode consumes electricity. This knowledge is not significantly associated with better energy saving practices. Of those who have a television set (99%), 29% never leave it

in standby mode; 17% do it sometimes; 17% often and 37% always. One third of the respondents who (claim to) know that stand-by mode consumes electricity turn off the television only using the remote control;

A multiple classification analysis (MCA) with electricity as the dependent variable; and household income quartile, number of household members and awareness of climate change as the explanatory variables; reveals that being better informed on energy related and environmental issues does not have a significant impact on (Belgian) household electricity consumption. [Bartiaux, 2008] proposes the following (reverse) hypotheses: environmentally friendlier practices raise the openness to environmental information as well as the concern for environmental protection.

[Wallenborn, 2007]

- Neither “positive” attitudes (towards the environment or the impact of one’s activities), nor “negative” attitudes (towards expensive energy, technological progress or the difficulty of controlling one’s energy consumption), seem to have any influence on actual (energy related) behaviour in Belgium;

2.1.1.4 Behavioural barrier: Behavioural spill-overs

A negative behavioural spill-over occurs when the adoption of a particular energy saving behaviour reduces the likelihood of adopting other energy saving behaviours. For example, when a consumer uses efficient lighting, he or she may feel that it is not necessary to leave the car at home, because “I am already doing my share”.

[Wallenborn, 2007]

- Belgian respondents who invested in energy efficient technologies felt *“that they had done what was necessary to save energy and made little effort to adopt more energy-saving behaviours.”*

2.1.1.5 Behavioural barrier: Identity

Advice on energy efficiency measures has to be in line with the “identity” of the household. More in particular, Belgian households must feel that they “remain in control”, rather than be dictated what to do.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- In Wallonia, energy assessments appear “useful both to raise the attention on unknown insulation possibilities, especially for the external walls, the floor and/or the cellar ceiling, and to provide a calculation method, but the identity factor has to be taken into account: home owners are reluctant to recognise the influence of this assessment on their energy-related renovations and do want to show themselves as the master of these works.”

2.1.1.6 Behavioural barrier: Social components of end-use behaviour – credibility and trust

The credibility of the information source and the trust placed in the source are very important. Trust is largely encouraged through interpersonal contacts.

Energy expert advice and customised information appears to be quickly forgotten or disregarded without the support of social networks (Bartiaux, 2008: 1178). Advice needs to be corroborated by persons whose opinion in these matters is valued the most by the home owners. These persons can be relatives, friends, acquaintances, neighbours, ... Social interactions may be particularly important in Belgium, because it is a society where large groups speak different languages; have different religious backgrounds; differ in political preferences, especially in terms of the political power of the

Green parties in the three regions; and with a substantial presence of citizens from all European countries [Bartiaux, 2008].

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- In Wallonia, all respondents (but one) refer to friends, relatives, acquaintances, neighbours or colleagues who helped out in various ways, e.g. offering their opinion on professionals, giving information on renovation matters, or providing practical assistance during the works;
- Many respondents have at least one friend or relative, acquaintance or client working in the construction sector or in energy-related areas (or the respondents may work in those sectors themselves). These professionals give practical advice, comment on cost estimates, or propose to do the work themselves;
- Respondents often acknowledge the help of their partner, especially if he (rarely she) is a DIY practitioner.

A number of Belgian respondents trust the energy advisors on replacing boilers, but only when the information from the experts converges with information from other sources; and/or with the home owner's own knowledge.

[Gram-Hanssen et al., 2007]:

- “ ... the people from Vito have done an energy simulation, so it's clear that it may be more interesting to switch to another heating system [than the electrical heating] but we must see if it is feasible and when the investment can be profitable (...) [and ask] acquaintances, who have more or less the same dwelling volume and who are using gas, how much they are paying per year and we must see a little.” [Michel];
- A respondent in Wallonia replaced a boiler on the advice of the energy expert who did an energy assessment of his dwelling, but only because this advice was “... congruent with two other trusted sources of information (his father-in-law, an engineer, and the journal of the main consumers' organisation) ... ” The energy expert “also said “gas” (...) and I myself have always had a good a-priori. (...) It's true that in “test-achats” [the journal of the main consumers' organisation], they also recommend gas boilers, if one is to replace it. (...) I have spoken to my father-in-law, who is an engineer and who is also always quite interested in these things. He also has gas (...)” [Luc].

The persons one trusts are not necessarily all that reliable.

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Belgian respondents declare to be well informed on how to save energy, but they often have too much confidence in information sources that are not always reliable;

2.1.1.7 Behavioural barrier: Form of information

The form of information (the way it is presented) is relevant. Barriers can refer to:

- Missing or partial information;
- Lack of dissemination of information;
- Badly presented information;
- Complexity of the information;
- Inconsistency of information from different sources.

Examples of **lack of dissemination of information** are:

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Respondents who are keen on doing the energy efficiency improvements themselves say it is very difficult to find reliable information. Professional support is lacking in all stages of the process (from design to inspection);
- Few Belgian respondents apply for subsidies, premiums or (tax) rebates, because they are not aware of their existence or because they do not know where to apply for them.

Examples of **badly presented information** are:

The information as presented may simply be incorrect.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]

- "... there is much information on the internet, but it may be hard for households to distinguish correct information from contradicting false information." [Ramaekers, 2013];
- Some information on the Flemish government website www.energiesparen.be is not accurate: "... the energy calculator does not correctly indicate the energy savings from different measures." [Verspeel, 2013].

The information as presented by the energy experts responsible for the energy assessment of a dwelling sometimes discourages home-owners to improve the energy efficiency of their homes, for example because the experts do not regard the investments worthwhile. Nearly all Belgian respondents seem to put too much weight on (the length of the) payback time, most likely because this is the only decision criterion calculated by the software of the energy advisors. Gram-Hanssen et al. [2007] recommends that experts should probably focus more on initial costs of the investments and possible energy savings, and let the home owners decide for themselves.

[Gram-Hanssen et al., 2007]:

- About replacing windows with double glazing, experts said: "Not worth the investment";
- About insulating the façade: "They say themselves that it was very expensive: to insulate the façade.";
- "He [the advisor] clearly stated it — and this has somewhat comforted us—that 'with a house like this one, you will never reach an A-label, because the house is not adequate for that. The materials are not modern.'"

Examples of **information that is too complex** are:

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]

- in a study on energy efficiency with underprivileged people, 82% of the respondents have difficulties finding information. Either they do not know where to start looking for information, or the information is too complex [Hendrickx, Smets, and Van der Wilt, 2011]

The search for information and the most advantageous solutions can be very complicated and time consuming (in Wallonia), even for highly educated people.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- "*You must be a keen calculating person and this is not our specialty.*" [couple where both have a BA degree];
- "*Both of us have a university degree [a Master] and we already had [problems] to sort out the papers. So for someone who does not have such a background, I don't know how he does it. So, I tell myself, it is stupid because these subsidies are normally accessible to everyone: are they really accessible?*" [Laura].

[Gram-Hanssen et al., 2007]:

- Homeowner in Belgium receive a report from energy advisors explaining the measurements and the calculations. Some respondents find the information too detailed, too technical and too complex. *“I found it very nice that they came, but I think that the report could be more synthesised, more ‘straight to the point’.”* [Wim]

Examples of **inconsistent information** are:

Several respondents (in Wallonia) reported contradictory advice on materials and techniques for roof insulation; or for boilers.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- “For the insulation material, there are many opinions on the matter. Many opinions... here I have more conflicting opinions than for the frames. On (hesitation) glass wool, hemp, (hesitation) extruded polystyrene, (hesitation) and so on and so on.” [Arnaud];
- “There are still many who do not know” [insulation with cellulose] and “the others who came were specialists of this type of insulation, so cellulose, and then, the issue was on the number of centimetres, so some were saying that the norm was “X centimetres”, and others that with that number, one did not get the reduction, the subsidy from the Walloon Region.” (Bénédicte).

Asking for and sorting out the cost estimates from several professionals is not so straightforward (in Wallonia).

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- An engineer with a PhD found himself “somewhat powerless when one must compare because one finds quite different cost estimates.”;
- A respondent was asked to sort out cost estimates by a friend who is an architect.

[Bartiaux, 2008]:

- A respondent in Wallonia did not want to replace his boiler, because the advice given by the energy expert who did an energy assessment of his dwelling contradicted the advice given by his heating installer.

Policy instruments may loose credibility because there is a discrepancy between the “actual” energy consumption and the “calculated” energy consumption as e.g. stated on the energy performance certificate.

[Mlechnik et al, 2010]:

- *“The implementation of energy saving measures is supported and enforced via standards and regulations, which define human behaviour and activities in buildings for the average situation and conditions and exclude non-building related issues. The instruments based on these standards lose some credibility of the public as they do not reflect the real energy consumption of a building.”* [p. 31]

2.1.2 ECONOMIC BARRIERS

The following table lists the main economic barriers in the buildings sector in Belgium.

Table 12 Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of knowledge about government support	Knowledge about government support for energy efficient technologies has improved in recent years in all regions, but there is

(imperfect information)	still a lot of room for improvement
Inability to estimate the magnitude of energy use (and related costs) (imperfect information)	Most Belgians are unable to tell how much energy they consume; or for that matter, how high their energy bills are
Lack of understanding how much energy (money) can be saved (imperfect information)	Lack of knowledge about what factors influence energy consumption; and about energy efficiency technologies in general.
Split incentives	Most tenants do not want to invest in energy efficiency measures because they rent the dwelling. Landlords are on average older, non-professional people who own a few houses and are not interested in energy efficiency investments.
Principal-agent relationships	The complex decision-making process related to co-ownership of multi-family dwellings
Heterogeneity across end-users	Energy-related behaviour differs, depending on whether one belongs to one of the following groups: highly educated, high income middle-class groups; recent buyers of a dwelling and young owners; lower education – lower income groups; elderly owners; and landlords.
Hidden costs	Inconveniences during construction works. Having to stay somewhere else during (deep) renovation works.
Access to capital	Initial (investment) costs of energy efficiency investments are considered too high, and households do not have sufficient access to funds.
Risk – long payback periods and length of occupancy	Some households only make the necessary “replacement” investments, but do not engage in “durable” investments, because they do not wish to stay for long in that particular building. Investments with long pay-back periods are therefore considered ‘risky’.

2.1.2.1 Economic barrier - market failure: Imperfect information (or lack of knowledge)

Imperfect information or lack of knowledge refers to:

- Lack of knowledge about availability of, benefits of, and government support for energy efficient technologies;
- Inability to estimate the magnitude of energy consumption (and costs) of energy services;
- Lack of understanding how much energy (and money) energy efficiency measures can help save.

Examples of **lack of knowledge about government support**.

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- Only 47% of Flemish households had heard about the government website www.energiesparen.be
- Only 63% to 72% of Flemish households know about financial support measures, although these figures have improved over the years.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- In Wallonia, knowledge of energy-saving issues (regional subsidies, federal rebates, energy assessments) is on the increase. Respondents interested in saving energy and/or money report that their search for information leads them to the Internet website on energy matters of the Walloon Region or to one of the energy offices (also managed and paid for by the Walloon Region) where they can receive free advice. They also refer to mass media, advertisements, TV broadcasts (“*you cannot escape them*”), press releases ...

Examples of the **inability to estimate magnitude of energy consumptions (and costs)**

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Belgian respondents are very often unable to tell how much energy (be it gas, heating fuel oil or electricity) they use. Most respondents are unable to give rough estimates of the energy consumption of their homes, either in cubic metres or kilowatt-hours; nor are they able to give estimates of monthly or annual energy costs;
- Belgian respondents overestimate the insulation of their dwelling.

Examples of **lack of understanding how much energy (and money) can be saved**

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- 65% of Flemish households do not know how much it costs to place roof insulation. Those who do have an idea overestimate the costs by on average 70%;

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- In Wallonia, the know-how and practical knowledge of energy efficiency measures is generally low. For example, a 29 year old male respondent with an MBA says that he does not belong to “*those people who don’t have the intellectual competences to master the topic [the energy assessment of a house]*”, but he finds that the boiler of their house “*is not an old boiler (...), it’s a boiler from the seventies.*”
- There is however a widespread “mental routine” of knowing that frames and windows of old houses have to be replaced. A woman upon her first visit to her future house recalls: “*... just by seeing the old frames with single glass windows, at this moment I knew that they had to be changed.*” [Viviane].

[Mlechnik et al, 2010]:

- “*One of the most significant barriers for achieving the goal of substantially improving energy efficiency of buildings is the lack of knowledge about the factors determining the energy use.*” [p. 31]
- “*..., instruments are lacking that enable the assessment of the energy use of buildings and give information about real cost-benefit relationship between investments in energy saving measures and profits.*” [p. 31]

2.1.2.2 Economic barrier - market failure: Split incentives

The tenant pays the energy bill. The landlord is responsible for making the energy efficiency investment. The tenant would benefit from the landlord’s investment. The landlord does not have an incentive to invest because she cannot realize the benefits of the investment. The tenant does not invest either, because he may move out before the investment has paid off. As a result, no investment is made.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- “Landlords are generally rather old and not professional. They own two to three buildings. They don’t see the need to invest in energy efficiency measures.” [Inslegers, 2013];
- One could “... encourage landlords to invest by allowing them to increase the rent pro rata with the energy savings.” [Van Dyck, 2012].

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- The split incentive consistently turns out to be the most (or second most) important barrier to energy efficiency. No less than 90% to 97% of Flemish tenants do not want to invest in various energy efficiency measures because they rent the dwelling.

[Mlecknik et al, 2010]:

- *“The main barrier to sustainable renovation in both private and social rented sector seems to be the return on investment: the one who invests is not the one who profits.”* [p. 30]

To make things worse, the Belgian private rental market is becoming tighter and tighter, due to federal policies promoting house ownership (e.g. fiscal stimuli policy for mortgages).

(BECO, 2010):

- Demand for rental homes is larger than the supply;

[Heylen and Winters, 2009]:

- The scarcity in the rental market combined with the split incentive barrier ensures that dwellings in the Flemish social housing market have a lower structural and energy efficiency quality compared to privately owned dwellings.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- “... tenants on the private rental market often are frictional tenants or underprivileged people.” [Schaerlaekens, 2013];
- “These are people who have a difficult relationship with their landlord, but who are nevertheless dependent on the goodwill of their landlord for the quality of their house.” [Hendrickx et al., 2011].

It is the case however that in Belgium a relatively high portion of the market consists of owner-occupied dwellings (67 %) [Jespers et al, 2012].

2.1.2.3 Economic barrier - market failure: Principal-agent relationships

Principal-agent relationships occur when one party (the principal) depends on the actions of another (the agent).

In multi-family dwellings multiple owners first have to agree on energy saving investments, and once approved, have to make a financial contribution.

[BECO, 2010a]:

- In Flanders, different owners in a multi-family building have to approve investments in a general assembly with a 75% majority. This holds for investments in communal parts such as insulation of the building shell or central heating;
- The apartment property manager has to put forward potential measures to maintain the value of the apartment. The property manager often has a lack of knowledge about energy efficiency measures and/or members of the general assembly have a lack of trust in the property manager.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- “The general assembly of the co-owners association is very diverse. It is a mix of poor and rich, young and old.” Some of the decision makers might also be owner-landlords subject to the split incentive barrier. “... this leads to perverse situations where the general assembly decides whether or not the owner of the top floor may insulate the roof, even though the lack of insulation mostly affects his energy bill.” [Matthys, 2013].

[Mlecknik et al, 2010]:

- “... *the complex decision-making process related to the co-ownership of building parts in multi-family dwellings, is an additional barrier.*” [p. 30].

It is the case however that In Belgium there is a high proportion of single-family dwellings. Apartments account for only a quarter of all dwellings.

It should also be noted that the size of households has been continuously decreasing in Belgium since 1990. The average size of existing single-family dwellings is not ideal for increasingly smaller families.

2.1.2.4 Economic barrier - non-market failure: Heterogeneity across end-users

End users are very heterogeneous concerning the costs and benefits of energy efficient technologies. This heterogeneity can be either static (cross-sectional) or dynamic (intertemporal). The first may refer to differences within a country or region, as well as between countries (cultural differences). The latter refers amongst others to “early adopters” and the presence of an option value to waiting [Stavins, 2013]. End users should therefore be divided into a limited number of subsets, who have more or less common energy saving behaviours (or energy-related “preferences/attitudes/beliefs”).

The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) outlines in its Energy Renovation Programme (ERP) specific groups who have not undertaken replacement of high-impact components such as roof insulation, double glazing and heating systems. VEA acknowledges that some groups in society can not be reached by conventional policy instruments. “*We have to respond to the specific reasons why certain sections of the population until now have not executed very profitable energy saving investments.*” [VEA, 2011, p.26].

1. The VEA distinguishes the following priority groups:
2. Highly educated, high income and middle class groups;
3. Recent buyers of a dwelling and young owners;
4. Lower education - lower income groups;
5. Elderly owners;
6. Landlords.

Each of those groups is identified by a number of characteristics and the most important barriers that apply to them.

Highly educated, high income and middle class groups

This group generally has high environmental awareness, is well informed about technical features and government support and is prepared to make the necessary energy efficiency investments.

[Tns and VEA, 2011]:

- Flemish households belonging to a higher “social class” are more likely to contemplate their energy consumption. The more educated, the more likely households are familiar with the Flemish government information website www.energiesparen.be;

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- Financial motives play a role. "... middle-aged families, whose children have moved out and whose mortgage is paid off, often invest in thermal retrofits in order to benefit from tax advantages." [Verspeel, 2013]

Recent buyers of a dwelling and young owners

The natural moment for a new owner to renovate a building is soon after the dwelling is bought. Every retrofit should be a deep thermal retrofit to avoid lock-in, since the building shell may remain untouched for several decades.

[Tns and VEA, 2011]:

- Most single-family dwellings in Flanders undergo a (major) renovation within a year after the (existing) building is bought. The fraction of recently bought apartments undergoing a major renovation is substantially less. Thermal retrofits in that instance are mostly limited to improvements in glazing, most likely because of the specific barriers related to multi-family buildings;
- The knowledge of recent owners about technical particulars and government support is fairly detailed;
- Little use is made of government support. Renovators restrain themselves to the minimum legal obligations or simply want to execute many building activities themselves (mostly "to save money"), as a result of which they cannot apply for most subsidies;
- They attach higher priority to other factors, and invest mainly in " ... *building activities which make the dwelling more appropriate to the way of living of the new occupants*" [VEA,2011, p.17];

Lower education - lower income groups

Underprivileged households combining a low level of education with a low income face a number of constraints, most significantly *lack of knowledge, other priorities* and *financial constraints*.

First. Underprivileged people lack knowledge about the financial benefits of thermal retrofits, about governments support and energy consumption in general.

[Hendrickx et al., 2011]:

- 80% of underprivileged people find issues on energy efficiency difficult to understand. 90% lack technical knowledge in this matter. 63% have no idea what to do about energy issues. Another 63% are ignorant about government support.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- Not all underprivileged people are ignorant on energy matters. "... a certain portion of underprivileged people do have high awareness about their energy use, simply because they have such limited resources." [Starckx, 2013].

Second. Underprivileged people attach more importance to other urgent problems.

(Samenlevingsopbouw, 2010):

- Energy efficiency issues only receive limited attention;

[Hendrickx et al, 2011]

- 82% of underprivileged people give other matters priority over energy efficiency.

Third. Underprivileged people face financial constraints.

[Hendrickx et al, 2011]:

- 88% of underprivileged homeowners consider the cost of energy efficiency investments way too high.

Fourth. Other constraints faced by underprivileged people.

[Samenlevingsopbouw, 2010]:

- Underprivileged people in Flanders cannot summon the courage to undergo all the inconveniences associated with building activities;
- The administrative load is perceived as a significant hurdle.

[Hendrickx et al, 2011]:

- 60% of underprivileged people mentions not having the emotional strength to actively look for solutions;
- 70% of underprivileged homeowners see the inconvenience of moving materials for renovation as an important obstacle;
- For underprivileged tenants a sour relationships with their landlord often makes it difficult to invest in energy efficiency.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- “ ... a relatively large portion of underprivileged people are tenants.” They thus face the split incentive barrier. [Starckx, 2013].

Elderly owners

[Tns and VEA, 2011]:

- Elderly owners in Flanders have a positive attitude towards saving energy, but have insufficient knowledge of energy efficiency measures;
- They do not see the benefits of investing in a thermal retrofit, because they probably will not be around long enough to fully profit from the investment.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- Practical and administrative inconvenience are significant barriers for the elderly. *“Actually, elderly people just want peace and quiet.”* [Vermeiren, 2013];
- *“... the inconvenience linked to renovation activities is an important barrier to elderly people.”* [Claessens and Ledeganck, 2012];
- Financial concern for children or grandchildren may be a relevant factor. *“Elderly people do not want to invest because they are afraid of higher inheritance taxes once they die.”* [Van Damme and Van Vooren, 2012];
- Elderly people appear to be less aware of environmental problems. [Bachus and Van Ootegem, 2011]

Landlords

Landlords face a number of pertinent barriers.

[BECO, 2010]:

- 56% of landlords did not invest in energy efficiency in the preceding 10 years, because they considered these improvements unnecessary (low priority). Only 11% mentioned as the most important reason the fact that they could not realize the benefits from the investment (split-incentive);
- Landlords also refer to the administrative load, both to obtain government support and during the execution of the building activities;
- Landlords in general lack sufficient knowledge of energy efficiency measures.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "... the average age of landlords is quite high." The problems linked to elderly people thus apply for landlords. "... another serious problem is the shortage of rental houses. Landlords in low-quality rental segments always find a tenant. Therefore, there is a guarantee of demand. As such, they do not see the necessity of increasing the energy efficiency because energy efficiency measures such as roof insulation and double glazing are much less observable than increased comfort." [Inslegers, 2013].

The Flemish government hopes to partially solve these problems through an initiative called "Huurschatter" to estimate the fair rental price of a dwelling, which would include both energy efficiency and the energy performance certificate (EPC) as determinants.

[Wallenborn et al., 2006] and [Wallenborn, 2007] tried to draw up a typology of six profiles for Belgian households on the basis of differentiated energy use "practices" and the ways in which energy-saving arguments and incentives are received by the households, but did not pursue this line of research, because the dynamics of household energy consumption differs substantially according to the various energy services (space heating, domestic hot water, cooking, lighting, etc.)

[Mlechnik et al, 2010, p. 17] observe that "*different target groups (buyers, social rent, private rent) will need an individual marketing approach.*"

2.1.2.5 Economic barrier - non-market failure: Hidden costs

Hidden costs, which are very real but difficult to express in monetary terms, refer to a number of opportunity costs, such as:

- The time needed to collect information on energy efficiency technologies, funding, possible government support, and building professionals;
- The time needed to properly analyse all this information;
- The time spent on the administrative load of demanding government support (if relevant);
- The time spent living somewhere else, when deep renovation is needed for the home;
- Other inconveniences during construction works.

Households in Flanders and Belgium are reluctant to retrofit their homes (this applies especially to 'deep' renovation), because of the inconveniences and the potential necessity of having to live somewhere else during the renovation works.

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- In Flanders practical considerations are consistently among the three most important reasons for not investing in energy efficiency measures. Especially for wall insulation and floor insulation households saw '*too much fuss*' as an important barrier.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- As an example of an inconvenience: "... elderly) people also don't like the fact that strangers are present in their house." [Claessens and Ledeganck, 2012].

[Mlechnik et al, 2010]:

An important barrier to tackle is the situation of the existing inhabitants when renovating.

- "*Can they stay in their flats during the renovation works, thus minimizing social and economical impact, or do they have to move (permanently or temporarily)?*" [p. 82]

2.1.2.6 Economic barrier - non-market failure: Access to capital

Lack of capital prevents households (in particular the lower income sections of the population) from paying the upfront costs needed for investments in energy efficient technologies, aggravated by the fact that those technologies often have higher prices. Lack of capital may refer to:

- Unavailability of internal funds;
- Insufficient access to a loan on agreeable terms;
- Overall reluctance to contract a loan.

[Mlecnik et al, 2010] identify “low investment capacity” as one of the main barriers to sustainable renovation in Belgium.

A significant barrier in Flanders seems to be the high initial costs of energy efficiency investments. This can be caused by insufficient capital (through either internal funds or borrowing), but the cause might also be a form of bounded rationality, in particular shortsightedness or myopia. Unfortunately, the literature does not make this clear.

[Tns & VEA, 2011]:

- The reason ‘*no money, too expensive*’ was consistently one of the most important reasons for Flemish households to abstain from investments in energy efficient measures.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- The fundamental problem is the higher price of energy efficient products. “*Higher prices restrict energy efficiency goods to a niche position.*” [Claessens and Ledeganck, 2012];
- “The [abolished] federal support measures were a trigger for many households because they decreased the relative cost to ‘normal’ products.” [Bonnarens, 2013].

2.1.2.7 Economic barrier - non-market failure: risk

The length of occupancy of a homeowners may be shorter than the payback period of the energy efficiency measure. As a result the measures are often not implemented. The short payback times required for energy efficiency measures may be seen as a response to risk.

The prime motive for home renovation in Belgium is in most cases not to improve the value of the property as an investment. In that perspective, “payback time” does not play a decisive role in the decision to renovate a house or not. However, there are notable differences between households.

[Gram-Hanssen et al., 2007]:

- One young Belgian couple plans to sell the newly bought house after a few years. They therefore limit their investments to “replacement investments”, simply to meet the legal standards;
- Another young couple intends to turn the newly bought house into a “home” for a longer period. Their investments are therefore more durable, although the “sustainability issue” may also be inspired by the moral implications of their self-proclaimed “ecological conscience”.

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Envisioned length of occupancy is an important factor.

2.1.3 INSTITUTIONAL AND ORGANISATIONAL BARRIERS

The following table lists the most relevant organisational barriers in Belgium, discussed in this chapter. It also includes the institutional barriers, discussed in depth in chapter 3..

Table 13 Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Old housing stock	Residential building stock in Belgium is (very) old, and not well insulated. Demolition and renovation rates are below EU-averages
Adverse selection	Professionals deliver goods and services on the basis of customer preferences, and customers find (lower) price more important than the (initially more) expensive energy efficiency measures
Lack of knowledge and education of building professionals	Building professionals in Belgium lack the necessary knowledge and skills with regard to energy efficiency measures
Structure of the building sector	The building sector structure is very scattered, with many small companies each specialized in their own domain, thus preventing 'holistic' solutions
Low energy and transport related taxes	Energy and transport taxes in Belgium are lower than EU-averages, thus making the upfront costs of energy efficiency improvements higher than future financial savings
Fragmentation of authority - interregional	The strong degree of decentralization of energy policy in Belgium leads to fragmentation, where e.g. contractors are confronted with different regulations in the regions
Fragmentation of authority - intraregional	Within the regions there is a confusing crisscross of incentives; and different authorities (e.g. energy versus housing administrations) do not always co-ordinate
Discontinuity	The frequent federal and regional changes in the content of policy instruments, without clear transition periods, leads to uncertainty and lack of transparency
Administrative load	The administrative load is too high for both consumers (e.g. obtaining subsidies) and buildings professionals (e.g. certification of their work)
Legal barriers concerning split incentives	Federal regulations make it difficult to solve the split incentive barrier (e.g. landlords are not allowed to raise the rent after an efficiency improvement)
Legal barriers concerning financial and technical conditions to subsidies	Renovation works are sometimes not or only partly covered by subsidies, because home-owners want to use traditional techniques or would prefer to do the work themselves rather than by a building professional.
Urban legislation prohibiting façade insulation	Urban regulation in Wallonia prohibits exterior insulation of the front façade
Weak monitoring and evaluation	Monitoring and evaluation of energy efficiency policies and their effectiveness is extremely weak in Belgium and its regions

2.1.3.1 Building sector barrier: Old housing stock

The residential building stock in Belgium is on average very old, particularly in Wallonia. A high percentage of Belgian houses (66%) originate before 1970. On top of that, demolition rates and retrofit rates are relatively low compared to EU averages.

[Minaraad and SERV, 2012]:

- Buildings in Flanders have an average life span of more than 80 years.

[BPIE, 2011]:

- The renovation rate in Belgium in 2011 was 0.75%. This is very low compared to the European average of 1%;
- The new build rate in the residential sector is 0.68%.

In Wallonia home buyers make a trade-off between three elements: price of the house, the amount of work to be done (except if the house has already been renovated) and location & proximity of highways and railways.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- Two respondents in Wallonia said that they have recently bought “*a ruin*”, two others did not dare to use that word (even though appropriate) and a fifth one reported that her house dates “*from the 16th or 17th century*”. Another one said that their house was “*good and not too old since it was built around 1954.*”

2.1.3.2 Building sector barrier: Adverse selection

The adverse selection mechanism means that building sector professionals often deliver goods and services on the basis of customer preferences rather than on quality, lest they should exclude themselves from consideration by the customer. In many instances, the clients will tend to select options on the basis of (more) visible aspects such as price, rather than being willing to pay the price premium for high energy efficiency products.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- “*...price, rather than energy efficiency, is the most important criterion*”. [Matthys, 2013];
- The adverse selection mechanism is illustrated by the following example. “*A carpenter offers to make an airtight installation of windows, even though this is not explicitly required in the tender. Airtightness causes an increase in installation time of 15%, but makes the window more energy efficient. This feature makes the total cost of installation rise by 3 to 4%. As the customer does not know the importance of airtightness, he drops this feature to decrease costs.*” [Ramaekers, 2013].

2.1.3.3 Building sector barrier: Lack of knowledge and education of professionals

The lack of knowledge and education of building sector professionals (including architects and financiers) can have a number of adverse effects:

- Wrong or conflicting advice may deter potential investors;
- Low quality work by professionals may lead to negative feedbacks from customers, thus deterring potential investors belonging to the customer’s social network;
- Poorly executed (deep) renovations of buildings lead to a lock-in, because those buildings will not be renovated for many years to come.

There is a major shortage of qualified workers in the Belgian construction industry. The quality of existing training courses can also be improved.

[BUILD UP Skills Belgium, 2013]

BUILD UP Skills Belgium (BUSB) identified a number of barriers to arriving at a population of construction workers with a suitable level of competency. The barriers were confirmed by 30% or more of respondents surveyed [p. 9]:

- a shortage of qualified workers (irrespective of training);
- a shortage of trained workers;
- a high-quality execution of contracts does not offer any economic added value;
- the existing training courses are too theoretical;
- the existing manpower allocation does not offer any opportunity to enter into any results or performance commitments;
- technical progress is not being followed up on soon enough;
- the way in which the work is organised does not allow workers to be sent for training;
- the cost of training is too high to send workers for training;
- there are no results or performance commitments included in the scope of contract execution.

In Flanders, stakeholders, policy-makers and building sector professionals all point to a lack of knowledge and skills of building professionals regarding energy efficiency measures.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "... only 25% of building professionals have an adequate knowledge of energy efficiency measures and techniques." The cause is insufficient education. "Young professionals who enter the labour market lack knowledge about the latest energy efficiency techniques and materials due to inadequate education." However, as of 2014, "...curricula in technical schools will cover more techniques on energy efficiency." Also, architects seem to be more up to date. "Architects are more knowledgeable of trends and novelties regarding energy efficiency. They have to keep up with the regulations for the construction of new buildings." [Ramaekers, 2013];
- Enterprise culture is partly responsible for the lack of education. "... small contracting enterprises have difficulties to afford to send their employees on training. Especially older managers do not see the need to waste valuable working hours of themselves or their staff." [Vermeiren, 2013];
- There is a need for more cross-competence education. "Building professionals need to learn about techniques outside of their own field of expertise as techniques from different fields increasingly need to be integrated. Only then a more holistic functioning of the building chain is possible." [Matthys, 2013]

In Wallonia, some professionals appear to be less knowledgeable on energy issues than some home owners.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- "No professional, no professional is interested at the problem of insulation. For them, it is ... it is a chore. And in general, anything related to energy has no interest for the professionals. They really focus on the aspects [related to] installations, mechanics, and the aesthetics of the result. But insulation, no, not at all. Furthermore, in general, they rather don't care about regulations.";
- One respondent spoke about a (window) frames installer who found triple-glass windows "exaggerated" and "not worthwhile for our house";

- Another respondent interested in new technologies recounts how a heating installer did not want to expound on the topic of condensing boilers. "... it was by far too complicated and he didn't want to go into that." [Flore].

It may also be the case of the blind leading the blind.

[Mlecknik et al, 2010]:

Activity in the building sector in Belgium is often organized around three loosely interacting actors, the client, the architect and the contractor.

- *"In practice, for small constructions, the client often takes the role of a not very well informed commissioning agent. The architect (when involved) tries to make the best choices from a budget imposed by the client, while his environmental knowledge is often limited. The contractor remains often the executor of a task that the design team has specified by means of plans and often informal discussions. In practice, this situation often leads to conflicts in the definition of responsibilities."* [p. 64]

2.1.3.4 Building sector barrier: Structure of the building sector

When there is a large number of small companies each specialized in their own domain, responsibilities throughout each stage of design, construction and operation are fragmented over many actors, who tend to focus on individual products at the detriment of 'holistic' solutions.

The Flemish "Bouwunie", a union of small building enterprises in Flanders, counts 8,000 members. The Flemish "Vlaamse Confederatie Bouw", a confederation accepting every type of building enterprise in the Flemish region, counts 9,000 members. For a small region like Flanders this indicates a very scattered structure of the building sector.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "The building chain for renovations consist of a high number of small companies such as carpenters, general contractors, glaziers, builders etc." [Matthys, 2013];
- A more integrated approach is essential. "... retrofits need a holistic approach to obtain the most efficient, integrated solution." [Verspeel, 2013];
- "Building teams" may be part of the solution. "Building teams, in which professionals of different specializations work more closely together, could be a good solution for these problems." [Ramaekers, 2013];
- The Flemish market of building professionals (architects and contractors) is non-transparent. "... customers have little means to check the skills and reliability of building professionals. It is hard to compare building professionals." The "Bouwunie" introduced a label for energy-conscious contractors, but "... for building professionals still only a small fraction of the market is certified." [Bonnarens, 2013]

[Mlecknik et al, 2010]:

A more quality oriented building process as well as better collaboration within building teams is needed to understand the potentials and limitations of innovative energy saving technologies. The Belgian building sector needs to transition toward contractual energy performance requirements and quality insurance.

- Owner-occupants for low energy housing retrofits often do not require ambitious energy saving targets directly from the start of the building process. This often leads to "lack of quality and complicated building processes involving many different and sometimes inexperienced actors." [p. 65]
- "... a holistic approach is much needed in order to assure quality and market penetration of low energy housing retrofit." [p. 82]

- “...compared to ordinary renovation, low energy housing retrofit needs more holistic approaches, higher skill competence and stronger coordination in the planning and renovation process.” [p. 83]

Mlecknic et al [2010] also observe that “the building sector, as a whole, is reported as diverse, complex, conservative and characterized by fragmentation” [p. 83]

2.1.4 ASSESSMENT OF BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from ‘High’ to ‘Low’, taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report “Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport”.

Table 14 Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of Barrier	Barriers
High	Low priority – other attributes
	Attitude-Action gap
	Social interactions – credibility & trust
	Access to capital
	Structure of the building sector
	Low energy and transport related taxes
	Fragmentation of authority - interregional
	Fragmentation of authority - intraregional
	Discontinuity
	Administrative load
	Weak monitoring and evaluation
Medium	Behavioural spill-overs
	Lack of dissemination of information
	Badly presented information
	Information is too complex
	Inconsistent information
	Lack of knowledge about government support (imperfect information)
	Inability to estimate the magnitude of energy use (and related costs) (imperfect information)
	Lack of understanding how much energy (money) can be saved (imperfect information)
	Split incentives
	Principal-agent relationships
	Heterogeneity across end-users
	Hidden costs
	Adverse selection
	Lack of knowledge and education of building professionals
Legal barriers concerning split incentives	
Legal barriers concerning financial and technical conditions to subsidies	
Low	Bounded rationality
	Identity
	Risk – long payback periods and length of occupancy
	Old housing stock
	Urban legislation prohibiting façade insulation

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

There is very little empirical research on barriers in the transport sector in Belgium. We discuss two research projects, one on (the introduction) of electric vehicles [TRANS2HOUSE, 2013], and one on biofuels [BIOSES, 2012].

- The TRANSHOUSE2 project aimed to better understand the factors that influence household energy consumption and to formulate driving forces to shift existing barriers (social, cultural, technological, economic, legislative and political). The study also aimed to assess the transition towards electric vehicles (EVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) for Belgium and its regions.
- The BIOSES project looked into the practical feasibility and the ecological, socio-economic and macroeconomic impact of the introduction of biofuels in Belgium; and identified a number of barriers for the introduction of biofuels in the Belgian market.

Table 15 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Cultural	Low priority - Other attributes	People are reluctant to buy more efficient or “greener” vehicles because of limited driving ranges (esp. for electric cars; long charging times (in case of plug-in hybrid or battery electric vehicles)
Cultural	Attitude-Action gap	In spite of acclaimed positive attitudes toward “greener” vehicles, this does not lead to purchasing them
Social	Group influence	The social group one belongs to has a great influence on the purchase of a (more efficient) vehicle

2.2.1 BEHAVIOURAL BARRIERS

2.2.1.1 Behavioural barrier: Low priority of energy efficiency - Other attributes

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]:

Many factors influence the purchase decision of a car, including the “environmental friendliness” of the vehicle. Most consumers still opt for conventional internal combustion engine or ICE vehicles.

The “Vrije Universiteit Brussel” (VUB) asked 1196 Belgian respondents to evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of electric cars [VUB-MOBI, 2011]. Electric car refers to battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs).

The main advantages for buying electric cars, in order of importance, are:

1. The relative low cost per kilometre;
2. The green image;
3. The possibility to charge at home;
4. Cost factors such as government incentives;
5. The possibility to charge at work.

The possibility of smart-phone applications and the style and looks of electric vehicles are perceived as the least important advantages of electric vehicles.

The most critical disadvantages for the adoption of electric vehicles, in order of importance, are:

1. The high purchase price;
2. The limited driving range;
3. The scarcity of the charging infrastructure;
4. The long charging times;
5. The impossibility of charging at home when not having a private parking space or garage.

The absence of sound, the automatic transmission and the style and looks are perceived as the least important disadvantages of electric vehicles.

Price, space and range are seen as essential “characteristics” or “attributes” in the choice of a (city or road) car, whether it be a conventional car or an electric vehicle.

The main “barriers” linked to these attributes in the case of electric vehicles (EV) are:

- Their supposed power;
- Their autonomy;
- Their real advantages concerning the environment;
- Their supposed purchasing price.

There are however attractive “drivers” linked to electric vehicles, namely:

- The personal energy independence;
- The feeling of being inscribed in the track of progress;
- The reduction in the consumption of fossil fuels and energy in general.

[BIOSES, 2012]:

The sustainability aspect is an important attribute of biofuels. There is an ongoing debate on the potential risks of large scale biofuel (and other biomass) production.

2.2.1.2 Behavioural barrier: Attitude-Action gap

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]:

There can be a difference between the attitude consumers have towards a certain purchase and the final decision they make. This is called the “attitude-action gap” in literature.

2.2.1.3 Behavioural barrier: Social components of end-use behaviour

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]

The role of group influence on the consumer’s choice should not be neglected.

2.2.2 ECONOMIC BARRIERS

The following table lists the most relevant economic barriers in the transport sector in Belgium.

Table 16 Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of knowledge (imperfect information)	There is limited knowledge on more efficient or greener cars. Electric cars have a “weak spontaneous reputation”. Policy-makers and the public at large also lack knowledge on biofuels, in particular the “pure” biofuels.

Heterogeneity of end-users	The market for electric vehicles is situated in the first phase, the “innovators”, rather than early adopters or early majority.
Access to capital	People are reluctant to buy more efficient cars, electric cars in particular, because of the higher purchasing price. Biofuels are more expensive .

2.2.2.1 Economic barrier - market failure: Lack of knowledge (imperfect information)

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]

The purchase of a car is a “complex buying behaviour”. The gathering of knowledge during the decision-making process is regarded as very important, especially for new products that are relatively unknown to current customers. In this respect, the purchase of an electric vehicle has to be approached as a new technology acquisition.

[VUB-MOBI, 2011]:

- The knowledge on electric vehicles in Flanders is still very limited. This may have an impact on the attitude consumers have towards this new product;
- Electric vehicles have a weak reputation. Most Belgian respondents, even those who considered buying an electric vehicle, were unable to name a single brand. This contrasts sharply with hybrid vehicles, which the respondents mainly associated with the Toyota Prius. The “weak spontaneous reputation” of electric vehicles was seen by most potential buyers as one of the most important barriers.

[BIOSES, 2012]

Politicians, decision-makers and the general public in Belgium lack sufficient knowledge on biofuels, in particular the biofuels for higher blends or “pure biofuels”.

2.2.2.2 Economic barrier - non-market failure: Heterogeneity across end-users

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]

VUB-MOBI [2011] looks at 5 different types of consumer groups: the innovators, the early adopters, the early majority, the late majority and the laggard.

The market for electric vehicles is still situated in the first phase of the innovators.

2.2.2.3 Economic barrier - non-market failure: Access to capital

[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]

The total cost of ownership (TCO) of electric vehicles is higher compared to conventional (ICE) cars, in particular for city cars, as a result of the (much) higher purchase costs which are not adequately compensated for by the lower “fuel” costs of EVs.

[BIOSES, 2012]

Biofuels are more expensive than fossil fuels.

2.2.3 ORGANISATIONAL BARRIERS

The following table lists the most relevant economic barriers in the transport sector in Belgium.

Table 17 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of infrastructure	People are reluctant to buy more efficient or “greener” vehicles because of the scarcity of infrastructure (biofuels, electric or

	hydrogen)
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[TRANS2HOUSE, 2013]

Distribution grids with a relatively large density of electrical vehicles may require extensive infrastructure investments (cable reinforcements, installation of a transformer with higher rate, etc.) to maintain good power quality. An alternative is to integrate intelligence in the charging infrastructure of the electric vehicles.

[BIOSES, 2012]

- The most important technical barrier is the (in)compatibility of the existing car fleets to certain (future) biofuel blends. Existing models should be converted to higher biofuel compatibility; and flexi-fuel models should be introduced;
- A dedicated infrastructure may be needed for certain biofuels. The extra costs (e.g. for E85 pumps) can only be justified if there are clear market prospects;
- The biofuels have to be clearly standardized and checked for their quality, in order to create confidence with manufacturers and end-users alike.

2.2.4 ASSESSMENT OF BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report "Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport".

Table 18 Assessment of barriers in the transport sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Low priority - Other attributes
	Attitude-Action gap
	Group influence
	Access to capital
	Lack of infrastructure
Medium	Lack of knowledge (imperfect information)
	Heterogeneity of end-users

CHAPTER 3: MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

Institutional barriers are barriers caused by (state) government and local authorities. Almost all energy efficiency institutional barriers in Belgium relate to buildings as well as transport. They are therefore discussed together, after listing the most relevant ones for the building and transport sectors.

3.1 BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

The following table list the main driving factors for implementing energy efficiency in the building sector.

Table 19 Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social, cultural , educational	Low priority – other attributes	National	
	Bounded rationality	National	
	Attitude-Action gap	National	
	Behavioural spill-overs	National	
	Identity	National	
	Social interactions – credibility & trust	National	
	Lack of dissemination of information	National	
	Badly presented information	National	
	Information is too complex	National	
	Inconsistent information	National	
Economic	Lack of knowledge about government support (imperfect information)	National Regional	Energy guzzlers website
			www.energiesparen.be website
			Energy desks Wallonia Energy House
	Inability to estimate the magnitude of energy use (and related costs) (imperfect information)	National	
	Lack of understanding how much energy (money) can be saved (imperfect information)	Regional	Energy Performance Certificates
			Mandatory audit requirement
			Heating audit
	Split incentives	National	
	Principal-agent relationships	National	
	Heterogeneity across end-users	National	
Hidden costs	National		
Access to capital	National Regional Local	Federal personal income tax relief	
		Promotion of RUE by electricity distribution companies	
		Financial incentives encouraging RUE	

			Energy Renovation Programme 2020
			Building renovation subsidy
			Property tax reduction
			Ecopack UREBA Subsidies to improve Energy Efficiency of Public buildings
			Energy premiums
			Zero interest Brussels Green Loan
			FEDESCO
	Risk – long payback periods and length of occupancy	National	
Institutional	Old housing stock	Regional	Energy Performance Requirements Energy Renovation Programme 2020
	Adverse selection	National	
	Lack of knowledge and education of building sector professionals	National Regional	Flemish support programme for energy consultants
			Build Up Skills Belgium
			Energ'ethic Communities
			Employment-Environment Alliance
			Exemplary buildings
			Sustainable Building Facilitator Network
			Milieu- en Energietechnologie-innovatieplatform (MIP)
	Programme Mobilisateur ENERGYWALL		
	Structure of the building sector	Regional	
	Low energy and transport related taxes	National Regional	
	Fragmentation of authority - interregional	National Regional	
	Fragmentation of authority - intraregional	Regional	
Discontinuity	National Regional		
Administrative load	National Regional		
Legal barriers concerning split incentives	National Regional		
Legal barriers concerning financial and technical conditions to subsidies	National Regional		
Urban legislation prohibiting façade insulation	Regional		
Weak monitoring and evaluation	National Regional		

3.2 BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

The following table list the main driving factors for implementing energy efficiency in the building sector. The pure institutional barriers are not repeated, as they are the same for the buildings sector.

Table 20 Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social, cultural, educational	Low priority - Other attributes	National	
	Attitude-Action gap	National	
	Group influence	National	
Economic	Lack of knowledge (imperfect information)	National Regional	Green Mobility Plan
			Action plan to promote use of public transport
			CO2 guide of the clean vehicle
			www.ecoscore.be website
			Provincial Mobility Desks
			Eco-driving
			ReTiBo
			Test project on passenger vehicles
	Proeftuin elektrisch voertuig		
	Heterogeneity of end-users	National	
	Access to capital	National Regional	Fiscal benefits for commuting by bike
			Fiscal benefits for commuting by car-pooling
			Deductibility under corporate tax of expenses related to the use of company cars
			Tax exemptions for surplus value upon ship sale
			80/20% system for public transport season tickets
Green car registration tax			
Flanders Commuter Fund			
Ecobonus-Ecomalus			
Bruxell'air premium			
Institutional	Lack of infrastructure	National	

3.3 REVIEW OF BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN BUILDING AND TRANSPORT SECTOR

3.3.1 LOW ENERGY AND TRANSPORT RELATED TAXES

The energy market prices do not reflect all social and environmental social costs. Energy is subsidized and externalities are not included in the price of energy. This makes the upfront cost of energy efficiency investments higher compared to (discounted) future financial savings of the investment.

Energy and transport related taxes in Belgium are lower than the EU-average, due to the comparatively low taxation of heat, electricity and transport fuels (although taxation on transport vehicles is above average).

[IMF, 2013]:

- Post-tax subsidies in Belgium are 0.21% of GDP for natural gas and 0.09% for coal (this is 0.42% and 0.19% of government revenue).

[Ecofys and WWF, 2011]:

- Energy tax levels in Belgium are relatively low for households and [transport](#).

[FGTB Wallonne, 2011]:

- Institutional complexity in Belgium hinders the implementation of comprehensive fiscal policies.

[Wallenborn, 2007]:

- Belgian stakeholders in the area of residential energy consumption (architects, contractors, heating installers, energy advisors, energy administration, ...) perceive subsidies *"... to be good tools for communication but of rather limited effectiveness when it came to influencing energy consumption."*
- Belgian households differed on what would prompt them to pay more attention to their energy consumption, but there was general agreement on *"high energy prices"*, along with more regulation, better visualisation of energy consumption and its environmental impacts, and personalised advice.

3.3.2 FRAGMENTATION OF AUTHORITY BETWEEN FEDERAL AND REGIONAL AUTHORITIES AND BETWEEN REGIONS

Belgium is a federal state, where most of the authority related to energy efficiency regulations is situated at the level of the Flemish, Walloon and Brussels-Capital regions. The strong degree of decentralization of energy policy in Belgium leads to regional fragmentation.

[Ecofys and WWF, 2011, p. 3]:

- *"While at the regional level there were some ambitious approaches, there was an overall lack of harmonisation across the measures, and those issues which required national level solutions often lagged behind."*

[Estache & Kaufmann, 2011]:

- *"The degree of autonomy of the various government levels is such that coordination needs are extremely high."* CONCERE/ENOVERE is a good step in the direction of

better coordination, but overlap and duplication of efforts are still all too common in Belgium. This leads to confusion among investors and consumers.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "... contractors have to cope with different regulations if they work in the Brussels-capital region or in Flanders." [Verspeel, 2013].

3.3.3 FRAGMENTATION OF AUTHORITY WITHIN THE REGIONS

Energy efficiency policies are related to other domains, in particular housing. In Flanders the energy policies are crafted by the Flemish Ministry of Energy and executed by the Flemish Energy Administration (VEA). It is entirely possible to obtain subsidies for insulating the roof of a dwelling in Flanders, whereas at the same time this dwelling has to be demolished because of poor structural quality.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "... both policy fields should more closely consult with each other." This is not evident. "The two policy fields have different priorities. A social housing policy should ensure affordable housing for everyone. Energy efficiency policies try to minimize carbon dioxide emissions. That is why the cabinets of energy and housing do not want to merge." [VEA, Tanghe and Bieseman, 2012];
- From 2009 to 2014 one Minister was responsible for both the Flemish energy and housing portfolio. "The fact that the housing and energy portfolios were with one minister, was seen by many people as a chance to integrate the energy and housing policy more closely. Until now, this has only marginally been the case though." [Vermeiren, 2013].

Several institutions in Belgium and its regions offer incentives independently of each other to encourage investments in energy efficiency, leading to a crisscross of incentives. For example, incentives for energy efficiency measures are provided for by:

- The federal government (tax cuts for a variety of energy efficiency measures, although the number of tax cuts has decreased significantly in recent years);
- The regional governments (e.g. renovation subsidies by the Flemish government);
- The provinces and municipalities within a region;
- The energy distributors within a region.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- "People are confused by the multitude of institutions offering support. They don't know where to start in the crisscross of incentives." [Claessens and Ledeganck 2012]

[IWEPS, 2014]:

In Wallonia, an evaluation of the "First Employment-Environment Alliance" policy package recommended that:

- *"To improve the visibility of the policies, it would be interesting to avoid complex and diversified incentive structures. We recommend a simplification of the package of incentive measures targeted on households."* [p. 2]
- Special attention would be paid to informing the sector's professionals, in particular on the offers of vocational training. The majority of companies said that they needed to be trained on the new energy-saving techniques and materials, but among those most were apparently unaware of the training-cheque system proposed by the Employment-Environment Alliance.

3.3.4 DISCONTINUITY AND LACK OF TRANSPARENCY

There is a lot of uncertainty about government policies in Belgium, because policy-makers change their policies frequently and without a clear transition period, making it difficult to stay up-to-date. For example, at the end of 2011 the federal government quite suddenly and unexpectedly abolished many of the tax cuts on energy efficiency investments.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- People abhor discontinuity. "... people are sceptical about government support. They fear that such support is too good to be true and it will suddenly be abolished, as was the fact with the federal tax cuts for energy efficiency measures." [Verspeel, 2013];
- People prefer transparent time paths showing the future evolution of policy support. "... a certain group of people only decides to invest in energy efficiency measures, when they know subsidies will disappear within a certain time period." [Claessens and Ledeganck, 2012];
- Regulations provide more certainty than subsidies. "... subsidies are more instable than regulation, because subsidies are always re-evaluated during budgetary decisions." [Schaerlaekens, 2013].

[IWEPS, 2014]:

In Wallonia, the evaluation of the "First Employment-Environment Alliance" policy package deplored the frequent changes to the content of the policy instruments (granting criteria, financial conditions, technical requirements, etc.), hampering the ability of companies to provide households with updated information..

- *"Household demand for sustainable renovation works is highly sensitive to the changes of the technical and financial conditions relating to the public incentive systems. Consequently, overly abrupt or too frequent changes of the legislation are likely to induce erratic variations of demand..."* [p. 2].

3.3.5 ADMINISTRATIVE LOAD

Administrative load is on the one hand a burden to professionals.

[As quoted by Depouillon, 2013]:

- For example, "...contractors of boilers either need a quality certificate or have to prove their work is in line with quality requirements." [Matthys, 2013];
- "... especially contractors and boiler installers are subject to a high administrative burden concerning certification of their work. ... This administrative work takes time they cannot use to install boilers. Professionals have to charge this time to their customers." [Bonnarens, 2013];

Administrative load is on the other hand also a burden to customers. To obtain government support (e.g. tax cuts or subsidies) they have to cope with different application forms from a variety of institutions.

[Minaraad and SERV, 2012]:

- A more automated approach in granting subsidies would be preferable.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- Subsidies granted by the Walloon region should be “less time consuming for the search of information, involve less administrative and calculation work and competence ...”

3.3.6 LEGAL BARRIERS CONCERNING SPLIT INCENTIVES

Federal regulation makes it difficult to solve the split incentives barrier.

[BECO, 2010]:

- Due to federal regulations, a Belgian landlord in most cases is not allowed to raise the rent after an energy efficiency investment, even if the tenant would agree with such an arrangement. Firstly, the investment would have to raise the value of the building by more than 10% to justify a raise in the rent. This is seldom the case for the type of energy efficiency investments the Belgian government (as of 2010) stimulates (low cost separate components, no deep retrofits). Secondly, the frequency with which the landlord is allowed to raise the rent is restricted to every three years.

3.3.7 LEGAL BARRIERS CONCERNING FINANCIAL AND TECHNICAL CONDITIONS TO SUBSIDIES

Respondents complained that subsidies granted by the Walloon region should be affordable for all homeowners, including the low-income ones; and they should also be available for DIY persons who do the work themselves.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- Several respondents in Wallonia grumbled that one has to advance the money for the renovation works, before receiving the subsidies. *“Because I have bought [the house] four years ago, I have no money and at the same time, I have in practice no access to the subsidies. (...) To have access to the subsidies, money is needed because to be able to invest is needed.”* [Full-time employee, BA degree, living alone];
- A few respondents in Wallonia complained that not all renovation works are covered by the subsidies (e.g. building walls with traditional mud and straw techniques) or for those who wish to do the energy-related renovation (e.g. wall insulation) themselves. *“...there is a kind of policy to boost employment – not only to encourage energy savings – but in addition to have perhaps a less skilled labour force back on the labour market (...) but still, I find that the difference is too important between the two scenarios and I find that there should be instead a subsidy, maybe lower, for people doing it themselves, and then the higher one for people asking a contractor.”* [a DIY respondent]

3.3.8 BUILDING REGULATION BARRIER: URBAN LEGISLATION PROHIBITING EXTERIOR INSULATION OF FRONT FAÇADE

City regulations requiring a uniform alignment of the façades and thus equally wide pavements may prohibit exterior insulation of the (front) façade.

[Bartiaux, 2011]:

- Respondents in Wallonia with façades they are not allowed to touch because of city regulations told they were not interested in insulation from the inside, because that would mean losing space (and taking down all radiators, as one respondent added).

This particular legal barrier no longer exists in the Flemish region.

3.3.9 EXTREMELY WEAK MONITORING AND EVALUATION

[Estache & Kaufmann, 2011]:

- "... monitoring and evaluation of energy efficiency policies and of their effectiveness is particularly weak in Belgium." This makes enforcement of the policies a lot more complex.

CHAPTER 4: KEY FINDINGS

The key findings in terms of barriers are:

- The housing stock in Belgium on average is old; and both demolition and renovation (retrofit) rates are low (below EU averages);
- Although both consumers (households) and building professionals in Belgium still lack considerable knowledge as far as energy efficiency measures and policy instruments are concerned, (qualitative) research seems to indicate that more or better knowledge has little or no effect on energy-related behaviour. This begs the question whether the numerous policy initiatives in Belgium to tear down the so-called imperfect knowledge barrier are really all that effective and efficient?;
- Social networks in Belgium matter a lot. Even the best advice of the most competent professional will not be accepted, if it is not corroborated by the opinions and experiences of relatives, friends, colleagues, ... (even if those networks are not as competent as they claim to be);
- The “attitude-action gap” is very real in Belgium. Households or individuals aware of energy-related and environmental issues (e.g. energy efficiency, renewables, climate change), or who claim to be, in general do not behave in more (or less) energy efficient ways than others;
- Energy efficiency has low priority, simply because households (even the environmentally aware ones) are much more attracted to other attributes of the products (i.e. dwellings, vehicles), such as thermal, visual and acoustic comfort, aesthetics, safety and health, ...;
- The financial barrier is real, especially for lower-income households. Although Belgium (or rather its regions) provide a large number of instruments to compensate the high initial investment costs, consumers are confused by the plethora of subsidies, premiums, tax rebates, etc.; or are simply not aware that they exist.

Key findings in terms of policies and barriers are:

- The most typical policy obstacle for Belgium is the extreme complexity of its state structure. Energy-related policies continuously overlap. Competences are very fragmented, not only between the federal state and the regions, but also between various authorities within the different regions. Attempts to improve coordination are rarely successful. The “sixth state reform”, in progress, is not likely to improve matters (on the contrary, competences will be even more fragmented);
- The administrative burden to obtain subsidies is too high, and subsidies may not reach the right households;
- Energy-related taxes are low in Belgium, and do not provide much of an incentive. But households themselves clearly indicate that higher energy prices (internalisation of externalities) would steer them to more energy efficient behaviour. As economists are known to say: “Prices do matter!”. This should also be viewed from the perspective of Belgian stakeholders who see the multitude of subsidies more as “a tool of communication” rather than as an instrument to accomplish behavioural changes;
- The effectiveness of Belgian federal and regional energy-related policies is severely hindered by the lack of adequate monitoring and evaluation.

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WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORT FOR BULGARIA

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ABBREVIATIONS USED

Abbreviation	Description
BGN	Bulgarian Lev (National currency)
CITA	Corporate Income Tax Act
CFL	Compact Fluorescent Lamp
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EE	Energy efficiency
EEA	Energy Efficiency Act
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EERSF	Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund
ESCO	Energy Service Company
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Green house gases
KIDSF	Kozloduy International Decommissioning Support Fund
LED	Lighting Emitting Diode
ME	Ministry of Energy
MEE	Ministry of Economy and Energy
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
NREAP	National Renewable Energy Action Plan
NSI	National Statistical Institute
NZEB	Nearly zero-energy buildings
REECL	Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line
RES	Renewable energy sources
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SEDA	Sustainable Energy Development Agency
SNEEAP	Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
TOE	Tons Oil Equivalent

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Building sector

According to the National Statistical Institute residential buildings in Bulgaria amount to about 3,9 million. Around 66% of them are located in towns. The average number of persons living in a household is 2,4 (2,4 in towns and 2,5 in villages). The buildings constructed before 1970 are 60% and the ones constructed in the period 2000 – 2011 – only 0,5% (NSI 2015b). The higher number of buildings constructed before 1990 show low energy performance and these buildings need renovation in order to improve the indoor comfort and optimize the energy expenses for heating and cooling.

In Bulgaria, 96,6% of the building stock is owned by physical persons, 1% by companies and 2,4% by municipal or state authorities (Census 2011). Therefore, most of the efforts should be directed to private houses owners in order to reach the energy efficiency targets set.

The EU energy directives have been fully transposed and Bulgaria has adopted national energy efficiency targets, supported by acts, action plans, strategies, etc.

The main barriers to the successful implementation of the policy framework are economic, social, and educational.

Transport sector

Transport is the most energy intensive economic sector in Bulgaria. Its share in the total energy demand amounts to 33%. The energy consumption in the period 2000 – 2011 had been directly connected to the GDP growth/ decreasing. In the last years the energy intensity of the sector correlated with the GDP has decreased compared to the levels in the year 2000. The energy consumption increase before the world financial crisis had been 3,5%/year and after 2007 it started decreasing (Nikolova & Minkov 2014).

In 2012 the share of car transport in fuel consumption was in average 86%, of air-transportation – 5%, railroad – 1,37%. The energy used by cars increases by 4% each year, and by air-transportation - by 6,7%. Railroad transport suffers from a decrease of the share by 5,5%/year, not because of implementation of energy efficiency measures, but due to the significant decrease of transportation loads (Nikolova & Minkov 2014).

The efforts in the field of energy efficiency have been directed mainly towards residential and municipal sectors as most energy intensive. The policy framework in the transport sector is still to be elaborated in order to meet the more efficient requirements.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 CONTEXT

Building and transport sectors in Bulgaria possess vast potential for implementation of energy saving measures. The poor energy efficiency performance in those sectors is mainly due to keeping up of low energy prices for a long time period. The easily accessible energy resources have driven to high intensity in all energy related processes. In the last years a progress in decreasing the energy demand has been made and the EU energy directives have been fully transposed into the Bulgarian legislation along with the development of many strategies, action plans and information campaigns at national and local levels.

1.1.1 Energy policy

The body responsible for the elaboration of energy policy in Bulgaria is the Ministry of Energy (ME). The Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) is the executive authority within the Ministry of Energy, which monitors and evaluates the implemented by the obligated parties measures, and supports the development and actualization of the strategies and action plans.

In 2011 Bulgaria adopted an Energy Strategy until 2020, which identifies the resources for promotion of energy efficiency in the country. It corresponds to the current EU energy policy framework and reflects the global trends in energy efficiency technologies. The strategy aims at the overcoming of the following major challenges (MEET 2011):

- Very high intensiveness of GDP. The energy needed for production of one unit GDP is higher than the EU average by 89% (considering the parity of purchasing power).
- Dependency on fuel imports. Bulgaria imports more than 2/3 of its gross energy demand, mainly from the Russian Federation.
- Need of securing the country’s sustainable development and reducing greenhouse gases emissions.

Fig. 1. Primary and final energy efficiency, 2000 – 2012, kgtoe/BGN, 2005

Source: SEDA 2014

The main priorities set by the Energy Strategy can be grouped into five main directions (MEET 2011):

- To provide conditions for securing the energy supply;
- To achieve the targets set for energy produced from renewable sources;
- To increase the energy efficiency;
- To establish a competitive energy market and to elaborate appropriate policy framework to meet the present and future energy needs;
- To protect the consumers' rights and interests.

The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (SEDA 2014) sets the national goals and obligations for increasing the energy efficiency during the period 2014 – 2020. It includes horizontal measures and measures for energy efficiency in all sectors (buildings, public bodies, end-use energy efficiency (including in transport and industry), promotion of efficient heating and cooling, and energy transformation, transmission, distribution and consumption.

1.1.2 Actors involved in the attainment of energy efficiency targets

The parties, obligated for reaching the targets are the energy and fuel distributors and/or retail sales companies, which meet the following criteria (ME 2015a):

1. Sales of energy to final users in the previous calendar year greater than the equivalent of 75 GWh (6,45 ktoe) p.a. and includes:

- Traders selling electricity to final energy users in amounts exceeding 75 GWh/y;
- Transmission companies selling heat energy to final users in amounts exceeding 75 GWh/y;
- Natural gas traders selling more than 8 million normal cubic meters p.a. to final energy users;
- Liquid fuel traders selling in amounts exceeding 6,5 thousand tonnes p.a., excluding transport fuels, to final energy users;
- Solid fuel traders selling in amounts exceeding 13 thousand tonnes p.a. to final energy users;

2. Employers with more than 10 people employed in the previous year;

3. Companies with turnover and/or balance sheet position at the end of the previous year of more than BGN 3,9 million in respect of energy trading.

The obligations scheme does not include distributors and retailers of fuels for the transport sector.

The energy efficiency policy defined in accordance with the requirements of Directive 2006/32/EC is based on the fulfilment of the individual energy saving targets as a leading factor for the successful implementation of energy efficiency measures (SEDA 2014).

Article 10 of the Energy Efficiency Act states that the national energy saving goal is allocated in the form of individual energy saving targets to three groups of obligated parties (ME 2015a):

- Energy traders;
- Owners of state and/or municipal buildings in use with total floor area of more than 1 000 m² (since 12 March 2013 the threshold became 500 m² and after 9 July 2015 the certification threshold is reduced to 250 m²);
- Owners of industrial systems consuming more than 3 000 MWh/year.

The obliged parties should attain the overall aim of 5 984 GWh (516 toe) reduction, which accounts for 82% of the overall national energy saving target. The remaining 18% are expected to be achieved by the final energy users, who are not targeted by obligation (ME 2015a).

Individual energy savings targets for owners of buildings with a total floor area of more than 1 000 m² are within the aggregate amount of 521,03 GWh (ME 2015a).

1.1.3 Breakdown of energy use by sectors, thousands of toe

The table below provides a historical overview of the final energy consumption in the country by sectors.

Table 1. Final energy consumption by sectors, thousands of toe

Sectors	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Industry	3689	3831	3451	2443	2549	2693	2576	2579
Transport	2801	2678	2832	2772	2738	2722	2871	2604
Households	2183	2073	2125	2149	2262	2391	2377	2257
Agriculture	295	265	186	183	184	204	198	193
Tertiary	911	899	958	939	987	1040	1021	964

Source: NSI 2015a

The next tables present the shares of the different means of transportation in the energy consumption of the sector.

Table 2. Actual and forecasted share of means of transportation

Year	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Transport sector	Gpkm (Giga passenger kilometre)										
Passenger transport activity	47,7	56	65,5	68,3	71	73,8	76,8	79,4	82	83,7	85,5
Public road transport	14,6	13,7	10,6	10,9	11,2	11,5	11,9	12,2	12,5	12,6	12,7
Private cars and motorcycles	27,5	35,8	47,9	49,1	50	50,9	51,8	52,9	53,7	54	54,1
Rail	3,9	2,8	3	3,4	3,8	4,1	4,4	4,5	4,7	4,8	4,9
Aviation	1,7	3,6	3,9	4,8	6	7,2	8,7	9,8	11,1	12,3	13,7
Inland navigation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Freight transport activity	Gtkm (Gigatonne kilometre)										

Year	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Trucks	6,4	14,4	19,4	20,6	21,8	23,1	24,5	26	27,5	28,4	29,3
Rail	5,5	5,2	3,1	3,5	4	4,6	5,2	5,5	5,8	6	6,2
Inland navigation	0,3	0,8	1,2	1,4	1,5	1,6	1,8	1,9	2	2,1	2,1

Source: Capros et al 2013

The statistical data presented in the above tables have been taken from the PRIMES project (Capros et al 2013) and it bases on the Eurostat and the publications “EU Energy in Figures” of Directorate General for Mobility and Transport (European Commission). Usually the energy demand in transport reflects sales of fuels at the point of refuelling, which do not represent automatically the regional consumption. Road freight transport activity is defined at national level, due to the lack of sufficiently long time series of territorially segregated data. These differences should be borne in mind when comparing energy and transport figures. This applies in particular to transport activity ratios, such as energy efficiency in freight transport, which is measured in tonnes of oil equivalent per million tonne-km (Capros et al 2013).

Table 3. Energy intensity of the economy in Bulgaria

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
toe for 1000 EUR GDP (2005 = 100)	0,854	0,853	0,827	0,751	0,701	0,647	0,655	0,690	0,658	0,603

Source: NSI 2015a

1.2 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

1.2.1 Buildings sector

Regulatory mechanisms

The Energy Efficiency Act (EEA) (ME 2015a) is the main policy tool that regulates the delivery of energy services in Bulgaria. Chapter III, section VI sets out the main provisions about this process, which concern the legal entities registered under the Bulgarian Law on Commerce or under the meaning of another Member State’s legislation, particularly energy traders and provision of energy services to energy end users. The Regulation issued under Art. 9 (2) of the EEA provides the methods for assessment of the achieved energy savings. In addition, the Regulation No. RD-16-347 of 2 April 2009 on the conditions and procedure for the establishment and payment of the funds planned under Energy Performance Contracts sets out the financial mechanisms for the activities of ESCO contractors.

Financial mechanisms

The Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund (EERSF) was established in 2004 under the EEA with intergovernmental agreements between the Global Environment Facility (through the World Bank), the Government of Austria and the Government of Bulgaria. It is a state-independent body, operating according to the provisions of the Energy Efficiency Act, the Energy from Renewable Sources Act and the agreements with the Donors, and is not part of the consolidated state budget. Its main purpose is to provide low interest loans or loan guarantees and technical consultations. The Fund is expected to play a major role in developing the energy services market as a co-financing and guarantee institution for ESCO services contracts (EERSF 2015).

The National Trust EcoFund was established in October 1995 by the Debt-for-Environment swap agreement between the Government of the Confederation of Switzerland and the Government of the Republic of Bulgaria. Pursuant to Article 66(1) of the Environment Protection Act, the objective of the Fund is to manage the proceeds from Debt-for-Environment and Debt-for-Nature swaps, from international trade in GHG assigned amount units and from the sale of GHG emission allowances for aviation activities, as well as proceeds from other types of agreements with international, foreign or Bulgarian sources for financing environmental protection activities in the country. The Fund supports the implementation of the Bulgarian government's policy and the country's international commitments in the area of environmental protection. To date, the Fund has financed 100 projects with a total amount of around BGN 24 million (National Trust EcoFund 2015).

The National Trust EcoFund is an independent institution, supported by the Bulgarian government.

The Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Credit Line (BEERECL) was established to support the private investments in energy efficiency measures in the industrial sector and the investments in small-scale renewable energy sources projects. Since its beginning, EUR 155 million have been utilized to support 230 sustainable energy projects by disbursing EUR 135,7 million in loans and EUR 21,5 million in grants (subsidies). These projects have reduced the Bulgarian carbon dioxide emissions by more than 682 000 tonnes CO₂ per year and have replaced 1 047 000 MWh of electrical capacity at NPP Kozloduy with green energy resources that are sufficient to cover the electricity demand of approximately 310 000 households. BEERECL closed in January 2014 (BEERECL 2015).

The Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL) was created in 2005 as a joint initiative of the Bulgarian Government, the EBRD and the KIDSF. Its liquidity consisted of an EBRD loan for EUR 90 million and a KIDSF grant of EUR 24,6 million. Six local banks (UBB, Raiffeisenbank, ProCredit Bank, DSK Bank, SIBANK and Pireos bank) provide technical partnership to the EBRD through distribution of low interest loans for energy efficiency and RES projects in households. In addition to the loan, the facility provides pro bono technical assistance and grant funding of up to 35% of the loan. The greater interest caused extension of the credit line and the available financial resources amount to EUR 40 million in loans and EUR 14 million in grants. More than 20 000 households have received support from this financial instrument (REECL 2015).

Structural and Investment Funds in the new programming period will continue to support the implementation of the European 2020 policy. The financial instruments for 2014 - 2020 are of revolving type, which makes the repayment usable for new investments. The support is provided through loans, guarantees, equity and other risk-bearing instruments. The beneficiaries can combine the funding with interest rate subsidies or guarantee fee subsidies to leverage private funding. In this manner, the EU funds can effectively increase the impact of the public money spending and stimulate financially sustainable investments instead of using grants to fund energy efficiency. (EU SIF 2015)

Legislative measures

Measures based on the Energy Efficiency Act (ME 2015a):

- Development of a national plan to increase the number of nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEB), including a national definition of NZEB and the criteria they must meet, time span, national targets aimed at increasing the number of NZEB in the various classes of buildings, as well as policies and mechanisms, including financial ones, to promote the construction of this type of buildings.
- Introduction of individual energy saving targets for owners of buildings with a total floor area of more than 1 000 m² within the aggregate amount of 521,03 GWh.

- Introduction of mandatory certification of public buildings with a total floor area of more than 500 m²; after 9 July 2015 the certification threshold is reduced to 250 m².
- Introduction of obligation that after reconstruction, rehabilitation or major renovation of a building in use, the energy performance of the building or of its renovated parts must be improved to a level that corresponds to the minimum energy performance requirements insofar as this is technically feasible and economically justified. Conformity with the energy efficiency requirements is deemed to have been achieved in the following cases:
 - New buildings under design or construction: when the calculated values of the indicators correspond to Class B in the energy consumption scale;
 - Existing buildings: when the calculated values of the indicators correspond to:
 - at least Class C in the energy consumption scale for buildings commissioned between 1991 and 2009 inclusive;
 - at least Class D in the energy consumption scale for buildings commissioned in 1990 or earlier.
- The energy saving measures recommended for each reconstruction, rehabilitation or major renovation of a building in use or parts thereof will be assessed in respect of the technical and economic feasibility of the use of alternative high efficiency systems.
- When a building or individual parts of a building are sold or let, the seller/lessor must provide the buyer with the energy performance certificate of the building. The owners of apartments in multi-family buildings are entitled to receive a notarised copy of the energy performance certificate of the building, while the original certificate is kept by the building manager.
- Requirement for inspections of heating systems that use water boilers with a rated heating capacity of more than 20 kW and of air conditioning systems with a rated electric capacity of more than 12 kW in public services buildings. The objective is to establish how efficiently they are operated and to identify efficiency improvement measures. The inspections consist of:
 - assessment of the conformity of the existing configuration, operation and maintenance;
 - assessment of the actual energy performance;
 - formulation of recommendations for feasible energy performance improvements in order to reduce the use of energy resources and carbon dioxide emissions.
- Management of energy efficiency in buildings.

Measures based on the Energy from Renewable Sources Act (ME 2015b):

The Energy from Renewable Sources Act requires the introduction of systems for production of energy from RES, when this is technically feasible and economically justified, as part of the construction of new buildings or reconstruction, major renovation, rehabilitation or rebuilding of existing buildings. This requirement applies to public services buildings as from 1 January 2012 and will apply to all other buildings after 31 December 2014. The analysis of the options for the use of renewable energy is part of the estimation of the annual energy consumption of the building.

In this case, at least 15% of the building's overall demand for heating and cooling energy must be met by renewable sources through the introduction of:

- a central heating source using biomass or geothermal energy;

- individual biomass combustion equipment with transformation efficiency of at least 85% in residential or commercial buildings and at least 70% in industrial buildings;
- solar heating systems;
- heat pumps and ground-connected geothermal systems.

Strategic measures

Since 2008 the local and central bodies have been obliged by the law to develop action plans and strategies on improving the energy efficiency of the building stock owned by them. Art. 5(7) of the Energy Efficiency Directive provides for an alternative way to reach the minimum requirements for energy performance of the buildings by obliging the local and central authorities to renovate every year at least 3% of the total heated and cooled floor area occupied by their administrations.

Every year the obligated owners of public buildings submit to the Sustainable Energy Development Agency reports based on requirements of Art. 12 of the EEA (ME 2015a) on the level of attainment of their individual energy saving targets set in the Local Energy Efficiency Plans (SEDA 2014).

According to these reports 1 718 projects were completed in 2013, a part of them concerning public street lighting (SEDA 2014).

Renovation of buildings is supported through tax reduction stimuli. The Local Taxes and Fees Act (LTFA 2015) states that buildings are not taxed for 7 or 10 years (the longer period applies if RES measures are implemented) if they had been built before:

- 1st January 2005 and have received Class B for energy performance;
- 1st January 1990 and have received Class C for energy performance.

Buildings are not subject to taxation for 3 or 5 years (the longer period applies if RES measures are implemented) if they had been built (LTFA 2015):

- after 1st January 1990 and before 1st January 2005 and have received Class C for energy performance;
- before 1st January 1990 and have received Class D for energy performance.

Facilitate and promote demand response according to the provisions of the Art. 15 of the EED (Directive 2012/27/EU):

The legislation provides the introduction of dynamic tariffs as a measure for the final clients to optimise their electricity use by means of:

- tariffs that take into account the period in which energy is used;
- tariffs for the critical peak-load periods;
- pricing in real time;
- discounts for reducing the use of energy during peak-load periods.

Reduction of due taxes by 10% is available also through donation to EERSF (CITA 2015).

Another policy measure is the White Certificates scheme, which development and preparation have been part of the activities of the project “Strengthening the institutional capacity of SEDA to provide more and better services in the field of energy efficiency”, funded by the OP “Competitiveness of the Bulgarian Economy” 2007-2013, and which is under consultations with the national stakeholders (SEDA 2013).

1.2.2 Transport sector

Transport is the most energy intensive sector, which fuel consumption exceeds that of the industry. In the last years the number of vehicles increased at the expense of the more efficient and ecological rail transport. Special attention should be paid in the coming years in order to mitigate the consequences in the sector. The following measures are undertaken to reach this objective (ME 2015a):

Legislative measures

The Energy from Renewable Sources Act and the Environmental Protection Act are the main legislative instruments to support energy savings in the transport sector.

Measures based on the Energy from Renewable Sources Act (ME 2015b):

The Act stipulates that the suppliers of petroleum-derived liquid transport fuels should deliver fuels for diesel and petrol engines blended with biofuels in certain proportions.

Measures based on the Environmental Protection Act (MOEW 2014):

The Act requires from suppliers of liquid transport fuels to reduce GHG emissions per energy unit of liquid fuels delivered against a fixed baseline level, and reach an overall reduction of 6% by 31 December 2020.

Strategic measures

Measures based on the National Action Plan on Climate Change (MOEW & ICC 2012):

- Rehabilitation and modernisation of the road infrastructure in order to allow for optimal travelling speeds and ensure that vehicle engines operate in the optimum mode;
- Introduction of intelligent transport systems on national roads and in urban environments;
- Increase of the share of biofuels;
- Reduction of the relative share of trips with private motor vehicles by improving public urban transport and promoting non-motorised transport;
- Development and promotion of the use of bicycles;
- Increase of the share of electrified urban transport by rail, metro, trolleybuses and tramcars;
- Development and construction of intermodal terminals for multimodal services;
- Development and promotion of the use of hybrid and electric vehicles;
- Ensuring that fiscal policy stimulates savings and less use of conventional fuels;
- Reduction of the number of urban transport vehicles using conventional fuels by 2020;
- Reduction of the freight transported more than 300 kilometres by road vehicles by changing it to more environmental modes of transport, including rail;
- Construction of railway connections between the central airport hubs of Sofia, Varna, Burgas, Plovdiv and Gorna Oryahovitsa;
- Sustainable transport statistics;
- Informed vehicle choices;
- Training in energy efficient driving.

Measures based on the National Renewable Energy Action Plan (NREAP) (MEET 2010):

- Promotion of the production of biofuels and requirement for state and municipal administrations to provide examples of good practices in the implementation of energy efficiency measures and RES use in the transport sector. When launching public procurements for new vehicles, municipalities should require the engines of the vehicles to be able to run on blended and pure biofuels.
- Establishment of a support scheme for transport operators where there are significant differences between the prices of conventional fuels and biofuels, following an analysis and assessment of the economic and environmental benefits from the use of biofuels.
- Improvement of the mechanisms for promotion of the use of biofuels, including second-generation biofuels, subject to sustainability criteria, and taking into account the specific characteristics of the entire process, from growing of primary materials to the use of biofuels in the transport sector.
- Increase of the number of electric vehicles and individual systems for production of electricity from RES in the transport sector by constructing and developing smart grids and electric vehicle charging stations. According to the report on the implementation of the “National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility 2012-2014”, adopted by the Council of Ministers on 17.10.2012, the total number of electric vehicles had risen by 61% by 31 December 2013, while the number of hybrids had increased by 119% in one year (new registrations of 366 electric and 586 hybrid vehicles) (MOEW 2014). The priorities for 2014 are mainly related to expanding the charging infrastructure.

Measures based on the Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (SEDA 2011):

- The implementation of the measure “Development of rail infrastructure, improvement of inland waterways navigation and expansion of metro transport” began in 2014. The measure aims to create conditions for the priority development of energy efficient modes of transport and includes the implementation of rail, inland waterways and metro projects under the Operational Programme “Transport and Transport Infrastructure 2014–2020”.
- Another measure in this sector, “Requirements for purchasing EE vehicles for the public sector and for the public transport sector”, was foreseen to be launched in 2014. The measure concerns the development of a regulatory framework laying down the minimum EE requirements for purchasing EE vehicles for the public sector and for the public transport sector, while the resources required for its implementation amount to BGN 56 million. The savings expected from the implementation of this measure by 2020 are estimated at 326 GWh/y (28 000 toe/y).

Table 4. Summary of the Bulgarian policy instruments in the building sector

Bulgarian policy instruments for the buildings sector	
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ordinance №7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings; • Ordinance №RD-16-932 of 23/10/2009 on the terms and conditions for energy efficiency inspection of boilers and air conditioning systems; • Ordinance №RD-16-1057 of 10/12/2009 on the conditions and procedures for conducting energy efficiency audits and certification of buildings, the issue of energy performance certificates and categories of certificates; • Ordinance №RD-16-1058 of 10/12/2009 on buildings indicators for energy consumption & performance;

Bulgarian policy instruments for the buildings sector	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspections of boilers and heating/cooling installations; • Heating cost regulation; • Energy performance certificate.
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information campaigns by SEDA; • Energy efficiency Bureau at Municipal administration in several municipalities; • Information campaigns by energy distributors.
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund (EERSF); • National Trust EcoFund; • Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Credit Line (BEERECL); • Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL) • Energy tax • Structural and Investment Funds
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated budget for energy performance contracting in public buildings • ESCO portfolio guarantees

Table 5. Summary of the Bulgarian policy instruments in the transport sector

Bulgarian policy instruments for the transport sector	
Planning Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitation and modernisation of the road infrastructure in order to allow for optimal travelling speeds and ensure that vehicle engines operate in the optimum mode; • Introduction of intelligent transport systems on national roads and in urban environments; • Reduction of the relative share of trips with private motor vehicles by improving public urban transport and promoting non-motorised transport; • Increase of the share of electrified urban transport by rail, metro, trolleybuses and tramcars; • Development and promotion of the use of bicycles; • Development and construction of intermodal terminals for multimodal services; • Development and promotion of the use of hybrid and electric vehicles; • Ensuring that fiscal policy stimulates savings and less use of conventional fuels; • Reduction of the number of urban transport vehicles using conventional fuels by 2020; • Reduction of the freight transported more than 300 kilometres by road vehicles by changing it to more environmental modes of transport, including rail; • Construction of railway connections between the central airport hubs of Sofia, Varna, Burgas, Plovdiv and Gorna Oryahovitsa; • Development of rail infrastructure, improvement of inland waterways navigation and expansion of metro transport
Regulatory instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the production of biofuels and requirement for state and municipal administrations to provide examples of good practices in the implementation of energy efficiency

Bulgarian policy instruments for the transport sector	
	measures and RES use in the transport sector. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public procurement requirements for new vehicles to be able to run on blended and pure biofuels. • CO2-emission standards on new vehicles • Increase of the number of electric vehicles and individual systems for production of electricity from RES in the transport sector by constructing and developing smart grids and electric vehicle charging stations; • Maintaining sustainable transport statistic
Economic instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and promotion of the use of bicycles; • Establishment of a support scheme for transport operators where there are significant differences between the prices of conventional fuels and biofuels, following an analysis and assessment of the economic and environmental benefits from the use of biofuels.
Information and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in energy efficient driving; • Informed vehicle choices.

1.3 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

The most commonly implemented energy efficiency measures include **replacing of windows, insulation of walls, roof and floors**. The average initial investment is around 60 EUR/m², which is not affordable for the ordinary people, and supporting policies for these measures have a major role for improving the energy performance in the building sector (BSERC 2015).

Gas boilers and gasification of households have limited penetration due to the lower prices of electricity, compared to natural gas. The low number of potential consumers of natural gas holds back the expansion of the gas network system.

Biomass fuelled room heaters, stoves and boiler systems are widely used in smaller settlements. The technologies that are mostly used are old and inefficient. In the last 10 years an increase of the share of high efficiency biomass heating installations has been marked. The price of firewood is about 20 EUR/MWh and of the wood pellets 27 – 30 EUR/MWh. The price of high efficiency heating boilers for firewood with capacity of 25 – 44 kW is 1500 – 2200 EUR, and for wood pellets with capacity of 22 – 52 kW - 2200 – 3000 EUR (BSERC 2015).

Solar collectors for hot water production represent a technology with significant increase of the share. The demonstration projects have led to many projects for replacement of electricity fuelled boilers. The price of conventional solar collectors is 80 – 110 EUR/m² and for heat pipe collectors about 150 EUR/m² (BSERC 2015).

The low level of electricity prices considerable increases the share of **highly efficient air-conditioning systems** for space heating and cooling. The price of an efficient air conditioner with Seasonal Condition of Performance (SCOP) 4,06 and heating capacity 4,8 kW is around 430 EUR (BSERC 2015).

Bulgaria has adopted a definition for “**Nearly zero energy consumption building**”, which puts the following parameters for these buildings (ME 2015a):

- energy consumption of the building, defined as primary energy, corresponds to class A of the scale of energy classes for the type of buildings;

- not less than 55 percent of the energy consumed (supplied) for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting is energy from renewable sources produced on-site at the building level or near the building.

Energy efficient street lighting technologies are represented at the Bulgarian market mainly through CFL and LED lighting fixtures. In households a common replacement of old incandescent bulbs is made with LED bulbs with 50-70 lm/W and in street lighting the replacement is with 18W, 2100 lm (BSERC 2015).

During the last several years the number of **electric and hybrid cars** has increased. In 2014 the number of electric cars was 497 and of hybrid cars - 1031 (ME & MOEW 2015).

The improvement of the quality of the **public transport vehicles** has been in the scope of many local actions. Replacement of the old, inefficient and uncomfortable buses with new **buses running on CNG or methane** is going on in most of the big towns.

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

The described barriers are based on the BSERC experts' opinion and map the present dynamic situation in Bulgaria. The literature on this topic is limited and out-of-date. References to other sources are made for some of the listed barriers as they are still present. In this sense, the HERON project will be the first to map completely the obstacles for increasing the share of energy efficiency implementation.

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

The barriers in the Bulgarian building sector are presented in the next tables.

Table 6. Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Tertiary or housing sector	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Tertiary and housing	Lack of finance	Often the initial capital is beyond affordability of the consumers. In addition, uncertainties in the investment payback period contribute to denial of loans for such projects.
Social	Tertiary and housing	Distortion of energy prices	The unstable prices of fuels and electricity make the energy end users uncertain in investing in EE technologies.
Social	Tertiary and housing	Low energy prices	The electricity prices in Bulgaria are the lowest in the EU. This market situation leads to ignoring the need of improving the energy performance of buildings.
Social	Tertiary and housing	Lack of social approval	There are not many demonstration projects yet, which leads to uncertainty of the economic profits for the consumers.
Social	Housing	Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing	The programme for building renovation requires 2/3 of the apartment owners to approve the energy efficiency measures implementation. This leads to difficulties in obtaining commitment to participate in such programmes.
Social	Tertiary and housing	Lack of trust in ESCOs	This barrier is interrelated to two other barriers - lack of standardized M&V practices and lack of customer demand (see Fig. 1). These call for standardization, either in a regulatory manner or by establishment of a voluntary agreement

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Tertiary or housing sector	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
			(e.g. Code of Conduct) (BSERC 2013)
Social	Housing	Split of incentives in house renting sector	In the case of rentals the tenant is receiving the benefits of less energy costs after the building owner invests in the property. This issue causes lack of willingness by the owner to implement EE measures, since he won't benefit directly from them. In Bulgaria there is no legislation to arrange these relations.
Organisational	Tertiary	Lack of power for initiation an EE action	The energy manager does not hold authority to promote the EE measures implementation. Local authorities should entrust these experts with more power in order to carry out effective EE policy. Many municipalities have such responsible person, but he does not possess the power to engage all stakeholders in the process. The same applies to some companies.
Cultural	Tertiary	Neglecting the EE needs	Organisational behaviour and routine may systematically neglect the need of optimising the EE in building.
Cultural	Tertiary and housing	No sufficient energy data for planning	The lack of education and motivation of local administrations leads to insufficient and unreliable energy data needed for better planning. Significant share of the baseline numbers are estimated, since there are no historical data kept. In some municipalities this barrier extends even for the present energy consumption data.
Educational	Tertiary and housing	Lack of information	The low level of awareness on climate change and environmental issues causes denial of energy efficiency opportunities. More educational seminars and trainings are needed not only for the authorities to implement the EE policy, but also for the citizens.
Educational	Tertiary and housing	Lack of capacity	Lack of skilled professionals, which leads to inefficient decisions or lack of EE initiatives at all.

Table 7. Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Financial risk	Market or business environment distortion, or increasing the instability of covering the loan repayment. Due to the financial crisis many building owners do not consider investments in energy efficiency. The uncertainty on the labour market increases the risk for carrying out the repayment's obligations and puts such projects backwards. Additional to this barrier are the present high interests of bank loans due to the Currency Board limitation of the Central Bank mechanisms.
Lack of finance	Higher initial costs impede investments in EE projects.
High costs	The higher cost of energy efficient technologies makes measures implementation not preferable by the consumers.
Low level energy prices	The low level of energy prices does not stimulate the owners to invest in energy efficiency. Many consumers use inefficient outworn boilers and the lack of incentives for their replacement is one of the main reasons for keeping the old heating solutions.
No incentives for EE projects	There are no incentives for investments in energy efficiency projects besides building's annual tax reduction under specific conditions. Building owners do not find EE projects attractive as there are no economic stimuli and the low energy prices increase the payback period of the projects.
Energy tariff system structure does not reflect correctly the cost of energy and carriers	The tariffs do not reflect the real energy costs, which misleads the consumers while choosing energy carriers and technologies. For instance, low electricity prices justify a tendency to use electricity for heating, instead of the much more effective CHP. This results in highly inefficient consumption.
Hidden costs	Additional costs or loss of benefits appear during the EE measures implementation, which are not applied in the engineering design.

Table 8. Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Long administrative procedures	The time needed for applying for a grant scheme is inefficiently long according to beneficiaries.
Historical preservation	For historical buildings only limited EE measures could be implemented if they do not disturb the buildings' original vision. Many buildings in Bulgaria need improvements but are subject to protection by the Law on the Cultural Heritage.
Insufficient marketing of EE programmes	Lack of enough information for a more informed decision making process among the building owners.
Shortcomings in the legislation with regard to common property	Lack of management of the blocks of flats, power and possibilities to undertake common projects. There is a need for substantial improvement of the legislation for the building facility management and ownership's rights. Presently, for some renovations approval by 100% of the apartment owners is needed, which hampers extremely

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
	the EE activities. The lack of regulatory framework makes difficult the gathering of owners for applying for EE projects.
Mistrust in the institutions and governmental system	The years of political transition had turned the Bulgarian citizens to be distrustful of any ideas and actions on political basis.
Low level of demonstration projects for nZEB	The definition of nearly zero energy building was introduced in the Bulgarian legislation last year. The nZEB requirements will be mandatory for all new public buildings constructed after 31 st December 2018, therefore there is a very low number of demonstration projects , which follow particularly the nZEB definition.
Frequent ungrounded change of regulatory framework	The change of political parties is often a reason for new changes in the regulatory framework. This uncertainty in the legislation causes decreasing in investments at all and specifically in energy performance improvement of buildings (BSERC 2013).
Insufficient national statistics	The information about energy consumption by carriers, consumer categories, sectors, etc. is limited, unreliable and smattering. This barrier fully applies to both the building and transport sectors.
Poor regional and municipal energy statistics	Local authorities are not obliged to collect and store energy data. These activities are supported mainly by EU projects and some municipalities maintain energy statistics mainly for keeping track of their energy costs. The fuels used in private and commercial sectors remain unknown.

The classification is based on the methodology proposed by UoA-KEPA for evaluation of the barriers' confrontation impact.

Table 9. Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Lack of finance
	High costs
	Distortion of energy prices
	Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing
	Insufficient national statistics
	Low level energy prices
	Insufficient marketing of EE programmes
	No incentives for EE projects
	Poor regional and municipal energy statistics
Medium	Hidden costs
	Long administrative procedures Energy tariff system structure not reflecting correctly the cost of energy and carriers

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
	Shortcomings in the legislation with regard to common property
	Low level of demonstration projects for nZEBs
	Lack of trust in ESCOs
	Frequent ungrounded change of regulatory framework
	No sufficient energy data for planning
	Split of incentives in house renting sector
	Lack of social approval
	Mistrust in the institutions and governmental system
	Neglecting the EE needs
	Lack of information
	Lack of capacity
	Financial risk
Low	Historical preservation
	Lack of power for initiation of EE actions

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

The barriers in the Bulgarian transport sector are presented in the next tables.

Table 10. Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Matter of social status	In Bulgaria private car usage is preferred by the majority of passengers compared to the public transport as it stays for better social image. There are various reasons for that: long years of limited possibility for owning a car; old, slow and unreliable public vehicles; policy supporting the use of private transportation, etc. Although in the last years many things have been made – replacement of the old vehicles servicing the public transportation, construction of underground (in the capital city), etc., there is still room for improvement in order to get higher attractiveness, which would change the social behaviour.
Social	Avoiding railway transportation	The hard situation of the Bulgarian railways and the failed or ineffective reforms in the sector made it less preferable by the

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
		passengers.
Education	Lack of information on the electric mobility	The limited information on electric vehicles makes them “utopia” for many buyers. These products represent high initial costs and the absence of marketing strategy supports the neglecting of environmental and economic benefits.
Education	Lack of information on green transportation	The idea for sustainable transportation is not very popular. Many passengers do not give account for the damages caused to environment due to their transportation habits and behaviour, i.e. the exclusive use of cars, travelling alone, getting stuck in traffic, etc. Usually they do not embrace the idea for changing their way of transportation.

Table 11. Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of finance	Local authorities invest in efficient vehicles through grant programmes and own budget. Most of the large Bulgarian cities have renewed a significant share of their transport fleet, but much more is needed to attract back the majority of the population. Poverty causes using of old and inefficient cars.
Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles	The stimuli for increasing the purchases of electric or hybrid vehicles include exemption from registration and annual taxes, parking fees (for now only in the capital Sofia) and vignette taxes. There are no economic supporting schemes as premiums of the purchasing value or reduction of VAT.
Not well developed first class road network	Road network needs serious improvement as it causes inefficient performance of the vehicles.
Inefficient transport structure	The State has practically neglected the needs for modernization of the railway transportation system. This ignoring, along with corruption practices, have led to prevailing road freight transport.

Table 12. Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans	Only several larger cities in Bulgaria have elaborated Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, which integrate urban planning, economic development, social needs, quality of environment and healthcare. Urban planning in other cities is concentrated mainly on traffic control, without taking into account the quality of life.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of electric mobility infrastructure	The charging infrastructure for electric vehicles should be developed in order to meet the buyers' requirements.
Inefficient urban transport infrastructure	Vehicles of the public transport usually share the same infrastructure with all the rest of the traffic (e.g. there are no separate lanes for the public buses). Additionally there is a need of development/expansion of cycling routes as stimuli for fuel-free movement.
Inefficient transport intercity infrastructure	A serious problem for intercity mobility in Bulgaria is the lack of ring roads in the settlements. The main roads pass through many villages and cause local air pollution. Additionally the speed changes bring along deterioration of the efficiency performance of the vehicle.
Lack of support for rail transportation	A huge flow back from the railway transportation has happened in the last years. Due to the serious problems in the sector, a lot of routes have been cut off, the rolling stock is outworn and unreliable, travelling is much more time consuming, compared to the other means of transportation. The reforms in the sector have not brought to its revival, but on the contrary.
Lack of regular transport services in smaller settlements	The only means of transportation in many smaller settlements are private motor vehicles. In some places there exist bus or rail road system infrastructures, but their schedule is inefficient and are less and less preferable.

The classification is based on the methodology proposed by UoA-KEPA for evaluation of the barriers' confrontation impact.

Table 13. Assessment of barriers in the transport sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Lack of finance
	Lack of support for rail transportation
	Inefficient urban transport infrastructure
	Inefficient transport structure
	Lack of electric mobility infrastructure
	Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles
	Inefficient transport intercity infrastructure
Medium	Matter of social status
	Avoiding railway transportation
	Lack of information on green transportation
	Lack of information on the electric mobility
	Lack of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
	Lack of regular transport services in smaller settlements
Low	Not well developed first class road network

3. BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

The next table presents the identified barriers in the building sector, divided by types, and the policy instruments addressing them.

Table 14. Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
Social, cultural and educational	Lack of finance	National	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	Distortion of energy prices	National	Regulatory framework
	Low energy prices	National	Regulatory framework
	Lack of social approval	National	SEAP (Covenant of Mayors), Local/Regional action plans
	Strong dependency on the neighbours in multi-family housing	National/Local	National Programme for Energy Renovation of Multi-family Residential Buildings, Structural funds
	Lack of trust in ESCOs	National	No specific policy instrument
	Split of incentives in house renting sector	National/Local	National policy framework on EE
	Historical preservation	National/regional/local	Energy Efficiency Act
	Lack of power for initiation an EE action	Local	Local authorities' policy framework, Companies' policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)
	Neglecting the EE needs	Local	Companies' policy framework on EE, SEAP

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
			(Covenant of Mayors)
	No sufficient energy data for planning	Regional/Local	National policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)
	Lack of information	National/Local	National policy framework on EE, Local/Regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)
	Lack of capacity	National/Local	National policy framework on EE, Local/Regional policy framework on EE, SEAP (Covenant of Mayors)
Economic	Financial risk	Local	EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	Lack of finance	National/Local	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	High costs	National	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	Low level of energy prices	National	National regulatory framework on energy
	Hidden costs	Local	No specific policy instrument
	No incentives for EE projects	National/ Regional/ Local	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
			mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	Energy tariff system structure does not reflect correctly the cost of energy and carriers	National	National regulatory framework on energy
	Not efficient selection of means and source for heating	National/ Local	National and local action plans on EE
Institutional	Long administrative procedures	National/Local	National policy framework on EE (as a whole)
	Unsufficient marketing of EE programmes	National/Regional/Local	National policy framework on EE (as a whole)
	Shortcomings in the legislation with regards to common property	National	National policy framework on EE (as a whole)
	Mistrust in the institutions and governmental system	National	No specific regulation
	Low level of demonstration projects for nZEB	National	Outline National plan to increase the number of nearly zero-energy buildings in accordance with article 9 of Directive 2010/31/EU on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD recast) (MRDPW 2013)
	Frequent ungrounded change of regulatory	National	No specific regulation
	Unsufficient national statistics	National	Statistics Act
	Poor regional and	National	Statistics Act

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
	municipal energy statistics		

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

The next table presents the identified barriers in the transport sector, divided by types, and the policy instruments addressing them.

Table 15. Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
Social Cultural Educational	Matter of social status	Local	No policy instrument
	Avoiding railway transportation	National	No policy instrument
	Lack of information on green transportation	National/Local	National policy on EE in transport sector
Economic	Lack of finance	National/Local	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, EU funds, National/Local budget, other financial mechanisms, grants, subsidies
	Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles	National	National Action Plan on Climate Change
	Not well developed first class road network	National	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015
	Inefficient transport structure	National	No specific policy instrument
Institutional	Lack of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans	Local	No specific policy instrument

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
	Inefficient urban transport infrastructure	Local	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015, Local/Regional Mobility Plans, National Action Plan on Climate Change
	Inefficient transport intercity infrastructure	National	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015, Local/Regional Mobility Plans, National Action Plan on Climate Change
	Lack of electric mobility infrastructure	National	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015, Local/Regional Mobility Plans, National Action Plan on Climate Change, National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility 2012-2014
	Lack of economic stimuli for purchasing electric/hybrid vehicles	National	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015, Local/Regional Mobility Plans, National Action Plan on Climate Change, National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles,

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
			including Electric Mobility 2012-2014
	Lack of support for rail transportation	National	Strategy for the Development of the Transport Infrastructure of the Republic of Bulgaria by 2015

4. KEY FINDINGS

Key findings on the barriers in the building sector:

- The low energy prices reduce the economic feasibility of (motivation to) the energy efficiency improvements in the sector. Furthermore, due to the long payback period, consumers often do not find attractive such investments.
- The world financial crisis has induced uncertainty of consumers about making investments at all. The lack of finance in combination with the long payback period affects the implementation of EE projects.
- There is no sufficient information regarding the existing incentives for EE projects. Both the engineering consultants and the consumers need additional knowledge on these opportunities.
- There is a serious need of demonstration projects. People tend to trust “their eyes” and the friends’, colleagues’, relatives’ opinion.
- The requirement for wider consent by the inhabitants of multi-family houses for implementation of energy efficiency improvements causes reluctance to initiate projects for increasing the energy performance of buildings.
- Bulgarian municipal authorities “suffer” from deficiency of sufficient data about the energy consumption on their territories, which is needed for the better energy planning. Only the municipalities, which have signed the Covenant of Mayors initiative, have put efforts into collecting historical energy data. Seeing the benefits, few more have started following their energy consumption and maintaining energy data bases.

Key findings on the barriers in the transport sector:

- The high prices and the lack of economic stimuli for purchasing of electric or hybrid motor vehicles are prerequisites for the very low share of these vehicles. Other countries have introduced stimuli, such as VAT reduction or reimbursement of a part of the investment, which, if applied also in Bulgaria, will encourage the clients to buy efficient cars.
- Regarding private transportation, one of the main barriers is the lack of liquidity of the car owners, which is the reason for the presence of enormous number of old and inefficient cars.
- Despite the considerable improvements introduced in public transportation in the last years, i.e. replacement of the old vehicles with comfortable, air-conditioned and more efficient ones, especially in the bigger cities, there should be put much more efforts in order to bring back the passengers and make the public transport services more attractive. Additional taxes for parking in or passing through cities’ centres could lead to traffic reduction.
- The Bulgarian railroad system is hindered by inadequate supporting schemes and policy framework. New measures for revival of the sector are seriously needed.

5. REFERENCES

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HERON project (No: 649690)

D.2.1 WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORTS

DATE 16 JULY 2015

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HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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⁽¹⁾ *The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.*

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ACRONYMS

AAU	- Assigned Amount Units under UN FCCC
DH	- District heating
EIC	- Environmental Investment Centre
ELMO	- Estonian Electro-Mobility Programme
ENMAK	- Estonian National Energy Sector Development Plan
GIS	- Green Investment Scheme
EPBD	- Energy Performance of Buildings
EPC	- Energy Performance Certificates
EU ETS	- EU Emissions Trading Scheme
EV	- Electric Vehicle
JI	- Joint Implementation, flexible mechanism under Kyoto Protocol
EIC	- Estonian Environmental Investment Fund [Keskkonnainvesteeringute Keskus]
KredEx	- Credit and Export Guarantee Foundation
LEB	- Low-Energy Building
MEAC	- The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication
NEEAP	- National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
nZEB	- nearly Zero-Energy Buildings
ODEX	- Energy efficiency index of industry
RKAS	- State Real Estate Company Ltd [Riigi Kinnisvara AS]
SEAP	- Sustainable Energy Action Plan
UNFCCC	- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Buildings sector

The share of residential sector in Estonia is the biggest - 32.8%, share of transport - 26.3%, industry - 22.8%, commercial and other services - 18.1%.

Estonia has 630 000 dwellings. 58 % out of all the housing stock has been built during the soviet era (1946-1990) which means these are not responding to present day requirements anymore in terms of insulation and indoor climate. Most recent study by Kredex revealed that an average energy intensity varies around approximately 200 kWh/m², which is very high compared to that in Sweden and Finland (150kWh/m²). When reconstructing multi apartment panel buildings, their lifetime may increase up to 50-80 years. At the same time, the importance of economic efficiency needs to be considered, assuming the risks of falling out of use. Based on the KredEx 2012 data, it is cheaper to renovate big panel apartment house with 100 and more flats than little wooden apartment houses with up to 20 flats.

In Estonia, 96 % of the housing stock belongs to private owners. This makes the household income an important factor when it comes to investments made in energy efficiency or reconstruction. According to the recent household energy usage research in 2012 about 50 % of the households considers the lack of money as the main barrier when it comes to improving their house or flat insulation. That was confirmed by 44% of the urban inhabitants in Estonia and 55% of the countryside inhabitants. More than half of all the households who have not yet improved the insulation of their homes, are neither planning to do so in the near future. Yet about 20 % of the households are planning to improve the insulation of their homes and about the same percentage of households' plans to invest in the insulation after longer than in 3 years period, as was stated in the 2014 report. At the same time, low income households, which makes about 60 % of the overall stock, watch after their energy usage more carefully than the households with higher salaries.

Several significant changes have taken place in the structure of the energy supply. The most essential one is the steady growth of electricity consumption: the use of electricity by households has increased 89.6%. Also, the share of electricity in households' total energy consumption has increased from 9.5% in 1995 to 16.8% in 2010. Specific energy consumption (climate corrected) calculated per dwelling has been, with some exceptions, declining. It has to be considered that the average area of dwellings has increased year by year. Space heating needs take the major share of households' energy consumption. The efficiency of energy use for space heating has been improved significantly.

Main barriers in buildings sector are related to social, educational and economic barriers. The following major big barriers could be listed: behavioural habits and typical models of energy usage; energy intensity in relation to relatively cold climate; gas supply security issue; lack of a bigger volume of high level specialists; regionally differentiated energy saving potential; dependence on private investment; aging of the housing stock; development of building sector and the price of energetic refurbishment; access to financing; finding agreement between the members of living association.

Transport sector

It accounts for a quarter of Estonian final energy demand (of which 94 per cent is cars and trucks) and energy demand has been rising over 33% during the last 15 years primarily due to economic growth, rapid increase in private car use and road freight, urban sprawl and decreasing share of

public transport and walking in daily mobility. Road transport has increased at the same pace as economic growth which puts Estonia as one of the most transport and energy intensive economies in the EU. Contrary to EU average and most other sectors' trends in Estonia the overall energy efficiency (based on aggregated ODEX indicator) in transport decreased in 1996-2010 by more than 15%.

Energy efficiency has had a minor role in national and local transport policies and strategies over the last 20 years as energy production and housing sector was the main focus for energy efficiency improvements and emission reduction. Growing economy, urban sprawl and relocation of jobs has driven increased demand in road transport and private car use, resulting in the overall decrease in transport energy efficiency since 2000. This demonstrates that policies in the transport sector have not addressed energy efficiency sufficiently and there is lack of systematic policy packaging, lack of research regarding barriers and tackling them. Transport sector's high energy and emissions saving potential was first recognized in Sustainable Transport Report in 2011, which was further elaborated in the preparation of National Energy Strategy 2030+ in 2012-2014. National Transport Strategy 2014-2020 sets clear energy efficiency targets for transport sector.

Main barriers in the field of transport are related to lack of fiscal measures to improve fuel efficiency of vehicle fleet, lack of long-term funding schemes for developing public transport and cycling, low density of population and lack of integrated urban and transport planning and integrated governance.

INTRODUCTION

The material collected through this report on Estonia's buildings and transport sectors will be used to inform deliverable D.2.1 'Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in building and transport'. The outcome of D.2.1 will be used in tasks WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country in WP2 will be considered in the development of the scenarios build in the LEAP software.

WP2 will provide a qualitative assessment of the key barriers for Estonia categorized to small impact, medium impact and big impact. The assessment of the current situation in two sectors under consideration is based on literature review and on the expert view of the project team. The qualitative indicators will be attempted to quantify the effect of these barriers in combination with the policy instruments used in Estonia to improve the energy efficiency.

Many aspects of Estonia's energy system are currently at a crossroads: market liberalisation, effective co-operation with neighbouring countries via transparent energy markets, diversification into sustainable energy resources and energy efficient technologies. Regardless of the economics and practicalities of supply-side options, realising energy efficiency is central to all aspects of future energy policy. Estonia clearly aspires to a more energy-efficient and sustainable economy. Notwithstanding sound commitment to the EU objectives for energy efficiency, Estonia's policy challenges and opportunities extend beyond the 2020 horizon of EU obligations. The government aims to use the EU directives as a step on the way to shaping longer-term objectives and has started working on Energy Strategy of Estonia to 2050 (Estonia 2013..., 2013).

Country has transposed the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU (EED) into its' legislation. There are many activities to prepare for increased financing of energy efficiency from EU structural funds and other sources. Enhanced legislative basis based on EED and expected continuing of financing from EU structural funds provide significant contribution to achieve the main goal of the national energy efficiency policy. The National Reform Programme Estonia 2020 sets the target for keeping final energy consumption at the level of 2010 in 2020. The Estonian government has made tangible progress in meeting the targets set so far. The updated 'Estonia 2020' Competitiveness Strategy' approved by the Estonian government in April 2013 established the energy efficiency objective that final energy consumption in 2020 should not exceed the 2010 level. According to Statistics Estonia, final energy consumption in 2010 was 119 PJ (petajoules), in 2011 it fell to 115 PJ. According to the estimates the goal to cap final energy consumption in 2020 at the level of 2010 seems realistic and achievable (NEEAP, 2014). This is considered quite an ambitious challenges in the field of energy efficiency improvement.

Estonia's second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) listed 99 energy efficiency measures in eight policy areas, including 34 measures in the buildings sector; seven in the public sector (except buildings); 12 in industry; 14 in the energy sector; 17 in transport; four in household appliances and the service sector; four in agriculture and seven in other areas. The largest reductions in energy use are expected to come from the following sectors:

- ✓ buildings: 3.5 PJ;
- ✓ transport: 2.5 PJ from changing motor fuels to biofuels;
- ✓ industry: 2.2 PJ; comprising 0.9 PJ ordinary fuels, 0.7 PJ electricity and 0.6 PJ heat.

The full opening of the electricity market since January 2013 resulted in an increase in electricity prices (by approximately 20%) and this encouraged a reorientation in electricity use relative to other energy supply options, and investment in buildings' insulation and more efficient appliances (NEEAP, 2014).

Energy Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) has designed the list of measures to remove regulatory and non-regulatory barriers to energy efficiency. It is the task of the ministry to monitor the effect of legislation on influencing energy efficiency. This work is carried out continually, mainly by examining and commenting on draft legislation or strategies.

Dwellings in Estonia are privately owned, and each apartment property has an owner. The home owners predominately live in their own homes. The renting of individual houses or terraced houses is not common at all. A small portion of apartments belong to the state or to local governments, but their proportional share is decreasing. Still, some new dwellings are under way within the initiative of the local government in capital city Tallinn. The rental market in Estonia is estimated to represent about 15% of the total housing market, which is quite small in comparison with the European average. Most apartment buildings have an apartment association founded by the apartment owners in the building, which jointly represents apartment owners. The decisions regarding the management of apartment buildings are made by a vote in favour by a majority of the apartment owners in the building. Based on the above, the differences between the interests of owners and renters in Estonia are not a significant obstacle preventing dwellings from being made more energy efficient. Quite a number of apartment associations have undertaken the energetic refurbishment of their dwellings (NEEAP, 2014).

In the case of public sector buildings, the buildings belong to the state, to local governments or to private companies established by them. In the commercial sector, buildings also belong to private owners, and as a result there are all of the prerequisites for energy efficiency measures to operate in this area. The market for commercial premises, where renting is more prevalent, generally has the effect of stimulating the achievement of energy efficiency objectives: there is a sufficient supply of rental space to ensure that renters retain freedom of choice. Many public buildings have been renovated to raise significantly their energy efficiency. The major source of financing has been and continuously is the international sale of unused national emission quotas in relation to the Kyoto Protocol. This programme has been successfully initiated in 2010 (see for more in the following paragraphs). The management of central government buildings is being consolidated. The grounds for that consolidation are described in the “National Real Estate Strategy” available at the following address: (<http://riigivara.fin.ee/lr1/web/guest/strateegia>).

1 CONTEXT

1.1 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) has overall responsibility for energy and economic policies. Ministry prepares economic development plans in sectors that have a direct impact on climate change: industry, trade, energy, housing, buildings, transport and traffic management. The ministry is responsible for co-ordinating the implementation of the National Development Plan for the Energy Sector, the Development Plan for Estonian Electricity Sector, the Action Plan for Renewable Energy, the Development Plan for Housing Sector, Transport Development Programme and the Energy Conservation (energy efficiency) Programme for Estonia. It holds the overall accountability for energy efficiency policy as part of the energy policy mandate. It is responsible for the EU legislation, including the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED), Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), etc. The Energy Department and the Building and Housing Department within the ministry are responsible for the majority of matters related to energy efficiency, district heating (DH) and renewable energy policies. The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications collaborates with two executive agencies acting as implementing agencies of energy efficiency policy measures. Both agencies have specialised units for energy measures, working on issues closely linked to the promotion of energy efficiency (NEEAP, 2014).

One well-functioning executive agency, The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund (KredEx Fund) works with measures targeted to residential sector and electro-mobility (<http://www.kredex.ee/en/>). KredEx develops and offers financial services aimed at energy efficiency. KredEx provides grants for installing renewable energy generation installations for private households (solar panels, wind generators, heat pumps, etc.) and also, for energetic refurbishment, as well as guarantees for loans for reconstruction of multistore apartment houses to improve their energy efficiency.

Another agency in energy efficiency field is The Environmental Investment Centre (EIC) which implements the measures targeting public infrastructure, particularly heat and electricity generation, energy distribution systems and street lighting. EIC funds larger-scale energy efficiency projects such as DH systems and both onshore and offshore wind parks, reconstructing or constructing combined heat and power (CHP) plant (<http://www.kik.ee/en>).

The Ministry of the Environment (MoE) which is responsible for the development of green public procurement rules and guidelines for the purchase of energy-efficient goods (<http://www.envir.ee/et/keskkonnahoidlikud-riigihanked>). It is increasingly involved in energy policy and in particular energy efficiency policy management. Given the historical dependence on oil shale electricity driving climate emissions, there is a need for close co-ordination of energy and environment policy developments. Policies on local air and water quality are driven by European Union requirements and are based on emission taxes for local water and air discharges, including mining activities. These are useful complementary drivers for a more sustainable development and energy efficiency (Estonia 2013..., 2013).

In addition, the ministry supervises state commercial enterprises such as the State Forest Management Centre and the Plc. Geological Survey of Estonia. Land-use issues related to agricultural biomass are dealt by the Ministry of Agriculture.

Energy efficiency is also being promoted via energy tariff coordination by the Competition Authority which supervises the (DH) markets and electricity, and it ensures fair competition on the renewable energy market. The development of energy efficiency and energy-saving related research is largely supported by the Programme of green economy and energy set up by the Estonian Development Fund (Estonia 2013..., 2013).

The topics related to the energy efficiency are also dealt by the Riigi Kinnisvara AS (RKAS), The State Real Estate Ltd, which is the real estate development company engaged in the development and administration of state-owned buildings - public buildings such as schools and government agencies, and whose stocks are 100% owned by the Republic of Estonia. Company has the objective to guarantee the saving and effective provision of the real estate service to the executors of state authority (<http://www.rkas.ee/about-rkas>).

The transmission system operator (TSO) AS Elering manages the subsidy system for electricity generators. AS Elering keeps track of the production of renewables-based electricity generation and takes care of billing the consumers, delivering the subsidies to the electricity producers.

At the local level, the governments are developing local energy efficiency and renewable energy strategies, while ensuring that they are in accordance with the national policy framework and principles. The local governments in Estonia that have developed energy efficiency action plan are the cities of Tallinn, Tartu, Võru, Valga, Jõgeva and Rakvere (Estonia 2013..., 2013).

1.2 BREAKDOWN OF ENERGY USE BY SECTORS

1.2.1 HOUSING SECTOR ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Total final consumption in Estonia in 2011 was 2.8 million tonnes of oil-equivalent (Mt oe). Oil comprised 34.3%, electricity 20%, biofuels and waste 17.5%, heat 16.7%, natural gas 7.1% and coal 4.4%. The share of residential sector was the biggest - 32.8%, share of transport - 26.3%, industry - 22.8%, commercial and other services - 18.1% (Estonia 2013 ..., 2013, p. 39). Space heating demand comprises the major share of households' energy consumption.

During the period 1995 – 2010 the number of population in Estonia continued to decline. When analysing the households' energy consumption the population decrease is very important factor which should be taken into account. The estimated population of Estonia was 1.34 million at 1 January 2011. Since 1995, the reduction has been 6.7%, i.e. – 0.46% a year. According to the official statistics in 2010 the number of dwellings was 653.6 thousand. The estimated number of households was 583.9 thousand. Roughly 70% of dwellings are in apartment buildings. The relatively large share of apartment buildings in the housing stock resulted from the structure of construction activities in 1950–1990, when most of the residential houses built were apartment buildings (Energy ..., 2012).

Several significant changes have taken place in the energy consumption and dwelling stock. Firstly, the average area of dwellings has increased year by year: from 58.6 m² in 1995 to 61.3 m² in 2010 as the size of new dwellings is growing: the average living area of new dwellings in 2010 was 103.5 m². Of course, there are great area differences between various types of dwellings. For example, in 2010 the average living area of a new single family house was 167.8 m² and of the new apartment 62.1 m².

Secondly, from 1999 to 2006 the households' total energy consumption had a slightly declining trend, since 2007 the consumption has slightly grown. The estimated share of space heating in households' total energy consumption is approximately 60–70%. The annual consumption of purchased district heat has declined both in relative (from 53.9% to 34.6%) and absolute (from 0.52 to 0.36 Mt oe) terms. Households' use of oil fuels has fallen from 59 to 8 Mt oe. The oil fuels have been replaced with other energy sources: solid fuels, natural gas and electricity. The supply of local firewood increased fast. At the same time energy efficiency issues started to occur in agenda of residential sector renovation plans.

Thirdly, still the most essential change has been the steady growth of electricity consumption: the use of electricity by households has increased 89.6% – from 1,067 GWh in 1995 to 2,023 GWh in 2010 which makes 4.4% per year as average. Also, the share of electricity in households' total energy consumption has increased from 9.5% in 1995 to 16.8% in 2010 (Energy ..., 2012).

The common widespread reflection (knowledge) is that Estonia's average yearly consumption per square metre of dwelling is relatively high reaching 180 or even up to 200 kWh/m² compared with European average of 130 kWh/m². However, the efficiency of energy use for space heating has been improved significantly starting from 1990ies, and particular speedy development has taken place during last 5 to 7 years. Above all, it is important to consider that Estonia is located quite much to North compared to most of the European countries. For making fair comparison of households' specific energy consumption between EU Member States, the difference in climate conditions in countries should be taken in account. Therefore, the specific consumption per area unit (m²) should be considered as the more representative one. It is reflected by indicators of consumption per unit (per dwelling and/or per m²) and considering the so-called heating degree days (HDD).

The annual amount of energy used for space heating depends on the outdoor temperature during the heating season. Therefore, to find the actual changes in energy use efficiency for space heating there is a need to eliminate the annual climate changes. The heating degree days, which express the severity of the cold in a specific time period give the opportunity to take into consideration both the outdoor temperature and room temperature. In frames of the Odyssee – Mure 2010 project a methodology was elaborated for scaling the households' energy consumption to the EU average climate. The annual specific space heating energy calculated per heating degree day enable to compare the average energy use efficiency in dwelling sector in Estonia and in average EU (Energy ..., 2012). These average figures are informative and allow to make fair comparison, see Table 1.

Table 1 Key indicators of households' annual specific energy consumption, 2010

Indicator	Unit	Estonia	EU av.
Energy consumption (all purposes)	t oe/dwelling	1.56	1.42
	kg oe/m ²	25.5	16.5
Energy consumption (all purposes) scaled to EU average climate	t oe/dwelling	1.20*	1.42
	kg oe/m ²	19.7*	16.5
Energy consumption for space heating scaled to EU average climate	t oe/dwelling	0.64	0.94
	kg oe/m ²	10.5	11
Energy consumption for space heating per	t oe/dwelling	0.163	0.252

heating degree day	kg oe/m ²	2.66	2.94
Electricity consumption	kWh/dwelling	3226	4062

* - data for 2009.

Source: Energy Efficiency Policies and Measures in Estonia, 2012.

One could conclude from the comparison of average figures on Estonia and EU average that considering climate conditions the energy consumption per dwelling (and per m²) in Estonia seems to be at quite good level. Significant progress has been made since 2010 in improving the energy efficiency in the course of energetic refurbishment of apartment houses, also in bright new buildings' stock. There is a need for updated energy efficiency statistics of buildings.

1.2.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR ENERGY CONSUMPTION

A quarter of Estonian final energy demand comes from the transport sector and the energy demand have grown during the last 15 years by over 33% (see Figure 1-2). Contrary to EU average and most other sectors' trends in Estonia the overall energy efficiency (based on aggregated ODEX indicator) in transport decreased in 1996-2010 by more than 15% (Energy ..., 2012).

Figure 1 Transport sector energy consumption by fuel type

Source: Keskkonnauuringute Keskus, 2015

Figure 2 Energy consumption by transport mode 1995-2010 (TJ)

Source: Jüssi et al, 2014

Ca 94 per cent of the energy is consumed in road transport, of which ca 60% by private cars, which has been the fastest growing transport mode in Estonia (Figure 3). Ca 44% of the fuel consumed on Estonian roads can be associated with local roads and streets, which shows that the local level plays a big role in energy efficiency policies (Jüssi et al., 2014).

Figure 3 Energy consumption in Estonian road transport by mode 2000-2011

Source: Jüssi et al 2014

Energy demand has been rising primarily due to economic growth, rapid increase in private car use (more than 50% of increase in annual mileage) and road freight, urban sprawl, also due to a decreasing share of public transport and walking in daily mobility (see Figure 4). Road transport has increased at the same pace as economic growth which puts Estonia as one of the most transport and energy intensive economies in the EU. For example Estonia uses twice as much transport fuel per unit of GDP than the average EU country (Jüssi et al., 2011).

Figure 4 Home to work trips by mode in Estonia 2000-2011

Source: Estonian Statistics Board, 2013 ref Jüssi et al., 2014

Even though the fuel economy of new cars has improved over the last seven years, new passenger cars registered in Estonia rank lowest in the fuel efficiency comparison with other EU countries, with average cars being 10% less fuel efficient than the EU average (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Average CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars in selected countries 2007, 2014 (g/km)

Source: Eurostat

1.3 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

1.3.1 HOUSING SECTOR POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Quite a number of policy instruments in the field of energy efficiency is in place in Estonia. Here an important role has the legal framework of the European Union. The obligations related to climate issues and energy usage for the architects, constructors and occupiers come from the EU's climate and energy policy framework of 2030. This framework includes a requirement of energy efficiency according to which the final energy consumption in 2020 may not exceed the 2010th final energy consumption, and by 2030 energy efficiency must increase 27% (European..., 2015). This 2030 policy framework aims to make the European Union's economy and energy system more competitive, secure and sustainable and also sets a target of at least 27% for renewable energy and energy savings by 2030. Estonia has finalised the transposition of the, Energy Performance of Buildings Directive 2010/31/EU, EPBD. New levels of the minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) are set to be adopted which determine near zero-energy performance levels. Policy measures targeting energy efficiency improvements in public and private buildings are being carried out, using the funds available under the scheme for financing multi-apartment buildings. The renovation of the existing building stock will be one of the key areas addressed in the next period of Structural Funds (2014-2020). New support schemes have now been explored to stimulate the renovation of detached houses (Estonia 2013..., 2013).

In addition there are a number of national strategies which set ambitious targets also for the building sector, such as the "2030 Energy Management Development Plan" with an outlook to 2050. The mentioned strategy also replaces the current electricity development plan 2018, development plan for promoting the use of biomass and bioenergy for the period of 2007-2013 and the National Housing Development Plan for 2008-2013 (National ..., 2008). The new development plan is therefore

more comprehensive, assigning also the starting points for the development plans which by law must be also presented to the EU (Energiatagud, 2015).

Under the UN FCCC Kyoto Protocol, Estonia has been using two flexible mechanisms: EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and Joint Implementation (JI). Arising from the Protocol, Estonia as other former economies in transition, currently has the right to offer unused emission quota for sale. Estonia has had significant volumes of excess Assigned Amount Units (AAU), which are carbon credits to be sold internationally. This new financing measure was added to Environmental Investment Centre's portfolio and is titled the Green Investment Scheme (GIS) pursuant to which the revenue is directed to investments ensuring a decrease in CO₂ emissions as agreed with the buyer of the quota, for example ensuring the energy efficiency of public buildings or finance the electro-mobility programme in transport sector. This is, in fact the financing instrument where the money is received through the sale of the excess CO₂ quota, Assigned Amount Units. Estonia started selling AAUs in 2009, under the GIS and has earmarked the proceeds for projects that facilitate emissions reductions. Examples include wind farms, CHP installations, improving DH networks, retrofitting boiler houses, improving energy efficiency in buildings and industry, and introducing more efficient buses and trams in city traffic, and electric vehicles. In the frame of the instrument the areas of financing will be decided by the buyers. The first grants channelled through EIC were for the renovation of the district heating networks, renovation of combined generation plants and more environmentally-sustainable boiler houses (<http://www.kik.ee/en/energy>). However, the significant financing has been channelled to energetic refurbishment of public buildings, also electro-mobility programme. In 2010-2013 the Riigi Kinnisvara AS (RKAS) has elaborated to implementation the energetic refurbishment directed to increasing the energy efficiency of 543 public buildings based on the Assigned Amount Units trade in total volume of EUR 165,67 million (<http://www.rkas.ee/co2-en>).

There is another example in housing sector connected to foundation Kredex. It has been the practice for many years already (first funding period 2010-2014) Kredex allocated the grants for reconstruction of apartment buildings to numerous apartment associations and local governments which had the possibility to receive support from the state for energetic refurbishment of apartment buildings and thus reduce energy expenses of flat owners. The grants funded from the EU Cohesion Fund have allowed for the reconstruction of more than 1,000 apartment buildings (The overview..., 2014). The second round of the support measures to housing sector energetic refurbishment started at the end of 2014. The volume of the grant to be funded from the Cohesion Fund is EUR 102 million, which will allow for the reconstruction of an estimated 1,000 apartment buildings during the period of 2014-2020. In the field of energy efficiency it is the first European Union's funding support measure introduced up today. The grant is aimed at achieving energy efficiency and better indoor climate in existing relatively low-quality apartment buildings, also facilitating the implementation of renewable energy based equipment. The grant helps to reduce the energy expenses of households, extend the lifetime of buildings, and improve the general living environment. The latter is considered as the most important from the point of view of habitants' health. Related to that the inclusion of ventilation system has been made mandatory in renovation plans applying for grant.

Energy labelling of buildings could be considered as one of the significant policy instrument in further developing of energy efficiency in buildings sector. It is in force as of January 1, 2009 being mandatory. Energy label or energy performance certificate is a document, the objective of which is to give an information about how much does a building with the assurance of internal climate consume energy in comparison with the average energy consumption of other equivalent buildings. Energy consumption includes the amount of energy that is needed for heating, cooling, hot water, ventilation and lighting of a building. The energy label gives the building's energy efficiency class. The higher the energy efficiency class (from A, B, C ... to G) of the building is, the lower are the electricity and heat consumption per square metre of the building

(<http://www.estivo.ee/en/services/energy/energy-audit-energy-label-thermographyrtificate-thermography/energy-label1/>)

). The legal basis for issuing the energy label is the Regulation No. 107 of 17 December 2008 of the Minister of Economic Affairs and Communications “Form of Energy Performance Certificate and Issuing Procedure” (<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/527102014001/consolide>). At present, new single-family dwellings need to achieve a 160 kilowatt hour per square metre (kWh/m²) total annual weighted energy consumption, and multi-apartment houses to achieve total weighted energy levels of 150 kWh/m² per year. New stricter energy performance requirements for all the buildings have been in effect since 9 January 2013 (Estonia 2013...,2013). Also, new Building Act came into force as of 01.07.2015, <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/527082014001/consolide>.

Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings (hereafter called the EPBD) is the main legislative instrument at EU level for improving the energy efficiency of European buildings. A key element of the EPBD, especially for achieving these longer term objectives, is its requirements regarding nearly zero-energy buildings. Following the study performed by Ecofys by the request of European Commission, the main policies and measures in support of new NZEBs in the different Member States are the following (Ecofys, 2014):

- Awareness raising/Information strengthening;
- Building regulations;
- Energy performance certificates;
- Education and Training;
- Demonstration and pilot projects;
- Financial support schemes;
- Supervision (energy audits etc.) and
- R&D

Estonia is practicing most of the policies and measures, still the financial support schemes and supervision have been quite modest yet and need more elaboration from the governmental institutions.

There exist preconditions for carrying out energy savings projects using the model of energy services undertakings, but one must take into account the various restrictions arising from the legal environment. The service sector's high consumption of thermal energy and electricity is also caused by the low technical level conditions of the buildings in the commercial sector. It is usually not the building's owner, but its renter, that represents the service sector. As a result, building owners are not interested in investing in energy savings, because their clients are forced to pay the energy costs in any case. Here one can also find the preconditions for a market for energy services, yet the development of the market for energy services goes hand in hand with the development of the real estate sector – if the quality of the rental space increases (and energy consumption falls) as a result, the owners of the rental space will be forced to invest in energy savings themselves. Solutions similar to the energy services model have now been offered to commercial and real estate undertakings in Estonia, and Riigi Kinnisvara AS (Estonian State Real Estate Ltd) has added energy efficiency clauses to its long-term rental contracts.

The Estonian industrial sector is very energy-intensive, which has an influence on both industrial processes and buildings. In comparison with Finland, the proportion of labour costs in various branches of industry is higher in Finland than in Estonia, but energy costs are higher in Estonia in almost all branches of industry. In the Estonian industrial sector, energy services undertakings would also help reduce energy costs, improve energy efficiency, manage risk and raise competitiveness. In Estonia today there are only a few examples (mainly in food production) of an energy service being used. In the case of Estonia, various experts estimate that there could be significant potential for energy savings in both industrial processes and industrial buildings (Estonia 2013...,2013).

The list of abovementioned barriers addressed policy instruments is presented in the following Table 2.

Table 2 Estonian policy instruments in building sector

Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various regulations set under the Building Act: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009 - The requirements of minimum energy performance of buildings (30.08.2012 no. 68) • Emergency Act 15.06.2009 (§ 34) • Environmental Charges Act 01.01.2006 (KeTS) • Electricity Market Act, Chpt.5.Generation, §57, 58, 59 • Flat ownership and co-operative flat law (19.02.2014), to be put on effect on 01.01.2018 (KrtS)
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The educational programmes to encourage clients by Kredex • Establishment of the smart energy network data portal Estfeed • Energy audit of the buildings (04.04.2014 nr.16) • European Commission Green Public Procurement Toolkit (GPP) 2008 • The website of http://www.energiatalgud.ee has been established by the Estonian Development Fund in order to collect all energy related information for the new 2030 +
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\EIC) financial support to living associations and private house owners for energetic refurbishment • EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\EIC) financial support to private house owners to make fuel switch from LFO • Green Investment Scheme, GIS (new financing measure in EIC's portfolio to sale excess volumes of AAU) • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • Demolition support given by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre (EIC)
Capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered (grant issuing, trainings and consultations). • Guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants
Policy instruments for the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The establishment of housing unit in Foundation

promotion of energy services	<p>KredEx to start the apartment houses energetic refurbishment programme</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable Energy Action Plan 2020 and the new Energy Sector Development Plan 2030 • Estonian cities Rakvere and Tallinn have submitted their sustainable energy action plans (SEAPs) to EU
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030 +) which integrates many previous strategies under new and revised document • Grants programmes by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre, EIC • EU 6th FP and 7th FP 6th and energy research programme

1.3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Until 2014 there were no particular quantified energy efficiency targets in national nor local transport strategies. National transport strategy 2014-2020 (Transpordi arengukava 2014-2020, 2014) sets a target of capping transport sector’s energy demand to 2012 level (33 000 TJ¹). For reaching energy efficiency and other environmental goals (reducing GHG emissions, PM emissions) the strategy sets out four main policy areas: managing traffic demand, giving preference to sustainable commuting modes over car use, implementing new technologies, incl. alternative fuels and increasing the fuel efficiency of car fleet.

- Developing E-services and teleworking
- Better integration of transport and land use planning, encouraging more compact and public transport oriented development
- Improving living environment, developing public transport, walking and cycling conditions
- Increasing the fuel efficiency of car fleet (One of sub-targets in the document is the share of energy class A-C vehicles among new registered passenger cars – with target share of 50% by 2020 (2011 share: 20%). through energy labelling and public procurement requirements
- Encouraging the take-up of renewable transport fuels, especially local biomethane.

Over the last 5 years national and local level government have implemented or planning a number of measures that will have an effect on transport’s energy efficiency.

Table 3 Estonian policy instruments in transport sector

Planning/infrastructure instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reconstruction of railways (increased speeds) - Renewal of passenger train fleet (2013)
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¹ There is a unit error in the official original strategy document, energy consumption target indicator sets a unit of „million TJ“ – should be „thousand TJ“, as this is the level of 2012 consumption.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ELMO quick EV-charging network covering all Estonia (165 charging points) - Green Investment schemes (incl. ELMO, Tallinn trams, 110 county buses) - Investment scheme for multi-modal access to rail stations facilitates the development of areas close to rail stations. - investment scheme for urban mobility and county centres - Investment in harbours and ferry services - Local investment in cycling, walking and public transport - dedicated bus lanes in Tallinn - Plans for bicycle share schemes in 5 cities, new cycle infrastructure in city centres - Developing teleworking opportunities
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy labelling of cars - Energy efficiency requirements for public procurement conditions (vehicle purchases)
Financial policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing fuel excise duty 2016-2018 - decreasing VAT reimbursement rate and procedures for company cars - Support scheme for electro-mobility program ELMO (supporting purchase of EV-s, support for EV charging, ELMO-rent and EV taxis) - Support scheme for low-emission public transport rolling stock - Abolishing earmarking of fuel duty revenues for roads. New schemes on investment for integrated solutions in urban areas/railway stations, county centres - Free public transport in Tallinn (local measure) - Expanding the area of paid on-street parking in city centres (Tallinn, Tartu)
Dissemination and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness raising campaigns for PT, walking and cycling (European Cycling Challenge 2012-2015) - Compulsory eco-driving module for driving licence training. Eco-driving promotion. - Common information system for all Estonian PT providers – www.peatus.ee - Common ticket payment system (contactless card) for Tallinn city and Harju county - Speed limit enforcement through automatic speed controls on main intercity roads. - Planning guidance being developed by Ministry of Interior; National Spatial Development Plan 2030+ - Network of sustainable urban mobility planning (brings together cities, government, experts, NGOs)
Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-Estonia, E-Governance and other e-solutions - Smart City cluster to develop ICT tools - R&D program planned for transport energy efficiency development

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing ICT in transport - Promoting co-operation between universities, authorities and businesses for common curriculum on planning - Tallinn and Tartu travel survey (end of 2015) to analyse travel patterns and key drivers
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Selected transport policy measures are more closely elaborated in WP1 papers.

1.4 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

Estonia's policies and objectives regarding RD&I are laid out in the Estonian Research, Development and Innovation Strategy 2007-2013 "Knowledge-based Estonia". The main objectives are to increase the quality of public research and private-sector innovation and the potential for long-term economic growth. Energy Technology Programme was one out of the six national R&D programmes included in the 2007-2013 strategy. The other five were information and communications technology (ICT), biotechnology, health, environment technology and materials technology. In order to achieve the goals to become more energy efficient "Estonian Energy Technology Programme" was established in 2008 under the strategy of the "Knowledge based Estonia 2007-2013." (ENMAK 2030+, 2015) Today this document is not in use anymore, and the new energy development strategy directions and potentials have been studied for and implemented within the new Estonian Energy Development Plan 2030. The energy efficiency in buildings has been mainly achieved thanks to the loan programme for the renovation of apartment buildings implemented by KredEx Fund in co-operation with the German Development Bank KfW Bankengruppe (Estonia 2013...,2013). The KredEx Fund provides grants, funded through AAU CO₂ quota sales, for the renovation of apartment blocks and smaller houses. Among the others the eligible tasks for the second financing period include replacement or reconstruction of the heating systems, e.g. installation of renewable energy technologies, such as solar panel based water heaters, heat pumps or biomass fuelled boilers. Also, reconstruction of the ventilation system or installation of a system with heat recirculation. Still, switching from the existing DH network to an individual or collective heating option is allowed only if the new heating system is based on renewable energy (<http://kredex.ee/grant/>). These are just few examples of tasks under way at present.

One of the technological measures in Estonia for achieving higher energy efficiency in buildings is the thermal inspection method used to locate heat leaks in the building. The thermal image of the building taken with an infra-red camera showing temperatures in different colours. This in turn is used for making energy audits, the technical analysis service for building owners, offered by Eesti Energia AS auditors, also by a number of private consulting companies. Thermal inspection together with the total energy audit provides a quick overview of the building's energy efficiency condition. Based on the audit the design of various measures including improvement of roof and walls isolation, change of windows, removing heat leakages, etc. could be undertaken to improve the energy efficiency performance of building (Eesti Energia, <https://www.energia.ee/en/termoylevaatus>, 01.07.2015).

Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings requires all new buildings to be nearly zero-energy by the end of 2020. All new public buildings must be nearly zero-energy by the end of 2018. Its provisions cover energy needs for the heating of premises, the production of hot water, cooling, ventilation and lighting for new and existing buildings, whether they are residential or not.

In Estonia there are a quite a number of nearly zero energy pilot buildings already, the most recent one was built at the campus of Tallinn University of Technology in 2015. The first truly functioning “Smart house” has been designed by Smart House Competence Centre in Rakvere town (<http://www.rakveretarkmaja.ee/>) which was opened in May 2015. The capacity, knowledge, and lack of experience and experiments to achieve this ambitious EU target of nearly zero energy buildings in Estonia is however, not at the desirable level yet. Nevertheless, the relevant training courses for target groups have been started four-five years ago already. Still, there are a number of construction companies specialising on design and implementation of nearly zero energy buildings in private housing also, in public buildings sector. Relevant market is rapidly developing and gaining high popularity for the people planning to build the private house.

The definitions of nearly zero-energy-buildings differ by EU Member States as the building regulations and calculation methods may significantly differ from country to country. In the study “Overview of Member States information on NZEBs” by Ecofys Germany GmbH the Estonian definition is given as the following. A NZEB is a building which is characterised by sound engineering solutions, which is built according to the best possible construction practice, which employs energy efficiency and renewable energy technology solutions and whose energy performance indicator is greater than 0 kWh/m²/y but does not exceed the limit values established (Ecofys, 2014).

An important role is also on the research and innovation, such as development of the smart grid network, the introduction of smart meters and new energy saving solutions. This is one of the actions under fulfilling the targets of “Estonia 2020” strategy. In order to monitor and administer energy usage, the smart energy network data portal Estfeed is currently funded by Norwegian Financial Mechanism 2009-2014 (project manager AS Elering). Estfeed is a data-sharing Internet based platform designed for organisations and individuals to more efficiently organise their energy consumption. Here one can find a variety of applications created by different parties that will help better understand the information related to one’s energy usage. The project aims to build a software platform capable to integrate many data sources and to provide appropriate services to convert these data into valuable information for energy flexibility management, audit and benchmarking (<http://estfeed.ee/en/>).

In the transport sector the main technological policies are:

- Electro-mobility program, a support and investment scheme to encourage the take-up of electric vehicles in Estonia (see WP1 for closer description).
- Developing e-government and e-governance in Estonia
- Smart City Cluster for developing intelligent and mobile solutions for smart planning and mobility solutions

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

Table 4 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Increasing client/ consumer wellness	Growth of welfare in the society has increased the requirements for quality of life. People are more and more using the technologies which make their life more comfortable. Year to year the dwelling spaces per person increase, as well as the indoor climate user requirements. The consumer behaviour is also affected by the household products imported from foreign countries. More electrical appliances are used. The energy consumption of small consumers to the final energy consumption is increasing and without large scale national guidance and support it is difficult to achieve success. In implementing the energy saving policies, the wide range of possible energy savings methods might be problematic; on the other hand there are individual actions which can led to positive results in all sectors (MEAC, 2007).
	Big multistore apartment habitants never find easy way to common ground to undertake the energy efficiency renovation	Although there is a higher level of cost-effectiveness in targeting large buildings, it is easier to initiate projects in smaller buildings as fewer individuals need to agree to the intervention. The government is exploring new support schemes to stimulate renovation of detached housing (Uuring..., 2013).
	Low awareness. Lack of relevant easily understandable to all tenants information	Nevertheless KredEx has proceed massive information activities and trainings to the heads of living associations all over the country, it is obviously still not yet enough to convince the majority of an association members to undertake the energetic refurbishment of their dwelling. More publicity and relevant information dissemination activities are planned.
	Low income of aged people	People, living on their pension only, are afraid of the future costs of renovation which will be added to the monthly bills, thus remaining too small income for normal living (ENMAK2030+..., 2015).
	Lack of clients' courage and initiative to undertake certain investments to their dwelling	Misunderstanding the advantage of stable costs and revenues is a significant barrier to necessary investment. Lack of enough courage among dwelling owners to invest in more energy efficient technologies or modernizing technologies in general. Low incomes and therefore insecurity whether an investment to insulate or renovate house is beneficial and worth of an effort (MEAC, 2007; ENMAK 2030+..., 2015).
	Dwellings left empty	Due to increasing urbanisation, aging population and emigration issues, some regions with apartment blocks and other residential buildings

		will be left empty and many of them are abandoned. Today about 25 % of housing stock in Estonia is said to be empty. This happens mainly in Valga, Ida-Virumaa and Lääne-Virumaa counties. The biggest number of left apartments, more than 2200 is registered in Kohtla-Järve. In privatized apartment buildings many flats are not in use any more which makes the life of the remained tenants\flat owners in a half empty apartment building rather hard due to the heat costs which are distributed to apartments still in use (Uuring..., 2013).
Cultural	Energy usage habits in relation to relatively autonomous national energy market	Estonia has used oil shale for electricity production for almost a century (since 1924), in 2012 70% of total primary energy supply was derived from this indigenous energy source. This means only 15 % dependence on foreign resources. The availability of this national resource makes the energy price for Estonians relatively low and the consumption of energy therefore relatively high. Also, while it provides a large degree of energy security, oil shale is highly carbon-intensive (94.2% of all CO2 emissions come from power generation). The CO2 intensity of electricity and heat generation in Estonia is nearly twice the International Energy Agency (IEA) average and one of the highest in the world. The government however is seeking to lessen the negative environmental impacts by phasing out old power plants and developing new technologies to reduce significantly CO2 emissions. Over the longer term, the Estonian government is aiming towards a reduction in the use of oil shale for electricity production and is partially shifting the use of oil shale in favour of the more environment-conscious production of shale oil and there is a constant shift towards renewable energy sources (Estonia 2013, 2013).
	Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate	As a result of Estonian cold climate, demand for heat in Estonia is quite strong. The energy intensity of the Estonian building stock is 200 kilowatt hours of heat per square metre per year ($\text{kWh}_{\text{heat}}/\text{m}^2/\text{yr}$), typical for cold climate European countries with building stocks dominated by older multi-story commercial buildings and apartment housing. The target is for comprehensive renovations to bring heat intensity of existing buildings down to 150 $\text{kWh}_{\text{heat}}/\text{m}^2/\text{yr}$. (Estonia 2013, 2013).
	Question of actual tenants when accessing relevant data and actual consumers	As households account for 33.8% (according to 2012 data) of the total final energy consumption (building sector in general 50% of total energy consumption) and considering that large part of the households make up the apartment buildings (apartment buildings house 75 % of the population), this makes the question of who owns the flat and who actually lives in it rather important in terms monitoring and evaluating the consumer behaviour, such as accessing directly the actual consumers. In Estonia many flat owners do not officially register the people who rent their flats as this brings with the unnecessary costs and bureaucracy for them. This is a general fear and way of renting in whole country (Estonia 2013, 2013).

	Size of the country	Given the small size of the country and its administration, it is far more important for Estonia to focus on a few critical priorities in energy efficiency, than to attempt a broad portfolio of activities. Recognising that some areas of energy efficiency policy are driven by EU regional processes, as a small country, these will create demand on operational resources. For a small country it can be difficult to manage the internal priorities with external requirements. It is important that Estonia minimises the effort and overheads in delivering energy efficiency policies (Estonia 2013, 2013).
	Gas supply security	Natural gas is primarily used for heat generation in Estonia. The use for electricity generation is extremely modest, as only 4% gas is used for electricity generation. Natural gas consumption for district heating (DH) is 48%, residential heating 25%, and industry 24%. Estonia has no own natural gas production, which makes the country fully dependent on gas imported directly from Russia by pipelines or drawn from storage facilities in Latvia. Thus the international relations in that level play an important key role in the supply security when it comes to DH and it is not that easy to exchange that portion of heat source with other local renewable sources. In Estonia natural gas plays an important role in the heating sector in both direct residential use and boiler houses and in combined power and heat production. For instance, in Estonia's capital Tallinn, DH is currently up to 70% dependent on gas. Natural gas thus plays a pivotal role in residential heating (Estonia 2013, 2013).
Educational	Clients lack appropriate knowledge on economic gains of energy efficiency and technologies thus do not feel like equal partners	In terms of energy saving measures, the awareness of consumers plays an important role in the success of the implementation of certain policies. There are barriers in many levels – the limited knowledge of energy saving in everyday life and the cost benefit which it can occur to as well the general environmental awareness which is linked to it. (MEAC, 2007)
	Technical problems	Clients lack technical knowledge and understanding the overall effect of renovation therefore being warding off the cooperation (ENMAK2030+..., 2015).
	Lack of comprehensive and systematic technical data for research	Lack of information and analysis regarding the potential usage of renewable energy in buildings. This is planned however, as one of the activities to be soon undertaken as stated in the Directive of Renewable Energy. Without this information it is difficult to educate engineers, architects and builders who are however, one of the main stakeholders when it comes to the implementation of energy efficiency measures and policies. There is no overview about the energy usage of authorities and social buildings, also the standards which would allow to compare energy usage criterions of public authorities for instance about equipment, rooms etc. These are just missing (NEEAP, 2014).
	Weak national guidance. Lack of knowledge on indoor air quality and health effects	National guidelines to inform the public have been rather weak and not well justified to different target groups. Awareness rising has been done or ordered

		by organisations responsible for national energy policies, or the unions of renewable energies who use the information available in Europe and elsewhere in the World (NEEAP, 2014). Still, situation is improving fast. Thanks to SA KredEX, Tallinn University of Technology and Tartu University Institute of technology consultants the wider public awareness on energy efficiency has constitutently rising during past 3...5 years.
	Not enough high-level trained specialists in energy efficiency matters	Large changes in economics have increased the capacity for specialists who would know modern technologies and solutions for more sustainable energy usage and who are capable to modernize, design and implement new and existing equipment, facilities and production units. The drought of specialists is mainly caused by lack of interest among youth towards engineering science and the improved opportunities for locals to work abroad rather than at home. The underfunding of some important science- and development sectors is also causing lack of experts in the country (MEAC, 2007). Up to present time the situation has been improved significantly. Architects and engineers have the specialised curricula including energy efficiency basic disciplines in housing and tertiary sector.

Table 5 Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Relatively cheap energy and fuel prices	The availability of local resources has for a long time helped to keep down the costs of heat and electricity prices which in turn affects the motivation to save energy. The stricter environmental restrictions in the energy sector have helped to control the energy prices, yet for more clear energy saving attitude, consumers must be controlled via stricter fuel and energy prices. In 2006 Environmental Charges Act was implemented in Estonia which determined the structure of the environmental laws and which is a good platform for the implementation of the so called <i>ecological tax reform</i> (MEAC, 2007).
Regionally fragmented energy saving potential	The cost of energy differs per region in Estonia – more expensive in the countryside than in the city due to longer pipelines, fewer consumers as well as due to depreciated boiler houses at smaller places. It remains to be that locations with higher energy prices (Tartu, Tallinn) but high incomes invest more in reconstruction and house insulation than cities\vilages where energy prices and household incomes are lower, such as in Narva where the waste heat from local power plant is directly used to heat up the local houses and where the income rates are lower, the proportion of compulsory costs are higher, also the real estate prices are lower. That also explains why KredEx apartment renovation grant applications are more actively being made in Tallinn compared to Narva (Lauri, M., 2014).
Dependence on private investment only	In Estonia, 96 % of the housing stock belongs to private owners. This makes the household income an important factor when it comes to investments made in energy efficiency or reconstruction. The more so, as the household sector is the main energy consumer in Estonia (low level of industrial activity). According to the household energy usage research (2012) about 50 % of the households considers the lack of money as the main barrier when it comes to improving their house\flat insulation. That was confirmed by 44% of the urban inhabitants in Estonia and 55% of the countryside inhabitants. More than half of all the households who have not yet improved the insulation of their homes, are neither planning to do so in the near future. Yet about 20 % of the households

	are planning to improve the insulation of their homes and about the same percentage of households' plans to invest in the insulation after longer than in 3 years period, as was stated in the 2014 report. At the same time, low income households, which makes about 60 % of the overall stock, watch after their energy usage more carefully than the households with higher salaries (Lauri, M., 2014).
Aging housing stock	Estonia has 630 000 dwellings. 58 % out of all the housing stock has been built during the soviet era (1946-1990) which means these are not responding to present day requirements anymore in terms of insulation and indoor climate. Most recent study revealed that an average energy intensity varies from 220 to 250 kWh/m ² , which is very high compared to that in Sweden and Finland (150kWh/m ²). When reconstructing these panel buildings, their lifetime may increase up to 50-80 years. At the same time, the importance of economic efficiency needs to be considered, assuming the risks of falling out of use. Yet based on the KredEx 2012 data, it was cheaper to renovate big panel apartment house with 45 flats (106 euros per square meter) than little wooden apartment houses (382 euros per square meter) with 2-19 flats (Lauri, M., 2014).
Development of building sector and the cost of renovations	The capacity of construction in Estonia has decreased since 2007 and has only started to increase again in 2011. Most of that increase is thanks to renovation funding given out by KredEx. Since 2011 the reconstruction prices have increased due to rising demand caused by available reconstruction grants (given out since September 2010). Yet the amounts paid have been lower than the grants which have been decided to be given out (support rate is 24 %) which means that the aid measure exceeds the amounts granted. KredEX grants have been given to 3.1 % of flats built before 1991 (SA KredEx, 2014).
Prerequisites for energy service undertakings within the commercial and public building sector	There exist preconditions for carrying out energy savings projects using the model of energy services undertakings, but one must take into account the various restrictions arising from the legal environment. The service sector's high consumption of thermal energy and electricity is also caused by the condition of buildings in the commercial sector. It is usually not the building's owner, but its' renter, that represents the service sector. As a result, building owners are not interested in investing in energy savings, because their clients are forced to pay the energy costs in any case. Here one can also find the preconditions for a market for energy services, yet the development of the market for energy services goes hand in hand with the development of the real estate sector if the quality of the rental space increases (and energy consumption falls) as a result, the owners of the rental space will be forced to invest in energy savings themselves. Solutions similar to the energy services model have now been offered to commercial and real estate undertakings in Estonia, and Riigi Kinnisvara AS has added energy efficiency clauses to its long-term rental contracts (NEEAP, 2014).
Energy services not too well connected with the potential client savings	There are not many companies in Estonia that advertise themselves as energy service enterprises. None of these operates as an energy services undertaking in the sense that payment for services provided is connected with savings to be achieved in the future, so-called ESCO principle. Instead, the purchaser pays for the investment and if this results in energy savings that exceed expectations, in some cases the savings are divided between the client and the energy service undertaking (NEEAP, 2014).
Dotation to renewable energy generators	Estonian transmission system operator Elering AS provides authorisations for grid connection on a first-come first-served basis. The renewable energy generators have to pay for all the cost related to the grid connection, including the cost of deep grid reinforcement. This encourages project developers to find locations with the lowest grid connection costs. Reportedly, some companies reserve connection capacity without using it, which impedes the use of best locations by potential other users. On the other hand, the renewable energy producers in Estonia have the possibility to apply for the renewable energy dotation (NEEAP, 2014; Renewable energy charge - https://www.elektrilevi.ee/taastuenergia-tasu).
Energy service enterprises' capacity to finance EE projects very low	Lack of enough finances hinders the energy service enterprises to undertake bigger energetic refurbishment projects in housing sector, not to speak about industry and tertiary. Banks do not guarantee such type of undertakings yet (ENMAK2030+..., 2015).

Availability of government financing support	Today, the use of biomass for heating is an economic/environmental option in many cases without any government support. Access to financing is a key barrier to increased investment in modernising heat boilers and switching from the use of fossil fuels to firing biomass. Therefore, the specific measures to promote renewable energy in the heating and cooling sector are limited to investment support (IEA, 2013). Still, under the Kyoto protocol JI mechanism the fuel switch has been performed in a small number of cases.
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Table 6 Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Finding agreement between different parties	In Estonia, only a small portion of apartments belong to the state or to a local governments. Most apartment buildings have an apartment association founded by the apartment owners in the building, which jointly represents apartment owners. The board is the body that represents and manages the affairs of an apartment association, while the supreme decision making and management body is the general meeting, which passes decisions by a majority vote. Obligations undertaken by the apartment association are connected with apartment ownership, i.e. in the event of the sale of the apartment ownership, the obligation will remain tied to the apartment, and will be transferred to the new owner. In connection with the above, there exist sufficient preconditions for the operation of energy services undertakings in the housing market in Estonia since the need for all parties to agree before committing to any energy efficiency improvements is one of the barriers. (NEEAP, 2014).
Lack of experience in procurement	The opportunities for considering energy saving aspect in acts regulating government procurement is yet weak and rather new, and there is lack of experience yet in organizing these kind of procurements. On the other hand, the Government of Estonia has approved the strategy of "The priorities of Estonian green and sustainable procurements for the years 2007-2009." (Directive 2004/17/EC, 2004; Õiguslik..., 2015) http://www.envir.ee/et/oiguslik-taust-keskkonnahoidlikud-riigihanked ,
Technical problems	Clients lack technical knowledge and understanding the overall effect of renovation therefore being shy to cooperate.
Operational overlap and clarity	The management and integration of operational activities in energy efficiency and the relationship with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) are unclear. The relationship between the MEAC, and the Ministry of the Environment and operational programmes should be restructured to remove operational overlaps and improve consistency. Estonia should consider creating an energy efficiency unit, which would be able to commission, research, evaluate and implement energy efficiency priorities maximising delivery efficiency, reporting to the Energy Department in the MEAC. The latter should lead co-ordination of energy efficiency policies across government to merit required focus and operational clarity. The Estonian Renewable Energy Association has drafted a proposal to streamline and centralise the procedures: to have an authority (a one-stop shop) that would facilitate all the processes for renewable energy project developers (Estonia 2013, 2013).
Co-operation between local municipalities	Space planning and land use are mainly in the hands of the local governments, and thus procedures differ significantly from one municipality to another. In addition there is also lack of communication between the local municipalities, whilst better co-operation would lead to more efficient and better results (Estonia 2013, 2013).
Estonia's dependence on district heating – principal agent failure	District heating is a natural choice of heating in densely built areas in colder climates and an efficient system can play an important role in improving living standards and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. In Estonia 70% of heating is provided as DH. The country has a comprehensive, but ageing DH pipeline system over 1,400 kilometres long. Householders, tenants and owners have limited options for alternative or improved heating systems

	while compulsorily tied to their own system, or to a system with inadequate price signals. For owner-occupants, apartment buildings are not easily retrofitted with insulation or heating efficiency improvements, and for tenants it may be difficult to seek improved performance from landlords, or DH service providers. In terms of buildings energy efficiency, this is probably one of the most widespread and least tractable examples of institutionalised principal agent failure. In addition, DH systems have high upfront infrastructure costs and many DH systems have inadequate or no metering (Estonia 2013, 2013).
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For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report "Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport".

Table 7 Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Energy usage habits in relation to relatively autonomous national energy market
	Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate
	Gas supply security
	Lack of high level specialists
	Regionally fragmented energy saving potential
	Dependence on private investment
	Aging housing stock
	Development of building sector and the price of renovations
	Access to financing
	Finding agreement between different parties, also between members of living association
Medium	Increasing consumer wellness
	Lack of client courage to do certain investments
	Dwellings left empty because of unemployment
	Clients do not feel like equal partners, lacking knowledge
	Weak national guidance
	Relatively cheap energy (only in Narva town which uses the waste heat from power plants) and fuel prices
	Prerequisites for energy service undertakings within the commercial and public building sector
	Energy services weakly connected with the potential savings
	High costs to renewable energy generators
Low	Lack of experience in procurement
	Operational overlap and clarity
	Co-operation between local municipalities
	Estonia's dependence on district heating – principal agent failure
	Question of actual tenants when accessing relevant data and actual consumers
	Size of the country
	Lack of sufficient data for comprehensive research

2.2 Mapping barriers in the transport sector

Energy efficiency in transport sector is derived by the following factors across both passenger and freight sectors: transport/travel demand; modal choice; vehicle technology-efficiency and user behaviour.

There are not many specific studies on barriers for transport energy efficiency. Current overview is mainly based on three studies:

- *Säästva transpordi raport* (Jüssi et al., 2010, a study on sustainable transport perspectives in Estonia, commissioned by Government Office of Estonia);
- *Eesti transpordi ja liikuvuse energiasäästupotentsiaali uuring* (Jüssi et al., 2014, a study on the energy saving potential and more than 20 policy instruments, commissioned in the framework of updating national energy sector development plan, ENMAK 2030+);
- *Energiasäästlik käitumine elanikkonnas. Eesti elanikkonna uuring* (Turu-uuringute AS 2012, a survey on consumer behaviour and energy saving, 1028 respondents over Estonia)

Table 8 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Cultural	Summer houses/ Second homes in low density areas	Property reform in 1990-s returned rural properties to many city dwellers and the cultural tradition of week-end travel to summer houses/family properties in the countryside are strong. This derives extra travel demand in low density rural areas and requires car ownership for urban households who would not need a private car. In 2000-s there was tendency to turn summer houses into permanent dwellings, generating overall car-based travel demand (Ahas et al., 2013).
	“Own house far from neighbours”	Estonian settlement structure has been traditionally very low density, with farmhouses located far from each other. Urbanization in the 60s and soviet area brought along high-rise urban developments, with counter-development of 90s- and 2000-s, with urban sprawl pressure by families moving outside the cities into low density suburban developments. This has generated high car dependency rates and long commuting distances. (Ahas et al., 2013).
Social	Social pressure for SUV-s and powerful passenger cars	Estonian vehicle fleet is one of the least fuel efficient ones in Europe. New passenger cars bought in Estonia are on average the least fuel efficient across EU (Transport and Environment, 2014). Trend: Continuous.
	Aggressive/ speedy driving style	In uncongested driving environments general traffic flow exceeds speed limits by 10 km/h in urban areas (Kendra et al., 2014) and more than 30% of drivers exceed speed limits on the main inter-city roads (of which 20% exceed the speed limit by 10 km/h). This also shapes general traffic culture, triggers perception of unsafety from one hand and choice of vehicles on the other hand (see previous barrier). Trend: Slightly reversing on main intercity roads due to automated speed control.
	Poor image of public transport	Before 1990-s car ownership level was relatively low and public transport and walking the main modes of mobility. In 1990- and early 2000-s public transport was rather seen as a rudiment of Soviet area and as a mode that

		rather carries the function of social support to low-income groups. Aging of public transport vehicles (especially train, trolleybuses, trams, second-hand buses from Scandinavia) and poor quality of rail infrastructure also enhanced this image. (Rannala et al., 2013). Trend: Slightly reversing.
	Image of cycling as sports and leisure activity	Cycling has still a marginal share of urban trips in Estonian cities (1-4% of commuting trips) (Jüssi et al., 2014) and is rather seen as a sports or Sunday activity (Antov et al., 2012). Trend: Increasing popularity of cycling as a transport mode.
Educational	Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals	Educational background of transport related professionals and civil servants does not support energy efficient transport system, highly road engineering oriented or civil servants employed with not relevant educational background. Trend: Educational background getting more relevant and diverse, more opportunities for degree studies abroad.

Table 9 Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Fiscal instruments in transport sector not sufficient for encouraging energy efficiency	Estonia is one of the few EU countries that does not have any car taxation (Jüssi et al., 2014). Trend: Income increases quicker than fuel excise duty, role of fiscal instruments weak (Jüssi et al., 2010).
Perverse incentives by employers/Employee benefits regarding cars	Tax free/low tax schemes for company cars and compensation of private car use, providing free parking (Jüssi et al., 2010; 2014).
National investment schemes encourage growth in road sector	National and EU funding of new investments primarily into road sector (by-passes, inter-city highway extensions, multi-level urban intersections). 75% of fuel duty income has been earmarked for road administration (until 2014). Trend: EU funding of new investments continuously prioritizing road sector (Ühtekuuluvuspoliitika... 2014).
Low population density	Estonia has a population of 1.32 million, with the capital region Tallinn of ca 550 000 inhabitants. The second largest city, Tartu, has 100 000 and third largest city, Narva 60 000 inhabitants. Apart from the bigger towns, the density is relatively low and efficient management of public transport challenging due to low overall demand. New urban developments have not enhanced settlement structure – especially existing rail corridors have not attracted public nor private investment.

Table 10 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Transport/mobility sector management is split between several departments, lack of integrated governance	Both on national and regional level, the management of transport and mobility issues is split between different ministries, state level departments and on local level – municipal departments. For example in Tallinn transport planning issues are split between 4 different departments – Urban planning department (spatial planning and building permits), Transport Department (public transport management, traffic and parking management), Public Works Department (cycling policy, building of infrastructure), Environmental Department (environmental assessment, emission and noise reduction, promoting sustainable transport).

	On the national level, the institutional capacity lies mainly in Road Administration (responsible for national road network, traffic safety, minor role in regional PT planning). (Jüssi et al 2014; Rannala et al., 2013)
Contradicting policy goals and implementation	Lack of integrated governance creates controversial policy goals and inconsistent policy implantation (national transport strategy gives priority to public transport, walking and cycling – but road infrastructure is planned to facilitate increasing car ownership, Tallinn city offers free public transport for its citizens, at the same time subsidizes building of parking lots and requires high number of parking spaces for new developments). (Authors’ analyses based on Jüssi et al 2014, Transpordi arengukava 2014)
Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance	Estonia is divided into 15 counties (state level regional administration) and 183 local municipalities and 30 cities. Local mobility/public transport and management of municipal roads and is streets is the responsibility of local municipalities and cities, whereas regional public transport, management of rail is organized by the state level. This creates unnatural barriers to seamless mobility, different ticketing and information systems and weak interconnectedness between different service providers. (Authors’ analyses based on Jüssi et al 2014, Rannala et al., 2013)
Lack of investment in public transport and walking/cycling infrastructure	There is neither national nor local level long-term development and investment scheme for public transport and cycling. Tallinn is partly closing trolleybus lines and replacing with diesel buses due to high investment needs and un-flexibility of current trolley-lines. Low investment in walking and cycling infrastructure reduces traffic safety of walking and cycling. (Jüssi et al 2014; Turu-uuringute AS 2012) Trend: Some re-investment into new buses, trams, new passenger trains, highly dependent on Green Investment Scheme agreements (CO ₂ sales), cost efficiency and take-up potential not considered.
Lack of integrated transport and land-use planning	New developments – housing areas, new office blocks, governmental buildings, shopping centres – do not take into account public transport potential and prioritize locations with good car accessibility. This is a major barrier for passenger rail development as the rail corridor density is relatively low already now. (Jüssi et al., 2014) After economic recession in 2008-2010, real estate developers increasingly take into account PT accessibility as an asset of properties. Policies: National spatial development plan Estonia 2030+ stresses the importance of rail network as a backbone for regional and national mobility. Enforcement weak due to relatively weak influence on private property developers. Ministry of Interior is working on planning guidance for integrating land use and transport planning. Investment scheme for multi-modal access to rail stations facilitates the development of areas close to rail stations.

For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from ‘High’ to ‘Low’, taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report “Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport”.

Table 11 Assessment of barriers in the transport sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
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High	Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals
	Fiscal instruments in transport sector not sufficient for encouraging energy efficiency
	Perverse incentives by employers/Employee benefits regarding cars
	National investment schemes encourage growth in road sector
	Low population density
	Transport/mobility sector management split between several departments, lack of integrated governance
	Contradicting policy goals and implementation
	Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance
	Lack of investment in public transport and cycling infrastructure
	Lack of integrated transport and land-use planning
Medium	Summer houses/ Second homes in low population density areas
	"Own house far from neighbours"
	Social pressure for SUV-s and powerful passenger cars
	Poor image of public transport
	Image of cycling as sports and leisure activity
Low	Lack of finances for road and street maintenance
	Aggressive/speedy driving style

3 BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

A good process status has been recognised by experts interviewed to assess the state of implementation of Energy Efficiency Action Plan. For Estonia the building sector energy efficiency is of high priority. In 2008, measures on the energy performance of buildings and also, a National Housing Development Plan for 2008 – 2013 were adopted (National ..., 2008). This is underlined by many good and efficient policy measures. There exist the incentive schemes like subsidies for energy efficient refurbishment of multistore apartment buildings, also for private houses, for energy audits and tax incentives to foster comprehensive renovation including introduction of energy recovering ventilation systems. Energy savings in buildings is the main priority of the policy, since most of the building stock was constructed before any performance requirements were introduced. Energetic refurbishment of building stock is pushed by Minimum Energy Performance standards and Energy performance Certificates. These instruments are supported by large soft loans and financial support programmes. (Energy ..., 2013).

The industrial and tertiary sector is well balanced, it considers many aspects and provides arrange of incentives and legislative acts to support energy efficiency in production processes. There are support measures available for energy conservation by manufacturers and a financial instrument that includes energy audits and financing opportunities. There is still considered to have too little or even lack of comprehensive programmes to promote energy efficiency in whole sector (Energy ..., 2013).

An important role when it comes to motivation behind achieving energy efficiency in building sector is the European Union. Based on the obligations set by EU, Estonia similarly to other EU countries, needs to aim for its energy targets in line with its national requirements set on buildings. Energy efficiency is a hot topic in many countries, being one of the priorities within EU economic growth strategy “Europe 2020”.

One of the key drivers in achieving energy efficiency in buildings is due to the fact that buildings make up around 50% of the total energy consumption in Estonia (average 40% within EU in total). Therefore it makes the largest energy consumption sector before transport-and industry and that is why the current national austerity measures are focused on improving the energy efficiency of multistore houses. In parallel with this the government is exploring another support schemes to stimulate renovation also of detached housing (Uuring...,2013). Up to 40% of the costs of energetic refurbishment costs of detached houses are compensated to the house-owners, and up to 60% in case of implementation of renewable energy appliances like solar heat panels or small wind turbines, up to 10 kW, see at: (<http://www.kredex.ee/eramaja/>). Unfortunately this has been the single action in 2012. During the next funding period starting from 2015 the 40% costs compensation (up to certain fixed level, EUR 4000) is foreseen to private houses in the course of replacement light fuel oil boilers to heat pumps

(Kredex..., 2015). People are enthusiastic to renovate their dwelling to make them better energy efficiency. Most significant barrier here happens to be the lack of proper finances, relevant knowledge on most rational solutions and lack of high quality construction companies able to achieve high performance standards, e.g. those fixed for nearly zero energy buildings (NZEB).

An important activity to in the field of information dissemination and informing general public on energy efficiency principal questions, practical learning sessions and other relevant undertakings, also training for justified target groups is Energy Efficiency week under title "Energy Wise" (Energiatark), see for more at: <http://energiatark.ee/seminaridkoolitused/>. During a week in November each year the whole country is informed via all communication channels about energy efficiency issues starting from kindergartens, schools and universities up to wider public. Big number of experienced specialists in the field are giving lectures, introducing novel EE appliances and presenting news on EE applications. The ongoing yearly event has gained high popularity. The organising team includes Kredex, AS Eesti Energia, SEI Tallinn Centre, Estonian Housing Association, Tartu Regional Energy Agency, Tallinn Energy Agency, Swedbank, et al. (<http://energiatark.ee/avaleh/>).

Another important driver to design energy efficient buildings already today is the financial aspect. An average lifetime of a building is estimated about 50-100 years. This means that about 92% of the buildings built in 2005 will also remain in 2020, and about 75% out of these will probably remain even by 2050. Building energy efficient houses\apartment blocks and other buildings is therefore a crucial investment already today as the decisions taken today will influence us for the next century. (KredEx, <http://www.kredex.ee>, 01.07.2015

The rising environmental awareness of public in Estonia is yet weak; however it is an important driver and motivation in the future, which could help to reduce energy consumption.

Each of the above listed barrier is different by its' character, some easier to solve and\or consider than the others. For instance, it is rather complicated to change the social values of the inhabitants, and one can never achieve everyone to start thinking in the same way, the more so when money is involved in terms of renovation and insulation as the issuing of Kredex financing depends on ones capacity to contribute your own financial contribution to it as well. Thus the matter of income plays an important role as in Estonia 96% of the housing stock is privately owned, making the access to financing a major barrier when implementing energy efficiency in the building sector.

The other barriers, such as institutional and educational, are a bit softer in their character since these are more of a matter of better re-thinking and organising, however also not easy to achieve. In order to eliminate institutional and operational overlapping, Estonia should consider steps to restructure and integrate the various agencies and ministries delivering energy efficiency policies and programmes into one central unit.

All the above listed barriers are in one way or another discussed in current Estonian policy documents and political strategy documents. Yet they are mainly elaborated as barriers to be still solved or which are being slightly worked on, but not entirely solved. Table 12 gives an overview of the barriers and the policy instruments in which these are addressed.

Table 12 Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers <i>(name the barrier)</i>	Scale <i>(Local/Regional/National?)</i>	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments <i>(name the instrument)</i>
Social	Increasing consumer wellness	National, regional, local	Various regulations set under the Building Act: - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009. - The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68). In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.
	Lack of client courage to do certain investments	National, regional, local	The educational programmes to encourage clients thanks to EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\EIC) financial support. The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered (grant issuing, trainings and consultations). Establishment of the smart energy network data portal Estfeed (www.estfeed.ee) as one of the actions taken under the strategy of "Estonia 2020".
	Dwellings left empty	National, regional, local <u>Note.</u> Although this happens all over the country, there are main key areas such as Lääne-Virumaa and Ida-Virumaa and Valga region.	Demolition support given by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre (EIC) The draft of the Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030 +)
Cultural	Energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate	National, regional, local	Various regulations set under the Building Act: - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). - The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68). In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.

	Energy usage habits in relation to relatively autonomous national energy market	National	Various regulations set under the Building Act: -The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.
	Question of actual tenants when accessing relevant data and actual consumers	National	No control mechanisms available to follow the legal act
	Size of the country	National	Depending on EU policies introduced and the internal legislation available
	Gas supply security	National	Estonian Gas supply risk assessment by MEAC 05.06.2013 Emergency Act 15.06.2009 (§ 34) Estonian Long-term Power Scenarios, Elering, 2014. The report on the Estonian electrical supply security, Elering, 2013.
Economic	Relatively cheap energy and fuel prices	National	Various regulations set under the Building Act: - Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009. -The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 no. 68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings. Environmental Charges Act 01.01.2006 (KeTS)
	Regionally fragmented energy saving potential	National, regional, local	Various regulations set under the Building Act: -Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107) -Introduction of stricter building codes in the new buildings. Minimum energy performance requirements (30.08.2012 no. 68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.
	Dependence on private investment	National	The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered. Various regulations set under the Building Act: -Introduction of stricter building codes in the new buildings. Minimum energy performance requirements (30.08.2012 nr.68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings

			must be net-zero energy buildings.
	Increasing heat cost impact on energy efficiency improvement . Aging housing stock	National	The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its funding programmes. The draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 +, (ENMAK 2030 +). Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107)
	Development of building sector and the price of renovations	National	The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered. Regulations set under the Building Act: -Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107) -The requirements of minimum energy performance (30.08.2012 nr.68) In line with EU Directive 2010\31\EU from 2019 onward all the new public buildings must be zero-energy buildings, and from 2021 onward all the new buildings must be net-zero energy buildings.
	Prerequisites for energy service undertakings within the commercial and public building sector	National	The Republic of Estonia established the company with the business name Riigi Kinnisvara Aktsiaselts(<i>State Real Estate Ltd, hereinafter RKAS</i>) according to the order no. 461 of the Government of the Republic of 28 June 2001 with the objective to guarantee the saving and effective provision of the real estate service to the executors of state authority. Riigi Kinnisvara AS has added energy efficiency clauses to its long-term rental contracts, see at: (http://www.rkas.ee/about-rkas)
	Costs to renewable energy generators	National	Redrafting the Electricity Market Act, Chpt.5.Generation, §57, 58, 59, see at: https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/523012015001/consolidate/current
	Access to financing	National, regional, local	The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered.
Educational	Clients do not feel like equal partners, lacking knowledge	National, regional, local	The educational programmes thanks to EU Cohesion Fund (KredEx\MEAC\EIC) financial support. The establishment of Foundation KredEx and its activities and services offered (energy audits, trainings and consultations). Establishment of the smart energy network data portal Estfeed (http://estfeed.ee/en/) as one of the actions taken under the strategy of “Estonia 2020”. Regulations set under the Building Act: -The issuing and formulation requirements of energy audit of the buildings (04.04.2014 nr.16)
	Lack of data for research	National, regional, local	Energy Sector Development Plan 2030 currently in the process of drafting the final version of legislation
	Weak national guidance	National	Various regulations set under the Building Act: -Energy label and the issuing procedures (17.12.2008 nr.107). Obligatory since 2009.

			-The requirements of minimum energy performance (04.08.2012 nr.68) -The issuing and formulation requirements of energy audit of the buildings (04.04.2014 nr.16)
	Lack of specialists	National, regional, local	Different state funded trainings by MEAC and KredEx. Barrier addressed in the draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030+, 2015)
Institutional	Finding agreement between different parties	National, regional, local	Establishment of Flat ownership and co-operative flat law (19.02.2014), to be put on effect on 01.01.2018 (Krts)
	Lack of experience in procurement	National, regional, local	European Commission Green Public Procurement Toolkit (GPP) 2008 - http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/toolkit_en.htm Instruction Materials on green public procurement by the Estonian Ministry of Environment - http://www.envir.ee/et/trukised-ja-artiklid-keskkonnahoidlike-hangete-teemal
	Operational overlap and clarity	National, regional, local	The draft of Estonian National Energy Development Plan 2030 + (ENMAK 2030 +) which integrates many previous strategies under new and revised document The website of http://www.energiatalgud.ee has been established by the Estonian Development Fund in order to collect all energy related information for the new 2030 + Development Plan and which integrates all the energy related information under one platform. The mentioned platform helps the different government agencies, sectoral experts, citizens and businesses to communicate in a more simple and coherent way.
	Co-operation between local municipalities	Regional, local	After joining the Covenant of Mayors Act, Estonian cities Rakvere and Tallinn have submitted their sustainable energy action plans to EU. Such actions could indirectly help to increase co-operation between local governments.
	Estonia's dependence on district heating – principal agent failure	National, regional, local	Grants programmes by Estonian Environmental Investment Centre, EIC.

3.2 Transport Sector

Main driving forces for energy efficiency in both public and private transport are economic. Increasing fuel prices and increased demand for transport increases both private and public transport costs and energy saving is an important source for saving. Reducing dependence on oil and coping with volatile oil prices are one of the drivers also listed in the National Transport Development Plan 2014-2020 (Transpordi arengukava, 2013).

International commitments (air pollution and emission targets) and EU transport, energy, climate and environmental policies also have a role, but as Estonia has a very high share of GHG emissions from energy production and the overall emissions are far lower than the 1990, transport emissions have received minor attention. With Effort Sharing Decision and new targets for 2030 with base year 2005 – reducing energy demand in transport sector receives more attention and several policy packages are being worked out to reach these targets (Estonian Energy Strategy 2030+, (ENMAK 2030+..., 2015)prepared by Ministry of Economy and National Climate Policy, currently drafted by working groups in Ministry of Environment.)

Social drivers are also significant – urbanization, aging population, changing attitudes of younger generation towards car ownership and urban lifestyle, quality of living environment, health issues related to sedentary and car based lifestyles, renaissance of cycling culture in the cities and high mobility of young international workforce tend to support more sustainable mobility patterns in Estonia. However, these issues have not been systematically studied in Estonia.

Even though in most cases policy instruments and policy packages do not implicitly elaborate on barriers, then most of the barriers are addressed in either existing or planned policy measures. Lack of appropriate transport infrastructure, driving culture, image of public transport and cycling, lack of fiscal incentives and capacity building are barriers that are more clearly addressed with current policy measures.

Table 13 Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers (name the barrier)	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments (name the instrument)
Social Cultural Educational	Summer houses/Second homes in low density areas	National	Land tax higher for properties where are no permanent residents.
	“Own house far from neighbours”	National	Better integration of transport and land use planning, encouraging more compact development – currently generally weak tools to enforce this policy. Planning guidance is being worked out in the Min. of Interior.
	Social pressure for SUV-s and powerful passenger cars	National	Increase of fuel excise duty; decreasing VAT reimbursement rate and additional reporting procedures for company cars; proposal of energy labelling scheme for cars (to come into force 2016).
	Aggressive/speedy driving style	National	Automatic speed controls, speed limit enforcement, redesigning infrastructure. Compulsory eco-driving module for driving licence training. Eco-driving promotion. Traffic safety campaigns.
	Poor image of public	Regional,	Renewal of public transport vehicle fleet (all

	transport	Local	passenger train fleet renewed in 2013, new trams and buses), reconstruction of railways (increased speeds) awareness raising campaigns, dedicated bus lanes in Tallinn. Free public transport in Tallinn. Public transport campaigns.
	Image of cycling as sports and leisure activity	National, Local	Plans for bicycle share schemes in 5 cities, new cycle infrastructure in city centres, awareness raising campaigns (European Cycling Challenge 2012-2015).
	Lack of integrated transport/mobility and planning professionals	National, Regional, Local	Promoting co-operation between universities, authorities and businesses for common curriculum on planning. R&D program for energy efficient transport planned.
Economic	Fiscal instruments in transport sector not sufficient for encouraging energy efficiency	National, Local	Increasing fuel excise duty, government considering other transport taxation alternatives (road charging, car taxation). Decreasing the VAT reimbursement rate for company cars. EV support scheme ELMO (purchase of EV-s, quick-charging stations, EV rent and taxis).
	Perverse incentives by employers/Employee benefits regarding cars	National	Decreasing the VAT reimbursement rate for company cars. (2014) Free public transport for Tallinn citizens.
	National investment schemes encourage growth in road sector	National, local	Abolishing earmarking of fuel duty revenues for roads. New schemes on investment for integrated solutions in urban areas/railway stations, county centres.
	Low density	National, regional, local	Planning guidance being developed by Ministry of Interior; National Spatial Development Plan 2030+.
Institutional	Transport/mobility sector management is split between several departments, lack of integrated governance	National, local	No policy on national and local level. Public Transport centres (<i>ühistranspordikeskus</i>) established in 4 regions.
	Contradicting policy goals and implementation	National, local	No implicit policy. R&D program planned for transport energy efficiency. SUMP network of experts and cities.
	Administrative fragmentation and lack of integrated governance	National, regional, local	Public transport centres created in 4 counties for better coordination of public transport at regional level. Common information system for all Estonian PT providers – Common ticket payment system (contactless card) for Tallinn city and Harju county
	Lack of investment in public transport and walking/cycling	National, local	No long-term investment plan for public transport and cycling. New schemes on

	infrastructure		investment for integrated solutions in urban areas/railway stations, county centres. Green Investment Schemes.
	Lack of integrated transport and land-use planning	National, regional, local	National spatial development plan Estonia 2030+ stresses the importance of rail network as a backbone for regional and national mobility (Eesti 2030+, 2012). Enforcement weak due to relatively weak influence on private property developers. Ministry of Interior is working on planning guidance for integrating land use and transport planning. Investment scheme for multi-modal access to rail stations facilitates the development of areas close to rail stations.
	Lack of finances for road and street maintenance	National, local	Increasing fuel excise duty 2016-2018.

4 KEY FINDINGS

Buildings

The second NEEAP presents 99 measures for increasing energy efficiency. It also includes a long-term forecast of the final energy consumption in Estonia by the year 2020 compiled by the MEAC. According to this forecast, Estonia's final energy consumption would be 137 PJ (3 272 kt oe) in the case of the basic (reference) scenario and 131 PJ (3 127 kt oe) in the case of the additional energy efficiency scenario in 2020. Additionally, it has to be noted that the National Reform Programme 'Estonia 2020' (approved by the Government in 2011) established two major priorities of the Government for moving towards environmentally sustainable economy and energy sector:

- implementing long-term structural changes in the energy sector in harmony with Estonia's energy security and energy efficiency objectives;
- reducing the general resource-intensity, including energy intensity, of the economy, through increasing energy efficiency.

In the Programme the Government has set an ambitious goal for making final energy consumption more efficient in Estonia – to keep the final energy consumption in 2020 at the same level it was in 2010, i.e. reducing final consumption of energy by approx. 11% compared to the forecast for 2020.

The measures introduced by the National Housing Development Plan for the years 2008–2013 are carried out by the MEAC, together with KredEx and in co-operation with local authorities. Estonia started to support the refurbishment of apartment buildings built before 1990 in 2003 already.

Tallinn University of Technology arranges training courses for energy auditors. The energy efficiency certificates for buildings are issued since January 2009. Estonia has a surplus of Kyoto Protocol assigned amount units amounting to 85 million units. Starting from the end of 2010 Estonia has successfully sold a great amount of AAUs. The revenues from the sales (up to now 365 M€) are used according to the relevant Green Investment Scheme. According to statistics from GIS almost 500 buildings in the public sector have been refurbished, including improvement of thermal insulation. The actual number of state and municipality owned buildings being currently renovated in frames of

the GIS is 493 with the total floor area of more than 1.1 Mm² (Energy ..., 2012). The total renovation budget reached approximately 172 MEUR.

Regarding the residential sector, for investments in apartment buildings the detailed application procedures were elaborated as well. To get the grant money the energy savings from 20% to 50% have to be reached. The potential of energy savings together with plan for proposed renovation works have to be compiled by the certified energy auditor. Currently, the first wave of renovation works are completed. The average renovation cost is 60 EUR/m² and estimated energy saving is 40%. The similar grant was available for renovation (thermal insulation) of small residential buildings: family houses, detached and semi-detached houses). According to the energy audits, the average renovation cost in this type of buildings is 160 EUR/m² and estimated energy saving will be 68 kWh/m² a year.

Main barriers in buildings sector are related to social, educational and economic barriers. The following list of major big barriers could be emphasised:

- energy usage habits in relation to relatively autonomous national energy market;
- energy intensity in relation to Estonian cold climate;
- gas supply security;
- lack of high level specialists;
- regionally fragmented energy saving potential;
- dependence on private investment;
- aging housing stock;
- development of building sector and the price of renovations;
- access to financing;
- finding agreement between different parties, also between members of living association.

Transport

Energy efficiency has had a minor role in national and local transport policies and strategies over the last 20 years as energy production and housing sector was the main focus for energy efficiency improvements and emission reduction. Growing economy, urban sprawl and relocation of jobs has driven increased demand in road transport and private car use, resulting in the overall decrease in transport energy efficiency since 2000. This demonstrates that policies in the transport sector have not addressed energy efficiency sufficiently and there is lack of systematic policy packaging, lack of research regarding barriers and tackling them.

Transport sector's high energy and emissions saving potential was first recognized in Sustainable Transport Report in 2011, which was further elaborated in the preparation of National Energy Strategy 2030+ in 2012-2014. National Transport Strategy 2014-2020 sets clear energy efficiency targets for transport sector.

Main barriers are related to lack of fiscal measures to improve fuel efficiency of vehicle fleet, lack of long-term funding schemes for developing public transport and cycling, lack of integrated urban and transport planning and low density of population.

Many of the listed barriers in buildings and transport sectors have been already addressed through existing policies. It however, will take time and appropriate supporting financing to overcome and reach higher energy efficiency targets set in national strategies and action plans.

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

BAFA – Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle, Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export control

BDI – Bundesverband der Deutschen Industrie, Federal Association of the German Industry

BEV – Battery electrified vehicle

BfEE – Bundesstelle für Energieeffizienz, Federal Department for Energy Efficiency

BMWi – Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie, Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

BMUB – Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, Bau und Reaktorsicherheit, Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety

BMVI – Bundesministerium für Verkehr und Digitale Infrastruktur, Federal Ministry for Transport and Digital Infrastructure

CO₂ – Carbon dioxide

Dena – Deutsche Energieagentur, German Energy Agency

DDIV - Dachverband deutscher Immobilienverwalter, Umbrella organisation of German property managers

EED – Energy Efficiency Directive

EMS – Energy management system

EnEV – Energieeinsparverordnung, Energy Saving Ordinance

EPBD – Energy Performance of Buildings Directive

EU – European Union

EV – Electric vehicle

GDP – Gross domestic product

GdW - Bundesverband deutscher Wohnungs- und Immobilienunternehmen, Federal Association of German Apartment and Real Estate Companies

HEV – Hybrid electrified vehicle

ICCT - International Council on Clean Transportation

ITDP – Institute for Transportation and Development Policy

KBA – Kraftfahrtbundesamt, Federal Motor Transport Authority

KfW – Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau, Bank for Reconstruction

kWh – kilowatt hours

LPJ – liquefied petroleum gas

MBWSV - Ministerium für Bauen, Wohnen, Stadtentwicklung und Verkehr des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen, Ministry for Construction, Living, Urban Development and Transport of the Federal State of Northrhine-Westfalia

m₂ – Square meter

NAPE – Nationale Aktionsplan Energieeffizienz, National Action Plan Energy Efficiency

PJ - Petajoule

PV – Photovoltaic

PHEV – Plug-in electric vehicle

R&D – Research and development

SME – Small- and medium-sized company

SRU – Rat von Sachverständigen für Umweltfragen, Council of Experts for Ecologic Questions

TCO – Total Cost of Ownership

TRAWOS - Institut für Transformation, Wohnen und Soziale Raumentwicklung, Institute for Transformation, Habitation and Social Spatial Development

UBA – Umweltbundesamt, Federal Environment Agency

VCD – Verkehrsclub Deutschland

WP – Working package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In Germany, the buildings and the transport sectors have shares of 38% and 28% in final energy consumption. Combined with high potentials for energy savings, buildings and transport are key sectors to improve energy efficiency.

The report identifies barriers in Germany hindering the diffusion of energy efficiency. In this context, complex incentive structures are presented and manifold barriers discussed; sub-grouped by social, cultural, educational, economic and institutional barriers. Moreover, links between barriers and policies are presented. Relevant actors involved are individuals, the national, regional, local level as well as actors in support chains (e.g. qualified craft business and energy consultants in the buildings sector). For buildings, the existing stock was the focus of the analysis.

Concerning *buildings*, the household sector makes over 60% of building-related final energy consumption, followed by the commercial buildings with approx. 29% and industrial buildings with 10%. Thermal heating has the highest share in all sectors. The high importance in energy consumption is also reflected by the German energy policy, particularly thermal refurbishment has a priority in the set national building targets. Most of the found literature on barriers in the buildings sector deal with refurbishment of residential buildings. Key findings for the German buildings sector concerning barriers are:

- Several barriers in the building sector exist. These are highly complex and interrelations between the sub-groups exist (e.g. age of building owners as a social barrier also influences investment decisions)
- When barriers are discussed, it is important to distinguish between the group of actors (e.g. landlords might respond differently to motivation factors than homeowners)
- Barriers, which dwelling owners are aware of, need to be distinguished from those owners are not aware of (e.g. misperception of the energetic building condition vs. technical/constructional issues). A distinction also needs to be made for benefits of refurbishments.
- The review has shown that according to barriers specific target groups (e.g. older dwelling owners, energy saving motivated owners) play an important role and an differentiation needs to be made when barriers are to be overcome
- The identified manifold economic barriers show that financial support is still necessary to accelerate the uptake of energy efficiency improvement, however information tools on all levels are also necessary. Particularly to address 'soft' or non-economic barriers like lack of awareness and risk perception and thus incentivise end-users to change their behaviour.

One or more policy instruments already address several of the identified barriers towards energy-efficient buildings. Other barriers have not been explicitly addressed by policies yet.

Energy-efficient *transportation* can be addressed on three different levels. Potentials for energy efficiency are available for single vehicles (vehicle efficiency), individual trips (travel efficiency - based on the modal choice) and for the whole transport system (system efficiency – based on the generation of transport demand). Road based transport is responsible for 82% of the energy consumption in the German transport system. Consequently, the largest potential for energy efficiency improvements can be seen in increasing the efficiency of road vehicles and in shifting passenger and freight transport to more efficient modes. However, several barriers impede the full utilization of the energy efficiency potential in the German transport sector:

- Passenger transport is heavily relying on passenger cars. Private cars have a long tradition as status symbol in Germany and are often perceived as most flexible and convenient form of travelling. Decision making processes on different governmental levels have led to a

predominantly car-oriented infrastructure in many regions and a paradigm shift towards prioritization of energy-efficient modes in planning and investment decision is still at the beginning. Consequently, the framework conditions (e.g. infrastructure provision, taxation) for passenger mobility are very attractive for individual motorized transport, while non-motorized transport and public transport is perceived as less attractive.

- The technological potential of vehicle efficiency is not fully tackled due to higher purchasing prices for energy-efficient vehicles or alternative drivetrains. Most consumers are not willing to accept surcharges. Furthermore, they usually do not reflect the vehicle's energy efficiency in their purchasing decision.

One or more policy instruments already address several of the identified barriers towards energy-efficient transport, but a clear prioritization of energy efficient modes and vehicles through targeted investment decisions and taxation is still missing. Furthermore, some policy instruments target important lever for more energy efficiency, but have only a limited effect due to their inherent design (e.g. limited effect of CO₂ based vehicle taxation).

INTRODUCTION

This report provides the contents of the national report for Germany, which seeks to identify country-specific barriers to energy efficiency policy.

The national report is structured as follows:

1. Context
2. Mapping country-specific barriers in the building sector at local, regional and national scales
 - Social
 - Cultural
 - Economic
 - Educational
 - Institutional
3. Mapping country-specific barriers in the transport sector at local, regional and national scales
 - Social
 - Cultural
 - Economic
 - Educational
 - Institutional
4. Linking country-specific barriers to policy instruments
5. Key findings

The material collected through this country report will be used to inform deliverable D.2.1 'Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in building and transport'. The outcome of D.2.1 will be used in tasks WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country in WP2 will be considered in the development of the scenarios build in the LEAP software.

More specifically, WP2 provides a qualitative assessment of the key barriers for each country (e.g. low impact, medium impact, high impact), as these will be presented in this report by each partner. This assessment will be based on the expert view of each partner. WP3 will then attempt to quantify the effect of these barriers in combination with the policy instruments that allow overcoming them. The research outcome of WP3 will be included in WP4.

1. CONTEXT

1.1. BUILDINGS SECTOR

Final energy consumption in Germany accounted for approx. 8,800 PJ and is typically divided into industry (2,634 PJ; 30%), transport (2,568 PJ; 29%), households (2,333 PJ; 27%) and the commercial sector (1,346 PJ; 15%) (BMWI 2014b; data for 2011).

Buildings have a share of around 40% in total final energy consumption (BMWI 2014a) and account for one quarter of CO₂ emissions in Germany (UBA 2013). Building-related energy consumption by the private household sector amounts to 1,940 PJ in 2011; taking into account buildings in industry and the commercial sector, this leads to 3,151 PJ¹. Space heating alone has a share of over 28% in total final energy consumption (BMWI, 2014a). Combined with the high potential for energy savings (Horst et al. 2011), buildings are a main target sector in Germany to mitigate climate change and to improve energy security.

Concerning shares of single sectors in building-related energy consumption (Figure 1), the household sector (space heating and hot water requirements) makes over 60% of building-related final energy consumption, followed by the commercial buildings with approx. 29% and industrial buildings with 10%. Applicable to all sectors, space heating has the highest share, followed by hot water requirements and lighting.

Figure 1 Building-related energy consumption by end-use in % (2011). Source: BMWI 2014.

¹ only including permanently installed lighting in the commercial sector and excluding appliances, information and communication technologies etc.

In the last decade, Germany was already successful in lowering specific space heat requirements of the residential buildings stock as temperature adjusted consumption fell from 198 kWh/m² (2000-2002 average) to 146 kWh/m² (2010-2012 average) (BMW_i, 2014a)². However, the whole potential for energy savings was not utilised as growth in living space, triggered by growth in income and demographic structures, occurred during the same time period. The annual growth rate in living space has been 1% since 1996 (Weiß & Dunkelberg 2010). Currently, the floor area of residential buildings adds up to 3,720 million m² (2011) and is expected to grow by 7% until 2030 (Schlesinger et al. 2014).

The absolute number of non-residential buildings is estimated to be 1.7 million (of which 12% are publicly owned). Residential buildings amount to 18.2 million (BDI, no year). Weiß & Dunkelberg (2010) stress the importance of single to two-family houses as a sub-group of residential buildings, as specific heat energy requirements are higher than in multi-family houses. Floor area of single to two-family houses and multi-family houses is 2,167 and 1,481 million m² respectively in 2011 (Schlesinger et al. 2014). The share of single to two-family houses accounts for 60% of floor area.

Krémer et al. (2005) further points out that the quality of new buildings and existing buildings highly differs. While more than 35% of new buildings are built with a low-energy-house standard (less than 70 kWh/m²a)³, the existing building stock shows huge potentials for energy efficient modernisation (between 160-200 kWh/m²a). Currently, 60% of the German building stock has not been energetically refurbished (DDIV, 2015).

The importance of thermal heating in energy consumption is also reflected by the German energy policy, particularly thermal refurbishment has a high priority in the set national building targets. Linked with the governments decision to reduce primary energy demand of buildings by 80% until 2050 and heat consumption by 20% until 2020, is the requirement to increase the rate of thermal refurbishment from currently approx. 1% to 2% per year (BMW_i, 2014a).

Table 1 lists the annual modernisation rate of single building components in residential buildings. The most common technical measure taken is the renewing of the heating system, while insulation of the basement and the façade are least favoured (Jahnke & Verhoog, 2012).

Table 1 Annual modernisation rate (in %) of buildings components (residential). Source: Jahnke & Verhoog (2012) and Diefenbach et al. (2010), numbers adapted from Jahnke & Verhoog (2012).

Technical measure	Diefenbach et al. (2010)	Jahnke & Verhoog (2012)
Heating	2.8-3.5	3.2
Facade	0.8-1.1	0.9
Roof/ upper floor	1.3-1.7	1.4
Basement	0.3-0.4	0.5
Windows	1.3-1.8	1.6

¹⁾ years 2000-2009

² The specific energy consumption of non-residential buildings is much higher than in residential buildings. However, statistical data for non-residential buildings is scarce (BMW_i, 2014a).

³ Further improvements in the future are expected due to further strengthening of the EnEV (energy saving ordinance).

1.2. TRANSPORT SECTOR

With more than 2,600 PJ, transport accounted for 28% of total final energy consumption in 2013, with greenhouse gas emissions in the sector amounting to some 17% of the German greenhouse gas emissions (BMW⁴ 2014c, p. 40). The energy consumption of the transport sector includes final energy consumption of rail transport, road transport, air transport, coastal shipping and inland navigation⁴. Road transport accounts for the largest share of transport energy consumption and is responsible for about 82% (2,167 PJ) of the energy consumed. Private motorized transport can be identified as being responsible for about two-thirds of the energy consumption in road transport – and for more than half of the total transport energy consumption. Road-based public passenger transport accounts only for a minor share in the energy consumption (1.5% of road based energy consumption). Road-based goods transport is responsible for nearly one third of the road-based energy consumption (BMVI 2014)

Aviation⁵ is responsible for about 14% (375.2 PJ), followed by rail transport (2.2%, 57.5 PJ). Coastal shipping and inland navigation have only a minor share in transport final energy consumption (0.4%, 12.2 PJ (BMW⁴ 2014a, p. 39).

Energy consumption in the German transport sector reached its highest level in 1999 at 2,781 PJ. Hence, a reduction of about 6% was achieved between 1999 and 2013 (Figure 2). However, in recent years, a slight increase in energy consumption is observed, so that the 2013 level is 1% higher compared to 2005. This is mainly due to rising energy consumption from road transport, while rail transport, coastal shipping and inland navigation experienced a decrease compared to 2005. This development has to be seen against the background of rising transport volume in passenger and goods transport. In total, a decrease of energy consumption per passenger kilometre and tonne kilometre is observed – indicating rising energy efficiency in the transport sector. Passenger kilometres travelled increased by 56% compared to 1990 (by 5% compared to 2005) and tonne kilometres by 115% compared to 1990 (11% compared to 2005).

Figure 2 Development of energy consumption in the transport sector in Germany. Source: BMW⁴ 2014b.

⁴ The final energy consumed by providing transport services is included, while energy consumption from lighting and other infrastructural services are not covered (BMW⁴, 2014).

⁵ Based on the aviation fuel consumption in Germany, thus also aviation fuel is included, which is consumed by international aviation.

Still, Germany is far away from its objectives for the transport sector, which are (1) the reduction of final energy consumption from transport by about 10% by 2020 compared to 2005, (2) the reduction of final energy consumption from transport by about 40% by 2050 compared to 2005, and (3) the distribution of 1 million electric vehicles by 2020/ 6 million electric vehicles by 2030.

Currently, conventional vehicles clearly dominate the German vehicle fleet. Less than 2% of the passenger car fleet is equipped with alternative propulsion system. 67% are conventional gasoline vehicles and 31% run on diesel (KBA 2015). Among the alternative fuels, LPG (liquefied petroleum gas) has a share of 1.1% and natural gas a share of 0.2%. Only 0.2% of the passenger car fleet is partially electrified (Hybrid electric vehicles/ Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles) or fully electrified (BEV). However, there is a positive development in terms of electric vehicle registrations (see Figure 3). In 2014, about 8,500 fully electrified vehicles were newly registered, thus a market share of 0,3% was achieved (Figure 3). Partially electrified vehicles had a market share of 0.9 %, while HEV dominate clearly in this segment. Still, Germany has a relatively low market share of EVs compared to other European countries like Norway, the Netherlands, France or Denmark.

Figure 3 Annual registrations electric passenger cars in Germany and total registrations. Source: KBA 2015.

Figure 4 highlights the efficiency improvements realised in Germany since 1990 for different modes⁶. Strong energy efficiency increases have been achieved for passenger cars, passenger air transport and lorry-based goods transport. Comparing the differences in energy efficiency between the various modes in passenger transport reveals that rail-based transport and coach services are nearly twice as efficient as passenger cars. Regarding of goods transport waterway and rail-based transport need less than half of the energy per tonne kilometre than road-based transport by lorries. Consequently, a significant potential for increased energy efficiency in the transport sector lies in mode shift e.g. from road to rail transport.

Figure 4 Final energy consumption of selected transport modes in MJ/pkm or MJ/tkm in 1990 to 2010. Source: dena 2012.

In general, it has to be acknowledged that to achieve a more energy-efficient transport system all determinates of energy consumption in transport have to be addressed. The full potential for energy savings can only be realised by taking all elements of the transport system into account - ranging from energy consumption of single vehicles to the overall need for transport. Energy-efficient transportation can be realised on three different levels. Potentials for energy efficiency are available for single vehicles (vehicle efficiency), individual trips (travel efficiency - based on the modal choice) and for the whole transport system (system efficiency – based on the generation of transport demand). The overall energy efficiency of the transport system results from the performance on all three levels (Böhler-Baedeker et al., 2012).

In Germany, passenger transport volume constantly increased from 1,087 billion passenger kilometres in 2005 to 1,141 billion passenger kilometres in 2013 (BMVI, 2015). About 80% of this is covered by private motorized transport, which has a relative constant modal share since 2005. The domestic freight transport volume increased from 580 billion tonne-kilometres in 2005 to 645 billion tonne-kilometres in 2013. About 70% of the freight transport volume is covered by road-based transport. Consequently, there is significant energy efficiency potential in shifting trips from road to rail.

⁶ Improvements are realised in terms of energy consumption per passenger kilometre or tonne kilometre. This indicator depends not only the technical vehicle efficiency (fuel use per vehicle kilometre travelled), but is also influenced by the occupancy rate of the vehicle (e.g. passengers per car), thus can be influenced by organisational efficiency improvements.

1.3. OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Energy efficiency plays a major role in Germany. Together with renewable energies, energy efficiency is a central pillar of the energy transition (“Energiewende”). In the energy concept of 2010, concrete targets for energy efficiency have been set. In order to implement the energy transition and to fulfil the targets of the energy concept, the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE) was adopted. Together with the Climate Action Programme 2020, comprehensive policy packages have been introduced.

Germany has a long tradition of energy efficiency policy – the first thermal insulation ordinance (Germ.: Wärmeschutzverordnung⁷) was adopted in 1979. Especially regarding the buildings sector, comprehensive policy packages are already in place.

Concerning buildings, the main national authorities are the Federal Ministry for Economy Affairs and Energy and Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety. The federal government is, moreover, supported by the German energy agency (dena) and the government-owned development bank KfW to implement regulations, initiatives and programmes. Financial incentives are additionally provided by the German Federal Office of Economics and Export Control (BAFA). Furthermore, a division of the BAFA also supports the Government by evaluating energy efficiency policies.

Besides national activities, the federal state and municipal level supports the uptake of energy efficiency (BMW 2014c). Federal states play an important role in implementing regulatory provision of the energy saving ordinance (Germ.: Energieeinsparverordnung, EnEV) and the EU Ecodesign Directive (2009/EC/125, as they are responsible for supervising these (BMW 2014c). Many cities and municipalities (e.g. the cities of Hamburg, Heidelberg, Munich, Freiburg) committed themselves to significant emission reductions or joined frameworks of international city-alliances. Due to financial short passes, many municipalities use national or EU-funds to take energy efficiency action. Moreover, several energy agencies have emerged and implemented additional energy efficiency programmes.

Concerning the transport sector, the main national authorities are the Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure, the Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration, the Federal Motor Transport Authority, the Federal Office of Civil Aviation, the Federal Office for Goods Transport and the Federal Railway Authority. Additionally, there are transport authorities at the level of the Federal States. However, other Federal ministries (e.g. Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety and the Federal Ministry of Finance) are (partly) involved in the decision-making process concerning transport policy. Furthermore, there are more important actors influencing the transport policy at different levels, e.g. German railways (Deutsche Bahn), regional authorities of public transport, transport associations, German car industry etc. to name just a few.

Table 2 and Table 3 display the most relevant policy instruments for energy efficiency in the buildings and the transport sector currently in place in Germany, and must not be taken as an exhaustive list. Most of the policy instruments refer to the national level. Additionally, there are also actions taken at the level of the Federal States and on local level.

⁷ Full German title: Verordnung über energiesparenden Wärmeschutz bei Gebäuden.

Table 2 Main German policy instruments for the buildings sector.

German policy instruments for the buildings sector	
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance (Energieeinsparverordnung, EnEV) • Inspections of boilers (based on EnEV Section 3 §10 & EnEV Section 6 §26b) and heating/cooling installations (based on EnEV Section 3 §12) • Heating cost regulation (Germ.: Verordnung über die verbrauchsabhängige Abrechnung der Heiz- und Warmwasserkosten) • Energy performance certificate • Act on changes in the rent law (Germ.: Mietrechtsänderungsgesetz) • Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (2010/31/EU, EPBD) • EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (2012/27/EU, EED) • EU Ecodesign Directive (2009/EC/125) • Mandatory energy audits in non-SMEs (based on EED) • Smart metering rollout
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seal of quality efficiency house • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs (KfW) • KfW construction monitoring • co2online • Mission E • Heating system check (Germ.: Heizungscheck) • Pilot Programme Energy Saving Meters • Initiative Energy Efficiency • Energy efficiency award
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW Energy-efficient construction • KfW Energy-efficient refurbishment • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • Energy tax • BAFA cross-cutting technologies
Capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency networks Initiative • Promotion of energy management systems (EMS) • Funding for the retraining as an energy consultant • Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants • IPEEC (International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation)
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence centre for public buildings incl. default guarantees

German policy instruments for the buildings sector (continuation)	
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low energy buildings project (dena) • Efficiency house Plus • Research initiative “Zukunft Bau” • Research for energy-optimised construction • Public procurement guidelines • 6th energy research programme

Table 3 Main German policy instruments for the transport sector.

German policy instruments for the transport sector	
Planning Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility and fuel strategy: introduction of alternative fuels and innovative drive technologies • Improving bicycle infrastructure: investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks, and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic • Federal transport infrastructure plan 2015: stronger emphasis on railways and waterways (freight) concerning budget • National cycling plan • Single European Sky: Improving flight paths in regard to environmental efficiency
Regulatory instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂-emission standards of new vehicles • Fuel quality ordinance: fuel quality standards, biofuel quotas, biomass sustainability ordinance etc. • Voluntary agreement with German National Railways: specific CO₂ reduction targets for the period 2006-2020
Economic instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂-related motor vehicle tax • Fiscal allowances for work-related travel expenses • Heavy goods vehicle toll charges • Municipal transport financing act and regionalisation act: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities • Investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic • Ecological tax reform: eco tax on motor fuels, extension of tax reduction for natural gas in the transport sector • Levy on air traffic: “ecological” levy on air traffic at the national level for all flights from German airports
Information and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling • Mobility management action programme • “me and my car” campaign • “new driving” campaign
Policy instruments for Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National innovation programme for hydrogen and fuel cell technology • Government electro mobility programme • Funding programme for electro mobility in model regions • Electro mobility funding

1.4. OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY

The German green-tech market is expected to grow: for the period of 2013 to 2025 an average annual growth rate of 6.6% is forecasted, implying that the market volume would increase from EUR 344 billion in 2013 to EUR 470 billion in 2025 (BMUB 2014). This green tech market does of course not only include energy efficiency in buildings and transport⁸, however, it has a big share: with a current market volume of EUR 100 billion, energy efficiency is the biggest of the green tech lead markets. The market volume of sustainable mobility accounts for EUR 53 billion.

Nearly half of the lead market for energy efficiency (EUR 45 billion) belongs to energy-efficient buildings and energy-efficient appliances. Most important technologies are the following (BMUB 2014):

Energy-efficient buildings:

- Thermal insulation
- Building automation
- Efficient heating, ventilation and air-conditioning systems
- Passive houses / PlusEnergy houses

Energy-efficient appliances:

- Energy-efficient white goods
- Green IT
- Energy-efficient lighting
- Energy-efficient consumer electronics

The lead market for sustainable mobility shows the strongest growth among the lead markets, on the national as well as on the global market. The following **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.** shows the market segments and their most important technologies.

⁸ Six green-tech lead markets can be regarded: energy efficiency; sustainable water management; environmentally friendly power generation, storage and distribution; material efficiency; sustainable mobility; and waste management and recycling (BMUB, 2014).

Sustainable mobility	
Market segments	Key technology lines
Alternative drive technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hybrid drive systems Electric drive systems Fuel cell drive systems
Renewable fuels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bioethanol Biodiesel Biomethane Hydrogen from renewable resources Biokerosene
Technologies to increase efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency gains in combustion engines Lightweight engineering technologies Energy-saving tires
Transportation infrastructure and traffic management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rail vehicles and infrastructure Traffic control systems Filling station infrastructure for alternative drive systems Public transport Car sharing Cycle paths

Figure 5: Market segments and key technology lines in the lead market for sustainable mobility. Source: Roland Berger (BMUB, 2014).

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

To better understand how existing economic as well as non-economic barriers can be overcome, it is important to understand the overall attitude of the German society towards the environment in general and energy efficiency in particular. This will be discussed in 2.1.

Chapter 2.2. and 2.3. then map the main identified social, economic, cultural, educational and institutional barriers in the German context, which currently limit a further diffusion of energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sectors. Moreover, the importance of identified sector-specific barriers is qualitatively assessed.

2.1. AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ENVIRONMENT IN THE TWO RESPECTIVE SECTORS

The overall attitude of the German population towards the environment in general is relatively stable as suggested by a study survey⁹ investigating on the environmental awareness and behaviour of the German population. Study data of the last decade (2004 to 2014) shows that around one fifth of the respondents think that the environment is the most urgent problem in Germany (BMU & UBA, 2015).¹⁰

With respect to the buildings, UBA (2014b)¹¹ finds that the majority of respondents (62%), particularly those with a household net income of more than EUR 3,000, see large living space occupied by few people as environmentally harmful. However, at the same time, for many Germans (54%) owning a house is a central life goal, especially for those with a monthly net household-income above EUR 3,000.

Environmental behaviour of Germans over time is contextual. On the one hand, the number of respondents obtaining green electricity from utilities increased from 8% in 2008 to 20% in 2012. On the other hand, the share of people purchasing energy-efficient appliances stagnated in the same period (2008: 53%, 2012: 52%). Moreover, the number of interviewees switching off unused appliances or unnecessary lights remained at 74% and 52% respond to buy energy efficient appliances.¹² Based on this study's findings environment friendly practices are, generally, attributed to groups with higher income and higher education. People with a less environment benign lifestyle are below 29 years, singles without children and have a household income below EUR 2,000 (UBA 2014b).

Public transportation as the main means of transport is used by 25% of the German respondents. In general terms, users of public transportation can be characterised as younger than 29 years, single (with or without children), with a household-income that is below EUR 2,000, living in cities and

⁹ The German Government together with the Environmental Protection Agency publishes studies of this series every two years. For methodological information see (UBA, 2015)

¹⁰ The survey year 2012 marks an anomaly with 35% of interviewees responding that the environment is the most critical problem of our time. The authors assume that this was due to the Fukushima disaster in 2010 and the German Government's decision to phase out nuclear energy. Both of these events have drawn substantial attention on environmental challenges (UBA, 2015).

¹¹ This study report interviewed from July to August 2012 2,000 respondents (1,585 from the western part of Germany and 415 from the eastern part of Germany).

¹² Other questions seeking to assess the environmental behaviour of Germans were, for instance, "Do you keep the consumption of water and electricity low?", confirmed by 85% of respondents, or "Do you provide financial compensation payments for emissions self-induced?", which was affirmed by only 12% of interviewees.

female. The arguments for choosing public transport are: it is fast (85%), comfortable (83%) and environment friendly (82%). In contrast to this group, car-based transportation is, generally, preferred by males, between 30 and 49 years of age, couples and people living in rural areas or towns and with a household income of more than EUR 3,000. Car-users mostly argue that the mode of transport is comfortable (99%), faster (96%) and “has always been used” (81%) (UBA, 2014b)¹³.

With respect to e-mobility and car sharing, the large majority of Germans perceive both as quite positive issues for the environment. In particular, younger (<29 years) males are primarily interested in e-mobility as are highly educated Germans. Males are interested in car-sharing opportunities. At the same time, there are several concerns. For instance e-mobility “does not change traffic problems in German cities”, “is expensive” and “requires more information.” Moreover, Germans consider car sharing to be “restricted in terms of availability” and “suitable only for cities” (UBA, 2014b).

To group the German society by lifestyles and their attitude toward the environment, UBA (2014b) employ the “typology of everyday lifestyles” established by Otte (2004, 2005). In his typology, Otte classifies people along two dimensions, which are the level of endowment (low, high, medium) and the level of modernity (traditional, partly modern, modern), resulting in a 3x3 matrix.

The study concludes that traditional values (e.g. sense of duty) attributed to the “traditional worker”, “conventionalist” and “upper conservative” facilitate a “resource saving behaviour” (UBA, 2014b). In total, 19% of respondents are categorised as one of these three types. Types with a partly-modern lifestyle (“home-centred”, “upward oriented”, “upper liberals”), including 63% of respondents, promote an “openness for the environmental benign transformation of the economy as long as it is in harmony with the quality of living. Last but not least, “entertainment searchers”, “hedonists” and “reflexivists” constituting 18% of respondents show openness for innovation and are concerned about social justice. A description of the types of lifestyles and their attitude towards the environment can be found in the Annex.

¹³ Since 2002, two comprehensive studies have been published on mobility in Germany offering further insights into the topic. Please consult the latest of these publications (infas & DLR 2008) for further information.

2.2. MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

A broad range of barriers exists why energy efficiency potential cannot be successfully addressed and exploited. These can be grouped under economic, social, cultural, educational dimensions (see following tables accordingly).

For the case of buildings, the energy users' point of view is taken and listed barriers mainly deal with investment decisions hindering end users to implement energy efficiency measures (pre-investment viewpoint). Effects, which might occur after the implementation of technical measures and lower achieved energy savings post-investment are not discussed (e.g. economically motivated rebound effects, pre-rebound)¹⁴. Other barriers, which are independent of energy efficiency improvement actions and linked investments (i.e. general drivers for energy consumption) are also not covered, e.g. the increase in living space due to changed lifestyles.

In this section we focus on barriers hindering the retrofitting process of buildings. On the one hand, building retrofit in Germany is an important topic as described above (low energy quality of old buildings, political acknowledgement); on the other hand, the process of retrofitting is highly complex leading to manifold (also actor-specific) barriers, which need particular attention. However, the analysis is not limited to retrofitting, but also points out barriers applicable to the whole buildings sector.

The review for the case of Germany shows that thermal refurbishment of residential buildings is particularly addressed by the present literature and that some empirical studies have been conducted in this field to quantify the importance of barriers (mainly based on quantitative surveys). These findings have been complemented by findings for non-residential buildings (public and commercial sector).

Before presenting identified barriers in the German buildings sector, motivation factors (linked to attributes of energy efficiency improvements) and the decision processes is shortly discussed. Motivation and potential benefits of actions are found to be important factors in the decision making for energy efficiency (e.g. Schüle et al., 2011; Novikova et al., 2011). The target of a successful policy making is to communicate and strengthen benefits, while weakening the existing barriers.

2.2.1. Motivation, attributes and decision making

Concerning motivation factors for energy efficiency related investments in buildings, Friege and Chappin (2014) conclude that many economic and non-economic attributes may motivate homeowners to undertake an energy efficiency renovation, namely investment payback, increase in home's value, reduced energy bills and vulnerability against volatile prices, status and improved thermal comfort. For the case of Germany, Novikova et al. (2011) emphasises energy cost savings and thermal comfort to be key attributes influencing the thermal modernisation of buildings¹⁵. They conclude that the importance of benefits linked to attributes (like thermal comfort) increases with the progress in the decision-making process of the household. Moreover, they find that building appearance is one of the main motivations, therefore energetic improvements should be linked to building appearance (e.g. by information campaigns). Schüle et al. (2011) name the most important anticipated motivation for households to be the reduction of energy costs, though they also mention that most people in Germany are not aware of their own energy consumption and corresponding energy costs. Besides, the authors stress that motivation factors, like comfort, are anticipated to a

¹⁴ Though a case where these effects are anticipated by the building owner and therewith influence investments is conceivable. Rebounds and technology-induced pre-bounds are indirectly discussed in the context of risk perception of investments.

¹⁵ The question of status is usually not directly asked in surveys conducted as by Novikova et al. (2011). Moreover, they use a closed questions in their survey.

less extent in advance of an investment decision. Besides energy cost savings and comfort enhancement, Stieß et al. (2010) and Albrecht et al. (2010) name value maintenance and the increase of value as important for the German case. Non-economic attributes like safety or health are not named in the literature.

Since some of these attributes, like the increase in thermal comfort, will only benefit the person living in the building, these might be of lower importance to the decision making of landlords or residential property companies. This is one consequence of the often-discussed split incentives subsumed under the concept of the landlord-tenant dilemma (e.g. Ástmarsson et al., 2013; Thomas, 2006). It points to the importance to distinguish between actors. Concerning the decision for an energy efficiency investment and the importance between economic and non-economic factors, the heterogeneity of decision-makers matters. Financial incentives compared to other factors might be of relative higher importance for one group (e.g. landlords vs. homeowners). Thomas (2006) distinguishes between three actor groups on the demand site for buildings, appliances and equipment: (1) Investors into energy efficiency and at the same time users (e.g. homeowners), (2) investors into energy efficiency, who are not users at the same time (e.g. landlords, project development companies, residential property companies) and (3) users, who are not investors at the same time (e.g. tenants, buyers of buildings).

The decision-making process plays a key role and needs to be better understood when barriers are to be addressed and overcome. With this in mind, Friege et al. (forthcoming) developed an agent-based model for Germany and structured the process of decision making for the example of dwelling insulation by homeowners. They stress another aspect of the decision process besides the named motivation factors and the attitude towards energetic retrofit in the decision making process: an occasion as a first trigger of property owners to start thinking about a renovation of their property (e.g. the structural condition of the house requires maintenance). Also Achtnicht & Madlener (2012) find that building components are first replaced or renovated when they approach the end of their useful life. According to Friege et al. homeowners decide in the process of information and planning, which type of renovation they will follow, i.e. whether they will conduct an energy efficiency improvement action or will only carry out a standard renovation. According to Albrecht et al. (2010¹⁶) nearly 70% of home-owners see maintenance as a trigger for renovation. Financial constraints might delay the decision process and other situational factors (barriers) will also influence the outcome.

Table 4 Inventory of situational factors, occasions and renovation activities. Source: Friege et al. (forthcoming).

When to start thinking about renovating		Deciding about which type of renovation to undertake		
Situational factors		Occasions	Standard renovation	Combinable insulation
Structural condition of house	Financial constraints	Maintenance	Standard glazing	Insulating glazing ¹⁾
			Exterior rendering	Wall insulation
			Facade painting	
			Roof renewal	Roof insulation
		Heating system renewal and queuing standard renovations	Queuing (combinable) insulation	
Socio-demographic situation		Attic extension	Roof renewal	Roof insulation
		House purchase	Queuing standard renovations	Queuing (combinable) insulation
			Basement extension	Floor insulation

¹⁾rather than standard glazing

¹⁶ survey with home owners and refurbishers (n=1,008)

2.2.2. Identified barriers

Each of the tables below present identified main barriers for Germany by sub-group of types. However, as barriers are vast and complex, interrelations between the clusters of barriers and single barriers exist. Moreover, the list of barriers is not exhaustive.

Several authors stress the importance of non-economic barriers for energy efficiency improvement in the buildings sector (e.g. Stieß et al., 2010; Thomas, 2006; Schüle et al., 2011). With this in mind, Table 5 lists the main identified social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector for Germany¹⁷.

¹⁷ As information deficit has several differing aspects important to investment decision (e.g. lack of awareness on non-energy benefits, misperception of building condition, performance risk and linked investment uncertainty), the lack of sufficient information is addressed by several of the listed barriers, rather than being addressed by one single economic barrier (imperfect information leading to market failure).

Table 6 lists the main identified economic barriers. However, missing internalisation of external costs (e.g. on the environment and health) and energy subsidies are not addressed in this section as these are overarching barriers to buildings and transport.

Table 7 summarizes the main institutional barriers, which comprise of policy-induced barriers (legal requirements, support programmes), constructional conditions and ownership of buildings as well as market situations and failure conditions. The sequence of barriers does not follow a specific pattern. The assessment of the importance of barriers is made in

Table 8.

Table 5 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector.

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Cultural/ educational	Lack of awareness on non-energy benefits (value)	Main reasons why energy efficiency actions are not successful are information deficits and thus a general lack of awareness on the possibility to gain benefit from non-energy attributes. Awareness rising at an early stage of the decision making process might increase the pick-up rate of thermal retrofits (Novikova et al., 2011) ¹⁸ . Building appearance, comfort and energy costs savings, value maintenance and the increase of value are seen as major benefits (Schüle et al. 2011; Friedrich et al., 2007; Novikova et al., 2011).

¹⁸ 2,000 German single- and double-family homeowners were surveyed via the internet, with a similar sample from each state. The mean age of the participants was 43 years, probably biased due to the choice of using the internet. There are three groups of categories (Households that have neither implemented nor are planning a retrofit; households planning a retrofit; having implemented a retrofit).

The results were controlled for building age, geographical distribution, homeowner age, and homeowner education level in order to be able to provide recommendations to promote thermal energy efficiency.

Cross-cutting (mainly educational)	Misperception of building condition (bounded rationality)	A survey among single-house owners finds that 85% of owners see their house in a good condition and not see any action required. Though house owners often argue that their buildings have a high energetic standard, their perception often differs from political objectives and BAT standards (e.g. triple instead of double glazing of windows) (Krmer et al., 2005). Stie et al. (2010) find that approx. 60/62% ¹⁹ respondents experience their building to have a good energetic condition.
Cultural, educational	Missing credibility and trust concerning technologies	Prejudgment and doubt on energy efficiency improvement measures results in non-investment, particularly for the case of bigger investments. In a survey by Stie et al. (2010) 18/16% of respondents indicated that they are unsure whether technologies are mature and 12%/18% are afraid of building damages (e.g. mould) ²⁰ . Novikova et al. (2011) further mentions general quality concerns of retrofit measures based on survey results.
Cultural	Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit (value)	Based on findings of several studies, the Institute for Housing and the Environment (Hacke & Lohmann, 2006) conclude that energetic quality of an apartment or a house is currently seen as less important than other attributes, e.g. balcony, garage, a modern bathroom etc.
Social	Low social recognition	Social recognition of using particular technologies can play an important role in the diffusion of innovative technologies. In German, however, energy efficiency measures appear to be e.g. in a rather disadvantageous position in comparison to renewable energy technologies (e.g. PV installation). In particular, some energy experts (e.g. Jochem, 2005) insinuate that German building owners seek to proactively demonstrate an environmental friendly behaviour. Such a 'demonstration effect' may be less effective with energy efficiency building technologies, which are rather 'hidden' insight ²¹ .

¹⁹ In a representative and standardised survey 1,008 German homeowners of single- and two-family houses, including households having already applied greater retrofitting of the thermal insulation or the heating system between 2005 and 2008 (ex post) were questioned (in 2009). The named percentages refer to energetic retrofitting (1) and standard retrofitting (2).

²⁰ Mould and safety issues with respect to thermal insulation have been widely addressed by the Germany media and have lead to great uncertainty among the population.

²¹ Please note that literature on this issue is hardly available and should be analysed in future research.

Social	Age of building owners	A survey by Cischinsky et al. (2015) ²² finds the age of dwelling owners matters to investment decisions; this has been confirmed by 10% of respondents to a survey (particularly by older house owners). The argumentation is that older owners see that the financial investment risks rise with age. In Germany, over 70% of dwelling owners are older than 50 years (Cischinsky et al. 2015, p. 82). The current share of this age group in the Germany society is less than 50%. Concerning building-related investment decisions, this barrier might even become more important in Germany (ageing society). Furthermore, for elderly people it can be difficult to get a loan for higher investments (link to economic barriers).
Cross-cutting (also economically driven)	Preferences for single measures than comprehensive retrofitting	A combination of several measures is advantageous as synergy effects in energetic terms can be materialised. However, a survey conducted by Jahnke & Verhoog (2012) ²³ finds that only 12% of respondents have conducted a retrofit by applying three or more measures. In 70% of the cases only one measure was implemented. As Table 1 already indicated heating system retrofits are the most common modernisation actions (in 44% of the cases). Façades were retrofitted in 8% of cases, mostly combined with other measures. Moreover, Albert et al. (2010) finds that the comprehensiveness of retrofitting decisions is dependent on lifestyles: “convinced energy savers” and “open-minded sceptics” combine several measures more often than “unreflective maintenance oriented building owners”, “uninterested unwilling building owners” and “committed building owners” interested in residential amenity”.

²² Focus of this survey are multi-family homeowners (landlords) who rent out their flats. Cischinsky et al. define that this includes only owners who are legal persons (a company) and who own and rent out more than one flat in one or several multi-family house(s). The survey was carried out between 2010 and 2012, addressing different aspects of multi-family houses like geographical, municipal housing stock, and situation of the housing market in Germany. In total 2,938 questionnaires were used for the survey.

²³ Online-based survey with 1000 house owners. No further differentiation made

Table 6 Main economic barriers in the building sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Length of payback period	<p>Friedrich et al. (2007) find that approx. half of respondents are willing to invest in measures which redeem after 5 years. However, in case investments redeem after 12 years, the share of respondents drops to 3%. In case of high financial requirement for some energy efficiency measures, payback periods can take longer; often more than ten years.</p> <p>This barrier is particularly linked to the age of dwelling owners. With age, private owners tend to have a higher aversion to longer payback periods (Cischinsky et al., 2015; Schätzle et al., 2007).</p> <p>Length of payback period is also found to be of high importance for investments by smaller companies (BfEE, no year) and for public sector facilities (e.g. municipalities) (BAFA, 2012).</p>
High up-front costs, lack of capital and missing profitability	<p>Several improvement actions require high up-front costs. Independent of the payback period, these can constitute a highly relevant barrier.</p> <p>According to Krémer et al. (2005), 75% of dwelling owners finance retrofitting measures with equity capital. However, respondents also name missing equity capital as the most important barrier; Cischinsky et al. (2015) find similar results. Also housing associations are named to often face financial restrictions in Germany (Krémer et al., 2005).</p> <p>According to Stieß et al. (2010), nearly half of the respondents (residential) answered that equity capital for investments is missing. Existing programmes in Germany (KfW, BAFA) address this barrier by providing grants and loans. However, aversion to borrow capital still exists. 70% of households do not want to take a loan though financing is available (BfEE, no year). Also Albrecht et al. (2010) name an aversion of homeowners to borrow capital for retrofits. Service companies also lack access to capital; the problem increases with company size. Moreover, the core business is always given priority in investment decisions and 'profitability' one of the core criteria by companies and households (BfEE, no year).</p> <p>Also the public sector faces financial constraints to invest in energy efficiency (BAFA, 2012).</p>
Uncertainty on investment	<p>Performance risks (also linked to missing credibility and trust) create uncertainty for investors. Uncertainty on cost savings is found to be important for one third of companies (BfEE, no year). According to BfEE (2013), over half of companies is uninformed or is unsure on benefits of energy services in general.</p> <p>Moreover, Friedrich et al. (2007) emphasises that potential private retrofitters often over- or underestimate potential achievable energy savings and therewith cost savings.</p>
Time costs	<p>As the planning of retrofitting is highly time consuming, time (e.g. expressed in opportunity costs) can be identified to be an important economic variable besides the direct financial burden. Financial flows/engineering models do not capture these costs. According to Stieß et al. (2010), approx. half of respondents see missing time as an important constraint for energetic retrofitting. The barrier is also mentioned to be of importance in the public sector, as employees are time-constrained (BAFA, 2012). Time costs can mainly be lowered by qualified energy advice and information.</p>

Table 7 Main institutional barriers in the building sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Split incentives / owner-tenant (investor-user) dilemma	<p>This barrier has been well understood and stressed by many publications as a main market failure (e.g. Krémer et al., 2005; Schüle et al., 2011). The barrier is of particular importance for Germany as approx. 57% of dwellings are rented. The barrier is of particular importance for the case of multi-family houses and less important for single- to two-family houses; the latter are mostly inhabited by self-users. The current share of self-used single- to two-family houses is approx. 76% (GdW, 2014).</p> <p>Over 40% of tenants want their landlords to carry retrofitting costs by their own. Cost savings in e.g. heating are perceived as savings due to own behavioural changes and are not related to changes in technologies due to investment by the landlord in Germany (Bardt et al., 2008). Energetic refurbishment costs can be allocated to the rent by 11% per year.</p>
Technical/constructional issues	<p>Technical/constructional issues relate to building components and requirements for building technologies hindering the implementation of energy efficiency measures (e.g. balconies, staircases, construction of the roof). These may lead to no implementation or only a fraction of the first-planned actions (Weiß & Dunkelberg, 2010; Stieß et al., 2010). A survey by Weiß & Dunkelberg finds that 17% of the respondents see constructional issues as important factor in the decision making process of energetic retrofitting. The authors conclude that constructional issues will not have a high direct impact on retrofits, however additional financial and time expenses, as well as less energy savings might appear for single owners. Therewith a link to other listed barriers exists.</p>
Legal barriers	<p>Legal requirements impeding energy efficiency cover e.g. distance to property lines and compliance with existing preservation for historic buildings (Weiß & Dunkelberg, 2010). An extensive overview of legal barriers in Germany is presented by UBA (2013). Legal barriers exist on local, regional as well as national level.</p> <p>To address the aspect of split incentives energetic refurbishment costs may be allocated to the rent by 11% per year (see above). In practice it appears that in regions with a low rental market this would lead to rents above the average and, thus, the danger of vacancies rises (see also barrier on local/regional real estate markets).</p>
Complexity and target conflicts of support programmes	<p>In Germany several support programmes are available on local, regional and national level. Though policies are introduced to, e.g. lower financial burdens, the number and complexity of programmes make it difficult for households and companies to decide which programme/combination of programmes are most beneficial (Krémer et al., Schüle et al. 2011).</p> <p>Furthermore, the different programmes addressing buildings from different perspectives (e.g. energetic refurbishment, barrier-free refurbishment, urban development, protected buildings) are not coordinated well. Thus, the programmes support single issues neglecting the targets of neighbouring programmes. E.g. the urban development programme “Soziale Stadt” supports the design and painting of facades, but at the same time it is interdicted to use KfW funds for energetic measures on the same building.</p>
Missing supply of qualified craft business and energy consultants	<p>Qualified craft business needs to be locally available for house owners, however this is not always the case in Germany. Particularly in the case of ecological building materials or innovative measures this was found to hinder the energy efficient retrofits in Germany (Gossen & Nischan, 2014). Albrecht et al. (2010) stress the fear of homeowners of dubious providers.</p> <p>Also the qualification and certification of energy consultants is still a challenge in Germany to enhance trust in energy consultation. Standards in energy advice are missing and ‘energy advisor’ is a not protected title. Thus, finding qualified offers can be a challenge.</p>

Difficult real estate markets in some cities/regions	In Germany divergent real estate market developments exist. Prospering real estate markets exist in e.g. Munich, Berlin, while cities in the Ruhr area are rather shrinking, so that it is more difficult for landlords to pass renovation costs to tenants.
Missing strategic development	For instance, professional actors on the real estate market with a profit maximisation strategy often decide for or against energetic refurbishment regarding the future possible revenues rather than energy savings (TRAWOS, 2012).
Adverse long-term effect of municipalities' investments	Municipalities in consolidation of public budget need to present a financial plan to the federal government. Higher investments as necessity for the energetic refurbishment of public buildings usually are interdicted due to financial constraints even if they might be beneficial for the public budget in the long term.
Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings	The average renovation cycle of buildings in Germany is 30 to 60 years (Kohler, 2012). Consequently, there is a significant time lag until new and efficient technologies will materialise in the building stock.
Joint ownership of buildings	If single flats in multi family houses are owned by different parties, energetic refurbishment on outer walls, central heating systems and anything that is shared needs to be decided by all parties. This could be a very difficult process. Once a decision is made, the owners as a group of parties often have difficulties to get a loan due to liability questions. In 9% of apartments in Germany, the tenant cannot necessarily decide on retrofitting decisions himself/herself, but has to agree with other dwelling owners living in the same building (e.g. concerning retrofits of the facade) (GdW, 2014).
Missing support chains	Energy advice often is a first step on the way to an energetic refurbished house. But afterwards it often lacks further help during the process of finding the right company, application for support programmes, organisation of crafts people, etc.
Missing incentives by single policies	For instance, the German "Energieausweis" (energy performance certificate) has to be in place for renting and selling buildings. But in practice it has very little power, is rarely asked for and does not include obligations for energetic refurbishment.

Table 8 summarizes the barriers given above, grouped by barriers with high, medium and low impact in impeding energy efficiency investments in Germany's buildings sector. Though the importance of barriers can further be rated depending on specific end-user groups with particular lifestyles (e.g. energy saving motivated vs. only maintenance motivated investor; cf. Albert et al., 2010), barriers are often interrelated and partly highly subtle, the relative classification gives a first rough estimate based on literature findings as well as own estimates by the Wuppertal Institute. Particularly the evaluation of the named social, cultural, educational barriers is afflicted with high uncertainty. Concerning the assessment of barriers, following criteria were taken into account: i) the number of publications that found the same barrier to occur, ii) the importance of a barrier in terms of quantitative potential for efficiency improvements (e.g. indicated by conducted surveys between relevant actors), iii) the easiness by which the barrier can be overcome and iv) its persistency in terms of duration of its appearance.

Table 8 Assessment of barriers in the building sector.

Impact of Barriers	Barrier type	Barriers	
High	Social, cultural, educational	Misperception of building condition (bounded rationality)	
		Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit (value)	
	Economic	Length of payback period	
		High up-front costs, lack of capital and missing profitability	
	Institutional	Split incentives / owner-tenant (investor-user) dilemma	
		Legal barriers	
		Missing support chains	
	Medium	Social, cultural, educational	Lack of awareness on non-energy benefits (value)
			Preferences for single measures than comprehensive retrofitting
Low social recognition of energy efficiency			
Economic		Time costs	
		Uncertainty on investment	
Institutional		Missing strategic development	
		Missing supply of qualified craft business and energy consultants	
		Missing incentives by single policies	
		Complexity and target conflicts of support programmes	
		Adverse long-term effect of municipalities' investments	
Low		Social, cultural, educational	Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings
	Age of private investors		
	Institutional	Missing credibility and trust concerning technologies	
		Technical/constructional issues	
		Difficult real estate markets in some cities/regions (depending on the individual situation)	
		Joint ownership of buildings	

2.3. Mapping barriers in the transport sector

As outlined in section 1.2 energy efficiency in transport can be realised on vehicle level (vehicle efficiency), can target modal choice (travel efficiency) and can address transport demand (system efficiency). The barriers for energy efficiency improvements differ significantly between these three efficiency aspects. Especially, mode shift and reduction of transport demand require behaviour changes or alternative organisational or planning (e.g. urban planning) approaches. These improvements are usually more difficult to achieve than sole technical vehicle improvement, which are often associated with fuel savings and thus beneficial to the vehicle operator. Barriers can be linked to several key factors that impede a more energy-efficient transport system in Germany:

1. Limited attractiveness / availability of public transport
2. Limited attractiveness of non-motorized modes
3. Dominance of private motorized transport
4. Preference of conventionally fuelled vehicles
5. Economic interest related to automobile industry and logistics

Table 9,

Table 10 and Table 11 list the most important barriers for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Germany without any claim to be exhaustive. The listed barriers are often closely related. The actual transport behaviour and consequently the energy efficiency of the transport system depends on the one hand on aspects “pulling” people to use energy efficient modes or vehicles and on the other hand on factors “pushing” people out of inefficient modes/vehicles – or the absence or limited effectiveness of these push and pull factors.

It should be noted, that the relevance of the listed barriers can vary across different social groups and be influenced by spatial characteristic (e.g. rural vs. urban regions).

Table 9 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector.

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Suburbanisation trends	Travel distances are getting longer and public transport, walking and cycling becomes more and more unattractive. Daily travel distances in Germany increase with decreasing density. Residents in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants travel on average 36 km per day, whereas in rural areas (below 150 inhabitants per km ²) daily travel distances amount to 42 km per day (infas and DLR, 2010).
Cultural	Cars as status symbol	A car as status symbol has a long tradition in Germany and this perception is supported by mass media (SRU 2005). It is not only about the ownership of a car, but there is also a tendency in Germany for larger cars and higher engine power. In 2009, the German fleet had the third highest average fuel intensity of diesel cars among the EU15 countries, and ranked also above the average terms of gasoline fuel intensity (Ajanovic 2013).

Social	Vulnerability of pedestrians	Most pedestrians in Germany perceive roads as safe. In a study by Papadimitriou et al. (2012) 90 % of the pedestrians think roads are safe or very safe for pedestrians. However, less than 50 % are satisfied with the speed of traffic and the volume of traffic in Germany.
Cultural	Tradition of car ownership and use	Owing and travelling by car is perceived a value itself, due to status, privacy and safety. Car ownership is still increasing. In 2000, 475 passenger cars were registered by 1000 inhabitants, while in 2010 this indicator increased to 517 cars per 1000 inhabitants (UBA 2012). Also the share of driving licence holders increases. In 2008, 88 % of the people above 18 had a driving licence, compared to 84 % in 2002. However, among younger people (age 18 to 29) there is a slight decrease in driving licence ownership (infas and DLR, 2010). There are strong regional (and demographic) differences in the perception of cars. In some larger cities (usually university cities) car ownership is not a status symbol especially among younger generations, while in other cities and rural areas cars are still an important status symbol. About 30% of all households in Germany hold more than one car (infas and DLR 2010). Automobility has a long tradition in Germany. After the second world war, mass motorization was associated with employment generation, wealth and lifestyle changes. The automobile industry still plays an important role for the national economy (makes up 3% of the national GDP).
Cultural	Opposition against (tighter) speed limits (e.g. on highways)	Associations of the German automobile industry as well as driver associations lobby against a general speed limit on German highways. German car manufacturers especially produce vehicles with high engine power and high maximum speeds. In contrast, about half of the German population favour a general speed limit on highways. A speed limit of 120 km/h would lead to emission reductions of 9 % (UBA 1999).

Cultural	Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternative fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles)	Paternoga et al. (2013) found that 25% of the survey participants would be willing to accept a higher purchasing price for an EV. However, among those willing to pay a surcharge, only few were willing to cover extra purchasing costs above EUR 3,000 According to a study conducted by Bozem et al. (2013), costs are important criteria in vehicle purchasing decisions. If cost of alternatively fuelled vehicles were comparable to those of diesel and gasoline vehicles, 80% of respondents would consider switching to a vehicle running on alternative fuels. Free parking for electric vehicles or inner city access restriction for diesel or gasoline vehicles can be a motivation for people to choose an EV. In the survey, about 36% would consider to by an EV, if parking was free for EVs and about 24% would consider an EV if access restrictions were implemented.
Cultural	Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for an energy-efficient vehicles	In a survey by BMU and UBA (2015), 87% of the respondents were of the opinion that electric vehicles are too expensive. According to Aral (2011) only 57% of potential vehicle buyers would accept surcharges of 1000 Euro (or more), but 91% would accept 500 Euro additional costs for a more energy efficient vehicle.
Cultural	High performance expectations for electric vehicles	The majority of new car buyers do not consider buying an electric vehicle. Only 28% of the participants of a survey (Aral 2011) are considering buying an EV. Of those people who are willing to buy an EV only 20% are satisfied with a driving range below 300 km. According to Peters and Hoffmann (2011), higher purchasing prices are perceived as main disadvantage of electric vehicles. Limited driving range, lack of infrastructure and charging time were mentioned as additional important barriers in decreasing order of magnitude.
Educational	Limited awareness of actual driving behaviour and range requirements	Many private and commercial vehicle owners are of the opinion that an electric vehicle would not meet their range requirements in their daily driving behaviour. However, fleet analysis reveals that the daily driving range of most vehicles is blow the range limitations of available electric vehicles (infas and DLR, 2010; Hacker et al. 2011).
Cross-cutting	(Perceived) lack of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles	More than 60% of vehicle users in Germany have a garage or a fixt parking spot, where charging infrastructure could be easily installed (Peters and Wietschel, 2012). Still potential buyers see the lack of public charging infrastructure as barrier to use an electric vehicle.

Cultural	Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy-efficiency in vehicle purchasing decisions	In 2011, only 47% of potential vehicle buyers rate the vehicle's CO ₂ -emission level as important or very important and there is a tendency towards less importance. In 2009, this criterion was important or very important for 59% (Aral, 2011).
Educational	Lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emission of own vehicles	According to Aral (2011), only 8% know the average CO ₂ emission level of their own car. The awareness of own vehicle emissions is decreasing as well.
Cultural	Car-oriented urban planning	Reconstruction of cities after world war two was focused on private cars in many Germany cities. Even though, planning paradigms are changing, still many cities have an auto-oriented structure and transport system. Klinger et al. (2013) identified 10 out of 44 investigated cities above 100,000 inhabitants as auto-oriented cities.
Educational	Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers	Consumers lack awareness of the energy costs of their purchases and respective deliveries (e.g. due to online shopping) (Böhler-Baedeker et al. 2013).
Educational	Limited awareness about actual travel costs of different modes	Car owners do not take into account the full costs of car travel. Usually, fuel costs and travel time are included in the decision making, while reduced value, maintenance cost, wear and tear are not included in the decision making process. Consequently, car travel is often favoured compared to public transport.
Cross-cutting	Criteria for mode choice favour car use	According to VCD (2009) 75% of the survey participants stated that flexibility is an important decision criterion for their mode choice. 50% see travel time and punctuality as additional important decision criterion.

Table 10 Main economic barriers in the transport sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport	For urban public transport there is a rising discrepancy between growing passenger numbers and investments in public transport. In several regions there is need for expansion of public transport supply, which would require public investments. However, as many German municipalities have a tight budget and the continuation of federal funding is currently under revision, expansion of public transport remains undone (UBA 2014). MBWSV (2013) comes to the conclusion that for the state of North-Rhine Westphalia, a 50 to 100 % increase in public transport capacity is needed.
Tax policies that negatively affect road transport energy efficiency	Some tax policies in place in Germany are suggested to have potentially counterproductive effects on road transport energy efficiency. The option to deduct commuter travel from income tax has this potential. Until 2001 only travel by car was eligible for deduction from income tax, which was considered as boosting urban sprawl as it fiscally incentivises long distances between home and work (UBA 2010). There is a fixed rate per kilometre travelled that can be deducted. While this tax deduction option is now applicable to all modes of travel it is still considered to provide unjust benefits car based commuter travel. This is for instance because the maximum limit of deductible costs can be increased if the commuter uses a private car (UBA 2010). Tax incentives for house ownership and building are also considered to contribute to urban sprawl and incentivise commuting by car (Hirte and Tscharaktschiew, 2012).
Priorization of megaprojects, at the expense of more cost-effective sustainable/energy-efficient transport options	Even where financial resources are available, there are cases where the allocation/prioritization of funding jeopardizes the development of sustainable transport. Financing institutions, including national governments, have a tendency to favour mega-projects, which are politically more attractive, at the expense of often more effective small-scale projects including those that target non-motorized transport (see Flyvbjerg et al, 2003). In addition, cost-intensive new development lead draw resources needed for the maintenance of existing infrastructures (UBA, 2014).
Limited focus on energy efficiency and co-benefits in the public decision making process	The way in which the costs and benefits of transport projects are appraised (with a predominant focus on short-term vehicle operating cost savings and time cost savings) also bias financing towards options, which favour motorized private transport (see ITDP, 2010).
Lacking cost competitiveness of electric vehicles	Currently, electric vehicles are not cost competitive from a TCO perspective for most vehicle owners. The international comparison conducted by ICCT (2014) reveal that, under the current fuel prices and tax structures TCOs are much higher for a BEV than a conventional vehicle in Germany. Also TCOs for PHEVs are slightly higher than for conventional vehicles. As Witschel et al. (2012) revealed, BEV can be cost competitive for vehicles with high annual millage (above 20,000 km) which are used for many, but short distances. Private cars in Germany have an average annual mileage of 12,500 km (Hacker et al. 2011).
Limited rail infrastructure capacity	The shift of freight transport from road to rail is limited by bottlenecks resulting from highly utilise routes, which have reached their capacity limit. Additional infrastructure and rail connections for important areas that lack rail infrastructure are needed (Böhler-Baedeker et al. 2013).

High economic importance of the automobile industry in Germany	The automobile industry still plays an important role for the national economy (makes up 3% of the national GDP). German manufactures have a strong market share in upper and middle class vehicles. Among the top-selling passenger car manufactures in Europe, German brands have the highest vehicle weight and also the CO ₂ emission level exceeds the European average (ICCT, 2015).
Tax policies that favour inefficient modes	VAT is not imposed on international flights, whereas cross-boarder rail services are subject to VAT. In addition, rail operators have to pay fees for the use of tracks and stations, while aviation benefits from subsidised take-off and landing fees (UBA, 2014).
Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles	While investments in energy-efficient vehicles result in considerable economy-wide benefits over the lifetime of a vehicle, they may not create sufficient payback rates for individuals responsible for vehicle purchasing decisions. Most car buyer do not account for costs-savings from efficiency beyond 2 to 3 years (Lah, 2015).

Table 11 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Fragmentation of public transport operators	Responsibility for public transport is divided into different levels: municipal, regional and national. As a consequence there are many different tariff structures, scattered information and missing integration of schedules for the user. This is leading to in-transparency and unattractiveness for the user. The introduction of transport associations (Verkehrsverbünde) combined several public authorities (e.g. municipalities) to integrate tariff system, information and schedules, but still tariff structures are not perceived as user friendly especially for visitors and when travelling across different associations. In addition, municipalities have sovereignty of public transport planning impeding the interoperability of the systems due to differences in light-rail infrastructure and stations. (Knieps, 2006; Franz, 2014).
Parallel extension of road networks	Instead of required clear prioritization of energy-efficient modes, often there is a parallel investment in different modes – reducing the incentive for modal shift. Even though, the government has the objective to shift transport from road to rail and waterway transport, road infrastructure is continuously extended. Between 2005 and 2011, 500 kilometres of additional highway infrastructure was added, while at the same time the total rail track length was reduced by about 550 km (BMW, 2015).
Lack of long-term vision regarding the improvements of and investments in transport infrastructure	There is a lack of an overall strategic concept that links infrastructural investments with national transport policy objectives such as shift from road to rail (UBA 2014).
Inconsistency in national, regional and local priorities	All three levels of administration (i.e. federal government, federal states and municipalities) hold responsibilities for different transport infrastructures and develop their own transport concepts, which impede strategic transport planning.

Complex funding structures in urban public transport	Funding for urban public transport comes from various sources including national and state government as well as municipal budgets. Funding is differentiated in support for infrastructure and vehicles and several other aspects. In addition, some funding instruments expire in the coming years and a decision on respective successor sources is still lacking. Some existing funding instruments inhibit the orientation towards the costumers' needs and expectations. This leads to inadequate supply of urban public transport and lack of acceptance. (Bormann et al. 2010).
Segmented planning of transport infrastructure	Responsibilities for transport infrastructure as well as financing responsibility is segmented between different stakeholders. This inhibits an integrated strategic transport planning across different modes and identification of bottlenecks (UBA, 2014). There is a lack of an overall strategic concept that links infrastructural investments with national transport policy objectives such as shift from road to rail. Often, financing of infrastructure maintenance is not secured.
Limited cooperation in city logistics	Organisational efficiency improvements in urban deliveries are impeded by competitive interests of different logistic companies.
Investment lock-in of vehicle owners	The average age of passenger cars in Germany is about nine years (KBA 2015). Consequently, there is a significant time lag till new and efficient technologies have fully penetrated the vehicle fleet.

In Table 12 the barriers outlined above are ranked according to their importance in impeding energy efficiency in the German transport sector. The ranking is based on expert opinion by transport professionals at the Wuppertal Institute. It should be noted that there is a strong interrelation between several barriers and the energy efficiency advancements are usually impeded by a combination of various barriers. The relative classification can only provide a first rough estimate and the relevance of a specific barrier can vary geographically and by socio-economic characteristic of a specific user group. The ranking takes into account i) the importance of the barrier in terms of estimated quantitative potential for efficiency improvements, ii) the easiness with which the barrier can be overcome and iii) its persistency in terms of duration of its appearance.

Table 12 Assessment of barriers in the transport sector.

Impact of Barriers	Type	Barriers
High	Social, cultural, educational	Tradition of car ownership and use
		Car-oriented urban planning
	Economic	Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport
		Tax policies that negatively affect road transport energy efficiency
		Lacking cost competitiveness of electric vehicles
	Institutional	Lack of long-term vision in regard to improvements of and investments in transport infrastructure
		Fragmentation of public transport operators
		Parallel extension of road networks
		Complex funding structures in urban public transport
	Medium	Social, cultural, educational
Suburbanisation trends		
Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternative fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles)		
Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for an energy-efficient vehicles		
Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy-efficiency in vehicle purchasing decisions and lack of awareness		
Opposition against (tighter) speed limits (e.g. on highways)		
(Perceived) lack of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles		
Economic		Limited awareness about actual travel costs of different modes
		Prioritization of megaprojects, at the expense of more cost-effective sustainable/energy-efficient transport options
		Limited focus on energy efficiency and co-benefits in the public decision making process
		Limited rail infrastructure capacity
		Tax policies that favour inefficient modes
		High economic importance of the automobile industry in Germany
Institutional		Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles
		Inconsistency in national, regional and local priorities
		Segmented planning of transport infrastructure
Low		Social, cultural, educational
	High performance expectations for electric vehicles	
	Limited awareness of actual driving behaviour and range requirements	
	Lack of awareness of fuel consumption and emissions of own vehicles	
	Vulnerability of pedestrians	
	Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers	
Institutional	Limited cooperation in city logistics	

3. BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1. Building Sector

As mentioned above, Germany's buildings sector has a large potential for improvement and several instruments have already been implemented to accelerate the uptake of energy efficiency. Past policy efforts have also matured, e.g. specific space heat requirements in residential buildings have successfully been lowered. Novikova et al. (2011) finds that households that receive support by KfW funds are more likely to implement comprehensive thermal retrofits and that the scope of the planned improvement actions stays the same through the retrofit planning process. Energy audits by the German consumer association and on site advice provided by BAFA are found to successfully stimulate investment decisions.

However, barriers are still existent and Germany needs to further refine existing instruments in the respective policy package, also to facilitate the development of energy service market. In this respect the NAPE (BMWI 2014c) is the main instrument to further support the uptake of energy efficiency. Table 13 summarizes identified barriers in the buildings sector and how current national policy instruments address them. Some barriers are comprehensively addressed at current state. Other barriers have not been explicitly addressed at all, in this case further actions will be needed.

One difficulty is that some of the identified barriers (e.g. missing credibility and trust concerning technologies) can only be indirectly addressed by policy – also in the future. Other factors like social interaction might be of more importance in this case (cf. Friege et al., forthcoming).

Table 13 Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector.

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Level (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments ²⁴
Social Cultural Educational	Lack of awareness on non-energy benefits	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Promotion of energy management systems
	Misperception of building condition	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Seal of quality efficiency house • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • Energy performance certificate
	Missing credibility and trust concerning technologies	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Energy performance certificate • Seal of quality efficiency

²⁴ based on D 1.2., national policies. Local and regional policies could not be reflected as information is not sufficient at current state.

			<p>House</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs
	Disadvantage of energetic quality to other attributes of a housing unit	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring
	Low social recognition	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Energy performance certificate • Seal of quality efficiency house
	Age of building owners	Needs to be addressed by all levels	
Economic	Length of payback period	Mainly addressed by national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring • KfW energy-efficient construction • KfW energy efficient refurbishment • Energy tax • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • BAFA cross-cutting technologies
	High up-front costs and lack of capital	Mainly addressed by national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW energy-efficient construction • KfW energy efficient refurbishment • Energy tax • Market incentive programme to promote the use of renewable energies in the heating market • BAFA cross-cutting technologies
	Uncertainty on investment	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seal of quality efficiency House • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for

			<p>SMEs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of energy management systems • Energy performance certificate • BAFA cross cutting technologies • KfW energy efficient construction • KfW energy efficient refurbishment
	Time costs	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Energy performance certificate • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring
	Split incentives / owner-tenant (investor-user) dilemma	Needs to be addressed by all levels, mainly national law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving ordinance • Inspections of boilers and heating/cooling installations • Heating cost regulation • Seal of quality efficiency House • Energy Performance Certificate
Institutional	Technical/constructional issues	All levels, rather local/regional level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection of boilers and heating/cooling installations • On-side energy consultation • Energy checks • Energy Performance Certificates • Heating cost regulation • Energy consultation for SMEs • KfW construction monitoring • BAFA cross-cutting technologies • Competence centre for public buildings • Low energy buildings project and efficiency house plus • Research initiative Zukunft Bau and Research for energy-optimised construction • 6th energy research programme
	Legal barriers	Existent on all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Saving Ordinance • Heating Cost Regulation

	Complexity and target conflicts of support programmes	Addresses all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is partly targeted by national programmes like Climate Action Plan 2020
	Missing supply of qualified craft business and energy consultants	Addresses all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants
	Difficult real estate markets in some cities/regions	Existent on local/regional level	/
	Adverse long-term effect of municipalities' investments	Local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding programmes for municipalities
	Joint ownership of buildings	Needs to be addressed by all levels	/
	Missing support chains	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW construction monitoring • Energy checks • On-side energy consultation • Promotion of energy management systems
	Missing incentives by single policies	Mostly national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong integration of the energy saving ordinance, the energy performance certificate, the seal of Quality Efficiency House, the on-side energy consultations and the KfW programmes
	Investment lock-in in private, commercial and public buildings	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirectly addressed by all instruments

3.2. Transport Sector

The shift to the most efficient modes of transport and further improvements in the performance of freight as well as increased use of efficient drive technologies offer considerable potential for reducing energy consumption in the transport sector. Regarding vehicle efficiency and alternative drive train technology, developments at EU level play a major role for domestic activities. The European CO₂-fleet emission limit for passenger cars and light duty vehicles is an important driver for the development and deployment of energy-efficient vehicles. Regarding alternative fuels and drive trains the EU directive “Clean Power for Transport” and the “Fuel quality directive” have an important influence on domestic activities. In addition, investments in R&D and demonstration of electric vehicles are also driven by the objective to strengthen the domestic automobile industry and to achieve an international leading position as supplier of electric vehicles. As road transport is heavily relying on oil, diversification of the fuel mix to become less dependent on import can be seen as additional driving factor.

Activities that address a shift to more efficient modes are not only motivated by the objective to reduce CO₂ emissions and fossil fuel consumption, but also by non-energy related factors. Congestion relief in inner cities as well as on interregional routs and freight corridors is an additional driver for shifting trips to more efficient modes. Parking pressure and the limited availability of urban space can be addressed by modal shift in inner cities as well. Most measures that increase energy efficiency in transport have the potential to reduce externalities associated with motorized transport such as air pollution affecting human health, the built environment and ecosystem or noise pollution.

According to VCD (2009), on an individual level, transport mode choice is mainly influenced by flexibility (75%), travel time (52%), punctuality (51%), comfort (47%), availability (44%) and costs (43%). Environmental protection and GHG emission mitigation are only for 21% an important decision criterion. Similarly, environmental factors are only of minor importance in vehicle purchasing decisions. According to Aral (2011) only 19% name environmental performance as criterion. Value for money is named by 61% as important criterion in vehicle purchasing decisions.

Table 14 Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector.

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Level (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Cars as status symbol	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National funding for the campaign “head on: engine off” targeting short distance travel Local campaigns (e.g. “cycling capital” Munich)
	Tradition of car ownership and use	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentives for climate-friendly mobility in the federal administration aimed at the increased use of public transport Mobility management programmes
	Limited willingness to accept high costs for alternative fuelled vehicles (e.g. electric vehicles)	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax benefits for natural and liquid gas; Tax exemption for electric vehicles,

	Limited willingness to accept higher purchasing prices for an energy-efficient vehicles	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Federal funding programme for energy efficient commercial vehicles to be launched in 2016 (BMW 2014c)
	High performance expectations for electric vehicles	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D investments in EV technology
	Limited awareness of actual driving behaviour and range requirements	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National and state government funding programmes on electric vehicle demonstrations,
	(Perceived) lack of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National and state government funding programmes on electric vehicle demonstrations, Development of a national strategy for charging infrastructure bases on the EU-directive "Clean Power for Transport"
	Limited relevance of environmental performance and energy-efficiency in vehicle purchasing decisions and lack of awareness	Needs to be addressed by all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passenger car labelling; CO2-related motor vehicle tax; "me and my car" campaign; "new driving" campaign
	Car-oriented urban planning	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National cycling plan; Federal funding for cycling lanes along federal roads; National funding programme for cycling infrastructure and intermodal hubs (NKI)
	Limited awareness of the energy consumption of goods deliveries among private consumers	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heavy goods vehicle toll charges
Economic	Lack of financial resources for high-quality public transport	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal transport financing act and regionalisation act: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities
	Lacking cost competitiveness of electric vehicles	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D funding for electric vehicles,
	Limited rail infrastructure capacity	National and regional level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2015: stronger emphasis on railways and waterways

			(freight) concerning budget
	Payback period of fuel efficient vehicles	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂-related motor vehicle tax
Institutional	Fragmentation of public transport operators	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of different transport association and introduction of a state wide tariff e.g. by the state of North Rhine-Westphalia
	Parallel extension of road networks	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2015: stronger emphasis on railways and waterways (freight) concerning budget
	Investment lock-in of vehicle owners	Needs to be addressed by all level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirectly addressed by all instruments

4. KEY FINDINGS

Concerning *buildings*, the household sector makes over 60% of building-related final energy consumption, followed by the commercial buildings with approx. 29% and industrial buildings with 10%. Thermal heating has the highest share in all sectors. The high importance in energy consumption is also reflected by the German energy policy, particularly thermal refurbishment has a priority in the set national building targets. Most of the found literature on barriers in the buildings sector deal with refurbishment of residential buildings. Key findings for the German buildings sector concerning identified barriers are:

- Several barriers in the building sector exist. These are highly complex and interrelations between the sub-groups exist (e.g. age of building owners as a social barrier also influences investment decisions)
- When barriers are discussed, it is important to distinguish between the group of actors (e.g. landlords might respond differently to motivation factors than homeowners)
- Barriers, which dwelling owners are aware of, need to be distinguished from those owners are not aware of (e.g. misperception of the energetic building condition vs. technical/constructional issues). A distinction also needs to be made for benefits of refurbishments.
- The review has shown that according to barriers specific target groups (e.g. older dwelling owners, energy saving motivated owners) play an important role and an differentiation needs to be made when barriers are to be overcome
- The identified manifold economic barriers show that financial support is still necessary to accelerate the uptake of energy efficiency improvement, however information tools on all levels are also necessary. Particularly to address 'soft' or non-economic barriers like lack of awareness and risk perception and thus incentivise end-users to change their behaviour.

One or more policy instruments already address several of the identified barriers towards energy-efficient buildings. Other barriers have not been explicitly addressed by policies yet.

Energy-efficient *transportation* can be addressed on three different levels. Potentials for energy efficiency are available for single vehicles (vehicle efficiency), individual trips (travel efficiency - based on the modal choice) and for the whole transport system (system efficiency – based on the generation of transport demand). Road based transport is responsible for 82% of the energy consumption in the German transport system. Consequently, the largest potential for energy efficiency improvements can be seen in increasing the efficiency of road vehicles and in shifting passenger and freight transport to more efficient modes. However, several barrier impede the full utilization of the energy efficiency potential in the German transport sector:

- Passenger transport is heavily relying on passenger cars. Private cars have a long tradition as status symbol in Germany and are often perceived as most flexible and convenient form of travelling. Decision making process on different governmental levels have led to a car-oriented infrastructure in many regions and a paradigm shift towards prioritization of energy-efficient modes in planning and investment decision is still at the beginning. Consequently, the framework conditions (e.g. infrastructure provision, taxation) for passenger mobility are very attractive for individual motorized transport, while non-motorized transport and public transport is perceived as less attractive.
- The technological potential of vehicle efficiency is not fully tackled due to higher purchasing prices for energy-efficient vehicles or alternative drivetrains. Most consumers are not willing to accept surcharges. Furthermore, they usually do not reflect the vehicle's energy efficiency in their purchasing decision.

One or more policy instruments already address several of the identified barriers towards energy-efficient transport, but a clear prioritization of energy efficient modes and vehicles through targeted investment decisions and taxation is still missing. Furthermore, some policy instrument target important lever for more energy efficiency, but have only a limited effect due to their inherent design (e.g. limited effect of CO₂ based vehicle taxation).

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ANNEX

Types of lifestyles and their attitude towards the environment

Type of lifestyles, % of respondents and attributes	Attitudes towards the environment
Traditional worker (10%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low level of endowment - low level of education - found in every age-group, but more often in the age group >65 - high appreciation of social security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - measures undertaken by the Government for environmental protection are perceived as sufficient - usually uses the car; also walks more often than other types; public transport is uncomfortable; car sharing and e-mobility are irrelevant for personnel situation - measures taken by themselves to live a more sustainable lifestyle are insignificant
Conventionalist (7%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - medium level of endowment - higher education - security is a core value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - concerned regarding climate change; inconclusive with respect to the commitment of the Government in that respect - cars and bikes are frequently used, while public transport is uncomfortable; interested in car-sharing and environment friendly (traffic) solutions - live in to the same extend in owned or rented homes; the choice of a home should be more in line with environmental criteria
Upper conservative (2%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high level of endowment - found rather in higher age group (50 - 65) - type is coined by conservatism and social distinction - exclusive lifestyle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no clear position regarding environmental protection through the government - use all modes of transportation - switching off unused appliances is found to be important - the choice of a home should be more in line with environmental criteria
Home-centred (27%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low level of endowment - more often found in age group <29 - low level of education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - environmental problems are very concerning but this does not translate into more demands towards the government - car is preferred, while public transportation is uncomfortable - within their own household, sustainability is rather irrelevant
Upward oriented (26%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - medium level of endowment - age group majorly between 30 and 49 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial and economic policies are core; but they also demand more commitment by the Government regarding social protection - Car is used more rarely and more often use public transport within their own household, sustainability is relevant - owning a house is a central life goal
Upper liberals (10%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high level of endowment - age group between 50 and 65 predominates - highly educated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - environmental protection is key; environmental protection is also important to achieve other policy goals - car-based transportation dominates; car-sharing is irrelevant for own situation - carry out sustainable measures in own household
Entertainment searchers (7%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low level of endowment - usually younger than 29 years - status is important for lifestyle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - security is key; environmental issues are not a matter of concern - use all modes of transportation, but hardly bikes - environment friendly behaviour is rather a restriction for finding the preferred lifestyle

<p>Hedonists (7%)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - medium level of endowment - found in every education, income and age group - lifestyle focus on enjoyment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - while social securitization is key, the type is ambivalent with respect to environmental and climate protection - use all modes of transportation, but hardly bikes; high interest in e-mobility - live rather in rented and smaller homes; large living space is perceived as environmentally harmful - own practices to reduce the environmental footprint are negligible; but they demand action from the Government in this field
<p>Reflexivists (4%)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high level of endowment - more likely found in the age group 30-65 - academic background - their attitude towards life has a global orientation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the position of environmental issues is inconclusive; but most think that environmental protection is key to achieve social justice - use all modes of transportation - household practices are in line with sustainability criteria - they generally live in large homes, which they own

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D2.1

D.2.1 WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORTS

JULY 2015

Partner: *Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens*

NATIONAL REPORT

HELLAS, JULY 2015

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

ATCW	Analytical Tariffication of Constructural Works
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
CRES	Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
DMP	Direct Marketing Program
EC	European Commission
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEW	Energy Efficiency Watch
EIB	European Investment Bank
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCO	Energy Services COmpany
EU	European Union
JESSICA	Joint European Support for Sustainable Investment in City Areas
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
LEAP	Long Range Alternatives Planning system
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MEECC	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
MEIST	Ministry of Economy, Infrastrucutre, Shipping and Tourism
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
PKM	Passenger - Kilometer
PPP	Public – Private – Partnership
R&D	Research and Development
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ROI	Return Of Investment
RUE	Rational Use of Energy
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
YPEKA	(Greek interpretation) Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In 2012, final energy consumption in Greece was 17,129 Mtoe (YPEKA, 2014). The two sectors with the highest energy consumption were the building sector with 45% (residential and tertiary) and the transport sector with 37% (YPEKA, 2014).

The national energy efficiency policy for the building and the transport sectors includes voluntary approaches, regulatory, dissemination-awareness and economic policy instruments. Most of them derive from EU Directives and Regulations. Moreover, financial initiatives and programmes particularly for the building sector, such as the Green Fund, are in place. Consequently, practices and interventions (such as bioclimatic design), energy efficiency technologies and energy management systems are promoted in the Greek building sector. Concerning the transport sector, financial incentives are provided for the use of alternative technology vehicles (natural gas, hybrid and electric vehicles), as well as vehicles with improved Euro 6 engine specifications.

User behavior is influenced by economic, social and psychological factors that influence both the buying of equipment and the use of energy. Energy use is determined by information/awareness and energy costs, plus social, educational and cultural factors (WBCSD, 2008). Consequently, there are barriers for the implementation of energy efficiency policy instruments and technologies that are related to the aforementioned factors. Mapping and analysis of such barriers for Greece led to the following key findings.

The barriers for both sectors are observed on two different levels: national and local/regional. In the local/regional, the barriers were mostly linked with the initiative of Covenant of Mayors and the implementation of SEAPs (buildings, mobility) and concerned the local authorities.

Starting from the cross-cutting barriers – common barriers that were observed in both sectors – the most prominent ones are the financial crisis (economic barrier) and the ineffective urban, land and transportation planning (institutional barrier).

Particularly, for the building sector, the Greek society has not yet strongly endorsed energy conservation and sustainability (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Also, the implementation network is considered inadequate, mainly due to the limited training of the technical staff, the inadequate procedures for monitoring and evaluation and the administrative burden. This was observed both in the national level, and in the municipality level for the development and implementation of SEAPs. In order to overcome these barriers, there is an on-going attempt with relevant initiatives, programmes, and dissemination actions.

Concerning the transport sector, most of the social-educational-cultural barriers are related with the perception that people have of owning and driving a vehicle. Particularly,

1. the eco-driving is hindered by the old habits (driving inefficiently),
2. the promotion of public transport is hindered by the citizens' preference of private cars due to convenience and their perception that owning and driving a private car shows the status symbol and good lifestyle,
3. the promotion of e-vehicles' use is hindered by the negative public perception that this technology is not robust yet, as well as the lack of financial support schemes.

This report is based on literature review with the use of official national and European reports and studies, results of national and European funded projects and published scientific papers.

INTRODUCTION

The present report, as part of the Deliverable D.2.1 'Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in building and transport', aims to identify the different typologies of barriers (social, economic, cultural and educational, institutional) that impede the uptake of energy efficiency, in Hellenic buildings and transport sectors.

Country overview

Hellas has a total area of 131.957 km², occupying the southernmost extension of the Balkan Peninsula, with the mainland covering the 80% of the land area and the 20% the islands, while its population consists of 10.815.197 inhabitants¹.

It has a typical Mediterranean climate, with mild and rainy winters, warm and dry summers, while during most of the year, there are extended periods of sunshine.

In 2012, final energy consumption in Greece was 17,129 Mtoe (YPEKA, 2014). The two sectors with the highest energy consumption were the building sector with 45% (residential and tertiary) and the transport sector with 37% (YPEKA, 2014).

Buildings

The percentage of electricity consumed by the buildings sector is accordingly high; 65% in total, corresponding to 33,894GWh (YPEKA, 2014).

The allocation of the average annual total energy consumed in the household sector by the fuel used (Table 1) and in the type of use (Figure 1) is the following:

Table 1: Percentage distribution of total household energy consumption by type of fuel used.

Fuel	Percentage
Heating Oil	44,1
Gas	5,4
District heating	0,5
kerosene	0,3
Core	0,3
LPG	1,8
firewood	17,4
Pellets (wood pellets)	0,5
Thermal energy (thermal solar systems)	2,9
Electricity	26,8

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2014

¹Hellenic Statistical Authority. 20 March 2014. Retrieved 16 February 2015.

Energy consumption end use in buildings	Percentage
Space heating	63,7
Production of Domestic Hot Water (DHW)	5,7
Cooking	17,3
Cooling Services	1,3
Lighting	1,7
Devices (electrical / electronic)	10,2

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of total household energy consumption by type of end-use

Source: Hellenic Statistic Authority, 2014

Transport

Since the 1980s, the Road and Rail network of Greece has been significantly modernized, including important works such as the A2 (Egnatia Odos), connecting the North-Westerns Hellas with the Northern and North-Eastern Hellas and the Rio – Antirio bridge, connecting Peloponnese to Central Hellas. At the aviation sector, according to the statistics for the Athens International Airport flights, the number of flights showed a robust rise of 17,7%² (in total for December 2014), mainly attributed to the significant increase in the capacity offered by the airlines during the current winter flight schedule, while both domestic and international flights achieved similar levels of growth, at the level of +17,3% and +17,9%, respectively. Overall for 2014, the number of flights amounted to 154,5 thousands, surpassing the corresponding 2013 levels by 10%³, while at the sea lines, with nearly 3.000 islands, Hellas has a broad network of navigation.

² https://www.aia.gr/userfiles/675393df-ab1a-4b77-826c-f3096a3d7f12/Flights_EN_2014_Final.pdf

³ https://www.aia.gr/userfiles/675393df-ab1a-4b77-826c-f3096a3d7f12/Flights_EN_2014_Final.pdf

Figure 1: Land Transport comparison

Source: Hellenic Statistic Authority, 2014

Concerning navigation, there are about 1.000 shipping companies with their headquarters located at Piraeus that support administratively a 20% share of the international shipping (SEB, 2012).

Concerning aviation, according to Eurostat data in 2010, 315.815 flights, 32.623.657 passengers and 88.715 tons of merchandise and mail were recorded (SEB, 2012).

1. CONTEXT

1.1 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

The national policy instruments that are currently implemented for supporting energy efficiency in Greece are presented synoptically in Table 1. More details are available at the respective deliverables of WP1 (D1.1 – D1.2).

There are two main entities/actors that are responsible for the national policy that supports energy efficiency. These are:

Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC)⁴, the responsible national authority for Energy and Climate Change Policy, coordinates the major dissemination programs and campaigns referring to the development and penetration of the technologies and policy instruments for energy efficiency.

MEECC monitors and supervises the implementation of measures for achieving the national indicative energy savings target through the provision of energy services and other measures to improve energy efficiency, and prepares a report on their results (2nd NEEAP; NEEAP, 2014). It has also the administrative, managing and executive responsibility of implementing the energy efficiency requirements of the "Energy Efficiency Action Plans" and relevant incentives and other measures to improve energy efficiency and those relating to the public sector.

The Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES) is the national centre for RES, Rational Use of Energy & Energy Saving. It is supervised by MEECC and has financial and administrative independence. It provides advice and assistance to MEECC on matters of RES/RUE/ES

⁴ <http://www.ypeka.gr>

national policy, strategy and planning, is entitled to conduct dissemination and training campaigns as well as awareness raising campaigns on RES. The main instruments used are, training activities, specialized events and production of material (technical guides, promotional publications, training software etc).

The support provided by CRES, particularly through studies, action plans and national reports, involves the fulfilment of national obligations under the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) and generally, under national and European legislation, relating to the energy efficiency of buildings, energy saving, renewable energy sources and cogeneration issues.

Other entities that are part of the implementation network for the national policy that supports energy efficiency will be presented in more details at the respective Deliverables of WP1 (D.1.1 and D.1.2). An indicative list of such important actors follows below (YPEKA, 2014):

- Ministry of Finance;
- Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction;
- Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Marine and Tourism;
- Ministry of Culture, Education and Religious Affairs;
- Ministry of Health;
- Administrative Divisions and Decentralized Divisions;
- Local Authorities;
- Public Properties Company⁵;
- Buildings' Infrastructures SA (merger of the School Buildings Organization - SBO SA, the Public Company for the Construction of Medical Institutions - DEPANOM SA and THEMIS CONSTRUCTION INC;
- Association of Building Manufacturers.

Finally, important players and institutions that are related to energy efficiency for the building and transport sectors should also be mentioned here, since, their contribution is necessary for the successful implementation of the respective national policy (YPEKA, 2014 and Chondrou-Karavasili M., 2009). These include:

- Academic Institutions (national technical and non-technical universities etc.);
- Technical Chamber of Greece;
- Research institutes (e.g. National Observatory of Athens etc.);
- Associations of property owners (e.g. Hellenic Property Federation);
- Manufacturers Associations (Federation of Manufacturers and Construction Industry Greece - OMKOE);
- Environmental NGOs and Institutes (eg Greenpeace, WWF, INZEB, Greek Institute of Passive Building - EIPAK, etc.);
- Banks Association;

⁵ <http://www.etasa.gr/page.aspx>

Urban and intercity transport companies (e.g. Athens Urban Transport Organisation – OASA, ATTIKO METRO S.A., National Federation Motorists of Long-distance Communications – POYAS, Railway Agency of Greece – OSE, Civil Aviation Authority - YPA etc).

1.2 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

The following section presents an overview of technologies used for improving energy efficiency in Greece. More information and technical characteristics are included in the deliverable D.1.4: Technological trends in energy efficiency (Work Package 1).

Buildings

Bioclimatic design interventions

The bio-climatic design, the energy efficiency and RES systems as well as the energy management systems are being implemented in more and more buildings of the private and public sectors (Chondrou-Karavasili M., 2009).

In Greece, bioclimatic design interventions are made, not only for climate and environmental reasons, but also for energy efficiency reasons targeting to heating-cooling and lighting uses (ERDF PP8 REGION OF WESTERN GREECE, 2014). These interventions include:

- solar chimneys,
- solar protection and shading systems,
- green roofs,
- various support systems and network connections, including data metering, monitoring systems for the building energy system,
- high performance fireplaces,
- and energy management systems for electromechanical installations, such as BEMS (Chondrou-Karavasili M., 2009).

Indicatively, for the Programme “Bioclimatic upgrades of public open spaces”, the eligible categories of intervention included:

- increasing soft permeable surfaces and reducing hard, accessible soil cover surfaces,
- replacing conventional hard materials,
- increasing shaded areas during summer period, and surfaces exposed to sunlight in winter,
- increasing green areas,
- making use of heat sinks,
- applying photovoltaic panels on sidewalks, pergolas and blinds.

Heating-cooling and water heating

For heating-cooling purposes, active and passive solar systems are used. Particularly, the most common passive solar system is based on the suitable orientation of the windows combined with sun protection and regular ventilation during summer period.

Apart from passive solar systems, there are also various systems for natural cooling which operate positively in winter, increasing the insulation of the building envelope, such as radiation barrier,

ventilated envelope and green roofs. The green roofs improve the thermal, optical and environmental conditions for the end-users.

Economic incentives were given for improving energy efficiency in the residential sector by the programme “Changing Air-Condition” for the replacement of old split air-condition units (led to the replacement of 140.000 units all over Greece). The programme’s aim was the replacement of air-conditioning units of low energy performance with others of inverter technology (high energy performance - energy class A or B), within the cooling range of 9.000 Btu/h to 24.000 Btu/h (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Also, the programme “Energy Savings in Households” aimed to the insulation refurbishment by components-walls, roofs, windows and replacement of heating and water heating equipment⁶.

The technology of heat pumps for space heating-cooling and hot water provision is also used (IEA, 2011). The installation of central solar thermal systems in households and tertiary buildings is promoted for hot water requirements.

Furthermore, the technology of high-efficiency Combined Heat and Power (CHP) systems and cooling systems with natural gas was used in public hospitals and it was financed through the programme “Energy efficiency, cogeneration, energy management”. This programme financed also construction of systems to assist heating/cooling systems with RES (NEEAP, 2014).

The programme “District heating networks” funded the construction of new district heating networks or the extension of existing ones, such as the “District heating network of Florina”.

Also, internal and external insulation systems were promoted not only for new buildings but also for existing and historical ones.

Appliances: Cooking, Refrigeration, Washing machines, Laundry dryer, Dishwasher

Energy labeling was promoted not only for public procurements but also for the general public, for the purchase of highly energy efficient appliances (NEEAP, 2014).

Lighting

The installation of lighting control systems with motion sensors and LED technology is promoted for improving energy efficiency in lighting.

Moreover, the compulsory replacement of all low energy efficient light fittings in the wider public sector, such as filament light bulbs or fluorescent light bulbs in an energy efficiency class lower than B, with high efficiency units (lamps, ballasts, reflectors, etc.) such as fluorescent light bulbs in energy efficiency class A or B with integral or external electronic ballast, was promoted. The target is to replace the majority of light bulbs with maximum energy efficiency ones (A, A+, A++). For street lighting, several municipalities used RES.

Transport

Road transport: passenger and freight (cars, buses, coaches, motorbikes, trucks)

“Since 1995 the number of advanced technology catalytic passenger cars is constantly increasing, while the number of medium and large size passenger cars has almost tripled compared to 1990 levels” (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

Concerning the road transport (mainly cars), tax incentives were provided for the use of alternative technology vehicles (natural gas vehicles, hybrid vehicles), and vehicles with improved Euro 6 engine specifications (Decree-Law 16.9.2009/2: “Measures to address air pollution”). Also, financial

⁶ <http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/profiles/greece-efficiency-trends.pdf>

incentives such as subsidies were given for private cars' scrapping and the purchase of new vehicles with EURO 4 and EURO 5 engines. The implementation of this legislative act stopped in 2009 with achieving the scrapping of 140.000 vehicles (NEEAP, 2014).

Other technologies for private cars are CNG and LPG-powered passenger vehicles (NEEAP, 2014).

The replacement of old public and private light trucks of EURO 3 standards with new vehicles meeting EURO 5 standards is promoted. Another technology for trucks is the private new technology light trucks (up to 2.000 cc).

The number of e-vehicles in Greece is limited. This market is not mature yet. By October 2012, it is estimated that 40 corporate e-cars, 15 e-bicycles for municipalities and a few private e-cars were available in Greece⁷. The infrastructure is poor, with 3 public recharging stations in Athens. Recent developments concerning the legislative framework for electricity tariffication/utilization and possible tax deduction for e-cars is estimated to stimulate the purchase of more e-vehicles. Also, Greek municipalities have submitted an application in order to receive funding for purchasing e-vehicles and investing recharging station from renewable energy sources.⁸ Furthermore, the Law 3855/2010, with which the Energy Service Directive is transported in national legislation, refers to energy efficient vehicles in the public sector.⁹

The Athens Urban Transport Organisation (OASA) proceeded with the replacement of 520 old and polluting public buses with new "clean" ones, out of which 200 are natural-gas fired. Also, it purchased twelve (12) electrical buses, one (1) hybrid and one (1) hydrogen one. The eco-driving is also included in the procedure of driving lessons from 2009 (Zarkadoula M., 2009).

The use of smart technologies and systems in the transport sector is also promoted (Bank of Greece, 2011).

Rail transport

The needs of this sub-sector are focused on modernized infrastructure such as electric and diesel locomotives with speeds of 220km/h, coaches of updated standards, high comfort and high speed and modern wagons for freight (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).

New tilting trains are also needed for achieving a significant reduction of time without proceeding with the costly required investment in civil works due to the mountainous terrain of the country (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).

Aviation

Concerning aviation, Aegean airlines, the biggest airline company in Greece, invested in the fleet modernization. In 2010, the last of the B737-400 of Aegean's fleet was retired. The aim of the company is to fly solely new generation, fuel efficient A320/321 and A319 aircrafts. Also, the company is aiming for a 1,5% reduction in fuel consumption attributed to fuel saving initiatives in 2011¹⁰. For this reason, Flight Operations has implemented the following initiatives in cooperation with Air Traffic Control:

- Reduced Flaps Take-off (subject to operational conditions),
- Reduced Acceleration Altitude (subject to operational conditions),
- Idle Reverse on Landing (subject to operational conditions),

⁷ Fact-sheet of Greece: <http://emobilityworks.com/gr/λήψεις/category/1-national-factsheet.html>

⁸ Fact-sheet of Greece: <http://emobilityworks.com/gr/λήψεις/category/1-national-factsheet.html>

⁹ <http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/profiles/greece-efficiency-trends.pdf>

¹⁰ <http://en.aegeanair.com/all-about-us/corporate-responsibility/flight-and-environment/>

- Single engine shutdown (subject to operational conditions).

Also, the company prepared an extensive study to calculate the fuel cost of transporting one kilogram of equipment on board the aircraft. Cutting the weight transported on-board, the aircraft can save significant amounts of fuel and thus reduce the CO₂ emissions.

The adopted and implemented suggestions include:

- Optimization of potable water quantity carried on-board the aircraft.
- Cutting the weight by clearing up galleys & bins from unnecessary material, cutlery and magazines/ newspapers also results in improved fuel efficiency and thus fewer emissions¹¹.

¹¹ <http://en.aegeanair.com/all-about-us/corporate-responsibility/flight-and-environment/>

Table 2: National policy for energy efficiency.

National policy	Policy instrument (type)	Directives/Regulations	National Laws/Ministerial Decisions
Buildings sector			
Promotion of energy efficient appliances and energy equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Energy labelling of household lamps and dishwashers, air-conditioners, electric ovens, electric refrigerators, freezers and their combinations (Regulatory standards) · labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products (Voluntary approaches) 	1998/11/EC, 1999/9/EC, 2002/31/EC, 2002/40/EC, 2003/66/EC, 2010/30/EC – Commission Regulation No. 626/2011 (supplementing Directive)	Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 (Government Gazette 2301 B, 14.10.2011)
	Ecodesign requirements for household washers, refrigerating appliances, televisions, washing machines; glandless circulators (standalone and integrated in products; electric motors; no-load condition power consumption and average active efficiency of external supplies, non-directional household lamps, fluorescent lamps without integrated ballast, high intensity discharge lamps, ballasts and luminaires able to operate such lamps; simple set-top boxes, standby and off mode electric power consumption of household and office equipment; energy efficiency requirements for ballasts for fluorescent lighting (Voluntary approaches)	Directive 2000/55/EC Directive 2005/32/EC (implemented through Regulations No 641/2009, 640/2009, 642/2009, 643/2009, 278/2009, 244/2009-amended by 859/2009, 245/2009-amended by 347/2010, 107/2009, 1275/2008) Directive 2009/125/EC (implemented through Regulations No 1016/2010, 1015/2010)	Presidential Decree 7/2011 (Government Gazette 14 A/11.2.2011) Presidential Decree 32/2010 (Government Gazette 70 A, 14.05.2010) Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 (Government Gazette 1122 B, 17.6.2008)
	Energy labelling (Voluntary approaches)	Regulation No. 2422/2001 – Program Energy Star (Voluntary participation), Regulation No. 106/2008	Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 – Government Gazette 1122/B/17.6.2008)
Promotion of energy efficiency	Efficiency of hot water boilers (Regulatory standards)	92/42/EC	
	Energy inspectors for energy performance of	2010/31/EC ¹²	Act of legislation (Government Gazette A 237, 5.12.2012),

¹² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EL:PDF>

	<p>buildings (Regulatory policy instruments) Energy audits (Regulatory policy instruments)</p>	<p>2002/91/EC</p>	<p>Presidential Degree 100/2010 (Government Gazette 177 A, 6.10.2010 for energy inspectors), Presidential Degree 72/2010 (Government Gazette 132 A, 05.08.2010), Law 3885/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010), Regulation for EE of buildings (Δ6/B/5825-30.3.2010, Government Gazette 407 B, 9.4.2010), Law 3661/2008 (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.5.2008)</p>
	<p>End-use efficiency and energy services (ESCOs) (Other policy instruments) Green Public Procurements (Voluntary approaches) Metering (Regulatory policy instrument) Voluntary agreements (Voluntary approaches)</p>	<p>2006/32/EC 2009/33/EC¹³</p>	<p>Ministerial Decision Δ5-HΛ/B/Φ1.20/οικ.6262/20.03.2013 (Government Gazette 832 B, 9.04.2013) Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010), Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/14826/2008 – Government Gazette 1122 B, 17.6.2008), Law 3661/2008 (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.5.2008)</p>
	<p>Energy Performance of Buildings (references to building code, minimum requirements, interventions, green roofs, renovations etc) (Regulatory, financial and informative policy instruments)</p>	<p>2010/31/EC</p>	<p>Law 4122/2013 (Government Gazette 42 A, 19.02.2013 - NZEB), Law 4067/2012 (Government Gazette 79A, 2012), Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010), Law 3842/2010 (Government Gazette 58 A, 23.04.2010), Law 3661/2008 (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.5.2008) Decision 3046/304/89 (Government Gazette 59Δ - Building code), Law 1577/1985 (Government Gazette 210 A, 18.12.1985)</p>

¹³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:120:0005:0012:EL:PDF>

	Financial incentives , energy efficiency requirements (Economic instrument)	Directive 2010/31/EU	Law 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 4.6.2010)
	Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel) for heating and other use, biodiesel and kerosene for heating and other use) (Economic instrument)	Directive 2010/31/EU, 2004/74/EC, 2004/75/EC, 2003/17/EC, 2003/96/EC,	Law 4092/2012 (Government Gazette 220 A, 8.11.2012), Law 3845/2010 (Government Gazette 65 A, 6.05.2010), Law 3833/2010 (Government Gazette 40 A, 15.03.2010), Law 3828/2010 (Government Gazette 31 A, 25.02.2010), Law 3336/2005 (Government Gazette 96 A, 20.04.2005)
	Green Fund (Regulatory and financial policy instrument)		Law 3889/2010 (Government Gazette 182 A, 14.10.2010)
	Financial incentives (subsidy) (replacement of oil heating systems with natural gas ones) (financial policy instrument)		Ministerial Decision Φ.14/02/19398/2927 (Government Gazette B 3071/14.11.2014 ¹⁴)
	Energy efficiency (energy audits, energy management system, metering, procurements by Public Bodies, ESCOs) (Regulatory policy instrument)	2012/27/EU	The draft law was -for second time- under public consultation until 1 st of July 2015 ¹⁵ and the results have not been announced yet (YPEKA, 2015; 2014 ¹⁶).
Transport sector			
Emission reduction actions in transport	Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6) (Regulatory policy instrument)	EU Regulation No. 715/2007	Draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC
	Establishment of Permanent Committee on Green Transportation (Regulatory policy instrument)		Law 3710/2008 (Government Gazette 216 A, 23.10.2008)
	Energy labeling for tyres in transport	EC Regulation 1235/2011	

¹⁴ https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7Jb_n_W6q6bR1INNE92THd3c1E/view?usp=sharing&pli=1

¹⁵ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6692>

¹⁶ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6288>

	(Regulatory – informative policy instrument)	EC Regulation No. 1222/2009	
	Consumer information on fuel economy and CO ₂ emissions of new passenger cars (Dissemination and awareness policy instrument)	1999/94/EC, 2003/73 (Regulations 1882/2003, 1137/2008)	Ministerial Decision 11762/2006 (Government Gazette 327 B, 17.3.2006)
Reduction of GHG emissions, promotion of RES, EE	Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel), biodiesel and kerosene for transport for transport (Economic instrument)	2003/96/EC, 2004/74/EC, 2004/75/EC, 2003/17/EC	Law 4092/2012 (Government Gazette 220 A, 8.11.2012) Law 3986/2011 (Government Gazette 152 A, 1.07.2011) Law 3845/2010 (Government Gazette 65 A, 6.05.2010), Law 3833/2010 (Government Gazette 40 A, 15.3.2010) Law 3828/2010 (Government Gazette 31 A, 25.02.2010), Law 3336/2005 (Government Gazette 96 A, 20.04.2005)
	Registration tax rates (Euro 5) (Hybrid and electric cars are exempted) (Economic instrument)	EC Regulations 566/2011, 692/2008 (Euro 5 and Euro 4), 715/2007 Directive 1998/69/EC Directive 94/12/EC	Law 3156/2003 (Government Gazette 157 A, 25.06.2003)
	Circulation fee (road tax) (Economic instrument)	EC Regulations 715/2007 (Euro 5 and Euro 6), Directive 1999/96/EC (Euro 3 and Euro 4) Directive 91/542/EC (Euro 2 and Euro 1)	Law 4093/2012 (Government Gazette 222 A, 12.11.2012) Law 3986/2011 (Government Gazette 152 A, 1.07.2011)
GHG reduction actions in transport and promotion of energy efficiency	Incentives to replace old technology cars (Economic policy instrument)		Law 4316/2014 (Government Gazette 270 A, 24.12.2014) Law 4223/2013 (Government Gazette 287 A, 31.12.2013) Law 4110/2013 (Government Gazette 17 A, 23.01.2013) Law 3943/2011 (Government Gazette 66 A, 31.03.2011),

			Decision No. 5006718EΞ2001 (Government Gazette 246 B, 11.02.2011), Law 3899/2010 (Government Gazette 212/A 17.12.2010 and 246/B 11.02.2011) Law 3333/2005 (Government Gazette 91 A, 12.4.2005) Law 3245/2004 (Government Gazette A 110, 16.6.2004) Law 3109/2003 (Government Gazette 38 A, 19.02.2003)
	Green Public Procurements for transport (Voluntary approaches)	Directive 2009/33/EC	Law 3982/2011 (Government Gazette 143 A, 17.06.2011) Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010)
	Cycling and pedestrianism in the city (Planning and dissemination-awareness policy instrument)		Expected legislation for the city of Athens within year 2015 ¹⁷ (MEECC, 2014) Ministerial Decision 33523/7564/10-6-2002 ¹⁸
	Improvement of infrastructure for electric vehicles (Planning policy instrument)		Joint Ministerial Decision 71287/6443 (Government Gazette 50 B, 15.01.2015) Law 4233/2014 (Government Gazette 22 A, 29.01.2014) Law 4070/2012 (Government Gazette 82 A, 10.04.2012)

¹⁷ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=cwreF0yvYc%3D&tabid=37&language=el-GR>

¹⁸ <http://www.hellenicparliament.gr/Praktika/Synedriaseis-Olomeleias?sessionRecord=e7696f4c-a10c-4222-a036-aa69e43b97ff>

Promotion of energy efficiency	Eco-driving (Dissemination – Awareness – educational policy instrument)		Ministerial Decision No. 76568/1197 (Government Gazette B 81, 19.01.2015 ¹⁹ , amending the previous one) Ministerial Decision A3/50984/7947 (Government Gazette B 3056/2/11/2013) Ministerial Decision 552/88 (Government Gazette B4/7-1-2013) Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010)
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Source: MEIST, 2015; MEECC, 2015; MEECC, 2013; Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014; DG Clima, DG Energy.

¹⁹ <http://www.odigostoupoliti.eu/adia-odigisis-ekpedefsi-ke-exetasi-ipopsifion-odigon-motopodilaton-motosikleton-ke-aftokiniton/>

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

Factors influencing behavior of Hellenic end-uses

Technologies and practices for Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and Energy Efficiency (EE) have been promoted in parallel, with those of RES to have gained more attention by the public due to the financial incentives that were used (Feed-in-tariffs, subsidies etc) (Kambezidis H. et al., 2010).

However, in both cases, for further promoting RES and EE, local public acceptance is required based primarily on the public's awareness and adequate knowledge about RES and EE (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014). Conducted in Greece, surveys on RES usually include also in the questionnaire a set of questions related to environmentally friendly behavior and energy saving actions (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014). The results indicated five factors that are significantly related with the various levels of RES and EE knowledge. More specifically (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014):

- **Gender:** Men are more likely than women to be aware about RES and EE technologies and practices. Men are usually more likely to present higher knowledge levels, although in some cases the opposite results were also found. These differences between the two genders are attributed to a number of other socioeconomic factors (ie age, educational background, religion, occupation and political ideology).
- **Age** (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014; Gelegenis J. et al., 2014): younger people are more likely to be aware about RES and EE due to improvements and changes in curriculum of schools and universities that are linked with environmental awareness and behaviour. Additionally, younger people have more opportunities to receive such information through various communication channels (ie websites and digital social networks), which are more easily reached by them than by older people.
- **Education level and education level of the head of the household** (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014; Gelegenis J. et al., 2014): People of higher education levels are more knowledgeable about such issues. So, the accomplishment of a wider awareness level on RES and EE, can be addressed by providing such information to students during their entire education, starting from elementary school. The educational level of the head of the household also affects knowledge.
- **Occupation:** When the job, studies or interests are related to environment, technology or engineering then the level of awareness is affected positively.
- **Environmental behavior** (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014; Gelegenis J. et al., 2014): People with better environmental behavior are more likely to know about RES and EE and support them since a broader environmental behaviour and education can stimulate awareness on such technologies and practices. People with such an attitude are more likely to get interested on information on RES and EE.

Apart from the aforementioned factors, there are other factors that have also been identified of affecting the penetration of EE technologies. Particularly for the household sector, household income, energy prices in combination with consumers behaviour are considered as primary determinants of fuel expenditures and investment on energy efficient technologies (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014).

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

Recorded trends

In Greece the energy use of the building sector - for the year 2011 - was approximately 40% of the total energy demand (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Residential, public and commercial premises used energy primarily for space heating and cooling, and domestic hot water production, while other energy uses were electricity for appliances/equipment and for operation of building services systems (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

Two factors, the improved living standards of the Greek society and the increased number of dwellings resulted in changes of the energy consumption of the building sector. More specifically, there were improved levels of heating and, recently, of cooling, and increased ownership of home electric appliances (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

There was also increased electricity demand for ventilation, lighting and other office equipment due to substantial increase in the floor area of commercial premises (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

The increased energy demand is the result of an increased demand for electricity and to a smaller extent for petroleum products (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). More specifically, the contribution of electricity to total energy consumption in the sector increased from 29% in 1990 (1,4 Mtoe) to 40% in 2011 (3,2 Mtoe), while consumption of oil products accounted for 39% of energy consumption in the sector from 54% in 1990 (2,7 Mtoe) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Compared to previous years there is a significant increase in using natural gas in the residential and the tertiary sector for year 2011 (21,5 PJ) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

The RES share of the sector in the total energy consumption was reduced from 15% in 1990 (0,7 Mtoe) to 10% in 2011 (0,8 Mtoe) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). A new trend for biomass was recorded. Biomass was the primary energy source until 1985 in the countryside for heat requirements of households and holiday homes (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Since then, gradually large urban areas, apart from the countryside, started using biomass as a secondary energy source. This shift was attributed to two reasons: i) increasing population of the large cities in Greece and ii) renewed demand for installation of fireplaces in private residences and apartment buildings (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

The final energy consumption in buildings depends on the: i) building type; ii) area at which it is located, iii) level of economic activity in the area and iv) modern way of living and the people's growing needs (Maleviti E. et al., 2012). The last one is linked with the extended use of appliances and equipment that require high electricity consumption such as ventilation and air-conditioning systems (Maleviti E. et al., 2012). For Greece the majority of equipment used in buildings does not have high energy efficient standards (Maleviti E. et al., 2012).

Subsectors

The Hellenic building sector has six subsectors as these are presented in Table 3. The number that corresponds to the domestic sector is about the buildings, while the number for households is about the number of occupied residencies that are in all those buildings. All residencies (occupied and empty) are 6.371.901 (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Households represent a share of 84% of the total building stock (72% of total surface) (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). From the remaining 16%, the 3,62% corresponds to offices,

stores, educational buildings, hospitals and hotels (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

For the sub-sectors of the Hellenic building sector the following information provides the necessary background for understanding the described barriers. Most of the available literature (official reports, funded research projects and published research papers) are addressing mainly two sectors, the public sector and the hotels.

Table 3: Number of buildings and their usage in years 2001 and 2011.

Usage of building	Number of buildings	
	Year 2001 (ELSTAT)	2011 (TABULA)
Domestic sector (Households)	2.755.570	2.468.124 (4.122.088)
Hotels	5.595	8.309
Schools – Buildings for education	16.804	15.576
Hospitals-Clinics	1.961	1.742
Others	625.630	625.630
TOTAL	3.516.657	3.271.931 (4.925.895)

(Source: Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

Domestic sector (Households)

The Hellenic domestic sector in Greece accounts for the 24% of the total final energy consumption of the country of year 2013 (YPEKA, 2015). The sector uses electricity (40% of the total final energy consumption of the sector), oil products (26%), natural gas (6%) and RES (26,5%, with biomass at 21% of the total final energy consumption of the sector) (YPEKA, 2015). The RES share concerns mainly biomass (wood used in fire places or ovens), solar energy for production of domestic hot water (YPEKA, 2015).

Public buildings

In 2007 the number of public buildings was estimated at approximately 200.000, representing a share of 5% of the tertiary sector (Greenpeace, 2007). These buildings demonstrate a wide diversity regarding their characteristics since they were built at different time periods and for fulfilling different needs than those that they are finally being used. As large portion of them (60% in 2007) are rented and differ among them in the used equipment, the heat convenience etc. The public sector uses new and old buildings (Greenpeace, 2007).

Hotels

Only a share of 0,26% of the total Greek buildings represents hotels, but they are responsible for the 29% of the energy consumption in the private sector (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011). This relatively high percentage is due to spaceheating and cooling equipment, hot water needs, facilities and services offered and the number of the tourist arrivals during the hotels' operation (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011). Hotels use gas, diesel fuel, natural gas and mainly electricity (for air-conditioning, heating, lighting, lifts, kitchen equipment and many static and portable appliances) which results to high energy cost (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011). Oil - used for heating needs and hot water-contributes to the high amount of energy consumption in hotels, but it is expected in the next years

to be replaced by natural gas which currently is lower in use²⁰ (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011). For hoteliers the most common and the easiest EE technologies and practices to be applied by them are efficient lighting and equipment (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).

Table 4: Social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector.

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social - Educational	Zero to low availability of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is lack of information not only for the public institutes regarding their energy consumption, but also towards the citizens regarding the energy renovation of the public buildings. The main reason for this situation is the fact that the government does not actually promote this type of renovation (CERTus, 2015). The buildings renovation is used for achieving the target for nearly zero energy buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU²¹). Residents/users usually have insufficient information and education, regarding the rational use and management of energy, leading to (YPEKA, 2010): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> installation of individual air-conditioning systems without technical study; use of poor performance devices; non maintenance of the heating system. <p>The relevant Ministry attempted to confront this barrier that emerged during the implementation of the national energy efficiency policy with the “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Program (YPEKA, 2010).</p>
Social	Variable ownership structure, age and condition of the existing building stock	Variable ownership structure, age and condition of the existing building stock prevents the targeted promotion of energy efficiency in buildings. For this reason, different thermal renovation types need to be promoted in order to cover the respective needs (ENTRANZE, 2014; YPEKA, 2014).
Social	Diverse socio-economic background in the plenty multifamily buildings in Greece	In multifamily buildings renovation is difficult to be decided, according to the research of ENTRANZE for some of the south European countries, including Greece (ENTRANZE, 2014). This is attributed to the many owners and the different opinions that they share due to their different socio-economic background (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014). The buildings renovation is one of the means for achieving the target for nearly zero energy buildings as it is set by Directive 2010/31/EU ²² .
Behavioral	End-users aloofness due to negative past experience	The occurrence of negative experiences is mentioned frequently in Europe (ENTRANZE, 2014). They are characterized either as historical and fading (ie early not-so-convincing demonstrations of solar thermal systems and groundsource heat pumps), as more recent or more persistent (ie opposition to mechanical ventilation, especially mechanical supply and exhaust

²⁰ Only hotels located in Athens and Thessaloniki use natural gas due to access to gas supplies (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).

²¹ http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/;ELX_SESSIONID=FZMjThLLzfxmmMCQGp2Y1s2d3TjwD8QS3pqdkhXZbwqGwlgY9KN!2064651424?uri=C ELEX:32010L0031

²² http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/;ELX_SESSIONID=FZMjThLLzfxmmMCQGp2Y1s2d3TjwD8QS3pqdkhXZbwqGwlgY9KN!2064651424?uri=C ELEX:32010L0031

		ventilation, which is a prerequisite for heat recovery; quality problems in thermal renovations; underperformance of airsource heat pumps; overblow marketing claims for solar thermal systems). The identification of appropriate means for managing these barriers is crucial in achieving public acceptance in the markets where most solutions are still at an initial stage and there are not enough good examples and widespread experiences (ENTRANZE, 2014).
Social	Shared ownership (multilateral ownership)	In Greece it is very often to have more than 10 apartment owners in multi-family buildings, leading to a mosaic of opinions, rarely converging, according to the beliefs and interests of each one (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014; Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Consequently, there can not be a common strategy on the energy upgrading measures for the whole building in an effort to comply with the first National Grant Program (EXOIKONOMO KAT OIKON) (subsidies for energy-upgrading measures in multi-family buildings, issued in 2011) (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).
Social	Low level of awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level of awareness regarding the environmental, economical and energy efficiency benefits has strong influence on energy refurbishment policies (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). The Greek society has not yet strongly endorsed energy conservation and sustainability (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). The ignorance of such benefits, along with the fear of still unknown technologies and restricted financial incentives, form a barrier for the broad implementation of such measures (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). • Research studies for certain areas in Greece have shown that people who considered themselves to be informed on energy saving were more likely to have installed a higher percentage of energy efficient devices (such as lamps) (Zografakis N. et al., 2012). These studies also emphasize on the fundamental role of energy awareness and particularly with having integrated a targeted information session, on technical and cost recovery issues (Zografakis N. et al., 2012). • The same barrier is mentioned by hotel owners ie low awareness of the technologies and their benefits in hotels along with low management capacity and commitment, lack of staff resources, and concerns about financing and performance (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Hotel owners or managers ask to be able to access simple information on EE and RES options, and particularly on their practical business benefits, ie in terms of cost savings and also improved sales (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). They would be facilitated if they were provided with lists of suitable technologies for each of the different operating areas of the hotel (eg. hallways, restaurants, bedrooms, etc.), so as to understand, assess and decide which technologies can be integrated into renovation of specific hotel areas (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). They also consider essential to know about the policy framework or examples from other countries where similar initiatives were applied (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011). For them it would be helpful if the

		<p>government or the “National Organisation of Tourism” could provide such information (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A research was addressed to 331 households of low income in the Kastoria prefecture, in Greece (Christidou C. et al., 2014). 271 questionnaires were finally collected (82% response rate). There were two interesting points: i) Out of the 19 energy saving practices that were included in the questionnaire, one was related with energy labeling (policy instrument). For that practice, only 35,8% of the respondents reported that they select “A” energy class electrical devices, placing this practice in the 18th position. ii) 73 (27%) out of the 271 surveyed households were already fully equipped with energy saving lamps by the time the research was conducted, while from the remaining 198 households, 174 (88%) stated that they were willing to change their remaining incandescent lamps with energy saving ones after considering the introductory informative session of the questionnaire (Christidou C. et al., 2014). • In Crete another face to face survey of 685 companies’ managers pointed out that only 9,8% were using Inverter technology of air-conditioning split units, while 44,2% of those who had not installed it were willing to do so (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012).
Social - cultural - educational	Lack of environmental consciousness, awareness and culture	The Hellenic society is not appropriately aware regarding the environment and more specifically the concept of “sustainable and energy efficient building” since more than 2/3 of the population does not believe that their buildings are responsible for environmental degradation (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). On the other hand governments did not provide society with relevant information or gave incentives to the public to invest in sustainable buildings (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).
Social	Lack of local social support	The lack of social support for energy efficiency (and RES) investments is considered to be a major parameter for the failure in implementing the Covenant of Mayors (ie the SEAP – set of relevant policy instruments) (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).
Social	Wrong use of information and communication of local scale governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many mayors did not have a clear picture about the Covenant of Mayors and particularly for the imposed obligations to the local communities (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). It is most likely that the Covenant of Mayors was used by candidate mayors as a mean for advertising/promoting themselves during the local elections (Christoforidis et al., 2013). A smaller number of elected mayors proceeded with the SEAP since the apophthegm “who is going to pay for this” prevailed when they were informed about the necessary studies that had to be prepared and the actions to be implemented for a SEAP (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). • Local governments fail to exploit the fact that the majority of their citizens agree with the signing of the Covenant of Mayors and with its commitments (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). It seems – based on the recorded data about the signatories and the

		submitted SEAPs - that one of most significant obstacles to the success of the Covenant of Mayors is the lack of information and the means of dissemination towards the citizens and even inside the local governments themselves (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).
Educational	Lack of expertise - Incomplete training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is identified deficiency in technical expertise of bioclimatic architecture by civil engineers and architects from the construction process (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Even when in certain cases bioclimatic design was applied by engineers and architects the outcome was not successful (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). • Inexperienced engineers are involved in the design of energy renovation while simultaneously there are only few construction companies and workers that are familiarized with the correct implementation of energy saving measures under the recent EU Directive²³ (for example avoidance of thermo-bridges or the elimination of water vapour condensation risk on renovations of facades) (CERTus, 2015). This increases the risk of damages and might result to significant reduction of the total performance of the measure. There is also lack of specialized personnel for the renovations of facades (CERTus, 2015). • The training of the municipality's technical service staff regarding EE issues in buildings and the usage of RES is incomplete (CERTus, 2015). Usually the offered to them seminars are relevant exclusively regarding the new legislation and the management of resources. The technical service considers that it does not have adequate access to information about systems for improved EE and RES, that are market available (CERTus, 2015). That is why, the study for a new building or for renovation is assigned to external partners. Therefore, the choice for using EE improvements is entirely up to the sub-contractor (CERTus, 2015). • The implementation of the JESSICA initiative in Greece faced difficulties due to the need of training of the officials in the municipalities regarding the preparation of the selected projects (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). Projects mature enough to generate cash flows are granted funding through the JESSICA initiative. However, this does not happen for the majority of the projects that are being proposed. So, specific actions need to be implemented by the implementation network and the municipalities so that any obstacles (institutional, environmental, technical) are overcome (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). • The technical services of the municipality stated that the received education by their staff is imposed as part

²³ nearly zero energy buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU)

		<p>of the implemented legislation. So, new technical knowledge is transferred only if it becomes part of the legislation. This fact prevents any type of innovative initiative of the staff regarding the energy and environmental performance/outcomes (CERTus, 2015).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installers and maintainers of building installations are usually uncertified (YPEKA, 2014).
Social educational	- Problematic cooperation among parties	During the design and construction of a bioclimatic building there was little or no integrated cooperation among architects, civil engineers and mechanical engineers (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). This situation inhibited the whole design and construction process (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).
Cultural	Negative public perception	There was a negative public perception for Green roofs (Green roofs were supported by recent law and the national programme "Green roofs in public buildings" (refurbishment of buildings) that was launched in 2011). There was lack of agreement among owners. Furthermore, the capital investment was high along with considerable administrative burden (CRISP project, 2012).
Social-economic	Reluctance to pay up front great amount of money for an investment with future returns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although there was interest for Green roofs in Greece (Law and programme), people were discouraged about such a technology since they had to pay up front for a high investment, and consequently new technologies were not easily adopted. Despite the level of communication and the visibility of efforts for a programme/initiative in the media and in different communities, economic-based initiatives require substantial support from the government (CRISP project, 2012). • the energy gain and the degree of re-accumulation of capital by the indicated type of renovation is often low (YPEKA, 2014).
Social-behavioral	South European occupant behavior towards shading	The usual south European occupant behavior installs external shadings in the eastern kitchen and the western living room windows, trying to keep cool the rooms (Kolaitis 2013). So, the energy efficiency policy for installation of external shadings of buildings is not fully applied.
Educational	Information barrier towards emerging innovative technologies	<p>The preparations for the 2000–2006 Action Plan of EU for energy efficiency identified a number of potential barriers concerning the access to and the spread of efficient energy technologies. These barriers concerned all EU Member States regarding the adoption of energy efficiency policies for SMES, services and buildings (Kounetas K. et al., 2011). More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete or no information hindered the use of cost-effective and energy-efficient technologies. The lack of readily available information and demonstration increases the investment costs in such technologies due to: increased transaction/search costs; increased uncertainty regarding the investment; and due to the risk of lock-in an inappropriate technology. In Greece, empirical evidence were gathered with the use of questionnaires and face-to-face interviews during 2004 (Kounetas K. et al., 2011). • SMEs faced heavy barriers regarding the adoption of energy efficient technologies due to information restrictions caused by their size or in other words by their

		<p>limited available resources. The acquisition of information is an advantage of larger firms. This advantage is rooted in a firm's financial capacity, and in the capability of its human resources to collect, screen and evaluate information. However, the advantage connected to size is relative. When the firm is engaged in activities that demand high quality human capital resources, such as R&D, its effective size is reduced. Hence, when the knowledge base of a firm is extended by, for example R&D activities, the knowledge base related to energy efficient technologies is not equally enhanced. On the contrary, the firm's information base on EE technologies may be reduced because qualitative human capital is re-directed to other activities. Evidence provided in this work supports the argument that the level of information or knowledge acquired by a firm is technology specific. The technology vintage is the key factor determining the heterogeneity underlying the level of knowledge among firms (Kounetas K. et al., 2011).</p>
Social	Working habits	<p>It is difficult to reduce the standby energy consumption for practical reasons; personnel such as bank staff consider that it is not practical to turn on/off equipment during the working hours due to heavy work pressure (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). Furthermore, office equipment such as automated teller machines, faxes and digital video recorders DVRs are required in standby mode continuously (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). That is why for working buildings/spaces potential energy savings office and electronic equipment under the requirements of the Energy Performance of Buildings (Law 3661/2008 – Common Ministerial Decision 5825/9.4.2010) were not considered (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011).</p>
Social	Established perception (hotels)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In Greece a share of the building stock is hotels. These end-users have the perception that high energy use is necessary to ensure the comfort of guests and do not proceed with energy efficiency actions (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). - Hoteliers that participated in a survey expressed the belief that hotel units that are based in a natural and sensitive environment (ie islands or mountainous areas) affect the environment while those units that are located in the city centre of Athens do not. If they were aware about the carbon footprint that occurs from the energy consumption from their facilities, perhaps they would had a different perception (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).
Social	Confusion and misuse of terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is often observed that there is confusion or misuse of terms such as “energy efficient buildings” or “low energy buildings” (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Due to this misunderstanding, owners of new buildings and particularly of hotels fulfil only the energy minimum standards (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). When buyers or owners ensure that their building is termed as efficient or with low energy, then they are satisfied and will less likely take further action to improve efficiency (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). • Hoteliers that participated in a survey expressed the belief that hotel units that are based in a natural and sensitive environment (ie islands or mountainous areas) affect the environment while those units that are located in the city

		centre of Athens do not. If they were aware about the carbon footprint that occurs from the energy consumption from their facilities, perhaps they would had a different perception (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).
Social	Unwillingness to do more than minimum requirements	Building owners and particularly hotel owners are unwilling to install energy efficiency measures that go beyond the minimum standards set in building codes, even if it is realized that efficiency standards in building codes rarely represent the optimum for efficiency (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Additionally, builders and designers rarely have incentives to exceed the required efficiency standards, much more if such efforts might increase initial costs (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).
Socio-economic	Higher consumption of oil than gas (habit)	Oil is more widely used in buildings compared to the other countries in South Europe, as gas grid connections are limited (and will probably be so in the future in many regions) (ENTRANZE, 2014). More than 75% of dwellings are heated by gas in the Netherlands or the UK, and by oil in Greece (ENTRANZE, 2014).
Social	Limitation in selected EE technologies	The most commonly recommended EE technologies under the EPC are aluminium frames and solar water heating collectors (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014). The criteria that affect mostly the retrofitting market are living styles, security matters, comfort and house appearance. This situation sets aside the primary objectives of the EPBD (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014).

Table 5: Main economic barriers in the building sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Market failure to understand financial and social benefits	For the Covenant of Mayors and the relevant SEAP that a city/town adopts the most important barrier appears to be the failure in the market to estimate the financial and social benefits for the local community due to an energy efficiency (or RES) project and to promote these benefits to the public (Christoforidis et al., 2013).
Financial crisis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The financial crisis prevails compliance towards the recent Directive for EE which requires strict EE measures for the public sector (CERTus, 2015). Due to this situation, banks have limited resources and their interest is restricted, particularly since the required investments for the renovation of public buildings so as to have nearly zero energy consumption have big payback period (CERTus, 2015). So, though many of the public buildings require a radical renovation for becoming nearly zero energy consuming, on the other hand, this situation is offering simultaneously an opportunity to companies activated in the energy and financial sector to gain (CERTus, 2015). Finally the impact of this barrier could be moderate. CRES, the national institute responsible for the promotion of EE and RES, has seen important budget cuts (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013). Limited national subsidies, banks' low willingness to provide loans and poor loan capability of private investors consist of a major drawback due to current economic crisis of Greece that strongly affects energy policies concerning the building sector (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Energy efficiency (but also RES) investments through the SEAPs are endangered due to cut downs of public spends in Greece (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Greek cities had to deal with a 40% cut in their budgets from the central government (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Financial instruments to be used for the SEAPs were not known to most cities administrations (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Due to the burst of the financial crisis in Greece at the end of 2009 the municipalities

	<p>could not comply with the procedures of the Covenant of Mayors (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were very few available supporting structures so most mayors sought assistance in private consultants and companies, but with a cost that they were extremely unwilling to cover themselves (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). • Barriers for the implementation of the JESSICA initiative are associated to the general liquidity problems of the Greek business sector and the Greek banks (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). • Reduction of incomes and changing consumption patterns of the population, as formulated in recent years due to the economic recession. In these conditions, the investment in energy renovations is often not a priority (YPEKA, 2014). • Bank lending, traditionally the dominant tool of financing consumption and investment needs in Greece, has undergone a significant contraction with a corresponding reduction in investment costs for building renovations. Indicatively, according to the latest data from the Bank of Greece, the net flow of credit to households was recorded negative from April 2010 and is estimated to reduce 202 million Euros in August 2014, while the growth rate of mortgage loans was at - 3,0% (YPEKA, 2014). • Companies do not work with public authorities due to delays of payment as a result of the economic crisis especially in the construction sector (EFFECT, 2012).
Restricted interest of financial institutes towards NZEB	The required investments for the renovation of public buildings so as to have nearly zero energy consumption have big payback period (CERTus, 2015).
Status of economic situation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The economic factors were among the most important ones that determined the success/failure of programmes, initiatives and particularly for energy efficiency measures of household buildings (refurbishment and appliances). Especially, the economic situation of households was the determinant in the case of investments in renewable energy sources, energy efficient appliances or refurbishment of their households. Such an example for Greece was the programme Green Roofs (CRISP, 2012). • The most significant barrier in the case of investments from hotels to environmentally friendly operations and refurbishment adopting energy efficiency technologies and practices is the economic element. The implementation of changes such as recycling and the request for guests to re-use towels and sheets in case of long stays, seem to be easily adopted. However, further investments on water monitoring systems, lighting regulation through motion-sensitive or key card systems etc. require high financial contributions, which are often relatively large compared to the small profits which small hotels expect (CRISP project, 2012). • Upfront investments for energy efficient systems reduce costs in the long run, but they are considered as non-profitable in the short run (CRISP project, 2012).
Higher income, higher energy consumption	It is confirmed that inhabitants with higher income live in relatively new constructions. These new constructions show improved energy performance. Only 8% of low income households live at buildings with isolation and double glazing windows, while the respective percentage for high income households is 64% (Association of Greek Contracting Companies, 2008). The improvement in the energy performance of the building's envelope and of heating systems - as part of the energy efficiency measure of refurbishment of residential buildings - is being offset by the higher living and comfort standards of those inhabitants, which leads to higher energy consumption. It is indicative that there is almost the same high energy consumption for heating by the very low income and the very high income households (Association of Greek Contracting Companies, 2008). The directly required renovation policies won't be easy to be implemented, due to the complexity of the Greek building sector, the limited interest of the owners, at least until there will be drastic energy price increases, and a series of legal and administrative hurdles (Theodoridou et al., 2011).
Poorly developed market for energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently, the national energy efficiency market lags behind those of other EU countries. The poorly developed market for energy services (emphasizing to Refurbishment of buildings towards NZEBs) and access for all consumers and market players to integrated and high-quality energy services provides a high potential for

	<p>future growth in energy efficiency and will be a key priority for Greece's energy policy (RePublic ZEB project, 2015).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of adequate renovations' supply chain service (YPEKA, 2014). • Lack of energy labelling, energy standards and certification in materials used in construction (YPEKA, 2014). • Lack of technical support and reliability of energy services (YPEKA, 2014). • Lack of metering / direct mechanisms (eg smart meters), which will show clearly and directly the saving energy in application renovation (YPEKA, 2014).
Cost distribution of central heating systems that favored the occupants of penthouses	<p>A study of a typical multi-family Greek building in 2007 compared common heating modes (including oil), natural gas and autonomous systems (Papadopoulos A. M. et al., 2007). The cost distribution of central heating mode was observed to favor penthouses over apartments in median floors. This possibly couldn't motivate some occupants towards energy conservation (through refurbishment of residential buildings (heating)) while it didn't also stimulate superior insulation of the roof of a building (Santamouris et al., 2013).</p>
Costly innovative technologies for end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative technologies that could contribute in achieving buildings of nearly zero energy consumption (recent EU Directive) are still new for the market and costly (CERTus, 2015). Such an example is the low market penetration of solar cooling due to high cost of this technology (CERTus, 2015). So, the nearly zero energy consumption renovations appear more difficult and costly (CERTus, 2015). • The technical services of the public buildings hesitate to approve the installation of new systems and innovative technologies, since the lack of actual successful examples reduce their trust to them (CERTus, 2015). • The person deciding for the level of energy efficiency of a building does not coincide with the person bearing the cost of energy consumed therein (e.g. the building leases, where the cost of their energy upgrade burdens the owner but the benefit from the energy savings is attributed to the lessee (YPEKA, 2014).
Insufficient budget for integrated energy efficiency plans	<p>For the programme EXOIKONOMO the available budget was considered as insufficient for the target groups (ie municipalities) in order to implement an integrated energy efficiency plan covering the total needs of municipalities (Remaco SA, 2010). Proposals for overcoming this barrier include the institutionalization of energy services contracts and third party financing (Remaco SA, 2010).</p>
Ignoring the Cost-Benefit ratio	<p>For any contractual work in the public sector, particularly for municipalities and the new Directive for nearly zero energy consumption, the call is assigned based on the lowest offered price without taking into consideration any outcome of a cost-benefit analysis (an index or a ratio) (CERTus, 2015). This selection criterion is not imposed by the legislation, so in practice an offer that does not provide the lowest price will be hardly approved (CERTus, 2015). This situation does not facilitate the promotion of renovations for nearly zero energy consumption, which might require a larger budget (for purchase and installation capital), but are more profitable when their economic assessment takes into account the cost of the entire life cycle of the interventions of the renovation (CERTus, 2015). The regulation concerning the definition of the nearly zero energy consumption, is expected to change the way of assigning these projects and to introduce provisions for energy savings and the payback period. The same requirements need to be adopted for the "Green Public Supplies/Procurements", which are up to now optional and are not a priority for municipalities (CERTus, 2015).</p>
Selecting actions with short payback periods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually, the municipalities prefer investments with a payback period up to five years since their financial planning coincides with their tenure of local administration which is five years. In any case they avoid making investments with a payback period more than 10 years (CERTus, 2015). EE investment with long payback periods (more than 10 years), are characterized as unattractive (INTERREG IVC, 2014). • Some of the energy efficiency options are considered rather expensive or have high payback periods making them of no practical interest from the point of market acceptability, particularly without any financial support, subsidies or other financial instruments (Droutsas K.G. et al., 2014). • For public schools also scholars identified preference of the school administration for EE

	<p>interventions (replacement of oil boilers with natural gas ones, thermal insulation of the hot water distribution pipes in the older buildings) that were cost effective and with very small payback periods (Dascalaki G. E., Sermpetzoglou G. V., 2011).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owners of buildings that rent their offices/apartments do not proceed with EE interventions such as double glazing windows due to the increased capital cost (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012). On the other hand, tenants are discouraged to undertake such actions, due to the long payback period and the fact that it is not possible to remove it when leaving the property (as with an electrical heater or an air-conditioning device) (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012). • The payback period of energy efficiency interventions are usually quite great (YPEKA, 2014).
Reduced budget for functional expenses due to EE	Public buildings receive money for their functional expenses depending on the respective costs of the previous year. This is done by the Treasury of the State. If the costs of a building are reduced due to EE actions then it will receive a reduced budget and the payback to the company of the energy services with which they cooperate is not secured (CERTus, 2015).
Negative Return of Investment for EE projects	A financial analysis for grants that were provided in the context of ‘EXOIKONOMO’ showed that they were critical for financing energy efficiency interventions for a municipality (Patlitzianas D. K., Kolybiris C., 2011). On the other hand, though, the cash flow forecasts showed that energy savings are not sufficient to pay back the overall investment while ROI was negative (Patlitzianas D. K., Kolybiris C., 2011). It is mentionable that when the investment was appraised in the context of Municipality’s own contribution, then the cash flow was sufficient to repay debt and the return on investment was positive, but there was great risk involved, since cash flows included savings that were questionable (Patlitzianas D. K., Kolybiris C., 2011).
Difficult access to finance (hotels)	The majority of hotels have difficulty in getting finance for any types of investments (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Due to their poor credit ratings, small- and medium- size hotels often face more costly loans than the large or chain hotels (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). So, easier access to finance at viable interest rates is needed for most hotels so as to implement EE and RES technology investments (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). A solution could be the development of innovative financial packages, with low interest loans and/or performance guarantees so as to overcome investment barriers for in EE and RES by hotels (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).
Financial burden for implementation	Significant management fees of the European Investment Bank led to the renegotiation of the financing agreement with commercial banks under the JESSICA initiative (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). The management fee was reduced to 1,2%, from the initially planned 1,9% (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012). It is possible this high management fee to be transferred to SMEs (final beneficiaries), making the use of Financial Engineering Instruments expensive (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).
Decommitment of funds	“Automatic decommitments” are most probable to happen for the JESSICA initiative in Greece since: i) negotiations with the EIB lasted longer than expected; ii) the operation of the schemes coincided with low liquidity in the banking sector and a serious credit crunch of the market. A possible decommitment of funds in specific Operational Programmes even before the end of the programme could help normalise the allocation of funds (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).
Absence of incentive measures for buyers	Contractors have a negative attitude towards the adoption of energy efficient technologies or practices such as the bioclimatic architecture (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). This is because of the higher total cost of the building due to the use of more expensive building materials and the installation of passive energy systems (Karkanias C., et al., 2010). The higher the construction cost the smaller is the selling profit of the contractor (Karkanias C., 2010). The profit from designing and constructing a conventional building is more quickly achievable and reaches up to 160% of the construction cost, while that from bioclimatic buildings is much smaller (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). So, the proportion of customers willing to invest in bioclimatic buildings is smaller than those selecting conventional ones (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). The absence of incentives for being bioclimatic buildings is a barrier (Karkanias C.,

2010).

Table 6 : Main institutional barriers in the building sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of legislation for modern EE technologies and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of relevant legislation for the past 30 years caused failure of modern technologies integration at the buildings, leading to problems, such as (YPEKA, 2010): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ partial or total lack of insulation; ○ obsolete frames; ○ lack of sun protection of the southern and western sides; ○ insufficient use of the high solar potential of the country; ○ inadequate maintenance of heating / air-conditioning resulting to poor performance. ● Greece has not yet defined the levels of nearly zero energy consumption according to the most recent Directive for EE (CERTus, 2015). There is also still no defined national standard for conducting adequate and confirmed measurements regarding actual energy consumption in buildings (YPEKA, 2014).
Low state support	State support for energy renovations and renewable heating and cooling systems appears to be lower in Greece than in similar south European countries (Italy and Spain) (ENTRANZE, 2014).
Complex and difficult legislation and procedures	Legislation and procedures concerning energy efficiency in buildings (i.e. in nZEB) are complexed and difficult to be understood by the public, due to lack of disseminated information (ENTRANZE, 2014). In addition, legislation on Energy Efficiency of the building stock is relatively recent - entered into force in 2010 - while during the last years, there were numerous amendments to existing legislation, accompanied by a considerable number of ministerial decisions and circulars (YPEKA, 2014).
Tenure status	Greece has a very large tenure quota, mainly for apartments, which can influence the implementation of retrofit measures to great extents (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). As aforementioned due to multiple ownerships there is low implementation or even rejection of energy refurbishment measures (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Unlike in the case of the Energy Building Certificate, the owners of multi-family building apartment are not legally bind to implement any kind of retrofit measures (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). So, if such interventions can be implemented partially, i.e. the retrospective thermal insulation of flat roofs or the pilotis floor, then the concerned party/owner can act on its will (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). But when the retrofitting measures concern the whole building, the legal framework is not as clear as expected allowing the following options (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012): i) according to the statute the respective works are in forced or simple majority could be demanded, ii) if one or more owners disagree to contribute to the respective costs, then the legal procedure for the “res judicata” could last even up to 3 years. Consequently, many owners avoid investing in energy upgrade related works. This situation is attributed to the respective legal framework which goes back to 1929 with the Regulation on the “horizontal property” (No.3741/ 1929), regarding terms of jointly owned and shared parts of the building. So there is a need to revise this legal framework. Another option would be to cofigurate the property pricing according to the energy performance characteristics, under a specific legal framework (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).
Lack of central coordination	A separate Ministry of Environment did not exist in Hellas until October 2009. This underlines the absence of focused and dedicated environmental planning by the state (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).
Inadequate implementation of policy instruments	There have been problems with the terms of Law 3661/2008 (Karkanias et al., 2010). More specifically about the adoption and implementation of standards, guidelines, and calculations’ procedures according to the Hellenic framework since the European directive leaves to each Member States the initiative to elaborate and apply those, with regard to local conditions (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). The Hellenic state needs to persist and overview the implementation of the standards in practice and not rely solely on the contractors’ consciousness and/ or good intentions (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Furthermore, the notion of

	<p>bioclimatic design in buildings must be clarified by details and characteristics of the minimum energy and environmental performance that a building has to achieve, so as to be classified as bioclimatic (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). More particularly, the Hellenic state must establish a mechanism to audit and verify certain levels of performance in design and construction phases (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). It is necessary to check if a building that received certification for its energy performance fulfils indeed all relevant requirements after the completion of its construction. This is a process that has not been carried out until now (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Public authorities must be reorganised for carrying out such inspections, or assign the audits to private auditors and verify the overall process (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). This solution has been foreseen by the EPBD and Law 3661/2008. This attitude indicates the lack of confidence in the function of auditors who are not civil servants. Another solution could be a targeted plan by the state to invest in the vocational training of engineers as auditors (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).</p>
Lack of urban and land planning	<p>Due to the lack of urban and land planning during the last 30 years in Hellas, the vast majority of new buildings has been constructed in a very dense and clustered urban space (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). The implementation of bioclimatic architecture is difficult since there is lack of wide streets, big sites, and exposed facades, limiting therefore the utilization of sun (Karnanias C. et al., 2010). Vertical tall buildings with narrow vents along the floors, without any thermal insulation in their walls and roofs and with very few features of traditional Hellenic architecture, dominated the decades of 1960s and 1970s (Karkanias C., et al., 2010). These buildings generated serious operational problems such as insufficient lighting and poor ventilation, besides their very high energy consumption and the resulting operational expenses (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).</p>
Hindering management of funds	<p>Municipalities face serious difficulties in having a successful participation in initiatives financing sustainable energy developments (e.g. SAVE or EXOIKONOMO) (Christoforidis et al., 2013). This failure is attributed to the fact that a part of the investments' funds is covered by the government and not by the municipalities themselves (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).</p>
Lack of experience and resources to implement the policy instrument	<p>Although the Covenant of Mayors is simple, it is also a mechanism for municipalities, for which they did not have the required experience (Christoforidis et al., 2013). Researchers have quoted the inability of rural Greek communities to construct suitable SEAPs, since they do not possess adequate capacity, in terms of necessary financial and/or human resources (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Furthermore, they insist that support is needed in order for such communities to construct action plans and monitor SEAP's implementation. Without the experience and the resources Greek cities face a difficult task in reducing energy consumption due to their complexity and thus precise tools are needed (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013), (YPEKA, 2014).</p>
Low information and problematic communication among higher and lower levels of administration and communities	<p>Mayors adopted the Covenant of Mayors during their election period, but afterwards they proved to be unfamiliar with the existing financial instruments for introducing the SEAP and the energy efficiency actions as well (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Additionally, the majority of municipalities' employees, along with citizens, were not informed about their mayor's initiative to sign the Covenant (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). This situation resulted to substantially low support to the preparation of SEAP from the employees, while the communities themselves had limited or even no information about the covenant of mayors and its possible benefits for their region (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Consequently, communities could not pressure the municipality administration to take action towards the SEAP and to EE also (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).</p>
Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division	<p>Due to the "Kallikrates plan", set into force in 2011, a major restructuring and reforming of the Greek municipalities took place, aiming to reduce the costs of the central government by at least 1.5 billion € by 2013 (Law 3852 of year 2010; Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). The expected transition to the new type of municipalities under this plan was not smooth. The problems that emerged were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mayors felt reluctant to assign responsibilities to employees for the SEAP preparation and implementation, because of the uncertainty of what would actually happen after the application of the new scheme (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most municipalities were not in a position to construct suitable organizational and work plans, for the preparation of the inventories and the SEAPs since they were not guided by a suitable supporting structure (Christoforidis et al., 2013). The work was often assigned to external consultants/companies that faced difficulties in communicating with municipality departments (ie technical services and the public relations departments) (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). • This situation resulted in a non-efficient procedure that was reflected on the number of signatories actually constructing a SEAP (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).
Lack of data/information –diversion of management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the considerable barriers in studying the energy performance and adopting energy efficiency technologies and practices accordingly in public buildings and particularly in schools is the lack of data and the diversion of management. The collection of data concerning actual energy consumption of school buildings is a difficult task (Dimoudi A., Kostarela P., 2009). This is attributed to the following: i) The heating energy expenses are covered by the school budget which is under the authority of the school committees. These committees usually change annually and in many cases do not keep records of the expenses (Dimoudi A., Kostarela P., 2009). ii) Electricity expenses are covered by the municipality (Dimoudi A., Kostarela P., 2009). The reported data in literature concern mainly school buildings in the Attiki area and there is a lack of data from cold regions of Greece (Dimoudi A., Kostarela P., 2009). • The lack of an established defined procedure or staff to monitor the energy consumption in municipality buildings, results in difficulties for the collection of energy data and any relevant information (CERTus, 2015; ADVANCE, 2014). This often leads also to incomplete/lacking elements/data regarding the study for renovating the building. The problem is expected to be overcome with a legislative provision that will be published soon from the Central Government and will concern the appointment of an energy manager in municipalities (CERTus, 2015). • The users of the building have lacking or incomplete information regarding the energy performance of their building. So, they do not know how they themselves can affect the energy performance of the building (CERTus, 2015). • The level of detail of the available Hellenic data for residential buildings (system types, information on their state of modernization (refurbishment action, year)) is not sufficient enough to be used in relevant research studies such as deriving a building stock model (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011). Data was restricted to the insulation level (missing, partial or completely insulated) while heat generation systems are not reported in detail, neither domestic hot water nor space heating, while no time series data are available on heat distribution systems (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011). Most of the statistical data on the residential building sector come from the reports. The data gaps are attributed to the absence of systematic collection of the data (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011). • Hotel managers usually express interest to participate in the research surveys and fill in questionnaires, but they cannot provide energy data since they did not keep an organized record about their hotels' energy consumption (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). This behavior underestimates the value of energy monitoring and the implementation of sustainable policies (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015; Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).
Special building cases in the Greek building sector	<p>In Greece there are historic, traditional or cultural heritage buildings, where no changes in the facade are allowed (the refurbishment of such buildings (internal and external thermal insulation) as part of the energy efficiency policy if Greece need to follow specific rules). That is why external thermal insulation is often not allowed to be installed. The internal insulation does not interfere with the facade, has significantly lower costs, provides a solution for adjacent buildings, where no space for external insulation is available, or in cases when all occupants do not agree on the installation of the external insulation system. On the other hand, the internal system leads to a non-negligible loss of indoor space and is related to high risk of moisture condensation (Kolaitis D. I. et al., 2013).</p>
Bureaucracy for publicly funded projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The objective of the “Green Neighborhoods Programme” is the energy renovation of a low-income neighborhood in the broad area of Athens (Greece), with the participation

	<p>of unemployed inhabitants, recruited and trained as installers and maintainers of their building. One of the main barriers in the project implementation was the bureaucratic procedures that were foreseen for publicly funded projects (Request 2 Action project, 2012).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of bureaucracy was also mentioned in the case of the “Green Roofs” initiative (CRISP, 2012).
Inadequate implementation network/governance framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was not an appropriate structure to ensure that the proposed EE measures under the programme EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON were actually necessary for each building (Remaco SA, 2010). This was due to the fact that the country did not have – at that time - a legislative framework regarding energy audits and energy service companies (Remaco SA, 2010). • This barrier still remains since there are still inadequate Monitoring and Evaluation Processes for the energy efficiency policies (ADVANCE, 2014). • Due to the absence of an institute that could provide information about all available financing mechanisms for EE actions, some European policy initiatives and funds are not used adequately by the Hellenic stakeholders (ELENA²⁴, European Energy Efficiency Fund²⁵, JESSICA) (based on the work of WP1). • Financial instruments to be used for the SEAPs were not known to most cities administrations (Christoforidis et al., 2013).
Lack of legislation for positive policy interactions	<p>End-users such as hotels do not adopt energy efficiency technologies or practices due to the lack of any effective national legislative policies in the sector of tourism to supplement the existing instruments in the framework of the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol such as those for energy efficiency (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). This barrier in combination with the fact that energy efficiency is pursued on a voluntary basis, sets energy audits and surveys about reporting the building environmental performance of hotels as a necessary preface that will facilitate policymaking for EE (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015).</p>
Management of reporting	<p>The implementation of the JESSICA initiative in Greece faced management difficulties due to the strict reporting standards imposed by the European Investment Bank (EIB). The participating banks probably were not able to cover a sizeable amount of the standardised reporting requested by the EIB, due to the need of significant investments in information technology systems (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).</p>
Unclear procedures for energy service contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EE projects under the recent EU Directive that are worth a total amount of less than 5 million Euro, the current official procedures that are applied for the assignment of their construction works, create barriers for contracts concerning EE (CERTus, 2015). • As aforementioned the legal framework based on which the municipality could award a contract with a company of energy services is not clear /concrete. Although there is a provision in the law about the assignment of the study and construction of projects as a set, for the last five years this article of the law is not practically in force, since the Audit Committee (a body appointed by the Central Government) does not approve such contracts. This is due to a decision taken in 2009 as a correction measure against practices resulting to reduced quality of the construction (CERTus, 2015).
Lack of pertinent authorities for building/apartment owners	<p>In Greece there is not an institution/authority for the block apartments such as Housing Associations” which undertakes the role of an authority to plan and implement energy efficiency measures in buildings under the EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON programme (Remaco SA, 2010; CERTus, 2015). The only administration body is the General Assembly of each block of apartments which consists of the owners of the apartments (Remaco SA, 2010). However, it is very difficult, especially in multi apartment buildings for the owners to reach an agreement about the necessity of such interventions and the cost burden (Remaco SA, 2010).</p>

²⁴ <http://www.eib.org/products/advising/elena/index.htm>

²⁵ <http://www.eeef.eu/objective-of-the-fund.html>

Time delays	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were delays up to 6 months in issuing the appropriate building permits as these are required by national law for proceeding with building interventions under the EXOIKONOMO KAT OIKON programme (Remaco SA, 2010). These delays were expected to be due to the radically increased volume of applications once the initiative was implemented (Remaco SA, 2010). • Greece has not yet defined the different levels of nearly zero energy consumption based on the different use of buildings (CERTus, 2015). According to the new Direction of Energy Policy and Performance of the Ministry for Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy²⁶ (old name Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change), the respective regulation is expected to be published by the end of 2015 (CERTus, 2015). It is also expected that for the existing buildings, with exemption of the governmental buildings, the levels of nearly zero energy consumption are not going to be mandatory unless radical renovations are made (CERTus, 2015). • There are time delays in updating the necessary documents for the implementation of the respective legislation. More specifically, for the new Directive about the nearly zero energy consumption the Legislation foresees that the tariffication for study and construction of any type of intervention in public buildings needs to be done according to the Analytical Tariffication of Constructural Works (ATCW) which differs significantly from the actual market prices) (CERTus, 2015). This occurs because the update of catalogues for material and works does not happen on regular basis. The last update of the ATCW took place in 2007 (CERTus, 2015). Therefore the list of the Analytical Tariffication of Constructural Works does not include the innovative systems and materials that have been developed lately. This creates problems regarding the description and costing of the works for a project. So, it is important to re-examine the update procedure of the ATCW for considering the market developments and the correct prices. Then the ATCW will become more flexible and adjustable to the market changes (CERTus, 2015).
Interior arrangements in public buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are difficulties in planning a renovation due to frequent changes in the configuration of interior spaces. This happens often to public buildings (CERTus, 2015). Changes in interior arrangement happen often in such buildings due to the addition of services or the re-allocation of duties. Both reasons depend highly on the decisions of the new management (new Municipality board, Mayor) (CERTus, 2015). • Large scale renovation creates difficulties in the management of employees and offered services (CERTus, 2015). In any case, there is a need to secure the smooth function of the municipality services during the renovation. There is no possibility to transfer the employees to another building and therefore the only solution is the gradual (step-by step) renovation of the building (CERTus, 2015).
Administrative burden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is difficult and time consuming for the municipality services to monitor and to be consistent with the legislation (for energy efficiency and particularly for the forthcoming new Directive concerning the nearly zero energy consumption)(CERTus, 2015). Particularly for public buildings there are numerous legislative and regulatory provisions that determine the procedure to conclude in study contracts and / or construction renovation projects. Any specific change in legislation affects the whole procedure for study and leads to its continuous review (CERTus, 2015). • Apart from the defined procedure of assigning a contract (under the new Directive about the nearly zero energy consumption), there is legislation that describes the payment procedure (ie registration at the budget, credit commitment, decision of undertaking, etc). This procedure is very complicated and time consuming resulting to delays of payments and consequently to delay of works (CERTus, 2015). • The technical service is obliged for the approval of any renovation study or work to follow a difficult and time-consuming process (CERTus, 2015). The difficulties come from mainly the pertinent authorities of the regional and central government (such as

²⁶ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=230&language=el-GR>

	<p>Ministries, Decentralised Administration of Attica, etc.) (CERTus, 2015). This lengthy process often involves the risk of non-implementation of interventions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in issuing the appropriate building permits required by national law for undertaking building interventions (CERTus, 2015).
Reluctance for PPP	<p>Even if the Law "PPP" provides the legal framework for cooperation between public sector and private companies for energy services (regarding big projects), the municipality management claims that there have to be clear examples of actual projects for which the contracts of energy performance with companies for energy services have been implemented successfully. The municipalities would not want to act as pioneers for the award of specific contracts (CERTus, 2015).</p>
Low prioritization of EE	<p>The EE improvement of municipality buildings is not included in the priorities of the technical services of the municipality (CERTus, 2015). The technical service of the municipality decides to have the building renovation only when there are serious static problems. For any other renovation of up-grading the service can make proposals, but these need to be evaluated by an independent institute, regarding their effectiveness as a mid-term investment of the municipality (CERTus, 2015).</p> <p>According to the employees of a municipality, the financing of the projects that do not improve the daily life of citizens are not a priority for municipalities. The fact that citizens are not informed regarding costs/benefits from EE in public buildings set these possible investments to low priority (CERTus, 2015).</p>

The identified barriers were assessed taking into consideration the following criteria:

- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

For the Hellenic case, this approach was more suitable given the extremely limited quantitative information that was available for the quoted barriers. Justifications for the assessment are presented in the table below.

Table 7: Assessment of barriers in the building sector.

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Financial crisis
	Low level of awareness
	Lack of expertise - Incomplete training
	Selecting actions with short payback periods
	Lack of data/information –diversion of management
	Inadequate implementation network/governance framework
Medium	Zero to low availability of information
	Shared ownership (multilateral ownership)
	Lack of urban and land planning
	Lack of experience and resources to implement the policy instrument
	Lack of environmental consciousness, awareness and culture
	Reluctance to pay up front great amount of money for an investment with future returns
	Information barrier towards emerging innovative technologies
	Working habits
	Unwillingness to do more than minimum requirements
	Poorly developed market for energy services
	Costly innovative technologies for end-users
	Insufficient budget for integrated energy efficiency plans

	Ignoring the Cost-Benefit ratio
	Lack of legislation for modern EE technologies and practices
	Low state support
	Complex and difficult legislation and procedures
	Tenure status
	Inadequate implementation of policy instruments
	Low information and problematic communication among higher and lower levels of administration and communities
	Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division
	Bureaucracy for publicly funded projects
	Lack of pertinent authorities for building/apartment owners
	Time delays
	Administrative burden
	Low prioritization of EE
Low	Variable ownership structure, age and condition of the existing building stock (social)
	Lack of local social support
	Wrong use of information and communication of local scale governments
	Problematic cooperation among parties
	South European occupant behavior towards shading
	Established perception (hotels)
	Confusion and misuse of terms
	Higher consumption of oil than gas (habit)
	Diverse socio-economic background in plenty multi-family buildings in Greece
	End-users aloofness due to negative past experience
	Negative public perception
	Market failure to understand financial and social benefits
	Restricted interest of financial institutes towards NZEB
	Status of economic situation
	Higher income, higher energy consumption
	Cost distribution of central heating systems that favored the occupants of penthouses
	Reduced budget for functional expenses due to EE
	Negative Return of Investment for EE projects
	Difficult access to finance (hotels)
	Decommitment of funds
	Absence of incentive measures for buyers
	Lack of central coordination
	Hindering management of funds
	Special building cases in the Greek building sector
	Lack of legislation for positive policy interactions
	Unclear procedures for energy service contracts
	Interior arrangements in public buildings
	Reluctance for PPP
	Financial burden for implementation
	Management of reporting
Limitation in selected EE technologies	

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Trends in the sector

In Greece during the previous decade the ownership of passenger cars increased due to the economic development and the improved living standards. This resulted to a tripled number of the passenger cars fleet compared to that of the 1990 levels, but also to increase in 2008 of the share of medium passenger vehicles by 27% and of the larger size ones by 36% compared again to the year 1990 (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Similar trends were recorded as well for the number of trucks, buses and motorcycles (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

Due to the economic crisis this trend is decelerating, even though the percentage of car ownership in Greece is lower than the EU average (Table 8). Additionally, the reduced trend will be retained due to the high taxation imposed on vehicles with engines over 2.000cm³ (in 2011, the share of of passenger cars with an engine capacity greater than 1.400cm³ was 34%) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

Table 8: Stock of registered vehicles on land.

Stock of registered vehicles	Year						
	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012
Passenger cars	1.736.000	2.205.000	3.195.000	4.303.000	5.217.000	5.204.000	5.168.000
Buses & Coaches	21.400	24.600	27.000	26.800	27.300	27.100	27.000
Goods vehicles	766.400	883.800	1.057.400	1.186.500	1.318.800	1.321.300	1.318.900
Powered two wheelers	-	-	781.400	1.124.200	1.499.100	1.534.900	1.556.400

(Source: Eurostat, 2014).

Table 9: New registrations in Hellenic transport sector.

Years					
2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013
New vehicles registrations – Road passenger cars					
290.200	269.700	141.500	97.700	58.500	58.700
New motorcycles registrations					
64.000	83.100	61.500	44.700	31.800	

(Source: Eurostat, 2014).

Table 10: Passenger Transport volume on land in billion pkm.

Passenger transport volume (in Billion pkm)	Year						
	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012
Passenger cars	35,0	44,0	63,0	85,0	99,6	98,3	96,9
Buses & Coaches	17,7	20,2	21,7	21,7	21,1	21,2	21,1
Tram & Metro	0,8	0,7	1,2	1,5	1,7	1,7	1,7
Railways	2,0	1,6	1,9	1,9	1,3	1,0	0,8

(Source: Eurostat, 2014).

The aforementioned trends are reflected in the energy use of the sector. The energy use almost doubled during the time period 1980–1995 (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and

Climate Change, 2014). In 2011, the energy consumption for transportation accounted for 35,9% of the total final energy demand in Greece (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). The oil products dominate the final energy use with a share of more than 99,5% (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). There is gasoline consumption mainly by passenger cars, diesel oil for trucking, maritime transport and railroads; jet fuel for aircraft; and smaller amounts of LPG and diesel oil for taxis (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Railroads (until 1996) used exclusively small amounts of steam coal, electric buses (trolleys) and the metro that operate in the central Athens area use electricity (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014).

According to estimations there are approximately 45.000 businesses covering all sizes are activated in Greece and concern all transportation activities (in mainland – road and railway, air, sea, logistics included) (SEB, 2012). These types range from private – personal to multi-national ones. The activity is more intensive at the big urban centers. More specifically:

Shipping: There are about 1000 shipping companies with their headquarters located at Piraeus that support administratively a 20% share of the international shipping (SEB, 2012).

Aviation: According to Eurostat data in 2010, 315.815 flights, 32.623.657 passengers and 88.715 tons of merchandise and mail were recorded (SEB, 2012).

Mainland transportation: For year 2010, there was a reduction compared to data of year 2008, in road transportation (-18.1%), railway cargo transportation (-6,5%) and passenger (-16,5%) (SEB, 2012).

Table 11: Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector.

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Cruising traffic	Often in the two largest cities of Greece, Athens and Thessaloniki, vehicles are searching for a parking spot and this lasts on average 15 minutes (Saliara K., 2014). Even if the driver intended to make a more energy efficient use of the car, this situation prevails to do so.
Social-behavioral	Old habits	Concerning the habits of the Greek drivers, most of them have learned and used to drive inefficiently (ECOWILL project, 2010). Eco-driving was not part of their education as drivers. Their adopted way of driving is enhanced by the poor existing infrastructure such as high traffic jams in cities, bad condition and maintenance of certain roads and lack of special tracks for application of eco-driving trainings (ECOWILL project, 2010).
Social-behavioral	Wrong perception of people towards their capacities on eco-driving	Many old drivers have the perception that they are driving well enough, even in cases that this does not happen (ECOWILL project, 2010). The eco-driving was part of the education as drivers after 2010.
Educational	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving	Another barrier for the promotion of eco-driving was the lack of a network of certified driving instructors and examiners. The driving instructors and examiners were not obliged to know, teach in depth and examine the eco-driving techniques. It was also obvious that some driving instructors and examiners would have objected to the implementation of a potential eco-driving program with relevant testing and certification (ECOWILL project, 2010).
Educational	Low public awareness towards eco-driving	The public awareness of eco-driving is quite low (ECOWILL project, 2010). Probably the only recent introduction of eco-

		driving as part of the drivers education has not improved the situation.
Social-behavioral	Low environmental sensitivity	Environmental issues were not the main reason for changing transport mode - shift to more sustainable mobility modes (particularly to public transport) - according to Ad Personam project. The shift mostly appealed to career women for reasons like avoiding driving stress and money saving. The project Ad Personam intended to promote public transport through a Direct Marketing Programme (DMP). In seven (7) selected cities of European Union, all citizens were invited to fill in a questionnaire on their mobility choices/behavior (CRISP project, 2012).
Social-behavioral	Limited knowledge on public transport	Limited knowledge towards Public Transport information among citizens, such as routes, timetables and fares, was observed. This barrier – for supporting the shift to more sustainable mobility modes (public transport) - was observed generally for EU about public transport. A Greek city, Heraklion in Crete island, took part in the questionnaire delivery (Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010).
Social-behavioral	Citizens' preference of private cars due to convenience and affordable running costs	Citizens believe that the use of private cars is as favorable as public transport, concerning the running costs. Furthermore, their own private cars provide them with the turn-up and-go convenience. Consequently, lack of interest towards public transport mode was evidenced. This barrier – for supporting the shift to more sustainable mobility modes (public transport) - was observed generally for EU. A Greek city, Heraklion in Crete island, took part in the questionnaire delivery (Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010).
Social	Perception that owning and driving a private car shows the status symbol and good lifestyle	For many people owning and driving a private car represent a status symbol and good lifestyle, comfort and freedom. The aforementioned psychological and social-cultural factors are important when compared to technological and institutional factors. This represents a strong barrier towards radical change. Cultural-normative barriers, or social norms, can influence the successful implementation of initiatives towards sustainable mobility. Individual car use as a status symbol and the sign of a good life predominate in much of contemporary society. These are barriers in case of policies related to congestion charges and strategies towards collective use of mobility services and hinder the shift to more sustainable mobility modes (public transport). This is a general observation on mobility in Europe (CRISP, 2012).
Social	Low penetration of ICT from elderly people	Because of the relatively low penetration of ICT from elderly people in Greece they may not be able to use and accept easily the new means of transportation (CityMobil2, 2013).
Social	Disappointment for new transport systems	Sometimes, people's expectations over a new transport system – more environmentally friendly, energy efficient - might not be met if they expect a system that will run smoothly, at high speed and will solve more problems than those for which it was introduced (CityMobil2, 2013).
Social	Negative public perception towards electric vehicles	In Greece, one of the main barriers for the purchase of electric vehicles is the negative public perception. The consumers should be convinced that the electric vehicle is a robust technology and can meet their requirements (YPEKA, 2012).
Cultural	Lack of 'green transport	Citizens are not familiarized with the concept of a green

	behavior'	transport system and cannot adopt this or similar mobility initiatives at once (CityMobil2, 2013). There is also the lack of precedent (CityMobil2, 2013).
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Table 12: Main economic barriers in the transport sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Financial crisis	Although the Greek public generally declares in favor of eco-driving and recognizes its multiple benefits, the financial crisis in Greece, with consequent tax growth, income decrease and unemployment increase, led to reluctance on investments in eco-driving both in the private and public sectors. Due to increased expenses, especially in the private sector, even small investments are ignored without taking into consideration the long-term benefits of EE technologies and practices. Indicative example is that firms and/or individuals usually don't proceed to, even free-of-charge, eco-driving trainings for their employees (ECOWILL project, 2010).
Energy efficient solutions more expensive than conventional ones.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most important barrier in selling their EE products/services is the higher cost of such energy efficient solutions and – in the sectors construction and transport – frequently the tender documents ask explicitly for conventional solutions (EFFECT, 2012). • In Greece, one of the main barriers for the purchase of electric vehicles is the high initial investment costs (YPEKA, 2012).
Conflict of financial interest among different target groups	It is often to have conflicts between citizens and local shop owners (mostly cafes) located within a proposed route area that could lead to energy efficient improvement (shorter route, less time in bus, etc). The latter group usually complains to the local municipality that such a decision could harm their daily business because of the noise, the fewer people that will see or enter their shop or the street narrow width (CityMobil2, 2013).
Non-renewal of fleet and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Railway companies are using the same rolling stock for several decades, resulting to slow penetration of innovative, more sustainable rolling stock and technologies (TRAINER, 2010; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). • There is delay in modernization of the infrastructure, reflecting the lag in funding for such projects (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).
Unattractiveness of sector for investments	There are difficulties in attracting private investments for railway projects due to the existing poor infrastructure, the state funding for maintenance and to competitiveness of the other transportation means, mainly road transport (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).

Table 13: Main institutional barriers in the transport sector.

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Ineffective urban transportation planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ineffective and incapable mass-transportation system to displace car dominance and, to diminish congestion-related problems (Saliara K., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006). ● The majority of the public bus network in almost all Hellenic cities uses the same road infrastructure with the rest of traffic. This situation results to traffic delays and congestion (Gavanas N. et al., 2013). ● There is lack of parking control policy and of traffic management that could reduce congestion (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006) ● In Greece, one of the main barriers for the purchase of electric vehicles is the lack of charging infrastructure for the batteries (YPEKA, 2012).
Non-integrated policies	Transport planning, connectivity between the transportation means and urban/spatial development strategies are developed separately. There is no integration between them. This incompatibility is critical due to the landscape features of most Hellenic cities (Pitsiava-Latinopoulou M. et al., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).
Non-integrated energy efficient modal shifts in urban planning	Cycling and walking infrastructures need to be integrated so that in road arteries – located at local level (towns, suburbs)- there is decreased traffic volume (Milakis D. & Vafeiadis E., 2014). Any proposed cycle network needs to facilitate bicycle trips between the residential areas and the centre, serving as an additional feeder to the railway station (particularl for suburbs and close to Athens towns such as Agios Stefanos) (Milakis D. & Vafeiadis E., 2014). For serving local commuting and leisure trips, the cycle network needs to be designed and implemented by using separate cycle lanes parallel to main arteries (Milakis D. & Vafeiadis E., 2014). This separation is critical for the safety of cyclists particularly in a Greek traffic environment not familiarized with this rather new mode of transport (Milakis D. & Vafeiadis E., 2014). The development of cycling facilities in urban environments with low cycle use and non-developed cycle culture most probably will enforce citizens’ sense of being able to use bicycles for their mobility needs (Milakis D. & Vafeiadis E., 2014).
Lack of support schemes	There is no national support scheme for the purchase of electric vehicles, while: i) there is exemption for hybrid and low- emission vehicles from the registration tax and ii) there are no traffic restrictions in Athens for hybrid vehicles (source: Deliverable of Work Package 1).
Low prioritization of EE	Emphasis was given to the primary long term objectives of the transportation sector which concerned the development of the sector through the improvement of the quality of the offered services and of the basic infrastructure. Energy efficiency was included and managed as a secondary objective (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).
Overlap of responsibilities	More than one authority is responsible for the planning of the system of public transportation in the big urban centers. This is an issue that needs to be resolved and allow integrated urban planning (Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006).

The identified barriers were assessed taking into consideration the following criteria:

- a. The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- b. The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- c. The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- d. The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- e. The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

For the Hellenic case, this approach was more suitable given the extremely limited quantitative information that was available for the quoted barriers. Justifications for the assessment are presented in the table below.

Table 14: Assessment of barriers in the transport sector.

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Cruising traffic
	Wrong perception of people towards their capacities on eco-driving
	Energy efficient solutions more expensive than conventional ones.
	Old habits
	Non-renewal of fleet and infrastructure
	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving
	Ineffective urban transportation planning
	Low public awareness towards eco-driving
Medium	Financial crisis
	Limited knowledge on public transport
	Citizens' preference of private cars due to convenience and affordable running costs
	Perception that owning and driving a private car shows the status symbol and good lifestyle
	Unattractiveness of sector for investments
	Lack of support schemes
	Non-integrated policies
	Non-integrated energy efficient modal shifts in urban planning
Low	Low environmental sensitivity
	Low penetration of ICT from elderly people
	Disappointment for new transport systems
	Lack of 'green transport behaviour
	Conflict of financial interest among different target groups
	Negative public perception towards electric vehicles
	Low prioritization of EE
	Overlap of responsibilities

3. BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

Table 15: Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector.

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale (Local/Regional/National)	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Lack of local social support	Local	There is not a specific policy instrument that addresses this barrier. Since it concerns the Covenant of Mayors – SEAP, it is the responsibility of the local authorities to be more active and promote such efforts. Probably they need to adopt also actions that rely on their citizens activation.
	Wrong use of information and communication of local scale governments	Local	Again it concerns the Covenant of Mayors – SEAP. The engagement of urban actors – from both parts, ie citizens and officials is necessary.
	Shared ownership (multilateral ownership)	National	The National Grant Program/ EXOIKONOMO KATOIKON was addressing this barrier particularly for private households that were located at buildings constructed before 1980 (Deliverables of WP1, D.1.1 and D.1.2). However, it was only for specific interventions and for a limited number of households compared to the total number of buildings. Each owner could make the decision for his/her apartment.
	Lack of expertise - Incomplete training	Local/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier yet. The under public consultation Directive 2012/27/EU is expected to temper the extent of the barrier.
	Problematic cooperation among parties	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of environmental consciousness, awareness and culture	National	This is a barrier that concerns the National policy for energy efficiency as a total. No specific policy instrument is currently implemented to address the barrier.
	Low level of awareness	National	Similar as above barrier.

	Working habits	National	Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation in combination with older provisions from Law 3661/2008 and common Ministerial Decision 5825/9.4.2010) might improve the situation.
	Established perception (hotels)	National	Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.
	Confusion and misuse of terms	National	Same as above.
	Zero to low availability of information	National	This barrier was encountered for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) the Directives for nZEB and EPBD. Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.
	Variable ownership structure, age and condition of existing building stock	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	End-users aloofness due to negative past experience	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Diverse socio-economic background in the plenty multi-family buildings in Greece	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Negative public perception	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Reluctance to pay up front great amount of money for an investment with future returns	National	This is a barrier that concerns the National policy for energy efficiency as a total. It is expected to be managed by one of the basic elements of the EPBD the Energy Performance Certificates. EPCs are expected to promote energy efficient technologies through (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · classification of buildings to specific energy performance categories: In this way a higher energy class possibly will lead to a

			<p>higher rental or selling price of the building/apartment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · commendations included in EPCs about improving the energy performance of the building/apartment using cost-effective ways that will possibly enhance awareness of owners. · MEECC has introduced financial policy instruments such as grants, subsidies, tax exemptions for renovations and purchase of energy efficient appliances. The response was positive, but yet not satisfactory (Delivarables of WP1, D.1.1. and D.1.2).
	South European occupant behavior towards shading	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier (perhaps in an updated building code).
	Higher consumption of oil than gas (habit)	National	The provided financial incentives (subsidy) (replacement of oil heating systems with natural gas ones) that were secured by the end of year 2014, will confront the barrier (see Table 1 of this report).
	Limitation in selected EE technologies	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Information barrier towards emerging innovative technologies	National	This is a weakness of the national policy for energy efficiency (as a total). This situation is still not confronted, despite the dissemination-awareness policy instruments that have been implemented (EXOIKONOMO KATOIKON, ALLAZO KLIMA, GREEN ROOFS, JESSICA etc). Probably the lack of brochures or accessible information that describes in simple way the benefits of emerging innovative technologies is the core of the barrier.
	Unwillingness to do more than minimum requirements	National	The MEECC in an effort to ensure that at least the minimum requirements are indeed secured proceeded with the implementation of the Energy Performance Certificate

			(see Ministerial Decisions and Presidential Degrees of year 2010 (Table 1 of this report) (Deliverables of WP1, D.1.1, D.1.2). These efforts concern the building sector as a whole and not only the sub-sector of Hotels from which the barrier was mentioned.
Economic	Market failure to understand financial and social benefits	Local/National	No actions are undertaken (mainly under the Covenant of Mayors – SEAP for the Hellenic case).
	Restricted interest of financial institutes towards NZEBs	National	This barrier was identified in the cases of: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total); ii) the respective incorporated Directive (see Table 1 of this report). This is linked with the economic recession and any recommendations need to be part of an integrated policy planning.
	Financial crisis	National	Same as above (the following policy instruments are already affected and new planning is required: Covenant of Mayors – SEAP; Financial instruments; supporting mechanisms; subsidies; JESSICA initiative).
	Status of economic situation	National	Same as above.
	Higher income, higher energy consumption	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Poorly developed market for energy services	National	The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU includes relevant provisions that are expected to support ESCOs.
	Costly innovative technologies for end-users	National	This barrier was encountered for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) the Directives for nZEB and EPBD. Probably the incorporation of the Directive 2012/27/EU (EPBD) into the national legislation will improve the situation.
	Cost distribution of central heating systems that favored the occupants of penthouse	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier (perhaps in an updated building code).
	Absence of incentive measures for buyers	National	Currently, no policy instrument is addressing this barrier.

	Insufficient budget for integrated EE plans	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Ignoring the Cost-benefit ratio	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Selecting actions with short payback periods	National	This barrier is one of the most persistent ones. It has been identified during the implementation of the: i) national policy for energy efficiency (as a total); ii) the efforts for implementing the two most recent Directives (for NZEB and EPBD; iii) Covenant of Mayors - SEAP). The financial incentives (by grants, subsidies, tax exemptions for renovations – see Table 1 of this report) are a possible manner to handle the barrier, but new policy instruments are required.
	Reduced budget for functional expenses due to EE	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Negative Return of Investment for EE projects	Local/National	The barrier was mentioned for EXOIKONOMO (subsidies) which has been completed.
	Difficult access to finance (hotels)	National	So far, the financial incentives that were implemented concerned mainly private buildings – households. This was reasonable given the large share that is attributed to this sub-sector for: i) energy use and ii) number of buildings. The sub-sector of hotels is much smaller, but due to its energy use, additional policy instruments might be necessary in combination with policies of the tourism area.
	Decommitment of funds	Local/Regional/National	The barrier was encountered in two cases (National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and JESSICA Initiative). There are no proposed solutions.
	Financial burden for implementation	Local/Regional/National	This was encountered for the JESSICA Initiative. Involved parties need to cooperate and find solutions.
Institutional	Tenure status	National	It was a barrier for the Energy Building Certificate. After the public consultancy for Directive 2012/27/EU there may be relevant provisions in the new Law.

	Lack of urban and land planning	National	No proposals.
	Lack of experience and resources to implement the action plan/policy instrument	Local	No proposals.
	Hindering management of funds	Local	It concerned SAVE or EXOIKONOMO (subsidies/grants). Currently no policy instrument is addressing the barrier since the initiatives were completed.
	Lack of central coordination	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of data/information – diversion of management	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of legislation for modern EE technologies and practices	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of legislation for positive policy interactions	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Inadequate implementation network/governance framework	National	It was identified for: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) EXOIKONOMO (subsidies). No proposals so far.
	Unclear procedures for energy service contracts	National	It concerns mainly: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total) and ii) ESCO - The under public consultancy Directive 2012/27/EU includes relevant provisions that are expected to support ESCOs. The outcomes of the public consultancy may dictate relevant provisions.
	Low state support	Local/Regional/National	This barrier was identified in the cases of: i) National policy for energy efficiency (as a total); ii) the respective incorporated Directive (see Table 1 of this report). No policy instrument is addressing it.
	Complex and difficult legislation and procedures	Local/Regional/National	National policy for energy efficiency (as a total)
	Lack of pertinent authorities for building/apartment owners	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Time delays	National	This is a persistent barrier that has been identified in two

			cases: i) EXOIKONOMO (subsidies) and ii) incorporation of the new Directive about EPBD and energy standards. As aforementioned there was a second public consultancy for the second policy instrument. No actions are foreseen for this barrier.
	Interior arrangements in public buildings	National	The incorporation of Directive 2012/27/EU into the Hellenic legislation will secure the commitment that there will be an annual renovation for the 3% share of the total building surface for the buildings that belong to the State and have a total surface more than 500m ² (MEECC, 2014).
	Administrative burden	Local/ Regional/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Bureaucracy for publicly funded projects	Local/ Regional/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Inadequate implementation of policy instruments	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Reluctance for PPP	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Low prioritization of EE	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Low information and problematic communication among higher and lower levels of administration and communities	Local	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Special building cases in the Greek building sector	National	Municipalities in cooperation with the respective Ministries are planning specific actions for historical and traditional buildings in the big urban centers (Municipality of Athens, 2014).
	Change of legislation for local/regional administrative division	Local/Regional/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Management of reporting	Local/ Regional/National	This situation was encountered during the implementation of the JESSICA Initiative. It is a matter that the involved entities need to discuss and handle.

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

Table 16: Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector.

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers <i>(name the barrier)</i>	Scale <i>(Local/Regional/National)</i>	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments <i>(name the instrument)</i>
Social Cultural Educational	Cruising traffic	Local	This is a persistent barrier of local scale (big urban centers face it). It is not only a barrier for the national policy for energy efficiency, but also of the and transportation policy. Several efforts have been examined and applied that have restricted partially the problem. The Municipality of Athens is planning such actions (informative signs, Digital Athens etc) (Municipality of Athens, 2014).
	Low penetration of ICT from elderly people	Local/National	Local authorities are examining actions that will allow to large parts of the population to get familiarized with new communication technologies (Municipality of Athens, 2014).
	Disappointment for new transport systems	Local/national	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of 'green transport behavior'	Local/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier. Proposals from municipalities (zones for cycling and walking) might assist in improving the situation (Municipality of Athens).
	Old habits	Local/National	There are no provisions for old drivers in the legislation for eco-driving (Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)
	Wrong perception of people towards their	Local/National	There are no provisions for old drivers in the legislation for eco-driving

	capacities on eco-driving		(Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)
	Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving	Local/National	There are no provisions for instructors in the legislation for eco-driving (Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)
	Low public awareness towards eco-driving	Local/National	There are no relevant provisions in the legislation for eco-driving (Dissemination-Awareness and educational policy instrument)
	Negative public perception towards electric vehicles	National	No policy instrument is addressing specifically this barrier apart from the financial incentives that are mentioned (Table 1 of this report).
	Low environmental sensitivity	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Limited knowledge on public transport	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Citizens' preference of private cars due to convenience and affordable running costs	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Perception of status symbol and good lifestyle	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
Economic	Conflict of financial interest among different target groups	Local	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Financial crisis	National	This is linked with the economic recession and any recommendations need to be part of an integrated policy planning.
	Non-renewal of fleet and infrastructure	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Unattractiveness of sector for investments	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.

	Energy efficient solutions more expensive than conventional ones	National	Financial policy instruments (grants, tax exemptions for hybrid and electric vehicles) are foreseen (see Table 1 of this report) so as to moderate the impact of this barrier.
Institutional	Ineffective urban transportation planning	Local/National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Non-integrated policies	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Low prioritization of EE	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Overlap of responsibilities	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Lack of support schemes	National	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.
	Non-integrated of energy efficient modal shifts in urban planning	Local	No policy instrument is addressing this barrier.

4. KEY FINDINGS

The behavioral change of consumers can result in significant reduction of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions in the EU, both in the shorter and in the long term (Faber J., 2012). User behavior is influenced by economic, social and psychological factors that influence both the buying of equipment and the use of energy. Energy use is determined by information/awareness and energy costs, plus social, educational and cultural factors (WBCSD, 2008).

Consequently, there are barriers for the implementation of energy efficiency policy instruments and technologies that are related to the aforementioned factors. Mapping and analysis of such barriers for Greece led to the following key findings.

According to surveys in Greece, the factors that determine RES and Energy Efficiency knowledge among the different types of end users are: i) gender, ii) age, iii) education level, iv) occupation (studies, job, interests), and iv) environmental behavior (Karytsas S., Theodoropoulou H., 2014). Particularly, for the household sector, apart for the consumer's behavior, primary determinants for energy efficiency investments are the household income and the energy prices (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014).

Although the residential sector accounts for 24% of the total final energy consumption of the country of year 2013, the information and data about the attitude of consumers towards EE policy instruments, technologies and practices are limited (YPEKA, 2015). Most of the official reports, funded research projects and published research papers are addressing mainly two sectors, the public sector and the hotels. There are no available large-scale survey concerning behavior of the different Hellenic social groups towards energy efficiency policies and technologies.

On the other hand, for the transport sector, most references concerned barriers about attitudes towards eco-driving. There were no available surveys for end-users of rail, aviation or navigation. Additionally, most of the relevant implemented EE policy instruments are horizontal – they are not addressing the particularities of each transport mode separately.

The barriers for both sectors are observed on two different levels: national and local/regional. In the local/regional, the barriers were mostly linked with the initiative of Covenant of Mayors and the implementation of SEAPs (buildings, mobility) and concerned the local authorities.

Starting from the cross-cutting barriers – common barriers that were observed in both sectors – the most prominent ones are the financial crisis (economic barrier) and the ineffective urban, land and transportation planning (institutional barrier).

Due to the economic recession, the household income has been decreased, the financing entities have been reluctant to provide loans to private investors and there have been limited subsidies and state support for EE interventions (YPEKA 2014; Theodoridou I. et al., 2012; Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013). Consequently, the investments on energy efficiency practices and technologies were limited, especially those with long pay-back periods (CERTus, 2015; INTERREG IVC, 2014; Drousa K.G. et al., 2014; Dascalaki G. E., Sermpetzoglou G. V., 2011; Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012; YPEKA, 2014). On the other hand, the financial crisis contributed to the annual decrease of energy consumption for both sectors in the recent years. According to EUROSTAT database for Greece, both building and transport sectors consumed less energy after the years 2009-2010. Also, the Programme “Energy Efficiency in Households” (Exoikonomisi kat’oikon) enhanced significantly the construction and engineering sector (construction companies, engineers, ESCOs) – which is in a recession period due to financial crisis – not only on the level of employment, but also for the promotion of building material that contribute to the energy efficiency (YPEKA, 2014).

Due to the urban and land planning during the last 30 years in Greece, the vast majority of new buildings have been constructed in a very dense and clustered urban space and old buildings follow

the traditional Hellenic architecture, dominated the decades of 1960s and 1970s, making the implementation of bioclimatic architecture difficult (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Also, concerning the transport, the ineffective mass-transportation system that leads to congestion-related problems and the limited charging infrastructure for the batteries of electric vehicles hinder the implementation of energy efficiency practices and technologies (Saliara K., 2014; Ministry of Transportation and Communications, 2006; YPEKA, 2012).

Table 17: Assessed as big barriers for Hellenic building sector.

Barrier	Criteria				
	a	b	c	d	e
Selecting actions with short payback periods (Economic barrier)	At least 3 different types of policy instruments	6 references	2 subsectors	Moderate to overcome	More than 3 years
Financial crisis (Economic barrier)	At least 3 different types of policy instruments	4 references	Whole sector, one sector	Difficult to overcome	More than 3 years
Low level of awareness (Social – cultural – educational barrier)	At least 2 different types of policy instruments	4 references	2 subsectors	Difficult-Moderate	More than 3 years
Lack of expertise - Incomplete training (Social – cultural – educational barrier)	At least 2 different types of policy instruments	4 references	1 subsector	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years
Lack of data/information – diversion of management (Institutional barrier)	At least 1 policy instrument	5 references	3 subsectors	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years
Lack of legislation for modern EE technologies and practices (Institutional barrier)	At least 2 policy instruments	3 references	2 subsectors	Moderate	More than 5 years
Inadequate implementation network/governance framework (Institutional barrier)	At least 2 policy instruments	4 references	Whole sector, one sub-sector	Moderate	More than 5 years

Note: The criteria are on page 36 of this report and have the same weight. The scales per criterion were: for a from 1 to 3 policy instruments, for b from 1 to 6 references, for c from 1 to 3 sub sectors taking into consideration also if the reference mentioned the whole sector, for d from easy to difficult way to handle and for e from 1 to more than 5 years.

Particularly, for the building sector, the Greek society has not yet strongly endorsed energy conservation and sustainability (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). One reason is that negative public perception towards emerging innovative technologies has been evidenced since consumers are reluctant to use innovative EE technologies without actual successful examples (ENTRANZE, 2014; CRISP project, 2012). This barrier is encountered also among the hotel owners who believe that the

more energy they consume, the more comfortable their guests are (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Also, the implementation network is considered inadequate, mainly due to the limited training of the technical staff, the inadequate procedures for monitoring and evaluation and the administrative burden (Remaco SA, 2010; ADVANCE, 2014). This was observed both in the national level, and in the municipality level for the development and implementation of SEAPs (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). In order to overcome this barrier, there is an on-going attempt with relevant initiatives, programmes, and dissemination actions.

Table 18: Assessed as big barriers for Hellenic transportation sector.

Barrier	Criteria				
	a	b	c	d	e
Energy efficient solutions more expensive (Economic barrier)	At least one policy instrument	2 references	Whole sector	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years
Ineffective urban transportation planning (Institutional barrier)	At least one policy instrument	4 references	Whole sector	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years
Non-renewal of fleet and infrastructure (Institutional barrier)	At least one policy instrument	2 references	One sub sector	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years
Cruising traffic, Old habits, Wrong perception of people towards their capacities on eco-driving, Lack of certified instructors and examiners for eco-driving, Low public awareness towards eco-driving (5 social-cultural-educational barriers)	Ecodriving	2 references	One sub sector	Difficult-Moderate	More than 5 years

Note: The criteria are on page 43 of this report and have the same weight. The scales per criterion were: for a from 1 to 3 policy instruments, for b from 1 to 6 references, for c from 1 to 3 sub sectors taking into consideration also if the reference mentioned the whole sector, for d from easy to difficult way to handle and for e from 1 to more than 5 years.

Concerning the transport sector, most of the social- cultural-educational barriers are related with the perception that people have of owning and driving a vehicle. Particularly,

1. the eco-driving is hindered by the old habits (driving inefficiently) (ECOWILL project, 2010),
2. the promotion of public transport is hindered by the citizens' preference of private cars due to convenience and their perception that owning and driving a private car shows the status symbol and good lifestyle (Ad Personam project, 2009; 2010; CRISP, 2012),

3. the promotion of e-vehicles' use is hindered by the negative public perception that this technology is not robust yet (YPEKA, 2012).

Furthermore, concerning the penetration of electric vehicles in Greek market, there is lack of support schemes (economic barrier) for their purchase (YPEKA, 2012). The incentives are limited to tax exemptions and no traffic restrictions.

It is expected that the above barriers will be restricted by the transposition of the latest EU Directive²⁷ (Directive 2012/27/EU)²⁸ to the Hellenic legislation. The second public consultation on the relevant draft law ended on 1st July 2015 and, until now, the outcomes have not been published yet.

Finally, the recently implemented measures for the "capital controls" in the Greek banking sector (July 2015) in conjunction with the relevant austerity measures will further increase the barrier among the banking sector in providing loans, until the withdrawal of the measures and of the end-users who are becoming more reluctant to undertake the risk for a loan that is not considered by them as first priority.

²⁷ Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC Text with EEA relevance

²⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1399375464230&uri=CELEX:32012L0027>

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D.2.1 WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORTS

DATE 29 JUNE 2015

Partner: “*Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi*”

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National Report

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

ACI: Automobile Club d'Italia.

AEEG: Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water.

AMAT: Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente Territorio (Agency for Mobility Environment Territory).

ASSTRA: Associazione Trasporti (Transport Association).

CATI: Computer-assisted telephone interviewing.

CDP: Cassa Depositi Prestiti (Deposit and Loan Fund).

CENSIS: Centro Studi Investimenti Sociali.

CNR: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council).

D.I.: Decreto Interministeriale (Inter-ministerial Decree).

D.L.: Decreto Legge (Law Decree).

Dlgs: Decreto Legislativo (Legislative Decree).

D.M.: Decreto Ministeriale (Ministerial Decree).

D.P.R.: Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica (Decree of the President of the Republic).

EE: Energy Efficiency.

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development)

EPBD: Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

ESCO: Energy Service Company.

EU: European Union.

FIAB: Federazione Italiana Amici della Bicicletta (Italian Federation of Friends of the Bicycle).

GPP: Green Public Procurement.

GSE: Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (Energy Service Operator).

IEA: International Energy Agency.

ISFORT: Istituto Superiore di Formazione e Ricerca per i Trasporti (Institute for Education and Research on Transport).

ISTAT: Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (National Institute for Statistics).

ITS: Intelligent Transport System.

L.: National Law.

LEAP: Long range Energy Alternatives Planning System.

LED: Light-Emitting Diode.

LEED: Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design.

LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas.

MATTM: Italian Ministry for the Environment and the Protection of Land and Sea.

MISE: Italian Ministry of Economic Development.

MIT: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport.

NEEAP: National Energy Efficiency Action Plan

NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics.

PIDEE: Piano integrato di diffusione dell'efficienza energetica (Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency).

PNIRE: Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica (National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points).

PRT: Personal Rapid Transport

PUM: Piano Urbano della Mobilità (Urban mobility plan)

PUMS: Piano Urbano della Mobilità Sostenibile (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan).

RSE: Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Research on the Energy System).

R&D: Research and Development.

SEAP: Sustainable Energy Action Plan.

SUMP: Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan.

TEP: tonnellata equivalente di petrolio (tonnes of equivalent oil).

TOE: tonnes of equivalent oil.

WP: Work Package.

WWF: World Wildlife Fund.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

During the past decade, energy consumption in Italy remained stable at '90s' level, mainly because of the economic stagnation occurred in the recent years. The composition of energy consumption in 2013 shows that buildings and transport are two key sectors for Italy. In fact civil use represents 39% of energy consumption and transportation 30%. Regarding the efficiency trend, Italy assumes a relatively good rank in the European context. However, energy intensity increased both in the residential sector and non-residential sector and transportation showed modest efficiency gains, considering the 2000-2013 period.

After a brief overview of the main policy instruments in force in Italy to promote energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sectors and of the main potential energy efficiency technologies, the report maps through a literature review the main social, economic, cultural, educational and institutional barriers that currently characterize the Italian context, and that are limiting a further diffusion of energy efficiency in these two sectors. For buildings, both residential and commercial sub-sectors are analysed; for transport, both people and freight transport are considered. The barriers are qualitatively assessed based on the authors' evaluation. The report also puts the identified barriers in relation with policy instruments currently in force in Italy and highlights which policy instruments are contributing (or could possibly contribute) to overcome them.

Regarding the **building sector**, the analysis shows that efficiency performances in Italy can be considered relatively high with respect to other Member States. However, the achievement of further efficiency gains is strongly bounded to a variety of barriers affecting different actors involved and at different degrees. Main limitations in the building sector are:

- lack of a 'culture of saving' that limits, and sometimes neutralizes, the effect of policies aimed at boosting efficiency gains;
- old age of the existing building stocks and the great historical importance of such buildings which strongly limit the technical options for energy-efficiency renovations and retrofits;
- dyscrasia between the national/supra-national and local governance, Italy being characterized by a high regional fragmentation which produces insufficient policy coordination, uncertainty among actors involved as well as delays in policy implementation;
- lack of monitoring and controls which generate free-riding behaviours and other market failures;
- the issue of split incentives and principal-agent problem, which in Italy assumes relevant dimension given the high ownership fragmentation in the real-estate market (relevant presence of condominiums);
- economic stagnation, which limits the access to credit and the expenditure budget for energy efficiency investments, both for households and public administrations.

Besides these, behavioural and social issues (misperception of economic returns, different purchasing choice in presence of other people, limited trust in local and national public administration) and a lack of technical knowledge (both in households and in mediating subjects such as ESCo, building administrators etc.) further limit the adoption process of more efficient technologies.

The overview of barriers shows that further awareness raising and information provision to consumers, home-owners and building administrators are needed, to spread a culture of saving and to inform about benefits and opportunities of energy efficiency. Furthermore, economic instruments

or facilitating mechanisms to improve the access to available financial sources would be required. Also, action would be needed to address inefficiencies of bureaucracy and increase governance and policy coordination among the multiple administrative levels.

Regarding **transport**, the analysis shows that an inefficient use of energy is still present both in the people and freights transportation.

In relation to **public and private** transport sector, Italy is still a country where private mobility is prevalent, even if in some urban areas public transport services are well developed and contribute to reduce car use. The main barriers affecting the achievement of further efficiency gains in public and private transport sector are:

- Public transport supply in Italy is still limited in several Italian cities (with some remarkable exceptions), with significant problems in terms of quality and numbers of services. For many Italians, public transport is not reliable and attractive and for this reason they prefer not to use it;
- Soft mobility (bike and pedestrian) is less developed than in other European countries. This is strictly related both to cultural aspects and to the lack of adequate infrastructures in urban areas (bike and pedestrian pathways, etc.);
- Italy is one of the most motorised country in the world. Car is still a status symbol for a large part of population;
- In the last years, due to economic crisis and the national spending review process, several financial cuts were done to national funds dedicated to the regional and local public transport services. As local public transports are highly dependent from these resources (ordinary activities cover only a limited part of their annual budgets), these relevant cuts generate increasing difficulties in guaranteeing high public transport services levels;
- Innovative forms of private mobility (for example electric mobility, etc.) are not developed, as there is still a lack of adequate infrastructures (electric public recharge area in case of electric vehicles). Moreover it is important to highlight the importance given at national level to the promotion of biofuels and biomethane.

In relation to **freight** transport sector, the achievement of further efficiency gains is strongly bounded to a variety of barriers affecting mainly the logistic operators involved in national and urban freights delivery. Main limitations in the logistic sector are:

- Very competitive market, where it is difficult to set up forms of collaboration among the main logistic operators in order to reach more efficient solutions (sharing of vehicles and/or common usage of urban logistic platforms);
- Italy is affected by high delays in the main national and regional logistic infrastructures development and improvements (ports, inter-mobility nodes, etc.);
- Many competences in the urban transport regulation at urban level (access to city centres, etc.) are delegated to the municipal level without an adequate coordination at regional and national level. This aspect led to a high fragmentation of legislative frameworks that impede an efficient organization of logistic services and to create national business model usable in different cities;
- Italian logistic operators appear affected by significant problems in recruiting high-educated logistic manager and working forces. These education deficiencies limited their innovative capacity;

- All the previous barriers, together with a high bureaucracy level, create an economic framework where private investments (national and international) in the logistic sector are not perceived as attractive.

On one side, some barriers (promotion of green vehicles, bio fuels, ITS, coordination among different logistics operators) have been addressed by policy instruments in place. On the other side, other barriers, mainly related to the strengthening of people and freight transport infrastructures for more energy efficient and sustainable mobility received less attention in the Italian policies framework. Therefore investments to fill the gap of sustainable mobility infrastructures and services would be required, as well as information to consumers about the benefits and opportunities of sustainable mobility and to promote a more diffused culture of sustainable travel behaviours.

For the freight transport, beyond measures to address the infrastructural gap, also capacity building and coordination mechanisms for operators would be necessary, together with actions to address inefficiencies caused by bureaucracy.

INTRODUCTION

This report provides the contents of the national report for Italy, which seeks to identify country-specific barriers to energy efficiency policy.

The national report is structured as follows:

1. Context
2. Mapping country-specific barriers in the building sector at local, regional and national scales
 - Social
 - Cultural
 - Economic
 - Educational
 - Institutional
3. Mapping country-specific barriers in the transport sector at local, regional and national scales
 - Social
 - Cultural
 - Economic
 - Educational
 - Institutional
4. Linking country-specific barriers to policy instruments
5. Key findings

The material collected through this report will be used to inform deliverable D.2.1 'Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in building and transport'. The outcome of D.2.1 will be used in tasks WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country in WP2 will be considered in the development of the scenarios build in the LEAP software.

More specifically, WP2 will provide a qualitative assessment of the key barriers for each country (e.g. small impact, medium impact, big impact), as these will be presented in this report by each partner. This assessment will be based on the expert view of each partner. WP3 will then attempt to quantify the effect of these barriers in combination with the policy instruments that allow overcoming them. The research outcome of WP3 will be included in WP4.

1. CONTEXT

During the past decade, the energy consumption in Italy remained stable at '90s' level. The reason can be mainly attributable to the economic stagnation occurred in the recent years, which is still gripping the EU. However, the energy mix changed toward a cleaner and more sustainable energy system. While in 1997 oil adsorbed more than 50% of total demand, recently oil and gas contribute less than 35% of the primary energy demand, as renewable energy sources have grown, in the same period, more than 27% with a current relative contribution of around 20% in the Italian energy mix (ENEA, 2015). Overall, all the traditional energy sources have shown decreasing trend in contributing to the final energy demand. However, when compared to other 28 EU countries, Italy is still affected by some specific limitations such as the intensive use of natural gas, large energy dependence and absence of nuclear production. However, such limitations are compensated by a lower per-capita energy demand with respect to other EU countries (2,63 toe/inhabitant) and a decreasing consumption trend. Sectoral analysis (1997-2013) shows that, with the exception of commercial and residential building (+31,9%), all the other sectors (transportation, industry, agriculture) have followed a negative trend, while from 2012 to 2013 the negative consumption trend affected the energy demand as a whole. The composition of energy consumption, in 2013, appears to be composed by civil use (39%), transportation (30%), industry (22%), agriculture (2%) and other uses (7%). Regarding the efficiency trend, Italy assumes a relatively good rank in the European context (-17,2% with respect to EU-28 mean, -14,2% with respect to the Euro Zone in the 2000-2013 period). In this respect, it is worth noting that from the introduction of White Certificates in 2005, energy intensity decreased by 7,9%. Manufacturing industry also showed decreasing energy intensity, with a reduction of 31,5%. On the other hand, energy intensity in the residential sector raised both in total energy mix (+25,1%) as well as specifically in electricity (+12.8%) considering the 2000-2013 period, although the presence of seasonal trend due to winter months. Increasing energy intensity also characterized non-residential sector (+50% in electricity, +32% in energy as a whole), which confirms its dominant role in the civil sector. Transportation showed modest efficiency gains, also because of the EU interventions to boosting environmental-friendly mobility. Overall, the ODEX index shows, in the case of Italy, a constant trend equals to 86,6% of total efficiency (100%). If decomposed over time, the annual ODEX rate was higher in the 2004-2009 period (1,5%) than the one registered over the entire period 1990-2013 (0,5%) (ENEA, 2015).

1.1 BUILDINGS SECTOR

According to the latest available data (ENEA, 2015), in the 2012-2013 period the residential consumption pattern appears to be stable (-0,4%). However, long run data (Figure 1) highlights a slight increase in energy consumption, with a relevant change in the energy mix occurred in recent years.

Figure 1 - Energy consumption in building by fuel (Mtoe), 1992-2013

Source: ENEA, 2015

In particular, wood consumption grew dramatically because of the biomass systems, which showed better economic performances compared to natural gas systems, particularly in mountain provinces. Renovations of principal and secondary dwellings have been catalysts for such a technology turnover. However, the non-decreasing trend of natural gas is due to the enlargement of the existent gas network, especially in southern Italy. Consumption for conditioning and heating adsorbs around 76% of total residential consumption, with a growing trend in the recent years. On the contrary, constant trends have been detected for cooking, water heating and lighting (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Energy consumption in building by use (toe/dwelling) 2001-2013

Source:

ENEA, 2015.

Differing from the residential, the non-residential sector (commercial buildings, public administration) has shown an increasing trend in electricity consumption, with a limited slow down due to the economic crisis and a ratio consumption/employee almost doubled in the last twenty years (Figure 3).

Concerning the stock of buildings, Italy has shown a slightly increasing trend. In 2013, the number of total existing buildings is estimated to 14.515.795, with a growth of 13,1% with respect to 2001 (ISTAT, 2014a). Residential buildings account for 84,3% of total stock, of which 51,8% consists in single dwellings. The growth of residential buildings has been of 8,6% in the 2001-2011 period. The stock of non-residential buildings appears composed as follows: buildings devoted to manufacturing production (18,9%), commercial activities (16,2%), services (11,7%) and tourism (4%). At spatial level (Figure 4), the growth of buildings from 2001 to 2011 appears to be concentrated in central and

northern areas, while the southern region, characterized by lower residential energy consumption due to higher temperatures and moderate precipitation levels, shows very little variation.

Figure 3 - Electricity consumption in non-residential buildings (index numb. 1995=100), 1995-2013

Source: ENEA, 2015

Figure 4 - Change of building stock 2001-2011, by province

Source: ISTAT, 2014a.

1.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

Energy consumption in the transport sector is characterized by a rather constant trend, with little variation in the most recent years, although maintaining a long-run constant share in the final energy consumption (30%). In 2012, the last available year, maritime and road transport showed the most relevant reduction (-11% and -10%, respectively), followed by aviation (-5%) and trains (-3%). However, road transport represents the lion’s share of transport sector in Italy (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Final energy consumption in transport sector, by type (Mtoe) 2005-2012.

Source: ENEA, 2015

The energy mix in the transport sector is dominated by fossil fuels (95%) and petroleum products, even though the share shows little negative and constant change. By looking at the longer-run trend (2000-2013), passenger and freight transportation sectors have shown efficiency gains. In particular, fleet turnover, increased load factor as well as intensification of daily trips, have concurred to positive efficiency performances. In the case of aviation, the reasons of such gains can be also due to the competition with the high-speed railway system, which has induced aviation companies to modify their tariff schemes and service supply. On the other hand, road transport has not shown the same efficiency trend, although the intensification of the government’s intervention aimed at incentivizing the turnover of the existing vehicle stock with a more efficient one. This can be determined by the economic crisis, which has limited the expenditure capacity. Besides this, per-vehicle load factors remained constant over years. With respect to the freight transport system, efficiency gains derived from the increase of coastal navigation (*cabotaggio*), by the growth of load factors due to the higher competition in maritime transport sector as well as by higher fuel prices, which contributed to largely reduce energy consumption, in particular in the 2005-2012 period (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Energy consumption trend in transport sector, by type (goe/Tkm) 2005-2012

Source: ENEA, 2015

1.3 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Italy has developed a large set of policies and tools in order to promote and strengthen energy efficiency both in buildings and transport sectors.

In the **building sector**, the regulatory policy framework is compliant with the main EU directives on the theme (EPBD, EPBD recast and Energy Efficiency Directive). There have been some delays in the transposition of these directives into the Italian legislative framework, but to date the transposition has been completed. Also economic policy instruments are well developed, covering the needs of both public and private sectors buildings. One of the most significant economic instrument adopted for promoting energy efficiency is the White Certificates scheme, mainly targeting industrial and commercial buildings. Other important Italian economic policy instruments for promoting energy efficiency in buildings are the “Thermal Account” (targeting public authorities), tax deductions (targeting private buildings and families) and the “National Energy Fund for Energy Efficiency” to strengthen the investments in the sector. Several dissemination and awareness policy instruments have been launched during the years. In Italian buildings energy efficiency policy schemes, a very important role is played by regional and local authorities, as several competencies (such as energy certification of buildings, etc.) have been transferred by central authorities to regional and local authorities.

Several **actors** are involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of the buildings energy efficiency policy instruments. A crucial role is played by national ministries (Ministry of the Environment and Protection of Land and Sea, Ministry of Economy and Finance, Ministry of Economic Development and Ministry for Regional Affairs) supported by national technical organizations like ENEA (Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development), CNR (National Research Council) and RSE (Research on the Energy System)¹. Regional authorities also play important roles, since they hold the legislative powers and the administrative competences regarding the energy certification of buildings. Also municipalities can develop and implement several policy instruments, such as building regulations and local planning instruments, influencing energy efficiency of buildings in their territorial areas. Furthermore, municipalities develop voluntary local Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) within the Covenant of Mayors initiative, which systematize several policies and measures regarding energy use in buildings at local level².

In order to involve all the different actors at national and regional level as well as private actors interested in energy efficiency, a national ‘energy efficiency control room’ was settled in 2014 by the Ministry of Economic Development.

Table A displays the most relevant policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector currently in force in Italy:

¹ Company financed by the Italian Electricity System Research Fund (Fondo per la Ricerca di Sistema) of the Italian Economic Development Ministry conducting research in the energy field.

² In Italy, up to now, more than 3.100 municipalities have signed the Covenant of Mayors and more than 2.500 have developed a Sustainable Energy Action Plan (data: Covenant of Mayors website, visited on 15 July 2015 http://www.eumayors.eu/index_en.html)

Table A: Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector in Italy

Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the building sector in Italy	
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Energy performance in buildings. Transposition of EPBD and EPBD recast EU directives (Dlgs. 19 August 2005, n. 192, modified with Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115; L. 3 August 2013, n. 90); · Transposition of the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102); · Rules for implementing the national energy plan in the field of rational use of energy, energy saving and development of renewable energy sources (L. 9 January 1991, n. 10); · Regulation on Accreditation of Italian Energy Certifiers (D.P.R. 16 April 2013, n. 75); · Green Public Procurement. Minimum Environmental Criteria for several appliances related to buildings, in particular public lighting and energy services for buildings (D.M. 25 February 2011, D.M. 25 July 2011, D.M. 7 March 2012); · Energy labeling of households appliances (Dlgs. 28 June 2012, n. 104); · Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures (municipal level); · Regional Regulatory Schemes on energy efficiency in buildings (regional level); · Municipal buildings regulations (municipal level).
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Pilot Projects on multi service smart metering (Deliberation 19 September 2013, 393/2013/R/gas of the AEEG); · Transparent billing methods (Deliberation 18 November 2008 – ARG/com 164/08 of the AEEG); · National Green Procurement Plan (“Piano d’Azione Nazionale per il GPP”) (D.M. 11 April 2008, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013); · ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” (Target: energy efficiency)³; · Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes (all experiences are mapped in the NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014)⁴;

³ <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/>

⁴ <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/politiche-e-strategie-1/politiche-e-strategie-in-italia/paee/paee-2014.aspx>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buildings energy efficiency voluntary certification schemes and environmental voluntary certification schemes (Casa Clima, Protocollo Itaca, LEED....); Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) (municipal level).
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermal Account (D.M. 28 December 2012)⁵; Tax deductions (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and renewed several times with modifications); White Certificates (or Energy Efficiency Certificates) scheme and Obligation for national energy distributors (D.M. 20 July 2004); Kyoto Fund (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and implemented through following acts); National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”) (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102); Measures for the energy efficiency in schools (“Misure per l’efficientamento energetico degli edifici scolastici”) (D.I. 14 April 2015, n. 66); Fund for home purchase and/or renovation (“Plafond Casa”)(Cassa Depositi e Prestiti) (D.L. 31 August 2013, n. 102, converted into L. 28 October 2013, n. 124).
Capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency (“Piano integrato di diffusione dell’efficienza energetica”, PIDEE)(Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102); General conference on Energy Efficiency (“Stati Generali Efficienza Energetica”⁶ (ENEA); ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings⁷.
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115).

⁵ Incentive mechanism for small projects designed to increase energy efficiency and generate thermal energy from renewable sources.

⁶ <http://www.statigeneralefficienzaenergetica.it/>

⁷ <http://www.formazione.enea.it/>

Research and Development and BAT promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · National Electric System Research (ENEA, CNR and RSE carry out R&D activities on urgent and strategic issues which have results for the benefit of the national electric system users as a whole); · National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds (2012 and 2013) (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric); · National prize for energy efficiency measures (GSE’s “Premio Efficienza Energetica”); · ENEA reports on energy efficiency best available technologies.

In the **transport sector**, several planning instruments have been launched in order to strengthen and coordinate the policy schemes, both in people and freights transports. Many regulatory and financial policy instruments are in place in order to discourage more polluting behaviors and vehicles. A national policy focus is dedicated to the promotion of electric mobility and biofuels. On the contrary, less attention is given to the promotion of maritime transports. As in the case of buildings, many competences have been transferred by central public authorities to regional and local levels. Hence, regional and local levels play a fundamental role in the promotion of a more sustainable and efficient transports system.

Several relevant actors are involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of the transport energy efficiency policy instruments. A central role in transport policy instruments at national level is played by the Ministry of Transport and by the National Transport Authority settled in 2013. At local level a fundamental role is devoted to municipalities and their mobility and traffic plans.

Table B displays the most relevant policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector currently in force in Italy:

Table B: Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy

Policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy	
Planning Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 may 2012); · National Strategic Plan for Ports and Logistic (Piano Strategico Nazionale della Portualità e della Logistica) (Ministry of Transport 2015); · National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134); · National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (Piano di Azione Nazionale sui Sistemi Intelligenti di Trasporto) (D.L. 12 February 2014, n.44); · Promotion of use of biomethane in transports. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, n.28, Article 8); · Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L. 27 December 2014, n.147); · Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21); · Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); · National Green Procurement Plan (Piano d'Azione Nazionale per il GPP) (D.M. 11 April 2008, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013); · Sustainable Energy Action Plan, SEAPs (Piani d'Azione per l'Energia Sostenibile).
Regulatory instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vehicle Certification. Vehicle CO₂ emissions standards (several national laws compliant with European policies on theme); · Renewable energy in transport sector. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, n.28); · Urban Traffic Plans (Piano Urbano del Traffico) (Dlgs. 30 April 1992, n.285); · Obligation for national fuel producers to input into consumption 1% of biofuels of total traditional fuel. (L.11 March 2006, n. 81); · National quality standards for biofuels (AEEG Resolution 160/2012/R/GAS); · Minimum Environmental Criteria for the acquisition of vehicles for road transport (Criteri Minimi Ambientali per l'acquisizione dei veicoli adibiti al trasporto su strada) (D.M

	<p>8 May 2012);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Limits to polluting vehicles (Regional legislations).
Economic instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (L. 9 April 2009, N.5 and L. 26 June 2012, N.134); · Incentives for the promotion of biofuels in transport sector (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28); · Ad-hoc fund of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on PNIRE implementation 2013-2015 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134); · Ministry call in favour of the Regions to fund a network of electric vehicle charging points (L. 7 August 2012, n.134); · National electric car sharing project in cities (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment); · National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws); · Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L. 27 December 2014, N.147); · Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds); · Road tax (tax exemption for electric vehicles and discount on car assurance) and regional schemes for tax exemption for GPL and methane vehicles. (Regional legislations); · National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws); · Funding for energy efficiency, renewable energy and bike-sharing (L. 24 December, n.244).
Information and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Guide to fuel saving and decreasing CO₂ emission by cars (Guida sul risparmio di carburanti e sulle emissioni di anidride carbonica delle autovetture) (Published by MATTM, MIT and MISE); · National Logistics Platform UIRNET⁸ (Sistema Nazionale della Logistica Integrata e Intermodalità) (D.M. 20 June 2005, n.18T); · Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week; · National observatory on local public transports policies (Osservatorio nazionale sulle politiche per il trasporto pubblico locale) (L. 24 December 2007, N.244).
Policy instruments for Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle (Initiative of Ministry of Environment); · National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds 2012 and 2013 (Director Decree 5 July 2012, n.391/Ric);

⁸ <https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National technological maritime platform (Piattaforma Tecnologica Nazionale Marittima) (Dlgs. 21 November 2005, n.284).
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A more detailed description and analysis of the most relevant policy instruments for Italy can be found in Deliverable 1.1. “Landscape of energy efficiency policy packages in a Multi-Level government system – National Report for Italy” and Deliverable 1.2. “Status-quo analysis of energy efficiency policies in 8 EU countries – National Report for Italy” of the HERON project.

1.4 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

In order to provide an overview that allows a quick comparison of the different existing solutions, the mapping of the key technologies for achieving energy efficiency in the *buildings sector* in Italy has been made by associating to each technology the annual potential energy savings (in TWh), as estimated by Energy Strategy Group (2013). In particular, the main technologies here considered are:

- *For space heating and air conditioning: heat pump (53,3 TWh per year)⁹, opaque building surfaces (63,4 TWh per year)¹⁰, fixtures with high efficiency (12,4 TWh per year)¹¹, solar cooling (0,76 TWh per year), solar thermal (11,4 TWh per year)¹²;*
- *For energy production and energy saving: small wind turbines (3,9 TWh per year) and photovoltaic¹³ (17,0 TWh per year);*
- *For water heating: building automation (16,1 TWh per year)¹⁴, condensing boilers (34,7 TWh per year)¹⁵ and biomass boilers (38,6 TWh per year);*
- *For cooking, washing machines, laundry dryers and dishwashers: induction cooking (1 TWh per year) and efficient and pre heated appliances (3,7 TWh per year);*
- *For lighting: efficient lighting systems (17 TWh per year)¹⁶.*

⁹ The heat pumps are now in about 2% of the stock of production equipment installed in Italian buildings. There are indeed 400,000 installations of heat pumps compression and 150.000 installations of absorption heat pumps (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹⁰ Currently in Italy about 50%-70% of buildings has levels of thermal insulation roofing, walls and ground higher than 1.5W/m²K (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹¹ Currently in Italy about 40% -60% of buildings has levels of thermal insulation closures windows more than 3W/m²K.

¹² It is estimated that currently Italy has a total installed 2.5-3 GW of solar thermal for the production of domestic hot water and heat for heating (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹³ The current situation of the photovoltaic market in Italy is characterized by the presence of more than 526.463 plants scattered throughout the country, with a capacity corresponding to 17.080.255 kW (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹⁴ Currently in Italy the Energy Management Systems record low uptake; thanks to the integration of wi-fi technologies, the Building Automation System counts about 150.000-250.000 applications (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹⁵ It is estimated that in mid-2013, about 20%-30% of total heating units in use (19 million units, including central heating systems) were condensing boilers (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

¹⁶ To date in Italy, the lighting equipment in use is composed by about 15-18% gas lamps, LED lamps for 9-13% and for the remaining part fluorescent lamps (source: Energy Strategy Group, 2013).

As regards the *transport sector*, the main fuel-efficient technologies, as identified by numerous sources (such as ENEL, 2013; ENEA, 2015; Marciani et al., 2014) are:

- For *road transport*: low emission vehicles (natural gas, hybrids, hydrogen and electric), innovative vehicles based on automation¹⁷, tire pressure monitoring¹⁸, awareness of "eco-driving"¹⁹ and mobility management actions²⁰;
- For *rail transport*: power magnetic induction and recovering energy from braking;
- For *navigation*: hull antifouling systems, replacement of propeller and rudder, engine auto tuning, optimizers of hydro-dynamic flow, information system for the optimization of consumption, Air Cavity System and Waste Heat Recovery System;
- For *aviation*: high efficiency motors and aircraft with long life cycle.

More details on the technologies for achieving energy efficiency and their degree of diffusion in Italy can be found in Deliverable 1.4. "Technological trends in the building and transport sector – Italy".

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

Within the following chapter, the main social, economic, cultural, educational and institutional barriers that currently characterize the Italian context, and that are limiting a further diffusion of energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sectors, are mapped through a literature review. For buildings, both residential and commercial sub-sectors are analysed; for transport, both people and freight transport are considered. The literature review analyses official documents and reports as well as scientific literature. Afterwards, the impact of barriers is qualitatively assessed based on the authors' evaluation.

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

Social, cultural and educational barriers - As recognized by specific studies (Galarraga *et al.*, 2011; Panzone, 2013), behavioural adjustments, consumption practices, and quality perceptions on consumer choices can represent relevant issues in reducing energy efficiency gaps. In this respect, Italy does not constitute an exception. According to ENEL (2013) and ENEA (2015), behavioural and cultural barriers represent in Italy major limitations to spurring the adoption of energy efficiency technologies. Broadly speaking, behavioural and cultural barriers reduce the awareness of individuals on energy savings deriving from efficiency gains, thus limiting the diffusion of a 'culture of saving'

¹⁷ Cyber car, personal rapid transport (PRT), high-tech bus, high-tech lorry and dual-mode vehicles.

¹⁸ It is estimated that proper tire pressure can cut fuel consumption by up to 5% (source: Managenergy: Energy efficient transport. 2008).

¹⁹ Eco-driving (changing gears as soon as possible, maintaining a steady speed, frequently checking the tire pressure and decelerating smoothly) allows to save on average 5-10% of fuel, in addition to ensuring an economic saving, reducing the likelihood of accidents, noise pollution and emissions (source: Ecodriven. 2008).

²⁰ For example: encouraging the use of bicycles and public transport; company buses, teleworking, company kindergarten and grocery shopping online, car-pooling, car-sharing, bike-sharing, etc.

both at individual and community level. Such a culture constitutes the precondition for successful public interventions and attractive private investments in energy efficiency, since without a shared and dynamic efficiency culture, the interest and the associated value of more efficient goods is limited and misperceived. As a consequence, economic returns associated to previous investments on energy efficiency are difficult to be achieved given the existence of market limitations and inefficiencies (lack of information, few market agents). In this respect, the issue of behavioural spillovers deriving from best practices of virtuous individuals or communities assumes crucial importance. Without considering such multiplicative additional effects, the impacts of policies aimed at promoting a social awareness of efficiency benefits would be underestimated, both at individual as well as at country level, where international policy spillovers have been found to play a large role in inducing national regulation (see Costantini *et al.*, 2015).

Data on environmental attitudes in Italy show that, despite the environmental awareness is increasing over time, the level of interest towards environmental issues and proactive action appears to be moderate, although not far from the European average. According to a survey conducted by the national statistical office (ISTAT 2014b, based on 2012 data), only 45% of the Italian population is interested in environmental issues, with an 8% increase from a previous analysis conducted in 1998 (37,4%). The level of interest varies according to geographical localisation of respondents (more interested citizens in the Northern regions in comparison with Southern regions). It slightly differs according to gender, with more interest from males (46,7% for males, 43,2% for females) and it significantly varies according to age. The share of interested people is higher in adult-age ranges (45-54 years and 55-64 years, namely 51% and 53%), and the lowest among the very young and very old people (14-24 years and over 75 years, namely 38% and 27%). Also the level of education plays a role. In fact the level of interest increases with an increase of the level of education.

Regarding the means used by the population to be informed about the environment, Italians tend to inform themselves mainly through TV/radios (85%), newspapers (53,8%) and less frequently through specialized magazines or books (11,5%), whereas more active forms of participation (like attending conferencing, participating in environmental associations) are not widely diffused. The typology of used information means varies significantly only according to the level of education; more educated people tend to rely less on TV/radio and more on newspapers/specialized magazines, as well as are more engaged in an active participation. Interestingly, the use of all environmental information means decreased over time between 1998 and 2012. Despite the fact that mass media are the most frequently used information means, they are not positively evaluated by respondents. In fact, more than half of respondents declares a low satisfaction for information provided by mass media regarding the environment.

Climate change is considered a relevant environmental problem. ISTAT's survey (2014b) ranked climate change third in terms of share of Italian population that has identified it as urgent problem (46,6% of respondents), after air pollution (52,1%), and waste production and disposal (46,7%). Notably, the share of people that considers climate change an urgent problem has increased by 11% in comparison with 1998. This environmental issue has attracted increasing attention by citizens in this time frame. Climate change and availability of energy emerge as serious problems also within another survey, conducted at EU-level by Eurobarometer (European Commission, 2011b). Both issues rank third in terms of share of Italian citizens that have identified them as most serious problem

faced by the world (identified both by 42% of respondents), after the economic situation (53%), and international terrorisms (44%). Italians also quite agree that fighting climate change and improving energy efficiency can result in positive economic effects, boosting EU economy and jobs (77% agree, 12% disagree, 11% don't know) in line with EU-27 average data (European Commission, 2011b). As far as environmentally-friendly and climate protection behaviours are concerned, Italians' behaviours seem to be in line with those of the European average, as revealed by the Eurobarometer survey (European Commission, 2011b). When asked about personal action to face climate change, 45% of Italian respondents state that they carried out actions to fight climate change in the last 6 months, whereas 45% did not carry out actions and 10% didn't know. When asked about which actions specifically they had carried out, actions linked to energy efficiency behaviours both in the buildings and transport sector were named significantly less frequently than the other typologies of actions, consistently with EU-27 data²¹. The most frequently cited climate-protection actions were related to waste reducing and recycling (55%), reducing the use of disposable items (41%) and buying local/seasonal food (35%). Regarding the attitudes in purchasing specific equipment using energy, Italians seem to assign a relevant importance to energy consumption in choosing new equipment to be purchased. When asked about how much attention they pay to buying a new light bulb, refrigerator or car, relevant percentages of respondents declared that they pay "a lot of attention" to their energy uses, with higher shares than EU-25 average data (European Commission, 2006). Finally, regarding attitudes towards specific energy policies, and in particular when asked about which priority public authorities should pursue to support people in reducing their energy consumption, the development of tax incentives to promote an efficient use of energy emerged as the most important (45% of respondents), followed by the provision of more information on the efficient use of energy (33%), and adopting higher efficiency standards for energy consuming equipment (27%) (European Commission, 2006). These results slightly differ from the overall EU-25 result, where most importance was attributed to the provision of information (43%), followed by tax incentives (40%). In a more recent survey (European Commission, 2011b), Italians seem also to agree with the idea of designing taxation schemes more on the energy use, in line with average EU-27 responses. In fact 73% of respondents agrees with such (24% totally agree, 49% tends to agree), whereas only 17% disagrees (13% tends to disagree, 4% totally disagrees), with a relatively high percentage of respondents that cannot express an opinion (10% does not know) (European Commission, 2011b). To summarize, the level of interest of the Italian population for the environment is rather weak, and they prefer passive forms of information rather than active and participative ones. Some regional and age differences can be detected, in particular youngest generations seem to be the least responsive in paying attention to the environment preservation. However, climate change is perceived as a serious problem and stimulates forms of personal initiatives, even though pro-energy efficient behaviours are not diffusely implemented to this aim. Nonetheless, Italians attribute a high relevance to energy uses when they purchase new equipment. The reasons of such results deserve a

²¹ Energy efficient behaviours investigated and answers given by Italian citizens were (listed by relevance): choosing a more energy efficient household appliance when buying a new one (29%), using regularly environmentally-friendly alternatives to private cars (e.g. walking, biking, taking public transport or car-sharing) (21%), better home insulation (12%), having assigned importance to a low fuel consumption in the purchase of a new car (10%), avoiding short-haul flights whenever possible (5%), purchase of a low-energy home (4%) (European Commission, 2011b).

specific focus and should be further investigated in order to understand whether they are determined by other co-benefits of energy-efficiency (e.g. monetary savings, positive social recognition). Regarding the attitude towards specific policies, there seem to be a diffused agreement with the idea of taxation schemes based on the amount of energy used. A survey conducted within the project Promotion3e²², in collaboration with 8 EU countries including Italy, provides further interesting information on the environmental attitudes, habits and choices of private consumers in purchasing home appliances. Although the project relies on the analysis of a limited sample based on several municipalities belonging to the Province of Teramo, the results constitute one of the few case study in Italy on environmental attitudes. In the survey report, the most important choice factors of more efficient goods are reported. Although the cost always assumes the greatest importance in driving consumer choices, power consumption, energy-efficiency performance and power rating also constitute relevant factors (fourth, seventh and eighth position). In particular, when only environmental-specific factors are ranked, energy efficiency performances and energy labelling class reveal as factors of primary importance. The report also signals gender and age differences in environmental attitudes. Namely, female customers are reported to have more consideration for water and energy consumption in their choices of electrical appliances than male customers do. In addition, female customers report significantly more positive general attitude towards the environment than male customers and show greater confidence in sales support. With respect to age, customers younger than 30 years old pay relatively less attention to factors such as energy consumption. On the contrary, older women seem to be more prone to the consideration of environmental aspects, especially for energy efficiency classes. As a final consideration, it is worth noting that the attitude for choosing environmental-friendly and more efficient appliances (also being persuaded by technicians and sales advisors) is stronger when other people accompany buyers. Thus, the presence of friends and relatives seems to assume a positive role to the promotion of ecological buying. A specific issue regards those barriers affecting condominiums. It is worth considering that in Italy more than 75% of buildings date back to periods in which no norms or regulation related to energy performance was in force (ENEA, 2015). In light of this, a strong intervention aimed at renovating the stock of existing buildings is required. Nevertheless, a set of specific factors negatively affect the success of government plans to promote energy efficiency in residential buildings. More specifically, a study conducted by Politecnico di Milano and University of Insubria (WWF, 2007) detects cultural, technical and economic barriers. With respect to educational and technical barriers, WWF (2007) highlights the lack of technical expertise of building administrators, these being not able to identify and propose the correct set of interventions and investments in order to achieve energy efficiency gains. Moreover, the ownership fragmentation existing in condominium also affects the decision process. When a plurality of individuals with heterogeneous preferences are involved in decision process (e.g., to invest in energy efficiency technologies), this can result in initiative failures due to a lack of managerial capacity and coordination ability by the building administrator.

²² The Promotion3e project aimed to reduce the energy consumption of households' electric equipment and products by implementing actions to encourage the take-up of energy efficient appliances as well as measures that increase quality and efficiency of information available to consumers. The project involves 8 EU countries, namely Portugal, Spain, UK (North Ireland), France, Greece, Italy, Germany and Poland and it has been developed in the 2008-2011 period.

Table 1 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social, cultural, educational (several factors interacting)	Gender and age differences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Less consideration for water/energy consumption by male customers in electrical appliances choices. · Less positive general attitude towards the environment by male customers. · Less consideration of environmental aspects and energy efficiency classes by younger customers (< 30 yrs).
Social	Group as push factor to energy efficiency investments	Being alone when taking decisions on energy efficiency investment (appliances in particular) negatively affects the importance of saving issues and consumption performance. Being within a group (friends, relatives etc) seem to induce to environmental-friendly behaviour.
Social, cultural, educational (several factors interacting)	Lack of a “culture of saving”	This constitutes a precondition for successful public interventions and attractive private investments in energy efficiency.
Social, cultural	Fragmentation of home ownership (due to relevant presence of condominiums)	When a plurality of individuals with heterogeneous preferences are involved in decision process (e.g., to invest in energy efficiency technologies), this can result in initiative failures due to a lack of managerial capacity and coordination ability by the building administrator.
Educational	Lack of technical expertise of building administrators	Building administrators are often not able to identify and propose the correct set of interventions and investments in order to achieve energy efficiency gains.

Economic barriers - An Italian-specific economic barrier, affecting the building sector both at industrial and residential level, is constituted by the lack of incentive to invest in EE in consequence of the little incidence that energy costs assumes in most of the companies and families, although this aspect is particularly important in the case of electricity. Italy shows higher energy prices with respect to other EU countries (IEA, 2015), with an industrial pattern characterized by few energy-intensive companies whose energy bill covers more than 10% of the production cost (ENEL, 2013). The remaining companies show moderate energy consumptions and this mitigates the incentive to invest in energy efficiency technologies given by the well-known price-induced effect (Binswanger, 1974, among all). On the contrary, at household level this barrier is disappearing since the share of

households with energy bill higher than 10% of their income is increasing over time, a phenomenon known as ‘fuel poverty’ (Thomson and Snell, 2013). The issue of split incentives and principal-agent problem assumes crucial importance in the building sector. On one hand, owners could invest in energy efficiency with limited economic returns (excluding the extra cost to which the building is sold). On the other hand, those individuals that actually pay the bill and live in the building has limited incentive to invest in energy efficiency as do not own any properties and can only temporary occupy the building. In addition, difficulties in accessing credit caused by the economic stagnation also limits energy efficiency investments and affect both building administrators and ESCo companies.

Table 2 Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Little incidence of energy costs on companies/families	Little incidence of energy costs on companies/families means a lack of incentives to invest in EE. Higher energy prices could restore optimal level of EE investments although this could lead to ‘fuel poverty’ phenomena in poorer households.
Split incentives and principal-agent problem	On one hand, owners could invest in energy efficiency with limited economic returns (excluding the extra cost to which the building is sold). On the other hand, those individuals that actually pay the bill and live in the building have limited incentive to invest in energy efficiency as do not own any properties and can only temporary occupy the building.
Difficulty to access credit caused by the economic stagnation	Difficulties in accessing credit caused by the economic stagnation also limits energy efficiency investments, affecting both building administrators and ESCo companies.

Institutional, technical and technological barriers – In Italy the institutional and normative settings often constitute significant limitations to the promotion and diffusion of energy efficiency technologies, undermining the success of government regulation. Such a barriers are manifold and include: (i) lack of normative schemes; (ii) dyscrasia between national, supra-national and local norms which implies redundancy legislation, delays in adopting policy schemes, uncertainty as well as coordination failures due to the numerous Italian municipalities which often set different requirements; (iii) lack of transparency and long waiting times for authorizations to be faced by adopters and subjects involved (ENEL, 2013). In addition, the building sector is affected by the existence of a disconnection between the policy regulation and the effective implementation of policies in the real context. Apart from the numerous Italian regional fragmentation which induces to difficult policy coordination, this is also due to a lack of mediating subjects such as installers and technicians which seem not to have any particular incentive to operate in this sector, apart from that indirect given by the policy-induced market demand stimulus. Given the lack of incentives for providers, these latter seem not to provide consumers with sufficient technical information for adopting energy efficiency solutions (ENEL, 2013). A further institutional barrier lies on the lack of control to the initiatives actually undertaken by the building administrators, although the Italian legislation envisages specific control and penalty schemes. Technical limitations also constitute

relevant obstacles to energy efficiency gains. Also in this case, the Italian case shows specific features. According to ENEA (2015), more than 60% of Italian residential dwellings are older than 45 years and more than 25% show annual consumption between 160 and 220 kWh/m². Non-residential buildings are also characterized, on average, by an old age and low efficiency performances. The massive presence of low-efficient buildings represents a technical limitation difficult to be addressed in order to achieve energy efficiency targets, also considering the moderate propensity to demolish old buildings given the historical importance that these assume in the Italian urban setting.

Table 3 Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of normative schemes.	Lack of norms and regulations due to delays in adopting and implementing EU Directives.
Dyscrasia between national, supra-national and local norms and lack of policy coordination.	The regional fragmentation (at NUTS-3 level Italy counts 197 provinces and 8047 municipalities) affects the policy coordination across different administrative levels. It implies redundancy legislation, uncertainty as well as coordination failures due to the numerous Italian municipalities, which often set different requirements and adoption procedures.
Low-quality bureaucracy level.	The low level of Italian bureaucracy produces lack of transparency and long waiting times for authorizations to be faced by adopters and subjects involved.
Lack of mediating subjects such as installers and technicians.	These subjects seem not to have incentives to operate in the EE sector and they do not provide consumers with technical information for adopting energy efficiency solutions. This produces a disconnection between the in-force policies and the effective implementation in the real context.
Lack of control for non-compliant building administrators and enforcement schemes.	Lack of control for non-compliant building administrators.

Table 4 Main technical and technological barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Technical limitation (old age and low EE performance of the existing stock)	In Italy more than 75% of buildings dates back to periods in which no norms or regulation related to energy performance were in force.

Table 5 summarizes the barriers to energy efficiency in the building sector identified within literature, subdividing them according to their impact (high, medium, low). Given the lack of quantitative comparative assessments on the barriers in literature, the following impact assessment derives from a qualitative expert evaluation based on the authors' knowledge. For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report "Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport".

Table 5 Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Old age and low EE performance of the existing stock of buildings
	Lack of a “culture of saving”.
	Dyscrasia between national, supra-national and local norms (lack of policy coordination).
	Lack of control for non-compliant building administrators.
	Lack of normative schemes.
Medium	Fragmentation of home ownership (due to relevant presence of condominiums).
	Lack of technical expertise of building administrators.
	Low-quality bureaucracy level.
	Difficulty to access credit due to economic stagnation.
	Lack of mediating subjects such as installers and technicians.
	Split incentives and principal-agent problem.
Low	Group as push factor to energy efficiency investments.
	Little incidence of energy costs on companies/families.
	Gender and age differences in adopting EE technologies.

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

In the transport sector, Italy shows an infrastructural deficit which has to be recovered in order to boost a sustainable mobility. Relevant limitations lie to the amount of lines for mass rapid transport in large cities and exchange parking. In the public transportation system, a large replacement of old vehicles is required since the technology turnover is often insufficient to guarantee a quality service. The South of Italy has a significantly lower public transport offer, both quantitatively (in terms of car-km) and qualitative (mean age rolling stock, punctuality, technologies), than the rest of the country. It also offers an average standard of service well below average levels in Europe (Gentile, 2009).

With respect to the freight transport, it is worth signalling a lack of logistics in the ports and their connection to the power supply, especially in the south of the country (Messina et al., 2011).

Besides these structural deficits, the economic stagnation has exacerbated the lack of funds to be devolved to the transport system, although such investments, at different regional level, have been recognized to be able to boost the economy, with generation of new labour force. The automotive sector, particularly in the urban context, shows most of the inefficiency. This is due to the low car load factor (only 1.2 passenger/car) which produces large traffic congestion and urban disamenities (Marciani et al., 2014). For instance, statistics show that cars are used for 75% of private transportation within the urban areas and such a share is projected to increase over time (Marciani et al., 2014). The inefficiency also affects the freights transportation, which in the urban context shows the highest consumption rate per ton/km (Zunder and Ibanez, 2004).

Besides these infrastructural and structural factors, it is possible to identify a series of social, cultural and educational factors, as well as economic and institutional ones, which can hamper the use of more energy efficient transport modes in the personal travel and freight transportation in Italy.

The following paragraphs will present and briefly discuss these barriers to energy efficiency in the transport sector in Italy, differentiating them between transportation of people and of goods.

Transportation of people

Social, cultural and educational barriers

As shown by the data on the type of means of transport used by the different social categories (table below), the primacy of the car in Italy is very strong. Working-age men represent the main users of cars. Data seem to show a preference for walking by women and people who do not work (young people under 20 and people over 65 years). However, walking is marginal compared to the other modes. Overall, sustainable transport modes, such as public transport, walking and biking, have a relative low weight on the people mobility.

MODES OF TRANSPORT IN ITALY					
	Man	Woman	Young (<20 years)	Old (>65 years)	Worker (35-44 years)
Car	72,1	65,1	38,5	54,7	73,0
Public transport	2,6	4,2	5,8	3,2	3
Walking	9,5	14,4	21,5	27,2	10,1
Bicycle	3,6	4,5	7,7	1,7	3,2

Source: ISTAT, 2012

The table described above refers to Italian average data. Differences can be noted on the choice of transport modes at regional and local scales. In fact cars are more used in Southern regions in comparison with Northern regions and in rural areas with respect to urban areas (see table below by Isfort, 2014). This can be explained by the lack of public transport infrastructures and low quality transport services already explained above.

Figure 7 - Trips by modal share

Source: Isfort, 2014

No relevant differences at regional and local scales can be noted as far as preferences of mobility associated with sex and age are considered (Isfort, 2014).

The following paragraphs describe the main social, cultural and education factors that influence the use of each personal transport mode and lead to a preference of lower-energy efficient travel choices over more sustainable ones.

First of all, it should be noted that Italy, after Luxembourg, is the second European country for motorization rate, with 621 cars per 1.000 inhabitants, considerably above the European average of 487 cars (ISTAT, 2012). This produces relevant disamenities and Italy is the fourth country - considering European countries, Canada and the United States - for the level of traffic congestion (INRIX, 2013).

The reasons for the preference of private over public transportation are numerous. The choice of public transport closely depends on its accessibility and availability (Handy and Niemeier, 1997; Kwan, 1998; Ocelli 1999, quoted by Borlini and Memo, 2009). Public transport does not guarantee the same flexibility and rapidity as private cars. Also, it seems not to provide the same freedom, prestige and safety as private cars or bikes (Curtins and Perkins, 2006).

In Italy, such preference for private cars over public transport can be explained by the low satisfaction of Italians for public transport service. A survey promoted by the EU Commission shows that Italians are less satisfied of public transportation than citizens of other European countries (EU Commission, 2011a). According to this study, the reasons of low satisfaction for the public transport

can be detected in: (i) lack of stations and stops (identified as relevant by 80% of survey respondents), low comfort of vehicles (78%), low frequency of vehicle passages (76%), insufficient timetables (63%), lack of service reliability (62%), safety concerns (44%) and high costs (42%) (EU Commission, 2011a). A further survey, conducted by Aci-Censis (2011) based on 3.992 interviews elaborated using the CATI method, provides further information on the main barriers to public transport's use; more precisely, these are: (i) absence of direct connections (30,4%), low stop frequency and long stop distance from home (respectively 25,2% and 23%), low trip comfort (21%), low economic advantage (11%).

Among those factors, safety is identified as one of the main barrier to public transportation use also by the Isfort (2012), which indicates that, according to a relevant share of Italians, public transportation is affected by safety concerns. In detail, subway trips are considered as the most dangerous, while trains and walking are perceived as relatively more safe.

Furthermore, in Italy, citizens and policy makers do not acknowledge the environmental and social benefits of a greater use of public transport (in terms of energy savings, health and quality of life) (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

As far as biking is concerned, Italy is characterized by a scarce usage of bicycles with respect to other Member States such as The Netherlands (FIAB, 2012). Such a gap seems to be attributed to lack of street maintenance, safety concerns (theft of bicycles in particular) and unfavourable weather conditions. The same barriers, associated with lack of adequate space and opportunity to cover short distances, concern walking (Legambiente and ACI, 2010).

Along with the "traditional" transport modes described above, other forms of sustainable mobility are spreading in Italy, such as car sharing and car-pooling. Among these, car-pooling appears not to be diffused (Zoccarato G., 2013), even though in the last year it is increasing (CarPooling, 2013). It was not possible to identify specific barriers to the diffusion of these alternative transport modes, because of lack of specific studies and data.

A cultural phenomenon that generates energy inefficiencies in the transport sector in Italy is definitely the chaotic parking. A relevant share (54,4%) of respondents interviewed by Isfort (2007) declares to face systematically double parked cars during their trips.

Within this national context, exceptions and specific situations at local level can be identified, such as in the Milan city area. In the last years, Milan has seen a significantly diffusion of bike sharing and car sharing systems, with high numbers of users and a relevant impact on transport choices. The city has also increased its metro lines supply and suburban railways, which have also contributed to modal changes. Furthermore, the city has implemented a road pricing scheme (previously a pollution charge, "Ecopass", then transformed into a congestion charge, "Area C"), which has enabled a relevant reduction of congestion in the city centre. The overall combined effect of these sustainable mobility policies and measures has generated an increase of public transport modal share and a decrease of motorization rates, as shown by the data included in the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan recently adopted by the City of Milan (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015).

Social, cultural and educational barriers in the public and private transport sector above described can be summarized as follows (Table 6).

Table 6 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the public and private transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Car ownership (private transport)	Italy is the second European country for motorization rate (ISTAT, 2012) and is the fourth country for the level of traffic congestion (INRIX, 2013)
Social, cultural	Low satisfaction for the public transport (includes several elements, such as the perception of public transport as unsafe and as less flexible/rapid than private means)	According to a survey promoted by the EU Commission, Italians are less satisfied of public transportation than citizens of other European countries (EU Commission, 2011a). Private transport is often privileged since public transport does not guarantee the same rapidity (Handy e Niemeier, 1997; Kwan, 1998; Occelli 1999) and seems not to provide the same freedom, prestige and safety as private cars or bikes (Curtins and Perkins, 2006)
Social, cultural, educational	Low acknowledgement of environmental/social benefits of public transport use	Citizens and policy makers do not acknowledge the environmental and social benefits of a greater use of public transport in Italy (in terms of energy savings, health and quality of life) (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).
Social, cultural	Bike perceived as dangerous and not compatible with some weather conditions (private transport)	Italy is characterized by a scarce usage of bicycles with respect to other Member States such as The Netherlands (FIAB, 2012). Such a gap seems to be attributed to lack of street maintenance, safety concerns (theft of bicycles in particular) and unfavourable weather conditions.
Cultural, educational	Insufficient safety, lack of adequate space for walking (private transport)	In Italy there is little walking mobility because of insufficient safety, lack of adequate space and opportunity to cover short distances (Legambiente and ACI, 2010)
Cultural, educational	Chaotic parking (private transport)	A cultural phenomenon that generates energy inefficiencies in the transport sector in Italy is definitely the chaotic parking (Isfort, 2007)

Economic barriers

A relevant economic barrier to energy efficiency in the Italian public transport is related to the high dependency of management authorities on national and regional funds. Own earnings cover only a limited part of general public transport costs (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

Furthermore, the responsibility for public transport is divided into different levels: municipal, regional and national. As a consequence there are many different tariff structures, scattered information and missing integration of schedules for the user (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

Also, the tariff of the travels is currently lower than the average EU. This implies less coverage of the costs necessary to make the system more efficient (Messina et al., 2011). To this, it must be added that the rate of ticket evasion is higher in Italian transport companies than in the major foreign transport companies: such a rate is estimated at least 6% in about 43% of Italian companies, whereas 27% of them are able to maintain this rate under 2% (ASSTRA, 2007).

A further factor to be considered is that the companies operating in the field of public transport heavily depend on government grants: in 2013, more than half of revenues came from public compensation, while the remainder is covered for 30% by revenues from traffic and for 17% by revenue complementary services (advertising and rentals) and parking. Companies, therefore, are obliged to update the ticket tariff only after receiving the indications of grantors, which are based on considerations of distributive equity rather than on economic and industrial considerations. In Italy ticket tariffs are low, poorly differentiated across regions and population groups, and not enough related to the costs and objectives of the transport companies (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

A further economic barrier to energy efficiency in transport regarding public transportation concerns investments in low-density areas. Investments needed to realize high-capacity transport systems in low-density residential areas with a high urban sprawl are characterized by a low economic viability. Therefore, investments in these areas are not pursued, generating a lack of public transport service provision. Urban sprawl produces also an effect in terms of trips increase by private cars in the urban areas, producing higher environmental pressure. Traversi *et al.* (2010) estimated that in Italian municipalities urban sprawl has generated a 37% increase of car trips.

Finally, a relevant economic barrier related to energy efficiency in public and private transport concerns electric vehicles. This is mainly related to the high cost of batteries. Although the recent technological developments, which enable batteries with better performances than in the past, the cost of batteries is not affordable yet (for a 150 km-range battery, the cost is estimated around Euro 9000). Such low battery performances limit the electric vehicles to cities and urban areas and contribute to the diffusion of hybrid vehicles.

Table 7 Main economic barriers in the public and private transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Critical economic condition of several public transport management authorities (public transport)	High dependency of Italian public transport management authorities on national and regional funds (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013)
Fragmentation of public transport operators (public transport)	Responsibility for public transport is divided into different levels: municipal, regional and national (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013)
High evasion rate of public transport tickets (public transport)	The rate of ticket evasion is higher in Italian transport companies than in the major foreign transport companies (ASSTRA, 2007)
Spending review conducted by central government on public transport services (public transport)	Companies operating in the field of public transport service are obliged to update the ticket tariff only after receiving the indications of grantors, which are based on considerations of distributive equity rather than on economic and industrial considerations (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013)

Low economic viability of the investment necessary for the realization of high-capacity transport in low-density residential areas (public transport)	Investments needed to realize high-capacity transport systems in low-density residential areas with a high urban sprawl are characterized by a low economic viability. Therefore, investments in these areas are not pursued, generating a lack of public transport service provision.
Urban sprawl (private transport)	Urban sprawl in Italy has resulted in an increase of car trips (up to 37%) in urban areas in Italian municipalities (Travisi et al., 2010)
High cost of batteries for electric vehicles (public/private transport)	The cost of batteries with better performances is not affordable yet, for a 150 km-range battery, the cost is estimated around Euro 9000 (Marciani et al., 2014)

Institutional/organizational barriers

Following the economic crisis of recent years, the public funds allocated to the management of the transport sector have plummeted. This resulted in a very serious and intolerable situation in terms of reduced services, social unrest, tariff increases, reduction of employment in the sector, traffic congestion and pollution (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

The lack of funds has also prevented the renewal of the vehicles stock, resulting in a reduction of the quality of service and a negative impact on the operating costs of the transport companies, whose maintenance costs have increased dramatically (ACI, Fondazione Caracciolo, 2013).

Key institutional barriers for promoting a more efficient mobility of people are the lack of a national strategy for bike and pedestrian mobility and the delay of establishment of an Italian Transport Authority, which was established only in September 2013.

Delays in the definition of the strategic national plan have also affected the completion of the regional planning frameworks (regional transport plans), whose completion took longer than desirable, particularly for the southern regions (Il Sole 24 Ore, 2012).

More institutional barriers are represented by a scarce attention in the public transport concession of qualitative standards of services and myopia for long-term vision regarding the future of transport infrastructures. Particularly, it should be noted that in the concessions contracts of public transport services, few attention is given to quality standards of public transport providers, because only economic aspects are considered. The Italian transport strategy "tends to leave an emergency approach to prevail" (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).

Table 8 Main institutional/organizational barriers in the public and private transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Reduction of national public investments in the public transport sector	Following the economic crisis, the public funds allocated to the management of the transport sector have plummeted. This resulted in a very serious and intolerable situation in terms of reduced services, social unrest, tariff increases, reduction of employment in

	the sector, traffic congestion and pollution (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013).
Lack of a national strategy for bike and pedestrian mobility	There have been several proposals in the national parliament to set a national plan for bike and pedestrian mobility and infrastructure. To date no plan was accepted.
Lack of an Italian Transport Authority for a long time	There has been a delay in the establishment of an Italian Transport Authority (established only in 2013).
Delays in the definition of the strategic national plan	Delays in the definition of the strategic national plan have affected the completion of the regional planning frameworks (regional transport plans) (Il Sole 24 Ore, 2012).
Scarce attention in the public transport concession of qualitative standards of services	In the concessions contracts of public transport services few attention is given to quality standards of public transport offers. Only economic aspects are considered.
Lack of a long term vision regarding the future of transport infrastructures	According to the CDP, the Italian transport strategy "tends to leave an emergency approach to prevail" (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2013)

Infrastructural/technical/technological barriers

The main Italian technological barrier within the public transport is represented by the old fleets. In Italy, road vehicles for public transport have, on average, a longer life with respect to other European countries: 11.6 years on average compared to 7 in Europe (ACI, Fondazione Caracciolo, 2013). As a consequence, a lack of transport infrastructure must be added, which is particularly evident for the underground lines. The main Italian cities, in fact, have a lower number of subway lines in comparison with the other European member states with similar size (Eurispes, 2015).

A further infrastructural gap which constitutes a barrier to the diffusion of electric vehicles is due to the lack of recharge stations, these latter being at a low implementation stage also because of problems of electric loads and interconnections (Marciani, 2011).

Bio-methane vehicles are scarcely diffused in Italy because of the limited fuel production. Moreover, as in the case of methane, fuel stations are poorly diffused and far from urban centres (Messina et al., 2011).

Table 9 Main infrastructural/technical barriers in the public and private transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Old Italian public transport fleets (public transport)	In Italy public transport fleets have, on average, a longer life with respect to other European countries: 11.6 years on average, compared to 7 in Europe (ACI, Fondazione Caracciolo, 2013)
Few underground lines in Italian cities (public transport)	The main Italian cities have a lower number of subway lines in comparison with the other European members states with similar size (Eurispes, 2015).
Lack of recharge stations for electric vehicles (public and private transport)	A further barrier to the diffusion of electric vehicles is due to the lack of recharge stations, these latter being at a low implementation stage also because of problems of electric loads and

	interconnections (Marciani et al., 2014)
Technical limitations of electric vehicles (public and private transport)	Although the recent technological developments, electric vehicles still show large limitations to be fully employed in the road transport sector (Marciani et al., 2014)
Scarce diffusion of Bio-methane in Italy (private transport)	Bio-methane vehicles are scarcely diffused in Italy because of the limited fuel production. Moreover, as in the case of methane, fuel stations are poorly diffused and far from urban centres (Messina et al., 2011)

Table 10 summarizes the barriers to energy efficiency in the people transport sector identified within literature, subdividing them according to their impact (high, medium, low). Given the lack of quantitative comparative assessments on the barriers in literature, the following impact assessment derives from a qualitative expert evaluation based on the authors’ knowledge. For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from ‘High’ to ‘Low’, taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report “Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport”.

Table 10 Assessment of barriers in the people transport sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Low satisfaction for the public transport
	Critical economic condition of several public transport management authorities
	Low economic viability of the investment necessary for the realization of high-capacity transport in low-density residential areas
	Spending review conducted by central government on public transport services
	Urban Sprawl
	Reduction of national public investments in the public transport sector
	Old Italian public transport fleets
	Lack of a national strategy for bike and pedestrian mobility
Medium	Fragmentation of public transport operators
	Lack of an Italian Transport Authority for a long time
	Chaotic parking
	Delays in the definition of the strategic national plan
	High cost of batteries for electric vehicles
	High evasion rate of public transport tickets
	Scarce attention in the public transport concession of qualitative standards of services
	Scarce diffusion of Bio-methane in Italy
	Few underground lines in Italian cities
	Lack of recharge stations for electric vehicles
	Lack of a long term vision regarding the future of transport infrastructures
Low	Bike perceived as dangerous and not compatible with some weather conditions
	Car ownership
	Low acknowledgement of environmental/social benefits of public transport use
	Insufficient safety, lack of adequate space for walking
	Technical limitations of electric vehicles
	Scarce diffusion of Bio-methane in Italy

Transportation of goods/freight transport

In Italy, freight transport is responsible for a high share of urban pollutant emissions. In fact even if the logistic sector represents only 8-15% of total urban vehicles flows, it produces 20-30% of the total urban emissions (MDS Transmodal and DG Transport, 2012).

According to CE Delft data (2011), Italy is one of the countries where the logistic sector generates more negative externalities. This high impact of the logistic sector on Italian pollutants emissions is strongly related to the low efficiency of the sector (ISFORT, 2013).

The following paragraphs describe the main social, cultural, educational, economic, institutional and technical barriers to energy efficiency in the logistic transport.

Social, cultural and educational barriers

In Italy, last-mile freight transportation is characterized by a strong competition among market players, especially on prices and timing of deliveries, related mainly to the needs to protect their own quota of market in a very high competitive market. This makes it difficult to implement solutions that could increase energy-efficiency (such as consolidation of loads and the use of shared logistics platforms).

A further element which limits efficiency is the irregular parking. High levels of irregularity in parking logistic vehicles are documented in Italian urban areas. More than 60% of logistic operators declare to avoid the use of regular parking areas for the last mile delivery activities (Transport Ministry, 2011). This plays a crucial role in the high congestion levels affecting several Italian cities. The low control levels conducted by municipal police does not contribute to mitigate such a negative context.

A lack of high-level managerial competencies can also be identified. A survey conducted by ISFORT among the main Italian logistic operators reveals that the lack of an adequate educational level of Italian managers is considered the first problem in the logistic sector in Italy.

Several Italian economic operators organize by themselves their freights supply (“Conto Proprio”) (namely 45% of total freights moved in a year in Italy) (Confindustria Vicenza, 2008). Since private travel is less efficient than trips organized by specialized logistic operators (Marciani et al., 2014), this barrier has a detrimental effect on urban congestion and pollution levels.

Italian logistic operators (Marciani et al., 2014) are characterized by high level of outsourcing of last mile delivery activities to very little and often low qualified last mile delivery companies (“Padroncini”). These outsourcers are less efficient compared to big logistics operators, due to their very little corporate dimensions and lack of adequate financial resources to invest in more efficient delivery services.

A relevant cultural aspect regarding consumer preferences regards the e-commerce, which in Italy is rapidly growing (Casaleggio associati, 2014). As e-commerce foresees short delivery time, for logistic operators it is more difficult to organize in a more efficient way their delivery plans (for example using a single vehicle to deliver all goods addressed to the same urban area).

Another aspect is the high importance attributed by logistics operators to showing their logo in the last mile delivery and to control the quality of delivery (brand identity). Such a strong “brand identity” of the main logistic operators limits all the experiences in sharing vehicles in the last mile delivery (vehicles characterized also for this reason by very low load factors). Moreover, this creates an incentive for the growing of “door-to-door” and “business-to-consumers” services.

A last cultural barrier is the role of lobbies. Italian small logistic operators have a very important political weight. Often they act as a barrier to develop new national and regional policies.

Social, cultural and educational barriers in the freight transport sector can be summarized as follows (table below).

Table 11 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the freight transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Cross-cutting	Low cooperation between logistic operators	Low cooperation between different market players ²³ limit the adoption of more sustainable measures (Marciani et al., 2014) (for example sharing of last mile vehicles, use of the same urban logistic platforms, etc.).
Cultural, educational	Low probability to be sanctioned for irregular parking	High level of irregularity in parking logistic vehicles are documented in Italian urban areas. In fact in urban areas, more than 60% of logistic operators declare to avoid the use of regular parking areas for the last mile delivery activities (Transport Ministry, 2011). This plays a crucial role in the high congestion levels affecting several Italian cities. This high level of irregularities is strictly related to the low control levels conducted by municipal police.
Educational	Lack of high level managerial competencies	A survey conducted by ISFORT among the main Italian logistic operators reveals that the lack of an adequate educational level of Italian managers is considered the first problem in the logistic sector in Italy.
Cultural	Several economic operators organize by itself their freights supply (Conto Proprio)	A high quota of Italian economic operators (45% of total freights moved in a year in Italy) (Confindustria Vicenza, 2008), organizes by themselves their freights supply. As private travel is less efficient than trips organized by specialized logistic operators (Marciani et al., 2014), this barrier has a detrimental effect on urban congestion and

²³ Evidences collected by IEFE-Bocconi University during the research regional project OPTILOG (<http://www.optilog.it/>)

		pollution levels.
Cross-cutting	High outsourcing level of main logistic operators	Italian logistic operators (Marciani et al., 2014) are characterized by high level of outsourcing of last mile delivery activities to very little and often low qualified last mile delivery companies (Padroncini). These outsourcers are less efficient compared to big logistics operators due to their very little corporate dimensions and lack of adequate financial resources to invest in more efficient delivery services.
Cross-cutting	E-commerce rapid growth	In Italy e-commerce is rapidly growing (Casaleggio associati, 2014). As e-commerce foresees short delivery time, for logistic operators it is more difficult to organize in a more efficient way their delivery plans.
Cultural	High importance for logistics operators to show their logo in the last mile delivery and control the quality of delivery (brand identity)	The strong “brand identity” of the main logistic operators limits all the experiences in sharing vehicles in the last mile delivery (vehicles characterized also for this reason by very low load factors) ²⁴ . Moreover this creates an incentive for the growing of “door-to-door” and “business-to-consumers” services.
Cultural	Strong lobbies block political reforms	Italian small logistic operators have a very important political weight. Often they act as a barrier to develop new national and regional policies.

Economic/institutional barriers

Local traffic regulation in Italy is highly fragmented. Each Italian municipality has its own traffic regulation, which often differs from those adopted in other cities within the same region or even province. This fragmentation limits the possibility of logistic operators to organize in a more efficient way their delivery plans and/or to export efficient organization models from one city to another.

Few external/international investments are carried out in the Italian logistic sector. As documented by ISFORT, Italy receives less external/international investments in the logistic sector compared to other European countries.

²⁴ Evidences collected by IEFE-Bocconi University during the research regional project OPTILOG (<http://www.optilog.it/>)

The logistic sector is characterized by higher levels of bureaucracy, compared to other European countries (ISFORT, 2013). This affects many aspects of the logistic sector, from the vehicles quality requirements to the organization of the delivery services.

Regulatory aspects limit the growth of green logistic solutions. Both at national and regional levels, norms limiting the growing of green logistic solutions exist. For instance, there are limits on the dimension of cargo bikes usable in the last mile deliveries, or there are limits in trains maximum length impeding to optimize single train trip (ISFORT, 2013). Also the Italian normative on road and traffic management (Codice della Strada) generates several limitations in the definition of innovative services and business models.

Further limitations derive from a relevant lack of infrastructures for intermodal logistics (especially in urban areas). This regards in particular:

- Train to lorries;
- Ship to train/lorries.

These limits are related both to scarce public and private investments for the development of these infrastructures and to the lack of an adequate political will.

Finally, there is a lack of adequate economic resources for local public administrations (ISFORT, 2013). This aspect has a detrimental effect on several activities of local public administrations in the logistic sectors, like:

- Scarce road check activities conducted by municipal police forces and low level of violations sanctioning;
- Reduction in the investments on urban logistic infrastructures.

Main economic and institutional barriers in the freight transport sector can be summarized as follows (table below).

Table 12 Main economic/institutional barriers in the freight transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
High fragmentation of local traffic regulation	Each Italian municipality has its own traffic regulation, often very different one to another ²⁵ . This fragmentation limits the possibility of logistic operators to organize in a more efficient way their delivery plans and/or to export efficient organization models from one city to another.
Few external/international investments in Italian logistic sector	As documented by ISFORT, Italy receives less external/international investments in the logistic sector compared to other European countries.

²⁵ See for example the case of Lombardy Region and its investigation report on the different municipal traffic regulation in more than 80 cities (Merci in Città. Regole vigenti nei principali comuni Lombardi). (http://www.agendadigitale.regione.lombardia.it/shared/ccurl/14/313/MERCI%20citt%C3%A0_aggiornamento%20novembre2013.pdf)

High bureaucracy in the logistic sector (both national and regional level)	The logistic sector in Italy is affected by a higher level of bureaucracy compared to other European countries (ISFORT, 2013). This high level of bureaucracy affects many aspects of the logistic sector, from the vehicles quality requirements to the organization of the delivery services.
Regulatory aspects limit the growing of green logistic solutions (both national and regional level)	Both at national and regional levels, norms limiting the growing of green logistic solutions exist. For example there are limits on the dimension of cargo bikes usable in the last mile deliveries, or there are limits in trains maximum length impeding to optimize single train trip (ISFORT, 2013). Also the Italian normative on road and traffic management (Codice della Strada) generates several problems in the definition of innovative services and business models ²⁶ .
Lack of infrastructures for intermodal logistics (especially in urban areas)	<p>Italy is affected by a strong lack of adequate infrastructures (ISFORT, 2013) (especially in urban areas) for the organization of intermodal logistics services both in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train to lorries; • Ship to train/lorries. <p>These limits are related both to scarce public and private investments for the development of these infrastructures and to the lack of an adequate political will.</p>
Lack of adequate economic resources for local public administrations	<p>Local administrations are increasingly affected by a shrinking of their budget (ISFORT, 2013). This aspect has a detrimental effect on several activities of local public administrations in the logistic sectors, like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scarce road check activities conducted by municipal police forces and low level of violations sanctioning; • Reduction in the investments on urban logistic infrastructures.

Technical and technological barriers

The national logistic infrastructures gap is a relevant technical barrier. As evidenced in many official national documents, Italy is affected by a significant delay in the logistic infrastructural development. The most significant infrastructural weakness directly affecting the logistic sector is related to a poor ports infrastructures development. In fact, in a country like Italy surrounded by the sea, more than 90% of freights delivery are conducted by lorries (Transport Ministry, 2011).

In particular, Italian southern regions have weaknesses in freights infrastructures development, compared to the northern regions. Such a delay, both in quantitative and qualitative terms, affects

²⁶ Evidences collected by IEFE-Bocconi University during the research regional project OPTILOG (<http://www.optilog.it/>)

the development of transport infrastructures and reduces the opportunities to organize more efficient freights transport services.

Finally, there are technical limitations in electric freights vehicles technology. Electric vehicles do not guarantee the required performances standards for national freights delivery. Electric vehicles are more attractive at urban scale, particularly where restricted traffic areas are in place. For instance, a last-generation small-size commercial vehicle has only 100 km of autonomy with a full recharge cycle of 5 hours, which are not always sufficient to guarantee a standard workflow. Besides this, the battery weight (around 1 ton) reduces the maximum payload. Main technical and technological barriers in the freight transport sector can be summarized as follows (table below).

Table 13 Main technical and technological barriers in the freight transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
National logistic infrastructures gap	As evidenced in many official national documents, Italy is affected by a significant delay in the logistic infrastructural development ²⁷ . The most significant infrastructural weakness directly affecting the logistic sector is related to a poor ports infrastructures development (ISFORT, 2013). In fact, in a country like Italy surrounded by sea, more than 90% of freights delivery are conducted by lorries (Transport Ministry, 2011).
Italian southern regions weaknesses in freights infrastructures development	Italian southern regions are characterized by bigger weaknesses in logistic infrastructures equipment compared to the northern part of Italy (ISFORT, 2013). Such a delay, both in quantitative and qualitative terms, reduces the opportunities to organize more efficient freights transport services.
Technical limitations in electric freights vehicles technology	Electric vehicles do not guarantee the required performances standards for national freights delivery. Electric vehicles are more attractive at urban scale, particularly where restricted traffic areas are in place.

Table 14 summarizes the barriers to energy efficiency in the goods transport sector identified within literature, subdividing them according to their impact (high, medium, low). Given the lack of quantitative comparative assessments on the barriers in literature, the following impact assessment derives from a qualitative expert evaluation based on the authors' knowledge. For this national report (included as Annex), the identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the criteria mentioned in the main report "Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in buildings and transport".

²⁷http://www.repubblica.it/economia/2013/06/09/news/italia_il_ritardo_delle_infrastrutture_ci_costato_24_miliardi_di_pil-60727307/

Table 14 Assessment of barriers in the goods/freight transport

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Low cooperation between logistic operators
	Low probability to be sanctioned for irregular parking
	Several economic operators organize by itself their freights supply (Conto Proprio)
	High outsourcing level of main logistic operators
	Old logistics vehicles
	Italian southern regions weaknesses in freights infrastructures development
	National logistic infrastructures gap
Medium	High importance for logistics operators to show their logo in the last mile delivery and control the quality of delivery (brand identity)
	Lack of infrastructures for intermodal logistics (especially in urban areas)
	E-commerce rapid growth
	Regulatory aspects limits the growing of green logistic solutions (both national and regional level)
	High bureaucracy in the logistic sector (both national and regional level)
	High fragmentation of local traffic regulation
	Few external/international investments in Italian logistic sector
	Lack of adequate economic resources for local public administrations
Low	Technical limitations in electric freights vehicles technology
	Lack of high level managerial competencies
	Strong lobbies block political reforms

3. BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The following chapter puts the barriers mapped through literature in relation with policy instruments currently in force in Italy and highlights which policy instruments are contributing (or could possibly contribute) to overcome them.

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

Looking at the building sector, it seems that the mix of policy instruments implemented in Italy addresses several existing barriers to energy efficiency.

Social, cultural and educational barriers are mainly tackled through **awareness raising campaigns**. These are conducted by the national energy agency ENEA, as well as, at regional and local levels, by regional and local energy agencies which are active in their respective territories. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning the numerous campaigns promoted by private and civil society actors, such as environmental and professional associations, aimed at raising awareness. These often focus on a specific target group, such as young population or children, and envisage different targets and tools according to **gender/age differences**.

Also the issue **fragmentation of home ownership** is being addressed by specific awareness raising campaigns, which aim to inform people living in condominiums about the possibilities and benefits to jointly renovate their homes. Furthermore, the growing ESCOs market in Italy (Energy Strategy Group, 2015), focussing more on big energy efficiency projects, could contribute to overcome this relevant Italian barrier in order to boost energy efficiency renovation of Italian residential sector. However, the reliance on ESCOs for interventions on private houses/condominiums is not yet widespread in Italy (Energy Strategy Group, 2015).

Regarding **economic barriers**, the Italian government launched different economic policy instruments aimed at reducing the impact of economic barriers on buildings energy efficiency improvement. In particular, a set of three main economic policy instruments were launched targeted to specific building owners, and namely tax deduction mechanism targeted to families, Thermal Account targeted to national and regional/local public authorities and White Certificate mechanism to industrial and commercial buildings. Several **awareness raising campaigns** are in place in order to inform consumers about energy savings possibilities connected with energy renovation and the purchase of more energy efficient appliances, as well as a more virtuous use of appliances. As shown above, **fuel poverty** concerns are increasing in Italy since energy costs are assuming a relevant weight in some parts of population. **Transparent billing** is another policy instrument which can serve to this purpose and is being used as a tool to increase consumers' awareness (AEEG, 2010), as well as to enhance their knowledge on the **weight of energy costs**.

Since the economic crisis has tightened the possibility to **access credit** from bank and financial institutions, which can be among the enabling conditions of an energy renovation decision by families, policies such as the **establishment of dedicated funds** (Kyoto fund until 2014 and since 2015 the National Energy Efficiency Fund) have been put in place to facilitate the access to financial resources for energy renovation interventions. Also **tax deductions** for energy renovations and purchase of energy efficient appliances are in line with this direction, although they target only specific parts of population.

Moreover, the definition of **quality rules for ESCOs** and of **an official list** of ESCOs could contribute to tackle the barrier of access to credit (Energy Strategy Group, 2015), since ESCOs assume the financial risks and therefore could be used by private owners as means to finance their interventions by a third-party financing. However, the reliance on ESCOs for interventions on private houses/condominiums is not yet widespread in Italy (Energy Strategy Group, 2015).

As far as **institutional barriers** are concerned, the complex administrative structure and the government articulation in diverse administrative sub-national levels in Italy (Regions, Provinces - now abolished and substituted in specific cases by "Metropolitan Cities", and Municipalities) generates **policy coordination** problems (De Paoli, 2014) and **dyscrasia between norms** at diverse levels (Cresme Ricerche, Legambiente, 2013). At this purpose, the government has established a **coordination structure** named "Energy efficiency control room" (Cabina di Regia efficienza energetica). Other barriers linked to heavy bureaucracy and inefficiency of the public administration (Energy Strategy Group, 2014) are currently being addressed by **regulations and reforms of the public administration**, not specifically focused on energy efficiency.

Finally, among the **organizational barriers**, the **lack of mediating subjects** such as installers and technicians has been highlighted. Also this aspect is being addressed through dedicated **awareness raising campaigns**, as well as through specific **training platform and e-learning courses** for experts on energy efficiency in buildings set up by ENEA – national energy efficiency.

The overview of barriers and policy instruments in force shows that further awareness raising and information provision to consumers, home-owners and building administrators are needed, to spread a culture of saving and to inform about benefits and opportunities of energy efficiency.

Furthermore, economic instruments or facilitating mechanisms to improve the access to available financial sources would be required. Also, action would be needed to address inefficiencies of bureaucracy and increase governance and policy coordination among the multiple administrative levels.

Table 15 Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Gender and age differences	<i>Probably differentiated at local/regional/national scale, should be further investigated by studies/surveys.</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes
	Group as push factor to energy efficiency investments	<i>Probably differentiated at local/regional/national scale, should be further investigated by studies/surveys.</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes
	Lack of a "culture of saving"	<i>Probably differentiated at local/regional/national scale, should be further investigated by studies/surveys.</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes
	Fragmentation of home ownership (due to relevant presence of condominiums)	<i>National/regional/local</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes, Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115).
	Lack of technical expertise of building administrators	<i>National/regional/local</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes.
Economic	Little incidence of energy costs on companies/families	<i>Probably differentiated at local/regional/national scale, should be further investigated by studies/surveys.</i>	Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes, Transparent billing methods (Deliberation 18 November 2008 – ARG/com 164/08 of the

			AEEG).
	Split incentives and principal-agent problem	<i>National</i>	Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115).
	Lowering in purchasing power due to economic crisis	<i>National</i>	Tax deductions (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and renewed several times with modifications)
	Difficulty to access credit caused by the economic stagnation	<i>National</i>	<p>Kyoto fund (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and implemented through following acts) and National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”) (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102);</p> <p>Tax deductions (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and renewed several times with modifications),</p> <p>Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for certified ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115).</p>
Institutional	Lack of normative schemes	<i>National</i>	/

	Dyscrasia between national, supra-national and local norms and lack of policy coordination	<i>National</i>	Energy efficiency control room” (Cabina di Regia efficienza energetica)
	Low-quality bureaucracy level	<i>National</i>	Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures, Reforms to increase efficiency in the public administration.
	Lack of mediating subjects such as installers and technicians	<i>National</i>	ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings.
	Lack of control for non-compliant building administrators and enforcement schemes	<i>National</i>	/
Technical/ technological	Technical limitations (old age and low EE performance of the existing stock)	<i>National</i>	Issue addressed in several policies.

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

Barriers and policy instruments

Looking at the set of energy efficiency policy instruments defined in Italy for people and freights transport, it appears that some barriers (promotion of green vehicles, bio fuels, ITS, coordination among different logistics operators) have been addressed by policy instruments in place. On the contrary, other barriers, mainly related to the strengthening of people and freight transport infrastructures, received less attention in the Italian policies framework.

Therefore investments to fill the gap of sustainable mobility infrastructures and services would be required, as well as information to consumers about the benefits and opportunities of sustainable mobility and to promote a more diffused culture of sustainable travel behaviours.

For the freight transport, beyond measures to address the infrastructural gap, also capacity building and coordination mechanisms for operators would be necessary, together with actions to address inefficiencies caused by bureaucracy.

People transport sector

Social, cultural and educational barriers are mainly tackled through awareness raising campaigns. These are conducted by the Ministry of the Environment, as well as, at regional and local levels, by regional and local public authorities which operate in their respective territories. Furthermore, campaigns are also promoted by private (e.g. the managing authority of national railway network and the local managing authorities of local public transport services) and civil society actors (e.g. environmental associations, professional associations, consumer associations, etc.) in order to promote a wider use of public transports especially in urban areas.

Economic barriers

Italian policy instruments show a clear intention of the central government (supported by regional and local public authorities) to overcome the main technical and economic barriers threatening the large diffusion of less polluting vehicles and more sustainable fuels. In order to overcome the main economic barriers slowing down the renewal of Italian car fleets, the Italian government set a variety of **subsidies** supporting the purchasing of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), methane and electric vehicles. Instead, technical barriers to a nation-wide dissemination of green-vehicles (linked mainly to poor refuel/recharge infrastructures) were tackled by the Italian government both by a **national plan for the promotion of the methane infrastructures** in Italian urban areas and by a **plan** supported by **funds** dedicated to set up a wider national **network of electric vehicles charging points**.

Institutional/organizational barriers

In relation to the scarce diffusion of Bio-methane, the Italian Government (in accordance with the EU directive) set an obligation for national fuels sellers to use a quota of biofuels and incentives to the producers of biomethane.

Freight transport sector

Educational barriers in the freights transport sector are not currently addressed by Italian policy instruments, since specific awareness campaigns have not been launched.

Economic barriers in the freights transport sector are mainly tackled by Italy's "National Plan for logistics 2011/2020". This plan, beyond involving all the main national logistic operators in a participatory process, defined a series of measures aimed to improve the level of cooperation among the different operators. In order to give concrete tools to improve cooperation, the national government gave rise to a national logistics platform (called UIRNET) which enabled the sharing of information and data among logistic operators.

Also some measures launched by municipalities (e.g. the institution of urban low emission zones or restricted access areas to more pollutants vehicles) had a relevant impact on the renewal of the logistic fleets.

Technical and technological barriers in the freight transports, related mainly to scarce diffusion of green vehicles in the logistic sector, have been tackled, as for the private mobility, by a plan to set up a national network of electric vehicles charging points.

Table 16 Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector**Transportation of people**

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Car ownership (private transport)	<i>National</i>	<p>Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (L. 9 April 2009, N.5 and L. 26 June 2012, N.134);</p> <p>National electric car sharing project in cities (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment);</p> <p>Road tax (tax exemption for electric vehicles and discount on car assurance) and regional schemes for tax exemption for LPG and methane vehicles;</p> <p>Awareness campaigns and Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week;</p> <p>National programmes and funds aimed to improve public transport services.</p>
	Low satisfaction for the public transport	<i>National</i>	<p>Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L. 27 December 2014, n.147);</p> <p>Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21);</p> <p>Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile);</p> <p>Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs);</p> <p>National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);</p> <p>Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L. 27 December 2014, n.147);</p> <p>Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds);</p>

			National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);
	Low acknowledgement of environmental/social benefits of public transport use (private transport)	<i>National</i>	National Green Procurement Plan (Piano d'Azione Nazionale per il GPP) (D.M. 11 April 2008, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013) (public administrations); Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs); Awareness campaigns and Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week.
	Bike perceived as dangerous and not compatible with some weather conditions (private transport)	<i>National</i>	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs); Funding for energy efficiency, renewable energy and bike-sharing (L. 24 December, N.244); Awareness campaigns and Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week.
	Insufficient safety, lack of adequate space for walking (private transport)	<i>Local</i>	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs); Urban Traffic Plans (Piano Urbano del Traffico) (Dlgs. 30 April 1992, n.285); Awareness campaigns and Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week.
	Chaotic parking (private transport)	<i>Local</i>	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile); Urban Traffic Plans (Piano Urbano del Traffico) (Dlgs. 30 April 1992, n.285).
Economic	Critical economic	<i>National/ Local</i>	Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano

	condition of several public transport management authorities (public transport)		<p>quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L 27 December 2014, N.147);</p> <p>Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21);</p> <p>National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);</p> <p>Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L 27 December 2014, N.147);</p> <p>Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds);</p> <p>National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws).</p>
	Fragmentation of public transport operators (public transport)	<i>National/ Local</i>	/
	High evasion rate of public transport tickets (public transport)	<i>Local</i>	/
	Spending review conducted by central government on public transport services (public transport)	<i>National/Regional</i>	Several European and national funds for promotion of sustainable urban transport measures
	Low economic viability of the investment necessary for the realization of high-capacity transport in low-density residential areas (public transport)	<i>National</i>	<p>Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L 27 December 2014, N.147);</p> <p>Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21);</p> <p>National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);</p> <p>Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L 27 December 2014, N.147);</p>

			Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds); National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws).
	Urban Sprawl	<i>National</i>	/
	High cost of batteries for electric vehicles (public/private transport)	<i>National</i>	National funds for local public transports, Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (L. 9 April 2009, N.5 and L. 26 June 2012, N.134).
Institutional	Reduction of national public investments in the public transport sector	<i>National/Regional</i>	Several European and national funds for promotion of sustainable urban transport measures
	Lack of a national strategy for bike and pedestrian mobility	<i>National</i>	/
	Lack of an Italian Transport Authority for a long time (public transport)	<i>National</i>	Since September 2013 National Transport Authority is fully operative
	Delays in the definition of the strategic national plan	<i>Regional</i>	/
	Scarce attention in the public transport concession of qualitative standards of services	<i>National</i>	/
	Lack of a long term vision regarding the future of transport infrastructures	<i>National</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012).
Infrastructural and technical	Old Italian public transport fleets (public transport)	<i>Local</i>	Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L. 27 December 2014, N.147); National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws).
	Few underground line in Italian cities (public transport)	<i>Local</i>	National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws).

	Lack of recharge stations for electric vehicles (private transport)	<i>National</i>	National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134); Ad-hoc fund of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on PNIRE implementation 2013-2015 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134);
	Technical limitations of electric vehicles (private transport)	<i>National</i>	National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134); Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (L. 9 April 2009, N.5 and L. 26 June 2012, N.134).
	Scarce diffusion of Bio-methane in Italy (private transport)	<i>National</i>	Incentives for the promotion of biofuels in transport sector, Promotion of use of biomethane in transports (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28).

Transportation of goods/freight transport

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Low cooperation between logistic operators	<i>National</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012); National Logistics Platform UIRNET (Sistema Nazionale della Logistica Integrata e Intermodalità) (D.M 20 June 2005, N.18T).
	Low probability to be sanctioned for irregular parking	<i>Local</i>	/
	Lack of high level managerial competencies	<i>National</i>	National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (Piano di Azione Nazionale sui Sistemi Intelligenti di Trasporto) (D.L. 12 February 2014, n.44).
	Several economic operators	<i>Local</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics

	organize by itself their freights supply (Conto Proprio)		2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012); Municipal limits to city center access
	High outsourcing level of main logistic operators	<i>National</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012).
	E-commerce rapid growth	<i>National</i>	/
	Brand identity	<i>National</i>	/
	Strong lobbies block political reforms	<i>National</i>	/
Economic and Institutional	High fragmentation of local traffic regulation	<i>Local</i>	/
	Few external/international investments in Italian logistic sector	<i>National</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012).
	High bureaucracy in the logistic sector (both national and regional level)	<i>National/local</i>	/
	Regulatory aspects limits the growing of green logistic solutions (both national and regional level)	<i>National/Regional/local</i>	/
	Lack of infrastructures for intermodal logistics (especially in urban areas)	<i>National/Regional/local</i>	/
	Lack of adequate economic resources for local public administrations	<i>Regional/Local</i>	National "Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation" funds 2012 and 2013 (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric).
Technical and technological	National logistic infrastructures gap	<i>National</i>	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012). National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (Piano di Azione Nazionale sui Sistemi Intelligenti di Trasporto) (D.L. 12 February 2014, n.44). Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures

			(Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21).
	Italian southern regions weaknesses in freights infrastructures development	National	Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 May 2012).
	Technical limitations in electric freights vehicles technology	National	National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134).

4. KEY FINDINGS

Buildings:

Efficiency performances in the Italian building sector can be considered relatively high with respect to other Member States. However, the achievement of further efficiency gains is strongly bounded to a variety of barriers affecting different actors involved and at different degrees. Main limitations in the building sector are:

- lack of a 'culture of saving' that limits, and sometimes neutralizes, the effect of policies aimed at boosting efficiency gains;
- old age of the existing building stocks and the great historical importance of such buildings which strongly limit the technical options for energy-efficiency renovations and retrofits;
- dyscrasia between the national/supra-national and local governance, Italy being characterized by a high regional fragmentation which produces insufficient policy coordination, uncertainty among actors involved as well as delays in policy implementation;
- lack of monitoring and controls which generate free-riding behaviours and other market failures;
- the issue of split incentives and principal-agent problem, which in Italy assumes relevant dimension given the high ownership fragmentation in the real-estate market (relevant presence of condominiums);
- economic stagnation, which limits the access to credit and the expenditure budget for energy efficiency investments, both for households and public administrations.

Besides these, behavioural and social issues (misperception of economic returns, different purchasing choice in presence of other people, limited trust in local and national public administration) and a lack of technical knowledge (both in households and in mediating subjects such as ESCo, building administrators etc.) further limit the adoption process of more efficient technologies.

The overview of barriers and policy instruments in force shows that further awareness raising and information provision to consumers, home-owners and building administrators are needed, to spread a culture of saving and to inform about benefits and opportunities of energy efficiency. Furthermore, economic instruments or facilitating mechanisms to improve the access to available financial sources would be required. Also, action would be needed to address inefficiencies of

bureaucracy and increase governance and policy coordination among the multiple administrative levels.

Transport

The transport sector in Italy is responsible of a high environmental pressure, since an inefficient use of energy is still present both in the people and freights transportation.

In relation to public and private transport sector, Italy is still a country where private mobility is prevalent, even if in some urban areas public transport services are well developed and contribute to reduce car use. The main barriers affecting the achievement of further efficiency gains in public and private transport sector are:

- Public transport supply in Italy is still limited in several Italian cities (with some remarkable exceptions), with significant problems in terms of quality and numbers of services. For many Italians, public transport is not reliable and attractive and for this reason they prefer not to use it;
- Soft mobility (bike and pedestrian) is less developed than in other European countries. This is strictly related both to cultural aspects and to the lack of adequate infrastructures in urban areas (bike and pedestrian pathways, etc.);
- Italy is one of the most motorised country in the world. Car is still a status symbol for a large part of population;
- In the last years, due to economic crisis and the national spending review process, several financial cuts were done to national funds dedicated to the regional and local public transport services. As local public transports are highly dependent from these resources (ordinary activities cover only a limited part of their annual budgets), these relevant cuts generate increasing difficulties in guaranteeing high public transport services levels;
- Innovative forms of private mobility (for example electric mobility, etc.) are not developed, as there is still a lack of adequate infrastructures (electric public recharge area in case of electric vehicles). Moreover it is important to highlight the importance given at national level to the promotion of biofuels and biomethane.

In relation to freights transport sector, the achievement of further efficiency gains is strongly bounded to a variety of barriers affecting mainly the logistic operators involved in national and urban freights delivery. Main limitations in the logistic sector are:

- Very competitive market, where it is difficult to set up forms of collaboration among the main logistic operators in order to reach more efficient solutions (sharing of vehicles and/or common usage of urban logistic platforms);
- Italy is affected by high delays in the main national and regional logistic infrastructures development and improvements (ports, inter-mobility nodes, etc.);
- Many competences in the urban transport regulation at urban level (access to city centres, etc.) are delegated to the municipal level without an adequate coordination at regional and national level. This aspect led to a high fragmentation of legislative frameworks that impede an efficient organization of logistic services and to create national business model usable in different cities;
- Italian logistic operators appear affected by significant problems in recruiting high-educated logistic manager and working forces. These education deficiencies limited their innovative capacity;

- All the previous barriers, together with a high bureaucracy level, create an economic framework where private investments (national and international) in the logistic sector are not perceived as attractive.

On one side, some barriers (promotion of green vehicles, bio fuels, ITS, coordination among different logistics operators) have been addressed by policy instruments in place. On the other side, other barriers, mainly related to the strengthening of people and freight transport infrastructures for more energy efficient and sustainable mobility received less attention in the Italian policies framework. Therefore investments aimed at filling the gap of sustainable mobility infrastructures and services would be required, as well as information to consumers about the benefits and opportunities of sustainable mobility in order to promote a more diffused culture of sustainable travel behaviours.

For the freight transport, beyond the measures to address the infrastructural gap, also capacity building and coordination mechanisms for operators would be necessary, together with actions to address inefficiencies caused by bureaucracy.

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D.2.1 WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT WITHIN EACH PARTNER COUNTRY-NATIONAL REPORTS

DATE 09 AUGUST 2015

HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

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Serbia

National Report

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

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ACRONYMS

DHS	District Heating System
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEAP	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
EPBD	Energy Performance Building Directive
EUE	Efficient Use of Energy
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating, Air Conditioning
Mtoe	Million tons of oil equivalents
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SCTM	Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Values of basic energy efficiency indicators in Serbia are comparable with appropriate values of countries in the region, but significantly above average values for EU countries. In more detail, Serbian energy intensity in 2010 was more than 4 four times higher than the EU-27 average (0.642 kg oe/\$2005 vs. 0.132 kg oe/\$2005 in EU). If the ratio of primary energy consumption and GDP corrected compared to parity of purchasing power is analysed, ratio of Serbian and EU-27's indicators is higher than 2 (0.292 kg oe/\$2005 vs. 0.137 kg oe/\$2005 in EU) (IEA, Independent energy statistics, 2015). Still, the fact is that the consumption of energy per capita is almost 50% lower than EU average.

The buildings sector provides significant opportunities for energy savings. Estimation from the World Bank's report is that the building sector in Serbia can have saving potential of 16% of the final energy consumption (Econoler 2012). The highest share of energy consumed in buildings is related to heating (more than 60%), so the most of energy saving potential is in relation with thermal insulation and heat losses reduction. Almost 65% of buildings in residential sector are more than 35 years old (constructed in the period before 1981). This reflects on their relatively high specific heat consumption. The calculated values for specific heat consumption from project National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia are in the range from 80 to more than 300 kWh/m²/year, while the current average of specific heat consumption in this building subsector is estimated to be approximately 160 kWh/m²/year.

Main social, cultural and educational barriers to implementation of energy efficiency in the buildings sector are presented in this report. From the list of social barriers, untypical is the belief of citizens that the price of electricity will remain low in the future. This barrier arose as a consequence of experiences in last 25 years, and using electricity price as an instrument of social policy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a). For social segmentation besides previously stated fact of at-risk-of-poverty rate of 24.6% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015). Main economic barriers in the building sector are Serbian specific (Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering, Low Electricity Prices, Public sector budgeting does not allow municipalities to keep their baseline budget for a few years after energy efficiency projects). Concerning institutional barriers, as the Ministry of Energy and Mining is recognized as the key player in the most measures and instruments implementation stated in the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan, rising of its capacity is of great importance. Introduction of energy management systems in the public and commercial sectors and appropriate, proposed instruments should help capacity building at local level.

Transport sector in Serbia in general can be divided to railway, road, urban, air and inland water transport. Road traffic is the main mode of transport. In 2014, the share of road transport in passenger transport was 59.2%, while the share in freight transport was 38.9% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication 2014b). Number of passenger cars per 1000 inhabitants in 2013 was 247, while 49.7% of households had their own car. It should be noted that the age structure of vehicles is unsatisfactory. Approximately 52% of cars are older than 15 years, while only 4% of cars are less than one year old (Prvulović, et al. 2008). Renewal of vehicle fleet is necessary and some marketing analysis (Serbian association of car importers) show that Serbian market potential is 100,000 new vehicles per year. Although this number was overcome in previous years, it should be kept in mind that only between 15 and 25% of the first time registered vehicles were new, while the rest were imported used vehicles of all types.

Main social, cultural and educational barriers to implementation of energy efficiency in the transport sector are presented in this report. Social and cultural barriers are relevant for passenger transport during the purchasing of cars, as well as for swift to and selection of public transport. Targeted public information campaigns, as well as training and education are important, envisaged instruments for overcoming majority of identified barriers. Main economic barriers in the transport sector are related to low purchasing power of Serbian citizens. It can be expected that the overall economic growth will be the positive signal for removing or diminishing of identified barriers. Main institutional barriers in the transport sector are similar to those in building sector but with additional problem: the Ministry in charge for energy proposes measures that are in the competence of other institutions (Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry in charge of Economy, Ministry in charge of Transport, Ministry on Interior). The focus of interest of these institutions is usually not at energy efficiency.

The identified barriers in buildings and transport sectors are assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the following criteria:

- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

Law on rational use of energy that was adopted in 2013 (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2013), for the first time established legislative and legal framework for efficient use of energy in the Republic Serbia. The law determines some minimum standards and requirements on energy efficiency, as well as incentives, which are expected to create huge demand for energy efficiency services. These standards and requirements include: labelling of energy related products, minimal requirements for energy efficiency in the production, transmission and distribution of electricity, heat, oil and natural gas, incentives for the rational and efficient use of energy, penalties for inefficient use of energy, framework for the development of Energy Efficient Services Companies, etc. However, more needs to be done in the near future for full implementation of this Law, primary related to adoption of the comprehensive set of secondary legislation and creation of effective policy instruments (Energy Community, 2015). Proposed policy instruments, as well as policy instruments in charge are presented in this report, together with barriers that they address.

INTRODUCTION

1. CONTEXT

Total final consumption of energy in the Republic of Serbia in 2013 was 9.091 Mtoe (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). Oil products had the largest share (used primary in transport, but also in industry and for non-energy consumption). Electricity accounted more than one quarter of final consumption. It should be noted, that significant amount of electricity is used, inefficiently for direct space heating. Electricity is produced mostly in coal fired thermal power plants (app. 65%), and large hydropower plants (app. 35%) (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). Share of small hydropower plants and biogas in electricity production is less than 0.5%, while the use PV cells and wind for electricity production is neglected. Using of renewables in final consumption, except biomass, is very low (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2014). Biomass is mainly, used in traditional way for space heating in obsolete ovens. District heating systems exist in more than 50 towns. For heat production in district heating companies, natural gas heavy fuel oil and coal are used with shares of 50%, 25% and 25%, respectively. (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). Figure 1 provides information about final energy mix.

Figure 1: Final energy consumption by energy sources in 2013 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014)

Structure of final energy consumption by sector, for the same year is presented in Figure 2. Households, industry and transport are sectors with the highest energy consumption. Roughly, sectors of households and other consumers (commercial and public sector) can be considered as a Serbian building sector, so the total share of energy consumption in building sector reached 42%.

Figure 2: Final energy consumption by sectors in 2013, (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014)

Values of basic energy efficiency indicators in Serbia are comparable with appropriate values of countries in the region, but significantly above average values for EU countries. In more detail, Serbian energy intensity in 2010 was more than 4 four times higher than the EU-27 average (0.642 kg oe/\$2005 vs. 0.132 kg oe/\$2005 in EU). If the ratio of primary energy consumption and GDP corrected compared to parity of purchasing power is analysed, ratio of Serbian and EU-27's indicators is higher than 2 (0.292 kg oe/\$2005 vs. 0.137 kg oe/\$2005 in EU) (IEA, Independent energy statistics, 2015). Still, the fact is, that the consumption of energy per capita is almost 50% lower than EU average.

According to National Building Energy Efficiency Study for Serbia, prepared for The World Bank (Econoler, 2012) total building stock in Serbia (estimated to 235 m²) is divided to single-family houses in urban and rural area (app. 50%), and multi-story, commercial and public buildings (app. 50%). The predominant building subsector is residential (190 million m²), followed by the public sector (45 million m²), and the commercial sector (18 million m²). The majority of buildings, approximately 90%, is concentrated in cities and towns. Total estimated energy consumption in building sector in 2010, according to this study, was 3.2 Mtoe, with the structure presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Estimated structure of energy consumption in building sector in 2010. (Econoler, 2012)

For residential building subsector more detailed investigation on building types and energy consumption were conducted by project National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia (M. Jovanović Popović et al., 2013). This project included extensive on site research, a detailed overview of technical documentation on characteristic buildings, and calculations of theoretical values of relevant thermal characteristics of envelopes and estimations of annual heat consumption. In Figure 4, national typology of residential buildings, according to TABULA¹ methodology, is presented. Theoretical values for heat consumption per typical type of building are calculated, and the distribution of heat consumption, by type of the building is presented in Figure 5.

¹ www.building-typology.eu

Figure 4: National typology according to the TABULA – type distribution by area (%)

From: M. Jovanović Popović et al, National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture, GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, Belgrade, 2013

Figure 5: National typology according to the TABULA – type distribution by heat consumption (%)

From: M. Jovanović Popović et al, National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture, GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, Belgrade, 2013

One of key findings of these studies is that the buildings sector provides significant opportunities for energy savings. Estimation from the World Bank's report is that the building sector in Serbia can have saving potential of 16% of the final energy consumption (Econoler 2012). The highest share of energy consumed in buildings is related to heating (more than 60%), so the most of energy saving potential is in relation with thermal insulation and heat losses reduction. Almost 65% of buildings in residential sector are more than 35 years old (constructed in the period before 1981). This reflects on their relatively high specific heat consumption. The calculated values for specific heat consumption from project National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia are in the range from 80 to more than 300 kWh/m²/year, while the current average of specific heat consumption in this building subsector is estimated to be approximately 160 kWh/m²/year.

Transport sector in Serbia in general can be divided to railway, road, urban, air and inland water transport. Basic indicators for the transport sector for the period 2009 – 2013 are presented in figures 6 and 7. Although with small annual fluctuations, urban transport has the greatest share in volume of passenger transport (47%). Share of road transport is 42%, while air transport (13%) and railway transport (5%) have significantly less shares. In freight transport, railway transport is the dominant mode (between 47 and 61% in analysed period), while the share of road transport is also significant (between 20 and 47%). Share of inland waterway transport, in analysed period was between 10 and 15% (Statistical office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication, 2014a).

Energy consumption in transport sector accounts consumption of liquid fuels (oil derivatives) electricity and natural gas. Solid fuels are not used in transport sector in Serbia since 2011. Liquid fuels are dominantly used in road transport (1.79 million tonnes in 2013). Consumption of electricity in transport sector in Serbia in 2013 was 478 GWh, mostly used in railway transport. (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication, 2014a).

Figure 6: Basic indicator of transport sector in Serbia – Passenger-km (Statistical office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication, 2014b)

Figure 7: Basic indicator of transport sector in Serbia – Tonnes-km (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication)

Railway network in Serbia is 3,809 km long. Only 7.4% of railways are double track, and 32.7% are electrified. Main line of railway network is pan European corridor 10 (887.9 km). Magistral railways account 46.4% of whole network. Density of railway network in Serbia is similar to EU average, but less than for EU members from central Europe (Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia, Poland and Slovenia). Capacities of railways are enough, but technical and operational performances are inadequate for providing quality service (Fund for Development of Economic Science, Institute of Economics, 2010).

Railways are more than 40 years old, very deteriorated and with very low speed limits. Lack of financial resources, made investments, in railway transport vehicles, infrastructure and maintenance very low in last 15 years. As a result, major maintenance cycles are not performed regularly, while ordinary maintenance of infrastructure is limited. Averagely, 17.7 km of railway is repaired annually, instead of necessary length of 191 km (Fund for Development of Economic Science, Institute of Economics, 2010). As a result, speed limits are below 80 km/h at 76% of railways, and only at 3% of railways are allowed speeds between 100 and 120 km/h. Only 44% of railways meet EU standards in regards to maximal allowed load of 22.5 t per axle.

Railway vehicles are technologically very obsolete, inappropriate in number and structure. Share of inoperative vehicles is between 26 and 61%. As an indication, in 2009 daily average 129 locomotives were in operation (34% less than necessary), 130 passenger coaches (46% less than necessary) and 3,636 waggons (27% less than necessary). Availability of wagons is the main limit for freight railway transport.

However, in the structure of land transport, railway freight traffic has the largest share (39.2% in 2014), while the share in the passenger transport was only 6.4% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication, 2014b). Public passenger transport is commercially unprofitable at significant number of lines.

Serbian road infrastructure consists of road network with length of approximately 44,000 km. Road network is well developed concerning density, but the quality of roads and their performances are below the European level. Generally, roads have enough capacity for present and midterm demands. Length of state roads of the 1st category is 4,856 km (including 669 km of highways), length of state roads of 2nd category is 9,862 km, and rest are local roads (Fund for Development of Economic Science, Institute of Economics, 2010).

As a consequence of low level of investments for maintenance and reconstruction for a long time, the current state of road network is not satisfactory. Only 14% of the 1st and the 2nd category roads are up to 10 years old, while 32% of state roads are more than 20 years old. If the entire road network is analysed it can be concluded that 40% of the sections have crushed stone and earth carriageways. More than half of local roads are inadequate for meeting modern traffic demand. Such state of road network has negative influence to the traffic safety and quality of service. Also, it makes maintenance and operational costs higher.

Road traffic is the main mode of transport. In 2014, the share of road transport in passenger transport was 59.2%, while the share in freight transport was 38.9% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication 2014b). Number of passenger cars per 1000 inhabitants in 2013 was 247, while 49.7% of households had their own car. Number of new registered vehicles had growth in previous period (figures 8 and 9) (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistics of transport and communication, 2014b).

It should be noted that the age structure of vehicles is unsatisfactory. Approximately 52% of cars are older than 15 years, while only 4% of cars are less than one year old (Prvulović, et al. 2008). Current state and forecast of the number of vehicles by age group, in Serbia, are presented in figure 10 (Marinković et al. 2012)

Figure 8: Number of registered passenger cars in period 2008 – 2013 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Transport and telecommunications, 2014 a)

Figure 9: Number of registered trucks, commercial vehicles and other vehicles in period 2008 – 2013 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Transport and telecommunications, 2014 a)

Figure 10: Current state and forecast of the number of vehicles by age group, period 2001–2025 (Marinković et al. 2012).

Renewal of vehicle fleet is necessary and some marketing analysis (Serbian association of car importers) show that Serbian market potential is 100000 new vehicles per year. Although this number was overcome in previous years, it should be kept in mind that only between 15 and 25% of the first time registered vehicles were new, while the rest were imported used vehicles of all types.

Republic of Serbia has developed network of inland waterways. This network includes rivers Danube, Sava, Tisa and channels of hydro system Danube – Tisa – Danube. Overall length of waterways is 1680 km with density of 21.7 km/1,000 km². Danube is part of Pan-European Corridor VII, and approximately 85% of total freight transport in inland waterways is conducted by it. There are 9 international ports in Serbia. Ports are inadequate in capacity, and the equipment is obsolete and inefficient (Fund for Development of Economic Science, Institute of Economics, 2010).

Companies in inland waterway transport have on disposal about 400 vessels, with capacity of 403833 tones and total power of 60000 kW. More than 77% of vessels are used for transport of dry cargo. Generally, river fleet is in the bad condition, due to age structure and technological obsolete. The share of inland waterway transport is constantly decreasing in last years.

Issues related to public urban and suburban transport in Serbia are under jurisdiction of local self-governments. According to the Strategy of Traffic Development (The Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007), mobility in Serbia is 2 to 3 times lower than in the developed EU countries. Daily transport, mostly in urban areas, is responsible for 96% of total number of passengers, and for 70% of passenger-km. Public transport in urban areas is significantly larger than public suburban transport. Approximately 2/3 of travels are conducted by public urban and suburban transport, while the rest is the transport between the cities. As more than 1/3 of Serbian population live in 6 largest cities, 95% of urban transport is realized in them. A railway transport as a mode of urban and suburban transport is presented only in Belgrade.

In Serbia, there are two airports equipped for international flights: "Nikola Tesla" in Belgrade and "Constantine the Great" in Niš, as well as two airports for internal civil transport: Vršac and Bor. More than 75% of passenger and 90% of freight transport are realized through Nikola Tesla airport. Airports' capacity are more than 5.6 million passengers per year.

1.1 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Improvement of energy efficiency at supply side, in energy production and transformation, as well as at the demand side, in sectors of energy consumption, is recognized as one of the key elements of energy policy in the Republic of Serbia. Energy efficiency improvement is strategically recognized as an instrument that contributes to security of energy supply, industry competitiveness and standard of citizens. Also, energy efficiency could contribute to decrease of import dependency and reduction of negative influence of energy sector to environment. According to Draft of Energy sector development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia up to 2025, with the projections up to 2030 (The Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015 a), energy efficiency is named as "new, indigenous energy source" and it is defined as one of the basic elements for ensuring energy security, and for the transition to sustainable energy development. Refurbishment in the building sector and the introduction of energy management system in the public sector are stated as priority activities.

Republic of Serbia is in the process of accession to the EU, with the status of a candidate country. However, Serbia has signed and ratified in 2006 the Treaty establishing the Energy Community (between the EU, presented by European Council and the countries of the South-Eastern European region, 2005). Under the Treaty, Contracting Parties have agreed to implement core parts of the EU *acquis communautaire* in energy and environment. The main intent of the Treaty is to make Energy Community Contracting Parties to keep pace with EU developments and continuously align their regulatory frameworks in the energy and related sectors to those of the EU.

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", No. 25/2013) (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2013) is the basic law in the field of energy efficiency, as it regulates efficient use of energy in production, transmission, distribution and consumption. Enabling and initiating a responsible, rational and sustainable long-term use of energy is the basic goal of this Law. It proposes establishing a wide market of energy efficiency services, as well as behavioural and habitual changes with regard to the use of energy. Also, minimum requirements for energy efficiency, energy management for large public consumers with obligations for the implementation, monitoring and reporting on measures taken in regard to reduce energy consumption, energy audits and other provisions that encourage or impose a rational and efficient use of energy are introduced by the Law.

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy establishes a legal framework for the implementation of three basic EU energy efficiency directives: Directive 2006/32/EZ on energy end-use efficiency and energy services, Directive 2010/30/EU on the indication by labelling and standard product's information of the consumption of energy and other resources of energy-related products, and Directive 2010/31/EU on energy performance of buildings. The Law on Construction and Planning (the

Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a) also transposes relevant provisions of last stated directive.

In accordance with the commitments arising from the Treaty establishing the Energy Community, the Ministry in charge for energy issues (presently, Ministry of Mining and Energy) has prepared and the Government of the Republic of Serbia adopted in 2010, the first National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2010 – 2012 (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2010). This plan stipulates mean indicative energy savings target for two years period (amounts to 1.5% of final domestic energy consumption compared to year 2008, i.e. 0.1254 Mtoe). Also in the document was presented the ultimate goal of saving 9% of final energy or 0.752 Mtoe, up to 2018 (the ninth year after the beginning of Action Plan implementation). The same goal was sustained in the Second National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2013 – 2015 that was adopted by the Government in 2013 (The Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c). Action Plans for Energy Efficiency contain measures for energy efficiency directed to three sectors: buildings (residential, commercial and public service), industry and transport.

Ministry in charge for energy activities (presently Ministry of Mining and Energy) is main institution responsible for energy efficiency legal framework, as well as for implementation of energy efficiency programs and activities. Transposition and implementation of all EU directives and regulations concerning energy efficiency is under the authority of this ministry. Ministry of Mining and Energy is responsible for implementation of Action Plan for Energy Efficiency, and it is in charge for monitoring, verification and evaluation of energy savings achieved by implementation of measures stated in the Action Plan. This Ministry is also in charge for regulations related to the mandatory labelling of products` impact caused by consumption of energy and other resources. Ministry organizes, conducts and monitors energy management systems, and also verifies realization of energy managements` goals. In transport sector, besides Ministry of Mining and Energy, very important institutions are Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, Ministry of Interior, as well as local self-governments (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).

Besides Ministry in charge for energy issues, institutions that are actively engaged in energy efficiency improvement are Vojvodina Provincial Secretariat for Energy and Mineral Resources, as well as local self-governments. Provincial Secretariat for Energy and Mineral Resources implements projects and carries out programs aimed to energy savings, both at supply and demand side. According to the Law on Efficient use of energy, this regional body is an entity of energy management system, with responsibility to collect data and report to the Ministry in charge for energy activities.

Chamber of Engineers is responsible for the training of engineers for improvement of energy efficiency in buildings. Only the engineers with appropriate certificates issued by Chamber of Engineers are authorized to perform energy audits and to issue appropriate certificates of energy performances of buildings.

All local governments in Serbia are members of Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities (SCTM) - association of Serbian local self-governments. SCTM represents the common interests of local governments. In addition, it act`s in the interest of local authorities and lobby vis-à-vis central government in the process of defining strategic directions and the regulations of importance for local governments. SCTM provides various services to members through training, consultation and technical assistance. It deals with issues, which are in portfolio of every local government, including local finances, international cooperation, social services, local economic development, regional cooperation, communal services, urban planning, environmental protection, local energy end energy efficiency, renewables, and numerous other activities that contribute to the development of local communities.

According to the Law of Efficient Use of Energy the responsibilities of local self-governments are similar to these of the Provincial Secretariat concerning collecting data and reporting on evaluation and verification of action plan's activities. However, local self-governments are obliged to prepare energy efficiency programs and action plans. All municipalities with more than 20000 inhabitants should introduce energy management system, as well as to propose the program for improvement of energy efficiency in transport. As, according to the Energy Law, tariff system in district heating is within the responsibility of local self-governments, their role in shifting to billing according to delivered heat, instead on flat rate is significant. Local self-government is located, in the government system, at the closest position to the citizens, so it has the role of motivator and promoter of desired behaviour.

The Law of Efficient Energy Use envisages the founding of the Budget Fund for the Improvement of Energy Efficiency. This fund for financing projects on efficient energy use is considered as one of the key mechanisms for achieving the goals of the Action Plan. The Law also leaves the possibility to Vojvodina (as a region) or municipalities to use own budgets and other resources for establishing the regional/local funds for financing energy efficiency projects. Considering the necessary resources for financing energy efficiency projects, it is obvious that providing investing represents one of the mayor challenges.

Summary of proposed measures in the Second National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency of the Republic of Serbia, relevant, proposed instruments for their implementation in household, commercial and transport sector, as well as relevant institutions involved in the formulation/delivery/evaluation of the policy instruments are as follows:

Household sector

Measure:	H1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings
Instruments:	Financial instrument (credit line, subsidy, loan) Information and mandatory information measures (Energy audit)
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, Ministry of Construction and Urban Planning, autonomous province, local self-government
Measure:	H2 - New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD
Instruments:	Provisions (Standards and norms): Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 24/11) (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011) Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 61/11) (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b)
Institutions:	Ministry of Construction and Urban Planning, Chamber of Engineers
Measure:	H3 - Promotion of the use of energy-efficient household appliances
Instruments:	Information and mandatory information measures (public information campaigns, energy labelling):

Regulation on the types of energy related products that require labelling of consumption of energy and other resource (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 92/2013) (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2013 a)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household refrigerating appliances (Official Gazette of the RS, No 17/14); (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014a)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household washing machines (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14, (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014b)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household dishwashers (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14); (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 c)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric ovens (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14); (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 d)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric bulbs and lamps (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14); (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014 e)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of TVs (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14); (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014f)

Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of air-conditioning devices (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14) (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014g)

Institutions: Financial instruments (subsidies, credit lines)
Ministry of Energy and Mining, autonomous province, local self-government

Public and Commercial Sector

Measure: **PC1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in public and commercial buildings**

Instruments: Financial instrument (credit line, subsidy, loan)

Regulation on Programme of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014 ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 4/2014, 27/2014),(Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c)

Rulebook on conditions for allocation and use of Budget fund of Republic of Serbia for improvement energy efficiency and criteria for exemption from energy audit obligation ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 8/2014),(Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014h)

Information and mandatory information measures
(Significance of examples from the public sector, energy audit)

Institutions: Ministry of Energy and Mining, Ministry of Construction and Urban Planning, autonomous province, local self-government, ESCOs

Measure:	PC2 - New rules for the design and construction of buildings, the minimum requirements in terms of energy performance of buildings and their certification in accordance with the revised EPBD
Instruments:	Provisions (Standards and norms) Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 61/11) (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011a) Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 69/12) (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b)
Institutions:	Ministry of Construction and Urban Planning, Chamber of Engineers
Measure:	PC3 - Modernization of public lighting system in towns and municipalities
Instruments:	Voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (technology procurement, public procurement with the implementation of energy efficiency criteria). Rulebook on determination of contract model for energy services of energy efficiency measures implementation in public sector ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 41/2015)(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015a) Mechanisms for energy savings (fund) Information and required information measures (significant example of the public sector)
Institutions:	Local self-governments, Ministry of Energy and Mining, Ministry of Regional Development and Local Self-Government, Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, ESCOs
Measure:	PC4 - Introduction of energy management systems in the public and commercial sectors
Instruments:	Regulations: Rulebook on determination of contract model for energy services of energy efficiency measures implementation in public sector ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 41/2015) (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 a) Rulebook on methods and times for submission of data necessary for following the implementation of Action Plan for Energy Efficiency in the Republic of Serbia and methodology for following, audit and evaluation of implementation effects ("Official Gazette of the RS", No. 37/15)(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 b) Rulebook on conditions for human resources, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized

energy consultants (“Official Gazette of the RS”, No. 12/2015))(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 c)

Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination (“Official Gazette of the RS”, No. 12/2015))(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 d)

Information and required information measures - (significant example of the public sector)

Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, institutions designated by The Law on Efficient Use of Energy
Measure:	PC5 - Determination of energy efficiency as one of the criteria for the most economically advantageous tender in public procurement
Instruments:	Information and mandatory information measures. Regulations
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, Public Procurement Office, local self-governments, public companies
Measure:	PC6 - Incentive rates for highly efficient coupled / combined heat and power generation in public and commercial buildings
Instruments:	Financial instruments: The Regulation on the amount of special fees for incentives in 2015 (“Official Gazette of the RS”, No. 07/15), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b) The Regulation on the method of calculation and the method of distribution of funds collected from the fees to stimulate privileged power producers (“Official Gazette of the RS”, No. 08/13) (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b)
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, public and commercial companies
Measure:	PC7 - Mandatory regular control of the combustion process of boilers and other combustion chambers with the capacity over 20 kW, as well as air conditioning systems
Instruments:	Information and mandatory information measures. Regulations
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, public and commercial companies public and commercial companies and legal persons authorised by MEDEP in accordance with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy.

Transport Sector

Measure:	T1 - Introduction of the EU Regulation EC 443/2009 for energy efficiency in the transport sector
Instruments:	Further implementation of the Law on Ratification of the Agreement on the adoption of unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations (“Official Gazette of the RS - International agreements”, No. 11/11) (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2011a)
Institutions:	Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry of Energy and Mining, Ministry of Interior
Measure:	T2 - Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme
Instruments:	Information and mandatory information measures (Targeted public information campaigns; Training and Education)
Institutions:	Road Traffic Safety Agency, local self-governments
Measure:	T3 - Introduction of incentive mechanisms for replacement of the existing vehicles
Instruments:	Financial instruments: Subsidies (grants), Loans
Institutions:	Ministry in charge of Economy,
Measure:	T4 - Modernization of fleet in order to meet technical requirements for the performance of domestic and international transportation
Instruments:	Regulations
Institutions:	Ministry of Transport, Ministry on Interior
Measure:	T5 - Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance
Instruments:	Voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (procurement, energy-efficient public procurement technology, commercial and institutional voluntary agreement)
Institutions:	Local self-governments

In addition to measures and instruments directly dedicated to specific sector of consumption, very important are horizontal measures and appropriate instruments, too. Horizontal measures are related to institutional, regulatory, financial and informational mechanisms and measures, which are aimed to improvement, implementation and monitoring of results of energy efficiency measures.

Horizontal measures

Measure:	Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy to the consumers connected to district heating system
Instruments:	Financial instrument

Institutions:	Regulation on determination of heat energy price (“Official Gazette of the RS”, No. 125/14)(Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014 b) Ministry of Energy and Mining, local self-governments, district heating companies
Measure:	Promotion of ESCO model for energy efficiency projects financing
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, autonomous province institutions, local self-government, public and commercial companies
Measure:	Obligation to comply with eco-design requirements for products that affect energy consumption
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, public and commercial companies
Measure:	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, autonomous province institutions, local self-government, and other institutions and organisations
Measure:	Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas
Institutions:	Ministry of Energy and Mining, public companies and other companies engaged in the distribution and supply of electricity, heat or natural gas

1.2 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

BUILDING SECTOR

The building sector provides significant opportunities for energy savings. Two main technologies for improvement energy efficiency in this sector are concerning building envelope and systems for providing different forms of energy (heating, cooling, lighting, etc.) in the buildings.

BUILDING ENVELOPE

A building envelope is the physical separator between unconditioned environment and the conditioned environment of a building, including the resistance to air, water, heat, light, and noise transfer. The three basic elements of a building envelope are a weather barrier, air barrier, and thermal barrier. The weather barrier may be in a different location than the air and thermal barriers such as in house with an unheated attic.

Building envelope properties have significant influence one heating demand and cooling load.

Non-transparent envelope surfaces (walls and roof) thermal properties improvement

Technologies include improvement of thermal properties of walls and roof constructions by adding layers of insulation, usually 10 cm thick, where applicable. The walls are typically refurbished using a contact facade system. This method of building retrofit is the most common in Serbian practice, since it has short payback period and it is not technically demanding. An exception are

facade walls with brick cladding, which is technically difficult to re-apply; in this case it is possible to use special market ready systems in which ceramic cladding as the final facade layer has integrated thermal insulation.

National legislation (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011) defines maximum allowed values of heat transfer coefficients (U-value) for non-transparent envelope surfaces. According to that, U_{max} for outside walls is $0,4 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for existing buildings (after retrofit) and $0,3 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for new buildings.

Transparent envelope surfaces (windows, curtain walls etc.) thermal properties improvement

Replacement of the existing windows which provide poor thermal and air insulation, with new windows with high U-value and with new packages, the characteristics of which comply with the current Regulations or are close to the given values. Despite their poorer performance, installation of wooden windows was suggested in order to preserve the visual identity of the buildings.

BUILDING ENERGY SYSTEMS

Building energy systems may include heating system, cooling system, ventilation system and domestic hot water preparation system. The energy demands (e.g. heating and cooling loads) for those systems are defined by different factors such as building purpose, building thermal properties, users behaviour etc. However those energy needs should be covered in energy efficient way.

Heating system

The applicable and optimal technologies and measures for heating system energy efficiency improvement depend on the building thermal properties and heating system type. Technologies that are applied in Serbia, in different level and extent, include

- 1) Stoves and furnaces with improved efficiency
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Increased efficiency with same heating system
 - ii) Low investment cost
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Low efficiency comparing to other solutions (e.g. condensing boiler)
- 2) Condensing boiler
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Maximum possible efficiency for certain type of fuel
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) High investment cost compared to non-condensing boilers
- 3) Heat pump (air-source, ground-source or water-source)
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) High efficiency (if properly designed even higher than condensing boiler)
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Need proper planning and design of heating system. More demanding in that sense than boilers.
- 4) Micro combined heat and power (mCHP) unit;
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Offers solution for with overall high energy efficiency
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Extremely high investment costs. Rarely justified with current prices of fuels and cost of technology.
- 5) Connection to a district heating system (strictly speaking not a generator technology, but providing the same function)
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Possibility of efficient utilization of locally available renewable energy sources

- b) Disadvantages
 - i) Needs advanced planning on the community level in order to be sustainable or economically competitive to other solutions
 - ii) Not applicable for the zones with low heat demand density
- 6) Variable flow circulating pumps
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Electricity savings
 - b) Disadvantage
 - i) Larger investment costs comparing to pumps with no variable speed control
- 7) Thermostatic valves
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Low investment cost
 - ii) Offer significant energy savings by local regulation of heat exchange rate
 - b) Disadvantage
 - i) Aesthetics – much more robust and conspicuous comparing to regular valves
- 8) Low temperature heating (e.g. under-floor heating)
 - a) Advantage
 - i) Comfort - more comfortable temperatures of radiating surfaces
 - ii) Unlocks possibility for efficient utilization of renewable sources (e.g. heat pump) for heating
 - iii) Lower energy losses in distribution network
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Demanding in terms of design and control
 - ii) Goes only with buildings with proper thermal properties (not too high heat demand)
- 9) Building automation, controls and management: thermostats, supply hot water temperature regulation based on indoor temperature etc.
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Improved comfort and energy efficiency
 - b) Disadvantage
 - i) Can be too demanding in terms of planning and use for average designer or user

Cooling system

In buildings, cooling is most often provided by split systems or chilled water-cooling coils integrated with ventilation system. Depending on the type of the cooling system different technologies may be applied.

- 1) Split systems with inverter technology
 - a) Advantage:
 - i) Very energy efficient (high COP)
 - b) Disadvantage:
 - i) More expensive compared to split systems without inverter technology
- 2) Economizers - Economizers allow outside air to be used to support cooling during colder months, creating opportunities for energy-free cooling.
 - a) Advantages
 - i) Low investment costs
 - ii) Free cooling
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Cooling is not often needed when outside temperature is lower than indoor temperature
- 3) Heat pumps
 - a) Advantages:

- i) Geothermal heat pumps may provide passive cooling (using energy only for circulating water/glycol)
- b) Disadvantages
 - i) Investment costs
 - ii) Require specific location conditions for successful application

Ventilation system

Ventilation systems are almost exclusively used in tertiary sector (extremely rare in residential sector). They are commonly combined with heating system and cooling system.

- 1) Natural ventilation
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) No additional energy is needed for ventilation
 - b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Often demands careful planning by architects in design phase
 - ii) Hard to achieve total control of the process
- 2) Variable air flow systems (fresh air percentage regulated according to real needs)
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Lower energy consumption for air conditioning
 - b) Disadvantage:
 - i) Demands more equipment than constant air volume system
- 3) Insulation of air ducts
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Lower energy losses in cooling and heating period
- 4) Heat recovery from exhaust air
 - a) Advantages
 - i) Enables utilization of waste heat

Domestic hot water (DHW) preparation system

Because of low price of electricity, the most common way of DHW preparation in Serbia is in small electrical boilers. With this technology, every bathroom, washroom or kitchen has its own electrical boiler, which combines the functionality of water heater and DHW storage tank. Some of conventional technologies, which can improve the efficiency of DHW are as follow:

- 1) Central preparation of DHW
 - a) Advantages
 - i) Indirect advantages, such as possibility of more efficient usage of RES for DHW preparation
 - b) Disadvantages
 - i) Hard to apply in existing building – requires significant retrofit
- 2) Connection of DHW systems to district heating network
 - a) Advantages
 - i) Decrease electricity consumption
 - ii) Does not require heat source within the building
 - b) Disadvantages
 - i) Requires significant retrofit if central DHW preparation system does not already exist
 - ii) DH companies have frequent breakdowns and supply stoppages
- 3) Combination or “combi” space-water heating system. We refer to space heating;
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Offer improved overall efficiency of the system
- 4) Gas water heater

- a) Advantages:
 - i) More energy efficient than electric heater
- b) Disadvantages:
 - i) Gas infrastructure in Serbia is not very developed
- 5) Solar domestic hot water system (SDHW);
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Using RES
 - ii) Cheap in exploitation
 - b) Disadvantages
 - i) Using intermittent heat source
 - ii) Needs roof space or other area for solar collectors
- 6) Heat pump water heater (HPWH);
 - a) Advantages
 - i) Using RES
- 7) Waste water heat recovery
 - a) Advantages:
 - i) Using waste heat for space heating

Lightning systems

There are more options for improvement of energy efficiency of lightning in tertiary sector than in residential sector.

In residential sector, the possible technologies are

- 1) Better usage of daylight (need to be addressed in building design phase)
- 2) Occupancy sensors
- 3) Light-responsive sensors to adjust the level of output in response to daylight (indoor use only near windows)
- 4) Energy efficient light bulbs (instead of traditional)
 - a) Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFLs) instead of incandescent lamps or halogen lamps;
 - b) Solid State Lighting (SSL) instead of CFLs. SSL includes Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs), Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLEDs) and Light-Emitting Polymers (LEPs);
 - c) More efficient "tubes" (linear fluorescent lamps), e.g. T8 tubes with electronic ballasts instead of T12 tubes; or better still T5 tubes with electronic ballasts instead of T12 or T8 (this may require replacing existing luminaires);
 - d) Electronic ballasts instead of electromagnetic ballasts;
 - e) More efficient luminaires, e.g. with (better) reflectors and lenses.

Apart of aforementioned technologies, in tertiary sector, building automation system can have more active role in lightning control, which can lead to decrease energy consumption for lightning.

Household appliances

It is hard to point out technologies that can be used in order to improve household appliances. Energy label concept should be applied.

TRANSPORT SECTOR

Increase of energy efficiency in the transport sector in general should be based on following principles (Ministry of Science and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia, 2007): System approach by reducing the need for transport, higher efficiency of public and collective transport and increase of energy efficiency of vehicles through technical improvements. These principles can be implemented through series of organizational, legal and administrative and technical procedures.

The result is closely linked with numerous socio-economic, cultural, educational and institutional barriers.

Increasing the share of public transport

Reducing the need for traveling by private vehicles primarily in the passenger transport sector directly reflects on an increase of transported volume per unit of invested energy.

Promotions of public transport are usually carried out by subsidizing prepaid tickets, or organizing collective transport for companies where it is feasible. Additionally, it is necessary to introduce 'smart' traffic lights for public transport, reserved lanes in urban areas, to provide shorter waiting time, etc. Public transport restructuring includes introduction of new lines, economically attractive tariff packages, renovation and modernization of stations and accompanying infrastructure. Economic attractiveness and user comfort should be emphasized.

At the same time, it is necessary to de-motivate passengers to use own vehicles. To achieve this goal, economic measures should be applied. For example: Measures that were undertaken in public parking services in Serbia, included increase of prices and reduction of parking time available. Additional measures that are under consideration in Serbia are prohibition of private cars usage during rush hours, especially if in the vehicle is only one passenger, tolling per kilometre passed, additional taxation for commercial vehicles (to motivate companies to organize collective transport), transportation for school children organized by the local community or by schools, etc.

At locations where the stoppages often occur, signalization guiding to alternative routes should be set. Roads with steep inclines, generally difficult to drive on, should be reconstructed by building tunnels, viaducts, etc., with the financial participation of traffic participants. Further, by optimizing routes, constructing internal and external transport rings, one-way streets it is possible to additionally reduce fuel consumption.

Better organization of transport can reduce the period of vehicles` usage. Stopping at traffic lights can increase fuel consumption in average up to 10%. Recently, for better flow, roundabouts have been introduced instead of traditional intersections in major Serbian cities. Additionally, to avoid long stops at highways, ETC (Electronic toll collection) system has been installed and promoted. In urban areas "smart" signalling traffic lights should be developed.

Car sharing is a model of car rental, where person can rent a car for short period of time. System is acceptable for customers who occasionally use a vehicle, as well as for customers who need different type of vehicle than their own. Car sharing systems can be organized at the level of a company, local community, etc. Car sharing systems in Serbia is promoted as T2 measure - Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme in National action plan for energy efficiency.

Increased cost for using energy-inefficient vehicles can indirectly reduce fuel consumption. Common measures are introduction of progressive tax rates and registration costs determined by average consumption, and benefits (subsidies) while purchasing and registration of eco-friendly vehicles. Serbian practice has shown that an increase of fuel prices have small impact on reduction of use of inefficient vehicles.

Stimulating sales of cars with modern fuel injection systems, efficient combustion, etc. Agreement on Stabilization and Association with the European Union stipulates the obligation of acceptance and implementation of EU legislation in the field of homologation of road vehicles. Imported vehicles are controlled in order to provide data on compatibility with the appropriate standard. Currently, all new vehicles should be equipped with engines which fulfil minimum standard Euro 5. Advancements of engines can be particularly noticed for diesel engines. Technical improvements include catalysts and lambda probe introduction in the exhaust systems, 'start-stop system', improvement of aero dynamics, increased efficiency of air conditioners, more efficient bulbs, use of tires with lower rolling resistance and active control tire pressure, etc. Also, quality of

fuels is an influential factor for efficiency improvement. Therefore, the modernization of refineries in Serbia and labelling petroleum products (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) should improve efficiency in transport.

More strict and demanding annual technical inspection of vehicles, especially emission control, even for nominally Euro 5 and 6 engines, can contribute to their efficiency. Option can be introduction of vehicle's card. Such document should be filled in during the technical inspection with data on emissions and fuel consumption. In the same time, mandatory engine settings and control should be introduced. Also, it is necessary to insist on more strict standards for technical inspection as a common practice for reducing fuel consumption.

Self-control of fuel consumption should be promoted through measures such as educational campaign related to fuel reduction, introduction of compulsory labelling of vehicles which have high consumption, wide spread information about indicators of fuel consumption in order to influence on driving habits. An option is also eco-test rides as demonstration to drivers how aggressive driving increases fuel consumption. Rigorous speed control, also can contribute to self-control of fuel consumption.

Eco driving is a term used to label energy efficient use of vehicles. In last years, engine technology and performance of cars are improving, while most drivers still didn't adopted modified driving style. There are many driving techniques which can lead to significant fuel savings. There are five basic rules to follow² : anticipate traffic flow, maintain a steady speed at low RPM, Shift up early, check tires, and consider any extra energy consumer (air conditioner). Eco driving and self-control in general offer many benefits, primarily increase of energy efficiency and decrease of fuel cost, reduction of GHG emissions, greater safety and comfort. Eco driving represents a driving culture which suits to modern engines and makes the best use of progressive vehicle performances. Eco driving is promoted as T2 measure - Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme in National action plan for energy efficiency.

Development of an integrated and sustainable urban mobility plan represents integration of different organizational technologies for reduction impacts of the transport sector to environment and public health, and usually is applied in larger systems (local, regional, national). Also, big companies can be obliged to submit mobility plans to the state administration

Increasing the share of alternative forms of transportation, primarily walking and biking. In general, biking has some tradition of use in Vojvodina autonomous province, and recently in some parts of Belgrade. According to (United Nations Development Programme and Gef, 2014) share of students and employees who cycle in Belgrade is 1-2%. In Belgrade, the total length of bicycle paths is 55.6 kilometres, but the general impression is that infrastructure is mainly used for recreational and tourism purposes (United Nations Development Programme and Gef, 2014). For larger share, it is necessary to build infrastructure (safe bicycle lines, secure bicycle parking, pedestrian zone, etc.). Also, these transport modes must be taken into consideration while defining urban plans.

Park and drive system represents possibility to park vehicle at the place with good public transport connections (bus, railway system) to city centre. Alternatively, bicycle-sharing system could be also used. The system is applicable in the big cities with great migration from suburbs to city centre. This system reduces the cost of parking, pollution and fuel consumption.

Railway transport is generally considered as very efficient transport system. For increased share of railway transport, both in passenger and freight transport, preconditions are good infrastructure,

² <http://www.ecodrive.org>

the accuracy of the timetable, new stations with additional services, increased safety and security, new wagons with appropriate services. Also branding of railways can be additional measure.

Encouraging combined freight transport such as road-railway. It is necessary to encourage construction of transfer terminals, subsidizing purchases of special combined trailers that can be easily transferred from road to rail and vice versa.

2. MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

Although energy efficiency as an issue has been present in Serbia for years, objective achievements are very modest. The reasons are different, but for full understanding it is necessary to have in mind, that the real establishment of policy in this sector begun after year 2000., with negative legacy of the last decade of XX century (breakdown of previous country, wars, influx of refugees, NATO bombing, etc.) and that all selected barriers to implementation of energy efficiency measures in buildings and transport sectors should be considered in that context.

For energy efficiency the worst legacy is probably the idea that energy prices should be used as an instrument of social policy. This was especially emphasized for electric energy and in less extent for natural gas and heat provided by district heating systems. In addition, even energy consumption without paying was tolerated. This was the practice not only for the residential sector, but also for industry, commercial and public sector. As a consequence, public debt grew, but also awareness of the most of inhabitants that energy is widely available and affordable for very low price. In such situation energy efficiency couldn't be considered as very important issue. Also in 90's begun significant and uncontrolled import of used cars and others road vehicles (busses, trucks, commercial vehicles, etc.).

After 2000, situation in Serbian economy started to change, but very slowly. Gross domestic product in 2013 was 34,3 billions of €, or 4783 € per capita³. Unemployment rate is approximately 19%, and at-risk-of-poverty rate (for 2012) is 24,6 %⁴. Available household budget in 2013 (monthly average per household) was app. 470 €, and in the structure consumption share of electricity, gas and other fuels was app. 11%, while the share of transport costs was app 8% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2013).

Still electricity price is the lowest in the Europe, but the great effort was undertaken for improving the payment. Although the electricity market is fully open, Electric Power Industry of Serbia (vertically organized enterprise, 100% owned by the Republic of Serbia) has the 100% share at households market. Average price at this market segment is app. 0.06 €/kWh (EPS, 2015). However, it is expected that this price will rise in the following period. Natural gas price has risen to real market value (only Russian gas over Hungary is available), but as a consequence, lot of households (especially in the rural areas) decided to use firewood instead. Although firewood can be considered as renewable energy source, most people in Serbia use it in traditional, environmentally unacceptable and inefficient way (traditional stoves and ovens). District heating systems (exist in more than 50 towns) are in the competence of local self-governments and operate mostly as public companies. Common characteristics are problems in realization of payment, obsolete technology,

³<http://webrzs.stat.gov.rs/WebSite/Public/ReportResultView.aspx?rptKey=indId%3d09020101IND10%2c09020101IND20%266%3d1%2c2%2c3%26102%3drs%262%3d%23last%233%26sAreaId%3d09020101%26dType%3dName%26lType%3dEnglish>

⁴ <http://webrzs.stat.gov.rs/WebSite/Public/PageView.aspx?pKey=2>

inappropriate maintenance and significant energy losses. Also, although the Law on Efficient Use of Energy prescribes obligation of introduction of payment of real consumption, implementation process is very slow and with a lot of obstacles. Due to low purchase power, in the last two years, share of new cars decreased, for example from app. 100.000 the first time-registered cars, only app. 15.000 are new cars (Republic of Serbia, Road Traffic Safety Agency, 2015).

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector are presented in Table 1. From the list of social barriers, untypical is the belief of citizens that the price of electricity will remain low in the future. This barrier arose as a consequence of experiences in last 25 years, and using electricity price as an instrument of social policy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a). For social segmentation besides previously stated fact of at-risk-of-poverty rate of 24.6%, it is useful to know that 13.7% of citizens don't have even primary education, 20.8% have only primary education, 48.9% have finished secondary education and only 16.6% have high and university education (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015).

Table 1: Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Heterogeneity of consumers	Consumers behave differently because of heterogeneity in preferences. When individuals make decisions related to some energy need, a single standard would not be optimal as decision-making base for everyone. For example, products that are financially attractive for the average consumer may not be attractive for some groups of consumers because of differences in preferences, expected use of the product, and the cost of borrowing. For some consumers only important for decision-making, is the cost of product (Stadtmüller H. 2014), while some consider only fuel-efficiency products, and all expected costs during lifetime of products.
Social	Social group interactions and status considerations	Behaviour of consumers is not the result of conscious and motivated action. Everyday consumption behaviours are strongly shaped and enforced at the micro-level (Stadtmüller H. 2014). Consumer's decisions are influenced by behaviour of consumers from similar social groups.
Social	Inertia	This barrier represents absence of motivation to make a change. Consumers resist changing the behaviour and common practice. In Serbia this barrier is additionally affected with low purchasing power of consumers (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015) and low energy prices (Eurostat, 2015).
Social	The belief of citizens that the price of electricity will remain low in the future	Majority of citizens believe that in the future electricity price will be low. In last decades electricity price have been kept low, as an instrument of social policy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a).
Social	Commitment and motivation of public	Commitment and motivation play a key role in consumer decisions about energy efficiency investments. The experience in Serbia shows that the motivation, enthusiasm and commitment of officers in local

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
		government, affects directly activities directed to energy efficiency improvement (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). It is specifically important to encourage the public, to inform and train in order to affect the outcome.
Social	Bounded rationality	People are making decisions only partially rational, while the remaining part can be characterized as either emotional or irrational. There is a tendency for people to go along with the status quo or to stick with default options. At level of administration decision-making may also be divided up, and global objectives may be replaced by sub-goals whose achievement can be measured (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011).
Cultural	Mistrust of new technologies	Mistrust of new technologies and lack of willingness to adopt energy savings measures make a strong preference for the status quo, due to long-term experience (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). Those who are familiar with a particular product, give to it higher value, comparing to new product for the same purpose. Electric boilers for heating water in housing sector are considered as the most appropriate option. Other possible solutions are generally considered as unsafe or unreliable (using of centralized system or using solar collectors).
Cultural	Familiarisation with technology in general	The degree to which technology is part of the culture and every-day life of a population affects their actions. This barrier is closely linked with mistrust of new technologies (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). Even when citizens have all relevant information, in some cases they give a higher priority to technologies that they are more familiar with. For example, for domestic hot water are mainly used electric boilers.
Cultural	Willingness to adopt new measures	This barrier is linked with mistrust in new technologies and familiarization with some technology
Educational	Lack of information, knowledge and experience	Credibility and trust in the information is of the great importance for decisions. The importance of increasing information about benefits, projects undertaken, examples of good practice are needed both for population and decision makers (Gvozdenac, et all. 2013). Specific for decision makers is lack of knowledge and experience in preparing, carrying out and monitoring phases of the project (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c). In general data on energy consumption for subsectors, or cities or municipalities are usually not available. Most of the cities don't have data about actual energy consumption in buildings. Savings cannot be determined unless base year values are available (or exist).
Educational	Lack of awareness of the population and	Most people in general support energy efficiency and recognize it as important, but few have an understanding

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
	local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	of what it means and how to increase energy efficiency in their own homes. Also, most of citizens think, in current conditions, that energy efficiency projects are unnecessary costs for their municipality or city (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c). Because of that education of population is needed in order to provide basic understanding and benefits from more efficient use of energy. Energy efficiency improvement is usually not a priority for politicians (decision makers). They prefer to choose investments that are more "visible", in order to keep their positions in administration (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011), (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).
Educational	Lack of providing information from the best practice projects	Specific cases, informed by figures and data are needed to help convince different stakeholders of the advantages and benefits. Examples of preformed projects with credible information, financial aspects, implications, pictures, and experiences are missing in informing stakeholders (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011).
Educational	Lack of experience in cooperation with national and international funds	Lack of experience in cooperation with funds is emphasized at local level. This barrier reflects on ability to apply for funding from (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011).

Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance and Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas are horizontal measures proposed at National action plan for energy efficiency that generally address stated barriers. Public information campaigns and especially significant example of the public sector are emphasized in few measures and instruments and they should contribute to removing of some barriers.

Main economic barriers in the building sector are presented in table 2. They are divided to general and those relevant to households, commercial and public sector. These barriers are mostly Serbian specific and for their understanding, besides discussion at the beginning of this chapter, it is interesting to have in mind results of Survey of incomes and life conditions (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015). According to that document, structure of financial load of households regards to costs of housing is as follows:

- Not load at all 1.8%,
- Load in some extent 25.6%,
- Load significantly 72.6%.

From the same document is the general, subjective opinion on difficulty in meeting financial obligations:

- Very easy 0.1%,
- Easy 1%,

- Quite easy 3.7%,
- With some obstacles 26.9%,
- Difficult 33.4%, and
- Very difficult 34.9%.

Table 2: Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering	<p>Municipal district heating companies are under the jurisdiction of local authorities and a decisions on the prices of heating are made at a local level's administration (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014d). The billing tariffs for heating and domestic hot water are determined by the status of the user. Heat energy, which is distributed to households without embedded metering devices, is charged on a flat rate depending on the size of the heating space (Econoler, 2012). Households with installed metering devices for the heat may apply for the billing on the basis of energy consumed (consists of fixed and variable fees). Fixed fee is based on the capacity of installed heaters while variable fee depends on heat consumption.</p> <p>There are additional problems that affect the economic viability of district heating companies. There are several municipalities which own district heating companies. At the same time, these municipalities are heat consumers that are not paying for the heat delivered to the public buildings, creating a great burden to district heating companies. This leads to the creation of barriers to implementation of energy efficiency projects financed by external sources. For example if the municipal (public) building doesn't have sufficient money in the budget to pay energy bill, it will be difficult for them to use the reduction in energy cost to repay investments made to improve the energy efficiency of the building.</p> <p>Local government fails to demonstrate an adequate strong willingness to make the political decisions necessary to adjust the price of heat energy, as well as to introduce metering systems in all buildings.</p>
Low Electricity Prices	<p>Electricity price is the key parameter that influences the implementation of energy efficiency measures in buildings (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a). Two main components of energy consumed in buildings usually are heat energy (provided by district heating system) and electricity. Keeping low electricity prices (Eurostat, 2015) for end consumers seems to be component of the social policy, but such situation leads the market for energy efficiency in a hopeless position. Current practice only postpones the inevitable, since it lead to a possible dramatic increase of energy prices in the future (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a).</p> <p>Low energy prices represent a common barrier for the development of energy efficiency in some of the developing countries. This barrier fails to promote refurbishment, retrofit and improvement of energy efficiency in existing buildings. It also fails to promote implementation of prescribed norms for residential buildings in order to upgrade the building code (class).</p> <p>This barrier affects the buildings in all sectors, without exception. Even those buildings that are connected to the municipal district heating or local heating systems consume large amounts of electricity for lighting or heating water.</p>
Households	
High Interest Rates and Numerous Additional Bank Fees and Charges	<p>High interest rates (12% - 20%) (Econoler, 2012) represent the financial barrier that directly affects the internal rate of return of energy efficiency projects. Low energy prices complicate aforementioned unfavourable effect of high interest rates, which makes energy efficiency projects unfeasible within the timeframe for loans offered by banks. Bigger and more comprehensive investments in energy efficiency, which require financial support, often give negative net present value. The causes of these barriers are an integral part of the existing banking system, and cannot be solved easily and without endangering the stability of the financial system (Econoler, 2012). Good understanding of these barriers can lead to support programs that should</p>

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
	decrease the costs of financing from local banks. High interest rates have an impact on the entire housing sector. The housing sector is usually financed by unsecured customer loans, credit cards, or by mortgage loans. Compared to the commercial and public sectors, the residential sector command the highest interest rate.
Households Credit Capacity	<p>This barrier is closely associated with the creditworthiness and limited creditworthiness of customers in Serbia. In the residential sector, the main form of borrowing is by consumer loans. Banks link maximum debt that a person may have with monthly salary.</p> <p>Currently population borrows mainly for consumer goods, and has already used almost half of its creditworthiness for that purpose (Econoler, 2012). Finding residents who have not yet exceeded limit of their creditworthiness can be very difficult. This is particularly difficult when it is necessary improve energy efficiency of the whole building, and some of the homeowners have already borrowed as much as possible.</p>
Public Sector	
Limitation of Public Sector Entities to Provide Collateral	This is the financial barrier that is common for the public sector. Municipalities are not allowed to provide as collateral a mortgage over the real estate, since they are public assets. Instead, they can issue a letter of intent (a kind of guarantee) on the use of up to 20% of their revenues from local taxes as collateral on loan (Econoler, 2012). This barrier influences more the smaller than the larger municipalities. Also, there is less effect on the municipalities with higher income from local taxation of those municipalities that rely on state subsidies.
Lack of Dedicated Financing	There are limited dedicated funds or financial mechanisms for the public sector projects on energy efficiency. Law envisages national Energy Efficiency Fund, and it is established in 2014, but with limited resources (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c).
Small Size and High Transaction Costs of Energy Efficiency Projects	For small size projects, high costs of project development represent a major barrier for their implementation. High transaction costs make difficult development of a single project. Therefore, grouping of public energy efficiency projects could be the solution (Eric, Babin, 2013).
Public sector budgeting does not allow municipalities to keep their baseline budget for a few years after energy efficiency projects	<p>This regulatory barrier (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014e) that creates economic barrier that affects the public sector and creates negative impact to energy efficiency projects. Additional effort to develop and carry out energy efficiency projects is needed, but municipalities have no other benefit than an increased level of comfort in buildings. In comparison with other projects that municipalities are carrying out, the implementation of energy efficiency projects requires additional effort and costs in the development stage of the project.</p> <p>Municipalities receive as much money as is necessary to cover general expenses and planned investments for the following year (Djindjic, Lukovac, 2013). Regarding this, part of the energy budget is formed in relation to the energy bills for the current financial year and expected energy consumption and energy prices for the following year. If energy efficiency project is implementing, it is expected that consumption for next year would be reduced for the amount of the expected savings, which are results of the project. Budgeting mechanism automatically reduces the energy budget for next year.</p> <p>As a result, the municipalities can have two negative effects from implementation of energy efficiency measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They do not collect benefits of the energy efficiency project. Instead they have reduction of the energy budget. • If municipalities borrow money to implement energy efficiency projects, they are required to pay the loan from its remaining budget and must therefore refrain from other investment projects. If municipalities would be able to keep allocated budget for energy for years, they could pay the loans from energy savings.
Commercial Sector	

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
High Interest Rates and Collateral Requirements Make Borrowing Unattractive	High interest rates represent a general obstacle to investments in energy efficiency in the market with subsidized energy prices. In such environment, the owners of commercial buildings tend to invest only in those projects for which the return on investment makes financial sense. Unfortunately, the current market for lending (in conjunction with the current energy prices) makes difficult finding measures of energy efficiency that have short pay back periods (Eric, Babin, 2013).
Split Incentive for Rented Building – Landlord is Responsible for Renovations, but Tenants Pay the Bill	This barrier is very specific for the commercial sector. In all cases when commercial building is rented, the owner is obliged to conduct reconstruction and maintenance of the property, while tenants pay all the costs of utilities for the services used (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2003, 2011b). Tenant may be encouraged to contribute improving the efficiency of the building, but in the practice tenant is not responsible for the process of renewal and adaptation. Contracts for renting are not concluded for a sufficiently long period, to provide benefits of investments in energy efficiency Owners are generally not willing to deduct the cost of the energy efficiency project from rental payments (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). As a result, commercial buildings (especially old) are in poor condition and not very efficient.

Different financial instruments for removing economic barriers are foreseen in National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency - subsidies, loans, tax reliefs, etc. However, the main precondition for the functioning of these instruments, budget Energy Efficiency Fund was constituted in 2014. Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy to the consumers connected to district heating system and promotion of ESCO model for energy efficiency projects financing are horizontal measures that directly address these barriers. Of course, general economic development of the country should contribute to lower impact of some barriers.

Main institutional barriers in the building sector are presented in table 3. As the Ministry of Energy and Mining is recognized as the key player in the most measures and instruments implementation stated in National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency, rising of its capacity is of great importance. Introduction of energy management systems in the public and commercial sectors and appropriate, proposed instruments should help capacity building at local level.

Table 3: Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	This barrier is related to institutional capacity. The closing down of the only agency in the country devoted to supporting energy efficiency, can be interpreted and understood as a bad sign in the market. At national level, energy efficiency is under the authority of the Ministry in charge of the energy activities – Department of Improvement of Energy Efficiency. According to document National Programme for the Adoption of the EU Acquis (European Integration Office, 2014) this Department has a total of 9 employees, of whom two are engaged under the contract of temporary employment and occasional work, and three for the project that lasts until December 2015.
Institutional Capacity of the local self government	According to The Law on Efficient Use of Energy every municipality with more than 20000 inhabitants should introduce system of energy management, as well as to have the capacity for implementation of this system. Although the Law was adopted in 2013, only few of Serbian municipalities have introduced this system and appointed responsible persons for the implementation, as the secondary legislations are not finished (Energy Community, 2015).
Lack of Specific Home Owner Association (HOA)	Constitution and operation of HOA is not clearly defined by Law, especially in the cases when the energy efficiency project should be realized, since it is necessary for the Association of homeowners to have substance and to be recognized as

<p>Legislation</p>	<p>creditworthy by local banks in order to be able to take loans for implementation of energy efficiency projects in buildings.</p> <p>In Serbia there are Assemblies of homeowners (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2011b) and this concept works for the small-scale repairs with money collected by owners or money collected for the purposes of management of the building. However, when it comes to improving the energy efficiency of buildings, this barrier has several different aspects that influence the behaviour of homeowners and, ultimately, the implementation of energy efficiency projects.</p> <p>Implementation of energy efficiency project for the entire building requires investments that cannot be provided without financing from loans of commercial banks. However, the Assembly of homeowners does not represent creditworthy borrower (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2003, 2011b):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is almost impossible to prove a constant income of money over several years, as well as financial discipline of its members. • The assembly of homeowners has no means of imposing their decisions to owners who disagree with their decisions; • If the assembly of homeowners takes a loan and for some reason is not able to repay, for the bank it would be extremely difficult to prosecute the apartment owners.
<p>Association of homeowners' reluctance to make decisions to renovate</p>	<p>This represents an institutional barrier caused by the fact that the Assemblies of homeowners are not clearly defined organizations with set of rights, obligations and management mechanisms (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2011b).</p> <p>For every decision on adaptation of the building or implementation of energy efficiency project Association need to provide at least 51% of votes of the homeowners. Since investment decisions are based on income homeowners it may be difficult to reach 51% of votes.</p> <p>The discussions within the Assembly of homeowners inevitably lead to confrontation of different ways thinking of homeowners.</p>

Assessment of barriers in the building sector according to their significance in impeding the implementation of energy efficiency measures is presented in table 4. The identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the following criteria:

- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

Table 4: Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
<p>High</p>	<p>The belief of citizens that the price of electricity remains low in the future</p>
	<p>Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy</p>
	<p>Lack of information, knowledge and experience</p>
	<p>Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering</p>
	<p>Low Electricity Prices</p>
	<p>Public Sector Budgeting does not allow Municipalities to keep their Baseline Budget for a Few Years after Energy Efficiency Projects</p>
	<p>Institutional Capacity of the local self-government</p>

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
Medium	Inertia
	Commitment and motivation of public
	Mistrust of new technologies
	Willingness to adopt new measures
	High Interest Rates and Numerous Additional Bank Fees and Charges
	Households Credit Capacity
	Lack of Dedicated Financing
	Split Incentive for Rented Building – Landlord is Responsible for Renovations, but Tenants Pay the Bill
Low	Lack of Specific Home Owner Association (HOA) Legislation
	Social group interactions and status considerations
	Bounded rationality
	Heterogeneity of consumers
	Familiarisation with technology in general
	Lack of experience in cooperation with national and international funds
	Lack of providing information from the best practice projects
	Limitation of Public Sector Entities to Provide Collateral
	Small Size and High Transaction Costs of Energy Efficiency Projects
	High Interest Rates and Collateral Requirements Make Borrowing Unattractive
	Association of homeowners' reluctance to make decisions to renovate
	Energy Efficiency on the Government Agenda
Institutional Capacity of the local self-government	

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector are presented in table 5. Social and cultural barriers are relevant for passenger transport during the purchasing of cars, as well as for swift to and selection of public transport. Targeted public information campaigns, as well as training and education are important, envisaged instruments for overcoming majority of listed barriers.

Table 5: Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social	Heterogeneity of consumers	Consumers have heterogeneous preferences with regards to quality, price, efficiency and environmental impact of mode of transport. Consumers do not purchase energy-efficient vehicles based solely on a cost-effectiveness criterion (Prvulović et al., 2008), (Rankovic Plazinic B. et al. 2014). For some consumers the main factor for decision making is the cost, for some of them vehicle is status symbol. Some do not consider possibility for buying used car, some have preferences to by cars produced in in specific region or county (for example in Europe), some prefer cars with gasoline engines, etc.
Social	Social group interactions and status considerations	Behaviour of consumers is not the result of conscious and motivated action. Everyday consumption behaviours is strongly shaped and enforced at the micro-level. Consumer`s decisions are influenced by behaviour of consumers from similar social groups. Older population have different preferences and habits compared to younger. People from lower socio-economic backgrounds, for example prefer train transport, etc.

Type of barrier (Social, cultural, educational)	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
		Interactions with friends, families, and colleagues affect the way people make decisions, how they value impact to environment. Consequently their lifestyle has influence on purchase decisions and common practice (Prvulović et al., 2008), (Mrkajic V. et al. 2015), (Rankovic Plazinic B. et all. 2014).
Social	Inertia	This barrier represents absence of motivation to make a change. For the case of Serbia it is related to willingness to make a change in traffic organization in general, in existing public transport system, behaviour of drivers, passengers, etc. (Mrkajic V. et all. 2015), (Rankovic Plazinic B. et all. 2014).
Cultural	Credibility and trust	In the case of Serbia, mistrust in some modes of transport can be identified. For example, majority of passengers avoid traveling by train, although this is the cheapest mode of transport. Identified reasons (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007) are delays, low speed, duration of journey, poor and old infrastructure, unpredictable waiting time, etc.
Educational	Lack of information, knowledge and experience	Credibility and trust in the information is of the great importance for decisions. The importance of increasing information about benefits, achieved results, projects undertaken, examples of good practice are needed both for population and decision makers. Specific for decision makers is lack of knowledge and experience in preparing, carrying out and monitoring phases of the projects (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). In general data on energy consumption for transport subsectors for the local level are not available. Most of the citizens are not recognizing energy efficiency as priority in transport. Importance of energy conservation is still not understood by common people. Consequently, ordinary citizens have not yet assimilated the necessity of changing of attitude. When purchasing vehicle, is particularly important that customers need to have and understand objective data on fuel consumption.
Educational	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	Most people in general support energy efficiency, but most of citizens think, in current conditions, that energy efficiency projects are unnecessary costs for their municipality or city. Energy efficiency improvement is usually not a priority for decision makers at local level (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities, UNDP, 2011). Because of that education of population is needed in order to provide basic understanding and benefits from more efficient use of energy. It will contribute to awareness and change of attitude and values of individuals and the society.

Main economic barriers in the transport sector are related to low purchasing power of Serbian citizens. It can be expected that the overall economic growth will be the positive signal for removing or diminishing of listed barriers. The justification for this statement is the number of registered new car, which was more than 50000 in 2008. (before economic crisis), while in last few years was less than 20000.

Table 6: Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Lack of Dedicated Financing	There are no dedicated funds or financial mechanisms for the transport sector projects on energy efficiency (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c).
Low purchasing power of citizens	Average monthly salary in Serbia is 365 euro (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b). When buying, ordinary citizen is deciding dominantly based on the price/cost of the product/service. This is the main reason for purchasing used imported cars and the estimation is that more than 75% of new registered cars per year are used cars (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2015d).

Main institutional barriers in the transport sector are presented in table 7. Barriers are similar to those in building sector but with additional problem: the Ministry in charge for energy proposes measures that are in the competence of other institutions (Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry in charge of Economy, Ministry in charge of Transport and Ministry on Interior). The focus of interest of these institutions is usually not at energy efficiency.

Table 7: Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	Road Traffic Safety Agency, Ministry in charge of Economy, Ministry of Transport and Ministry on Interior, together with the Ministry in charge of the energy activities – Department of Improvement of Energy Efficiency should work together for improvement of energy efficiency in transport. Therefore, serious work in capacity building of stated institutions and their coordination in actions for energy efficiency improvement are necessary (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c).
Institutional Capacity of the local self government	According to The Law on Efficient Use of Energy every municipality with more than 20,000 inhabitants should introduce system of energy management. Although the Law was adopted in 2013, only few of Serbian municipalities have introduced this system and appointed persons responsible for implementation, as the secondary legislations are not finished (Energy Community, 2015).

Assessment of barriers in the transport sector according to their significance in impeding the implementation of energy efficiency measures is presented in table 8. The identified barriers were assessed according to their impact, from 'High' to 'Low', taking into consideration the following criteria:

- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier;
- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of its appearance (how long it is quoted as a problem).

Table 8: Assessment of barriers in the transport sector

Impact of Barriers	Barriers
High	Lack of Dedicated Financing
	Lack of information, knowledge and experience
	Low purchasing power of citizens
	Institutional capacity of the Government of Serbia
	Institutional capacity of the local self government

Medium	Inertia
	Credibility and trust
	Bounded rationality
Low	Social group interactions and status considerations
	Heterogeneity of consumers
	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy

3. BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Law on rational use of energy that was adopted in 2013 (Government of Republic of Serbia, 2013), for the first time established legislative and legal framework for efficient use of energy in the Republic Serbia. The law determines some minimum standards and requirements on energy efficiency, as well as incentives, which are expected to create huge demand for energy efficiency services.

These standards and requirements include: labelling of energy related products, minimal requirements for energy efficiency in the production, transmission and distribution of electricity, heat, oil and natural gas, incentives for the rational and efficient use of energy, penalties for inefficient use of energy, framework for the development of Energy Efficient Services Companies, etc.

For meeting numerous requirements provided by the Law, draft for incentive system is proposed. It includes:

- Partly exemption from VAT for energy-efficient equipment, materials, home appliances and technology;
- Partly exemption from income tax for the part of the investment related to energy efficiency.

Serbian government in **National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency set a target of achieving energy savings of 1% per year until 2018, which should result in 9% savings**. This is a strong driver for implementation energy efficiency measures and reduction of barriers impacts, because significant annual investments are expected in order to reach the target. According to the World Bank report expected investments, only in building sector should be 1.635 billion of euros up to 2020 (Econoler, 2012).

This target is important also for the reduction of import dependency. Net import dependency in 2013 was 25% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). Main imported fuels were natural gas (80.5% imported) and oil and oil products (61% imported). Indirectly an increase of energy efficiency contributes to an increase of energy safety.

Further, priority of the Serbian government is reducing government spending. Implementation of energy efficiency in the public sector should contribute in reaching this goal. Programs of government support to energy efficiency can be structured in a manner to be budget neutral. Main capital can be provided by public-private partnerships or ESCOs.

The first Energy Efficiency Action Plan determined number of voluntary and mandatory measures for energy efficiency, such as:

- Substitution of electricity for heating with natural gas, by connection to district heating system, renewable energy sources utilization (voluntary)
- Replacement of congenital bulbs with more efficient bulbs (voluntarily);
- Replacement of windows in small and medium companies and or thermal insulation for houses. (voluntary)

- Adoption of new standards for determining the temperature of the heating installation (regulatory/mandatory)
- Application of the new tariff system for heat energy (regulatory/mandatory)
- Energy certification of new buildings (regulatory)
- Introduction of energy management in public and commercial buildings (mandatory);
- Verification and certification of energy efficiency of existing buildings (mandatory);
- Introduction of Energy Efficiency Fund;
- Introduction of credit lines for renewable energy and energy efficiency for households, public and commercial buildings.

As a **candidate state for access to EU**, Serbia requires several adjustments (for example, harmonization of regulations, tariffs), aimed to decrease the energy intensity. Serbia has an annual target of reducing energy consumption in buildings by 1% per year. That should create market potential of 1.2 billion euros in the housing sector, 270 million euros in commercial buildings and 170 million euros in sector public buildings (Econoler, 2012). Also, as a **member of Energy Community**, Serbia is committed to reach 27% of renewable energy sources in gross final energy consumption by 2020. Increased utilization of renewable energy sources and reduced energy demand are needed in order to fulfil the commitment.

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

Main driver for energy efficiency in the residential sector is the need for adaptation. Old buildings are constructed using outdated materials and technology whose low efficiency during the years declined. Significant parts of residential buildings require urgent refurbishment. Any kind of renovation (walls, roofs, windows, etc.) will at least slightly improve the efficiency of buildings, even if the works are not directed towards energy efficiency improvement. The need for refurbishment is based on an effort to maintain the property and improve living comfort.

Similar, the public sector also, needs refurbishment. Many public institutions are dilapidated and comfort in such buildings is extremely low. The need for restoration and adaptation is based on the need to improve the level of comfort in these buildings. Programs for supporting energy efficiency can help in meeting this need.

In commercial sector, as in other sectors, there is a great need for renewal and adaptation. Most buildings are built forty years ago, and since then had only minimal renovation.

Commercial sector attracts foreign investments. New commercial buildings are built according to the standards of efficiency higher than for existing buildings. Landlords are constantly under pressure to offer more affordable prices for retail space. This creates driver of the market, where landlords of office space in older, less efficient, poorly maintained office buildings, want to improve the competitiveness of building on the market for rental for office or commercial space.

The Law on Construction and Planning, with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy present the base for this kind of activities in the building sector. Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011a) and the Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b) introduced obligations for improving energy class of the building after refurbishment and minimal energy class for new building should be C. Also for the residential building sector the obligation on the labelling of energy-related products, is introduced.

Identified barriers specific for Serbia for the building sector and policy instruments that are addressing them, in the building sector are presented in table 9.

Table 9: Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Heterogeneity of consumers	National	Rulebooks on the labelling of energy-related products (refrigerating appliances, washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, electric bulbs and lamps, TVs, air-conditioning devices) Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)
	Social group interactions and status considerations	National	
	Inertia	National	
	The belief of citizens that the price of electricity remains low in the future	National	
	Commitment and motivation of public	National	
	Bounded rationality	National	
	Customs, habits and relevant behavioural aspects	National	
	Mistrust of new technologies	National	
	Familiarisation with technology in general	National, local	
	Willingness to adopt new measures	National	
	Lack of information, knowledge and experience	National, local	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination
	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	National, regional, local	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c) Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy

			manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c)
	Lack of providing information from the best practice projects	Local	-
	Lack of experience in cooperation with national and international funds	National, regional, local	-
Economic	Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering	National, local	Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy to the consumers connected to district heating system (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) Regulation on determination of heat energy price (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b)
	Low Electricity Prices	National	-
	High Interest Rates and Numerous Additional Bank Fees and Charges	National	Financial instruments (credit lines, subsidies, loans) are proposed by measure H1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings in NEEAP. Still there is no policy instrument dedicated to household sector.
	Households Credit Capacity	National	
	Financial Institutions' Traditional Lending Procedures	National	
	Limitation of Public Sector Entities to Provide Collateral	Regional, local	Regulation on Programme of financing activities and measures for improvement efficient energy use in 2014 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014c) Rulebook on conditions for allocation and use of Budget fund of Republic of Serbia for improvement energy efficiency and criteria for exemption from energy audit obligation (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 2014 h), Regulation on the amount of special fees for incentives in 2015 The Regulation on the method of calculation and the method of distribution of funds collected from the fees to stimulate privileged power producers Rulebook on determination of contract model for energy services of energy efficiency measures implementation in public sector
	Lack of Dedicated Financing	Regional, local	
	Small Size and High Transaction Costs of Energy Efficiency Projects	Local	
	Public Sector Budgeting does	Local	-

	not allow Municipalities to keep their Baseline Budget for a Few Years after Energy Efficiency Projects		
	High Interest Rates and Collateral Requirements Make Borrowing Unattractive	National	Financial instruments (credit lines, subsidies, loans) are proposed by measure PC1 - Energy efficiency improvement measures in residential buildings in NEEAP. The Regulation on the amount of special fees for incentives in 2015 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b) The Regulation on the method of calculation and the method of distribution of funds collected from the fees to stimulate privileged power producers (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b)
	Split Incentive for Rented Building – Landlord is Responsible for Renovations, but Tenants Pay the Bill	National	-
Institutional	Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	National	-
	Energy Efficiency on the Government Agenda	National	-
	Institutional Capacity of the local self government	Local	Rulebook on conditions for human capacity, equipment and spaces for the institution that provide education for energy managers and authorized energy consultants (Ministry of Mining and Energy 2015c) Rulebook on method of implementation and contents of training programs for energy manager, costs of training programs, as well as on detail conditions, curriculum and method of examination)(Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015 d)
	Lack of Specific Home Owner Association (HOA) Legislation	National, local	-
	Association of homeowners' reluctance to make decisions to renovate	National, local	-

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

The main driving factors for achieving energy efficiency in the transport sector can be listed as follows:

Impact to environment; Transportation activities support increasing mobility demands for passengers and freight. As a result, transport sector make notable consequences to environment. The most important impacts of transport on the environment are related to air quality, noise, climate change, water quality, soil quality, etc.

- **Health related issues, Local pollutants;** Air is polluted by emissions of harmful exhaust gases: carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, sulphur dioxide, hydrocarbon compounds, alkaline compounds, dust, particles, etc. All mentioned pollutants affect human health.
- **Noise;** Noise can cause many negative effects to humans. Traffic is the biggest cause of noise that increase depending on the type and number of transport vehicles, structure of transport, speed, infrastructure, etc.

Introduction of biofuels; As a member of Energy Community Serbia adopted a target of 10% of biofuels in transport sector in 2020 (Ministry of energy, development and environment, 2013). Target can be reached by introduction of biofuels and reduced energy demand for transport sector.

Global oil price;

Level of comfort;

Travel time and cost of travel; When an individual decides to make a trip to a particular location, travel time and cost are the primary factors influencing decision. The costs perceived by users have two main components: monetary costs and value of time spent costs. Travel time and costs can be reduced with organized, optimised and efficient transport.

However, policy instruments are very modest and they are not primarily targeting energy efficiency. Barriers related to the transport and related policy instruments are presented in table 10.

Table 10: Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector

Types of barriers	Country-specific barriers	Scale	Barriers addressed in current policy instruments
Social Cultural Educational	Heterogeneity of consumers	National	Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme is T2 measure in NEEAP. Foreseen instruments are targeted public information campaigns and Training and Education.
	Social group interactions and status considerations	National	
	Bounded rationality	National	
	Inertia	National	
	Credibility and trust.	National	
	Customs, habits	National	

	Lack of information, knowledge and experience	National, local	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)
	Lack of awareness of the population and local politicians about the potential, economic and social benefits from rational use of energy	National, local	Raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP)
	Lack of providing information from the best practice projects	National, local	Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme is T2 measure in NEEAP. Foreseen instruments are targeted public information campaigns and Training and Education.
	Lack of experience in cooperation with national and international funds	National, local	-
Economic	High Interest Rates and Numerous Additional Bank Fees and Charges	National	Introduction of incentive mechanisms (subsidies - grants, loans, etc.) for replacement of the existing vehicles are foreseen as T3 measure in NAPEE. Also, measure T5 - Determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization and the assignment of public transport service performance foreseen voluntary agreements and cooperation instruments (procurement, energy-efficient public procurement technology, commercial and institutional voluntary agreement) as mechanisms for
	Lack of Dedicated Financing	National	
	Low purchasing power of citizens	National, local	

			overcoming these barriers.
Institutional	Institutional Capacity of the Government of Serbia	National	-
	Energy Efficiency on the Government Agenda	National	-
	Institutional Capacity of the local self government	Local	-

4. KEY FINDINGS

Legislative and legal framework for regulation of efficient use of energy in the Republic of Serbia, was established for the first time, two years ago, when the Law on Efficient use of Energy was adopted. Accordingly, one of the preconditions for successful implementation of energy efficiency action plan is fulfilled.

Analyses presented in this document shows that numerous obstacles and barriers can be expected and will influence implementing of proposed measures from the Action plan, reducing expected achievements. Main identified barriers are listed and described for the building and the transport sectors for the Republic of Serbia. It is concluded that different types of barriers are present: economic, cultural, social, behavioural and institutional.

The key barrier for the implementation of programs for increasing energy efficiency in the building sector is unrealistic parity of energy prices and their instability, and above all the inadequate parity prices of electricity and other fuels. In such surrounding end users do not have an economic interest to invest in projects to increase energy efficiency. Energy in the Republic of Serbia is not a commodity. A significant part of the concern related to the social status of the population is carried out through energy prices. That reflects on general position of energy and energy products, which is discouraging for increasing energy efficiency. Another consequence of such price policy resulted in establishing the belief among the citizens that electricity price will remain low and unchanged. The position and importance of energy efficiency in the building sector is additionally affected by heat energy billing on a flat rate. Having in mind that energy-efficiency improvements assume and require support and participation of the ultimate energy consumer, these barriers have specific role, since they are in the interconnection and relation with some other barriers. According to the experience it is identified that influential barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency measures in residential subsector are limited purchasing power of consumers and insufficient education and information, both consumers and traders about the importance and possible effects of energy efficiency. Lack of education and awareness of the decision makers about the potential, economic

and social benefits from rational use of energy, limited capacity of the Ministry in charge and self-governments additionally impede increase of energy efficiency in public and commercial buildings.

Distorted District Heating Price and Absence of Metering should be overcome by Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy to the consumers connected to district heating system (Horizontal measure in NEEAP) and Regulation on determination of heat energy price (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b)

Rising of awareness and education are addressed by following: Labelling of energy-related products (refrigerating appliances, washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, electric bulbs and lamps, TVs, air-conditioning devices), Mandatory dissemination of information to energy consumers on the monthly consumption of electricity and heat, or natural gas (Horizontal measure in NEEAP).

However, main barriers for residential sector low electricity price and related barriers, and purchasing power of citizens are still not addressed.

Impression is that the transport sector occupies less attention than the building sector, from Government, Ministry in charge, local self-government to citizens (passenger and drivers). In general energy efficiency of transport is not the topic of high priority. At the level of the end user, behaviour can be shaped by the cost, comfort and overall travel time. Education about complex impact of transport is necessary at all levels (decision makers, administrative staff, citizens (passengers and drivers). Unlike the building sector, barriers inertia and mistrust are more emphasized. Significant shift can be reached with systematic infrastructural, organizational projects. It is noticeable that decision makers resist initiating big projects, instead preferring to continue with status quo. Changing habits and behaviour can be reached with dedicated educational campaigns supported with incentives and penalties.

Policy instruments for the transport sector are very modest and they are not primarily targeting energy efficiency. Still, many barriers are identified. To change end user behaviour promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme are measures proposed. Foreseen instruments for all stakeholders are targeted public information campaigns and training and education as well as raising awareness about the energy efficiency importance (Horizontal measure in NEEAP).

To address low purchasing power and support efficient technologies Introduction of incentive mechanisms (subsidies grants, loans, etc.) is foreseen. For public and freight transport, replacement of the existing vehicles and determination of energy efficiency as a criterion for fleet modernization are proposed for overcoming barriers.

Numerous barriers related to energy efficiency in both sectors are identified. Some of them are addressed by policy instruments, but some not. Decision makers should be aware of possibilities and effects of energy efficiency improvements, but also should be aware of numerous barriers and their influences on different stakeholders.

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WORKING PAPER ON SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BARRIERS IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

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United Kingdom
National Report

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

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HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

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ACRONYMS

ASHP	Air Source Heat Pump
BAT	Best Available Technologies
BERR	Business, Enterprise and Regulatory Reform
BPIE	Building Performance Institute Europe
CARES	Community Renewable Energy Scheme
CCA	Climate Change Agreements
CCL	Climate Change Levy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture Storage
CEEF	Central Energy Efficiency Fund
CENEX	Centre of Excellence for low carbon and fuel cell technologies
CERT	Carbon Emission Reduction Target
CESP	Community Energy Saving Programme
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CRC	Carbon Reduction Commitment
CT	Community Transport
DCLG	Department for Communities and Local Government
DEC	Display Energy Certificates
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
DfT	Department of Transportation
DNO	Distribution Network Operator
ECA	Enhanced Capital Allowances
ECO	Energy Company Obligation
EDR	Electricity Demand Reduction
EEC	Energy Efficiency Commitment
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Building Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ESME	Energy System Modelling Environment
ESOS	Energy Saving Opportunity Scheme
ETS	Emission Trading Scheme
EV	Electric Vehicles

FITs	Feed-in Tariff
GD	Green Deal
GGC	Greening Government Commitments
GSHP	Ground Source Heat Pump
HEIF	Renewable Energy Investment Fund
HGV	Heavy Goods Vehicle
HNDU	Heat Networks Delivery Unit
ICE	Incentive on Connections Engagement
ICV	Internal Combustion Vehicles
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
LCC	London Cycling Campaign
LCIS	Low Carbon Industrial Strategy
LEBS	Low Emission Bus Scheme
LESA	Landlords Energy Saving Allowance
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MW	Megawatts
NCR	National Charge Point Registry
NERA	Consultant company
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NVP	Net Present Value
OFGEM	Office of Gas and Electricity Market
OLEV	Office for Low Emissions Vehicle
ONS	Office for National Statistics
ORB	Oversight and Registration Body
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles
PICG	Plug-in Car Grant
PiCG	Plug-in Car Grant
PiP	Plugged-In Places
R&D	Research and Development
RCEF	Rural Community Energy Fund
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme
RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive
RIIO ED	Revenue Incentives Innovation Outputs Electricity Distribution
RO	Renewable Obligation

ROC	Renewable Obligation Certificate
RTFO	Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation
SERES	Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TINA	Technology Innovation Needs Assessment
TSB	Technology Strategy Board
UKERC	UK Energy Research Centre
UK-GBC	UK Green Building Council
ULEV	Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicle
UREF	Urban Community Energy Fund
VAT	Value Added Tax
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides the findings of a literature review into the barriers to energy efficiency policy in the UK. The material collected through this report will be used to inform deliverable D.2.1 'Working paper on social, economic, cultural and educational barriers in building and transport'. The outcome of D.2.1 will be used in tasks WP3 and WP4. The main barriers identified for each country in WP2 will be considered in the development of the scenarios build in the LEAP software.

More specifically, WP2 will provide a qualitative assessment of the key barriers for each country (e.g. small impact, medium impact, big impact), as these will be presented in this report by each partner. This assessment will be based on the expert view of each partner. WP3 will then attempt to quantify the effect of these barriers in combination with the policy instruments that allow overcoming them. The research outcome of WP3 will be included in WP4.

In 2013, the building sector accounted for 43% (13% services, 30% residential) of the UK's total energy consumption in 2013 and the transport sector accounted for 37% of the UK's total energy consumption. Both sectors are critical in terms of meeting international, European and national carbon reduction and energy efficiency targets.

Despite this, many barriers to enhanced energy efficiency in both the building and transport sectors exist, and are often highly complex with multiple inter-relations. The literature review has uncovered a series of UK-specific social, cultural, educational, institutional and economic barriers to improving the energy efficiency in the two sectors.

Within the building sector the main barriers include the undervaluing of energy efficiency, lack of motivation and inertia within consumers/end users, infrastructural and planning barriers to medium-sized energy projects as well as practical and construction-related barriers such as a lack of skills and adequate standards. Economic barriers such as upfront/capital costs and the lack of adequate or misaligned financial incentives also appear to be significant in terms of preventing the uptake of energy efficiency technologies and measures within the building sector (both domestic and non-domestic).

Within the transport sector the main barriers identified include the immature status of developing technologies, and lack of the necessary infrastructure to support low carbon transport (freight and passenger), the hesitancy and/or inertia of end-users/consumers to trust and take up new technologies, and the prohibitive nature of the capital costs involved and the limited business case for energy efficient transport infrastructure investment.

UK energy efficiency policies include regulatory, economic, dissemination and awareness, promotion of energy services as well as research and development policy instruments. The majority target the main identified barriers to energy efficiency in both the building and transport sectors, although in recent months changes in the UK Government suggest a revisions in priorities, and subsequently changes to current energy efficiency policy instruments and measures appear to being undertaken.

CHAPTER 1: CONTEXT

The Climate Change Act of 2008 established a legally binding target to reduce the UK's greenhouse gas emissions by at least 80% below 1990 levels by 2050. To drive progress and set the UK on a pathway towards this target, the Act introduced a system of carbon budgets which provide legally binding limits on the amount of emissions that may be produced in successive five-year periods, beginning in 2008. The first three carbon budgets were set in law in May 2009 and require emissions to be reduced by at least 34% below base year levels in 2020. The fourth carbon budget, covering the period 2023–27, was set in law in June 2011 and requires emissions to be reduced by 50% below 1990 levels. The Committee on Climate Change will publish its advice to government on the fifth carbon budget in December 2015, covering the period 2028-2032, as required under Section 4 of the Climate Change Act. The government will propose draft legislation for the fifth budget in 2016 (Committee on Climate Change, 2015).

By 2011, buildings emissions had fallen by 18%, despite the growth in population and housing. Regulation has required the introduction of new, more efficient condensing boilers, saving at least 1.1 billion EUR in 2011 on energy bills. Eleven million homes, 60% of all homes with cavity walls, have been fitted with cavity wall insulation. This reduced the amount the UK spends on heating in 2011 by 1.8 billion EUR (HM Government, 2011). To continue to deliver these savings there are two key areas in housing government policy is focused: energy efficiency (the government's immediate priority) through fabric improvement and low carbon heat. Table 1 indicates the energy consumption from the building sector in 2013.

Table 1 Building energy consumption 2013 (DECC, 2014c)

Sub-category	Energy consumption (mtoe)	Percentage of category
Domestic buildings	43.8	53.7%
Space heating	28.7	65.5%
Water	7.5	17.1%
Cooking	1.1	2.5%
Lighting	1.2	2.7%
Appliances	5.4	12.3%
Non-domestic buildings	37.7	46.3%
Catering	4.1	10.9%
Computing	1.4	3.7%
Cooling & ventilation	2.1	5.6%
Hot water	2.8	7.4%

Heating	14.4	38.3%
Lighting	9.5	25.3%
Other	3.3	8.8%

Energy efficiency in buildings, until recently, had been encouraged through a series of economic incentives and regulatory policy measures such as ‘The Green Deal’, a finance measure created to remove the upfront costs to the consumer of energy efficiency, with the cost being recouped through savings on their energy bills and the Energy Company Obligation (ECO); which followed on from policy measures such as the Energy Efficiency Commitment (1 and 2) and the Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) which required energy companies both to reduce emissions through undertaking solid wall insulation and to tackle fuel poverty by installing central heating systems, replacing boilers, and subsidising cavity wall and loft insulation. In parallel, the deployment of Smart Meters to every home in the UK is to support consumers in managing their energy and expenditure intelligently. In addition there is the urgent need to support ways of heating buildings without emitting carbon. Through the Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) and Renewable Heat Premium Payment, over 130,000 low carbon heat installations are expected to be carried out by 2020. At the same time the Government will work with local authorities, where appropriate, to lay the foundations for district heating networks, particularly in urban areas with more densely packed demand for heat. This should enable the long-term delivery of heat from low carbon sources (HM Government, 2011)

In transport, emissions are roughly the same as they were in 1990. Emissions rose before 2007 as the economy grew and transport demand increased, but have since fallen due to improvements in new car efficiency, an increased uptake of biofuels and, to a lesser extent, the recent economic downturn. Table 2 indicates the energy consumption from the transport sector in 2013.

Table 2 Transport energy consumption 2013 (DECC, 2014b)

Sub-category	Energy consumption (mtoe)	Percentage of category
Road	39.3	74%
Passenger transport	24.9	63%
Freight	14.4	37%
Air	12.3	23%
Rail	1.1	2%
Water	0.8	<2%

Domestic transport emissions make up nearly a quarter of UK emissions. Over the next decade, average emissions of new cars are set to fall by around a third, primarily through more efficient combustion engines. Sustainable biofuels will also deliver substantial emissions reductions. As deeper cuts are required, vehicles will run on ultra-low emission technologies such as electric batteries, hydrogen fuel cells and plug-in hybrid technology. These vehicles could also help to deliver wider environmental benefits, including improved local air quality and reduced traffic noise. To

ensure that these emissions savings are delivered, the Government will continue to work at EU level to press for strong EU vehicle emissions standards for 2020 and beyond in order to deliver improvements in conventional vehicle efficiency and give certainty about future markets for ultra-low emission vehicles. To support the growth of the ultra-low emission vehicle market, the Government is providing around 425 million EUR this Parliament for consumer incentives, worth up to £5,000 per car, and further support for the research, development and demonstration of new technologies (HM Government, 2011).

1.1 OVERVIEW OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

1.1.1 BUILDINGS SECTOR

Since the 1990s the UK has implemented a large number of policies to drive energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors. In the building sector the basic objective of reducing energy use and cutting down on waste in the UK, is so that energy bills can be reduced for hard-pressed consumers; make energy supplies more secure and reduce reliance on overseas imports; and drive down greenhouse gas emissions cost-effectively. There is also the view that investment in energy efficiency will increase productivity and support long-term growth in the UK. In 2011/2012, the UK's energy efficiency market accounted for around 136,000 jobs and sales of over 25.5 billion EUR (DECC, 2014e). Though there are effective policies in place there is concern that the UK will not meet its Carbon Budgets given economic and political complications (Donat, Velten, & Duwe, 2014). Furthermore a number of policy measures and tools are being abandoned within the same month this report is being written (HM Treasury, 2015).

Most recently however, the UK Government implemented the regulatory policy instrument the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) to comply with Article 8 of the Energy Efficiency Directive. This scheme will provide large enterprises with cost-effective recommendations for energy efficiency improvements every four years. It is estimated that ESOS alone will result in overall net benefits to the UK economy of 2.7 billion EUR between 2015 and 2030, and drive around 3TWh of energy savings annually (DECC, 2014e). ESOS is evaluated and regulated by a registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office): England – Environment Agency, Northern Ireland – Northern Ireland Environment Agency, Scotland – Scottish Environment Protection Agency, Wales – Natural Resources Wales, Offshore – DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (Environment Agency, 2015). In addition to this, the UK is leading the way on the roll out of smart meters with in-home displays (dissemination and awareness instrument/regulatory for energy companies). This programme is considered essential to empowering consumers by providing them with access to the information they need to make informed decisions about their energy consumption (DECC, 2014e). DECC is responsible for driving delivery and providing active oversight of progress by all delivery parties. During 2014, industry partners including the Data and Communications Company and its contractors, energy suppliers, network operators and manufacturers have continued to develop the systems that will deliver smart meters to consumers when the main installation phase begins (DECC, 2012b).

One of the most important building related economic policy measures for the UK Government over the past several years has been the Green Deal. The Green Deal and the Energy Company Obligation (regulatory for energy companies) in combination help households insulate their homes and ensure that they have access to trusted information about energy efficiency. The Green Deal is also complemented by domestic Renewable Heat Incentive and the Feed-in Tariff scheme (economic) and the Green Open Homes initiative (dissemination and awareness instrument) (DECC, 2014e). The effectiveness of the Green Deal is still yet to be seen. The Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB), on behalf of the Secretary of State, manages the authorisation scheme for

participants in the Green Deal and is responsible for a number of functions aimed at providing effective administration and oversight of the scheme. The GD ORB is responsible for maintaining a register of all authorised Green Deal Providers, Certification Bodies, Assessors and Installers; maintaining the Green Deal Code of Practice and controlling the use of the Quality Mark; ongoing monitoring of Green Deal Participants against the Code of Practice; producing an annual Green Deal report; and gathering evidence of non-compliance and referring participants to the Ombudsman or the Secretary of State where appropriate and imposing sanctions when directed (DCLG, 2015). Table 3 displays the most relevant policy instruments and measures for energy efficiency in the building sector currently in place in the UK, and must not be taken as an exhaustive list.

Table 3 National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the building sector

Policy instrument	Policy measures
<p>Regulatory policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (EPBD) • EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED) • Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates) • Zero Carbon Homes • Code for Sustainable Homes • Warm Front • The Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • Renewable Energy Strategy • Renewable Obligation Certificate (ROC) • Planning and Energy Act 2008 • Smart Metering and Billing • Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Display Energy Certificates (DECs) • Low Carbon Transition Plan • Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) • Energy Efficiency Commitment 1 and 2 (EEC 1 and 2) • Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) • Community Energy Saving Programme (CESP) • Private and Social Sector Regulation (Scotland) • Greening Government Commitments (GGC) (similar schemes for the devolved governments) • Home Energy Conservation Act • Decent Homes Standard • Energy Act 2011 • National products policy (tranche 2 - adopted measures) • National products policy (tranche 1 - implemented measures) • Ecodesign for Energy Related Products Regulations (SI 2010 No 2617) • Ecodesign for energy related Products Directives (2009/125/EC) • Energy Labelling Directive (2010/30/EU)
<p>Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon Trust Measures • Smart Metering Implementation Programme • Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust • INVEST NI (Northern Ireland)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Savings Advice Service • Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES) • Big Energy Saving Week • Green Economy Awards • Open Homes Network • Act on CO2 Advice • Committee on Climate Change Guidance • Mandatory GHG reporting scheme • Voluntary Agreement on the Phase Out of Incandescent Light Bulbs • Community Energy Programme • Market Transformation Programme • Community Energy Advice Programme (pilot schemes)
<p>Economic policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Deal Finance Company • Warm Front Scheme • Renewable Obligation (RO) • Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) scheme • Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) • Government Buying Standards • Salix Project and public sector loans • Loans to SMEs by Carbo Trust • EU ETS Carbon Price Floor • Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme (CRC) • Green Investment Bank • Climate Change Agreements (CCA) • Electricity Market Reform • Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition • Re:FIT national programme • Climate Change Levy (CCL) • Public Sector Central Energy Efficiency Fund (CEEF) (Scotland) • Home Energy Efficiency Programmes (Scotland) • Home Renewables Loan Scheme (Scotland) • Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland) • Resource Efficiency Scotland (SME Loans Scheme) • Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF) • Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni’Fro (Wales) • Enhanced Capital Allowances (ECA) incl. Energy Technology List • Nest: Home Energy Efficiency Scheme (Wales) • Sustainable Energy Programme (Northern Ireland) • Boiler Replacement Scheme (Northern Ireland) • Landlords Energy Saving Allowance (LESA) • Stamp Duty Relief for Zero Carbon Homes • Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scottish District Heating Loan Fund • Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF) • Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)
<p>Capacity building and networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Technologies Institute • Resource Efficient Scotland • Green Deal Training and Certification for Assessors/Installers • Peer-to-peer community energy mentoring scheme • Funding for facilities/management apprenticeships • Funding competition for energy efficiency training • Community Energy Strategy • Capacity Market • One Stop Shop for community energy projects • Community First funding and community organisers training
<p>Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Energy Performance Contract and list of available energy service contracts on government website • Best Practice Guide to Energy Performance Contracting • Updated Guide to Financing Energy Efficiency in the Public Sector (20120) • Guide to Financing Energy Efficiency in the Private Sector • Review of Energy Services Market • Quality Assurance labels e.g. Green Deal Quality Mark • License Lite • Energy Services Directive • RIIO ED1 Price Control model for network regulation • Time to Connect incentive for DNOs • Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs
<p>Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Technology Institute (incl. Energy system modelling environment (ESME)) • CHP Development Map • National Heat Map and Strategy • Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU) • Innovation Rollout Mechanism • Low Carbon Industrial Strategy (LCIS) • Low Carbon Buildings Programme • Low Carbon Networks Fund • Energy Entrepreneurs Fund • Technology Innovation Needs Assessment • Small Business Research Initiative • TSB Future Energy Management in Buildings Programme • Invest in Innovative Refurbishment • Advanced Heat Storage Competition • End Use Energy Demand Research Centres

1.1.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

The UK transport sector has a key role to play in improving energy efficiency. As a result of Government policy, the transport sector is seeing increasing take up of energy efficiency measures; the efficiency of new cars in the UK improved by 27% between 2002 and 2012. Regulations in place since 2009 requiring the automotive industry to produce more efficient vehicles ensure that cars use much less fuel, equivalent, on average, to a saving of 42 pence per litre, as projected by 2020 (DECC, 2014e).

The UK Government recently announced a long-term, comprehensive package of support for the Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicle (ULEV) sector. The 2013 Spending Round announced 708m EUR to support the development of the ULEV market from 2015-2020, which builds on the £400m already committed. It is the Government's aspiration that by 2050 almost every car and van in the UK will be an ULEV. In February 2013 the Government announced a 52m EUR package of measures including grants for the installation of home, on-street and train station charging points. Additionally, the uptake of ultra-low emission cars is promoted through the provision of consumer grants. As of 31 December 2013, 6709 claims had been made through the Plug-in Car Grant scheme and 404 claims have been made through the Plug-in Van Grant scheme (DECC, 2014e). The Department of Transportation (DfT) through the Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV) supplies the grants. Auto dealerships will manage all paperwork with regard to the grants. It is a requirement of the Plug-In Car Grant that manufacturers of eligible vehicles set out how they will engage with purchasers to ensure safe recharging of their vehicles; and the Institution of Engineering and Technology, the standards body responsible for electrical safety, is producing a Code of Practice to advise electricians how to ensure safe plug-in vehicle recharging installations (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2011).

Other policy measures include Eco-driving training (regulatory – basics provided in practical driving tests / Dissemination and awareness instruments – Energy Saving Trust offers eco-driving lessons to business vehicle fleet drivers); The Low Emissions Bus Scheme (successor to the Green Bus Fund), economic policy measures, which aims to cut greenhouse gas emission levels and encourage bus operators and local councils to make the switch to greener and quieter buses including hybrid, electric and biomethane gas buses. The bus schemes are funded by OLEV and administered by DfT (DECC, 2014e). Table 4 displays the most relevant policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector currently in place in the UK, and must not be taken as an exhaustive list.

Table 4 National programmes and initiatives targeting energy efficiency in the transport sector

Policy instrument	Policy measures
Planning policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Infrastructure Plan 2014 • Smart Grid Forum (assessing vehicle uptake scenarios) • Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy) • Eco-towns: A supplement to Planning Policy Statement 1 • (Ultra-) Low Carbon Emissions Zones at local authority/regional level e.g. London • Development of Local/Regional Bicycling Networks e.g. London • Further electrification of rail network •
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Directives e.g. Renewable Energy Directive, Fuel Quality Directive, Energy Efficiency Directive

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Car policies (EU new car CO2 emissions targets: 130 gCO2/km by 2015 and 95 gCO2/km by 2020; and complementary measures) • LGV policies (EU new LGV CO2 emissions targets: 175g CO2/km by 2017 and 147 gCO2/km by 2020; and complementary measures) • HGV policies (low rolling resistance tyres and industry-led action to improve efficiencies) • Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands • Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) • Eco Driving training included in national driving tests • Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) • Road transport codes (speed limits etc.)
<p>Economic policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Company Car Tax Reform • Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • Plug-in car and van grants (including Electric Vehicle Homecharge Scheme) • Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS) (successor scheme to the Green Bus Fund) • Local Sustainable Transport Fund • Community transport minibus • Congestion Charges (local authority/regional level) • Local Authority funding/initiatives e.g. Kensington and Chelsea
<p>Dissemination and awareness policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel Economy labels for cars • The National Standard for cycle training • Eco Driving Training/FuelGood Driver Training • Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme • National Charge Point Registry (NCR) • Local/Regional initiatives e.g. Transport for London and London Cycling Campaign community bicycle project
<p>Research and Development policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • £82 million of research and development funding available from UK Government to support the new generation of ULEVs; with a focus on identifying and funding emerging technologies that the UK can exploit and lead on globally. • Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP) • Funding for development of ultra low emissions vehicles (ULEVs) e.g. Technology Strategy Board’s Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform • UK Government funding for advanced biofuel research • Low Carbon HGV Technology Taskforce (research and trials into energy efficiency measures for road freight) • UKH2Mobility project

1.2 OVERVIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE PARTNER COUNTRY

Overall, it is estimated that in the UK, a saving of 268TWh could be made through energy efficiency improvements by 2020; although this saving reduces to 196TWh¹, once measures have been evaluated for social cost-effectiveness (DECC, 2012a).

1.2.1 BUILDING SECTOR

The total potential energy efficiency in building-related sectors (domestic and commercial) is estimated to be 121TWh (93TWh from the domestic sector and 28TWh from the commercial sector) by 2020; with cost effective energy savings estimated to be 83TWh (56TWh from the domestic sector and 27TWh from the commercial sector). The following is a summary of the main existing technologies in the building sector² and their estimated energy savings by 2020 (DECC, 2012a):

- *Heating and hot water systems: domestic air source heat pumps (211-226TWh); commercial CHP (200-201TWh); internal solid wall insulation (226-236TWh); domestic loft insulation (150-151TWh)*
- *Appliances: domestic appliances best available technology (100-103TWh)*
- *Lighting: domestic lighting best available technology (0-1TWh); commercial retrofit lighting (16-19TWh)*
- *Energy generation: solar photovoltaics (6-18TWh)*

Furthermore, research (Low Carbon Innovation Coordination Group, 2012) suggests that innovation in energy efficient technologies in the UK's non-domestic building sector alone has the potential for estimated savings of 18MtCO₂e by 2020 as well as estimated savings of 11MtCO₂e by 2020 in domestic buildings. Both existing and innovative energy efficiency technologies in the building sector are currently supported to some extent by a variety of energy efficiency policy instruments, including regulatory, economic and informative, and are expected to provide energy savings of 76TWh by 2020. An example of this is the installation of cavity wall insulation in 73% of the UK's cavity wall dwellings through UK Government regulatory and economic policy instruments (such as the CERT, ECO and Green Deal) (DECC, 2015). A further example is that, of the total capacity of solar photovoltaics installed up to the end of May 2015 (7,265MW capacity over 709,550 systems), 42% (3,075MW over 694,961 systems) is accredited to Feed-in Tariff (FiTs) installations and 45% (3,300MW over 11,774 systems) is accredited to the Renewables Obligation (DECC, 2014d).

1.2.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

In terms of the transport sector, it is estimated that its total energy efficiency potential in 2020 is 66TWh, with projected energy savings from UK policy of 51TWh (DECC, 2012a). The main existing energy efficiency technologies in the UK, and, where applicable, their estimated energy savings in 2020 (DECC, 2012a) are:

- *For road transport: low rolling resistance tyres for HGVs (97-100TWh), (ultra-)low emission vehicles (245-260TWh)*
- *For rail transport: transport rail electrification (1-1.5TWh)*

¹ Resulting in the UK's final energy consumption in 2020 being 11% lower than the business as usual baseline

² Data relating to air conditioning has not been included due to the minimal use and installation of air conditioning technologies in UK buildings.

- For *navigation*: improved hydro- and aerodynamics, improved energy efficiency through waste heat recovery systems (Sekimizu, 2015);
- For *aviation*: engines with increased fuel efficiency, use of alternative fuels.

The majority of the UK's policies instruments that support both existing and innovative technologies in the transport sector are based on policies set at EU level, but include a mix of instrument types including regulatory (EU new car CO₂ emissions targets: 130 gCO₂/km by 2015 and 95 gCO₂/km by 2020; and complementary measures), economic (Plug-in car and van grants (including Electric Vehicle Homecharge Scheme) and planning ((Ultra-)Low Carbon Emissions Zones at local authority/regional level e.g. London). Innovative technologies are supported through policy instruments aimed at encouraging research and development such as the UK Government's advanced biofuel demonstration competition.

More details on the technologies for achieving energy efficiency and their degree of diffusion in the UK can be found in Deliverable 1.4. "Technological trends in the building and transport sector – UK".

CHAPTER 2: MAPPING COUNTRY-SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTORS

This chapter provides a review and assessment of the barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency, specifically in the UK’s building and transport sectors. The literature review has highlighted the vast array and complex nature of such barriers; whilst they can be broken down into economic and non-economic (social, cultural, educational and institutional) barriers, the majority of barriers are inter-related (e.g. socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-educational), and as such, can often be described as cross-cutting barriers. Furthermore, some barriers are specific to certain areas of the wider sector, and nearly all are dependent on the actors involved; in part due to economic reasons, but also due to the motivations and attitudes towards energy efficiency (for example, the landlord-tenant split incentive (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012)). The following tables outline the main economic and non-economic barriers in both the building and transport sectors, but it must be noted that the lists are not exhaustive, and are dependent on existing research and literature available.

The identified barriers were assessed in terms of their impact, from ‘High’ to ‘Low’, with the following criteria taken into consideration:

- The number of different resources that identified the same barrier;
- The number of sub-sectors that were linked with the same barrier;
- The easiness with which the barrier can be confronted;
- The duration of the barrier;
- The number of different policy instruments that were linked with the same type of barrier.

Tables 5-7 outline the main identified social, cultural and educational, economic and institutional barriers in the building sector in the UK, per main subsector (where applicable).

Tables 9-11 outline the main identified social, cultural and educational, economic and institutional barriers in the transport sector in the UK, per main subsector (where applicable).

An assessment of the importance of the barriers is made in Tables 8 and 12.

2.1 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE BUILDING SECTOR

The building sector contains several intersecting subsectors, including existing and new buildings, domestic and non-domestic buildings as well as energy efficiency technologies that can be installed across all building types. In order to provide a simplified overview of the UK-specific barriers within this complex sector, the following tables outline a) barriers that have impacts across all subsectors; b) barriers specific to retrofitting existing buildings (domestic and non-domestic); c) barriers specific to the uptake of efficient heating systems; d) barriers specific to the take-up of renewable (microgeneration) technologies; e) barriers specific to renewable heat systems (small- and medium-scale); and f) barriers specific to the adoption of green energy tariffs.

Table 5 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the building sector

Type of barrier	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Social/ educational/ cultural	Undervaluing energy efficiency	The lack of salience of energy efficiency increases the impact of hassle costs and behavioural barriers. Energy efficiency changes may involve significant hassle costs for those carrying out the investment, which increases the costs of the investment. For example, disruption caused by building works or disruption to production lines. Energy efficiency

		<p>improvements may not be seen as strategic for a company and therefore not prioritised. For example, outside of the energy intensive industry sectors, energy bills are only a small proportion of business costs. If the relative gain is small, then the hassle costs can act as a significant barrier, especially if there is uncertainty around the benefits of the investment. While hassle costs are not a market failure, they compound the impact of other behavioural barriers, reducing investment in energy efficiency. This is often why companies are reluctant to invest in energy efficiency, seeking short payback times, even if a project is cost-effective at usual interest rates. Wider economic uncertainty is also reducing willingness to invest. Partly as a result of the lack of trusted information, the long-term benefits of improved energy efficiency are often regarded as less certain. Consequently, energy efficiency is undervalued relative to other investment options and not prioritised as it might otherwise be.(DECC, 2012a)</p>
Social/ cultural	Inertia/Habit	<p>This may include inertia in decision making or basing decisions on habit (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). Research has shown that a significant barrier in occupants concerned the prospect of having to change one's lifestyle. This was because occupants consider that this would only be achievable with great discomfort and sacrifice of standards of living and social image. Participants in a survey conducted by Lorenzoni et al. (2007) tended to be reluctant to consider changing many of their routines and habits, and to consider alternative options(Lorenzoni, Nicholson-Cole, & Whitmarsh, 2007)</p>
Social/ cultural	Mistrust of technologies	<p>In some cases, consumers worry that high-efficiency devices (such as some washing machines and dishwashers) will not perform as well as conventional models. (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007)</p>
Social/ cultural	Inter-occupant relationships	<p>Slightly over 10% of all responses in a study by Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012) mentioned that their family, partner, or housemate was a barrier in their household. It is interesting to note that out of this category, over 60% of responses mentioned their children as being the main barrier. An illustrative quote highlights this issue: <i>"It doesn't occur to them [children]. They just don't think. You encourage them to switch off but they forget, there's far more, many more important things going on, like what they can eat next, who they are going to see"</i>. Some interviewees also mentioned their partners, for example: <i>"She [wife] rather have it look good than save on cost"</i> and <i>"I wish my husband turned off the lights and the television. (Interviewer): Why doesn't he? (Interviewee) because he's a lazy sod"</i>. These quotes highlight how poor energy efficiency behaviours are sometimes blamed on others. Such a shift in responsibility may weaken personal liability and create a self-reinforcing environment of poor behaviour, as illustrated in this quote, <i>"when you live in a shared house ... people can't really be bothered to put in any effort, myself included. Obviously when you have your own place, then you're much more keen on finding new solutions or controlling energy waste"</i>. This quote is interesting since it highlights how personal energy habits between tenants are more significant than the price of the wasted energy. This factor was associated with households with 3 or more occupants; future energy efficiency campaigns or interventions should address all of the occupants/family in a household, rather than just individuals (M. J. Pelenur & H. J. Cruickshank, 2012)</p>

Social/ cultural	Mistrust of energy companies or contractors	<i>I'm concerned with these people who cold call me about having loft insulation and pumping the walls full of junk ... I want to feel comfortable with the contractor, know that they will do what they say they will do</i> (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012).
Social	Perceived lack of impact	Research has shown that occupants feel that individual action would have little effect in comparison to other, larger scale emitters. Participants generally argued that it was not worthwhile taking action at this individual level given its limited efficacy (Lorenzoni et al., 2007)
Social/ cultural	Perceived lack of political action	Studies have shown that distrust in governments to take responsibility for the actions of the individual/community to be meaningful plays a significant role in affecting the motivation and attitudes of the public. Participants, even when willing to take action, often maintain that their behaviour is constrained by the lack of enabling infrastructures and mechanisms. For instance, in one research study, they pointed to a lack of affordable and reliable public transport in their locality, higher prices of environmentally-friendly goods, design of the built environment encouraging car use, lack of disincentives to pollute (e.g., higher car tax for bigger cars), and so on. (Lorenzoni et al., 2007)
Social/ cultural/ educational	Perceived lack of action by business and industry	Similarly, research suggests a lack of action by business and industry is seen as a barrier to the personal engagement of some individuals. Also, participants in a study conducted by Lorenzoni et al. (2007) were reluctant to change their behaviour when they felt others would not follow suit i.e. problem of free riding
Social/ cultural	Social norms and accepted behaviours	<p>Another form of constraint explicitly identified in research studies was social norms and the expectations required by carbon-dependent lifestyles. Socially-acceptable ways of behaving—for example, driving to work, frequent long-haul holidays and weekend breaks, leaving appliances on and the weekly supermarket shop—in turn become ingrained as unconscious habitual behaviours, making them unquestioned and thus more intractable (Jackson, 2005). Ownership and consumption, for example of cars and electronic goods, are important status symbols in our society and people feel they are expected to achieve this (Steg & Sievers, 2000). Some of the literature argues that once people become accustomed to a particular standard of living, their perceptions of needs and expectations change. Their revised expectations are perpetuated in discourses about quality of life, and once absorbed into daily routine become interpreted as “needs” rather than “wants” (Shove, 2003; Steg & Sievers, 2000). For example, participants talked about “needing” a car to get to work, do the shopping, take children to school and so on, without considering that there might be alternatives.</p> <p>The interdependency between physical infrastructures and social institutions contributes to creating a lock-in which restricts radical innovation (Jackson, 2005) and reinforces environmentally-detrimental behaviours (Hobson, 2003). For example, desires for consumption and links to status and cultural values are perpetuated in current western society by marketing mechanisms (Lorenzoni et al., 2007).</p>
Social/ cultural	Externalising responsibility	Research indicates that of the many participants who still felt that something could be done about climate change, many located responsibility for causing and mitigating climate change with others

	and blame	(individuals, governments, business, industry and other countries) or looked to technological solutions to “save us”. Shifting the blame and denying personal responsibility was found to be a major barrier to engagement in all three studies (Lorenzoni et al., 2007)
Educational	Access to trusted Information	<p>There is currently a lack of access to trusted and appropriate energy efficiency information. Where information is available it may be generic and not tailored to specific circumstances, which means that enterprises are not able to fully assess the benefits of an energy efficiency investment (DECC, 2012a).</p> <p>One of the key characteristics of the embryonic market is that there is a lack of access to trusted and appropriate information. Energy efficiency improvements are often made through purchasing upgraded equipment of which energy efficiency may only be one characteristic. Where information is available, it may be generic, and not tailored to specific circumstances, which means that potential investors are not in a position to assess the benefits of an energy efficiency investment. Financing of energy efficiency projects can be undermined by the absence of standardised monitoring and verification processes which means that the benefits of energy efficiency investments are not trusted. While information is available about overall energy consumption both in the home and in business settings, it can be difficult to relate that back to individual activities to identify opportunities to make energy efficiency improvements. In the absence of clear, trusted information, many individuals do not prioritise energy efficiency investments.</p>
Educational	Lack of information on energy use	<p>From a rational choice model of human behaviour if households do not know their level of energy expenditure, how energy can be reduced, by how much, or at what cost, they are unlikely to consider investment in energy efficiency. However although information provision is often necessary it is rarely sufficient in itself to encourage behaviour change (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). Occupants do not understand how much energy they use and feel they have poor control over it. A great deal of research and practical experimentation has attempted to make energy visible to householders through the provision of various kinds of feedback. This has included providing more informative bills, putting energy labels on domestic appliances (Boardman, 2004); providing in-depth energy advice via leaflets, websites and face-to-face (Abrahamse, Steg, Vlek, & Rothengatter, 2007; Darby, 2003) and, most recently, through a range of in-home real time displays and monitors (OFGEM, 2009). Notably, these studies reveal the importance and success of providing feedback that is clear, immediate and user-specific, resulting in savings of between 5% and 15% (Darby, 2006; Hargreaves, Nye, & Burgess, 2010).</p>
Educational	Visibility of energy efficiency	<p>In many markets, electricity customers do not see the real cost of power, which limits the potential for price signals to encourage changes in behaviour. Customers typically have no accurate information about the energy consumed by any particular application, such as the added cost of a spare refrigerator, or the relative benefit of having the refrigerator located in a cool basement, versus a warm garage. Furthermore, based on the way electricity is priced, customers do not receive accurate signals about the marginal cost of power, which, for example, can vary</p>

		significantly throughout the course of a day. (Creys et al, 2007)
Educational	Lack of awareness on savings potential	Consumers, architects, engineers, builders, contractors, installers and building operators are often not aware of savings potential, or are poorly informed about performance benefits.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). This also involves confusion about the links between environmental issues and their respective solutions (Lorenzoni et al., 2007)
Educational	Perceived information over-load.	Another barrier that relates to information, is the perception of information overload that prevents building users from looking into energy efficiency; in other words there is too much information available, but trusted sources are hard to find (Lorenzoni et al., 2007)
Barriers to retrofit		
Social/ cultural	Rebound effect	<p>The Rebound Effect is a phenomenon which occurs when energy efficiency improvements counter-intuitively lead to higher levels of energy consumption. One review attempted to examine the macro influence of the Rebound Effect on UK energy demand, and found in their model that the direct and indirect Rebound Effects resulted in an energy demand increase of 11% (Barker, Ekins, & Foxon, 2007). This result considers the aggregated effects from all UK energy policies, and may significantly impact the effectiveness of future policy interventions. However, such estimates are difficult to calculate, and other models expect the Rebound Effect for thermal insulation and heating systems to be much higher, in the region of 50% to 100% (Oreszczyn & Lowe, 2005). As such, the risk is that if the Rebound Effect is not properly considered or understood during the development of retrofit policies, then their effectiveness in practice may be muted (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012)</p> <p>This issue of thermal comfort ‘take-back’ was reported by (Bell & Lowe, 2000) in a study analysing the savings of energy efficient refurbishments on four similar sized semi-detached houses. The aim was to confirm that significant savings could be gained from conventional 1980s retrofit technologies. Following an extensive two-week energy monitoring period, a 47% reduction in energy consumption was observed, proving that significant savings could be achieved from conventional retrofit measures. However, this was 40% lower than their predictions, which Bell and Lowe (2000) suggested was mostly due to people’s behaviour and thermal comfort take-back from the new heating systems. (Dowson, Poole, Harrison, & Susman, 2012)</p>
Social/ cultural/ educational	Lack of awareness / interest / motivation	Awareness raising and promotional activities should address the psychological barriers which exist concerning deep renovation. A discussion about societal values needs to address behaviour change to support investment decisions in favour of sustainability rather than investment decisions driven by social status factors, or by short term return considerations. Soft measures need to support a shift in values which can speed up progress towards more sustainable behaviour by all actors in the buildings value chain. (BPIE, 2011)
Social/ cultural/	Refurbishment seen as low	(Ravetz, 2008) claims that many people do not view energy efficient refurbishments as a high priority when updating their homes. (Power,

educational	priority	2008) states that energy efficient refurbishment is undervalued by communities. People seem to prefer amenities such as new kitchens, bathrooms, central heating, and general repairs, instead of energy efficient refurbishments since the social gains are more obvious (Bell & Lowe, 2000).
Social	Socio-economic status of household	According to Roberts (2008), before the introduction of gas powered central heating systems in the 1970s, most people preferred indoor temperatures at 20 °C or less, and would wear more clothes during winter to prevent paying high energy costs. By comparison, nowadays people have developed thermal comfort preferences of 23–25 °C, which tends to be satisfied through higher quantities of energy consumed for heating (Roberts, 2008). Both (Clinch & Healy, 2000) and (Milne & Boardman, 2000), claim a large proportion of this take-back relates to the socio-economic status of the household prior to the refurbishment (Dowson et al., 2012)
Social	Confidence in contracting and delivery	Membership organisations such as the Green Register and the Association of Environmentally Conscious builders provide a route to lists of trained and passionate professionals but there is currently no accreditation scheme and little to provide confidence between those that claim and those that actually can deliver. As a result finding comparable quotes from trusted professionals can be extremely difficult (Ross, 2011).
Cultural	Aesthetics	It is interesting to note, that some respondents mentioned the aesthetics of the home as a barrier, for example, <i>“we've got original windows in our house, which aren't secondary double glazed, so that's a huge loss of heat, but secondary double glazing isn't ideal for aesthetics ... so this is something we know is not helpful in terms of energy efficiency, but we haven't changed it.”</i> (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012)
Educational	Skills and training	Skill shortages exist in both the contractor market responsible for effective installation of energy saving measures, as well as in professional services, with few architects and designers familiar with how to specify a low energy renovation. (BPIE, 2011)
Educational	Understanding of costs versus perceived benefits	As highlighted in the survey of Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012) the significance of cost is increased as a barrier if the benefits of the energy efficiency measures are unknown, or if the benefits are perceived to be very low. Two illustrative quotes highlight this point, <i>“The thing is, if you double glaze your house and everything, it is an awful lot of money, and how many years is it going to take before you get your money back?”</i> ; <i>“... Maybe cost, even though we don't know how much it [energy efficiency measures] costs.”</i> Uncertainty over lower fuel bills and payback period was also identified in research conducted by (UK-GBC, 2008)
Educational	Quality of information	One of the most significant challenges to ensure progression through these stages is the provision of information for each of the parties involved, to build trust and ensure appropriate action. Not only are the information requirements very different between the delivery professionals, from analysts to subcontractors, but also between property owners. According to Refit West homeowners: <i>“We found the gathering of information a headache, as detailed guidance was not readily available.”</i> the homeowner needs to be able to access

		independent impartial and considered advice, appropriate for their particular needs (Ross, 2011).
Social	Lack of time and resources	Reliance on a particular individual or small group of participants, particularly where they are volunteers, means energy efficiency projects can be very vulnerable to changes in circumstance, particularly in terms of time and resources. For example, changes in family or work commitments can result in lack of motivation and ability to undertake retrofit projects.
Barriers to uptake of efficient heating systems		
Social/ cultural/ educational	Unwillingness to replace systems	Despite lack of capital being cited as a key barrier to replacing systems, only 14% said they would be likely to do so given a higher income. Indeed, two thirds (67%) said they would be unlikely to do so in this circumstance. While providing upfront financial assistance may help overcome these financial barriers, a significant challenge will be that most homeowners do not anticipate replacing their heating system until it actually breaks down(DECC, 2013a)
Educational	Lack of awareness of available systems	Awareness levels of the more efficient heating technologies studied ranged from the 86% having heard of gas condensing boilers to only 27% for micro-CHP. The second most commonly recognised was solar thermal (83% claimed to have heard of this) followed by a GSHP and biomass boiler (both 47%). ASHPs recorded 32% and heat networks 31%. The low level of awareness of some of these heating systems is likely to be a significant barrier to uptake. (DECC, 2013a)
Barriers to microgeneration technologies		
Social/ cultural	Local oppositions to new energy infrastructure	Where there may be local opposition to new energy infrastructure, this can be a serious barrier. It is important that community-scale energy projects are able to get as much support from the wider community as possible, and to have a plan for addressing any concerns people have about local impacts. (DECC, 2014a)
Social/ cultural/ educational	Confidence in the system/Mistrust	A frequently cited barrier to installing microgeneration systems relates to a lack of confidence that the system will perform as desired. Whilst some studies suggest potential adopters are motivated to install by confidence in performance and reliability (e.g. (Caird & Roy, 2010)), many studies cite barriers such as performance uncertainties (Brook Lyndhurst Ltd., Mori., & Upstream, 2003; Caird & Roy, 2010; Ellison, 2004; Zahedi, 2011), uncertain payback on investment (Scarpa & Willis, 2010), uncertainty over the reliability, or even lack, of general and technical information, and uncertainty over the potential benefits of microgeneration (Williams, 2010). These barriers involve considerations such as: Home/location not suitable, system performance or reliability not good enough, energy reliability, access to trustworthy information/advice and trustworthy builders to install (Balcombe, Rigby, & Azapagic, 2013)

Social/ cultural	Low priority	A barrier to adopting microgeneration may simply be that households are generally content with their existing system and thus see the replacement of their system as a low priority since there is not enough perceived relative advantage (Balcombe et al., 2013).
Cultural/ educational	Perception that environmental benefits too small	Along with economic costs, environmental benefit appears to be a significant factor in the decision to install microgeneration (Claudy, Michelsen, O'Driscoll, & Mullen, 2010; Leenheer, de Nooij, & Sheikh, 2011). Microgeneration is generally perceived to be environmentally friendly, perhaps by its very definition as a 'low-carbon source' of energy. Some of the potential adopters are driven by the desire to reduce GHG emissions and most believe microgeneration will help achieve it. Although for many there is a desire to be more environmentally friendly, a number of studies suggest that this desire does not translate into a willingness to pay extra for it (Claudy et al., 2010). Many adopters might be environmentally aware, but will make a purchase decision based on cost and factors other than environmental benefit (Balcombe et al., 2013).
Barriers to renewable heat		
Social/ cultural/ educational	Lack of interest	Some end users are simply unwilling to explore the options or whether renewable heat is relevant to them. This is different from 'hassle' in that even if it was just as easy to install renewable heat as other alternatives, some users would simply not want to. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Social/ educational	Confidence in technology/ Perceived risk	Lack of confidence in technology and commercial infrastructure due to relatively small number of successful projects operating in UK. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Social/ cultural	Inertia	End users are often reluctant to move from a method of heating that they are familiar with. This can be due to concerns around whether the quality of heat supplied will be maintained or due to uncertainty around the costs & practicalities of the alternative options. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Social/ educational	Lack of awareness/Information gap	This includes lack of awareness of technology and potential benefits by end-users, policy makers and installers (plumbers, builders, architects etc.). If end users are not aware that a technology exists, or that that technology could service their needs, they will not consider installing it. This is predominantly where there is a lack of awareness over the potential for renewable heat or where end users' perceptions differ from actuality. It is often not that the information does not exist but rather than end users are not aware that it applies to them or that it can be time consuming to search out the information that is most relevant. Ensuring easy access to and awareness of existing information is one of the most straightforward ways to increase the uptake of renewable heat in the short term. In addition, there is a need to ensure that information is tailored to the target group of end users (both so that they can readily see that it applies to them, but also in order to provide confidence that other similar users have used renewable heat successfully in the past) (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Social/education	Lack of	Many end users do not have experience of using the technologies first-

al	experience (end users)	hand as they are still relatively new to the market. This can result in disconnect between the actual potential for renewable heat and end users' perception of it. In addition, it can mean that end users are not confident that there is sufficient capacity amongst experts to help them (e.g. to help avoid system design pitfalls) when and where required. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Educational	Training and skills	This type of issue has been identified as a barrier on both the supply and demand side. Addressing supply-side capacity issues (e.g. through training) will ameliorate some of these barriers, although it will still be necessary to ensure that end users have a thorough understanding of the situation i.e. that they are aware that there is sufficient capacity to help. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Barriers to adoption of green energy tariffs		
Social/cultural/educational	Inertia	The issue of inertia when switching energy tariffs was raised within most focus group discussions with many participants indicating this was an impediment to the adoption of green energy tariffs. Key concerns raised in these discussions included the lack of perceived financial incentives to switch energy tariffs and the perceived high financial cost of switching energy tariffs. (Diaz-Rainey & Ashton, 2008)
Educational	Consumer confusion	Consumer confusion has been viewed to arise from both the lack of accurate and clear information and the overly complex regulatory frameworks surrounding green electricity provision and investment (Diaz-Rainey & Ashton, 2008; Graham, 2006) Illustrating the links between trust, information and customer confusion issues, (Boardman, Jardine, & Lipp, 2006), noted "Consumers can be confused by spurious claims, misleading use of statistics and at worst mis-selling, either via advertising or direct marketing. The result has been a lack of confidence in the system, contributing to the continually poor uptake of green electricity schemes by domestic consumers".
Educational	Lack of trust of utility firms	Trust concerns and a low public perception of the motivations of the electricity generators and distributors have also been associated with the low take up of energy tariffs. In one research study, the issue of trust in relation to the UK energy market was discussed in focus groups. These debates considered trust from a range of perspectives. Initially most discussions indicated that the electricity suppliers are obligated to pursue shareholders interest, which often conflict with the interests of customers or the environment. (Diaz-Rainey & Ashton, 2008)
Educational	Marketing and information	Lack of easily interpreted metrics adopted by energy suppliers, the limited amount of easily understood information provided on company communications such as bills, and the confusing array of different energy tariffs are all considered barriers to improving energy efficiency and reducing energy consumption. Specifically, the limited ability to compare different energy tariffs and requirement to provide simple and easy understood information was prominent (Diaz-Rainey & Ashton, 2008)

Table 6 Main economic barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Embryonic markets	The UK already has an energy efficiency market but it is small relative to the size of the opportunity. There are significant economic benefits to be realised from growing this market and making energy efficiency a mainstream activity. While there are examples of companies focused on helping domestic and non-domestic consumers improve energy efficiency, the market remains underdeveloped, especially in comparison with the United States. Energy efficiency product and services companies could have much greater penetration into the wider commercial, industrial and public sectors, given the benefits they offer. In the absence of a developed market there is relatively little expertise on either the demand or supply side for energy efficiency investment. This constrains the development of financial products to support energy efficiency investment and leads to high transaction costs. Without a catalyst to drive development of the market, the costs around investing in energy efficiency will remain high, reducing cost-effectiveness (DECC, 2012a).
Barriers to retrofit	
Capital costs	These include the potentially higher upfront costs of energy efficiency products, e.g. cavity wall insulation, and the interest rates available to households.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). In an interview survey conducted in Manchester and Cardiff regarding the barriers that affect the adoption of domestic energy efficiency measures or behaviours, cost appeared to be the primary barrier. The cost of energy efficiency measures is mentioned with almost 25% of respondents in a further study (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012) (UK-GBC, 2008)
Lack of funds or access to finance	This applies at the level of the individual householder, businesses (large or small), social housing providers and the public sector, particularly in the aftermath of the credit crunch. Whilst the demand for a new kitchen or appliances from the consumer's perspective is high, there is no similar demand for energy efficiency. Even though they will in most cases be cost-effective over the long run (with a positive Net Present Value (NPV)), the initial investment costs can be high and this is seen as an obstacle to consumer investment decisions. The most ambitious retrofits will undoubtedly require considerable upfront funding. This upfront funding will have a positive impact on the asset value, especially for older buildings where energy efficiency retrofits not only improve significantly their energy consumption but also their aesthetics. Investing in energy efficiency now also offers some protection against increasing energy prices in the future. Some of the 'access to financing' issues have also been identified as administrative issues, as described below. (BPIE, 2011)
Payback expectations/Investment horizons	Even though many energy savings measures are financially rational in that they have a positive Net Present Value (NPV) or a high Internal Rate of Return (IRR), the time taken for the initial outlay to be recouped is a major barrier. For most households, energy bills for the home account for 3-4% of disposable income, hence they are not a major concern. Householders will be mindful that they may move home in the next few years, while many businesses will not consider non-core investments that do not pay for themselves within 3-5 years. Alternative financing mechanisms which try to ensure that the benefit from energy efficiency improvements are paid by those that benefit from them (e.g. recovering initial capital over 25 years through the energy bill) may

	<p>have a role to play here.(BPIE, 2011). Research in the UK has shown that two constraints felt by occupants are the total capital costs of the project and the expected returns on investment(Ross, 2011).</p> <p>Consumers expect many household investments to have a short, 2 or 3 year payback period, which implies a discount rate of nearly 40%. In addition, affordability constraints may reduce the willingness of the consumers to invest in measures offering greater efficiency, even if the financial benefits are satisfactory.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007)</p>
<p>Competing purchase decisions</p>	<p>Business will prioritise what are perceived as core investments in staff and equipment over energy costs, which (with the exception of energy intensive businesses) typically make up only a small fraction of business costs. For householders, investments in energy saving measures will struggle to compete with the latest electronic gadgets or a new kitchen or bathroom, which are not particularly cost-effective investments but yield a much higher perceived 'social benefit'. Some see this obstacle as an issue related to awareness; others deal with it separately as a financial issue. Moreover, many energy efficiency measures are not visible (unlike, say, photovoltaic systems) which makes them less 'attractive' as an investment option. The lack of attractiveness is sometimes reinforced by more generous subsidies which are more readily available for PVs compared to energy efficiency measures. Undoubtedly, consumers have a lot of choice and the case for reducing costs or improving other benefits (such as comfort) has to be seen in that context.(BPIE, 2011)</p>
<p>Price signals/Financial Incentive</p>	<p>Many of the financial barriers identified related to consumer price signals. If the financial incentive associated with investing in energy savings measures was sufficiently large, households, businesses and the public sector would have a higher propensity to undertake such investments. Put simply, energy costs often represent a small share of household expenditure resulting in lack of motivation for the vast majority of consumers to take meaningful action to reduce consumption levels. Furthermore, energy pricing structures do not reflect the full environmental costs of producing energy, in particular the costs associated with climate change, and hence there is a sub-optimal level of investment.(BPIE, 2011)</p>
<p>Additional costs/Hidden costs</p>	<p>These include 'transaction costs' associated with finding reputable providers, time costs of disruption, and the costs of differences in quality of product or service. Many of these hidden costs are related to the cost of acquiring information about, for example, suppliers.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). The challenge within the design phase of the project is to ensure the homeowner is informed of the potential for, and scale of, costs as early as possible so they can factor these into their budgeting. As with the costs and introduction of fees for detailed design, it is critical that the costs presented at the outset of the project are deliverable and the homeowner has sufficient budget in place. The balance here is for the independent survey results to accurately reflect the likely total costs of the measures installed and the property made good. Hidden costs, such as replacing cornicing, would reduce the certainty of the report and cost effectiveness of the recommendations. This will be another key challenge, which has significant impact on the Green Deal's 'golden rule'(DECC, 2010) that the cost of measures should be less than the savings achieved. (Ross, 2011)</p>
<p>Risks and uncertainty</p>	<p>Uncertainty about future energy prices can deter households from investing since they cannot be assured of further savings. Households may also be wary</p>

	of the risk associated with unfamiliar products.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007)
Barriers to adoption of green energy tariffs	
Cost of energy tariffs	Cost is a very important issue for most people when choosing a particular energy tariff. Further, it has been reported repeatedly that while environmental issues are important to most people, these concerns are often subsidiary to cost considerations. (Ipsos MORI, 2008)
Barriers to uptake of efficient heating systems	
Cost of new heating system	Research has shown that there are considerable barrier costs to homeowners replacing their current heating system with a more efficient system. The barrier costs represent the economic value homeowners would need to be compensated by, in order to address their concerns about the new technology (whether due to perceptions of it being disruptive to install, a hassle to maintain etc). (DECC, 2013a)
Barriers to microgeneration technologies	
Cost of microgeneration technology	It is well recognised that costs are the largest barrier to microgeneration adoption (Allen, Hammond, & McManus, 2008; Claudy et al., 2010; Scarpa & Willis, 2010; Wee, Yang, Chou, & Padilan, 2012). Capital costs are too high for the majority of potential adopters and the payback times are too long to warrant the large investment. For example, Caird and Roy (2010) found in an online survey of microgeneration ‘adopters’ (545), ‘considerers’ (314) and ‘rejecters’ (65) that the most frequently cited barriers to installing microgeneration systems were all related to costs: capital costs (86% of the respondents), long payback time (68%) and lack of grants (60%). A survey of 601 London home-owners by ORC International also found capital costs to be the most important barrier while assistance with costs was the most cited motivation (by over 75% of respondents) (Ellison, 2004). Another frequently cited cost-related barrier is concern about the resale value of the home. The ORC International study found that many respondents expressed concern that potential future house buyers would be put off by a microgeneration installation which could lead to a decrease in house price. (Faiers & Neame, 2006) also investigated whether potential adopters thought microgeneration would be a positive influence on house sales, but research suggested that this was not an important issue in the decision to adopt.(Balcombe et al., 2013)
Investment risk	Occupants are afraid that they will lose their investment if they move homes (Balcombe et al., 2013)

Table 7 Main institutional barriers in the building sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Misaligned financial	It is not always the case that the person who is responsible for making energy efficiency improvements will receive the benefits of their actions. For example, in

incentives	<p>most cases</p> <p>commercial rented tenants are responsible for their own bills and therefore it is in their interest to reduce the bills, but contractual arrangements around landlord/tenants or facilities management may inhibit investment. Landlords are unlikely to invest unless they will realise the benefits in monetary terms. On a societal level, wider benefits such as security of supply or emission reductions are not directly felt by those making energy efficiency investments and, as a result, the decision to invest is based only on the benefits directly received. Therefore, energy efficiency investments are not prioritised as they might otherwise be (DECC, 2012a).</p>
Lack of regulatory provision	<p>These relate specifically to the regulatory framework within the UK which can make it more difficult for certain households to benefit from or consider energy efficient measures.(NERA Economic Consulting, 2007)</p>
Construction standards	<p>Boardman notes that there: is a difference between the design standard and the way the building functions in practice. (Boardman, 2007). Regulation standards are not met in practice. The innate inability of the construction industry to deliver the expected performance means that predictive models, could easily over-estimate the CO2 savings achievable by sets of interventions: the de-carbonization challenge may be even greater than predicted.</p>
Lack of data	<p>Kohler and Yang state that: the establishment of long-term scenarios faces severe problems of data collection on the past behaviour of stocks (Kohler & Yang, 2007). Boardman notes that the: lack of post-occupancy evaluation of recently built homes means that there are virtually no data on what level of energy consumption is being achieved in practice (Boardman, 2007), as a result, whilst it is possible that regulatory developments in the UK, will mean that total CO2 emissions from new dwellings are now 40 –50% lower than the stock mean: an absence of empirical data unfortunately makes it impossible to be certain that these reductions are being achieved in practice. (Lowe, 2007)</p>
Infrastructure and planning barriers (medium sized energy projects and local access to grid connections)	<p>Medium-sized energy projects between 10-50 Megawatts (MW) are currently underused, despite having social, economic and security of supply benefits as well as improving the system efficiency of the UK's national energy infrastructure by increasing the diversity of generating capacity available and reducing the energy lost in transmission or wasted as unused heat. Currently, obtaining planning permission for such projects can be costly and time-consuming, increasing the risk if the energy projects are owned by community groups and/or small co-operatives. In addition, grid connection costs and process are seen as prohibitively high and complex, especially in areas where the grid would require an upgrade (House of Commons, 2013).</p>
Barriers to retrofits	
Multi-stakeholder issues	<p>One of the most commonly cited barrier is the 'landlord-tenant' split whereby landlords may under invest in energy efficiency measures because their tenants pay the energy bills or conversely tenants have no incentive to reduce their energy use as their landlord foots the bill (NERA Economic Consulting, 2007). Various barriers exist where there are multiple owners and/or occupiers of buildings. Ownership and responsibility can be opaque, while it can be very difficult to agree on energy saving investments in multi-family residential buildings if many different property owners have to either approve a decision or make a financial contribution.(BPIE, 2011). In a questionnaire survey conducted by Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012), nearly 13% of all responses mentioned that the split incentive between landlords and tenants was a barrier, or that they are unable to enact energy efficiency measures because they are</p>

	tenants of a housing/council house. This barrier is specifically targeted by the Green Deal, which is an example of a guided policy intervention (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012)
Poor compliance with building codes	<p>Enforcing compliance with building codes and standards will be key to countering the perception that energy saving renovation measures come with a price premium. Proper monitoring of compliance, enforcement and quality control the process through a qualified workforce should be part of any policy package to foster deep renovation. The relatively low compliance level is a significant barrier in reaching the estimated energy savings potential.(BPIE, 2011).</p> <p>In a report by (Olivier, 2001) it was argued that the official figures for <i>U</i>-values are optimistic and not achieved in practice. This is because actual <i>U</i>-values are often found to be higher than expected when measured in-situ, due to errors in the quality of construction, as well as thermal bridges and gaps in insulation. According to (Hamza & Greenwood, 2008), Building regulations do improve design teams' abilities to meet energy targets, however, many within the industry express concern about uncertainties and difficulties with compliance. (Lowe & Oreszczyn, 2008) claim that little is known regarding the actual impact of updates to the Building Regulations due to a lack of monitoring following construction. (Dowson et al., 2012)</p>
Performance gap	Regarding the complexities of achieving actual energy savings, Hong et al. (2006) claimed that large uncertainties related to the impacts of thermal bridges, gaps in insulation and the occupants using more heating following the refurbishment. (Dowson et al., 2012)
Quality of installation and commissioning	Appropriate information is equally important for the contractor as the homeowner, although often presented in a different format and with greater technical detail. The correct installation and commissioning of the majority of energy demand reduction measures, such as insulation and heating controls, can significantly influence the outcomes, both regarding energy consumption and long term structural concerns.(Ross, 2011)
Quality of workmanship	Another side-effect of a significant increase in demand could be the rapid growth of contractors offering to undertake low energy renovation work, which if not appropriately regulated or managed, could give rise to poor workmanship and even some serious short term failures.(BPIE, 2011)
Building stock characteristics	The second most referenced barrier in the study of Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012) concerns the property itself and can be further subdivided into two categories: property; and conservation & heritage. The property barrier refers to the limitations that the property structure itself imposes on residents, for example in the space available in the home, the age, the lack of cavity walls, poorly installed windows, or unsuitable roofs. The conservation & heritage sub-barrier captures the homes which are unable to install energy efficiency measures because they are either listed buildings or in a conservation area (M. Pelenur & H. Cruickshank, 2012). It is not possible to consider the roll out of large-scale domestic retrofit schemes for energy efficiency without addressing the inefficiency of the solid wall housing stock, which makes up the majority of our listed buildings and conservation areas. Approximately 21% of the homes in England were built prior to 1920, on average costing nearly twice in energy and producing twice as much carbon dioxide emissions per annum as a house built since 1990 (Ross, 2011)
Policy framework on refurbishments	The policy framework for improving the energy performance of existing housing is fragmented, with regulations, incentives and programmes having a wide range of direct and indirect influences (Karvonen, 2013)

<p>Mismatch between policy and occupant reality</p>	<p>Homeowners often decide to renovate their houses to modernize kitchens and bathrooms, and while they are interested in improved comfort conditions, energy performance tends to be a lower priority (Bell & Lowe, 2000; Meijer, Itard, & Sunikka-Blank, 2009). In effect, there is a mismatch between current policy and information offerings for domestic retrofit and the lived reality of how houses are inhabited and how they change over time. (Karvonen, 2013)</p> <p>Occupants are actively involved in shaping energy profiles and are at the centre of a complex network of activities, organizations and systems that produce domestic carbon emissions, while their role in the realization of long-term carbon emission reductions is often underappreciated or unacknowledged. The rational choice perspective does not take into account the different ways that occupants inhabit their houses, how they perceive their resource consumption activities, and how and why they decide to retrofit their houses (Crosbie & Baker, 2009). From a homeowner perspective, there are multiple reasons for the slow uptake of energy-efficiency measures: capital costs and the uncertainty of final costs; the risk of downstream teething problems; potential impacts on aesthetics and property value; and inconvenience and disruption during retrofit activities (Lomas, 2009; UK-GBC, 2008) .</p>
<p>Disruption /Hassle factor</p>	<p>Other issues raised during this small pilot study with regards to the scheduling of works were; The need to carry out all works in the shortest possible time and make the house habitable as the property was a new purchase and delay meant additional costs. The potential to carry out works when half of the household were away for a period of time. Delays in the building schedule raising security concerns about scaffolding being in place when the occupiers were away for a few days. Changes to the specifications during the works reducing the efficiency of the build process and increasing costs(Ross, 2011). The hassle factor is identified as a key barrier in many reports (UK-GBC, 2008)</p>
<p>Barriers to microgeneration technologies</p>	
<p>Disruption /Hassle factor</p>	<p>This includes hassle of installation, disruption or hassle of operation, potential requirement for planning permission.As well as finding an appropriate installer, the inconvenience of major modifications to heating or electrical systems, or to the roof or garden during installation, is also a significant barrier to adoption (Caird & Roy, 2010; Ellison, 2004; Scarpa & Willis, 2010; Wee et al., 2012). For example, installing a residential GSHP may require the garden to be dug up to install a ground heating loop (Balcombe et al., 2013).</p>
<p>Impact on residence</p>	<p>Considerations are that systems take up too much space, the installation might damage my home, they would not look good. Some microgeneration technologies use a significant amount of space within the home which is a barrier for some potential adopters (Brook Lyndhurst Ltd. et al., 2003; Caird & Roy, 2010; Scarpa & Willis, 2010). The value of space is often significant, but will vary across different population groups as well as locations. Another frequently cited barrier to installation is concern about disapproval of neighbours regarding the aesthetics of microgeneration installations (Balcombe et al., 2013).</p>
<p>Barriers to renewable heat</p>	
<p>Disruption/Hassle factor</p>	<p>This involves the increased ‘hassle’ factor created by the extra time and effort required to switch the system in a building or use non-conventional systems in a new</p>

	build project (Enviros Consulting, 2008). The extra time and effort required to use non-conventional system includes research, feasibility study, planning permission, finding an installer, installation of equipment etc.
Security of fuel supply, Availability of energy source	This is a barrier to the uptake of certain technologies (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Characteristics of technology/fuel	This barrier involves issues such as complexity in infrastructure requirements, complexity in design, the need to store fuel for biomass or the difficulty of retrofitting, that would be the direct result of using (a particular kind of) renewable fuel or technology. These are the factors that may well result in end users needing to modify their behaviour in some way, even once any barrier caused by a gap between perception and actuality (reflected under information gap and lack of experience above) is addressed. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Regulatory barriers	Planning requirements or noise controls would make it more time consuming to introduce renewable heat, or may prevent its introduction completely. In some cases there are good reasons for this and it may not be in the wider interest for the barrier to be overcome. However in other cases, particularly where the barrier delays rather than prevents the uptake of renewables, there is scope to raise awareness of the barrier and to seek routes to overcome it. Difficulties in the planning process may slow or prevent a project once the developers have decided to proceed and would therefore pose a barrier on the supply side. Anticipation of difficulties with getting planning permission may also put off developers or end-consumers so that potential projects fail to reach even the design stage, creating a barrier to increasing demand. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Lack of space	Some buildings will not have access to sufficient space for horizontal or even vertical collectors. Limits number of projects that are feasible (and may increase costs) hence putting end users off. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Electricity supply capacity	The lack of three phase electricity supply limits the capacity of domestic installations. Overall capacity of local networks may also become an issue for other sectors. Both factors may increase costs. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)
Difficulty of retrofitting to existing buildings	The technology requires low temperature heat distribution system for optimal performance (which is likely to deliver heat via an under-floor system). This creates extra hassle (and cost) which may put consumers off. (Enviros Consulting, 2008)

Table 8 Assessment of barriers in the building sector

Impact of barriers	Description of barrier
High	Undervaluing energy efficiency
	Inertia/Habit
	Perceived lack of impact
	Lack of time and resources
	Rebound effect

	Lack of awareness
	Refurbishment seen as low priority
	Socio-economic status of household
	Unwillingness to replace heating systems
	Access to trusted Information
	Lack of information on energy use
	Understanding of costs versus perceived benefits
	Misaligned financial incentives
	Construction standards
	Poor compliance with building codes
	Performance gap
	Building stock characteristics
	Quality of installation and commissioning
	Mismatch between policy and occupant reality
	Disruption /Hassle factor (Retrofits/Renewable heat/Microgeneration)
	Difficulty of retrofitting to existing buildings (renewable heat)
	Infrastructure and planning barriers (medium sized energy projects and local access to grid connections)
	Embryonic markets
	Capital costs
	Lack of funds or access to finance
	Payback expectations/Investment horizons
	Cost of new heating system
	Cost of microgeneration technology
Medium	Lack of interest and motivation
	Mistrust of technologies
	Mistrust of energy companies or contractors
	Social norms and accepted behaviours

	Visibility of energy efficiency
	Perception that environmental benefits too small
	Lack of awareness/Information gap on technologies
	Lack of user experience
	Skills and training
	Lack of regulatory provision
	Lack of data
	Multi-stakeholder issues
	Quality of workmanship
	Policy framework on refurbishments
	Characteristics of technology/fuel (renewable heat)
	Regulatory barriers (renewable heat)
	Competing purchase decisions
	Price signals/Financial Incentive
	Additional costs/Hidden costs
	Risks and uncertainty
Low	Confidence in contracting and delivery
	Inter-occupant relationships
	Perceived lack of political action
	Perceived lack of action by business and industry
	Local oppositions to new energy infrastructure (Community action)
	Externalising responsibility and blame
	Aesthetics (Retrofits)
	Perceived information over-load
	Consumer confusion on green tariffs
	Mistrust of green tariffs
	Marketing and information on green tariffs

	Impact on residence (Microgeneration)
	Security of fuel supply (renewable heat)
	Lack of space (renewable heat)
	Electricity supply capacity (renewable heat)
	Cost of energy tariffs

2.2 MAPPING BARRIERS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be achieved at three key levels; vehicle efficiency, travel efficiency and system efficiency. However, to add to the complexity of understanding the barriers to improving the energy efficiency in this sector, the transport sector contains several intersecting subsectors, including road, rail, marine, aviation, passenger and freight transport, and mode of transport (car, bicycle, train, HGV etc.). In order to provide a simplified overview of UK-specific barriers within this complex sector, the following tables outline a) barriers specific to electric vehicles/ultra-low emissions vehicles; b) barriers specific to the uptake of cycling; c) barriers specific to the uptake of car clubs; d) barriers to improving the efficiency of freight transport; e) barriers specific to the increase in energy efficiency in public transport; and f) barriers specific to the increased use of biofuel.

Table 9 Main social, cultural and educational barriers in the transport sector

Type of barrier	Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Barriers to EV/ULEVs		
Cultural/educational	Hesitation to trust new technologies	Research has shown current full EV models are considered an inferior product in terms of due to comparisons against ‘known’ technologies, even when fuel cost savings are taken into account. They offer smaller driving ranges and longer refuelling times at a considerable price premium. (Steinhilber, Wells, & Thankappan, 2013)
Cultural	Car as a status symbol	The car, as a status symbol, is a key factor in reinforcing anti-environmental car travel behaviour (Lane & Potter, 2007; RAC, 2004). A study from the Open University entitled ‘ <i>People-centred eco-design: factors influencing the adoption and use of low carbon products and systems</i> ’ makes the observation that some drivers like to advertise their ‘green’ credentials by using a highly observable eco-product. Whereas the Prius owner wanted a ‘normal’ looking vehicle, informal discussions with users of the G-WIZ battery-electric quadracycle reveal a readiness to be noticed as being a driver of a different, more environmentally friendly vehicle (Golob & Hensher, 1998)Whatever the preferences of particular driver segments, the key issue raised here is the importance (and role) of the car as a status symbol, one that has important

		implications for promoting cleaner vehicles.
Social/ cultural	Environmental awareness	The Low Carbon Vehicle Partnership study showed that when it comes to car purchasing, environmental issues have a very low priority for private and fleet consumers. This is at odds, both with the high level of concern declared by members of the public, and with the increasing importance of environmental issues within the business sector. (Lane & Potter, 2007)
Social/ cultural	Attitude-action gap	Research also underlines the fact that what consumers report as concerns or intended actions often have little relation to what they actually do. (Lane & Potter, 2007)
Social	Buyer attitude	Research suggests people tend to discount heavily (or not take into account) future cost savings from fuel economy at the time of purchasing a car, even though it would seem to be in their own interests as well as those of the environment. (King, 2009). Evidence suggests that many UK buyers discount heavily, and some do not consider, vehicle efficiency benefits at the point of purchasing a car. They are therefore less inclined to adopt efficient vehicles than the financial incentive from fuel economy savings might suggest. In addition, the majority of buyers tend to rate the environmental impact of vehicles relatively low in their purchase criteria.
Social/ cultural	Inertia	Industry research has shown that car buyers are resistant to change even if price signals are strong – on average, car buyers are prepared to endure an increase of £1100 (€1540) in annual running costs before switching to a different fuel, smaller engine or smaller car (RAC, 2004).
Social/ educational	Concern about vehicle reliability	The global EV and PHEV market is currently in its infancy with technology still developing and has yet to become mature. As a result there is little firm data on vehicle reliability and vehicle life. Also with technology continuing to develop there is a concern that early vehicles may quickly become obsolete. Both of these factors affect the consumer's confidence and leasing organisations' ability to predict residual values (ARUP, 2008).
Educational	Maintenance difficulties	An infrastructure for servicing and maintenance is also important for the continued adoption of innovative eco-products. The hybrid car buyer interviewee observed that it was difficult to find convenient, and not too costly, trained servicing and maintenance facilities, creating barriers to continuing use of the vehicle (Lane & Potter, 2007). The Low Carbon Vehicle Partnership study notes the example of a UK Government department that, after switching to using liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), returned to using conventional vehicles as a result of maintenance difficulties and lack of experienced technicians (House of Commons Transport Committee, 2004). Such legacies seriously affect the diffusion of eco-products out of an initial niche into the

		mass-market.
Social/ cultural/ educational	Limited understanding of environmental impact	It is apparent that detailed knowledge of environmental impacts, cleaner technologies and cost structures associated with road transport is extremely low (Lane & Potter, 2007).
Social/ educational	Consumer understanding and use of fuel economy information	Research shows that motorists use fuel consumption as a proxy of both environmental impacts and vehicle costs, this despite the evidence that car buyers have little understanding of the relationship between fuel use and emissions. (Lane & Potter, 2007). In practice, purchase decisions suggest that consumers take a very short-term view when weighing up vehicle purchase costs. On average, consumers apply a very high discount rate (60 per cent) ⁷ , which implies that they are looking to an 18-month payback period for fuel costs. Moreover, the average motorist underestimates their car running costs by around a factor of two (King, 2009)
Educational	Lack of knowledge	A lack of knowledge about EVs was identified as one of the main barriers to EV take-up. This related to all aspects of purchasing and using EVs (e.g. purchase cost, running costs, financial incentives, range, variations in vehicle technology, available models and charging routines and infrastructure)(Hutchins, Delmonte, Stannard, Evans, & Bussell, 2013).
Educational	Insufficient information	Evidence shows that potential plug-in vehicle buyers can be prevented from moving towards a purchase as a result of insufficient or inaccurate information. Research indicates non-ULEV purchasers suggests that many have little, if any, knowledge of ULEVs. (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013) Further research suggests those that have some knowledge tend to be confused by negative or inaccurate media information, or be hampered by concerns over the 'unknown' (including imagined sub-optimal performance, potential battery degradation or low residual value) (Hutchins et al., 2013)
Barriers to cycling		
Cultural	Cycling culture is marginalised	Case study data from Bristol and Hackney demonstrate struggles over identity, expressed for example in concerns over clothing, which seem linked to subcultural boundaries. However, analysis of Cambridge and Hull data suggests that even where cycling escapes subculture it has not escaped stigma. Unlike in higher-cycling countries, cyclists in Cambridge still face widespread negative perceptions, expressed for example in the local press. Even where cycling has become relatively normalised in the UK, it is still marginalised. (Aldred & Jungnickel, 2014)

Social/ cultural	Habit and social norm of driving	Evidence indicates that people base their travel decisions on approximate rules of thumb (heuristics), which may be out-of-date or incorrect, and are influenced by many factors that do not fit classical economic theory, including habit (past behaviour) and social norm (peer group behaviour) (Lynn et al., 2014)
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Table 10 Main economic barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Barriers to EVs/ ULEVs	
High purchase price and long payback	The annual UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) survey (Department for Transport, 2015) has found purchase cost to be a significant barrier to EV adoption. Even with the reduction offered by the PiCG (Plug-in Car Grant), EVs were often deemed unaffordable. (Hutchins et al., 2013). The UK lease cost for a Prius involves a significant premium over comparable conventional models the difference appears to be due to high servicing costs associated with the small network of dealers who maintain hybrids. These high lease costs have resulted in fleets failing to adopt the Prius and other lower carbon vehicles. (Lane & Potter, 2007)
Battery costs	Battery costs are also a key area of concern. For instance, (Yang, 2010) recognised that the cost of batteries is the primary barrier to making plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) and pure electric vehicles (EVs) commercially price competitive. With current battery costs, an EV equivalent of a current production vehicle could be more than double the forecourt price. This differential is too great even for early adopters (ARUP, 2008). Without pioneering companies offering loss-leader products, early entrants to the PHEV markets are likely to continue to face high-cost batteries and such markets suffer from inadequate demand. (Keith, Austin, & Sue, 2013)
Running costs	The current average life of vehicles registered in the UK is 14 years. Battery life for EVs and PHEVs is projected to reach ten years and 180,000 km; however current expectations over battery life and range are much lower. This presents the possibility of battery replacement during the life of the vehicle to ensure its continued use and brings with it significant additional cost. Given that most popular cars lose 50-60% of their purchase price after 3 years, the cost of a replacement battery is likely to exceed the value of the car, possibly leading to premature scrappage of the vehicle. (ARUP, 2008)
Limited business case for infrastructure investment	Government-supported research suggests that investment will be needed in infrastructure and the UK supply chain to support the increased usage of plug-in vehicles to 2020 and beyond. For plug-in vehicles, investment in charging infrastructure may be needed so that motorists can charge their plug-in vehicles safely and conveniently across the country. (DECC, 2011). There is a limited business case for private investment in new infrastructure until there are sufficient numbers of vehicles. This is the 'chicken and egg' challenge faced by the ULEV industry and an area where Government intervention is required. (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013)
Cost of domestic charging unit	The cost of a domestic charging unit is high (Office for Low Emission Vehicles,

	2013) and can prevent buyers.
Lack of market and policy certainty for hydrogen innovation	Research suggests that the largest short term barrier to private sector investment in innovation and scale-up, throughout the hydrogen transport system, is a lack of market and policy certainty. Confidence in future market support policies would unlock the private sector investment in innovation and large-scale manufacturing capacity which is essential for early cost reductions. (Low Carbon Innovation Coordination Group, 2014)
Barriers to car clubs	
Lack of financial support for car clubs	Evidence suggests that stronger financial support for a planned national network is needed, which the government could lead on; the creation of a seedcorn fund of £2.5m, allowing £50-100,000 for each car club start-up that could be allocated through the annual local transport settlement, would enable the creation of 40 new car clubs (UKERC, 2007)
Barriers to freight transport efficiency	
Limited financial incentives for freight electric vehicles	Companies such as DHL, TNT and UPS have stated that they are very close to the tipping point of changing to all EV's for urban logistics, as the gap in operating costs is closing with petrol and diesel vehicles. Small changes in costs of financing and incentives could tip this balance. (Gazzard, 2014)

Table 11 Main institutional barriers in the transport sector

Title of barrier	Description of barrier
Barriers to public transport	
Inadequate public transport across UK	In many towns and cities public transport does not offer an attractive choice. Buses are the main form of public transport for most local journeys, but bus patronage has declined by two-thirds since the 1950s. Outside London, only 15% of those working in metropolitan areas, and 7% in other towns, commute by public transport (Department for Transport, 2000). Inadequate transport provision can be a barrier to the prosperity of all those living in such areas. Commercial operators often struggle to run passenger transport services in communities where demand is thin or diffuse. Community transport (CT) can play an important role in providing services in these circumstances.(Department for Transport, 2014)
Barriers to EVs/ ULEVs	
Immature status of developing technologies	In a study conducted by Steinhilber et al (2013) a majority of interviewees (from industry, government, and research organisations), considered developments in battery technology and battery production technology as the most pressing research need for the industry. Interviewees from the automotive industry and government-supported pilot projects expressed an urgent need for governments to strategically support the re-establishment of this industry, even if this is may not be profitable in the short run.
Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations	There is no clear regulation as to where public EV charging spots may be installed. There are unclear regulations regarding parking on spaces equipped

	with a charging spot (Steinhilber et al., 2013)
No standards for infrastructure investments	Expert opinions differ on how much publicly accessible charging infrastructure is needed. A report by DECC (2011) states that a representative from Transport for London was of the view that the currently running pilot projects will provide important results on how EVs are used in real life, and how much publicly accessible infrastructure is really needed. The report also suggested investment will be needed in infrastructure and the UK supply chain to support the increased usage of plug-in vehicles to 2020 and beyond. For plug-in vehicles, investment in charging infrastructure may be needed so that motorists can charge their plug-in vehicles safely and conveniently across the country (DECC, 2011)
Non-standardisation of connectors	The standardization of technical specifications such as cables and plugs for recharging was identified widely as an important issue by industry interviewees in a research study (Steinhilber et al., 2013). A seemingly simple technological challenge had been that of connectors. In 2008, ARUP and CENEX identified the need for standardised connectors (ARUP, 2008). Evidence highlights that the the UK standardised on the EN62196-2 Type 2 socket, using Mode 3 control, whilst vehicles and hire vehicles in the UK are provided with the conventional 13Amp BS1363 type connector, leaving a disconnect between infrastructure installers and vehicle manufacturers (Keith et al., 2013). The additional cable that is required remains a tangible barrier to adoption (Keith et al., 2013)
Not developed infrastructure for recharging	<p>Research suggests a lack of systems' integration between products and systems often deters or prevents adoption of low carbon products. For vehicles this particularly applies to fuelling infrastructure. One key feature of petrol-hybrids is that the fuelling system is 'normal' and is the same as for a conventional car. This contrasts with the refuelling regime for battery-electric vehicles that can take several hours to recharge (Lane & Potter, 2007).</p> <p>In one study, one in four licence holders said the main things drivers said would discourage them from buying an electric car/van centre on facilities for recharging (Department for Transport, 2015). Both private and organisational respondents felt that, at the time of the research, public charging infrastructure did not meet their needs. In order to better meet user needs, respondents suggested that the infrastructure network should expand to support them in undertaking journeys that exceeded their vehicle range (Hutchins et al., 2013)</p> <p>In another study, private quantitative respondents who were PiP scheme members identified several barriers to the use of public charging infrastructure, such as a lack of rapid charging facilities on the strategic road network, a lack of charge points at 'destinations' (such as hotels and restaurants), incompatibility between various charge point providers, and a lack of accessible information about the location of charge points (Hutchins et al., 2013)</p>
Confusion about fleet averages for CO2 emissions	Research shows that opinions differ on the issue of CO2 emissions, as very different interests are involved. NGOs and environmental groups criticised the current EU regulation for considering EVs to be zero-emissions vehicles, and for giving super-credits to a vehicle which has CO ₂ emissions of less than 50 g/km. While the NGOs and environmental groups acknowledge that the automotive industry has no influence on the electricity mix which determines the emission of an EV, they fear that considering EVs to be zero-emissions will not provide an incentive to car makers to develop more energy efficient EVs. Furthermore, regulation does not take into account the expected actual mileage of a given car model (Steinhilber et al., 2013)

Limited R&D Incentives	In spite of various efforts by government departments underway to promote research relevant to EVs, the automotive industry may wish for more government funding to support their own R&D effort, as the industry is still suffering from the financial and economic crisis. In one study a representative from the automotive industry cited that it would be desirable to improve the general R&D investment climate in the UK, for instance in the upcoming reform of R&D tax credits. Credits are currently only attached to corporation tax profits, but not to R&D investment in the UK. In the same study, similar views were presented by other stakeholders, for example a prominent emerging concern was that Governments should ensure that the foreign-owned car makers not only place their manufacturing in the UK, but also their R&D, as this will secure a long-term future for the industry in the UK (Steinhilber et al., 2013). Ongoing research and development work is required to support the development and deployment of the emerging generation of new ultra low carbon vehicles. (DECC, 2011)
High costs preventing development of new technologies	Barriers created by large fixed costs in fuel production and vehicle manufacturing, sunk costs and the efficient scale for bringing new technologies to market (King, 2009)
Range of distance travelled between charges	Range was identified as another key barrier to EV purchase. Non-EV purchasers were concerned about the range that EVs could achieve and EV purchasers acknowledged that their own EV range had presented challenges for them as users.(Hutchins et al., 2013). One in four licence holders said one of the main things that would discourage them from buying an electric car/van centres on ranges achievable by EV's (Department for Transport, 2015). The current practical EV range limit is about 120 km. Although this is sufficient to cover over 93% of all two-way journeys made in the UK this is only about one fifth of the range of current ICVs. Consumers will have to adopt new "refuelling" regimes and be prepared to have to wait considerably longer than current refuelling times to enable continued use of their vehicle or to hire a long range ICV when needed (ARUP, 2008).
Lack of initiatives for fleets	Research by the Office for Low Emission Vehicles (2013) highlighted the fact that there are barriers and a lack of incentives to procure ULEVs through existing frameworks. The report states that Government Procurement Service manages the purchasing activity of central government departments and also makes its frameworks available to the wider public sector. Through these frameworks it is currently possible to buy ULEVs but they are not included in the regular competitions or e-auctions through which buyers access the most competitive rates for vehicle purchase. (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013)
Extra load on the electricity grid	A report by the Office for Low Emission Vehicles (2013) states that it is important that the electricity network is able to accommodate additional electricity demand and, in particular, that the right investments in the distribution networks are made at the right time and place. The overall forecast level of uptake in plug-in vehicles to 2020 is not expected to represent an issue for the national grid, though clustering of vehicles in particular locations could lead to the need for local grid-reinforcement. (Office for Low Emission Vehicles, 2013)
Barriers to car club uptake	
Limited car-sharing initiatives	Evidence suggests that support from London Borough councils for the development of car clubs in the capital has largely been behind the strong growth, and their development elsewhere in the country has been haphazard.

	(UKERC, 2007)
Barriers to cycling	
Undeveloped cycling infrastructure	Including lack of segregated cycling routes and lack of secure bicycle parking facilities. Research conducted by Aldred and Jungnickel (2014) in four UK cities (Bristol, Cambridge, Hackney, Hull) showed that that substantial infrastructural improvements could and should be made in all four areas. (Aldred & Jungnickel, 2014) (Transport for London, 2008)
Barriers to biofuel use	
Biofuel distribution and infrastructure	Research indicates it is not known which second generation technologies may become commercially viable or when the fuels produced may be available on the market (BERR, 2008). Vehicles running on cleaner fuels produce fewer harmful emissions, and can offer some savings on fuel costs, compared with petrol or diesel. This is even more favourable in long distance haulage (and freight transport), the costs of implementation, maintenance and the scarcity of refuelling points continue to hamper biofuel adoption. (Gazzard, 2014)
Biofuel vehicle limitations	Evidence suggests that there are vehicle technology barriers to increasing the volume of biofuel in road transport fuel. It is believed that most vehicles would be able to run on at least a 10% biofuel blend (by energy content) by 2020. However a study indicated that if it became apparent that a 10% (by energy content) blend would not be compatible with the vast majority of vehicles then there would be risk that the 10% energy target would not be met (BERR, 2008).
Concerns about sustainability of biofuels	Evidence shows that in order for biofuels to be beneficial they must be produced sustainably. In particular, their production should not place undue pressure on areas of high biodiversity, and they must deliver real emissions savings in comparison to the fossil fuels they are replacing (DECC, 2013c). Any potential measure which increases the volume of biofuels used in the UK will need to ensure that they are produced from a sustainable source before the Government will implement such a measure. If it is not possible to enforce sustainability requirements, there is a risk that using biofuels will have unintended impacts on biodiversity, food production/prices and result in unintended releases of greenhouse gases as a result of land conversion. (BERR, 2008)
Need for R&D in biofuels	Studies (DECC, 2013b) commissioned by Government indicate that advanced technologies may be an important element of meeting our needs to 2020, and increasingly valuable post 2020 as we move towards a low carbon transport system. Key areas already identified as potential routes include thermochemical conversion which can produce mid-distillates such as biodiesel and jet fuel. Developing these fuels will reduce the use of agricultural land needed for food, and increase the use of wastes for energy, as well as generating high lifecycle greenhouse gas savings (DECC, 2011)
Barriers to freight transport efficiency	
Lack of research in freight efficiency	A key risk identified in the literature, is the lack of independent (e.g. Government funded) research and statistics on the sector that creates a knowledge vacuum which a range of interested, and often partisan parties attempt to fill. The quality of research and case studies thus provided varies enormously, and outside of peer reviewed material from reputable

	organisations, the content can be unreliable, and often contradictory to other material. (Gazzard, 2014)
Lack of policy on freight efficiency	Despite the size of the UK logistics and freight industry, and its critical contribution to the UK economy, it is often said that the industry is a Cinderella sector, treated like a poor cousin by successive governments. The challenges for the UK industry include long standing weaknesses in UK freight governance, policy innovation, planning, infrastructure development, and available research and statistics. (Gazzard, 2014)

Table 12 Assessment of barriers in the transport sector

Impact of barriers	Barrier
High	Hesitation to trust new technologies
	Buyer attitude
	Inertia
	Concern about vehicle reliability
	Lack of knowledge
	Insufficient information
	Immature status of developing technologies
	No standards for infrastructure investments
	Not developed infrastructure for recharging
	Range of distance travelled between charges
	Biofuel distribution and infrastructure
	Biofuel vehicle limitations
	Lack of policy on freight efficiency
	High purchase price and long payback
Limited business case for infrastructure investment	
Medium	Environmental awareness
	Attitude-action gap
	Maintenance difficulties
	Limited understanding of environmental impact
	Consumer understanding and use of fuel economy information

	Undeveloped cycling infrastructure
	Inadequate public transport across England
	Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations
	Confusion about fleet averages for CO2 emissions
	Limited R&D Incentives
	High costs preventing development of new technologies
	Lack of initiatives for fleets
	Concerns about sustainability of biofuels
	Lack of research in freight efficiency
	Battery costs
	Running costs
	Limited financial incentives for freight electric vehicles
Low	Car as a status symbol
	Cycling culture is marginalised
	Habit and social norm of driving
	Need for R&D in biofuels
	Extra load on the electricity grid
	Limited car-sharing initiatives
	Non-standardisation of connectors
	Cost of domestic charging unit
	Lack of market and policy certainty for hydrogen innovation
	Lack of financial support for car clubs

CHAPTER 3: BARRIERS AND POLICY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 BUILDING SECTOR

The UK's recent energy efficiency policy strategies have sought to overcome the four main overarching areas of barriers identified in the Energy Efficiency Strategy (DECC, 2012a) through the use of a variety of policy instruments aimed across all sectors. Until 2015, the building sector had benefitted from a wide range of specific policy measures that targeted the specific building sector-related barriers (identified above). Table 13 provides an overview of the main identified barriers and the type of policy instrument (with examples of current/previous measures) used in the UK to overcome the barriers.

Table 13 Barriers and policy instruments in the building sector

Type of barrier	Barrier	Scale	Policy instruments and measures addressing barriers
Social, cultural & educational	Undervaluing energy efficiency	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal • <i>Dissemination and awareness/informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering implementation programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme (CRC) • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. the community energy strategy and community energy efficiency outreach programme
	Inertia/Habit	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Greening Government Commitments (GGC) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Carbon Trust Measures and the Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Feed-in Tariffs (FITs)
	Perceived lack of impact	National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EPCs and DECs • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme
	Lack of time and resources (communities and individuals)	National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland only), loans to SMEs by Carbon Trust • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Peer-to-peer community energy mentoring scheme • Barrier not addressed at individual domestic level.
	Rebound effect	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Smart Metering and Billing, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Display Energy Certificates (DECs)
	Lack of awareness	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme, Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Open Homes Network, Energy Savings Advice Service

Refurbishment seen as low priority	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation, Decent Homes Standard, Zero Carbon Homes Standard, Building Regulations • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Green Investment Bank • <i>Dissemination and awareness / Informative</i> e.g. mandatory GHG reporting scheme, Big Energy Saving Week 	
Socio-economic status of household	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Decent Homes Standard, Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Warm Front 	
Unwillingness to replace heating systems	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Boiler Replacement Scheme (Northern Ireland) 	
Lack of interest and motivation	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Community Energy Advice Programme, Energy Savings Advice Service, Open Homes Network, Market Transformation Programme • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF), Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) scheme 	
Social norms and accepted behaviours	National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. regional and community level energy efficiency schemes (Climate Challenge Fund, Low Carbon Communities Challenge, NEST) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Big Energy Saving Week 	
Inter-occupant relationships		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly; although the Community Energy Strategy recognises the need for large-scale behaviour change programmes</i> 	
Aesthetics (Retrofits and renewable technologies)	Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Technology Innovation Needs Assessment (TINA), Invest in Innovative Refurbishment • <i>Conservation and planning policies often outweigh energy efficiency technologies</i> 	
Local opposition to new energy infrastructure	National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Planning and Energy Act 2008 • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni'Fro (Wales) • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Community Energy Advice Schemes 	
Mistrust of technologies	National/ Regional/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. National products policy (tranches 1& 2), Ecodesign regulations and Directives, quality assurance labels 	

		Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES), Market Transformation Programme
Mistrust of energy companies or contractors		National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Renewable Obligation Certificate (ROC), Directives and Building Regulations • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES), Market Transformation Programme • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Green Deal training and certification for assessors/installers • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Quality Assurance labels, best practice guides
Confidence in contracting and delivery		National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Green Deal Training and Certification for Assessors/Installers • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Quality Assurance labels, Model contracts and best practice guides
Perceived lack of political action			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No policy instruments address this directly
Perceived lack of action by business and industry		National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness / informative</i> e.g. Carbon Trust Measures, Market Transformation Programme
Mistrust of green tariffs		National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Services Directive • <i>Dissemination and awareness/informative</i> e.g. Smart Meter Implementation Programme, Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Review of Energy Services Market, RIIO ED1 Price Control model for network regulation
Externalising responsibility and blame		National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Performance Certificates and Display Energy Certificates • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Community Energy Advice Programme, Act on CO2 Advice, Open Homes Network • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Climate Change Agreements/Climate Change Levy, Re:FIT National Programme
Access to trusted Information		National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Labelling Directive • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Energy Savings Advice Service, Committee on Climate Change Guidance • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. One Stop Shop, peer-to-peer mentoring

Lack of information on energy use	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme, Energy Savings Advice Service, Scottish Energy and Resource Efficiency Service (SERES), Open Homes Network 	
Understanding of costs versus perceived benefits	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering Implementation Programme, Energy Savings Advice Service, GHG reporting scheme • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Energy Technology Institute, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres 	
Visibility of energy efficiency	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EPCs and DECs, Smart Metering and Billing, EcoDesign and Labelling Directives 	
Perception that environmental benefits too small	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Big Energy Saving Week, Act on CO2 Advice 	
Lack of awareness/Information gap on technologies	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EcoDesign Directives and Regulations, EPCs and DECs • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Open Homes Network • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Energy Technologies Institute, facilities and management apprenticeship funding • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB funded innovation programmes, Low Carbon Buildings Programme 	
Lack of user experience	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Savings Advice Service, Act on CO2 Advice, Big Energy Saving Week, Open Homes Network 	
Skills and training	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Energy Technologies Institute, facilities and management apprenticeship funding, Green Deal Training and Certification for Assessors/installers • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB funded innovation programmes, Low Carbon Buildings Programme 	
Perceived information over-load	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly but measures such as the promotion of the Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust as well as the backing of a One Stop Shop for Community Energy Projects seek to address this in some way</i> 	

	Consumer confusion on green tariffs	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g Energy Savings Advice Service, Energy Saving Trust, Carbon Trust
	Marketing and information on green tariffs	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Bill Act 2011, OFGEM’s retail market review changes • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g Energy Savings Advice Service, Energy Saving Trust, Carbon Trust
Institutional	Misaligned financial incentives	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. The Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Climate Change Levy/Climate change Agreements, The CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, the Enhanced Capital Allowance scheme, the Electricity Demand Reduction project
	Construction standards	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (EPBD), EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED) , updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard
	Poor compliance with building codes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly</i>
	Performance gap	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB research funding, Energy Technology Institute
	Building stock characteristics	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. TSB research funding, Energy Technology Institute
	Quality of installation and commissioning	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. funding for facilities/management apprenticeships, funding for energy efficiency training, Green Deal Training and Certification • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Model Energy Performance Contracts and best practice guides, quality assurance labels • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, TSB and Innovate UK research programmes
	Mismatch between policy and occupant reality		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly</i>
	Disruption /Hassle factor		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly</i>

<p>Infrastructure and planning barriers (medium sized energy projects and local access to grid connections)</p>	<p>National/ Regional/ Local</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Directives, Low Carbon Transition Plan, • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Carbon Reduction Commitment Energy Efficiency Scheme, UREF & RCEF, Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES – Scotland only) • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Community First funding and community organisers training, peer-to-peer mentoring • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. License Lite, Time to Connect incentive for DNOs, Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. CHP Development Map, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)
<p>Lack of regulatory provision (incl. barriers to renewable heat)</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Energy Performance of Buildings Directive Recast EU Directives (EPBD), EU Energy Efficiency Directive 2012 (EED), Updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Planning and Energy Act 2008, Low Carbon Transition Plan, Home Energy Conservation Act, Decent Homes Standard, Energy Act 2011
<p>Lack of data</p>	<p>National/ Regional</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Energy Technology Institute (incl. Energy system modelling environment (ESME)), CHP Development Map, National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Technology Innovation Needs Assessment, TSB Future Energy Management in Buildings Programme, Invest in Innovative Refurbishment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres
<p>Multi-stakeholder issues</p>	<p>National</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Landlords Energy Saving Allowance (LESA)
<p>Quality of workmanship</p>	<p>National</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. updates to Building Regulations (2010 with 2012-2015 updates), Zero Carbon Homes, Code for Sustainable Homes, Decent Homes Standard
<p>Policy framework on refurbishments</p>	<p>National/ Regional</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Updated Building Regulations, Decent Homes Standard, Green Deal and ECO, Low Carbon Transition Plan, Greening Government Commitments (GGC), Home Energy Conservation Act, Energy Act 2011
<p>Characteristics of technology/fuel (renewable heat)</p>	<p>National</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Renewable Energy Strategy, Energy Act 2011, National Planning Framework, EcoDesign Regulations and Directives • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Low Carbon Networks Fund, Advanced Heat Storage competition
<p>Impact on residence (Microgeneration)</p>	<p>National</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, Technology Innovation Needs Assessment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, Energy Technology Institute

	Security of fuel supply (renewable heat)	National/ Regional/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Low Carbon Transition Plan, EU Directives, Renewable Energy Strategy, Energy Act 2011, Planning and Energy Act 2008 • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Carbon capture storage (CCS) commercialisation competition, Re:FIT National Programme, UREF and RCEF, Scottish District Heating Loan Fund • <i>Capacity building and networking</i> e.g. Peer-to-peer community energy mentoring scheme, community energy strategy • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. Time to Connect Incentive for DNOs, Incentive on Connections Engagement (ICE) for DNOs, best practice guides to energy performance contracting • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. CHP development map, National Heat Map and Strategy, Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU), Advanced Heat Storage Competition
	Lack of space (renewable heat)	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, Technology Innovation Needs Assessment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, Energy Technology Institute
	Electricity supply capacity (renewable heat)	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. Low Carbon Buildings Programme, Technology Innovation Needs Assessment, End Use Energy Demand Research Centres, Energy Technology Institute
Economic	Embryonic markets	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation • <i>Economic</i> e.g. the CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, Climate Change Levy/Climate change Agreements, Salix Finance Limited, the UK Green Investment Bank, Re:FIT national programme, Electricity Demand Reduction • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. publishing guidance on financing energy efficiency for the public sector • <i>R&D and BAT promotion</i> e.g. initiating an assessment of compatibility of energy efficiency investments with the public sector budgeting framework, innovation rollout mechanism, Technology Innovation Needs Assessments (TINAs), Green Business Awards
	Capital costs	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni’Fro (Wales), Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Scottish District Heating Loan Fund
	Lack of funds or access to finance	National/ Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Warm Front Scheme, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF)
	Payback	National/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO

expectations/Investment horizons	Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Government Buying Standards, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, EU ETS Carbon Price Floor, Electricity Market Reform, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition, Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Community Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) (Scotland) and Ynni’Fro (Wales), Enhanced Capital Allowances (ECA) incl. Energy Technology List, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)
Cost of new heating system	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Commercialisation Competition, Climate Challenge Fund (Scotland), Urban Community Energy Fund & Rural Community Energy Fund (UREF & RCEF), Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Scottish District Heating Loan Fund, Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF), Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Boiler Replacement Scheme (Northern Ireland)
Cost of microgeneration technology	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Green Deal and ECO • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Green Deal Finance Company, Salix Project and public sector loans, Loans to SMEs, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS), Renewable Energy Investment Fund (HEIF), Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) scheme, Home Renewables Scheme (Scotland)
Competing purchase decisions	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. <i>Greening Government Commitments (GGC)</i> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. <i>mandatory GHG reporting scheme, Market Transformation Programme, Green Economy Awards</i> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. <i>Government Buying Standards, Loans to SMEs (national and devolved governments), EU ETS Carbon Price Floor, Climate Change Agreements/Climate Change Levy</i>
Price signals/Financial Incentive	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Smart Metering and Billing, EPCs and DECs, EcoDesign regulation and directives • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Smart Metering, Energy Savings Advice Service, Big Energy Saving Week, Market Transformation Programme, Green Economy Awards • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Government Buying Standards, Loans to SMEs (national and devolved governments), EU ETS Carbon Price Floor, Climate Change Agreements/Climate Change Levy, Green Deal Finance Company, Feed-in Tariffs (FITs) and Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI), Stamp Duty Relief for Zero Carbon Homes
Additional costs/Hidden costs	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Committee on Climate Change Guidance
Risks and uncertainty	National/Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Open Homes Network, Community energy Advice Programme

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. RIIO ED1 Price Control model
	Cost of energy tariffs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness/Informative</i> e.g. Energy Saving Trust and Carbon Trust, Energy Savings Advice Service • <i>Promotion of energy services</i> e.g. RIIO ED1 Price Control model

3.2 TRANSPORT SECTOR

The UK's recent energy efficiency policy strategies have sought to overcome the four main overarching areas of barriers identified in the Energy Efficiency Strategy (DECC, 2012a) through the use of a variety of policy instruments aimed across all sectors. Table 14 provides an overview of the main identified barriers in relation to the transport sector and the type of policy instrument (with examples of current/previous measures) used in the UK to overcome them.

Table 14 Barriers and policy instruments in the transport sector

Type of barrier	Barriers	Scale	Policy instruments and measures addressing barriers
Cultural, Social, Educational	Hesitation to trust new technologies		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly</i>
	Car as a status symbol	Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Government funding to support new generation of ULEVs
	Environmental awareness	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. EU Energy Efficiency Directive, Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for cars • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants, company car tax reform
	Cycling culture is marginalised	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. The National Standard for cycle training
	Inertia		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No policy instruments address this directly</i>
	Habit and social norm of driving	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory policy</i> e.g. Eco-driving training included in national driving tests, local road transport codes • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Good driver training • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Congestion Charges
	Limited understanding of environmental impact	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel Economy labels for car
	Consumer	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Fuel

	understanding and use of fuel economy information		Economy labels for car
Institutional	Inadequate public transport across UK	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, rail electrification • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Low Emission Bus Scheme, community transport minibus, local sustainable transport fund • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. TSB's Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform
	Immature status of developing technologies	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Renewable Energy Directive • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Government's strategy for ultra-low emission vehicles (ULEVs) 'Driving the Future Today', funding for advanced biofuel research
	Unclear urban planning and traffic road regulations	National/ Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Low Carbon Emissions Zones (regional/local authority), Eco-towns: supplement to planning policy
	No standards for infrastructure investments	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Low carbon emissions ones (regional/local authority)
	Non-standardisation of connectors	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy)
	Not developed infrastructure for recharging	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy) • <i>Dissemination and awareness instruments</i> e.g. The National Charge point Registry (NCR)
	Confusion about fleet averages for CO2 emissions	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands
	Limited R&D Incentives	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. £82 million of research and development funding has now been committed to support the new generation of ULEVs and to help build the necessary skills and knowledge base here in the UK. This funding is focussed on identifying and funding emerging technologies that the UK can exploit and lead on globally. Funding for development of ultra low emissions vehicles (ULEVs) e.g. Technology Strategy Board's Low Carbon Vehicle Innovation Platform
	Range of distance	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. £82 million of

	travelled between charges		research and development funding has now been committed to support the new generation of ULEVs
	Lack of initiatives for fleets	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No policy instruments address this directly
	Extra load on the electricity grid	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-in Places (The Plug-In Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy), Smart Grid Forum
	Limited car-sharing initiatives	Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Local support from councils such as Kensington and Chelsea
	Undeveloped cycling infrastructure	National / Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Financial</i> e.g. Cycle to Work Scheme (Green Transport Plan) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Transport for London (TfL) and London Cycling Campaign (LCC) community bicycling project • <i>Planning</i> e.g. Development of London Bicycling Network since 2000, Eco-towns: supplement to planning policy
	Biofuel distribution and infrastructure	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Low Carbon HGV Technology Taskforce, Government funding for advanced biofuel research
	Concerns about sustainability of biofuels	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. UK Government funding for advanced biofuel research
	Need for R&D in biofuels and hydrogen	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP), Government funding for advanced biofuel research
	Lack of policy on freight efficiency	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regulatory</i> e.g. Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle band, EU Directives (low rolling resistance tyres, LGV emissions targets and complementary measures) • <i>Dissemination and awareness</i> e.g. Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme
Economic	High purchase price and long payback	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. The Plug-in car and van grants
	Limited business case for infrastructure investment	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Planning</i> e.g. National Infrastructure Plan, Plugged-In Places (PIP) programme
	Cost of domestic charging unit	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plugged-In Places (PIP) programme includes the domestic chargepoint grant. Under this scheme homeowners are

			able to claim up to 75% (capped at £1,000 including VAT) off the total capital costs of the chargepoint and associated installation costs
	Lack of market and policy certainty for hydrogen innovation	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. UKH2Mobility project
	Lack of research in freight efficiency	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research and Development</i> e.g. Department for Transport has initiated a number of trials to explore the real, practical benefits of energy efficiency measures for road freight. In 2012 they started a two year trial of low carbon trucks whose CO2 emissions were at least 15% lower than those emitted by equivalent diesel vehicles, to demonstrate that new fuels are feasible and practical.
	Limited financial incentives for freight efficiency	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Economic</i> e.g. Plug-in car and van grants

CHAPTER 4: KEY FINDINGS

Key findings for the UK's *building sector* are:

- Many barriers to enhanced energy efficiency in the building sector exist, which are highly complex with multiple inter-relations.
- Barriers are often specific to subsectors within the building sector (e.g. domestic/non-domestic, existing/new builds, specific technology types) but some are also relevant across all sub-sectors.
- The main barriers relevant to all subsectors are mainly social and cultural issues; emphasising the importance of policy instruments and measures that consider the socio-cultural context and key actors involved.
- In terms of the main social/cultural and educational barriers with the highest potential impact, the majority related to the undervaluing of energy efficiency and unwillingness and/or inability to undertake energy efficiency improvements, particularly through a lack of motivation (inertia), awareness, knowledge and understanding as well as habitual behaviours and the socio-economic and demographic profiles of the end-users.
- The main institutional barriers included infrastructural and planning barriers (particularly in relation to medium-sized energy projects), as well as practical and construction-related barriers such as the inherent difficulties of the UK's building stock in terms of suitable skills, standards and compliance, which subsequently results in the performance gap.
- The main economic barriers within the building sector related to prohibitive upfront/capital costs of energy efficiency measures (from national to local-scale), the lack of (or misaligned) financial incentives in terms of payback expectations and investment horizons as well as the embryonic energy efficiency market that requires substantial input in order to ensure economic growth and a self-sustaining energy efficiency market.
- The majority of the barriers have been (or are being) addressed through previous and existing policies; using a variety of policy instruments including regulatory, economic, dissemination and awareness, and research and development. Such policy instruments include measures that have been (or are being) undertaken at national, regional and local levels. However, a recent change in UK Government has seen a number of key energy efficiency policy measures, that were critical in overcoming economic, institutional, social and cultural barriers scrapped and as this report is being written, there is uncertainty in terms of the will and urgency to ensure adequate replacement policy measures are provided.

Key findings for the UK's *transport sector* are:

- Many barriers to enhanced energy efficiency exist in the transport sector. Although most are specific to subsectors, they are at a variety of levels from system efficiency to vehicle efficiency.
- The main barriers identified are a mix of social, cultural, educational, institutional and economic. However, the majority are institutional; emphasising the importance of policy instruments and measures that recognise the need for fundamental high-level changes in the implementation of the infrastructural and technical aspects of energy efficiency.
- In terms of the main social/cultural and educational barriers with the highest potential impact, the majority related to the end-user/consumer, in terms of their hesitancy in trusting new technologies, attitude and inertia. Lack of knowledge and availability of sufficient information also appeared to be significant educational barriers and highlight the need for dissemination and awareness/informative policy instruments.

- The main institutional barriers included the immature status of developing technologies and lack of necessary infrastructure to support low carbon transport (freight and passenger).
- The main economic barriers within the transport sector related to prohibitive upfront/capital costs of energy efficiency measures (from national to local-scale) and long payback as well as the fact there is a limited business case for energy efficiency infrastructure investment due to a lack of appropriate incentives for the key stakeholders and actors involved.
- The majority of the barriers have been (or are being) addressed through previous and existing policies. However, the majority of the UK's energy efficiency transport policies are based directly on EU directives and regulation, which does not necessarily address the need for behavioural and attitudinal changes in consumers and end-users. In addition, a recent change in UK Government has seen the potential shift away from energy efficiency policies, particularly in terms of system and travel efficiency (avoidance of travel and shift to more energy efficient modes) and highlighted in current UK Government policy in relation to aviation and road transport.

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